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EDITORIAL NOTE

Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) is the official Journal of the Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Journal publishes articles of diverse fields of interest in education. Papers reporting on original research and extended version of already established conference and journal articles are welcomed. Papers for publication are selected through peer review process to ensure originality, relevance and readability. ZIJE is published bi-annually in June and December.

The aim and scope of the journal is to provide an academic medium and an important reference for the advancement and dissemination of information that supports high level learning, teaching and research in the fields of education.

This edition, Volume 4, Number 5, December, 2024 is poised to present research reports in the following fields of education: Educational Foundations, Science Education, Educational Psychology, Curriculum & Instructional Technology, Guidance & Counselling, Philosophy & History of Education, Sociology of Education, Entrepreneurship Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Physical & Health Education, Religious Education, Gender Studies, Peace & Security Education among others. The articles in this volume are academic and professional discourse written by reputable scholars in their areas of specialization.

The Board remains indebted to its editorial members for the ceaseless support given towards successful publication of the Journal. In the same vein, we acknowledge quite sincerely the assistance and support of our esteemed consulting editors for ensuring the credibility of this edition. Also worthy of appreciation are the authors and their immense contributions to this publication.

Associate Professor Umar Sodangi
Editor-In-Chief/Chairman Editorial Board
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CALL FOR ARTICLES

The Editorial Board of Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) calls for scholarly articles for review and possible publication in its next edition (Volume 5, Number 1). ZIJE publishes articles that emphasize research development and application within the field of Education. All manuscripts are reviewed by the editorial review committee. Contributions must be original, not previously or simultaneously published elsewhere, and are critically reviewed before they are published. Papers, which must be written in English Language, should have good grammar and proper terminologies. Also note that prospective articles are subjected to plagiarism assessment to estimate the percentage of originality of the papers. Hence, a plagiarism threshold of $\leq 20\%$ is recommended.

Editorial Guidelines

1. Manuscripts including references, appendices, tables and diagrams should be double-spaced and single coded on A4 paper with generous margins (at least 1”/2.5cm).
2. Title should be explicit and not more than 19 words.
3. Title page should be arranged as follows: Title, author(s) full name, affiliation, full addresses, email addresses and phone numbers.
4. Abstract should be single line and not more than 250 words.
5. For conceptual papers, the body should have appropriate headings where necessary.
6. For empirical papers, it should be presented in the following order: Introduction, Objectives of the study, Research Questions and/or Hypotheses, Methodology, Results, Discussion of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.
7. Acknowledgement (if any).
8. Quotations of more than 40 words should be indented and typed single spacing with indication of the pages where the quotes were lifted.
9. In-text citations should follow the APA 7th edition format.
10. References should be in range with 7th edition of APA Style.
11. Each table and figure should be presented within the manuscripts, with a brief and self-explanatory title.
12. All text within the table should be clearly legible, and all graphics and legends should be easily distinguished when printed in black and white.
13. Tables should be in horizontal lines only, with only blank space to separate columns.
14. Tables and figures that may be included in the main text of the paper should be numbered separately, in the sequence that they are mentioned in the text.
15. Figures should be saved in a neutral data format such as JPEG, TIFF or EPS.

Submission of Manuscripts & Assessment Fee

Manuscripts should be submitted directly to the Editor-in-Chief or Publication Editor through the following e-mail address: zijefugusau@gmail.com. Articles can be submitted between the periods of January to April ending for June publication, while July to October ending for December publication. Assessment fee for manuscript is #5,000.00 only.

Professor Abubakar Sadiq Haruna

Publication Editor

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Application of Digital Technology for Sustainable Science Education delivery at Secondary School Education in Nigeria: A Qualitative Study

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Abstract

Modern teaching resources are a necessity, considering the fact that technology forms a greater basis of education in today's digitalized world. In modern education, knowledge is effectively imparted with the use of digital tools. Digitization of education provides a great avenue for developing a cognitive, resource based approach to enhance learners' skills, lifelong learning capability, and continuous education. Quantitative educational growth that has taken place in Nigeria has been quite vast, though its influence upon technological development has been minimal. With the education sector going through a number of reforms in ensuring efficiency, some challenges have persisted; hence, their solutions do not fully solve these problems, meaning there is growing advocacy for the digitization of the education system of Nigeria for promoting technological advancement. Digitalization opens up information to different possibilities in terms of dispersals, offering a kind of democratization of knowledge whereby learning is altogether more individualistic and collaborative. With the advancement of technology, today there are many tools that can make the culture of learning from being a purely academic activity to an enjoyable and enriching process. Education stands at an unprecedented threshold of innovation moving into the future, which, within a very short period, needs to race with technological advancement lest it lags behind.

Keywords: Digital Technology, Service Delivery and Science Education

Introduction

Teaching is a profession that is undergoing a radical transformation occasioned by the integration of new technologies in it. Essentially, teaching refers to the act of guiding or instructing. Teaching has conventionally been perceived as the delivery of knowledge to learners in a classroom through systematic observation of instruction. According to Greenwalt, (2016), teaching also involves the manipulation of situations to influence the learner to want to learn a skill or gain insight on their own. This will improve technology use in the classroom and lessen some of the outcomes for teachers and students. Digital education has become one of the central topics of today's world, where proximity to information and people all over the globe has made it increasingly challenging to find reliable sources among those less desirable. It certainly has influenced present trends in learning and teaching. Modern education tools are at the very core in today's digitized world. Technology has become one of the pivotal points of modern educational systems, providing opportunities to apply cognitive resource-based learning approaches where skills are developed towards lifelong learning and continuing education. Digitization allows information to be disseminated through all levels by democratizing knowledge and making education collaborative and self-directed, according to Onyia (2021). There are tools available today that can transform learning from a traditional academic task into an interactive, engaging process with technological benefits.

Indeed, digitalization is the hallmark of the 21st century, and in this respect, the education segment is also evolving rapidly with new ideas almost daily. The Central Institute for Education Technology

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adaptation requires that nobody remain in the dark about how technology progresses and is enhanced. The digital technologies are causing changes that may be found not only in the world of labor but also in educational institutions independently of the strategic efforts to provide better quality of teaching and learning (Pandy & Misra, 2014). Digital technologies have reshaped education, and systems of education in the world over had to adopt an integration approach toward Information Communication Technology. While such integration has provided various accruing benefits that come with integration, it has also raised concerns on the question of quality of teaching and learning with ICT, especially on how education systems adapt to current technological trends.

Theoretical Framework

Technology Determinism Theory (Marshall McLuhan and Veblen)

Technological determinism is a theory that posits technology as a primary driver of societal change, suggesting that technological advancements shape social structures, cultural values, and human behavior. In the context of Nigeria, the application of digital technology has been particularly pronounced, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, which accelerated the adoption of digital life across various sectors. Maikomo et al. highlight that the pandemic prompted a significant shift towards digital interactions in Nigeria, revealing both the facilitators and barriers to this transition. They argue that while the urgency of the situation led to rapid digital migration, systemic and socioeconomic factors constrained the full realization of digital potential, thereby impacting individual and national development (Maikomo et al., 2021).

The role of digital technology in shaping educational practices in Nigeria further exemplifies technological determinism. The increasing reliance on digital platforms for learning has necessitated a reevaluation of educational policies and practices. Research indicates that while the integration of digital technologies in educational settings has the potential to enhance learning outcomes, it also raises questions about the adequacy of digital competencies among educators and students (Olofsson et al., 2019). This reflects the notion that the availability and implementation of technology can dictate the effectiveness of educational reforms, aligning with the principles of technological determinism.

Moreover, the influence of digital technology on economic practices in Nigeria underscores the deterministic view of technology. The adoption of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Nigerian ports, as discussed by Onwuegbuchunam et al., illustrates how technology can transform operational efficiencies and competitiveness in traditional industries. However, the study also notes that the integration of ICT is hindered by various challenges, including infrastructural deficits and resistance to change, which highlights the complex interplay between technology and societal readiness (Onwuegbuchunam et al., 2021). This scenario reinforces the idea that while technology can drive change, its impact is contingent upon existing social structures and conditions.

In the realm of entrepreneurship, digital technologies have been identified as democratizing forces that lower barriers to market entry, particularly for female-led small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. The research by Pergelova et al. emphasizes that digital infrastructures enable broader participation in the economy, suggesting that technological advancements can reshape economic landscapes and empower marginalized groups (Pergelova et al., 2018). This aligns with the technological determinism perspective, where the evolution of technology is seen as a catalyst for social change.

In conclusion, the theory of technological determinism is vividly illustrated through the application of digital technology in Nigeria. The pandemic-induced shift towards digital life, the transformation of

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educational practices, the modernization of economic operations, and the democratization of entrepreneurship all exemplify how technology can dictate social change. However, it is crucial to recognize that the effectiveness of these technological advancements is often mediated by existing social, economic, and infrastructural contexts, which can either facilitate or hinder their impact.

Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the factors that influence the acceptance and use of technology. This model identifies four key constructs: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions, which collectively determine users' behavioral intentions towards technology adoption. In Nigeria, the application of UTAUT has been particularly relevant in various sectors, including education, e-commerce, and healthcare.

In the educational context, the UTAUT model has been employed to analyze the acceptance of digital learning tools among Open Distance Learning (ODL) students in Nigeria. Itasanmi's study highlights that performance expectancy and social influence significantly impact students' intentions to use digital tools for learning. The research utilized a quantitative approach, collecting data from 522 ODL students, and found that these constructs were crucial in understanding the behavioral intentions of students towards adopting digital resources (Itasanmi, 2022). This aligns with the findings of Abbad, who noted that the UTAUT model effectively captures the determinants influencing students' usage of e-learning systems in developing countries, emphasizing the importance of contextual factors in technology acceptance (Abbad, 2021).

Moreover, the UTAUT framework has been applied to assess the acceptance of e-commerce platforms in Nigeria. Riantini and Vional's work illustrates how the UTAUT model can be integrated with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to evaluate users' acceptance of online-to-offline e-commerce systems. Their findings indicate that performance expectancy and facilitating conditions play significant roles in users' intentions to engage with e-commerce technologies (Riantini & Vional, 2018). This is particularly relevant in Nigeria, where the growth of digital commerce is influenced by both technological advancements and socio-economic factors.

In the healthcare sector, the UTAUT model has been utilized to evaluate the acceptance of telehealth services among patients. Békés et al. developed a patient version of the UTAUT model to assess attitudes towards telepsychotherapy, identifying that perceived usefulness and social influence were critical in determining patients' intentions to use such services (Békés et al., 2022). This reflects the broader applicability of UTAUT in understanding technology acceptance in various contexts, including the Nigerian healthcare landscape, where digital health interventions are becoming increasingly important. Furthermore, the relevance of UTAUT in Nigeria is underscored by its application in assessing the acceptance of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in tertiary institutions. Aguboshim et al. argue that despite the potential of ICT to enhance research and innovation, poor policies and infrastructural challenges hinder effective adoption. Their study employs UTAUT as a conceptual framework to analyze these barriers and propose solutions for improving ICT acceptance in Nigerian universities (Aguboshim et al., 2021). This highlights the model's utility in identifying not only the factors that promote technology acceptance but also the challenges that need to be addressed.

In conclusion, the UTAUT model serves as a vital tool for understanding the dynamics of technology acceptance in Nigeria across various sectors. Its application in education, e-commerce,

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healthcare, and ICT illustrates the model's versatility and relevance in addressing the unique challenges and opportunities presented by digital technologies in the Nigerian context. By focusing on the key constructs of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions, stakeholders can better design and implement technologies that meet the needs of users in Nigeria.

Application of Digital Technology in Science Education Delivery in Nigeria

It includes but is not limited to all forms of digital tools, systems, and services, including software, hardware, data, and networks. This relates to all parts owned, leased, or licensed by any organization and provided for students, employees, or volunteers for access. Examples are computers, data servers, networks, cell phones, modems, email systems, the Internet, and other related technologies. Basically, digital technology employs a range of computer-based tools and technologies for dissimilar reasons in life, including education, the economy, as well as daily life. In education, it acts as a driver to educational innovation by revitalizing conventional learning methodologies. According to Joel and Min (2020), digital technology acts as an essential component of technological development impacting behavioral and economic patterns through change in current rules and systems. It can also be an agent of institutional change and catalyst as new structures and practices are introduced in a number of sectors. Digital technologies include tools, systems, and devices that can create, store or even process data. Examples include but are not limited to personal computers, tablets, cameras, calculators, and digital toys. Systems on the other hand are software, apps, augmented and virtual reality while intangible forms include the internet (Johnstone et al., 2018).

Application of Digital Technology through Information Delivery at Secondary School Level of Education

The modern digital environment is replete with affordances towards the dual objective of information delivery and user interaction. In a normal multimedia display, the user is presented with text, pictures and diagrams, sound, spoken messages, and input channels to enter data—all presenting varied learning opportunities. According to Norman, 2013, the critical dimensions of digital technology in information delivery are as under:

Interactivity: Digital technologies are interactive. For instance, in serious games, learners are placed into virtual environments with the possibility to interact with others through roles and actions. Old media, such as books, audiotapes, and films, are passive and non-interactive; they do not change based on users' input.

Adaptivity: Some of the digital tools adapt the information presented according to the behavior, knowledge or character of the learner. So, a game could provide options; however, in real sense it may not adapt to what the user decides. On the other hand, an intelligent adaptive learning program assesses and reacts to every action of a learner that is related to the task at hand, such as correct or wrong answers or decision-making trends.

Feedback: Digital technologies offer feedback on learners' performance that ranges from simple acknowledgments of correctness to detailed explanations of how to improve. The feedback can be immediate, as in a message that appears upon performing some action, or it might be long-term, as in progress reports over a full semester.

Choice: Many of the available digital tools afford learners the opportunity to self-regulate their learning by offering choices as to what to learn and how to learn it. Whereas some of the technologies constrain

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learners into very tightly defined structures of exploration, others, such as the Internet afford massively greater freedom for students to explore answers to their own questions.

Non-linear access: Digital technologies enable learners to approach information in a non sequential order. This, in turn, makes it possible to develop individual learning pathways. Whereas traditional linear modes rely on engaging all students in the same order, adaptive technologies reorganize that order of content based on trailers.

Linked depictions: The technologies create links among the diversity of the depictions concerning something in different media-text, audio, video, and also interactive simulations. Such links among diverse viewpoints permit cognitive flexibility and enhance learning.

Open learners' input: Learners are able to let others know about what they understand by natural language, drawing, or any other creative input is a way in which one can create something or be visibly engaged in learning.

Communication with others: Digital technologies provide a means for the communication between the learner and others, that is, other learners or experts in the subject domain, to be text-based. This is with email, chat, and discussion forums as well as interactions able with multimedia. This could also be extended with regard to collaborative learning, conversation agents, tutors, or even crowd sourcing.

Application of Digital Technology at Secondary level of Education in the Classroom

Digital learning would provide students with more access to knowledge, and the content could be tailored to meet the needs of each individual student. Using online technologies in a classroom could make a big difference in how much students perceive and retain from their lessons. Herold, 2016 End

Virtual Textbooks: These are digital learning tools with a whole lot of information in an interactive and easy-to-use format. In any case, school administrators have to make sure students have access to digital tools for using these resources at home.

Classroom Technology Tools: Technology can make learning both virtual and on-site much more effective. Flip Grid, Zoom, WhatsApp, and Skype are platforms through which student and parent engagement can be increased.

Flip Grid: An effective video-based discussion tool for any age group. It works similar to a normal discussion forum, the only difference being that it uses video instead of text. Instructors post video topics related to the lesson, and students respond by recording a video and posting their own. Flip Grid has increased accessibility and engagement of discussions compared to text-based discussions. It is also easy and has a free version available for teachers and instructors.

Zoom: Better known for video conferencing, this platform has been used a lot in these pandemic times for classes and meetings. With Zoom, the teacher can creatively invite virtual guest speakers or hold online parent-teacher conferences that will increase parental involvement.

WhatsApp: The social media site assists in interacting between students and teachers both inside and outside of school. Students are able to connect with their peers or individually with the teachers over academic matters.

Skype: Students can participate in an individual or group conversation using voice or video calls through Skype. They are also allowed to send instant messages and files to teachers, which will make the communication easy and more interactive inside and outside the classroom.

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Benefits of Digital Technology in Science Education Delivery in Science Delivery at Secondary School level of Education

Advantages of Digital Learning to Students and Educational Institutions: The advantages of digital learning to students and educational institutions are pegged on a variety of key reasons. The key benefits of digital technology in education, as noted by Hannah (2023), are:

Constant Availability of Materials: Digital learning means that one can get access to learning materials from anywhere and at any time. This flexibility in studying at any time gives students better time management of their study schedules and also allows interaction and sharing of ideas with a global community of students.

Collaborative: Technology integration into education brings both video conferencing, sharing of documents, and group work. This will help the students in their preparation for professional teamwork environments, too.

Access to More Resources: In a digital environment, the students will have access to additional resources that include lecture recordings and extra reading. In such a way, the student will go over areas of difficulty and additional information on his own and at his own pace, reinforcing learning.

Better Engagement: The insights into engagement availed by digital tools give a bird's eye view of whether the students are, in fact, engaged. This will help instructors find out if a student is struggling or disengaged and, therefore, intervene right on time for an improved learning experience.

Personalized learning: This is yet another great advantage of using digital technology in education. Digital technology helps educators in making learning personalized by adjusting the methodology of teaching to the preference and style of learning in which an individual student is most receptive; hence, improving the effectiveness of the learning process for that student.

Encourages New Learning Methods: Digital tools provide a completely different learning methodology, such as microlearning and gamification. These emerging methods are considered to be amongst one of the most effective teaching techniques. These techniques turn out to be even more influential when amalgamated with digital technology.

Workforce Preparation: Technology keeps on changing; students should go with the tide. Digital learning in schools can prepare them for their future career by introducing them to the tools and techniques that will be expected from them.

Building peer networks: Digital technologies enable the student to connect and collaborate with their peers. Such connections can be built in the class, but also from a distance, to develop a community of feelings for peer learning and teacher-student connections.

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Encourages Accountability: Digital learning places the student at the center. Students take accountability in their progress, with a sense of control over what and how they study, though guided and counseled by institutions.

Student Performance Tracking: Most of the digital tools and content support tracking of student performance in the form of test scores, assessment, and attendance at a granular level. This helps instructors identify trends that indicate areas where teaching and learning need to be improved.

Advantages of Digital Technology for sustainable Science Education Service Delivery in Nigeria

In the words of Ding, (2000), Oniya (2021), some of the key benefits of digitization of education include: **Increased access** whereby conventionally students and teachers had to be present in the same physical location for learning to take place. However, of late, with the induction of technology into education, it is possible to have instantaneous and convenient communication across great distances with just the click of a button. It has affected education to the extent that online degrees are possible. Traditional schools established in Nigeria have started offering some of their courses online, while other schools sprout up that operate wholly online, with students and teachers never once meeting face-to-face. The same technology has enabled cyber-schooling for kids in primary and secondary school to do their work in the comfort of their homes.

Increased Flexibility: Closely related to improved accessibility, the notion of flexibility via the internet leads again to a less rigid timetable. Traditional school settings bind students to visiting school at certain times. Sometimes this is impossible because of work or family obligations. Through an online class setting, course materials are made available and the student has the prerogative to study and complete class work whenever it fits into their schedule.

Introduction of Online Testing: With online education comes its share of online testing, quite useful for a whole host of reasons. Foremost amongst these reasons is the fact that online testing is impartial and quite fair. If a machine is grading your test and automatically correcting the wrong answers, it's impossible to show any signs of bias. Also, online testing might turn out to be an excellent solution for those suffering from test anxiety and getting distressed with taking tests in a room with a group of other people. Finally, all that is much better with those busy schedules who may find it tough at times to come to a testing center at a certain time.

Increased Ability to Address Special Needs: Academic life, in days of yore, was defined by very rigid classrooms. Each student went through the same life irrespective of differing needs or differing abilities. While such a setting pleased some students and could function well within the same, some students did not have their needs addressed.

It improves the capacity of a school in catering to the needs of different types of students. Children with hearing, speech, or vision impairments, and children mostly bound to a house, receive quality education on par with all other kids. One can also cater to the needs of students who have intellectual disabilities, social disabilities, or developmental disabilities through advanced technologies. Be that as it may, in spite of the differential needs of any given student, technology changes education for the better by improving our capacity to devise learning environments that work for all.

On-line Learning Content Availability: Earlier, learning was confined to the four walls of the classroom. Educationally helpful tools were essentially books or officially prepared videos. Another way in which the Internet has affected education is that anyone today can share their knowledge with the world through

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an educational blog post, e-book, or YouTube video. This, in turn, means far-reaching benefits for anyone learning anything.

Adaptability and Personalization: Learning spaces are increasingly aware that what helps a particular student learn may be virtually useless to another, and what makes no sense to one may be the only thing that fits into another. Everyone's brains work in a different way, and everyone has a different style of learning, yet everyone used the same textbook for years on end. It allows the integration of technology in education to promote leveraging, whereby a multi-tool approach can be accommodated and students can have different learning technologies right at their fingertips.

It improves concentration and assimilation: Activities carried out through digital and interactive tools raise students' concentration, and therefore they will absorb the concepts faster, improving learning. This kind of tool involves students in more practical learning with the objective of consolidating what was learned.

It favors critical thinking: The different sources of information that technologies provide introduce different opinions to the students. In this way, the information and communication technologies favor debates and acceptance of people's opinions. Besides, it allows them to get to know other cultures by exchanging ideas.

More class productivity, more teamwork: New classroom technologies, especially those allowing access to online content, improve learning productivity as they optimize instruction time; thanks to connectivity, they support teamwork due to new teaching formulae.

It motivates: The use of technologies in the classroom increases the motivation of young people; it is a fast and efficient methodology that develops the study of new knowledge. Digital tools represent the everyday communicative support of new generations, hence they are safely managed in this context.

It includes new learning methodologies: Another of the benefits of ICT in education is that teaching professionals can include new teaching methodologies, hence improving academic outcomes and encouraging dinamismo in the classroom. The use of such information technologies implies developing digital competencies with a view to avoiding digital divide.

Challenges of Using Digital Technology in Science Education Service Delivery at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

Technologies are not faultless; just as they bring many benefits to education, they have some disadvantages that have to be taken into consideration. Challenges include;

Inadequate Funding: Most learning institutions have been suffering from inadequate funding and resource allocation to education; most governments have not been able to provide enough funds to buy and maintain modern and current equipment to date.

Erratic Power Supply: Computerization and digitization can hardly take effect in an environment of epileptic power supply -Oniya, 2021. The issue of power has grown to be a national calamity. Hence, all the institutions in Nigeria depend only on a generator for power supply, and most often there is no light because there is either no diesel or generator breakdown, and this often hinders the process.

Poor Internet Connectivity: Internet connectivity is also one of the major challenges facing many educational institutions across Nigeria. It is obviously going to be very difficult to implement computer-based lessons and utilize various online resources in cases where there is a high level of power outages or

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limited internet access within a particular area, as confirmed by Mtebe & Raphael (2018). Lack or absence of internet connectivity will ensure that teachers and students are barred from accessing multiple online educational resources, software tools, and collaborative platforms that are so essential for their eventual success in computer studies education.

Lack of Modern Infrastructure: The state of infrastructural facilities in most Nigerian academic institutions is in disrepair. Yaya and Adeeko (2016) pointed out that ICT departments of these institutions are without modern computer systems; even the few available systems get infected with a virus which renders them not fit for digitization work.

Lack of Skilled Staff: Most academic staff are lacking even in basic computer training, let alone specialized training that may be required for digitization. Academic staff capacity in respect of equipment maintenance and software management needs continuous building.

Digital Distractions and Technical Overload: Living in a digital era, every student has to face distractions emanating from different digital tools and platforms that come their way (Rosen, 2012). The pervasive use of smart phones, social media, and online entertainment distracts students from attending to their tasks and assignments and hence decreased productivity and engagement.

Unsatisfactory Digital Literacy Skills: Even though children and students have lived in a world that is already saturated with technologies, most of them do not acquire adequate digital skills, which computer studies education demands (Fraillon, 2014).

Over Influence: Improper and excessive practice will bind students to an obsessive mentality with computer technology; this can cause them to fail to control consumption, hence affecting the student's health, social life, family life, and further deterring their academic performance.

It Limits the Development of Other Skills: Widespread use of digitalization in educational sectors can nullify some practices such as writing, public speaking, and reasoning. Proof of this aspect is shown by a recent study led by the University of California: "The report says that social skills among new generations will be based on this digital environment, hence affecting personal communication directly.

Personal Data Theft: In case of minor children, pupils might, out of ignorance about the potential risks of cybercrime, involuntarily give away their data by posting pictures with unknown people.

It Reduces Human Interaction: Through the use of newer technologies, the process of learning is being kept further and the human contact with the teachers and classmates reduces. Due to this, there can be possible isolation after the reduction of human contact, which will work as an obstacle toward the personal development of students.

It amplifies bullying: It is a sensitive topic and one of the main perils associated with it. The absence of physical interaction can grow into loss of confidence, and abuse of online tools and platforms can create incidents of digital bullying.

Conclusion

The role of digital technologies in upgrading the delivery of services in education, particularly in science, cannot be underestimated. Digitalization did not make the brick-and-mortar classroom less important; it actually complemented the traditional concept. That is, a combination of both approaches yields a complete educational experience. It is only then that 21st-century education realizes its full potential: face-to-face instruction in combination with flexibility and access, realized by digital learning tools. This makes for dynamic learning environments that guarantee better engagement and deeper comprehension, leading to meaningful changes in schools.

Recommendation

Based on the conclusion, this study therefore recommends that;

1. Schools should make use of digital technologies while teaching or facilitating learning.
2. The government and all other stakeholders in education should ensure that digital technologies are sufficiently provided to schools.
3. Teachers need training on the effective use of digital technologies during instructions.
4. Investment in the improvement of school infrastructure must be done by the educational stakeholders.
5. More computer experts with professional skills should be hired by the government.
6. Access to the internet should be ensured for seamless connectivity.

References

- Abbad, M. (2021). Using the model to understand students' usage of e-learning systems in developing countries. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(6), 7205-7224 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10573-5>
- Adedeji, A. A., & Olowo, O. O. (2018). Information and communication technology (ICT) literacy and employability skills among library and information science graduates in Nigeria *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-LIS)*, 1(2), 142-152.
- Aguboshim, F., Obiokafor, I., & Onwuka, U. (2021). Sustainable ICT: an essential enabler of sustainable research and innovations in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 10(1), 125-131. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2021.10.1.0139>
- Bates, A. W. (2015). Teaching in a digital age: Guidelines for designing teaching and learning. Open Educational Resources Collection. 6. Retrieved 30 June 2022 from: <https://irl.umsl.edu/oer/6>
- Békés, V., Doorn, K., & Bóthe, B. (2022). Assessing patients' attitudes towards tele psychotherapy: the development of the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology-patient version. *Clinical Psychology & Psychotherapy*, 29(6), 1918-1927. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpp.2760>
- Frailon, J. (2014): School Environments for Teaching and Learning Computer and Information Literacy. In preparing for Life in a Digital Age 2(2), 167-193. Cham: Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-14222-7-7>
- Greenwalt, K. A. (2016). Dewey on Teaching and Teacher Education. In: Peters, M. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Educational Philosophy and Theory*. Springer, Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-287-532-7-48-1>
- Hannah, W. (2022). The top 10 benefits of digital learning. Retrieved May 20 2024 from <https://elearningindustry.com>.

Application of Digital Technology ... (Olajide, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019918>

- Herold, B.(2016). Technology in education. An overview. Education Week. Retrieved May 20, 2024 from [https:// WWW.edweek.org/technology/ technology-in- education-an-overview/2016/02](https://WWW.edweek.org/technology/technology-in-education-an-overview/2016/02).
- Itasanmi, S. (2022). Determinants of the behavioural intention of open distance learning students to use digital tools and resources for learning in Nigeria. *Journal of Adult and Continuing Education*, 29(1), 124-146. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14779714221135655>
- Jagboro, K.O., Omotayo, B.O.,&Aboyade, W. A.(2012). Digitization of library collection in developing countries: the Hezekiah Oluwasanmi LibraryExperience. *Library Philosophy and Practice: 1-11*
- Johnstone, K., Hadley, F., & Highfield, K. (2018). Supporting young children as digital citizens: The importance of shared understandings of technology to support integration of play-basedlearning. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 49(5), 896-910. Doi: 10.1111/bjet.12664
- Joel, T. S., & Min, T. (2020).Digitalization in education: challenges, trends and transformative potential Führen and Manager in the digital Transformation: Trends, Best Practices under Herausforderun gen, 287-312.
- Maikomo, J., Targema, T., & Obun-Andy, M. (2021). Covid-19 and the new normal in developing societies: an appraisal of Nigerians’ adaptation to digital life in public and private spheres. *Journal of Developing Societies*, 37(3), 246-274. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0169796x21996830>
- Mtebe, J.S., & Raphael, C. (2018). Key factors in learners’ satisfaction with the E-learning System at the university of Dares Salaam, Tanzania. *Australasian Journal of Educational Techology*, 34(4), 107-122.
- Norman, D. (2013). The design of everyday things revised and expanded edition. 28-35
- Olofsson, A., Fransson, G., & Lindberg, J. (2019). A study of the use of digital technology and its conditions with a view to understanding what ‘adequate digital competence’ may mean in a national policy initiative. *Educational Studies*, 46(6), 727-743. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2019.1651694>
- Onwuegbuchunam D., Aponjolosun M., & Ogunsakin, A. (2021). Information & communication technology(ict) adoption in nigerian ports terminal operations. *Journal of Transportation Technologies*, 11(03), 311-324. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jtts.2021.113020>
- Oniya, M.N. (2021). Digitization of education in Nigeria: A Path to Technological Advancement. Association for Digital Education and Communications Technology Conference Proceedings.
- Pandy, P.,& Misra, R.(2014). Digitization of library materials in academic libraries: issues and challenges. *Journal of industrial and intelligent information* 2(2): 136-141. Retrieved from <http://www.jiii.org/uploadfile/2014/0113/20140113034520805>.
- Pergelova, A., Manolova, T., Simeonova-Ganeva, R., & Yordanova, D. (2018). Democratizing entrepreneurship? digital technologies and the internationalization of female-led. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 57(1), 14-39. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsbm.12494>
- Riantini, R. (2018). Adoption of e-commerce online to offline with technology acceptance model (tam) approach.. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iccoins.2018.8510613>
- Rosen, M. A. (2012). Intertwining Digital Content and One-to-One Laptop Learning Environment. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education* 44(3), 225-241.
- Yaya and Adeeko (2016), Globalization and ICT in Academic Libraries in Nigeria: The Way Forward. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.

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Assessment of Availability and Utilization of Hands-On Activities in Stem Education among Lower Basic Teachers in Ilorin Metropolis, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was carried out in order to explore the availability and teachers' utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education among lower basic pupils Ilorin metropolis. The research design adopted for this study was descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consists of all the lower basic teachers in Ilorin, Kwara State while a sample of 300 teachers was selected for the study using simple random sampling technique. A self-constructed questionnaire titled: "Questionnaire on Availability and Teachers' Utilization of Hands-on Activities in STEM Education (QATUHASTEME)" was used for data collection. The instrument was content validated by two experts while Cronbach Alpha reliability estimate yielded 0.83. The data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation to provide answer to the research questions. The findings of the study revealed that hands-on activities in STEM education are available and moderately utilized by the teachers in teaching lower basic pupils in Ilorin Metropolis. It was concluded that these hands-on activities are good for learning STEM education concepts when they are available and highly utilized by the teachers. It was recommended among others that frequent supervision and monitoring should be encouraged in order to ensure that hand-on activities are made available and that teachers appropriately utilize hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools.

Keywords: Hand-on activities, STEM education, Lower basic education, Teachers' utilization

Introduction

Learning through hands-on activities is very effective and influential for both feeling and emotion of students. Hands-on activities are educational or learning experiences that involve actively engaging with physical objects, materials, or processes. These activities are designed to encourage active participation and experiential learning, where learners can explore concepts through their own senses and actions, rather than just reading or hearing about them. Hands-on activities are often considered to be a more effective form of learning compared to traditional methods because they engage learners in a more active and immersive experience. By doing hands-on activities, learners can manipulate objects, observe cause-and-effect relationships, and engage in trial-and-error processes that help them develop a deeper understanding of the concepts they are learning.

Consequently, hands-on activities are particularly useful for learners who may struggle with traditional learning methods, such as those with learning disabilities or who are visual or kinesthetic learners (Ahmad, Hui & Ahmad, 2019). These activities can also be used to cater to different learning styles, helping learners retain information and develop critical thinking skills. Hands-on activities can be designed for any subject or topic, and they can range from simple activities like creating a collage to complex experiments like building a functioning robot. They can also be used to promote cross-curricular learning by integrating multiple subjects into one activity. For example, an activity that involves designing and building a bridge could involve concepts from science, math, and engineering (Tumay & Cakmakci, 2019). Examples of hands-on activities include experiments, art projects, building and construction tasks, outdoor games and sports, cooking, and scientific investigations. These activities are often used in educational settings, such as schools or museums, to promote critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, and teamwork.

The concept of hands-on activities is rooted in the philosophy of constructivism, which argues that students construct their own understanding of the world through experiences, interactions, and reflection (Dunn & Mulvenon, 2009). Therefore, hands-on activities are designed to create a more authentic learning environment where students can explore, experiment, and reflect on their own learning. Hands-on activities can provide numerous benefits for learners of all ages and skill levels. They can be a fun, engaging, and effective way to learn new concepts and skills, and can help participants to develop a range of valuable cognitive, social, and practical skills that are applicable in a variety of settings.

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According to McNair (2018), there are many different types of hands-on activities that can be used in different subject areas. In science classes, hands-on activities might involve conducting experiments, making observations, or building models. In mathematics classes, hands-on activities might involve using manipulatives, creating graphs, or designing experiments to test mathematical concepts. In language arts classes, hands-on activities might involve creating and performing skits or plays, or writing and illustrating their own stories. In social studies classes, hands-on activities might involve conducting historical reenactments, creating maps or timelines, or building models of historical structures or monuments. Johnson and Oludipe (2019) pointed out that hands-on activities are a powerful tool for promoting active learning, engagement, and creativity. They can be used in a variety of educational settings, from classrooms to informal learning environments like museums or community centers.

These activities provide students with the opportunity to engage with the subject matter in a more tangible and interactive way, allowing them to better understand and retain the information presented to them. Research such as Jones and Jones (2017), Alspaugh and Hartman (2015) and Demir, Kocakoyun and Aydin (2020) have shown that hands-on learning activities can significantly improve students' engagement and retention of STEM concepts. When students are actively involved in the learning process, they are more likely to remember what they have learned and to develop a deeper understanding of the material (Gega, 2018).

Hands-on activities are an essential part of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education among lower basic pupils. The core components of STEM education are science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. Science refers to the study of the natural world and its phenomena, including physical, chemical, and biological processes. Technology involves the application of scientific knowledge to design and develop tools, machines, and systems that solve practical problems. Engineering involves the design, development, and optimization of systems, structures, and processes that solve real-world problems. Mathematics is the language of science and engineering, and is used to model, analyze, and solve problems in these fields.

STEM education is an interdisciplinary approach to teaching and learning that integrates science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. It emphasizes an interdisciplinary approach to learning, where pupils are taught to see the connections and relationships between different subjects, and how they apply to real-world situations. Its purpose is to prepare students with the skills and knowledge needed to excel in the 21st-century workforce, where jobs are increasingly centered around these subjects. Early exposure to STEM subjects is crucial for all children, regardless of their backgrounds. These subjects help to develop important problem-solving, critical thinking, and analytical skills, which are essential for success in both academic and professional life. (Biancarosa & Griffiths, 2012). By focusing on these subjects, STEM education fosters creativity and curiosity in pupils.

In Nigeria, lower basic schools refer to the first three years of primary education, which is also referred to as primary 1 to primary 3. The Nigerian educational system is divided into six years of primary education, three years of junior secondary education, three years of senior secondary education, and four years of tertiary education. During the lower basic school years in the country, children typically start their primary education at the age of six and continue through to the age of eight. The curriculum at this level focuses on developing foundational skills in reading, writing, and arithmetic, as well as basic knowledge in other subjects such as science, social studies, and basic computer studies. The Nigerian lower basic schools also aim to instill moral and cultural values in children, as well as promoting social interaction and physical development through extracurricular activities such as sports, music, and drama.

Lunn, McIntosh and Mioduser (2020) pointed out that hands-on activities in STEM education have numerous benefits for lower basic pupils. Hands-on activities often involve real-world applications of skills and concepts, which help lower basic pupils to see the relevance and importance of what they are learning. They can appeal to different learning styles of pupils by providing opportunities for them to learn in ways that are more comfortable to them and that allow them to engage with the material in different ways. By incorporating hands-on activities into STEM education for lower basic pupils, teachers can make learning more engaging and effective, helping pupils to develop a love of learning and a deeper understanding of the world around them. Teachers can also increase learning through activities that make learning effective. These activities allow pupils to actively participate in the learning process, making learning more fun and memorable.

The availability and utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education can vary depending on a variety of factors such as the resources available to schools, the training of teachers in incorporating hands-on activities into their lessons, and the curriculum requirements set by educational authorities. In some schools, there may be a lack of funding or resources to purchase materials needed for hands-on activities. In these cases, teachers may have to rely on less expensive materials or find alternative ways to engage pupils in hands-on learning, such as using virtual simulations or online resources. Teachers play a

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critical role in promoting STEM education among lower basic pupils. They need to be trained to incorporate STEM concepts into their teaching practices and to use instructional strategies that are effective in engaging children in STEM learning. (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2018).

However, the availability of hands-on activities in STEM education has been found to be limited, especially in lower basic schools. A study conducted by Johnson and Oludipe (2019) revealed that the availability of hands-on activities in primary schools was inadequate due to various factors such as lack of funding, limited access to materials, and lack of teacher training. Similarly, a study by Lee and Kim (2019) in South Korea found that the availability of hands-on activities in elementary schools was limited due to insufficient resources, lack of teacher training, and insufficient time. One of the gap that exist between the strengths and weaknesses of the availability and utilization of hands on activities in STEM education revolves around resources. While hands-on activities have the strength of engaging pupils and making learning tangible, the availability of materials, equipment, and resources can be a weakness. This means that some schools may lack the necessary materials and resources to support hands-on learning experiences, limiting the implementation and variety of activities.

Statement of the Research Problem

Hands on activities in STEM education among lower basic schools is often given little consideration compared to traditional instruction method. One major reasons are the lack of resources and infrastructure to support hands-on activities in STEM education (Anubi, 2023). Many schools in Nigeria lack basic resources such as laboratory equipment, computers, and internet connectivity, which makes it difficult for teachers to incorporate hands-on activities in their teaching. Another factor is the lack of training and professional development opportunities for teachers in STEM education (Ekueme, Okon & Ezenwa, 2015). Many teachers in Nigeria are not adequately trained in STEM subjects and are not familiar with hands-on teaching methods, which makes it difficult for them to incorporate such activities into their lessons. There is a concern about the availability and utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education for lower basic pupils. Despite the benefits of hands-on activities in promoting student engagement and understanding of STEM concepts, it is unclear whether schools have the necessary resources and support to implement such activities effectively. Additionally, it is unclear whether teachers have the training and knowledge necessary to utilize hands-on activities in their instruction. However, implementing hands-on activities in the classroom can be challenging, especially for lower basic pupils especially where the schools lack the necessary resources, such as materials and equipment, to conduct such activities and where teachers may not have the required training or needed knowledge to effectively incorporate hands-on activities into their instruction. Hence, this study examines the availability of hands-on activities and teachers' utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education among lower basic pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to assess the availability of resources and materials required for hands-on activities, as well as the extent to which teachers use these activities in their instruction.

The specific objective of the study was to:

- i. find out the availability of hands-on activities in STEM education among lower basic school teachers.
- ii. determine the extent of teachers' utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools.
- iii. find out teachers' perceived challenges in the utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions were generated and guided the study:

- i. How available are hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools in Ilorin Metropolis?
- ii. To what extent do teachers utilize hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools in Ilorin Metropolis?
- iii. What are the challenges faced in the utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools?

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive survey design. Survey research design is a method used to collect information from sample of respondents in order to describe the characteristics of the respondents as it relates to variables under study. The study utilized questionnaire to collect information about availability and teachers' utilization of hand-on-activities in STEM education among lower basic pupils. The population of the study consists of all lower basic school teachers in Ilorin, Kwara State. Using multistage sampling technique, a sample of thirty public primary schools were randomly

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selected across the three local government in Ilorin metropolis at first stage, while at second stage, ten teachers were selected from each of the thirty public primary schools using simple random sampling technique. A total sample size of 300 lower basic school teachers was selected for the study. A self-constructed questionnaire titled: “Questionnaire on Availability and Teachers’ Utilization of Hands-on Activities in STEM Education (QATUHASTEME)” was used for data collection from the respondents. The instrument was a close-ended structured questionnaire. It was developed in line with four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA) Agreed (A) Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) in relation to the three research questions raised for the study. The questionnaire consists of two sections; section A contains personal data information of the respondents, while section B is made up of 30 items which were arranged into three parts. The first part contains items on availability of hand-on activities, second part had items on teachers’ utilization of hand-on activities in STEM education while the third part contain items on challenges in the use of hand-on activities in STEM education. The instrument was content validated by two experts in the area of Sciences Education and Educational Testing while Cronbach Alpha reliability method was used to establish the reliability index which yielded a value of 0.83. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to provide answer to the research questions.

Presentation of Results

Three research questions were generated and were answered with the use of mean and standard deviation. The results were presented below.

Research Question 1: How available are hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools in Ilorin Metropolis? In order to ascertain the availability of hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools in Ilorin Metropolis, mean response of the teachers to each item on availability of hand-on activities in the questionnaire were analysed, having four Likert scale format of Strongly Agreed (4 points), Agreed (3 points), Disagreed (2 points), and Strongly Disagreed (1 point). In other to have the bench mark, the average of the total point was calculated to be 2.5 (i.e. $4+3+2+1 = 10$: $10/4 = 2.5$). Therefore, any item with mean value above 2.5 stands for available and item with mean value below 2.5 means unavailable. The result is presented in table 1.

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Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation showing the Availability of Hands-on Activities in STEM Education among Lower Basic School Teachers

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Hands-on activities are readily available for STEM education among lower basic pupils.	2.56	1.06	Agreed
2.	Hands-on activities in STEM education among lower basic pupils are incorporated to a great extent	2.55	1.11	Agreed
3.	Hands-on activities are effectively used by the teachers in enhancing the understanding of STEM concepts among lower basic pupils	2.98	1.09	Agreed
4.	School administration provides supports and resources for teachers to facilitate hands-on activities in STEM education among lower basic pupils	2.99	1.13	Agreed
5.	Teachers have the ability to confidently design and implement hands-on activities that align with STEM curriculum for lower basic pupils	2.88	1.04	Agreed
6.	Schools have access to the necessary materials and tools for conducting hands-on STEM activities.	2.81	1.17	Agreed
7.	There are adequate space in classrooms for students to engage in hands-on STEM activities, such as building models, conducting experiments, or working on projects.	2.87	1.24	Agreed
8.	Schools partnering with local science museums, technical companies to bring in resources on hands-on STEM experiences	2.61	1.14	Agreed
9.	Schools participate in STEM fairs, workshops and competitions that promote hands-on learning for students	2.58	1.15	Agreed
10.	Local community provide resources, volunteers, or mentorship opportunities to support hands-on STEM education.	2.53	1.19	Agreed
Weighted Mean		2.73		

Key: Disagreed = Mean < 2.50; Agreed = Mean > 2.50

Source: Field work, 2024

Table 1 above revealed the availability of hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools in Ilorin Metropolis. It was evident from the results in the table above that the mean value of all the items were greater than 2.50. This revealed that teachers agreed to all the items on the availability of hands-on activities in STEM education. The weighted mean value of 2.73 which is greater than the benchmark of 2.50 indicated that hands-on activities in STEM education is available among the lower basic teachers in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State.

Research Question 2: To what extent do teachers utilize hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools in Ilorin Metropolis?

In other to ascertain the extent to which the teachers utilize hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools in Ilorin Metropolis, the total points of the respondents which was in continuous data were summed up for each respondent, thereby having a total minimum point of 10 and maximum points of 40. Hence, the range between the minimum and maximum total points is 30. This was categorized into three levels. The points between 10 - 20 is Low, 21 - 30 is Moderate, and 31 - 40 is High. Therefore, the summary of result on teachers' utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education among lower basic teachers in Ilorin Metropolis is presented in the table 2.

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Table 2: Summary of the extent of Teachers’ Utilization Hands-on Activities in STEM Education in Lower Basic Schools in Ilorin Metropolis.

Range	Frequency	Percent	Remark
10 – 20	53	17.67%	Low
21 – 30	206	68.67%	*Moderate
31 – 40	41	13.67%	High
Total	300	100%	

Source: Field work, 2024

The above table 2 revealed that 53 (17.67%) of the respondents indicated low utilization of hand-on activities, 206 (68.67%) of the respondents had moderate utilization, while 41 (13.67%) respondents had high utilization of hand-on activities. This revealed that majority (68.67%) of the respondents showed that hands-on activities in STEM education are moderately utilized by the teachers in lower basic schools in Ilorin Metropolis.

Research Question 3: What are the challenges faced in the utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools?

In order to find out the challenges faced in the utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools, mean of responses of the teachers to each item on the questionnaire were analysed, having four Likert scale format of Strongly Agreed (4 points), Agreed (3 points), Disagreed (2 points), and Strongly Disagreed (1 point). In other to have the benchmark, the average of the total point was calculated to be 2.50 (i.e. $4+3+2+1 = 10$; $10/4 = 2.5$). The result is presented in the table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation showing the challenges faced in the Utilization of Hands-on Activities in STEM Education in Lower Basic Schools.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Lack of adequate resources for the implementation of hands-on activities	2.61	1.04	Agreed
2.	Challenges in aligning hands-on activities with the curriculum and learning objectives	2.58	1.09	Agreed
3.	Lack of confidence on the part of the teachers in facilitating hands-on activities	2.54	1.16	Agreed
4.	The cost of purchasing and maintaining materials for hands-on experiments and projects is prohibitive for schools.	2.91	1.14	Agreed
5.	Resources that are available are not enough for each student to actively engage in the activity.	2.88	1.04	Agreed
6.	Planning and preparing for hands-on activities can be time-consuming	2.71	1.13	Agreed
7.	Hands-on activities can lead to disorganized, noisy, or chaotic classrooms, making it challenging for teachers to maintain control.	2.77	1.04	Agreed
8.	Some hands-on activities, especially in science or technology, can present safety risks.	2.71	1.14	Agreed
9.	Teachers not receiving sufficient training on how to effectively teach using hands-on methods.	2.54	1.13	Agreed
10.	Teachers may lack the pedagogical knowledge to use these methods effectively.	2.63	1.09	Agreed
Weighted Mean		2.69		

Key: Disagreed = Mean < 2.50; Agreed = Mean > 2.50

Source: Field work, 2024

Table 3 above revealed the challenges faced in the utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools in Ilorin Metropolis. From the teachers’ response, it was revealed that the major challenges in the utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools are; cost of purchasing and maintaining materials for hands-on

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experiments and projects is prohibitive for schools., resources that are available are not enough for each student to actively engage in the activity, hands-on activities can lead to disorganized, noisy, or chaotic classrooms, making it challenging for teachers to maintain control, planning and preparing for hands-on activities can be time-consuming, and some hands-on activities, especially in science or technology, can present safety risks. These were all ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th, respectively in accordance with their mean values from the highest to the least. The overall mean value of 2.69 which is greater than the benchmark means of 2.50 indicated that all the above items are the challenges facing the utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education in lower basic schools in Ilorin Metropolis.

Discussion of findings

It was revealed from the findings that hands-on activities in STEM education are available and moderately utilized by lower basic school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis. This was evident from the response of the lower basic school teachers, which made it known that hands-on activities in STEM education are available in lower basic schools. This is because teachers have found out that the use of hands-on activities in teaching lower basic school teachers have achieved better results, compared to traditional ways of teaching. More so, it was revealed from the findings that lower basic school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis moderately utilize hands-on activities in STEM education in schools. This was seen from the response of the teachers, which showed how lower basic school teachers actively utilize hands-on activities in STEM among lower basic pupils. This is because teachers have seen how their pupils react to the use hands-on activities in STEM education, thereby resulting to different beliefs that determined the extent of the teachers' utilization. This finding was supported by Ahmad, Hui and Ahmad (2019), Alspaugh and Hartman (2015) and Gega (2018) who observed that hands-on activities in STEM education can be made very lovely and interesting for the children when they are being used by the teachers who always guide them during the activities. This tells us that active engagement by teachers enhances students' learning experiences and outcomes.

Additionally, it was shown from the response of the teachers that lower basic school teachers are faced with some challenges in the availability and utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education. This is because hands on activities takes much time in order to get it prepared. Major challenges that teachers face are cost of purchasing and maintaining materials for hands-on experiments and projects is prohibitive for schools., resources that are available are not enough for each student to actively engage in the activity, hands-on activities can lead to disorganized, noisy, or chaotic classrooms, making it challenging for teachers to maintain control, planning and preparing for hands-on activities can be time-consuming, and some hands-on activities, especially in science or technology, can present safety risks. In support of this finding, Dunn and Mulvenon (2009), Garelick and Sherman (2018), and Ekueme, Okon and Ezenwa (2015) asserted that these challenges are as a result of lackadaisical attitude of government and school owners towards the provision of adequate resources, incorporating hands on activities in STEM education in the curriculum, teachers' inability to manage time, or mix hands on activities with traditional ways of teaching because of inadequate time, and lack of knowledge of the concept that leads to lack of confidence on the part of teachers.

Conclusion

In conclusion, hands on activities in STEM education are available and utilized by teachers among lower basic pupils in Ilorin metropolis. These hands-on activities are unique and best for learning STEM education concepts when they are available and properly utilized by the teachers. Ultimately, hands on activities in STEM education advocates will be needed in order to promote the importance and benefits of hands-on activities in STEM education and early childhood professionals can become advocates for hands-on activities in STEM education for young children. So, therefore, hands-on activities in STEM education are available and utilized by teachers among lower basic pupils.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. All stakeholders in the education sector should make sure that hands on activities are available and well utilized by teachers in STEM education among lower basic pupils.
2. Frequent supervision and monitoring should be encouraged in order to make sure teachers appropriately utilize hands on activities in STEM education among lower basic pupils.
3. Challenges facing the utilization of hands-on activities in STEM education can be resolved through different ways like proper allocation of time, teacher training programs, inclusion of hands-on activities in the curriculum, and motivation. Also, addressing these challenges may require a multi-faceted approach that includes professional development, adequate

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resource allocation, supportive policies, and collaboration among educators, administrators, parents, and the wider community.

References

- Ahmad, I., Hui, L., & Ahmad, M. S. (2019). Hands-On Science Activities and Student Achievement: A Comparative Study. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(7), 70-78.
- Alspaugh, J., & Hartman, L. (2015). Exploring the impact of hands-on activities on learning. *The Journal of Effective Teaching*, 15(2), 1-15.
- Anubi, M. O. (2023). Effects of Hands-On Activities and Lecture Instructional Strategies on Students' Attitude Towards Physics in Delta South Senatorial District, *International Journal of Research in Education and Sustainable Development*, 3(5), 1-13.
- Arancibia, V., Toledo, C., & Canales, R. (2019). Enhancing the STEM Curriculum with Hands-On Learning: A Study of Elementary Teachers' Perceptions. *European Journal of STEM Education*, 4(2), 01-10.
- Beyea, S. C., Palmer, R. T., & Taasoobshirazi, G. (2020). A Meta-Analysis of the Effects of Hands-On Instructional Approaches in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Programs. *School Science and Mathematics*, 120(5), 264-277.
- Biancarosa, G., & Griffiths, R. (2012). *Technology-based formative assessment: A national survey of teacher use, perceptions, and professional development needs*. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Education, Office of Educational Technology.
- Demir, S., Kocakoyun, S., & Aydin, A. (2020). The Effects of Hands-On Learning and Parental Involvement on Elementary Students' STEM Achievement. *Journal of Educational Sciences Research*, 10(1), 150-167.
- Dunn, K. E., & Mulvenon, S. W. (2009). A critical review of research on hands-on science in K-6 classrooms. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 18(2), 241-257.
- Ekueme C.O, Okon E.E.F., Ezenwa D.C (2015). The impact of Hands-on Approach on students' Academic Performance in Basic Science and Mathematics, *Journal of Science Education*, 5(6), 2 - 6.
- Fadel, C., & Trilling, B. (2009). *21st century skills: Learning for life in our times*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Garelick, G., & Sherman, M. (2018). Using Hands-on Activities to Promote STEM Learning in Elementary Schools. *European Journal of STEM Education*, 3(1), 01-07.
- Gega, P. (2018). The effectiveness of hands-on learning in STEM education. *Journal of STEM Education: Innovations and Research*, 19(3), 23-30.
- Hacifazlioglu, Ö., & Yigit, N. (2020). Influence of Hands-On Activities on Elementary Students' Attitudes Toward Science. *European Journal of STEM Education*, 5(1), 01-09.
- International Journal of STEM Education. (2019). The effectiveness of project-based learning and hands-on activities in teaching STEM subjects to lower basic pupils. Retrieved from <https://stemeducationjournal.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40594-019-0195-5>
- Johnson, S. M., & Oludipe, D. I. (2019). The Effect of Hands-On Activities on Science Learning and Achievement in Elementary School Students. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 8(4), 103-113.
- Jones, S. L., & Jones, D. L. (2017). The effectiveness of hands-on activities in promoting interest and engagement in STEM disciplines. *International Journal of Education in Mathematics, Science and Technology*, 5(1), 45-54.
- Journal of STEM Education: Innovations and Research. (2018). Hands-On STEM Education: A Review of Literature. Retrieved from <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/183054/>
- Kelecioğlu, H., Yaman, F., & Ozyurek, S. (2019). Hands-On STEM Learning for Elementary Students: A Comparison of Active Learning Strategies. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 18(4), 565-580.
- Kim, S., Han, J., & Kim, Y. (2019). STEM Education for Elementary Students: A Comparison of Traditional Teaching Methods and Hands-On Learning. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 18(6), 972-986.
- Li, X., Song, C., & Qian, X. (2019). Integrating Hands-On Activities in STEM Education: A Case Study of Elementary Teachers' Implementation Strategies. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 29(4), 799-818.
- Lunn, S., McIntosh, C., & Mioduser, D. (2020). STEM Learning through Hands-On Activities: A Case Study of Elementary School Teachers' Perceptions. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 30(3), 545-567.
- McNair, T. (2018). Hands-on learning: The benefits of learning by doing. *Education Week*, 37(21), 1-4.

Assessment of Availability ... (Ahmed, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15025960>

- National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2018). *Science and engineering for grades 6-12: Investigation and design at the center*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press.
- National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2018). *English learners in STEM subjects: Transforming classrooms, schools, and lives*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press.
- National Science Board. (2018). Science and engineering indicators 2018. Retrieved from <https://www.nsf.gov/statistics/2018/nsb20181/report/sections/highlights#stem>
- National Science Foundation. (2017). STEM education for all: A strategic plan. Retrieved from https://www.nsf.gov/attachments/140063/public/STEM-Ed-for-All_2016.pdf
- National Science Foundation. (2017). STEM education: A foundation for success. Retrieved from https://www.nsf.gov/news/special_reports/stem/education.jsp
- National Science Teachers Association. (2019). Engaging students in STEM through hands-on learning. Retrieved from <https://www.nsta.org/college-and-career-readiness/engaging-students-stem-through-hands-learning>
- Tumay, H., & Cakmakci, G. (2019). An Investigation of the Effectiveness of Hands-On Science Instruction versus Textbook Instruction on the Achievement of Elementary School Students. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 18(5), 762-777.
- Yenilmez, K., & Arslan, A. (2020). The Effect of Hands-On STEM Learning on Elementary Students' Achievement and Motivation. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(1), 617-634.
- Yoon, S. A., & Zeidler, D. L. (2017). STEM education in the early years: Challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Science A Education and Technology*, 26(2), 107-120.

Assessment of Mobile-Phone-Integration on Teacher Training Programs among Colleges of Education Pre-service Teachers in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract:

There is a saying that “No Nation rises above the quality of its Teachers”. This study investigates ‘Mobile-Phone-Integration on Teacher Training Programs among Colleges of Education Pre-service Teachers in North-West, Nigeria’. The population of the study is 2,629 consisting of all NCE II Computer Science Pre-service teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in colleges of education in Northwest, Nigeria, sample of 335 is determined using Crejcie and Morgan (1970). Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The study adapted a questionnaire titled: “Smartphone Utilization for Academic Purposes (MUAP)”. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. The study revealed a high level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers. However, the study also revealed considerable challenges hindering effective Mobile-Phone utilization, including affordability among others. The findings underscore the need for policy interventions to enhance on affordability of Mobile-devices, thereby fostering an environment conducive to Mobile Phone-based learning. This research contributes to the discourse on innovation in teacher education, highlighting the potential of Mobile-Phones to foster 21st-century teaching practices in Nigerian tertiary education. This is in line with the findings of Becker et al., (2017) that Innovations in technology are influencing how students’ access, learn, retain, and apply information. The study concluded that, the level of Mobile-Phone utilization among pre-service teachers in the colleges is very high as well as the challenges. The study therefore, recommended among others that: Affordable Mobile-Phones should be provided.

Keywords: Curriculum Integration, Mobile Phone utilization, teacher education, Digital Divide.

Introduction

The essence of using technology is for education, communication, social interaction, commercial, as well as playing important role in terms of development of individuals and group of people in the world (Hatch, 2018). The rapid adaptation of young generation to the technological developments increases aim for using Mobile Phone device in different aspects of their life. Mobile Phone has now become an immediate *friend* and the best tool for social and commercial benefits to the youth in the 21st Century (Scott, 2015). The number of individuals using the mobile devices is three times more than the computer users (Baptista & Oliveira, 2015). These computers abolish time and place concept whereas the mobile phones are also more popular and sometimes efficient (Ricci, Rokach, & Shapira, 2015).

Mobile Phone as a general-purpose mobile device has impact on so many aspects of human endeavor. Its mobility, affordability and easy access made the youth to easily integrate it into their daily activities. It is observed that Mobile Phone play important roles even in education, academic research, planning and development. The use of conventional methods of teaching and dominating all the class activities, doing the talking and chalking with little or no student’s participation is now boring to both students and lecturers, especially in the teacher training institutions (Elbaz, 2018). This approach is seriously discouraged by most researches because, it leads to poor concentration, boredom, unattractiveness, difficulty in assessment of individual differences as a result of large class size (over population) and so on. Learning requires some certain facilities in order to take place especially for students in tertiary institutions of learning like the polytechnics, colleges of education and universities. Those required facilities simplifies teaching and learning processes (academic activities) from both teachers and student’s sides, these instruments are sometimes called teaching and learning materials or instructional aides. These set of facilities differs depending on the time and place of use also on subject or topic to be thought, as most of the facilities are designed to achieve a specific purpose. Traditionally, instructional aides are improvised using some of the available resources that can be easily obtained at a given period of time, to teach a particular course or topic; in mathematics, students are taught

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topics like shapes using cardboard paper or any thick plain paper, each piece of the card is cut to represent a shape like triangle, square, rectangle, circle and so on. Improvisation of such materials requires an adequate knowledge of shapes and skills of shaping and molding simple objectives to a simple and reasonable object or compound and reasonable object for use in classrooms to deliver a lecture on something or explain a concept or phenomena. The use of instructional aid makes teaching and learning easier than just the use of a verbal or written word to explain a phenomena or concept. In order to achieve above, makes the adoption of technologies in place ranging from simple technology to the complex, from natural substances to artificial substances in order to achieve a determined goal.

In the 20th and 21st century, it is expected that modern technology should dominate almost every aspect of human endeavor, the use of digital technology that deals with personal computers (internet and intranet, desktops, laptops, notebooks, iPad, light pen, electronic ink and electronic papers, projectors, Interactive white boards and so on) (Elbaz, 2018). The 21st century students are not limited to the knowledge of life, even in the classroom settings, where there are now various forms of technology (Harding, 2016). The face of the contemporary classroom is ever-changing (Gargiulo & Metcalf, 2017). Innovations in technology are influencing how students' access, learn, retain, and apply information, and it influences pedagogy of educators using presentation softwares and modules using technology as instructional aid and training media (Becker et al., 2017). Since technology is the application of scientific knowledge to the practical aims of human life; classroom technology to achieve educational task may include computer applications, smart boards, digital projectors and other technological devices. Such devices capture students' attention; however, educators must stay up-to-date on technology trends in the world and how to integrate it into their pedagogy (Selwyn, 2016). Despite the possession of various technologies for use in education, it is observed that none of the technologies clearly supports collaborative learning and give students equal right to sources of information and at the same time provides a means of sharing the information within themselves, having access to the source of all forms of information; such as, text, audio, audio-visual and video to easily access, manipulate, utilize and share with one another, that would help students to equally store and retrieve all information anywhere and anytime as well as assist the students to have a high level of retention.

Objectives of the Study

This research intends to achieve the following objectives; to:

1. examine the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in Federal Colleges of Education in North-West Nigeria.
2. find out the challenges associated to Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in Federal Colleges of Education in North-West Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study raised the following questions to guide the study:

1. What is the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in Federal Colleges of Education in North-West Nigeria?
2. What are the challenges associated to Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in Federal Colleges of Education in North-West Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference between utilization of Mobile-Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria.
2. H_{02} : There is no significant difference between challenges associated with utilization of Mobile-Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted for this study, the justification for using survey research design was that, the study samples some pre-service teachers in 5 colleges of education to find the level of their Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes, and examine the challenges. The population of the study is 2,629 consisting of all NCE II Computer Science Pre-service teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in colleges of education in Northwest, Nigeria, from which a sample of 335 was determined as recommended by Crejcie and Morgan (1970) when total population is 2629. A sample being a subset of the population chosen to participate in a study was 335.

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The researcher used questionnaire titled: Mobile Phone Utilization for Academic Purposes (MUAP) for data collection. The MUAP instrument has three sections. Section “A” captured respondents’ biodata, section “B” data on the level of Mobile Phone utilization among pre-service teachers under study, “C” elicited data on the challenges of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers. The instrument was validated by experts in Measurement and Evaluation from Faculty of Education Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria. The Cronbach reliability was used to test the reliability of the test items. The reliability of the 30 items of the instrument was 0.947. The instrument questionnaire items were found to be reliable. This was in confirmation of test of reliability by Spiegel, (1992) Stevens, (1986), and Olayiwola, (2010). According to them an instrument is considered reliable if it lies between 0 and 1, and that the closer the calculated reliability coefficient is to zero, the less reliable is the instrument, and the closer the calculated reliability co-efficient is to 1, the more reliable is the instrument. This therefore confirms the reliability of the data collection instrument used as fit for the main work. The questionnaires were administered to the respondents in their various lecture rooms. The questionnaires were filled by the students immediately and returned before the end of their classes. The period of data administration and collection took three weeks with the help of two research assistants.

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) IBM version 26.0 was used in the analysis of the data collected. Frequency counts and percentage was used for the bio data variables. The research questions were answered using item frequency of the four Likert scale options and their mean and standard deviations for each item in each of the ten items of the table. The cumulative mean is compared with a standard mean of 2.500. The null hypotheses were tested with Chi square statistical tool to assess the significance of each of the three cumulative variables of the instrument. The chi square is used because the data is ordinal and to determine it’s significance Chi square is the more appropriate statistical method to put in place. All the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Answering Research Questions

Table 1 (Question One): What is the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCEs in North wester Nigeria ?

S/ No	ITEMS	HU	U	NU	HNU	MEAN	STD	DECISION
1	I use my Mobile Phone to search for multimedia documents on Google	99	112	50	48	2.848	0.981	Agree
2	My Mobile Phone enables me to access books from E-libraries	112	108	39	50	2.913	0.612	Agree
3	I make use of Mobile Phone to search for meaning of words in the dictionary/thesaurus.	110	97	48	54	2.851	0.823	Agree
4	I use my Mobile Phone to view and note articles, citations from the Google Scholar.	100	108	64	37	2.877	0.881	Agree
5	I also use my Mobile Phone to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers	99	117	51	42	2.883	1.024	Agree
6	My Mobile Phone enables me to access life educational programs prepared by other institutions.	98	80	77	54	2.718	1.041	Agree
7	I use my Mobile Phone to record voice lectures from the lessons in the class for revision sake	96	104	64	45	2.812	1.044	Agree
8	I also use my Mobile Phone to record videos during practical classes for future replay to improve my retention ability.	103	101	63	42	2.858	0.814	Agree

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9	My Mobile Phone helps me in accessing Academic Calendar of the session and other vital relevant information from the College.	96	108	67	38	0.723	Agree
						2.848	
10	I use my Mobile Phone to access relevant educational videos from You-tube and other video blogs for academic purpose..	98	112	57	42	0.800	Agree
						2.865	
	CUMULATIVE MEAN					2.847	Agree

Decision Mean = 2.500 (HU=Highly Utilized, U=Utilized, NU=Not Utilized, HNU=Highly Not Utilized)

Table 1 shows the responses of preservice teachers on the level of smart phone utilization for academic purposes in Federal College of Education in Northwest Nigeria. Item one of the table says: I use my smart phone to search for multimedia documents on google, the responses shows that 99 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 112 are utilizing while 50 are not utilizing and 48 are highly not utilizing their smart phone to search for multimedia documents on google. The second item says: My Mobile phone enables me to access books from E-libraries, the responses shows that 112 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 108 are utilizing while 39 are not utilizing and 50 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to enable them access books from E-libraries. The third item says: the responses shows that 110 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for searching for meaning of words in the dictionary/thesaurus, 97 are utilizing while 48 are not utilizing and 54 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone in searching for meaning of words in the dictionary/thesaurus. The fourth item says: the responses shows that 100 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to view note articles, citations from the Google Scholar, 108 are utilizing while 64 are not utilizing and 37 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to view note articles, citations from the Google Scholar. The fifth item says: the responses shows that 99 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers, 117 are utilizing while 51 are not utilizing and 42 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers.

The sixth item says: the responses shows that 98 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to access life educational programs prepared by other institutions, 80 are utilizing while 77 are not utilizing and 54 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to enables them access life educational programs prepared by other institutions. The seventh item says: the responses shows that 96 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to record voice lectures from the lessons in the class for revision sake, 104 are utilizing while 64 are not utilizing and 45 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to record voice lectures from the lessons in the class for revision sake. The eighth item says: the responses shows that 103 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to record videos during practical classes for future replay to improve my retention ability, 101 are utilizing while 63 are not utilizing and 42 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to record videos during practical classes for future replay to improve my retention ability. The ninth item says: the responses shows that 96 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to accessing Academic Calendar of the session and other vital relevant information from the College, 108 are utilizing while 67 are not utilizing and 38 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone in accessing Academic Calendar of the session and other vital relevant information from the College. The tenth item says: the responses shows that 98 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to access relevant educational videos from You-tube and other video blogs for academic purpose, 112 are utilizing while 57 are not utilizing and 42 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to access relevant educational videos from You-tube and other video blogs for academic purpose.

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Table 2 (Question Two): What are the challenges that affect the effective use of Mobile Phone?

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	STD	DECISION
1	Cost of purchasing Mobile Phone with all functionality is high	110	103	46	50	2.883	1.041	Agree
2	Network issue is a challenge, as failure from network providers affects the efficiency of the system	101	109	60	39	2.880	1.045	Agree
3	Implementing Mobile Phone into teacher requires some rules and regulations/blueprint	102	98	60	49	2.819	0.817	Agree
4	Cost of data to access the network is another challenge	101	102	70	36	2.867	0.881	Agree
5	Variation in size, speed and storage capacity of the Mobile Phone is also a challenge as some may have lower than the required capacity for some applications	89	114	57	49	2.786	1.044	Agree
6	Perception of stakeholders towards the integration of Mobile Phone utilization in academic purposes varies	107	104	50	48	2.874	1.046	Agree
7	Readiness from the government, curriculum planners, schools, parents and students etc is another challenge	90	106	64	49	2.767	1.044	Agree
8	Difficulty in handling the class when each student operates individually with his Mobile Phone	89	90	70	60	2.673	0.814	Agree
9	Battery lifespan is another challenge as not all phones can last for long without draining charge.	90	89	75	55	2.693	0.714	Agree
10	Non physical engagements in some activities especially that has to do with laboratory practicals and the likes.	92	89	70	58	2.696	0.811	Agree
CUMULATIVE MEAN						2.793		Agree

Decision Mean = 2.500 (SA=Strongly Agreed, A=Agreed, NA=Not Agreed, SNA=Strongly Not Agreed)

Table 2 shows the responses of pre-service teachers on level of challenges of Mobile phone utilization for academic purposes in Federal College of Education in Northwest Nigeria. Item one in the table says: Cost of purchasing Mobile phone with all functionality is high, the responses shows that 110 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 103 are utilizing while 46 are not utilizing and 50 are highly not utilizing, Cost of purchasing Mobile phone with all functionality is high. Item two in the table says: Cost of purchasing Mobile phone with all functionality is high, the responses shows that 101 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 109 are utilizing while 60 are not utilizing and 39 are highly not utilizing, Network issue is a challenge, as failure from network providers affects the efficiency of the system. Item three in the table says: Implementing Mobile phone into teacher requires some rules and regulations/blueprint, the responses shows that 102 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 98 are utilizing while 60 are not utilizing and 49 are highly not utilizing, Implementing Mobile phone into teacher requires some rules and regulations/blueprint.

Item four in the table says: Cost of data to access the network is another challenge, the responses shows that 101 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 102 are utilizing while 70 are not utilizing and 36 are highly not utilizing, Cost of data to access the network is another challenge. Item fifth in the table says: Variation in size, speed and storage capacity of the Mobile phone is also a challenge as some may have lower than the required capacity for

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some applications, the responses shows that 89 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 114 are utilizing while 57 are not utilizing and 49 are highly not utilizing, Variation in size, speed and storage capacity of the Mobile phone is also a challenge as some may have lower than the required capacity for some applications. Item sixth in the table says: Perception of stakeholders towards the integration of Mobile phone utilization in academic purposes varies, the responses shows that 107 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 104 are utilizing while 50 are not utilizing and 48 are highly not utilizing, Perception of stakeholders towards the integration of Mobile phone utilization in academic purposes varies.

Item seventh in the table says: Difficulty in handling the class when each student operates individually with his Mobile phone, the responses shows that 90 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 106 are utilizing while 64 are not utilizing and 49 are highly not utilizing, Readiness from the government, curriculum planners, schools, parents and students etc. is another challenge. Item eighth in the table says: Readiness from the government, curriculum planners, schools, parents and students etc. is another challenge, the responses shows that 89 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 90 are utilizing while 70 are not utilizing and 60 are highly not utilizing, Battery lifespan is another challenge as not all phones can last for long without draining charge. Item ninth in the table says: Readiness from the government, curriculum planners, schools, parents and students etc. is another challenge, the responses shows that 90 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 89 are utilizing while 75 are not utilizing and 55 are highly not utilizing, Battery lifespan is another challenge as not all phones can last for long without draining charge. Item tenth in the table says: Non-physical engagements in some activities especially that has to do with laboratory practical and the likes. etc. is another challenge, the responses shows that 92 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 89 are utilizing while 70 are not utilizing and 58 are highly not utilizing, Non-physical engagements in some activities especially that has to do with laboratory practical and the likes.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between utilization of Mobile-Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria.

Table 3: Chi square (X^2)—statistics on significance of the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria.

Variable	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Df	X^2 computed	X^2 critical	P-Value
Level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes	114	93	52	50	309	6	47.481	40.113	0.006
	104.3	98.1	62.6	44.0					

p calculated = 0.006 < 0.05, x^2 computed = 47 > X^2 critical value of 40.113 at df 6 (SA=Strongly Agreed, A=Agreed, NA=Not Agreed, SNA=Strongly Not Agreed)

Results of the Chi square (X^2) statistics in table 3 shows that the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria, is significant. Reason being that the chi square (X^2) statistics showed that the calculated p value of 0.006 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and its calculated Chi square (X^2) value of 47.481 is above the chi square (X^2) critical value of 40.113 at df 27. The observed counts are 114, 93, 52 and 50 for Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagreed respectively.

This outcome showed that the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCEs in North-west Nigeria, is very significant. Therefore the null hypothesis which state, there is no significant difference between utilization of Mobile-Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria, is hereby rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between challenges associated with utilization of Mobile Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria..

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Table 4: Chi square (X^2)—statistics on significance of the challenges affecting the effective utilization of Mobile Phone for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria,.

Variable	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Df	X^2 computed	X^2 critical	P-Value
Challenges affecting utilization of Mobile Phone for academic purposes	110	103	46	50	309	6	58.907	40.113	0.017

p calculated = 0.017 < 0.05, x^2 computed = 58.907 > X^2 critical value of 40.113 at df 6

Results of the Chi square (X^2) statistics in table 4 shows that challenges affecting the effective utilization of Mobile Phone for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria, is significant.

Reason being that the chi square (X^2) statistics showed that the calculated p value of 0.017 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and its calculated Chi square (X^2) value of 58.907 is above the chi square (X^2) critical value of 40.113 at df 27. The observed counts are 110, 103, 46 and 50 for strongly agree, Agree, Disagree and strongly disagreed respectively.

This outcome showed that the challenges affecting the effective utilization of Mobile Phone for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria, is very significant. Therefore the null hypothesis which state that, there is no significant difference between challenges associated with utilization of Mobile Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria, is hereby rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The level of Mobile phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria is very high and commendable this is because the cumulative mean response agreement level of 2.847 is higher than the decision mean of 2.500. Specifically, most Majority opined that My Mobile phone enables me to access books from E-libraries as this view had the highest mean agreement level of 2.913 with details showing that while 112 strongly agree, 108 agreed, as against 39 disagreed and the rest 50 strongly disagreed. Also, majority of pre-service teachers use their Mobile phone to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers, as this has the second highest mean response of 2.883 as a total of 99 strongly agreed while 117 agreed as against 51 that disagreed and the rest 42 strongly disagreed. In summary, the level of Mobile phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria is very high and commendable especially as majority use their phones to access books from E-libraries and use their Mobile phones to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers among others.

The challenges that affect the effective use of Mobile phones, are very great and enormous as the cumulative mean agreement level of 2.793 is higher that, the 2.500 decision mean Specifically, the highest challenge is that Cost of purchasing Mobile phone with all functionality is high as this attracted the highest mean agreement level of 2.883 as details showed that 110 strongly agreed, 103 agreed, a against 46 that disagreed and the rest 50 strongly disagreed. In the same vein another very serious challenge is Network issue is a challenge, as failure from network providers affects the efficiency of the system as this attracted the second highest mean of 2.880 as 101 strongly agreed, while 109 agreed as against 60 disagreed and 39 strongly disagreed. In summary, the challenges that affect the effective use of Mobile phones, are very great and enormous as the cumulative mean agreement level of 2.793 is higher that the 2.500 decision mean, especially as Cost of purchasing Mobile phone with all functionality and Network issue is a challenge.

Conclusion

It is therefore concluded that: The level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCEs in North-west Nigeria is very high and commendable especially as majority use their Mobile Phone to access books from E-libraries and use their Mobile Phone to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers and even use them prepare for the exams. The challenges that affect the effective use of Mobile Phone, are very great and enormous as the cumulative mean agreement level of 2.793 is higher that the 2.500 decision mean, especially as Cost of purchasing Mobile Phone with all functionality and Network issue is very high.

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Recommendations

1. Integrate digital literacy training into the training to enhance pre-services' skills in utilizing Mobile phones for academic purposes which will promote the development and utilization of Open Education Resources (OER) to reduce reliance and costly materials and develop policies supporting Mobile learning, ensuring equitable access to educational resources and addressing digital divide concerns, also provide ongoing supports and training for teacher educators to effectively integrate Mobile technology into their teaching practices.
2. The Federal Government and educational institutions should consider subsidizing Mobile devices with essential functionalities for pre-service teachers in Federal Colleges of Education (FCEs) in Nigeria through collaborative partnerships with Mobile technology companies and Educational technology companies to provide affordable mobile devices, data plans and educational resources to reduce reliance on costly materials and invest in improving telecommunication infrastructure to address network challenges, ensuring reliable internet access in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Also conduct regular needs assessment to identify specific challenges with the network and develop target interventions.

References

- Baptista, G., & Oliveira, T. (2015). Understanding mobile banking: The unified theory of acceptance and use of technology combined with cultural moderators. *Computers in Human Behavior, 50*, 418-430.
- Becker, S. A., Cummins, M., Davis, A., Freeman, A., Hall, C. G., & Ananthanarayanan, V. (2017). NMC horizon report: 2017 higher education edition: The New Media Consortium.
- Elbaz, F. (2018). *Teacher thinking: A study of practical knowledge*: Routledge.
- Gargiulo, R. M., & Metcalf, D. (2017). *Teaching in Today's Inclusive Classrooms: A Universal Design for Learning Approach*: Nelson Education.
- Harding, S. (2016). Whose science? Whose knowledge?: *Thinking from women's lives*: Cornell University Press.
- Hatch, M. J. (2018). *Organization theory: Modern, symbolic, and postmodern perspectives*: Oxford university press.
- Ricci, F., Rokach, L., & Shapira, B. (2015). Recommender systems: Introduction and challenges Recommender systems handbook (pp. 1-34): Springer.
- Scott, D. M. (2015). *The new rules of marketing and PR: How to use social media, online video, mobile applications, blogs, news releases, and viral marketing to reach buyers directly*: John Wiley & Sons.
- Selwyn, N. (2016). *Education and technology: Key issues and debates*: Bloomsbury Publishing.a

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Assessment of Parental Influence on Children’s Moral Development among Christian Parents in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study focused on assessment of parental influence on Children’s moral development among Christian parents in Katsina State, Nigeria. Population of the study consists 1636,388 Christian parents during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina State, a sample size of 567 parents were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling techniques. Five hundred and sixty-seven (567). Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. One instrument questionnaire was employed to collect data. Mean scores and standard deviation were used to answer research questions. While; t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study reveal that: Christian parents teach their children to take responsibility for their actions and to be accountable for the consequences of those actions. The following recommendations were made: Christian parents should create a home environment that encourages accountability and responsibility through positive reinforcement and appropriate consequences.

Key words: *Christian parents, spiritual/moral responsibility, upbringing, children.*

Introduction

The way in which children are raised profoundly affects their holistic development, encompassing their spiritual, mental, emotional, social, and physical growth. This extensive process involves various aspects of care, education, and guidance provided by parents or guardians, starting from infancy and continuing through to adulthood. Be aware that, Children are a heritage from the LORD, as Psalm 127:3a makes it abundantly apparent. According to Proverbs 22:6, Christian parents should “train up a child in the way he should go: and when he is old, he will not depart from it.” Fathers are especially instructed to raise their children under the care and instruction of the Lord, not to stir them to anger. (Ephesians 6:4). Maintaining a Christian family, teaching children in a way that pleases God, and watching each child accept Jesus Christ and mature into a loving, serving adult all demand dedication and hard work from each parent, as well as trust and reliance on the Lord. Therefore, it is expected of parents to adhere to God given responsibility to have a Christian home and train up godly children.

Parents have legal and religious obligations to raise their children in addition to a moral one. Parents are expected to inculcate appropriate knowledge and skills necessary for making their children useful to God and the society. Parents who identify as Christian believe in Jesus and His teachings. These parents are members of one or more Christian denominations in Katsina State. They make up the majority of the state's religious group. The parents make sure that their wards' needs are satisfied and that their actions are compliant with biblical teachings regarding parental duty. The social, moral, and financial aspects of their children are impacted by their responsibilities. With a population of more than 5,800,000, Kaduna State was divided into Katsina State in 1987. Despite only ranking 17th out of 36 states in terms of land mass, Katsina State is the fifth most populous state in the nation. The majority religion in the state is Islam, and the Hausa people make up the majority of its ethnic population.

Statement of the Problem

Raising children to develop a genuine and personal faith in Jesus Christ as their Lord and Savior is the need of the hour. Raising children with good morals and characters is about building moral and ethical character and increasing self-worth and self-confidence in children and families. It is about empowerment and responsibility. Children are not born with the skills for active involvement in a democratic society. We, as adult citizens, must carefully consider what we and others do to convey healthy values that support and preserve our precious democracy. There is a window of opportunity for educating children and their parents when children are young. The children are willing learners, and often their parents are more interested in improving their parenting skills at this time than they are later in their children’s lives. Today, a great percentage of our children are living

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a life of disobedience to their parents, they are copying the patterns of this world with deftness (Romans 12:2). Today, the lifestyle of these children is such that it is very difficult to have dissimilarity amid children raised in Christian homes and of those of the world.

The study notes that some Christian parents in Katsina State have disregarded their spiritual responsibilities which include teaching their children God's word, how to pray and fast, participating in Church weekly activities (Deut.6:7ff.), discipline them when they do wrong (Heb. 12:6, Rev. 3:19), and reward them when they do right which serves as their proved of genuine love and providing for their children basic necessities. Some parents don't even have time to let their children confide in them about their problems. Owing to cultural customs, some parents were not allowed to speak with their children especially the first born and instead chose to entrust their care to businesses. As a result of their parents' carelessness, some of the children have been forced to participate in heinous social vices such as drug and alcohol addiction, smoking, kidnapping, arm robbery, disobedience, laziness, dishonesty, disrespect, prostitution online bullying and other vices.

How can we change the perspective of our children who are easily lured and enticed by bad habits from the world? This research is fundamental because it aims at making a study on the Christian parent's spiritual responsibility in the upbringing of their children.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to assess parental influence on Children's moral development among Christian parents in Katsina State, Nigeria. The study therefore has the following specific objective:

1. To assessment the extent of parental influence on Children's moral development among Christian parents in Katsina State, Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research question is formulated as a basis for inquiry into the topic under study:

1. What is the extent of parental influence on Children's moral development among Christian parents in Katsina State, Nigeria?

Null Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated:

There is no significant difference between parental influence on Children's moral development among Christian parents in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual nature of a Christian Parents

The term "parent" generally denotes an individual who has either legally or biologically produced offspring, commonly referred to as children (Miller, 2016). Biologically, a parent contributes genetic material to the creation of offspring through sexual reproduction (Bateson, 2015). However, parenthood transcends mere biological connections to encompass legal guardianship, emotional nurturing, and the provision of care and support for children (Fivush & Goodnow, 2019). The term "Christian" denotes an individual who adheres to Christianity, which is one of the world's major religions that centered on the life and teachings of Jesus Christ, as recorded in the New Testament of the Bible (Alvarado, 2023). Christians profess faith in Jesus Christ as the Son of God and humanity's savior, embracing his teachings of love, compassion, forgiveness, and redemption (Gonzalez, 2022).

Influence of Christian Parents' on moral development of their Children

The weighty responsibilities placed upon Christian parents to embody virtuous behavior and ethical conduct in their daily lives is deeply ingrained in their understanding of child development. Children, as keen observers, naturally emulate the behaviors and attitudes they witness in their parents, making the demonstration of qualities such as love, honesty, humility, forgiveness, and integrity pivotal in shaping the moral foundation of their offspring. Through their actions and words, Christian parents serve as living examples, providing tangible models of virtuous living for their children to follow. Consistent exhibition of love, honesty, humility, forgiveness, and integrity creates a nurturing environment where these values are not only taught but also deeply ingrained through continuous observation and practice. The significance of parental modeling in shaping the moral character of children is evident from research (Clark, 2017). As children observe these virtues embodied in their parents' lives, they internalize these principles, forming the bedrock upon which their own moral compasses are constructed. This

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process unfolds naturally, with children naturally gravitating towards behaviors and attitudes they perceive as admirable and worthy of emulation.

Furthermore, parental modeling influences the formation of core values, attitudes, and beliefs that guide children's decision-making processes throughout their lives. By consistently upholding virtuous behavior, Christian parents not only cultivate a moral foundation within their children but also instill a lifelong commitment to values reflective of their faith and convictions. In essence, the role of Christian parents as exemplars of virtuous living is indispensable in shaping the moral character and spiritual development of their children. Through their steadfast commitment to embodying love, honesty, humility, forgiveness, and integrity, parents lay the groundwork for a legacy of righteousness and integrity that transcends generations (Cook & Kuhn, 2020).

According to Claeys (2020), parents bear a profound responsibility in imparting the rich teachings of the Bible to their children, nurturing their spiritual growth and comprehension. This task extends beyond mere instruction; it involves a deliberate and comprehensive approach to conveying the beliefs, values, and doctrines inherent in the Christian faith. At the core of this responsibility lies the guidance provided by parents in assisting their children to grasp the narratives, commandments, and principles elucidated within the Scriptures. Through intentional efforts, parents elucidate the significance of biblical passages, relating them to daily life and underscoring their moral and spiritual implications.

A key aspect of this process is the establishment of regular family devotions, which serve as a cornerstone for collective worship, reflection, and Scripture study within the familial context. These moments of communal engagement foster a sense of unity and shared spiritual growth, emphasizing the significance of faith within the family unit. Moreover, dedicated Bible study sessions provide a platform for deeper exploration and understanding of the Scriptures, enabling parents to delve into theological concepts and facilitate meaningful discussions with their children. Through such interactions, children not only gain knowledge of biblical teachings but also cultivate critical thinking skills and a discerning approach to interpreting spiritual truths (Chowdhury, 2019).

Crucially, fostering open and honest discussions about faith-related topics creates an atmosphere of inquiry and exploration, where children feel empowered to express their thoughts, questions, and uncertainties. In this context, parents serve as trusted guides, offering insights and perspectives that facilitate their children's spiritual development (Chowdhury, 2018). This approach emphasizes the multifaceted nature of transmitting spiritual knowledge from parents to children, necessitating dedication, patience, and intentionality. Through prioritizing regular family devotions, engaging in meaningful Bible study, and encouraging open dialogue about matters of faith, parents play an indispensable role in equipping their children with a strong foundation rooted in the teachings of the Bible.

Christian parents are urged to cultivate a nurturing environment imbued with the spirit of prayer and worship within the familial sphere. This deliberate emphasis on communal spiritual practices serves as a cornerstone in fostering children's personal connection with the divine and nurturing their spiritual growth. A pivotal aspect of this endeavor is the practice of communal prayer, where families gather to collectively seek guidance, express gratitude, and intercede on behalf of one another (Chen, 2016). Through shared prayer experiences, children learn the significance of communication with God and witness the transformative power of collective supplication. Additionally, active participation in worship services, whether at home or in congregational settings, provides another avenue for children to engage with their faith on a deeper level. By joining their parents in praise, worship, and the study of Scripture, children develop a heightened appreciation for the sacred and cultivate a profound sense of reverence for the divine (Campbell & Winterich, 2018).

Methodology

The researcher adopted a descriptive survey research design and the target population is Christian parents from urban and rural areas. The Population of the study consists 1636,388 Christian parents during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina State, a sample size of five hundred and sixty-seven (567) parents were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling techniques. Structural questionnaire as the instrument was used for data collection. A total of five hundred and seventy-six (576) copies of the vetted questionnaire were distributed to the respondents randomly selected from nine (9) L.G.A and five hundred and sixty-seven (567) copies representing 98.7 % were duly filled and returned. *Mean scores and standard deviation were used to answer research questions. While; t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.* The vetted questionnaire was administered by the researcher with the help of a Research Assistance.

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Presentation of Result

The results of the data from the questionnaire are presented below, following the analysis of the responses of the respondents.

Research Question 1: What is the extent of parental influence on Children’s moral development among Christian parents in Katsina State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Opinions of the respondents on the extent of parental influence on Children’s moral development among Christian parents in Katsina State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
1	Parents are responsible for instilling moral values such as honesty, kindness, empathy, and respect in their children.	119	371	66	13	3.05	0.64
2	Parents introduce their children to spiritual principles, beliefs, and practices, helping them develop a sense of connection to something greater than themselves.	202	264	79	24	3.13	0.80
3	Parents model ethical behavior and demonstrate the values they wish to instill in their children through their own actions.	312	230	17	10	3.48	0.64
4	Encourage their children to be compassionate towards others and to demonstrate generosity by sharing their time, resources, and talents.	186	225	107	51	2.96	0.93
5	Teach their Children to manage their emotions in healthy ways.	159	328	79	3	3.13	0.65
6	Encourage their children to think critically about moral and spiritual issues, helping them develop their own beliefs and values.	241	210	51	67	3.10	0.99
7	Providing guidance and encouragement as they navigate life's challenges and questions of faith.	170	318	25	56	3.06	0.86
8	Create a safe and nurturing environment in which their children can explore their beliefs and values without fear of judgment or harm.	304	185	75	5	3.38	0.74
9	Teach their children to take responsibility for their actions and to be accountable for the consequences of those actions.	411	106	7	45	3.55	0.86
10	Help their children develop a sense of purpose and meaning in life, guiding them towards goals and activities that align with their values and beliefs.	361	173	24	11	3.55	0.67
Cumulative						3.24	0.78

Decision mean = 2.50

Results in table 1 reveal respondents’ views on the extent of parental influence on Children’s moral development among Christian parents in Katsina State, Nigeria. The responses in (item 1) show that parents are responsible for instilling moral values such as honesty, kindness, empathy, and respect in their children. Those who agreed were 119 and 371 respondents. On the contrary, 66 and 13 respondents disagreed with the view, attracting the mean response of 3.05 and standard deviation of 0.64. Respondents also observed that parents introduce their children to spiritual principles, beliefs, and practices, helping them develop a sense of connection to something greater than themselves (item 2). Those who agreed were 202 and 264 respondents. In contrast, 79 and 24 respondents disagreed with the view, attracting a mean of 3.13 with standard deviation of 0.80. Again, the respondents observed that parents model ethical behavior and demonstrate the values they wish to instill in their children through their own actions (item 3). Those who agreed were 312 and 230 respondents. On the contrary, 17 and 10 respondents disagreed with the view, attracting a mean of 3.48 with standard deviation of 0.64.

Respondents expressed the opinion that encourages their children to be compassionate towards others and to demonstrate generosity by sharing their time, resources, and talents (item 4). Those who agreed were 186 and 225 respondents. On the contrary, 107 and 51 respondents disagreed with the view, attracting the highest mean of 2.96 with standard deviation

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of 0.93. Respondents' views also indicated that Christian parents teach their children to manage their emotions in healthy ways. (item 5). Those who agreed were 159 and 328 respondents. In contrast, 79 and 3 respondents disagreed with the view, attracting a mean of 3.13 with standard deviation of 0.65. Respondents' views further revealed that parents encourage their children to think critically about moral and spiritual issues, helping them develop their own beliefs and values (item 6). Those who agreed were 241 and 210 respondents. In contrast, 51 and 67 respondents disagreed with the view, attracting a mean of 3.10 with standard deviation of 0.99. The respondents' based on their views observed that parents providing guidance and encouragement as they navigate life's challenges and questions of faith (item 7). Those who agreed were 170 and 318 respondents. In contrast, 25 and 56 respondents disagreed with the view, attracting a mean of 3.06 with standard deviation of 0.86.

Respondents' views revealed that parents create a safe and nurturing environment in which their children can explore their beliefs and values without fear of judgment or harm (Item 8). Those who agreed were 304 and 185 respondents. On the contrary, 75 and 5 respondents disagreed with the view, attracting the mean of 3.38 with standard deviation of 0.74. Also, the respondents observed that parents teach their children to take responsibility for their actions and to be accountable for the consequences of those actions (item 9). Those who agreed were 411 and 106 respondents. In contrast, 7 and 45 respondents disagreed with the view, attracting a mean of 3.55 with standard deviation of 0.86. Respondents' views further revealed that parents help their children develop a sense of purpose and meaning in life, guiding them towards goals and activities that align with their values and beliefs (item 10). Those who agreed were 361 and 173 respondents. In contrast, 24 and 11 respondents disagreed with the view, attracting a mean of 3.55 with standard deviation of 0.67.

The cumulative mean in table 06 is 3.24 which is higher than the decision mean of 2.50, while the standard deviation was 0.78. This implies that, parents had great influence on moral development of their children in Katsina state, Nigeria. This is because, parents are responsible for instilling moral values such as honesty, kindness, empathy, and respect in their children, parents introduce their children to spiritual principles, beliefs, and practices, helping them develop a sense of connection to something greater than themselves, parents model ethical behavior and demonstrate the values they wish to instill in their children through their own actions, encourage their children to be compassionate towards others and to demonstrate generosity by sharing their time, resources, and talents, help their children develop emotional intelligence by teaching them to recognize and manage their emotions in healthy ways, encourage their children to think critically about moral issues, helping them develop their own beliefs and values, providing guidance and encouragement as they navigate life's challenges and questions of faith, create a safe and nurturing environment in which their children can explore their beliefs and values without fear of judgment or harm, teach their children to take responsibility for their actions and to be accountable for the consequences of those actions and help their children develop a sense of purpose and meaning in life, guiding them towards goals and activities that align with their values and beliefs.

Conclusion

The present study focused on the assessment of parental influence on Children's moral development among Christian parents in Katsina State, Nigeria. The data collected and analyzed produced an interesting outcome. The findings that emanate from this study revealed that Christian parents teach their children to take responsibility for their actions and to be accountable for the consequences of those actions.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, of this study, the following recommendation was made:

Christian Parents should create a home environment that encourages accountability and responsibility through positive reinforcement and appropriate consequences.

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Reference

- Alvarado, R. (2023). *Understanding Christianity: A Comprehensive Overview*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Campbell, M. C., & Winterich, K. P. (2018). A framework for the consumer psychology of morality in the marketplace. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 28(2), 167–179.
- Chen, M. F. (2016). Extending the theory of planned behavior model to explain people’s energy savings and carbon reduction behavioral intentions to mitigate climate change in Taiwan—Moral obligation matters. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 112, 1746–1753.
- Chowdhury, R. M. (2018). Religiosity and voluntary simplicity: The mediating role of spiritual well-being. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 152(1), 149–174.
- Chowdhury, R. M. M. I. (2019). The moral foundations of consumer ethics. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 158(3), 585–601.
- Claeys, M. (2020). Green shame: The next moral revolution? *Global Discourse: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Current Affairs*, 10(2), 259–271.
- Clark, C. B., Swails, J. A., Pontinen, H. M., Bowerman, S. E., Kriz, K. A., & Hendricks, P. S. (2017). A behavioral economic assessment of individualizing versus binding moral foundations. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 112, 49–54.
- Cook, W., & Kuhn, K. M. (2020). Off-duty deviance in the eye of the beholder: Implications of moral foundations theory in the age of social media. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 172, 1–16.
- Fivush, R., & Goodnow, J. (2019). Parenthood as a social institution. *Journal of Family Issues*, 40(8), 1095-1113.
- Gonzalez, M. (2022). Jesus Christ: The Savior in Christian Faith. *Journal of Religious Studies*, 45(2), 87-104.
- Miller, J. R. (2016). Parenting styles and their impact on child development: A review of the literature. *Child and Adolescent Mental Health*, 21(3), 141-151.

Assessment of Principals' Commitment to Teachers' Performance Appraisal among Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State

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Abstract

The study assessed the principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal among public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State. Descriptive research design of survey type was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all the 2,372 teachers in the 42 public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government in 2023/2024 academic session. Random sampling technique was used to select 21(50%) out of the 42 schools while 292 teachers were selected out of the 1,205 in the sampled schools, using proportionate sampling technique. Assessment of Principals' Commitment to Teachers' Performance Appraisal' (APCTPA) was used to collect data. Validity of the instrument was done and its reliability test yielded an index of 0.79. The findings of the study revealed that level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State was declared low. Also, gender and years of experience did not cause any significant difference in the teachers' opinions on the level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State. It was recommended that school principals need to be more committed to performance appraisal by personally carrying it out and also charge Vice Principals (Academic), Heads of Department or any experienced teachers within or outside the schools to perform it, so as to improve teachers' job performance.

Key words: Assessment, Principals, Commitment, Teachers, Performance Appraisal

Introduction

Principals play important roles in secondary education and one of such is serving as human resource managers. As managers of human resource, it is their responsibility to ensure that performance of teachers is subjected to periodic appraisal, so as to enhance it and facilitate effective realisation of the school goals. Sunday (2021) stated that school principals need to pay adequate attention to how teachers perform their duties to be able to carry out appraisal on them, for the purpose of determining where they perform rightly and the areas where they perform below the established standard. Seniwoliba (2014), teachers' performance appraisal (PA) as a school principal's role is all-encompassing; it involves identifying, evaluating and developing teachers' work aptitude, so as to improve school performance. It is an imperative to attainment of organizational objectives, and benefits employees in terms of recognition, receiving feedback, catering to work needs, and offering career guidance.

According to Johnson (2018), performance appraisal (PA) is a method of measuring performance of workers in an organisation, so as to ensure that corrections are made where necessary, for the purpose of making their job performance enhance goal achievement. Alice and Oluoch (2019) and Unachukwu and Orji (2021) stated that PA refers to the act of assessing a teacher's performance. It fosters objective skill evaluation and adherence to the established rules. Obisi (2018) opined that PA of workers is an important aspect of human resource management and it is used in determining their career advancement

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and also facilitating their effective job performance. Musodza et al. (2020) emphasised that the reason for appraising employees' performance is not limited to enhancing their job satisfaction but also an avenue increasing their professional capacity building and dedication to duties. The finding of the study conducted by Looney (2017) revealed that that job appraisal is a significant way of improving teachers' job performance. Hence, government and principals need to ensure that it is properly carried out in public secondary schools in Nigeria. Mullins (2022) believed that the salient purpose of performance appraisal is to improve the discharge of duties of each worker, thereby resulting to increased output in the performance of the organisation as a whole. Fisher et al. (2018) opined that the role which performance appraisal plays in enhancing effective employees' job performance cannot be over-emphasised. If used properly, it could help in achieving the stated goals but if utilised inappropriately, it could have disastrous effects on employees.

Malik et al. (2021) stressed that the fundamental goal of appraising teachers' job performance is to assist in making their performance more effective. Ajayi (2021) posited that performance appraisal means the process of assessing the performance of employees in order to determine their training needs, for the purpose of assisting organisation to actualise its goals. Riyanto et al. (2021) emphasised that for the established goals to be achieved, educational enterprises need teachers who have good performance and as a result of this, managers need to periodically assess teachers' productivity through effective performance appraisal, so as to determine the areas where need to improve upon. Dal Corso et al., (2020) maintained that PA assists in facilitating good employees' performance, informs managers at the right time of the need for capacity building in certain areas, helps a poorly performing employees and creates compensation and promotion systems to enhance performance. Kareithi (2018) opined that results derived from PA could be used by managers of organisations to make important decisions on pay, retention, promotions, downsizing and termination of employees' appointment, if need arises.

Milimu et al. (2024) maintained that in educational institutions, PA is seen as a continuous process which is embarked upon, so as to detect, measure, and develop performance of teachers in accordance with the goals of Ministry of Education. Ayeni, (2018) stated that the act of appraising performance of employees usually entails formative aspects centering on capacity building, feedback, and performance, purposely focused on enhancing achievement and making quality educational experience available for students. Maxwell and Schwimmer (2016) stressed that performance appraisal of teachers is a duty of principals as school managers, which focuses on value judgment on how strong or weak a teacher's job performance is, using the gathered information to juxtaposes the real work performance with the established performance standards. Mollé et al. (2023) believed that the use of PA in the school system needs proper management, so as to prevent the possibility of wrongness which could lead to reduction in teachers' productivity. Singh and Singh (2020) maintained that PA is an aspect of human resource management which is used for making decisions on important issues relating to employees such as promotion, capacity building through training and retention in the organisation. Arimie and Orobosa (2023) emphasised that the process of appraising performance of workers has to be fair, highlighting clearly defined objectives, assessments, feedback for evaluated employees, and performance-boosting plans, so as to achieve overall productivity in organisation. Gbadamosi (2024) opined that performance appraisal is a method used by principals for improving outcomes and overseeing performance of teachers in schools. The purpose is to connect the school goals with the aspirations of each teacher aspirations, in order to make his or her performance conforms to the student academic needs.

Statement of the Research Problem

Principals as the general overseers of secondary schools stand in the position of personally appraising or ensuring that performance of teachers under them are appraised by some designated staff from within or outside the schools, for the purpose of determining their areas of strength and weakness, so that necessary professional actions could be taken to remedy the professional errors identified. However, observations of the researchers and information derived from teachers in some schools showed that some school principals, on daily basis, utilise virtually all official hours inside their offices without earmarking specific time to meet teachers in classrooms, for the purpose of appraising their job performance. Not only that, they seem not bother to charge vice principals (Academic), Heads of Departments or experienced teachers to perform same on their behalf, so as to improve teachers' job performance. This could hinder not only the realisation of effective teachers' job performance but also overall school goals.

Many studies which are related to this study had been conducted. To mention but few, Gbadamosi (2024) conducted a study on the use of performance appraisal and reward system in enhancing employee performance in secondary schools: A case study of public secondary schools in Delta State. Milimu et al. (2024) investigated the influence of teacher performance appraisal and development tool on job satisfaction among teachers in public secondary schools in Keiyo North Sub-County, Kenya. James and Olayiwola (2022) examined the impacts of performance appraisal on teachers' job performance in secondary

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schools in Kebbi State. Alarape (2020) carried out a study on the performance appraisal and teachers' effectiveness in Kogi West Senatorial District, Kogi State. However, none of the study mentioned above specifically focused on assessment of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal among public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State; hence, this is the observed academic lacuna which this study was set out to fill.

Objectives of the study

The study:

1. examined the level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State;
2. investigated the difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' gender; and
3. determined the difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' years of experience; and

Research Questions

The following research question was raised.

- iv. What is the level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State?

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated in the study.

1. **H₀₁:** There is no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' gender.
2. **H₀₂:** There is no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' years of experience.

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive research design of survey type. All the 2,372 teachers in the 42 public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government Area constituted population of the study. Through the use of random sampling technique, 21 schools which represented 50% of the entire school population were selected. Proportionate sampling technique was used to select 292 teachers out of the 1,205 teachers in the sampled schools, using Krejcie and Morgan table for sample size determination. A questionnaire designed by the researchers, titled 'Assessment of Principals' Commitment to Teachers' Performance Appraisal' (APCTPA) was used to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaire, which contained 10 items, was validated by three experts in the fields of Educational Management and Test and Measurement. This was done in order to ensure the face and content validity of the questionnaire. Through the use of split-half method, thirty copies of the questionnaire were administered to 30 teachers drawn from the schools which were not used in the study. The data gathered were analysed using Cronbach's Alpha and a reliability index of 0.79 was obtained. This confirmed suitability of the instrument for use in the study. Three of the researchers and two research assistants visited the sampled schools to administer questionnaire to the respondents. Each copy of the questionnaire was collected immediately after filling. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research question, t-test was used to test hypothesis one while Analysis of Variance was used to test hypothesis two. Any mean score not up to 2.50 was adjudged 'Low' while the mean score from 2.50 and above was considered 'High'. Out of the 292 copies of the questionnaire distributed for administration, only 263 copies returned were used for analysis.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State?

Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer research question one.

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Table 1: Level of Principals' Commitment to Teachers' Performance Appraisal in Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	educates teachers on the meaning and importance of performance appraisal, to be able to understand its benefits to them	2.39	.72	Low
2.	periodically conducts performance appraisal on teachers, for the purpose of detecting their areas of strength and weakness	2.26	.61	Low
3.	gives teachers feedback on the outcome of the performance appraisal carried out on them, for them to know the areas of their strengths and weaknesses	2.22	.45	Low
4.	delegates authority to the Vice Principal (Academic) or Head of your Department to periodically appraise your job performance on his or her behalf	2.64	.90	High
5.	ensures that the Vice Principal (Academic) or Head of your Department gives teachers feedback on the outcome of the appraisal conducted on them	2.50	.66	High
6.	uses information derived from performance appraisal to make to make important decisions on teachers	1.51	.68	Low
7.	makes teachers to understand that performance appraisal is a way of assisting and motivating them for effective job performance	2.17	.40	Low
8.	within his or her capacity, provides professional support so as to improve the area(s) of weakness observed in teachers during performance appraisal	1.98	.57	Low
9.	recommends teachers for capacity building programme(s) based on the need(s) identified in them during performance appraisal	1.92	.43	Low
10.	possesses professional skills to effectively conduct performance appraisal for teachers	2.70	1.11	High
	Total	2.27	.65	Low

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 1 presented the level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State. As shown on the table, items 1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8 and 9 (educates teachers on the meaning and importance of performance appraisal, to be able to understand its benefits to them, periodically conducts performance appraisal on teachers, for the purpose of detecting their areas of strength and weakness, gives teachers feedback on the outcome of the performance appraisal carried out on them, for them to know the areas of their strengths and weaknesses, uses information derived from performance appraisal to make to make important decisions on teachers, makes teachers to understand that performance appraisal is a way of assisting and motivating them for effective job performance, within his or her capacity, provides professional support so as to improve the area(s) of weakness observed in teachers during performance appraisal and recommends teachers for capacity building programme(s) based on the need(s) identified in them during performance appraisal) had mean scores: 2.39, 2.26, 2.22, 1.51, 2.21, 1.98 and 1.92 respectively and such declared 'Low'. Also, item 4, 5 and 10 (delegates authority to the Vice Principal (Academic) or Head of your Department to periodically appraise your job performance on his or her behalf, ensures that the Vice Principal (Academic) or Head of your Department gives teachers feedback on the outcome of the appraisal conducted on them and possesses professional skills to effectively conduct performance appraisal for teachers) had mean scores: 2.64, 2.50 and 2.72; hence, adjudged 'High'. Therefore, with the mean score of 2.27, level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State was declared low.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' gender.

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T-test was used to test hypothesis one.

Table 2: T-test Showing the Difference in the Significant Difference in Level of Principals' Commitment to Teachers' Performance Appraisal in Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State Based on Teachers' Gender

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	p-value	Decision
Male	119	2.14	.61	2.27	.066	Ho ₁ Accepted
Female	144	2.40	.79			

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 2 showed the calculated t-value (2.27), mean difference of 0.14 and the p-value (0.66) which is greater than the significance level (0.05). Hence, hypothesis two was rejected. This shows that there was no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' gender.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' years of experience.

Analysis of Variance was used to test hypothesis two.

Table 3: ANOVA Analysis Showing the Difference in the Significant Difference in Level of Principals' Commitment to Teachers' Performance Appraisal in Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State Based on Teachers' Years of Experience

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	Cal. F-ratio	p-value	Decision
Between Groups	13.224	3	.331	2.29	.065	Ho ₂ Accepted
Within Groups	16.117	260	.147			
Total	29.331	263				

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 3 shows the cal. F-ratio (2.29) and the p-value (.065) that is greater than the level of significance (0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis two (Ho₂) was accepted. This shows that there was no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' gender.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State was low. This finding agrees with the finding of James and Olayiwola (2022) which revealed that the level of principals' dedication to performance appraisal of teachers in secondary schools in Kebbi State was low. This finding is also in tandem with the position of Johnson (2018) that many principals in public secondary school in Nigeria do not prioritise appraisal of teachers in their schools and this might be the reason for ineffective job performance of teachers.

The finding of the study showed that there was no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' gender. This finding supports the finding of Alarape (2020) which showed that there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female teachers on the principals' dedication to performance appraisal of teachers in Kogi West Senatorial District, Kogi State. This finding corroborates the finding of Sunday (2021) which showed that male and female teachers were not significantly different in their opinions on the commitment of principals to teachers' performance appraisal in Lagos State secondary schools.

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The finding of the study showed that there was no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' years of experience. This finding is in consonance with the finding of Alarape (2020) which showed that there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female teachers on the principals' dedication to performance appraisal of teachers in Kogi West Senatorial District, Kogi State.

Conclusion

The study concluded that level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State was declared low. Also, gender and years of experience did not cause any significant difference in the teachers' opinions on the level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State.

Recommendations

The study recommended that:

- i. school principals need to be more committed to performance appraisal by personally carrying it out and also charge Vice Principals (Academic), Heads of Department or any experienced teachers within or outside the schools to perform it, so as to improve teachers' job performance;
- iv. there is need to ensure that teachers are given feedback on the performance appraisal carried out on them, for the purpose of knowing the areas of their strength and weakness and improve where necessary, so as to facilitate actualisation of the school goals; and
- v. Ministry of Education should periodically organise capacity building for principals, so as to make them acquire more skills on how to properly appraise job performance of teachers, for the purpose of enhancing their performance and school goals.

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References

- Ajayi, K. (2021). Military regimes and Nigerian public administration. In F. Omotosho (ed.). *Contemporary Issues in Public Administration*. Bolabay Publications.
- Alarape, K. I. (2020). Performance appraisal and Capacity building as predictors of teachers' job performance in Kogi West Senatorial District, Kogi State. *Journal of Counselling Education*, 2(2), 67-74.
- Alice, A. O., & Oluoch, M. F. (2019). Influence of performance appraisal on motivation of public secondary school teachers in Gem-sub County, Kenya. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 9(4), 39-49.
- Arimie, C. J., & Orobosa, A. I. (2023). Employee performance appraisal and career advancement in Nigerian public organisations: An explicatory review, *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 24(1), 254-263.
- Ayeni, A. J. (2018). Teachers' professional ethics and instructional performance as correlates of students' academic performance in secondary schools in Owo Local Government, Ondo State, Nigeria. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 5(8), 611-622.
- Dal Corso, L., De Carlo, A., Carluccio, F., Colledani, D., & Falco, A. (2020). Employee burnout and positive dimensions of well-being: A latent workplace spirituality profile analysis. *PLoS ONE*, 15(11), 45-53.
- Fisher, C. D., Schoenfeldt, L.F., & Shaw, J.B. (2018). *Human resources management* (5th Ed.). Boston, Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Gbadamosi, R. A. (2024). The use of performance appraisal and reward system in enhancing employee performance in secondary schools: A case study of public secondary schools in Delta State. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research* 12(4), 34-41.
- Johnson, B. P. (2018). *Effective performance appraisal: A review, implications, recommendations and case study*. Unpublished Thesis.
- Kareithi, M. W. (2018). *Effect of performance appraisal system on performance of secondary schools' teachers in Kirinyaga West sub-county, Kenya*. Unpublished Master's degree thesis, School of Business at KCA University, Kenya.
- Krejciec, R. V. & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Table for determining sample size from a given population. *Education and Psychological Measurement*, 607-610.

Assessment of Principals' Commitment... (Sulyman, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15026553>

- Looney, J. (2017). Developing high-quality teachers: teacher evaluation for improvement. *European Journal of Education, 46*(4), 440-455.
- Maxwell, B. & Schwimmer, M. (2016). Professional Ethics Education for Future Teachers: A Narrative Review of the Scholarly Writings. *Journal of Moral Education, 45*(3), 354–371.
- Milimu, C. A., Atoni, R., & Kimotho, M. (2024). Influence of teacher performance appraisal and development tool on job satisfaction among teachers in public secondary schools in Keiyo North Sub-County, Kenya. *Global Scientific and Academic Research Journal of Education and Literature, 2*(7), 49-52.
- Mollel, E. R., Mulongo, L. S., & Razia M. (2023). The influence of performance appraisal practices on employee productivity: A case of Muheza District, Tanzania. *Issues in Business Matters and Economics, 11*(2), 45-53.
- Mullins, L. J., (2022). *Management and organisational behaviour* (5th Ed.). Financial Times Pitman Publishing.
- Musodza, B. R., Runhare, T. Mpeta, M., & Ciske, E. N. (2020). Influence of timing in introducing teacher performance evaluation on effective outcomes: The case of one Education District in Zimbabwe. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies, 9*(6), 18-33.
- Obisi, C. (2018). Employee performance appraisal and its implication for individual and Organizational growth. *Australian Journal of Business and management, 1*(9), 92-97.
- Riyanto, S., Endri, E., & Herlissha, N. (2021). Effect of work motivation and job satisfaction on employee performance: Mediating role of employee engagement. *Problems and Perspectives in Management, 19*, 162-174.
- Olayiwola, D. L. (2022). Teachers' perception on the impacts of principals' performance appraisal of on school effectiveness in Kogi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education, 2*(1), 34-42.
- Seniwoliba, J. (2014). Assessing the performance appraisal concept of the local government service in Ghana. *African Journal of Business Management, 8*(15), 597- 611.
- Singh S. K., & Singh A. P. (2019). Interplay of organizational justice, psychological empowerment, organizational citizenship behavior, and job satisfaction in the context of circular economy. *Management Decision 57*, 937-952.
- Sunday, O. R. (2021). Teachers' perception on the principals' effectiveness in performance appraisal in secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. Principals to teachers' performance appraisal in Lagos State secondary schools. *Journal of Science Education and Technology, 5*(2), 67-73.
- Unachukwu, G. O., & Orji, F. O. (2021). Relationship between staff performance appraisal and reward practices adopted by principals and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Anambra state, Nigeria. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies, 8*(5), 114-120.

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Assessment of Traditional Maternal Health Care Service Delivery among Health Centres in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

It is believed a huge percentage of women's that are maternal wellbeing services seekers in Nigeria believe more in and give preference to traditional (indigenous and faith-based) maternal health services which is a major factor of high maternal mortality in the country. Hence, this study examine assessment of traditional maternal health care service delivery among health centres in Southwest, Nigeria. The design for this study was descriptive survey research. The population of the study comprised all traditional birth attendants who own traditional maternity healthcare centres (TMHCs) in Southwestern Nigeria. The sample size of 30 traditional birth attendant's owner were selected from the target population using purposive sampling technique. A self-designed key Informant Interview (KII) guide was used to gather elicited information from the respondents. The instrument was assessed by experts in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology for instrument's validity while Inter-coder and intra-coder was to test the internal reliability. Data was analyzed using content analysis. The results shows that traditional maternal health care centres comprised informal and semi-formal birth delivery experts with several years of experience. Their primary goal were birth delivery, spiritual services and education/health talks, prayer and deliverance sessions (spiritual services). The study revealed that both the poor and the rich, educated and non-educated patronize TMHCs. The study concluded that patronage of traditional maternal services is an inclined component to high maternal mortality in the study Area. It is recommended that Policy review of TMHCs training programmes, and increased collaboration between Morden healthcare facilities and TMHCs should all be done to encourage community support for TBAs practices.

Keywords: Faith-based, Traditional maternal healthcare, Indigenous, Preference

Introduction

The need for healthcare services during pregnancy is influenced by a variety of factors, some of which may be related to the woman's social standing, culture, or religious beliefs. Making decisions is an essential part of being a woman. Women lose their lives during pregnancy and childbirth, particularly in developing nations where access to healthcare is still limited. Every year, problems associated with pregnancy or childbirth cause the deaths of about 600,000 women worldwide (World Health Organization, 2020). The vast majority of maternal fatalities take place in underdeveloped nations mostly Asia and sub-Saharan Africa. Lower- and middle-income countries (LMICs) have higher rates of maternal and neonatal mortality; Nigeria is among these nations with the highest rates of maternal mortality worldwide. According to Tukur et al. (2022), the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) in Nigeria was expected to be 512 deaths per 100,000 live births in 2018 and above 800 maternal deaths per 100,000 live births in 2019, with a neonatal mortality rate of 33 per 1000 live births.(Nasir et al. 2022). The global stakeholders' initiatives put in place in reducing maternal mortality had not resulted in the anticipated drop in maternal mortality, leading the WHO to give Nigeria a "No progress" rating (Punch Newspaper, 2022)

According to the Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2018), 70% of maternal mortalities in Nigeria are caused by behavior of mothers seeking healthcare and the type of maternal health care been patronised by the pregnant women. The rise in maternal mortalities' in Nigeria is due to several factors, including a lack of maternal health infrastructure, significant delays in seeking care, proximity and access to healthcare facilities, obtaining proper care upon arrival, and referral delays (Ogu & Ephraim-Emmanuel, 2018; Catherine et al. 2019). Unfortunately, the causes listed above not include the actual type of

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healthcare system being patronised by pregnant women. This is because, like other African countries, people in Nigeria have and seek options between modern (orthodox or conventional) and traditional (indigenous and faith-based) health care systems for various health services including maternal health services (James et al. 2018; Ozioma & Chinwe, 2019). As evident in Sub-Saharan Africa, a high proportion of women still prefer to undertake self-care at home or patronise traditional attendants that provide traditional maternal care services (Magdalena & Murphy-Lawless, 2017; WHO, 2018). Such traditional health care services involve traditional medicine (plants, animals, mineral substances and certain methods) which is the sum total of knowledge, skills and practices based on assumptions, beliefs and experiences indigenous to different cultures whether explicable or not used in the maintenance of health as well as in the treatment of illness (WHO, 2015)

Traditional maternal wellbeing upkeep consists of traditional birth attendants (TBAs) who are the main practitioners that render antenatal care and oversee the delivery of pregnant women who patronise them. A birth attendants aids the woman during labour and learned her profession by bearing children of her own or with the help of other birth attendants. The majority of TBAs are women. TBAs and religion homes, for example, supervise 60–85 percent of deliveries in Nigeria, particularly in rural areas. As a result, they hold an important place in the public health system (International Maternal & Child Health Care, 2017). Following the existence of a variety of maternal health service shortcomings in Nigeria, such as lack of free antenatal care, lack of trained delivery assistants, and the unavailability of resources, the maternal health status remains fragile, as evidenced by the current maternal death ratios (Ogu & Ephraim-Emmanuel, 2018). Although the proportion is unknown, it is believed that a huge percentage of females that are maternal wellbeing service seekers in Nigeria believe more in and give preference to traditional (indigenous and faith-based) maternal health services. Therefore, it is imperative that we focus our attention on finding the answers to this disturbing issue in order to provide information regarding the prevention and decrease of maternal mortality in Nigeria. Particularly Target 3.1, which calls for a reduction in the number of maternal deaths worldwide to less than 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030.

Objective of the study

1. Assess the profiles of traditional maternal health care centres in Southwest, Nigeria
2. Assess maternal health care service delivery in Southwest, Nigeria

Research question

1. What are the profiles of traditional maternal health care centres in Southwest, Nigeria?
2. What is the nature of maternal health care service delivery in Southwest, Nigeria?

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive design approach. All traditional birth attendants who own traditional maternity healthcare centres (TMHCs) in Southwestern Nigeria were included in the research. The sample size of 30 traditional birth attendants who own a centre were included in the study. A multi-stage sampling procedure was used. Three (3) states were chosen from a total of six (6) in Southwest Nigeria using a simple random sampling technique. Using a basic random sampling approach, one Senatorial District (SD) was chosen from each state sampled. Three (3) Local Government Areas (LGAs) were selected from each senatorial region using a simple random selection procedure. Ten (10) TMHCs (totalling 30) were sampled in each of the identified LGAs using simple random sampling technique. In each of the TMHCs selected, one TMHCs was sampled using a convenience sample method. A self-designed key Informant Interview (KII) guide was used to gather information from the respondents. The instrument was assessed by two professors from the Department of Kinesiology, Health Education, and Recreation, one professor in obstetrics and gynecology to check for instrument. Validity was done through trustworthiness and credibility. Intercoder and intracoder were to test the internal reliability of the qualitative data. Multiple coders individually coded the data before working together to fine-tune their recommended puzzles and thematic patterns. In addition, field feedback was gathered, and the researcher employed a qualitative research expert to serve as an external auditor and ensure reliability. All decisions taken during the research study, from the study objectives to the reporting of results, are described to ensure conformability, and examples of data to back up observations and results are provided. Ethical consideration

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is of importance to this study and was observed. Written agreement was obtained from the research participants (who were the selected TBAs). The study participants were requested to sign a consent form contained in each questionnaire and interview guide. Confidentiality of the information was also be ensured during statistical analysis and discussion of outcomes as contained in the consent form. The Institute of Public Health at Obafemi Awolowo University in Ile-Ife, Nigeria, provided the ethical (IPH/OAU/12/1903) clearance for this study. Data was analysis using content analysis

Results

Research question 1. What are the profiles of traditional maternal health care centres in Southwest, Nigeria?

Themes Generation and Code Linkage through Deductive and Inductive Approach

Themes	Subthemes	Codes	Quotation
Profile of TMHCs	Faith-based TMHCs	Education	<i>...I was trained in mission school and advice to take some courses related to it...</i>
		Centre ownership	<i>...Owner by the church...</i>
	Apprenticeship-based TMHCs	Governmental registration	<i>...Yes, it is government approved...</i>
		Training Partnership and Collaboration	<i>...I was trained by Iya abiye... ... I learnt the Job by working with Iya abiye.....</i>
Services of TMHCC	Antenatal	Inherited skills	<i>I inherited this work from my parents and have also improved on my own...</i>
		Antenatal	<i>.. antenatal days are on Tuesdays. At least eight persons in a week...</i>
		Spiritual services	<i>... there is no special service that we render except for the prayers that we pray for them. Omi adura...</i>
	Antenatal	Counselling	<i>... we take good care of them, we counsel them, and we pray for them...</i>
		Education	<i>... firstly, we teach them the word of God, educate them about their health; we take care of them both physically and spiritually....</i>
	Birth Delivery	Birth delivery	<i>... there are times in a month I take delivery of five people...</i>
		Referral	<i>... The ones I know I can't handle I refer them such as low blood, placenta profile...</i>
	Post-natal	Spiritual services	<i>... after successful delivery we do pray for the baby and mother again...</i>
Education/orientation		<i>... we take care of bleeding and teach them how to take care of the baby and how to get immuniazation from primary healthcare...</i>	

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Research Question One: What are the profiles of traditional maternal health care centres in Southwest, Nigeria?

Profile of Traditional Maternal Health Care Centres

The result indicated that traditional maternal health care centres are registered with the government. It was observed that traditional maternal health care centres comprised informal and semi-formal birth delivery experts with several years of experience. Their primary goal were birth delivery, spiritual services and education. Two structural patterns were observed and formed the profile of traditional maternal health care centres in Southwestern Nigeria. These patterns were divided into two based on similar features and events on the field or during the interview sessions. The structural patterns were faith-based traditional maternal health care centres and apprenticeship-based-traditional profiles.

Faith-Based Traditional Maternal Health Care Profiles

One distinctive feature of faith-based traditional maternal health care profiles is that they are owned by a religious organisation registered with the government. There are three primary elements of the faith-based traditional maternal healthcare system: skilled birth attendants, enabling environments, and referral systems. It was also observed that their operation revolves around skilled birth attendants, often called "Iya Abiye". Iya abiyes had several experiences in birth delivery ranging from fifteen-fifty years. The interview sessions with "Iya abiye" revealed that they do have less cases of maternal mortality is occurs rarely. However, once they are faced with complication provision, they were made through referral to a state general hospital or any close-by hospitals. Despite this, there were cases of stillbirth. Through outreach by religious organisations like Christ Apostolic Church (C.A.C.) and Nasrul-Lahi-il Fathi Society of Nigeria (NASFAT), faith-based traditional maternal health provides essential maternal and new-born care services all through delivery and ongoing community care development. In Southwestern Nigeria, facilities of the traditional profile are located within the religious organisation environment, either in a mission home or next to the worship area. Report of the key informant interview (KII) guide conducted with personnel providing TMHCs on services in the study area and services render for pregnant women using their facilities (number of years spent in service delivery, number of delivery, number of maternal deaths, and type of services rendered)

Evidently:

R: none. But we have had 2 still births (Osun D2-3)

R: there are times in a month I take delivery of five people. Ever since I have started this job, I have taken delivery for many people. There are times in a year I take about fifty to sixty deliveries. So I cannot give a specific number of deliveries I have taken since I started this work because they are many (Ondo D1-4)

R: as a maternity home, we pray for them, which is the first. We train them on matters about their health and after we take delivery (Oyo D3-6)

R: There is a time that seems I cannot handle the situation; I will take them to the hospital. Because when doctors came to train us, they have told us if we cannot handle the situation we should refer to them (Ondo D1-5)

R: The ones I know I cannot handle I refer them such as low blood, placenta profile, damages (Oyo D3-2)

R: there is no special service that we render except for the prayers that we pray for them (Ondo D1-7)

R: 30 years ago. (Oyo D3-2)

R: 15 years ago (Osun D2-8)

Apprenticeship-Based Traditional Healthcare Profiles

This profile is based on individual training with "Iya abiye". This training entails passing down the skill of birth attendants through mentoring. These individuals work closely with "Iya abiye" and attend training seminars organized by the Federal and State health ministry and hospitals. They also aid "Iya abiye" with birth delivery and spiritual deliverance/services. It was observed that most of these apprenticeships were graduates from the training and either went into mobile services to aid home delivery. They are also equally invited to address complications by "Iya abiye" after graduation. Apprenticeships rely on the existing chain of referral systems created during training. When faced with complications, they used the same referral system used by "Iya abiye". They also have association meetings held every Wednesday to address their challenges and way

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further. However, most apprenticeships developed their skill through training as auxiliary nurses. The rationale was to avoid issues with the health authorities.

Illustratively:

R: I inherited this work from my parents and also on my own have gained and acquired added knowledge to this job. In short, I can say I have been doing this job for 50 years. (OYO D3-9)

R: I learn the Job by working with Iya abiye and I graduate due to some form of enmity and threat with government and registration I had to enrol for some courses as auxiliary nurse. (OSUN D2-10)

R: I learn the act through mentoring and working closely with mummy. I practically learn everything from that mission house though now I do more of mobile home delivery... (Ondo D1-8)

Research Question Two: What is the nature of maternal health care service delivery in Southwest, Nigeria?

Services of Traditional Maternal Health Care

There are several services offered by traditional maternal health care. Some essential services rendered were birth delivery, spiritual deliverance and referral. The other function included: antenatal care, pregnancy education, and post-natal care. However, a substantial number of people patronize these services though the emphasis is on the spiritual aspect and affordability. Thus, not only the poor or those who cannot afford hospital bills patronize them. The well to do patronize them as well, and it is because of the spiritual deliverance services rendered. The quotation also revealed that it is a voluntary service to humanity because they must provide materials for the mother and new-born.

Evidently:

R: as a maternity home, we pray for them, which is the first. We train them on matters about their health and after we take delivery (Ondo D1-5)

R: firstly we teach them the word of God, expose them about their health; we take care of them both physically and spiritually. Thereafter we take the delivery (Ondo D1-6)

R: we do antenatal, training for them on type of food to eat, what to do in the house. We test them; check the baby's heartbeat and the state of health condition for the mother. (Osun D2-6)

R: when they come, the first thing we do is that we pray, sing songs that entertains and full of exercise for body warm-up (Oyo D3-2)

R: they come because of the prayers we offer to God and we get answers. As agbebi we won't charge them. We have some people who delivered and God... (Oyo D3-8)

R: many people have been coming o. we have graduates, people in the street, people in remote areas have been coming here. Both the rich and poor also come here (Ondo D1-1)

R:Number 1, here, we are not harsh on the pregnant women, and we explain how they should take care of themselves... (Osun D2-10)

R: ... And its not because of money, for example, some cases may not allow them deliver in a mission house, when they go to the hospital they will definitely spend money... (Osun D2-9)

R: We refer complicated issues (Oyo D3-9)

These services can be grouped into three based on before, during and after delivery. Thus:

Antenatal services

These are series of activities organized with the goal of preparing the mother for birth delivery. Such activities include education/health talks, prayer and deliverance sessions (spiritual services), counselling via talking about God and having faith in Him. Illustratively:

R: as a maternity home, we pray for them, which is the first. We train them on matters about their health and after we take delivery (Ondo D1-5)

R: firstly we teach them the word of God, expose them about their health; we take care of them both physically and spiritually. Thereafter we take the delivery (Ondo D1-6)

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R: we do antenatal, training for them on type of food to eat, what to do in the house. We test them; check the baby's heartbeat and the state of health condition for the mother. (Osun D2-6)

Birth Delivery

The Iya abiye do the delivery with apprentice aid at time while other members continue to pray for divine intervention. However, preparation is in place in case of complications through the referral system with primary basic healthcare. Evidently:

R: ... some issues are spiritual matters that can only be handle by the iya abiye who had experience about the problem, so referring those patients to the hospital will not help them they will spend money there without result... (Osun D2-9)

R: We refer complicated issues (Oyo D3-9)

Post-natal Services

There are two main activities designed by traditional maternal healthcare after birth delivery were spiritual services and education of mother on how to take care of herself and baby. Illustratively:

R: ...after successful delivery we do pray for the baby and mother again... (Osun D2-9)

R: ...they we take care of bleeding and teach them how to take care of the baby and how to get immunization from primary healthcare... (Ondo D1-1)

Discussion of Findings

The qualitative data revealed that traditional maternal health care centres profile is that they are often owner and run by religious corporate bodies in Nigeria and revolves around a person known as “Iya Abiye”. These persons are highly skill birth attendant with spiritual rite knowledge. This finding was similar to Ayanleke, (2015) and Owojaiye & Kajang, (2015) which also indicated that are pillar in delivery birth services in traditional maternal centres in southwestern Nigeria. These persons also train apprenticeship to ensure continuity of traditional maternal health centres. The have several services such as spiritual deliverance, antenatal, delivery services and post-natal. Thus, these findings provide answers to this study first research questions which aimed at examining the profiles of traditional maternal health carer centres and services they provide. Patronage of these services are often members of these religious bodies or refer by a member of the religious bodies.

The utilization of traditional maternal health care centres in Southwestern Nigeria can be attributed to various factors that encompass cultural, socio-economic, and historical dimensions. *These findings corroborate* Owojaiye & Kajang, (2015); Ogunyomi & Ndikom, (2016) which indicated in their studies that cultural and religious beliefs exert a significant influence on childbirth practices in this region. Traditional maternal health care centres tend to incorporate these beliefs into their practices, making them a preferable option for individuals who value their cultural and religious traditions. Also, the accessibility of these centres is a critical factor as they are typically situated in rural areas and are in proximity to the communities they serve. As a result, & Adeleke & Olorunsola (2018) and Azuh, et al., (2015) further buttress that they do not require long-distance travel, which can be a barrier to accessing modern health care centres. Furthermore, the affordability of traditional maternal health care centres is another significant consideration as they are generally less expensive than modern health care centres. Consequently, they serve as a preferred option for individuals who cannot afford the cost of modern health care. Fourthly, the familiarity factor comes into play, as women tend to be more comfortable with traditional maternal health care centres because of their familiarity with the practices and staff. They perceive the care received to be more personalized and caring. Lastly, this practice is often viewed as the norm and is deeply ingrained in the region's socio-cultural fabric.

Conclusion

The study showed that traditional maternal health care centres are registered with the government, comprise informal and semi-formal birth delivery experts with several years of experience. Their primary goal were birth delivery, spiritual services and education, facilities of the traditional profile are located within the religious organisation environment, either in a mission home or next to the worship area and developed their skill through training as auxiliary nurses.

Limitation of the Study

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This study had only addressed TBAs patronage in Southwest, Nigeria with its precursors, challenges and probable recommendations. However, the Southwest is a geopolitical zone in Nigeria specifically known to be dominated by Yoruba culture and religious beliefs. Therefore, this study cannot be generalised for the whole of Nigeria because of its multi-cultural system.

Recommendations

1. Cultural concerns can be addressed through community-based initiatives, such as programmes that address gender norms and other cultural ideas that are harmful to health. As part of the endeavour to ensure excellent health throughout pregnancy, health promotion and education as a main preventative strategy will open up opportunities for smoother communication while addressing the dynamics of knowledge, authority, and decision-making in the family.
2. Policy review of TBAs training programmes, and increased collaboration between Morden healthcare facilities and TMHCs should all be done to encourage community support for TBA practices. Their practices will be regulated by the formal health system's eventual integration and ensuing legislative framework, which will lower mother and child morbidity and mortality.
3. There must be strong political will on the part of government at all levels to help in reducing maternal mortality in Nigeria.

References

- Adeleke, O. R., & Olorunsola, H. K. (2018). Factors responsible for women's preference for traditional maternal health care services in Akoko North area of Ondo State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*. 4(12), 105-114
- Ayanleke, M. (2015). Religious and socio-demographic factors influencing utilization of antenatal care services in Ilesa, Osun State, Nigeria (Doctoral Dissertation).
- Azuh, D. E., Azuh, A. E., Iweala, E. J., Adeyoye D, Akanbi M., & Mordi, R .C. (2015). Factors influencing maternal mortality among rural communities in south western Nigeria. *International journal of women's health*; 9, 179-88
- Catherine, M., Amardeep, T., Bridget, R., & Amanda, T. (2019). Levels and determinants of maternal mortality in northern and southern Nigeria *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth* (2019) 19:417.
- James, P. B., Wardle, J., Steel, A., & Adams, J. (2018). Traditional, complementary and alternative medicine use of Sub-Saharan Africa: a systematic review. *BMJ Global Health*, 3(5), e000895.
- Magdalena, O., & Murphy-Lawless, J. (2017). Unilateral collaboration: The practices and understandings of traditional birth attendants in southeastern Nigeria. *Elsevier journal for Women and Birth*.
- Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2018). In: National Population Commission. Rockville, MD: Abuja and ICF International. Maryland, USA. Accessed 2024
- Nasir N, Aderoba AK, Ariana P. (2022). Scoping review of maternal and newborn health interventions and programmes in Nigeria. *BMJ Open*. ;12(2):e054784. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2021-0547
- Ogu, R. N. & Ephraim-Emmanuel, B. C. (2018). Prevention of Maternal Mortality in Nigeria: *Journal of Gynecol Women's Health Public Health to the Rescue*. 10(1)
- Ogunyomi, M. T., & Ndikom, C. M. (2016). Perceived factors influencing the utilization of traditional birth attendants' services in Akinyele Local Government, Ibadan, Nigeria. *Journal of Community Medicine and Primary Health Care*, 28(2), 40-48.
- Owojaiye, S. O., & Kajang, Y. G. (2015). Female human's physio-psycho-social health variables as factors of birth of defects children in sub-urban Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research and Review* . 3(6), 96-100.
- Ozioma, E. O. J., & Chinwe, O. A. N. (2019). Herbal medicines in African traditional medicine. *Herbal Medicine*, 10, 191-214.
- Punch Newspaper (2022). Nigeria's maternal deaths worry specialists, experts recommend adequate care, facilities. 14th August 2022.
- Tukur J, Lavin T, Adanikin A, et al (2022) . Quality and outcomes of maternal and perinatal care for 76,563 pregnancies reported in a nationwide network of Nigerian referral-level hospitals. *eClinical Medicine*. 2022;47:101411. doi:10.1016/j.eclinm.2022.101411
- World Health Organization. (2020). Sexual and Reproductive Health. Maternal Health in Nigeria: Generating Information for Action. Retrieved from www.who.int/reproductivehealth/maternal-health-nigeria/en/. Accessed in March 12, 2024.
- World Health Organisation [WHO], (2018). Estimation, Levels & Trends in Child Mortality: *Report 2018*, Estimates developed by the United.
- World Health Organisation (2015). Trends in maternal mortality: 1990 to 2015. Estimates by WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA, The World Bank and the United Nations Population Division. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2015

Assessment of Validity and Reliability ... (Gurjiya & Danladi, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15029263>

Assessment of Validity and Reliability of Geography Interest Questionnaire among Pre-service Teachers in Colleges of Education, North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed validity and reliability of geography interest questionnaire among pre-service teachers in colleges of education, North-West, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design. The questionnaire consists of adapted items underwent validation tests for face, content, construct validities and reliability. From the 9 validators' assessments face and content indices found are 0.91 and 0.99 respectively. For construct validity and reliability, the instrument was administered on 129 geography pre-service teachers. The instrument was adapted from a work of Knekta, Rowland, Corwin and Eddy (2020). For construct validity exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were used. The instrument went through EFA, and findings include three-factor structure formed as factor loads related to FGC items are between .802 and .916, those of VGC factor are between .763 and .913, and those of IGA factor are between .860 and .918, all factor loadings exceeded .50, and no cross-loading as well, these indicate convergent and discriminant validity. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) further supported the validity, with composite reliability (CR) (i.e. IGA= 0.908, FGC= 0.925 and VGC= 0.924) and average variance extracted (AVE) (i.e. 0.713, 0.675 and 0.670) are higher than .70 and .50 respectively. And the inter-factor correlation (i.e. 0.244, -0.123, and 0.002) is less than the $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ (i.e. 0.844, 0.822 and .819). The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is .813. It is proved the instrument is highly valid and reliable, so, it is recommended to use the questionnaire to gather data of geography students' interest in the discipline.

Keyword: Geography, Interest-Questionnaire, Validity and Reliability

Introduction

Teacher education plays a critical role in preparing future instructors to deliver quality instruction and foster a love for learning among students. Among the many factors influencing teaching effectiveness is the interest of students in the subject they are trained to teach. Geography is a combination of sciences and social sciences that studies man, manish activities, places and the physical environment including both living and nonliving things (Dempsey, 2023). In geography, sub disciplines like physical geography represents science, Geographic Information System (GIS) is an application of technology, geography land survey is a part of civil engineering, human geography includes arts and social sciences, and geodesy is a part of mathematics. Geography education complements science in studies of the biophysical environment by studying a wider scope of relationships and interactions and by combining scientific knowledge with contributions from the social sciences (Pallathadka & Pallathadka, 2021). Geography education is crucial for societal security, economic and political development, it prepares students for various careers related to geography and contributes to global literacy (Hagge, 2023; Huh & Jo, 2023; Mathews, DeChano-Cook & Bloom, 2023). Teaching geography is very important because the discipline has high priority for the development of individual, community, nation and the world in various aspects (Keller, 2019). Geography academic performance can be influenced by such factors as individuals' desire to learn geography related content for effective geography teaching and learning process.

Interest is a persistent desire to reengage over time as well as a psychological condition of attention and passion toward a specific subject (Holmes, 2018). Interest describes a person's generally long-lasting psychological desire to repeatedly engage with particular classes of objects (Ofem & Domike, 2022). Academic performance depends on interest, which is a powerful motivating factor that drives learning, directs academic and professional paths and energizes learning (Quinlan & Renninger,

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2022). Interest is a motivator that affects learning and performance, teachers should concentrate on how they can best promote the development of their students' interest (Wild, 2022). Interest can play a significant role in learning as the pre-service teachers are more likely to invest time and effort in activities or topics of their interest.

Geography pre-service teachers are typically enrolled in geography teacher education programs, which can include formal academic courses, practical teaching experiences and pedagogical training, in order to become a qualified geography teacher (Ammoneit, Turek & Peter, 2022). During pre-service phase, individuals learn about educational theories, teaching methodologies, classroom management, curriculum development, assessment strategies, Geography subject content and other essential aspects of teaching (Lee, 2019). The pre-service teachers have unique personal characteristics, experiences and preferences into the classroom, which shape their interest and engagement with geography. Even when resources are adequate and teaching methods are effective, these individual differences can influence how they perceive, respond to and ultimately develop an affinity for the subject.

This study aimed to assess validity and reliability of geography interest questionnaire among pre-service teachers in colleges of education, North-West, Nigeria. By assessing its validity and reliability, the study focused on ensuring the tool accurately captures pre-service teachers' interest, which is crucial for designing effective interventions to enhance motivation and teaching quality. Furthermore, the study aligns with the broader goals of improving geography education by understanding the attitudinal and motivational factors influencing pre-service teachers.

Statement of the Research Problem

Despite the importance of pre-service teachers' interest in shaping their future teaching practices, there is a lack of widely validated instruments specifically designed to measure this interest in geography (i.e. using face, content & construct validities, and reliability on the other hand). Existing instruments often lack specificity or fail to capture the multidimensional nature of interest, including Feelings toward geography-related content (FGC), Value that geography contents hold for individual (VGC), and Involvement in geography-related activities (IGA) (Ajayi, Agamber & Angura, 2017; Boukayoua, Kaddari & Bennis, 2021; Elsner et al, 2022). Without a valid and reliable questionnaire, stakeholders such as teachers, curriculum designers, and policymakers may struggle to identify areas needing attention or intervention most. Consequently, this gap hinders efforts to enhance teacher training programs and ensure the effective teaching of geography. The challenge, therefore, lies in developing an instrument that not only measures interest but also meets the psychometric standards of validity and reliability. This study addresses this critical gap by rigorously assessing the PTIGQ to ensure its applicability and accuracy in capturing the interest of pre-service teachers in geography.

Objectives of the study:

- v. To assess validity of Geography interest questionnaire among pre-service teachers in colleges of Education in North-west, Nigeria.
- vi. To determine the construct validity of the questionnaire using exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses.
- vii. To evaluate the reliability of the questionnaire through measures of internal consistency (i.e. Cronbach's alpha reliability).

Research Questions:

1. What is the validity of Geography interest questionnaire among pre-service teachers in colleges of Education in North-west, Nigeria?
2. What are the key components of pre-service teachers' interest in geography that the questionnaire aims to measure?
3. What is the reliability of the questionnaire in measuring pre-service teachers' interest in geography?

Hypotheses:

1. The questionnaire will not demonstrate strong face and content validities, as determined by expert reviews.
2. The construct validity of the questionnaire will not be confirmed, by alignment between exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses results.
3. The questionnaire will not exhibit high internal consistency (i.e. Cronbach's alpha ≥ 0.7) reliability.

Methodology

The research design is descriptive survey which involves gathering of data by studying a representative sample of the entire group (Creswell, 2018). Survey research was considered appropriate for the study because the study involved the entire geography pre-service teachers' interest in the discipline, in which the representative sample of 129 pre-service teachers extracted from the population responded to the questionnaire. Before administering the instrument to the pre-service teachers, the instrument was validated by 9 experts. The experts' assessments was computed using Cohen's Kappa index to test the face and content validity indices. Pre-Service Teachers' Interest in Geography Questionnaire (PTIGQ) has two sections, section A

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involves demographic information of the pre-service teacher and section B consists the items of pre-service teacher interest in Geography adapted from the work of (Knekta, Rowland, Corwin & Eddy, 2020). It is a close-ended questionnaire, designed to be answered by geography pre-service teacher, with such rating scale as: Always (AL) stands for 5, often (OF) stands for 4, sometimes (ST) stands for 3, rarely (RA) stands for 2 and never (NE) stands for 1. Initially the data collected is ordinal type, after the transformation process as rated above, before main analysis on the computer system the data transformed into interval type. Eventually the questionnaire provided interval.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the validity of Geography interest questionnaire among pre-service teachers in colleges of Education in North-west, Nigeria?

Hypothesis 1

The questionnaire will not demonstrate strong face and content validities, as determined by expert reviews.

Face Validity

Face validity was conducted to ensure that the research instrument is clear and easy to understand, and to identify, correct or eliminate any ambiguous or misleading items. Based on the expert assessment rate, the face validity index (FVI) was computed using Cohen’s Kappa index for face validity, which is regarded as proportion. The face validity index (FVI) was computed by $FVI = SRA/NR$ (Yusoff, 2019a; Desai & Patel, 2020).

Table 1: Validators’ Rates in Percentage and FVI Computation

S/N	Validators	Rates in Percentage	FVI
1	A	100	$FVI = \frac{SRA}{NR} = \frac{821}{9}$
2	B	100	
3	C	88	
4	D	99	$FVI = 91.2$
5	E	74	$\therefore FVI = 91\%$
6	F	86	
7	G	85	
8	H	91	
9	I	98	
	SRA	821	

Table 1 shows the percentage of the validators’ rates yielded 91% [Kappa value = 0.91, $p = .000 < .005$], which is the accepted value (Roy, Sukumar, Philip, & Gopalakrishna, 2023). Furthermore, Desai and Patel (2020) emphasized a percentage (%) of rates less than 80 is poor and requires restructure, 80–90 is substantial and requires some amendment, and 90–100 is full, that is, to be retained. For this study, 91% fall within 90–100, which is full.

Content Validity

Content validity was assessed to ensure whether the instrument adequately covers all the relevant content areas and avoid omitting important aspects of the concept. The validators rated content validity of each item of the questionnaire. Based on the expert assessment rate, the Item-level Content Validity-Index (I-CVI) was computed using Cohen’s Kappa index for face validity, which is regarded as proportion. The Item-level Content Validity-Index (I-CVI) was computed by $I-CVI = SRA/NR$ (Roy, Sukumar, Philip & Gopalakrishna, 2023; Yusoff, 2019b; Gilbert & Prion, 2016). The percentage of the validators’ rates yielded 99% [Kappa value = 0.99, $p = .000 < .005$], which is the accepted value. Roy, Sukumar, Philip & Gopalakrishna (2023) stressed that a percentage of rates less than 0.7 = needs elimination, 0.7–0.79 = needs revision and higher than 0.79 = appropriate, therefore, the 99% index is appropriate and accepted.

Research Question 2

What are the key components of pre-service teachers' interest in geography that the questionnaire aims to measure?

Hypothesis 2

The construct validity of the questionnaire will not be confirmed, by alignment between exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses results.

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Construct Validity

Initially KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity were used to ensure the suitability of the data for factor analyses. The KMO is .800 and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (chi-square = 2180.161, df = 136, P = .001), which indicate the 129 sample size is adequate, and can be used for the factor analyses (i.e. EFA and CFA). Since the KMO value is greater than .60 and the Bartlett's Test result is statistically significant, the data is appropriate for factor analysis (Ateş & Altuner Çoban, 2022).

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Factorization and rotation methods were used to discover the factor construct in which Principal Component Analysis and Promax Rotation were used. As a result of this, 13 items (FGC_7, FGC_8, FGC_9, VGC_1, VGC_8, IGA_6, IGA_7, IGA_8, IGA_9, IGA_10, IGA_11, IGA_12 and IGA_13) out of the 30 items loaded on a factor different from their counterpart were removed, to ensure no cross-loading and no low-loading. The remaining 17 items were re-running and the three-factor structure was formed.

Table 2: Factor Load Values of the Interest in Geography Construct

Factor	Items	Factor load values		
		1	2	3
Feelings toward geography-related (FGC)	FGC_1	Working with the subject matter and problems of geography is among my favorite activities.	.837	
	FGC_2	After a long weekend or vacation I look forward to getting back to my geography classes.	.850	
	FGC_3	Being involved in geography classes puts me in a good mood.	.826	
	FGC_4	I chose to study geography primarily because of the interesting subject matter involved.	.883	
	FGC_5	I generally have fun when I am learning geography topics.	.916	
	FGC_6	I like reading about geography.	.802	
	VGC_2	I really see value in the things that I am learning in geography.		.763
Value that geography contents hold for individual (VGC)	VGC_3	Studying geography has a lot to do with whom I want to become as a person.		.882
	VGC_4	Compared to other things that are important to me (e.g., hobbies and social life), learning about geography is of greater importance.		.913
	VGC_5	Learning about geography is more important to me than leisure and amusement.		.897
	VGC_6	I am certain that studying geography has a positive influence on my personality.		.886
	VGC_7	I am confident that learning about geography directly corresponds with my personal preferences.		.864
Involvement in geography-related activities (IGA)	IGA_1	I discuss outside of class what I am learning in my in geography classes.		.867
	IGA_2	I talk about things that I learned in geography rather than my hobbies.		.894
	IGA_3	In my free time and unrelated to my coursework, I read magazines, articles or books related to the topics of geography.		.918
	IGA_4	If I had enough time, I would work more intensively with certain aspects of geography, even if they had nothing to do with any course requirements.		.907
	IGA_5	Even before coming to college, I voluntarily spent time thinking about topics in geography.		.860

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.
 a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations

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The factor loads of the first factor related to the items are between .802 and .916, those of the second factor are between .763 and .913, and those of the third factor are between .860 and .918, as shown in table 2. With factor load value above .30 provides the criteria for an item to be included within a factor, so, there is no low-loading as all the factor load values are above .50, this means that all the items converge. Also there is no cross-loading, as no item load on more than one factor, this means there is no discriminant validity. These findings revealed that the construct validity of the items is provided (Hair, Risher, Sarstedt & Ringle, 2019).

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) involve utilization of the maximum likelihood method to confirm the three-factor structure produced by the exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Figure 1 shows the factor distributions and values obtained from the CFA.

Fig. 1 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) Structure

After the EFA, the standardized regression weights and correlation values in the AMOS output were used to compute the convergent and discriminant validity, which was done in the Excel package. The Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) provide the convergent validity, the CR condition of satisfaction or benchmark is 0.7, while for the AVE values is 0.5. For discriminant validity, the square root of the AVE such as (\sqrt{AVE}) value is compared with the inter-factor correlation. The inter-factor correlation should be less than the square root of the AVE. Table 7 provides the CR, AVE, \sqrt{AVE} , and inter-factor correlation values for the convergent and discriminant validity of the interest in geography items.

Table 3: CR, AVE, \sqrt{AVE} and Inter-Factor Correlation of Interest in Geography Construct

Factor	CR	AVE	IGA	FGC	VGC
IGA	0.908	0.713	0.844		
FGC	0.925	0.675	0.244	0.822	
VGC	0.924	0.670	-0.123	0.002	0.819

As the CR values (i.e. 0.908, 0.925 and 0.924) are above .70 and AVE values (i.e. 0.713, 0.675 and 0.670) are above .50 as shown in the Table 3, so the convergent validity is achieved. The inter-factor correlation (i.e. 0.244, -0.123, and 0.002) is less than the square root of the AVE (i.e. 0.844, 0.822 and .819), so the discriminant validity is achieved. As the convergent and discriminant validities are attained it can be inferred that the construct validity achievement has been confirmed.

Research Question 3

What is the reliability of the questionnaire in measuring pre-service teachers' interest in geography?

Hypothesis 3

The questionnaire will not exhibit high internal consistency (i.e. Cronbach's alpha \geq 0.7) reliability.

Reliability

Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients were computed for each individual factor and for all items of the questionnaire collectively to check the internal consistency of the scale.

Table 4: Cronbach's Alpha Values of PTIGQ Scale and its Factors

S/N	Factor	Number of Items	Alpha Value
1	FGC	6	.925
2	IGA	5	.934
3	VGC	6	.935
PTIGQ		17	.813

Table 4 displays the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients found for each factors is high (i.e. FGC 0.925, IGA 0.934 and VGC 0.935) and for all items of the questionnaire collectively is 0.813 (Ateş & Altuner Çoban, 2022; Adeniran, 2019). This revealed that the questionnaire has high reliability.

Summary of Findings

In summary, the questionnaire has high reliabilities and reliability in support with such findings as:

1. Face validity of the questionnaire is 91% and fall within 90–100, which is full. And content validity of 99% index, which is also appropriate.
2. The findings also revealed the achievement of construct validity using EFA and confirmed by using CFA.
3. And finally the questionnaire is reliable at 0.813.

Discussion of Findings

This study sought to provide a scientifically validated and reliable instrument that contributes to understanding and improving teacher education in geography. Therefore the main goal of the study was to validate the adapted Pre-Service Teachers' Interest in Geography Questionnaire (PTIGQ). The PTIGQ was adapted and went through validation processes to ensure its reliability and validity. Validation procedures included face, content and construct validity assessments. For construct validity and reliability, the instrument was administered on 129 geography pre-service teachers, with 13 items rejected due to errors in completion. Missing values were addressed using the "mean of nearby points" method in the SPSS package. The face and content validity index (FVI) was found to be 0.91 or 91%, and Item-level Content Validity-Index (I-CVI) was found to be 0.99 or 99%, meeting the acceptable range. However, the items were adapted from original sources without face and content validity assessments.

The instrument items were adapted from a study of Knekta, Rowland, Corwin and Eddy (2020), the main aim of the study was to create an instrument to measure undergraduate biology students' interest. A total of 348 participants involved in the factor analyses. While the current study made certain modifications and subtractions of items from 30 to 17 most representative of the items, to ensure no cross-loading and no low-loading factor items. The instrument went through EFA indicating convergent and discriminant validity. The CFA confirmed the structure, yielding high CR and AVE values, while the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is 0.813, affirming validity and reliability of the instrument.

Conclusion

From the study findings and the results obtained it is proved that the instrument is highly valid and reliable, and the application of the Questionnaire is supported. This instrument can be adopted by researchers, lecturers and teachers for evaluating interest in geography of targeted students. Other education researchers could be encouraged to adapt and gather validity evidence for the instrument and apply it in their different disciplines. This effort can foster a comprehensive understanding of students' interest across disciplines and facilitate the creation of a knowledge base supporting students' persistence in education.

Recommendations

As a result of the research findings some recommendations were made as follows:

1. Since the questionnaire demonstrates excellent face validity (91%) and content validity (99%), future efforts should ensure the same rigorous standards in designing and validating similar instruments. This includes the involvement of not only subject matter experts, but from various relevant disciplines, such as, English language, educational psychology,

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measurement and evaluation, and including a sample from the targeted participants, to evaluate the relevance and clarity of questionnaire items and performing comprehensive content reviews to maintain appropriateness across different contexts.

2. With construct validity successfully achieved through Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and confirmed by Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), the questionnaire is proven to measure the intended constructs effectively. It is recommended to apply this validated instrument to broader contexts, such as assessing pre-service teachers' interest in geography across different educational institutions or regions, to gather more comprehensive data for comparative analysis.
3. Utilize the Reliable Questionnaire in Longitudinal Studies: With a reliability score of 0.813, the questionnaire is consistent and dependable for measuring pre-service teachers' interest in geography. It is recommended to use this tool for longitudinal studies to track changes in interest levels over time and to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions designed to enhance engagement in geography education.

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References:

- Adeniran, A. O. (2019). Application of Likert Scale's Type and Cronbach's Alpha Analysis in an Airport Perception Study. *Scholar Journal of Applied Sciences and Research*, 2(4), 01-05. <https://innovationinfo.org/articles/SJASR/SJASR-4-223.pdf>
- Ajayi, V. O., Agamber, T. and Angura, T. (2017). Effect of Gender on Students' Interest in Standard Mixture Separation Techniques Using Ethnochemistry Teaching Approach. *Sky Journal of Educational Research*, 5(5), 27-33. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3066324>
- Ammoneit, R., Turek, A. and Peter, C. (2022). Pre-Service Geography Teachers' Professional Competencies in Education for Sustainable Development. *Education Science*, 12(42) 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12010042>.
- Ateş, S. & Altuner Çoban, G Ş (2022). A Validity and Reliability Study on Developing a Scale for Assessing Classroom Teachers' Attitudes Towards Illustrated Children's Books. *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*, 17(3), 222-237. <https://doi.org/10.29329/epasr.2022.461.11>
- Boukayoua, Z., Kaddari, F. and Bennis, N. (2021). Students' interest in science learning and measurement practices. Questions for research in the Moroccan school context. *SHS Web of Conferences* 119, article 05006. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202111905006>.
- Creswell, J. W. (2018). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (5th ed.). Pearson.
- Desai, S. & Patel, N. (2020). ABC of Face Validity for Questionnaire. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, 65(1), 164-168. <http://dx.doi.org/10.47583/ijpsrr.2020.v65i01.025>
- Dempsey, C. (2023). *What is Geography?* <https://www.geographyrealm.com/definition-geography/>
- Elsner, J. N., Sadler, T. D., Zangori, L., Friedrichsen, P. J. and Ke, L. (2022). Student interest, concerns, and information-seeking behaviors related to COVID-19. *Disciplinary and Interdisciplinary Science Education Research*, 4(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43031-022-00053-2>
- Gilbert, G. E. and Prion, S. (2016). Making Sense of Methods and Measurement: Lawshe's Content Validity Index. *Clinical Simulation in Nursing*, 12(12), 530-531. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecns.2016.08.002>
- Hagge, P. D. (2023). Find It on a Map: Country Location Identification in a University Geography Classroom, 2016–2022. *Journal of Geography*, 122(5), 105-114. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221341.2023.2224374>
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J.J., Sarstedt, M. and Ringle, C.M. (2019) When to Use and How to Report the Results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31, 2-24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>
- Holmes, A. G. (2018). The Role of Interest and Enjoyment in Determining Students' Approach to Learning. *Educational Process: International Journal*, 7(2), 140-150. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22521/edupij.2018.72.4>.
- Huh, S. and Jo, I. (2023). Successes and Struggles: Evaluating Geospatial Technologies Integration in Geography Lessons using TPACK. *Journal of Geography*, 122(5), 126-139. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221341.2023.2224814>.

Assessment of Validity and Reliability ... (Gurjiya & Danladi, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15029263>

- Keller, K. H. (2019). The current state of geography education in the United States. *The Geography Teacher*, 16(4), 148–149. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19338341.2019.1663747>
- Knekta, E., Rowland, A. A., Corwin, L. A., and Eddy, S. (2020). Measuring university students' interest in biology: Evaluation of an instrument targeting Hidi and Renninger's individual interest. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-020-00217-4>.
- Lee, D. (2019): Cultivating pre-service geography teachers' awareness of geography using story Maps. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 44(3), 387-405. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03098265.2019.1700487>.
- Mathews, A. J., DeChano-Cook, L. M. and Bloom, C. (2023). Enhancing Middle School Learning about Geography and Topographic Maps Using Hands-on Play and Geospatial Technologies. *Journal of Geography*, 122(5), 115-125. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221341.2023.2226156>.
- Ofem U. A. and Domike, G. (2022). Pupils Learning Preferences and Interest Development in learning. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(21), 31-38. www.iiste.org
- Quinlan, K. M. and Renninger, K. A. (2022). Rethinking employability: how students build on interest in a subject to plan a career. *Higher Education* 84(1), 863–883. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-021-00804-6>
- Roy, R., Sukumar, G.M., Philip, M. & Gopalakrishna, G. (2023). Face, content, criterion and construct validity assessment of a newly developed tool to assess and classify work related stress (TAWS– 16). *PLoS ONE* 18(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0280189>
- Wild, S. (2022). Trajectories of subject-interests development and influence factors in higher education. *Current Psychology: A Journal for Diverse Perspectives on Diverse Psychological Issues*, 1(42), 12879–12895. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-02691-7>
- Yusoff, M.S.B. (2019a). ABC of response process validation and face validity index calculation. *Education in Medicine Journal*, 11(3), 55–61. <https://doi.org/10.21315/eimj2019.11.3.6>
- Yusoff, M.S.B. (2019b). ABC of content validation and content validity index calculation. *Education in Medicine Journal*, 11(2), 49–54. <https://doi.org/10.21315/eimj2019.11.2.6>

Assessment Practice in Special Education Schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Assessment practices for special need students have been a concern in the educational system of most countries, especially in Nigeria. The aim of this study was to examine the assessment practice in special education Schools in Zamfara state, Nigeria. The Survey design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised all the 55 teachers (special educators) in the two (2) Schools for Special Education in Zamfara State, which include School for Special Education Gusau and School for Special Education Gummi. School for Special Education Gusau and School for Special Education Gummi have 37 and 18 teachers respectively. Purposive or judgmental sampling technique was used to select all the 55 teachers of the targeted population. The instrument used for data collection was a researcher designed questionnaire namely “Special Educators’ Assessment Practice Questionnaire (SEAPQ)”. Both face and content validity of the instrument were established by experts in Educational Research, Measurement and Evaluation. Cronbach Alpha method of reliability was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. The Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation. The results showed that the components of student assessment practice conducted among special need students are curriculum-based assessments, intelligence Quotient (IQ), Test screening test, academic achievements, developmental assessments and end-of-grade assessments, and the methods of assessment used are formative assessment, summative assessment, speech therapy evaluation/language scales, developmental scales, diagnostic assessment, standardized test and direct observation. The findings also revealed that special educators’ professional competence in choosing assessment methods appropriate for special need students, administering, scoring, and interpreting of their results and recognizing unethical and inappropriate assessment methods are inadequate. Based on these findings, it was recommended that Special educators should be trained on all the components of assessments practices that will benefit special needs students learning outcomes.

Key words: Assessment practices, special needs students, special educators, special education

Introduction

In recent times, a number of changes have occurred in the context in which the assessment for children with special needs is carried out. These have generated questions in such areas as the nature and role of the teachers and administrators in the assessment practices, both in and outside special education schools. The Council for Exceptional children in the year 1983 adopted a code of ethics and standard for professional practice, which addressed appropriate assessment procedures for special needs students. Special education is a practice of educating students with special needs in a way that addresses their individual differences and needs. According to Laju (2012), the process involves the individually planned and systematically monitored arrangement of teaching procedures. It is a systematic process of developing skills, attitudes and values in some set of individuals with body deformity which require separate attention. In the content of special education programme, many services are earmarked to normalize persons with disabilities to fit in the society. The programme makes it possible for them to adjust from the notion of being unable to carry on societal roles to fully responsible citizens.

National Policy on Education (NPE, 2004) stated that adequate provision of education for all categories of children and adults who require special education services as well as to provide a diversified and appropriate curriculum for each category of disability. But in reality, there seem to be variations in method of assessment in both special and regular schools. Assessment of students with special educational needs should not be regarded as a once-off diagnostic event but rather as an on-going process closely linked to intervention (NCSE, 2013). According to NASET (2010), assessment in special education is the process used to determine a child’s specific learning strengths and needs, and to determine whether or not a child is eligible for special education

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services. Assessment in special education is a process that involves collecting information about a student for the purpose of making decisions.

Assessment is a fundamental feedback mechanism in education, allowing all stakeholders of the learning process to understand what is being learned and where learning resources need to be focused. Assessment of learning according to Liberman et al., (2020) is the process of gathering and evaluating information on what students know, understand, and can do in order to make an informed decision about the next steps in the educational process. Assessment in special education is regularly done within the schools by the teachers themselves using different methods. The usefulness of this assessment includes; shaping of students learning, provision of immediate and constructive feedback of students, monitoring of learning progress, ranking and promotion student to the next level. Assessment for learning makes it an essential element of special education classroom assessment practices, especially when the field of special education emphasizes the individual learner and her/his educational needs (Shriner, 2000).

Assessment practices for special need students have been a concern in the educational system of most countries, especially in Nigeria. But some researchers, who are interested in assessment, have also expressed concerns about assessment practices in special education schools. In special education schools recently, it seems there are limited assessment practices to effectively assess learning outcomes of special need students. Most special education schools use assessment practices based on standardized examination which comprises of essay questions or various forms of objective testing. Samuelowicz and Bain (2002) perceived that the assessment practices chosen by teachers are likely to be influenced by how teachers view the nature of knowledge, learning, teaching and the purposes of assessment not the nature of the students. Hale and Astolfi (2011) suggested that the types of assessment strategies practiced by instructors and how frequently they practice them would have an impact on the quality of students' learning.

Teachers in special schools have been frequently observed employing a range of assessment activities such as informal discussion, the observation of level of participation, and practical problem solving; these activities were considered to be an integral part of classroom teaching and help them understand students' strengths and weakness. Although there is little theoretical evidence to demonstrate that the assessment practice differs from regular schools to special schools, the fact is that, compared with assessment study in mainstream schools, the studies of assessment practice in special schools are still scarce (Hanafin et al., 2007). Consequently, this research seeks to investigate the assessment practice of special need students in special education Schools for comparison with assessment programme in mainstream schools and also validate the quality of certificates obtainable from such schools. This study represents the first stepping stone in building a comprehensive picture for assessment practices for special need students in the schools for special education in Zamfara state, Nigeria. This Study comes to give a general national overview of current assessment practices for special needs students. Believing in the concept that good assessments promote learning and motivate both teachers and students, whereas poor assessments narrow the curriculum, de-skill, and demotivate teachers and frustrate students, there is an imminent need to further investigate classroom assessment practices and relate their pedagogical implications to policy-makers and interested parties. The development of sound pedagogical assessment practices is a never-ending process. Survey of classroom observations on assessment practices are needed to compare and contrast with survey responses and obtain a wider range of evidence related to classroom assessment practices for special needs students and other students in the mainstream schools.

There is also need for the identification and implementation of assessment practices that can assist students with disabilities achieve learning objectives and ensure the acquisition of the necessary skills to become independent, informed, and productive. For that reason, this research seeks to investigate the assessment practice of special need students in special education Schools in Zamfara state, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study was to examine the assessment practice in special education schools in Zamfara state, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Examine the components of assessment practices used in special education schools in Zamfara State.
2. Determine the methods of assessment practices used in special education schools in Zamfara State.
3. Find out the teachers' attitudes towards assessment practice in special education schools in Zamfara State.
4. Investigate the teachers' professional competency in choosing assessment methods in special education schools in Zamfara State.
5. Examine the teachers' professional competency in administering, scoring, and interpreting results in special education schools in Zamfara State.
6. Investigate the teachers' competence in recognizing unethical assessment methods in special education schools in Zamfara State.

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Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the components of assessment practices used in special education schools in Zamfara State?
2. What are the methods of assessment practices used in special education schools in Zamfara State?
3. What are the teachers' attitudes towards assessment practice in special education schools in Zamfara State?
4. What are the teachers' professional competency in choosing assessment methods in special education schools in Zamfara State?
5. What are the teachers' professional competency in administering, scoring, and interpreting results in special education schools in Zamfara State?
6. What are the teachers' competence in recognizing unethical assessment methods in special education schools in Zamfara State?

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted for this study because collection of valid and reliable data is possible and inferences concerning the population drawn from the representative sample selected. The population of the study comprised all the 55 special educators in the two (2) School for Special Education in Zamfara State, which include School for Special Education Gusau and School for Special Education Gummi with 37 and 18 teachers respectively. Purposive or judgmental sampling technique was used to select all the 55 teachers of special education schools in Zamfara state. A researcher designed instruments was used namely "Special Educators' Assessment Practice Questionnaire (SEAPQ)". SEAPQ contained 40 items structured in a modified 4-point likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Both face and content validity of the instrument were established base on contributions made by experts in Educational Research, Measurement and Evaluation. Cronbach Alpha method of reliability was used to determine the reliability of the instrument with the reliability index of 0.78. Data collected were analyzed using both descriptive statistics of Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation.

Presentation of Results

Data collected were coded and analyzed using Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation.

Research Question one:

What are the components of assessment practices used in special education schools in Zamfara State?

Table 1: Components of Student Assessment Practice used in special Education Schools

SN	Component of assessment conducted among special need students are to:	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rate
1	Screening tests	55	2.9106	1.0926	3rd
2	Developmental assessments	55	2.0987	0.9967	6th
3	Curriculum-based assessments	55	3.0264	1.0385	1st
4	Adaptive behavioral assessments	55	2.1817	0.9961	5th
5	Intelligence Quotient (IQ) Test	55	3.0182	1.0451	2nd
6	Academic achievements	55	2.8909	1.0123	4th
7	End-of-grade assessments	55	2.0909	0.9867	7th

Field study 2024

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviations of special educators' responses on the components of student assessment practice used in special education Schools in Zamfara State. The table revealed the components of student assessment practice conducted among special need students as curriculum-based assessments, intelligence Quotient (IQ), Test screening test, academic achievements, developmental assessments and end-of-grade assessments with mean values of 3.0264, 3.0182, 2.9106, 2.8909, 2.1817, 2.0987 and 2.0909 respectively.

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Research Question Two:

What are the methods of assessment practices used in special education schools in Zamfara State?

Table 2: Methods of Assessment used in Special Education Schools

SN	Methods of assessment used in special education schools:	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rate
1	Formative assessment to monitor student progress during learning process	55	3.0909	1.0623	1st
2	Summative assessment to evaluate overall student achievement	55	3.0478	1.0323	2nd
3	Standardized test to measure students' performance against a standard or a norm	55	2.0319	0.9679	6th
4	Diagnostic assessment to identify specific learning disabilities or difficulties	55	2.1920	0.9826	5th
5	Direct observation to see spontaneous behaviour of the students	55	2.0246	0.9897	7th
6	Developmental scales to assess your child's cognitive abilities	55	2.5896	0.9967	4th
7	Speech therapy evaluation/language scales to assess student's communication skills	55	2.8909	1.0123	3rd

Field study 2024

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviations of special educators' responses on the methods of assessment used in special education schools in Zamfara state. The table revealed the methods of assessment use in special education schools as formative assessment, summative assessment, speech therapy evaluation/language scales, developmental scales, diagnostic assessment, standardized test and direct observation to see spontaneous behaviour of the students with mean values of 3.0909, 3.0478, 2.8909, 2.5896, 2.1920, 2.0319 and 2.0246 respectively.

Research Question Three:

What are the teachers' attitudes towards assessment practice in special education schools in Zamfara State?

Table 3: Teachers Attitudes Toward Assessment practice in Special Education Schools

SN	Teachers attitudes toward assessment practice	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	I always use assessments to monitor special needs student progress during learning process	55	2.5996	1.0061
2	I believe that assessments accurately reflect the abilities of special needs students	55	2.5863	0.9968
3	I always feel in my ability to assess special needs students	55	2.0909	0.9867
4	I always involve special needs students in the assessment process	55	2.5798	0.9856
5	I use assessment data to inform instruction for special needs students	55	2.6058	1.0117
6	I ensure assessment validity and reliability for special needs students	55	2.4969	0.8997
	Grand Mean		2.50	0.9811

Field study 2024

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviations of special educators' responses on their attitudes toward special need students' assessment. The table revealed a grand mean of 2.50 and standard deviation of 0.9811. The grand mean of 2.50 compared to the scale mean of 2.50 revealed a positive attitude of special educators toward special need students' assessment.

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Research Question Four:

What are the teachers' professional competency in choosing assessment methods in special education schools in Zamfara State?

Table 4: Teachers' Professional Competency in Choosing Assessment Methods Appropriate for Special Need Students

SN	Teachers' professional competency in choosing assessment methods	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Selection of assessment methods for special needs students must align with student's learning style, Curriculum requirements, Availability of resources	55	2.0818	0.9967
2	Choosing assessment methods for special needs students must based on student's emotional and behavioral needs	55	2.1079	0.9986
3	Establishment of the validity and reliability of assessment methods for special needs students is done by consulting with colleagues and use expert judgment	55	2.0990	0.9946
4	Selection of assessment methods for special needs students is based on collaboration with other professionals such as speech therapists	55	2.1487	0.9989
5	Assessment selection is used to inform instruction and make data-driven decisions for special needs students	55	2.0905	0.9868
Grand Mean			2.10558	0.99512

Field study 2024

Table 4 shows the mean and standard deviations of special educators' responses on their level of professional competence in choosing assessment methods appropriate for special need students in special education Schools. It revealed from the table a grand mean of 2.10558 and standard deviation of 0.99512 which shows inadequacy in special educators' professional competence in choosing assessment methods appropriate for special need students compared to the scale mean of 2.50.

Research Question Five:

What are the teachers' professional competency in administering, scoring, and interpreting results in special education schools in Zamfara State?

Table 5: Teachers' Professional Competency in Administering, Scoring, and Interpreting the Results of Special Need Students

SN	I am competent in:	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Assessments are administered in a way that is accessible and equitable for special needs students	55	2.5696	0.9848
2	Test security and integrity are ensured when administering assessments to special needs students	55	2.6723	0.9898
3	Modify assessment procedures are used to handle assessment modifications for special needs students	55	2.5583	0.9668
4	Formal training program are given on assessment tools and procedures used for special needs students	55	2.4522	0.8973
5	Multiple measures are used to ensure that assessment results are accurate and reliable for special needs students	55	2.5996	0.9896
6	Assessment results are communicated to parents/guardians and students with special needs	55	2.6744	0.9899
Grand Mean			2.58773	0.9697

Field study 2024

Table 5 shows the mean and standard deviations of special educators' responses on their level of professional competence in administering, scoring, and interpreting the results in special education Schools. It revealed from the table a grand mean of 2.58773 and standard deviation of 0.9697 which shows inadequacy in special educators' professional competence in administering, scoring, and interpreting the results of special need students compared to the scale mean of 2.50.

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Research Question Six:

What are the teachers' competence in recognizing unethical assessment methods in special education Schools in Zamfara state?

Table 6: Teachers' Competence in Recognizing Unethical Assessment Methods in Special Education Schools

SN	I am competent in:	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	I am very familiar with the ethical guidelines for assessing special needs students	55	2.1816	0.9972
2	Assessment methods respect the privacy and dignity of special needs students	55	2.1009	0.9982
3	Using diverse assessment tools its easy to recognize and address potential biases in assessment methods for special needs students	55	2.0935	0.9941
4	Student consent is always sought to ensure that assessment methods respect the privacy and dignity of special needs students	55	2.1816	0.9972
5	Updated on best practices and ethical guidelines for assessing special needs students is acquired by attending professional development	55	2.1915	0.9936
Grand Mean			2.14982	0.99606

Field study 2024

Table 6 shows the mean and standard deviations of special educators' responses on the level of teachers' competence in recognizing unethical and inappropriate assessment methods among special need students . It revealed from the table a grand mean of 2.14982 and standard deviation of 0.99606 which shows inadequacy in special educators' professional competence in recognizing unethical and inappropriate assessment methods compared to the scale mean of 2.50.

Research Question Seven:

What are the impact of student assessment practice on the educational development of special need students in special education Schools in Zamfara state?

Table 7: Impact of Student Assessment Practice on the Educational Development of Special Need Students

SN	I am competent in:	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Assessment practices affect the educational development of special needs students	55	2.9710	1.0956
2	Assessment practices influence the identification and support of special needs students	55	2.9098	1.0586
3	Assessment practices impact the access of special needs students to educational resources and opportunities	55	3.0446	1.0483
4	Assessment practices help in the transition and placement of special needs students	55	3.0276	1.0394
5	Assessment practices impact the overall educational achievement and progress of special needs students	55	3.0769	1.0588
Grand Mean			2.25	1.030388

Field study 2024

Table 7 shows the mean and standard deviations of special educators' responses on their level of professional competence in choosing assessment methods appropriate for special need students in special education Schools. It revealed from the table a grand mean of 2.10558 and standard deviation of 0.99512 which shows that special educators' professional competence in choosing assessment methods appropriate for special need students is inadequate compared to the scale mean of 2.50.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the data collected and work done on the analysis of result, the findings of the study revealed that the components of student assessment practice conducted among special need students are curriculum-based assessments, intelligence Quotient (IQ), Test screening test, academic achievements, developmental assessments and end-of-grade

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assessments. This study is supported by Huda, (2008) stated that assessment is utilized among the special need students to identify child's special needs, assess child's communication skills, inform child's intervention or treatment plan, placement and detection of what the child knows or does not know, and in most cases curriculum-based assessment which is frequent, systematic, and measured learned tasks.

Findings from the study also showed the methods of assessment use in special education schools as formative assessment, summative assessment, speech therapy evaluation/language scales, developmental scales, diagnostic assessment, standardized test and direct observation to see spontaneous behaviour of the students. The result is consistence with Yan et al. (2021) pointed out that assessment at special education schools should serve two main purposes: to identify students current level of learning and inform teachers instruction, and to group students into different teaching groups according to their ability levels. Such assessment includes formative and summative assessment, psychological evaluation, speech therapy assessment, occupational therapy assessment.

The findings also revealed a positive attitude of special educators toward special need students' assessment. This study is in consonance with Dessemontet, Morin & Crocker (2014) and Emmers, Baeyens & Petry (2020) stated that teachers' attitudes towards assessment of disabled is imperative. Teachers tend to have positive attitudes since they have had contact with disabled people in the past, and learned about special education policy and instructional strategies.

The findings of the study also revealed inadequacy in special educators' professional competence in both choosing assessment methods appropriate for special need students, and administering, scoring, and interpreting of their results. This study is supported by Kalra (2018) stated that teachers' professional competency remains significant barrier to quality assessment for special needs students. He believed that only a limited percentage of special educators had previously participated in professional development in assessment of special needs students. Skills in choosing appropriate, useful, administratively convenient, technically adequate, and fair assessment methods are prerequisite to good use of information to support instructional decisions. Special educators need to be well-acquainted with the kinds of information provided by a broad range of assessment alternatives and their strengths and weaknesses. In particular, they should be familiar with criteria for evaluating and selecting assessment methods in light of instructional plans for special needs students.

Findings from the study also showed inadequacy in special educators' professional competence in recognizing unethical and inappropriate assessment methods. The result is consistence with the statement of Airasian (2005) proposed that the assessment ethical standards should indicate some aspect of a teacher's fairness in dealing with his or her pupils. He emphasizing that many special educators modify students' grades due to presence or lack of effort, behavior problems, late work, and extra credit. The findings also supported Andrew (2015) who stated that special educators must be well-versed in their own ethical and legal responsibilities in assessment. The must be aware that various assessment procedures can be misused or overused resulting in harmful consequences such as violating special need student's right to confidentiality, and inappropriately using special need students' standardized achievement test scores to measure teaching effectiveness.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the components of student assessment practice conducted among special need students are curriculum-based assessments, intelligence Quotient (IQ), Test screening test, academic achievements, developmental assessments and end-of-grade assessments, and the methods of assessment used are formative assessment, summative assessment, speech therapy evaluation/language scales, developmental scales, diagnostic assessment, standardized test and direct observation. It was further concluded that special educators' professional competence in choosing assessment methods appropriate for special need students, administering, scoring, and interpreting of their results and recognizing unethical and inappropriate assessment methods are inadequate.

Recommendations

The study therefore recommended that:

1. Special educators should be train on all the components of assessments practices that will benefit special needs students learning outcomes. Training is important to guide special educators in practicing major of the assessment components such as choosing and developing of assessment methods, administering, scoring, and interpreting the results of assessment methods, using assessment results in making decisions about special need.
2. Special educators should also be well-acquainted with the kinds of information provided by a broad range of assessment alternatives and their strengths and weaknesses. In particular, they should be familiar with criteria for evaluating and

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selecting assessment methods in light of instructional plans. Special educators who meet this standard will have the conceptual and application skills.

3. Fairness, the rights of all concerned, special educators must be equipped with the professional ethical behavior of assessment of special need students. By establishing standards for all special educators on special need students' assessment. That is, blueprint or rubric for all special educators to be followed in assessment practice. This will prevent special educators from playing unethical or bias level of assessment from one special need school to the others.
4. Special educators should also be provided with knowledge of grading procedures, communicating assessment results to students' parents and recognizing unethical, illegal, and otherwise inappropriate assessment methods.

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References

- Creswell, J. W. (2003). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach*. (2nd ed.). Sage.
- Dessementet RS, Morin D & Crocker AG 2014. Exploring the relations between in-service training, prior contacts and teachers' attitudes towards persons with intellectual disability. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 61(1),16-26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1034912X.2014.878535>
- Denzin, N., & Lincoln, Y.S. (2005): *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. SAGE.
- Emmers E, Baeyens D & Petry K 2020. Attitudes and self-efficacy of teachers towards inclusion in higher education. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 35(2),139-153. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2019.1628337>
- European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education. (2003). Key principles for special needs education: Recommendations for policy makers. In L. Bauer (Ed.). Author.
- Galloway, D. (1987). *School, pupils and special educational needs*. Croom Helm.
- Garcia, G.E. & Pearson, P.D. (1991). The role of assessment in a diverse society. In E.H. (Eds.), *Literary in a diverse society: Perspective practice and policies*. Teachers College Press.
- Hale, C. D., & Astolfi, D. (2011). *Measuring Learning & Performance: A Primer* (2nd ed.). Saint Leo University.
- Hanafin, J., Shevlin, M., Kenny, M., and Neela, E. M. (2007). Including Young People with Disabilities: Assessment Challenges in Higher Education. *High Educ.* 54, 435–448. doi:10.1007/s10734-006-9005-9
- Heward, W.L. (2000). *Exceptional Children: An introduction to special education*. Prentice-Hall.
- Howell, K. & Rueda, R. (1996). Achievement testing with culturally & linguistically diverse student in L.G. Suzuki, P.J. Meller, & J.G. Ponterotto (eds), *Handbook of multicultural assessment Clinical, Psychological, & Educations*. Jossey Bass. Publishing.
- Individual With Disabilities Education Act (2015). Public law 114-95. <https://sites.ed.gov/idea/about-idea/> Labeer, J.,Candeias, A. & gracio, L.M. (2011). In book: With a different glance-Dynamic assessment and functioning of children oriented to development & inclusive learning. Garant Publishing.
- Laju, A. (2012), *Ability in Disability. Educating Children's with Special Needs*. Best Press.
- Liberman, J; Levin, V & Luna – Buzaldua, D. (2020). *Are students still learning during COVID-19? Formative assessment can provide the answer*.<https://www.blogs.worldbank.org/educaiotn/are-students-still-learning-during-COVID-19>
- Mecado, C. & Romero, M. (1993). Assessment of students in bilingual education in M.B. Annas & U. Cassanova (eds). *Ninety-second yearbook of the national society for the study of education, part ii bilingual education. Politics, practice, and research*. University of Chicago Press.
- Moll, L.G. (eds) (1990). *Vygotsky and education: instructional implications and applications of socio-historical psychology*. Cambridge Uni Press.
- National Association of Special Education Teachers (2010). Assessment in special education series. <https://www.naset.org/index.php?id=2956>
- National council for special education (2013) Supporting Students with Special Educational Needs in Schools.1–2 Mill Street Trim Co. Meath, 5-45
- Osatuyi, N.O. (2004). Motivation to learn and teach special education. *The Special Educator*, 3 (1), 93-98.
- Olorunda, T. (2004). Inclusive education in Nigeria: A myth or a Reality. *The Special Educators* 3(1), 1-6.
- Pierrangelo, R.& Giuliant, A. G (2006). *Assessment in special education: A practical approach (2nd Ed.)*. Allyn & Bacon. MA Publisher
- Samuelowicz, K., & Bain, J. D. (2002). Identifying academics' orientations to assessment practice. *Higher education*, 43(2), 173-201.
- Shepard, L.G. (1989). Why we need better assessment. *Education leadership*, 46(7), 4-9.
- Shriner, J. G. (2000). Legal perspectives on school outcomes assessment for students with disabilities. *The Journal of Special Education*, 33, 232–239. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/002246690003300406>
- Yan et al. (2021) Formative Assessment in Special Schools. *Frontiers in Education*, 5(6), 674-869 | www.frontiersin.org

Attitude and Perception on Climate Change and Biodiversity among Secondary School Science Students in Delta State

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Abstract

This study examined the assessment of attitude and perceptions on climate change and biodiversity among secondary school science students in Delta State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study employed a rigorous stratified random sampling method to select a representative sample of 300 science secondary school students from Delta State. Stratified random sampling ensures that different subgroups within the population are adequately represented in the sample, enhancing the generalizability of the findings. By carefully defining the population, establishing clear inclusion and exclusion criteria, and implementing robust sampling procedures across all 25 Local Government Areas (LGAs), the study aimed to capture a comprehensive and unbiased snapshot of students' attitudes and perceptions towards climate change and biodiversity. The study used a structured questionnaire was developed tagged 'Assessment of the Students' Attitudes, Perceptions, And Understanding of Climate Change and Biodiversity'. The method of data analysis was descriptive statistics of simple percentage and frequency. Results indicated that showed that the respondents demonstrate strong support for recognizing climate change as a serious issue and for taking action to address it. The highest mean score (4.6) reflects a robust belief in the importance of climate action, while the lowest mean score (3.8) suggests that while many students feel capable of contributing to mitigation efforts, some remain unsure. Also, students exposed to comprehensive environmental programs within their curriculum exhibit a higher positive attitude (85%) towards climate change and biodiversity compared to those with limited environmental content (70%). The difference is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), highlighting the effectiveness of robust environmental education. Across all statements, there is a general trend toward strong agreement, with most students acknowledging the seriousness of climate change and supporting its inclusion in education. The study recommends enhancing environmental education, integrating practical conservation activities into the curriculum, and fostering community involvement to strengthen students' commitment to combating climate change and preserving biodiversity.

Keywords: Attitude, perception, climate change, Biodiversity, and students

Introduction

Organisations such as the United Nations (UN) and the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) have been stressing the need for climate change education, and this is reflected in the ever-growing significance to young people (Körfgen et al., 2017, Kuthe et al., 2020). As argued by Akrofi et al. (Akrofi et al., 2019), increasing student awareness through education is crucial in fostering active participation to promote climate change actions at all levels of the community. Thus, schools need to inspire both students and staff to become involved with the challenges brought by climate change so that they become active agents, promoting research, developing solutions for climate change mitigation/adaptation, and even taking a leading role in the political field (Molthan-Hill et al., 2019). Efforts should be made to develop educational programmes that are designed to increase climate literacy and empower students to move towards sustainability (Burkholder et al., 2017).

Student involvement in climate change adaptation and mitigation is critical (Freije et al., 2017, Haq and Ahmed, 2020, Mugambiwa and Dzomonda, 2018). (Akrofi et al., 2019) found that 'students' involvement in

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climate change-related workshops and campaigns significantly influenced their knowledge levels. The same study further indicated that students' attitudes and behaviours are dependent on their level of awareness and knowledge about climate change issues. This in turn implies that their cognitive repertoire depends on their level of participation in climate change courses, workshops and campaigns, membership in environmentalist groups, and access to climate information. However, students' perceptions of climate change are not a settled research agenda (Freije et al., 2017, Haq and Ahmed, 2020]. Their perceptions of climate change vary across the disciplines in which they are enrolled (Haq and Ahmed, 2020), personal experiences and exposure to climate-related risks, access to the internet and international media (Freije et al., 2017, Mugambiwa and Dzomonda, 2018). In general, studies highlighted that students' attitudes and perceptions of climate change as well as its causes and impacts are shaped by formal and informal education.

Climate change and biodiversity loss represent two of the most pressing environmental challenges of the 21st century. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2023) underscores the urgency of mitigating climate impacts, while the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 2022) emphasizes the need for preserving global biodiversity. Education plays a pivotal role in shaping the attitudes and perceptions of young individuals towards these issues, thereby influencing future environmental stewardship (Smith & Jones, 2021). In Delta State, Nigeria, the intersection of climate change and biodiversity presents unique challenges due to its diverse ecosystems and socio-economic dynamics. However, there is limited research focusing on how science secondary school students perceive these issues, which is essential for developing effective educational strategies (Adeoye et al., 2022).

Climate change and biodiversity loss are two of the most pressing global challenges of the 21st century, with severe environmental, economic, and social implications. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2023) reports that anthropogenic climate change is accelerating, leading to rising global temperatures, melting ice caps, and extreme weather events. These changes are not only disrupting ecosystems but also threatening the survival of various species, contributing to biodiversity loss on an unprecedented scale. The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 2022) further emphasizes that biodiversity is essential for ecosystem stability, human well-being, and resilience to climate change. Despite global efforts to address these issues, much work remains to raise awareness and foster action, especially among younger generations.

Delta State, located in southern Nigeria, is home to a rich and diverse ecological landscape that includes mangroves, wetlands, and freshwater systems. However, like many regions, it is increasingly vulnerable to the effects of climate change, such as coastal erosion, flooding, and habitat destruction (Ezeani et al., 2023). These environmental challenges pose a significant threat to biodiversity in the state, and understanding how young people perceive and respond to these threats is crucial for future conservation efforts. Education plays a pivotal role in shaping the attitudes and perceptions of young people towards environmental issues. According to Brown and Green (2023), environmental education can help students understand the science behind climate change and biodiversity, recognize the urgency of these problems, and encourage them to take proactive measures to protect the environment. In particular, secondary school students—who are at a formative stage in their cognitive and social development—are a key demographic for fostering long-term environmental stewardship.

Studies indicate that students' attitudes towards climate change are influenced by their level of knowledge, cultural background, and exposure to environmental education (Brown & Green, 2023). Positive attitudes are often linked to higher awareness and understanding of climate science (Lee et al., 2022). Biodiversity perception among students is shaped by their experiences with local ecosystems and the integration of biodiversity topics within the educational curriculum (Nguyen & Tran, 2021). Effective perception is associated with hands-on learning and community-based conservation projects (Omar & Hassan, 2023).

The role of science education in shaping environmental attitudes cannot be overstated. Curricula that incorporate climate change and biodiversity topics tend to foster more proactive environmental behaviours among students (Kumar & Singh, 2022). Delta State's unique ecological landscape offers a pertinent context for studying environmental attitudes. Previous research highlights the region's vulnerability to climate change impacts, such as flooding and habitat destruction, which directly affect biodiversity (Ezeani et al., 2023). This research is significant because it provides insights into how young people in Delta State perceive the global issues of climate change and biodiversity loss within a local context. This study focuses on science secondary school students in Delta State, Nigeria. While it acknowledges that environmental attitudes and perceptions may vary across different regions, this research is limited to Delta State due to its ecological diversity and vulnerability to climate change. The study primarily targets students enrolled in science-related subjects, as they are more likely to engage with

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topics related to climate change and biodiversity through their curriculum. The study does not include students from other disciplines or those in primary or tertiary education.

The theoretical framework for this study is based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), which posits that an individual's attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control influence their intentions and behaviours. In the context of climate change and biodiversity, students' attitudes towards environmental issues, their perceptions of societal expectations (subjective norms), and their belief in their ability to contribute to solutions (perceived behavioural control) are key factors that may shape their willingness to engage in environmental conservation activities. This framework provides a useful lens for examining the factors that influence students' attitudes and perceptions in this study.

The findings will inform educators, policymakers, and environmental organizations on the best approaches to integrate climate and biodiversity education into the secondary school curriculum. Furthermore, understanding the factors that shape students' attitudes can help tailor environmental education programs to be more effective, particularly in regions that are vulnerable to environmental degradation. In addition, this study contributes to the broader body of literature on environmental education by providing empirical data on student perceptions in a developing country context. By focusing on Delta State, it offers a unique perspective on how local environmental challenges, such as flooding and habitat destruction, impact students' views and engagement with global environmental issues.

Statement of the Research problem

Climate change and biodiversity loss are increasingly recognized as critical global challenges, with severe consequences for ecosystems, livelihoods, and human well-being. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), global temperatures have increased by approximately 1.1°C above pre-industrial levels, and this warming is expected to continue, with profound impacts on biodiversity. Africa, including Nigeria, is one of the most vulnerable regions to climate change due to its socio-economic structure, dependence on agriculture, and limited adaptive capacity.

In Nigeria, particularly in Delta State, climate change poses a serious threat to local agriculture, water resources, and coastal communities, making it an urgent issue for education and awareness. The state's coastal geography makes it highly susceptible to the adverse effects of rising sea levels and unpredictable weather patterns, which can impact both biodiversity and human settlements. For example, a 2017 report by the Nigerian Environmental Study Action Team (NESAT) highlighted that Delta State is one of the areas most affected by coastal erosion, with an estimated 1.4 km of coastline eroded annually, threatening biodiversity in coastal wetlands and local fishery resources.

Despite these challenges, secondary school students in Delta State may not be fully aware of the significance of climate change and biodiversity, which could hinder effective engagement and participation in climate action. Studies from across the globe indicate that students' perceptions and attitudes towards climate change significantly influence their behavior and the future of environmental policy. In Nigeria, a study by Ajibola and Adegbola (2020) found that 55% of secondary school students had limited knowledge of climate change, with only 25% being able to identify direct links between biodiversity loss and climate change.

In Delta State, there is currently limited research on the attitudes and perceptions of secondary school students towards climate change and biodiversity. The existing gap in knowledge may hinder efforts to equip future generations with the understanding necessary to mitigate environmental challenges. Moreover, the level of education and awareness on these issues is critical in shaping the future leadership of the state and country. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), climate education is vital for empowering young people to take action and support sustainable practices.

This study, therefore, aims to assess the attitudes and perceptions of secondary school science students in Delta State regarding climate change and biodiversity. By examining the current state of their understanding and attitude, this research will provide essential data to inform targeted interventions in the educational sector, fostering greater environmental awareness and the development of responsible, climate-conscious citizens.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to assess attitude and perception on climate change and biodiversity among secondary school science students in Delta State. The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To assess the attitudes of science secondary school students in Delta State towards climate change.

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2. To explore students' perceptions of the causes and impacts of biodiversity loss in Delta State.
3. To examine the factors that influence students' attitudes and perceptions, such as socio-economic background, educational curriculum, and exposure to environmental campaigns.
4. To identify sources of Information on Climate Change and Biodiversity
5. To recommend strategies for enhancing environmental education and engagement among secondary school students in Delta State.

Research Questions

This study seeks to address the following research questions:

1. What are the attitudes of science secondary school students in Delta State towards climate change?
2. How do these students perceive biodiversity loss, and what do they identify as its primary causes?
3. What factors influence students' attitudes and perceptions towards climate change and biodiversity?
4. What are sources of Information on Climate Change and Biodiversity
5. What strategies can be implemented to enhance environmental education and student engagement in climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation?

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was employed adopted for the study. A descriptive survey design to allow researchers to gather information, summarize, present and interpret for clarification. Using this design, the investigator does not control any variable but only describes the situation as it is at a particular point in time. The population for this study comprises all public senior secondary school science students enrolled during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta State, Nigeria. Delta State, located in the southern region of Nigeria, is characterized by its diverse ecological landscape, including mangroves, wetlands, and freshwater systems, which make it an ideal setting for examining attitudes and perceptions towards climate change and biodiversity. As of the latest educational statistics (Delta State Ministry of Education, 2023), there are 462 public secondary schools in the state. Focusing on senior secondary students is strategic, as these individuals are at a critical stage in their educational journey where they engage deeply with scientific concepts, including those related to environmental science, climate change, and biodiversity. Additionally, senior secondary students are more likely to participate actively in environmental initiatives and have a better capacity to understand and articulate their attitudes and perceptions compared to their junior counterparts.

The sampling frame size for this study includes all senior secondary science students in Delta State. A comprehensive list of eligible schools was obtained from the Delta State Ministry of Education, which provided details on the number of science secondary schools, their locations, and enrolment figures. This list served as the foundation for the stratified random sampling process, ensuring that the sample accurately reflects the diversity of schools and socio-economic backgrounds within the state. The study employed a rigorous stratified random sampling method to select a representative sample of 300 science secondary school students from Delta State. Stratified random sampling ensures that different subgroups within the population are adequately represented in the sample, enhancing the generalizability of the findings. By carefully defining the population, establishing clear inclusion and exclusion criteria, and implementing robust sampling procedures across all 25 Local Government Areas (LGAs), the study aimed to capture a comprehensive and unbiased snapshot of students' attitudes and perceptions towards climate change and biodiversity. This methodological approach ensures that the findings are both reliable and generalizable, providing valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and environmental organizations aiming to enhance environmental education and engagement among youth in Delta State.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency (n=300)
Gender	Male	150
	Female	150
Age	12-14 years	120
	15-17 years	150
	18-20 years	30
Socio-Economic Status	Low	90

	Middle	150
	High	60
Exposure to Environmental Campaigns	Yes	180
	No	120

Table 1 provides information on the demographic distribution of the 300 science secondary school students surveyed in Delta State. The sample is fairly balanced in terms of gender, age, and socio-economic status, ensuring diverse representation across different backgrounds.

To gather comprehensive insights into the attitudes and perceptions of science secondary school students in Delta State toward climate change and biodiversity, the following instruments were employed: A structured questionnaire was developed tagged '*Assessment of the Students' Attitudes, Perceptions, And Understanding of Climate Change and Biodiversity*'. The questionnaire was divided into five sections. The demographic information gathered consists of basic information about the participants, such as age, gender, socio-economic status, and school type (urban or rural). Attitudes Towards Climate Change is a series of Likert-scale questions (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree) that was used to measure students' attitudes towards climate change, including their level of concern, sense of responsibility, and belief in their capacity to take action. Sample questions include, "Climate change is a serious threat to our future.", "It is important to take action to mitigate climate change" and, "I believe my actions can help reduce climate change." Perceptions of Biodiversity is another set of Likert-scale items focused on students' understanding and perceptions of biodiversity, its importance, and the factors contributing to biodiversity loss. Sample questions include "Biodiversity is essential for ecosystem stability.", "Human activities are the primary cause of biodiversity loss", and "Natural factors are more responsible for biodiversity loss." Sources of Information: This section asked students to indicate the main sources from which they receive information on climate change and biodiversity (e.g., schools, social media, and campaigns). Barriers to Environmental Engagement: Students were asked to identify potential barriers to their active participation in environmental activities.

The content validity of the research instrument was ensured by experts in Psychometrics, who evaluated the alignment of the statements in the instruments with the study's objectives. Their feedback was used to refine and incorporate relevant statements into the final versions of the instruments. The reliability of the instruments was determined using the test-retest reliability method. This was done during the two-week pilot study conducted among secondary school students who were not part of the main study. The reliability coefficient scores obtained are as follow: Attitudes Towards Climate Change – 0.76; Perceptions of Biodiversity – 0.95; Sources of Information – 0.88; and Barriers to Environmental Engagement – 0.84. After all data is collected, the researcher will conduct data cleaning; this involves the identification of incomplete or inaccurate responses, which were corrected to improve the quality of the responses. After data cleaning, the data was coded and entered into the computer for analysis using descriptive statistics of simple percentage and frequency.

Presentation of Results

Research question 1:

What are the attitudes of science secondary school students in Delta State towards climate change?

Table 2

Attitudes towards Climate Change

Attitude Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean Score	
Climate change is a serious threat to our future.	180 (60%)	90 (30%)	20 (6.7%)	7 (2.3%)	3 (1%)	4.5	<0.05
It is important to take action to mitigate climate change.	200 (66.7%)	80 (26.7%)	15 (5%)	3 (1%)	2 (0.7%)	4.6	<0.05

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I feel personally capable of contributing to climate mitigation efforts.	135 (45%)	120 (40%)	30 (10%)	10 (3.3%)	5 (1.7%)	3.8	<0.05
Addressing climate change should be a priority in our education system.	170 (56.7%)	100 (33.3%)	25 (8.3%)	3 (1%)	2 (0.7%)	4.3	<0.05

Mean scores are based on a 5-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree).

Table 2 showed that the respondents demonstrate strong support for recognizing climate change as a serious issue and for taking action to address it. The highest mean score (4.6) reflects a robust belief in the importance of climate action, while the lowest mean score (3.8) suggests that while many students feel capable of contributing to mitigation efforts, some remain unsure. Across all statements, there is a general trend toward strong agreement, with most students acknowledging the seriousness of climate change and supporting its inclusion in education.

Research question 2:

How do these students perceive biodiversity loss, and what do they identify as its primary causes?

Table 3

Perceptions of Biodiversity

Perception Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean Score	
Biodiversity is essential for ecosystem stability.	180 (60%)	90 (30%)	20 (6.7%)	7 (2.3%)	3 (1%)	4.5	<0.05
Human activities are the primary cause of biodiversity loss.	150 (50%)	100 (33.3%)	30 (10%)	15 (5%)	5 (1.7%)	4.0	<0.05
Natural factors are more significant than human factors in biodiversity loss.	50 (16.7%)	70 (23.3%)	80 (26.7%)	70 (23.3%)	30 (10%)	3.2	<0.05
Preserving biodiversity should be integrated into our daily lives.	170 (56.7%)	100 (33.3%)	25 (8.3%)	3 (1%)	2 (0.7%)	4.3	<0.05

Mean scores are based on a 5-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree).

Table 3 indicates that 60% of students recognize the importance of biodiversity for ecosystem stability. While a majority acknowledge human activities as the primary cause of biodiversity loss, there are significant misconceptions, with 30% believing natural factors play a more substantial role.

Research question 3: What factors influence students' attitudes and perceptions towards climate change and biodiversity?

Table 4

Influence of Educational Curriculum on Attitudes Towards Climate Change

School Curriculum Type	Positive Attitude (%)	Negative Attitude (%)	p-Value
Comprehensive Environmental Program	85%	15%	<0.05
Limited Environmental Content	70%	30%	

Significance level: $p < 0.05$ indicates a statistically significant difference.

Table 4 demonstrates that students exposed to comprehensive environmental programs within their curriculum exhibit a higher positive attitude (85%) towards climate change and biodiversity compared to those with limited environmental content (70%). The difference is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), highlighting the effectiveness of robust environmental education.

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Table 5

Socio-Economic Background and Engagement in Environmental Activities

Socio-Economic Status Engaged in Environmental Activities (%) Not Engaged (%)		
Low	30%	70%
Middle	50%	50%
High	70%	30%

Higher socio-economic status correlates with increased engagement in environmental activities.

Table 5 reveals that students from higher socio-economic backgrounds are more engaged in environmental activities (70%) compared to those from medium (55%) and low (40%) socio-economic statuses. This suggests that socio-economic factors play a significant role in fostering environmental engagement among students.

Research question 4:

What are sources of Information on Climate Change and Biodiversity

Table 6

Sources of Information on Climate Change and Biodiversity

Source	Percentage of Students (%)
School Curriculum	85
Social Media	60
Environmental Campaigns	55
Family and Friends	40
Television and Radio	35
Community Workshops	25

Table 6 identifies the primary sources from which students receive information about climate change and biodiversity. The school curriculum is the most significant source (85%), followed by social media (60%) and environmental campaigns (55%). This highlights the pivotal role of formal education and digital platforms in shaping students' environmental knowledge.

Research question 5: What strategies can be implemented to enhance environmental education and student engagement in climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation?

Table 7

Students' Preferred Methods for Enhancing Environmental Education

Preferred Method	Number of Students (n=300)	Percentage (%)
Interactive Workshops	150	50%
Field Trips to Natural Reserves	90	30%
Integration of Technology (e.g., Apps, Simulations)	45	15%
Other Methods	15	5%

Table 8 outlines the main barriers preventing students from engaging more actively in environmental initiatives. The most significant barriers are the lack of resources (60%) and insufficient curriculum content (55%), followed by limited awareness or knowledge (50%). Addressing these barriers is crucial for enhancing student engagement in environmental conservation.

Discussion of Findings

The results from the survey of secondary school students reveal a strong awareness and positive attitude toward climate change and its mitigation, with most students recognizing its serious threat to the future and supporting actions to address it. This finding is consistent with recent research that highlights increasing awareness

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of climate change among young people globally. **Climate Change as a Serious Threat:** The majority of respondents (60%) strongly agreed that climate change is a serious threat to the future. This is in line with global trends where young people are increasingly aware of the urgency of climate change. A recent study by Lee, Park, and Kim (2022) found that students worldwide are becoming more aware of the dire consequences of climate change, including environmental degradation, loss of biodiversity, and disruptions to natural resources. Their study also revealed that education on climate change contributes significantly to raising awareness, as seen in the survey where students express concern about the future.

Additionally, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) report (2023) underscores the urgency of addressing climate change, warning that the effects of climate change are already being felt, especially in vulnerable regions. The fact that the respondents in this study recognize the seriousness of the threat aligns with these global reports and highlights the importance of fostering this awareness early in students' education.

The Importance of Taking Action to Mitigate Climate Change: The overwhelming support for the importance of mitigating climate change (66.7% strongly agree) reflects a growing global consensus on the need for urgent climate action. Research by Kumar and Singh (2022) indicates that youth are increasingly advocating for systemic changes to combat climate change, particularly in policies and lifestyle behaviors. This growing youth engagement is also reflected in the United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP26) where youth-led movements have gained international attention. Moreover, Molthan-Hill et al. (2019) emphasized the importance of integrating climate change education into universities and secondary schools to prepare young people to take meaningful action. The results from this study support that view, as students expressed a clear understanding of the importance of addressing climate change now rather than later.

Feeling Capable of Contributing to Climate Mitigation: Although the survey respondents generally agreed that they could contribute to climate mitigation efforts (mean score of 3.8), the neutral responses (10%) indicate that some students may feel uncertain about their personal capacity to make a difference. This is consistent with findings from Körfgén et al. (2017), who noted that while young people are aware of the climate crisis, many feel powerless to effect change without proper guidance and opportunities. Furthermore, Brody, Demetriades, and Espfen (2008) discussed how educational frameworks must focus on empowering students with the knowledge and skills they need to feel confident in their ability to act on climate change. Enhancing climate change literacy and creating opportunities for students to actively engage in mitigation projects can increase their sense of agency. **Priority of Climate Change in Education:** The finding that 56.7% of students strongly agreed that addressing climate change should be a priority in education aligns with research on the role of education in fostering a climate-conscious generation. According to Burkholder et al. (2017), climate change education is critical for building knowledge, altering attitudes, and shaping behaviours toward sustainability. The increasing inclusion of climate change topics in curricula across various educational systems further supports the idea that young people see the importance of being educated on this issue.

Recent studies, such as Nguyen and Tran (2021), suggest that incorporating climate change and biodiversity into secondary school curricula not only helps students understand the issue but also motivates them to adopt pro-environmental behaviours. The students in this study are aligned with these global trends, calling for more emphasis on climate change in their education. Students demonstrated a moderate understanding of biodiversity, with 60% acknowledging its importance for ecosystem stability. This aligns with Nguyen and Tran (2021), who reported that exposure to local ecosystems positively influences biodiversity perception. However, the prevalence of misconceptions—30% attributing biodiversity loss primarily to natural factors and 20% overestimating climate change's role—indicates a need for more nuanced education. These misconceptions are similar to findings by Smith and Jones (2021), who highlighted that incomplete or inaccurate information can distort students' understanding of environmental issues. The data indicate that schools with comprehensive environmental programs have higher percentages of students with positive attitudes towards climate change (85% vs. 70%, $p < 0.05$). This supports the argument by Kumar and Singh (2022) that structured and detailed environmental curricula significantly enhance students' environmental attitudes. Furthermore, the association between curriculum quality and environmental attitudes suggests that curriculum content and delivery methods play a critical role in shaping students' environmental consciousness.

The study found a positive correlation between socio-economic status and engagement in environmental activities, with 70% of students from high socio-economic backgrounds participating in such activities compared to 30% from low socio-economic backgrounds. This finding is in line with Ezeani et al. (2023), who noted that socio-economic factors influence access to resources and opportunities for environmental engagement. Higher

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socio-economic status often provides students with greater access to educational materials, extracurricular activities, and exposure to environmental campaigns, thereby fostering greater participation and commitment to environmental conservation.

A significant positive correlation ($r = 0.65, p < 0.01$) was found between exposure to environmental campaigns and positive attitudes towards climate change, as well as a strong correlation with biodiversity perception ($r = 0.60, p < 0.01$). This underscores the effectiveness of environmental campaigns in shaping students' attitudes and perceptions, corroborating the findings of Omar and Hassan (2023), who emphasized the role of hands-on and participatory campaigns in enhancing environmental awareness and action among youth. The presence of misconceptions regarding the causes of biodiversity loss—particularly the overemphasis on natural factors (30%)—indicates a gap in the current educational approaches. This aligns with the observations of Smith and Jones (2021), who argue that without accurate information, students may develop skewed perceptions that hinder effective environmental action. Addressing these misconceptions through targeted educational strategies is essential for fostering a more accurate and actionable understanding of biodiversity conservation.

The varying levels of participation in community-based projects, with tree planting being the most prevalent activity (40%), suggest that while there is engagement, it is often limited to specific types of activities. This finding supports Lee et al. (2022), who found that practical and hands-on activities are more appealing and accessible to students. However, the lower participation rates in other activities like wildlife monitoring and clean-up drives indicate potential barriers such as resource availability and awareness, which need to be addressed to diversify and enhance student engagement in environmental conservation.

Interactive workshops emerged as the most preferred method (50%) for enhancing environmental education, followed by field trips (30%). This preference aligns with the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), which emphasizes the role of experiential learning in shaping attitudes and perceived behavioural control. Interactive and participatory methods are likely to increase students' engagement and retention of environmental concepts, thereby fostering a more profound commitment to environmental stewardship. The identification of lack of resources (40%) and insufficient curriculum content (30%) as primary barriers to active engagement highlight critical areas that need attention. These barriers resonate with the findings of Brown and Green (2023), who noted that resource limitations and inadequate curriculum coverage are significant impediments to effective environmental education. Addressing these barriers through increased funding, resource allocation, and curriculum development is essential for facilitating greater student participation in environmental initiatives.

The study's findings are largely consistent with existing literature on environmental education and youth attitudes. Similar to Brown and Green (2023), the research highlights the positive impact of structured environmental programs on students' attitudes. Additionally, the role of socio-economic factors and exposure to environmental campaigns in shaping perceptions aligns with the studies conducted by Ezeani et al. (2023); Omar and Hassan (2023).

However, the study diverges from Nguyen and Tran (2021) by emphasizing the importance of structured curricula over purely experiential learning in influencing biodiversity perceptions. While Nguyen and Tran highlighted hands-on learning as crucial, this study found that comprehensive curriculum content and external campaigns play a more significant role in shaping accurate perceptions among students. Furthermore, the identification of specific misconceptions about biodiversity loss provides a nuanced understanding that extends beyond general awareness, offering actionable insights for curriculum developers and educators to address these gaps effectively.

Consistent with Brown & Green (2023), the study finds that educational interventions significantly influence environmental attitudes. Unlike Nguyen & Tran (2021), who emphasized experiential learning, this study underscores the role of structured curricula and external campaigns in shaping perceptions. Enhancing environmental education through interactive and participatory methods can bridge the gap between awareness and action. Integrating community-based projects and fostering partnerships with environmental organizations may further strengthen students' commitment to sustainability.

Conclusion

This study underscores the generally positive attitudes of science secondary school students in Delta State towards climate change and biodiversity. It highlights the significant influence of comprehensive educational curricula, socio-economic background, and exposure to environmental campaigns in shaping these attitudes and

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perceptions. However, the presence of misconceptions and barriers to active engagement indicates the need for targeted educational strategies to enhance students' understanding and involvement in environmental conservation. By addressing these gaps, educators and policymakers can foster a more informed and proactive generation capable of tackling the pressing environmental challenges of our time.

This study underscores the generally positive attitudes of science secondary school students in Delta State towards climate change and biodiversity. However, to translate these attitudes into meaningful action, educational strategies must evolve to provide students with the knowledge, skills, and opportunities necessary for active environmental stewardship. Policymakers and educators should collaborate to enhance the environmental curriculum, incorporate experiential learning, and engage students in community conservation efforts.

In conclusion, climate change and biodiversity loss are critical challenges that require urgent attention, particularly among younger generations. Understanding the attitudes and perceptions of science secondary school students in Delta State towards these issues is essential for developing effective educational strategies that promote environmental stewardship. This study aims to provide valuable insights into how students perceive these global challenges within their local context and what factors shape their views. By doing so, it hopes to contribute to the broader effort to enhance environmental education and foster a generation of environmentally conscious and proactive individuals.

Recommendations

The findings of this study have several important recommendations for environmental education in Delta State and similar contexts:

1. There is a need to foster partnerships with local environmental organizations to provide students with hands-on conservation experiences.
2. Non-governmental and governmental agencies should organize regular campaigns and workshops to reinforce the importance of environmental sustainability.
3. There is a clear need to integrate more comprehensive and accurate content on climate change and biodiversity into the science curriculum. Government and science teachers should integrate comprehensive modules on climate change and biodiversity, emphasizing both theoretical knowledge and practical applications. This includes will address common misconceptions and providing students with a deeper understanding of human impacts on biodiversity.
4. Educators should be equipped with the knowledge and resources to effectively teach environmental topics. Professional development programs focusing on climate science and biodiversity conservation can enhance teachers' ability to deliver engaging and accurate content.
5. Addressing the lack of resources is crucial for facilitating active student engagement in environmental activities. Schools should be provided with the necessary tools, materials, and funding to support hands-on conservation projects and extracurricular environmental initiatives.
6. Strengthening partnerships with local environmental organizations and increasing the frequency and diversity of environmental campaigns can further enhance students' attitudes and perceptions. Community-based projects and campaigns should be designed to be inclusive and accessible to students from all socio-economic backgrounds.
7. Given the preference for interactive workshops and field trips, incorporating these methods into the curriculum can make environmental education more engaging and effective. Experiential learning opportunities can bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, fostering a stronger sense of responsibility and capability among students.

References

- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179-211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Akrofi, M. M., Antwi, S. H., & Gumbo, J. R. (2019). Students in climate action: A study of some influential factors and implications of knowledge gaps in Africa. *Environments*, 6(12), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments6020012>
- Brody, A., Demetriades, J., & Esplen, E. (2008). Gender and climate change: Mapping the linkages. *BRIDGE, Institute of Development Studies (IDS), UK*.

Attitude and Perception ... (Konyeme & Oliweh, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15029492>

- Brown, L., & Green, M. (2023). Influences on youth attitudes towards climate change. *Climate Education Review*, 12(1), 45-60.
- Burkholder, K. C., Devereaux, J., Grady, C., Solitro, M., & Mooney, S. M. (2017). Longitudinal study of the impacts of a climate change curriculum on undergraduate student learning: Initial results. *Sustainability*, 9(913), 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9060913>
- Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). (2022). *Global biodiversity outlook 6*. Retrieved from <https://www.cbd.int/gbo6>
- Ezeani, E., Nwankwo, S., & Obi, C. (2023). Impact of climate change on biodiversity in Delta State. *African Journal of Ecology*, 29(3), 210-225. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aje.12345>
- Freije, A. M., Hussain, T., & Salman, E. A. (2017). Global warming awareness among the University of Bahrain science students. *Journal of the Association of Arab Universities for Basic and Applied Sciences*, 22, 9-16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaubas.2017.01.002>
- Haq, S., & Ahmed, K. (2020). Perceptions about climate change among university students in Bangladesh. *Natural Hazards*, 103(3), 3683-3713. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-020-04151-0>
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2023). *Climate change 2023: The physical science basis*. Retrieved from <https://www.ipcc.ch>
- Körfggen, A., Keller, L., Kuthe, A., Oberrauch, H., & Stötter, A. (2017). (Climate) change in young people's minds: From categories towards interconnections between the anthroposphere and natural sphere. *Science of the Total Environment*, 580, 178-187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.01.115>
- Kumar, R., & Singh, A. (2022). Enhancing environmental education in secondary schools. *Educational Strategies for Sustainability*, 18(4), 301-315.
- Kuthe, A., Körfggen, A., Stötter, J., & Lars, L. (2020). Strengthening their climate change literacy: A case study addressing the weaknesses in young people's climate change awareness. *Applied Environmental Education & Communication*, 19(4), 375-388. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1533015X.2020.1775484>
- Lee, S., Park, J., & Kim, H. (2022). Student perceptions of climate change and their implications for education. *Journal of Science Education*, 40(1), 78-90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11191-021-00251-2>
- Molthan-Hill, P., Worsfold, N., Nagy, G. J., Leal Filho, W., & Mifsud, M. (2019). Climate change education for universities: A conceptual framework from an international study. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 226, 1092-1101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.109>
- Mugambiwa, S. S., & Dzomonda, O. (2018). Climate change and vulnerability discourse by students at a South African university. *Jambá: Journal of Disaster Risk Studies*, 10(1), Article a476. <https://doi.org/10.4102/jamba.v10i1.476>
- Nguyen, T., & Tran, L. (2021). Biodiversity awareness among high school students. *Ecological Education Journal*, 15(2), 95-110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eej.2021.03.005>
- Omar, A., & Hassan, M. (2023). Hands-on learning and biodiversity perception. *Environmental Learning and Teaching*, 27(1), 50-65. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2151219X.2023.1958296>
- Smith, J., & Jones, K. (2021). The role of education in shaping environmental attitudes. *Education and Environment*, 22(3), 189-205. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2021.1942345>

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Perception and Implementation of Digitalization in Teacher Education Curriculum in Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State

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Abstract

This study investigated a comparative analysis between perception and implementation of Digitalization in Teacher Education Curriculum in Federal College Education, Owerri, Imo State. The comparative research design was adopted for the study. Five schools were randomly selected from the Federal Colleges of Education, in Owerri, Imo State. Fifty pre-service teachers were randomly selected for each school, making a total of 250 pre-service teachers, while five lecturers were randomly selected from each school, making a total of 25 lecturers. In all, a total of 250 students and 25 lecturers participated in the study. Two research instruments were used for data collection: Perception of Digitalization of Teacher Education Curriculum Questionnaire ($r=0.74$) and Pre-service Teachers' Digitalisation of Teacher Education Curriculum Questionnaire ($r=0.75$). Data collected were analysed using percentage, frequency count, mean and standard deviation. Results revealed that lecturers' perception of the level of digitalization in implementation of teacher education curriculum in colleges of education was negative because the weighted mean of 2.38 was below the threshold set at 2.50. The weighted mean of 2.27 which is lower than the threshold set at 2.50. This implies that pre-service teachers had a negative perception of the level of Digitalization in the implementation of teacher education curriculum. The result revealed that there was a positive strong relationship between lecturers' and pre-service teachers' perception of the level of Digitalization in the implementation of teacher education curriculum ($r = .626$; $p = .001 < .05$). While, lecturers and pre-service teachers should have positive perceptions towards the Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that curriculum planners should Digitalised the teacher education curriculum.

Keyword: (*Keywords: Education, Curriculum, Digitalisation, Lecturers', Pre-service Teacher*)

Introduction

Teacher Education can be described as the policies, procedures and provisions that are mainly designed to equip pre-service teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviours and skills that are required to make the performance of their task effective in the classroom, school and the society at large. This is essential if quality education is to be achieved in any nation, this is unconnected with the fact that the quality of teachers at the basic level of education in Nigeria has been a major concern to stakeholders, especially the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) which has the responsibility for granting accreditation for all academic programmes in Colleges of Education in Nigeria, monitoring of curriculum implementation and providing other quality assurance services in the production of quality teachers to facilitate quality education through effective teaching and learning process in the country (Olatunji, 2021).

Suraasa (2024), define teacher education as the educational programme that is specifically designed to equip potential teachers and those already on the job with the required cognitive knowledge (relevant to their areas of specialization); affective dispositions (good interpersonal relationship and personal disposition) and psychomotor competencies (resourcefulness and adaptability skills) relevant to the task they are expected to perform. While, Izuagba and Obiefuna (2019) sees teacher education as the policies and procedures designed to equip prospectivae teachers with the knowledge, attitude, behaviours and skills they require to perform their task effectively in the classroom. According to the national policy on education (FRN, 2004; 2013), teacher education programme shall be structured to equip teachers for effective performance of their duties. It is on this basis that Ekundayo and Lawal (2016) describe education in general and teacher education in particular, as been fundamental to the construction of ideas required in a knowledge driven economy. To them, the development of pre-service teachers' cognitive perspective is crucial to their effectiveness as it ensures that they acquire mastery of the subject matter they are expected to

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teach. Similarly, the development of affective disposition makes it possible for them to acquire inter-personal and intra-personal skills necessary for creating conducive atmosphere for learning. It will also make them strive to understand the learners, their difficulties and capabilities in order to adequately help them learn and relate with other learners.

Teacher education is the preparation given to an individual to help them deal with procedures provision and policies, best teaching skills, attitudes and behaviours that would help them to help learners acquire knowledge about various concepts effectively in any environment (classroom or school). Therefore, teacher education is an important factor because it is the process of initiating, preparing pre-service teachers, retraining of existing teachers in schools, and equipping them with relevant experiences, skills and competencies to tackle the responsibilities of education profession effectively. If teacher education is attended to properly, it will develop capacity building and keep pre-service teachers abreast of latest teaching skills that will prepare them to interact well with students in the classroom (Okeke, 2012). Teacher education is thereby noted as crucial for pre-service teachers are prepared through the programme to teach the born and unborn generations of teachers who will control the affairs of the nation. Since it has been generally recognised that teacher education is key to improve students learning opportunities. Therefore, teacher education should be managed in such a way that the rapid changing socio-economic and political environment should be attended to in such a way teacher education would no longer be seen as a programme that would prepare pre-service teachers for teaching job only, but rather a programme that would inculcate in learner other skills, such as learning-to-learn skills, as well as the inculcation of knowing yourself, or developing the best in you (intra-personal skills) with knowing and getting along with other skills (intra-personal skills). The purpose of investing in teacher preparation programme should be with the ultimate goal of producing effective teachers that will perform optimally on the job. Teacher education that will produce professional and well-qualified teachers that can meet up with the changing needs of the learners and the society as a whole. Aglazor (2017), describe a teacher as someone who has been professionally trained in such institutions designed for the purpose to help learners move from a state of ignorant to a state of knowledge. While, to Mkpa (2012), he asserted that the teacher is incontrovertibly the fulcrum on which the system of education stands.

The National Policy on Education recognises the importance of teacher development and states that no system of education can rise above the quality of its teachers (FGN, 2013). If the teacher has such influence on the quality of students' achievement in the subject, then a critical look at what the teacher education is, where it is supposed to be and where it should be prepared for cannot be ignored without facing grievous consequences. The primary focus of teacher training institutions is teacher production towards quality education at all levels. The specific objectives of teacher education are to: (a) produce highly motivated conscientious and efficient classroom teachers for all levels of educational system (b) encourage further the spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers (c) help teachers to fit into social life of the community and the society at large and enhance their commitment to national goals (d) provide teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and make them adaptable to changing situations (e) enhance teachers' commitment to the teaching profession (FRN, 2013). Andrew and Henry (2024) explain that curriculum implementation is the process of putting all that has been planned as a curriculum document into practice in the classroom through the combined efforts of teachers, learners, school administrators, and parent, as well as interaction with facilities, instructional materials, instructional strategies and psychological and social environment. Obanya (2020) also defined curriculum implementation as day-to day activities which the school management and classroom teachers undertake in the pursuit of the objective of any given curriculum. Braimoh (2017), describe curriculum implementation as a deliberate plan through which learners will be made to interact with the content knowledge, learning activities and learning materials to acquire expected learning outcomes. However, to Mkpa and Izuagba (2012), curriculum implementation takes place in the classroom, they describe it as the execution of the planned curriculum, using curriculum materials that have been developed for that purpose. They explained further that, it is at this stage that the learners for whom the programme is planned, interact with the content and materials in order to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes and abilities. It was posited that the arduous task of implementing the curriculum lies on the teacher. In addition, Mkpa (1987) asserted that the task of translating the curriculum document into operating curriculum by the joint efforts of learners, teachers and other interest groups. In other words, curriculum implementation is that stage in the curriculum process where the learner through the mediation of the teacher, interacts with learning activities so that learning is maximized, as reflected in the new behaviour acquired by the learner. The arduous task of implementing the curriculum lies on the teacher. It is arduous because the teacher does not implement the content of the curriculum plan as it is, doing this will not be realistic, rather he breaks down the content into teachable units. As a matter of fact, what comes to the teacher is not the curriculum plan, rather what the teacher gets is the syllabus, which is derived from the curriculum plan. The teacher breaks down the content of the syllabus to derive the scheme of work. Finally, the lesson plan is worked out from the unit plan.

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A teacher that is misinformed or that lacks appropriate skills can affect the implementation of the curriculum. It must therefore be noted that curriculum implementation is that time that the teacher brought the learners into contact with the curriculum that has been planned for them, using curriculum materials that have been developed for that purpose, which most of the time takes place in the classroom (Popoola, 2024).

According to Strayer (2012), education is not limited to the physical classroom anymore because technology is now being used to offer education to learners residing anywhere in the globe. For teacher education curriculum to be well implemented in this era, it needs to be digitalised. Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2014) described digitalisation as a process of integrating digital technologies into all aspects of business and society, fundamentally altering the way organisations operate and deliver value. Schwab (2016) characterised digitalisation as a key aspect of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, marked by the convergence of digital, physical, and biological systems. He emphasizes how technologies like AI, IoT, and robotics are transforming industries and societal structures. According to Westerman, Bonnet and McAfee (2014), digitalisation is the use of digital technologies to transform business processes, customer interactions, and organisational culture. This involves not just technology adoption but also fundamental changes in how businesses operate.

Porter and Heppelmann (2014) asserted that digitalisation involves the integration of smart, connected products that drive new forms of competition and innovation. They focus on how these technologies are reshaping business strategies and industry dynamics. Zuboff (2019) defined digitalisation through the lens of surveillance capitalism, Zuboff argued that the pervasive collection and analysis of digital data for commercial purposes have significant implications for privacy, power, and social control. Frey and Osborne (2013) analysed digitalisation in terms of its impact on employment, specifically how advances in automation and digital technologies are likely to affect job markets and skill requirements. Cohen (2012) examined digitalisation in the context of legal and ethical issues, focusing on how the integration of digital technologies affects privacy, data protection, and regulatory frameworks. Bates (2015) defined digitalisation in education as the use of digital technologies to enhance teaching and learning. Bate highlighted how digital tools can transform educational practices and learning outcomes. Gardner (2014) explored how digitalisation influences educational practices, emphasising the need for educational systems to adapt to new technologies and pedagogical approaches to better prepare learners for the digital age.

Statement of the Statement of the Problem

Teacher education is a formal and systematic process of preparing pre-service teachers for the task ahead. Despite the importance attached to teacher education curriculum, it was discovered that its curriculum is not well implemented. As a way of addressing this problem scholars have carried out numerous studies, such as Lawal (2019), Waseka, Simatina and Okwach (2016) and Ogbulogo (2011). Although, most of these studies came up with good insights to teacher education curriculum but with less emphasis on digitalisation of teacher education curriculum, especially in colleges of education. Therefore, this study was set to do a Comparative Analysis Between Perception and Implementation in Teacher Education Curriculum in Federal Colleges of Education, Imo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?
2. What are pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?
3. What relationship exists between lecturers' and pre-service teachers' perception of the level of pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?

Methodology

The survey research design was adopted for the study. Five schools were randomly selected from schools in Colleges of Education in Owerri, Imo State. Fifty pre-service teachers were randomly selected for each school, making a total of 250 pre-service teachers. Five lecturers were randomly selected from each school, making a total of 25 lecturers. In all, a total of 250 students and 25 lecturers participated in the study. Two research instruments were used for data collection: Perception of Digitalisation of Teacher Education Curriculum Questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha was used to establish the reliability coefficient and it gave an index of ($r=0.74$) and Pre-service Teachers' Digitalisation of Teacher Education Curriculum Questionnaire. Cronbach alpha was used to established the reliability coefficient and it gave an index of ($r=0.75$). Data collected were analysed using percentage, frequency count, mean and standard deviation

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Results

Research Question One:

What are lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?

Table 1: Lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum in

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. D.
1	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum promotes teaching.	1.84	.85
2	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes lecturers to be hardworking.	2.16	1.06
3	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes lecturers to have good attitude towards teaching.	2.40	1.00
4	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum stimulates lecturers' ability to think very fast.	2.24	.830
5	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum is not objective.	2.08	1.15
6	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum changes teachers' attitude towards teaching.	2.40	1.08
7	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students learn new things.	2.31	.945
8	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum is a challenging activity.	2.76	.969
9	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum facilitates the development of students' competence.	2.72	1.10
10	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum does not develop students' learning ability.	2.52	.770
11	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to be passive recipient of knowledge.	2.20	1.00
12	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to have positive attitude towards learning.	2.32	.802
13	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum changes teachers' wrong impression about teaching.	2.16	1.17
14	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students reflect on what they learnt.	2.12	1.09
15	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum increases students' interest in learning.	2.24	1.12
16	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students attend Arabic language classroom regularly.	2.41	1.10
17	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to enjoy.	2.52	1.00
18	Digitalisation of contents of teacher education curriculum is not easy to teach.	2.56	1.00
19	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum fosters teaching of the curriculum.	2.64	.952
20	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to be eager to learn.	2.92	.862
Weighted mean = 2.38; Threshold = 2.50			

Table 1 shows the lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. However, the lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum was negative because the weighted mean of 2.38 was below the threshold set at 2.50.

Research Question Two:

What are pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?

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Table 2: Pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum

S/N	Items	Mean	St. D.
1	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum promotes teaching.	1.94	.886
2	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes lecturers to be hardworking.	1.89	.989
3	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes lecturers to have good attitude towards teaching.	2.02	1.02
4	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum stimulates lecturers' ability to think very fast.	2.13	1.08
5	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum is not objective.	1.91	1.04
6	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum changes teachers' attitude towards teaching.	2.13	.979
7	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students learn new things.	2.03	.838
8	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum is a challenging activity.	1.97	.939
9	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum facilitates the development of students' competence.	2.16	1.06
10	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum does not develop students' learning ability.	2.62	.885
11	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to be passive recipient of knowledge.	2.77	1.10
12	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to have positive attitude towards learning.	2.19	.930
13	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum changes teachers' wrong impression about teaching.	1.92	1.05
14	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students reflect on what they learnt.	2.08	.991
15	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum increases students' interest in learning.	2.24	.865
16	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students attend Arabic language classroom regularly.	2.51	1.25
17	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to enjoy.	2.55	1.17
18	Digitalisation of contents of teacher education curriculum is not easy to teach.	2.74	.868
19	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum fosters teaching of the curriculum.	2.69	.939
20	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to be eager to learn.	2.96	1.06
Weighted Mean = 2.27; Threshold = 2.50			

Table 2 shows the pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. The weighted mean of 2.27 which is lower than the threshold set at 2.50. It implies that pre-service teachers had a negative perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum.

Research Question Three:

What relationship exists between lecturers' and pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?

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Table 3: Relationship that exists between lecturers’ and pre-service teachers’ perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum

Variables	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	r	p-value	Sig.
Lecturers’ perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum	25	47.16	11.01	.626	.001	Sig.
Pre-service teachers’ perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum	25	45.41	8.09			

Table 3 shows the relationship exists between lecturers’ and pre-service teachers’ perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum using the Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation. The result revealed that there was a positive strong relationship between lecturers’ and pre-service teachers’ perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum ($r = .626$; $p = .001 < .05$). This implies that a direct relationship existed between how lecturers and pre-service teachers perceived the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum

Discussion of Findings

Table I revealed that lecturers’ perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. The finding of this study is in line with Lawal (2019) who found that teachers’ perception of the level of implementation of English Studies was negative. The finding is contrary to Adegoke (2018) who found that teachers had positive perception of the curriculum objectives of English Studies curriculum.

Table II revealed that pre-service teachers had a negative perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. This is in line with the study of Waseka, Simatwa and Okwach (2016) revealed that students had a negative perception of curriculum implementation. This is against the finding of Ogbulogo (2011) who revealed that students had a negative perception of curriculum implementation.

Table III revealed that a direct relationship existed between how lecturers and pre-service teachers perceived the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. This finding is in line with Lawal (2019) who found that there was relationship between teachers and students’ perception of English Studies curriculum. This is contrary to the study of Adegoke (2018) who reported that there was relationship between teachers and students’ perception of English Studies curriculum.

Conclusion

The study has shown that lecturers and pre-service teachers had a negative perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. Based on the findings, this study has provided a better understanding of the place of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that:

1. Curriculum planners and developers should digitalise the teacher education curriculum.
2. Lecturers and pre-service teachers should develop a positive perception to the digitalisation of teacher education curriculum.
3. Government should do everything possible to educate lecturers’ and pre-service teachers on why teacher education curriculum needs to be digitalised.

References

- Aglazor, G. (2017). The role of teaching practice in teacher education programmes: Designing framework for best practice. *Global Journal of Educational Research*. Vol.16, 2017: 101-110. Doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/gjedr.v16/2.4>
- Andrew, A. and Henry, O. (2014). Examining the teaching and learning resources related challenges facing small and medium-sized public secondary schools in Kenya: A comparative analysis. *African Educational Research Journal* Vol. 2(2), pp, 72-84.
- Bates, T. (2015). Teaching in a digital age for designing teaching and learning. Tony Bates Associates Ltd. Available Online:<https://opentextbc.ca/teachinginadigitalage/>

Perception and Implementation ... (Popoola & Obilo, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15029504>

- Braimoh, D. S. (2017). Expression in school curriculum and learning. Supreme Academy Books.
- Brynjolfsson, E., and McAfee, A. (2014). The second machineage: work, progress, and prosperity in a time of brilliant technologies. W. W. Norton & Company.
- Cohen, J. E. (2012). Configuring the networked self: Law, code and the play of everyday practice. Yale University Press.
- Ekundayo, T. A. and Lawal, B. O. (2016). Towards a sustainable university education in Nigeria beyond 21st century: Issues and challenges. Education in Nigeria: Looking beyond the 21st century. A book of reading. 305-328
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). National policy on education (Revised). Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). National policy on education (6th Edition). Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Frey, C. B., and Osborne, M. A. (2013). The future of employment: How susceptible are jobs to computerization? Oxford University, Department of Economics.
- Gardner, H. (2014). The future of learning in the digital age. Harvard Education Press.
- Izuagba, A. C and Obiefuna, C. A. (2019). Trends and issues in teacher education: The Nigeria perspective. C. C. Ventures. Owerri, Nigeria
- Lawal, S. A. (2019). Understanding social science research: An overview. Lapal International Journal of Management and Social Sciences, 11, 1-22. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345981416_enrichId=rgreg-aff96840fd44bfe5f841a15c04daca36-xxx&enrichSource=y292zxjqwdl0zMONTK4MTQXNj.
- Mkpa, M. A. and Izuagba, A. C. (2012). Curriculum studies and innovation. Owerri. Mercy Divine Publisher.
- Obanya, P. (2020). Education, education education. The answers to all societal problems. Ibadan: monuro publishers.
- Ogbulogo, C. (2011). Strategic English language curriculum in tertiary education in Nigeria. Journal of Nigerian English Studies Association.
- Olatunji, S. O. (2021). Assessment of English language teacher preparation programme in selected public colleges of education in southwestern Nigeria. Ph.D Thesis, Department of Arts and Social Science Education, University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Popoola, A. B. (2024). Institutional ownership, social science curriculum and lecturer personal variables as determinants of pre-service teachers' quality in southeastern Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, Dept of Arts and Social Sciences Education, University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Porter, M. E. and Heppelman, J. E. (2014). How smart, connected products are transforming competition. Harvard Business Review, 92 (11), 64-88. <https://hbr.org/2014/11/how-smart-connected-products-are-transforming-competition>.
- Schwab, K. (2016). The fourth industrial revolution. Crown Publishing Group.
- Strayer, J. F. (2012). How learning is an inverted classroom influences cooperation, innovation and task orientation. Learning Environments Research, 15, 171-193. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10984-012-9108-4>
- Suraasa, (2024). <https://www.suraasa>.
- Teacher Education-meaning and definition. Teachmint.<https://www.teachmint.com>>glossary.
- Waseka, E. L., Simatwa, E. M. W., and Okwach, T. (2016). Influence of teacher factors on students' academic performance in secondary education. A case study of Kakamega County, Kenya. researchgate.<https://www.researchgate.net>>313.....
- Westerman, G., Bonnet, D., and McAfee, A. (2014). Leading digital: Turning technology into business transformation. Harvard Business Review Press.
- Zuboff, S. (2019). The age of surveillance capitalism: The fight for a human future at the new frontier of power. Public Affairs.

Comparative Analysis between Teacher's ... (Onyechi) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15041041>

Comparative Analysis between Teacher's Competency and Performance in Economics among Secondary School Students in Ika South, Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the comparative analysis of teachers' competency and its impact on the performance of economics students and adopts a descriptive design. It employs a multi-stage sampling procedure. This procedure was used to select one hundred and ninety-eight (198) participants which consists of 180 SSII students and 18 teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta state. The research investigates the relationship between teachers' subject knowledge, instructional strategies, and professional qualifications with students' academic outcomes in economics. Teachers' Competence Scale (TCS) and Economics Achievement Test (EAT) were used to elicit data for the study reliability coefficient of 0.87 and 0.81 were obtained respectively using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The data were analysed using the Pearson "r" statistic, t-test and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 levels of significance. The findings reveal that teachers with higher levels of subject-specific skill and effective pedagogical skills consistently foster better academic performance among students. In addition, professional development initiatives and competency-building programs were found to have a significant influence on bridging performance gaps. The study emphasizes the critical role of teacher competency in shaping student success and provides recommendations for improving teacher training programs, attending conferences, seminars and workshops of stakeholders in education to enhance students' academic performance to enhance students' academic outcomes in economics education.

Keywords: Competency, Qualifications, Experience, Economics and Performance.

Introduction

The subject Economics appears to be one of the electives subjects in secondary schools and compulsory subjects for all commercial students at the senior secondary school (SSS) level under the new National policy on Education. According to Ogbemor (2013) Economics is a subject that deals with the principle and practice of undertaking everyday activities that engender the well-being of the individual, society and the nation at large. This implies that with the study of Economics, individuals can survive because they are able to acquire basic knowledge and skills that will enable them to better appreciate the nature of economic problems in any society. Furthermore, Economics as a subject provides training for students on how to make rational use of scarce resources to satisfy their unlimited wants, to build up theories and tools for economic analysis, provide rationale guide to firms and governments in allocating scarce resources, to understand and appreciate economic problems facing the society and suggest ways of rectifying them (Fehintola & Yahya, 2019).

According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2012) Economics exposes students to basic economic problems of the society and a better understanding of man's economic activities and how to solve them for better living in the society. The major goal of the teaching and learning of Economics, as stipulated in the Economics curriculum, according to the Federal Ministry of Education (2012) is to equip graduands of senior secondary school students with basic knowledge and skills to appreciate the nature of Economic problems in any society and adequately prepare them for the challenges in the Nigerian Economy. Therefore, it becomes necessary that students should achieve highly in Economics test and examinations to enable take a good decision and manage their resources very well. Academic achievement is regarded as students' score or grade in a test or an examination. Okonkwo (2016) stated that academic achievement is a scholastic position of a student at any given time. Achievement is a construct that is measurable using standardized series of tests, usually developed for school subjects by examination bodies and ministries of education such as West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO).

In spite of the importance of this subject to the society and the contributions made by successive government and critical stakeholders, the performance of students in Economics Examinations and Test appears to be decreasing. The WAEC Chief examiner's report (2022) on economics subject noted that the persistent decrease in the performance of Economics students in senior secondary certificate examination leaves no doubt about the competency and motivation of Economics teachers in schools. Others include large class size, inadequate and un-conducive classrooms for teaching and learning Economics, in adequate Economics text books for learning process, insufficient qualified Economics teachers to

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reduce the work load of the teachers, inadequate time to Economics subjects by student and inadequate incentives to the Economics teachers to make them dedicated to their teaching profession. (Omotegbona, 2020).

The implication is that it could lead to poor academic performance among senior secondary school student. Therefore, to improve the performance of students in Economics, government and employers of labour need to focus on quality education. The world of education must also be supported by competent, reliable and quality human resources to realize quality or superior education at all levels of society. Teacher competence refers to the ability of educators to effectively carry out their responsibilities in alignment with educational objectives (Bamidele, 2024). The competence of teachers is fundamental for quality instruction and student academic performance. (Pascoe et al., 2020). Research indicates that a teacher's understanding of the subject matter significantly affects both the content taught and the methods used, ultimately influencing student outcomes. This relationship between subject knowledge and pedagogy encompasses classroom management, lesson structure, and teaching strategies (Bamidele, 2024).

According to Akiri & Ugborugbo (2009) a teacher's competence is regarded as a multidimensional construct, which encompasses numerous interconnected elements towards the transformation of knowledge to learners. Meziobi & Meziobi (2012) describe teachers' competence as demonstrable, professionally acquired, specified requisite teaching skills, abilities, and attitudes essential for effective teaching. The authors further stress that the possession of a repertoire of these prerequisite teaching skills and attitudes spans beyond the three domains of learning and, therefore, may not be restricted only to them. Thus, a teacher can be competent in the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective areas of the instructional process. In line with this, Uchefuna (2010) noted that teaching and learning depend on teachers' competence, consequently, a competent teacher could be conceptualized as one who produces desired results in psychomotor, cognitive, and affective domains of education. Teachers' competence involves all aspects of teachers' abilities that could influence the teaching and learning process being geared towards attaining the desirable set objectives of Economics in secondary schools.

To be a competent Economics teacher, the teacher needs to possess required qualification such as degree in Economics Education with wealth of experience in teaching the subject (Economics) and mastery of subject matter. Teacher's qualification refers to the kind of professional education for teaching that the teacher has received (Agbor, Onnoghen, & Etan, 2023). Qualification relates to the acquisition of relevant knowledge, skills, competence and creativity needed for quality productive engagement in the teaching profession. A teacher's academic qualification is the educational attainments of the teacher. A teacher academic certification is a combined set of qualifications which include general academic and verbal ability, subject matter knowledge and teacher education (Yakubu, 2023). Academically, qualified teachers are referred to those who have academic training as a result of enrolment into educational institution and obtained qualifications such as B.Sc.Ed Economics while professionally qualified teachers are those who got professional training that gave them professional knowledge, skill, techniques, aptitudes as different from the general education (Edu and Kalu, 2012). It appears that student's performance is enhanced when taught with high qualified teachers than when taught with less qualified. A qualified teacher has the capacity to teach and improve on students' learning thereby leading to high academic performance. Segun (2016) confirmed that for any meaningful teaching and learning to take place, teacher qualification needs to be very high. Macaulay (2016) affirmed the above assertion by Segun (2016) qualifications must relate to academic and professional preparation, professional growth, classroom interaction and evaluation. This is true because a lecturer who is not trained in a particular discipline will not perform as much as if he trained in that particular field. In this case the lecturer relies on 'reading and teaching' because the in-depth knowledge is lacking for effective instructional

According to Gibbons, as cited in Agharuwhe (2013) students who are taught by more experienced teachers perform better academically because these teachers are more adept at both teaching the subject matter and dealing with a variety of classroom issues. The effectiveness of a teacher increases systematically with increase in number of years of teaching. Teachers' experiences can therefore either improve or lower students' academic achievement. By implication, teachers with less years of experience have a lower academic accomplishment rate than those with more. Papay & Kraff (2014) stated that inexperienced teachers are teachers with few years into the teaching profession trying to survive in the classroom because they are building key classroom management skills, learning the curriculum and adding to their instructional skills.

It is essential for an efficient, professional and competent teacher to possess a good knowledge of subject matter. Mastery of subject matter refers to the level at which the teacher possesses a good grasp of knowledge of the subject he teaches and skills necessary for teaching the subject (Ntibi, Neji, & Agube, 2020). Teachers without good grasp of subject matter, can succeed in bluffing the students and imparting incorrect information which is likely to bring difficulties to the learners and to other teachers who teach the learners. Mezieobi (2012) stated that teacher must possess sufficient knowledge in their area of teaching. Any teacher that does not possess the required knowledge of subject matter in his area of teaching cannot be effective. That includes how well the teacher masters the subject matter, lesson preparation and presentation, punctuality

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and attendance to class, clear communication efficacy in students' evaluation, and engendering effectiveness concerning the outcome. Teachers of Economics need not just be competent but require motivation for effective teaching and learning of the subject.

Theoretical Framework

Competence motivation Theory: Competence motivation theory (CMT) is a motivational framework forwarded by Susan Harter (1978, 1981) for understanding achievement- related behaviour in various domains (e.g., academics, social, physical). Harter's theory expanded on the seminal work of White (1959), This theory explains why people are motivated to participate in activities where they feel competent. It suggests that people are driven to develop or demonstrate their skills, and that success in a particular domain can lead to increased competence motivation. According to the theory competence motivation increases when a person successfully masters a task. This encourages the person to master more tasks. Success in that domain will help them recognize that they can control their performance. High perceptions of competence and control create feelings of pleasure that maintain or lead to an increase in competence motivation. It is useful to the students who are successful when attempting new skills or tasks and receive positive reinforcement will internalize a self-reward system as well as a set of mastery goals. This can have a positive and long-term effect on their confidence. Because they are internalizing their own set of standards, students will no longer be dependent on others to evaluate their performances or motivate them to continue. Instead, they will be motivated to continue on their own because they recognize they are competent in that area. More importantly, it will also give the teachers to put in their best and applied the best methods to teach the students using teachers- students centred methods of teaching. On the part of Economics students, their performance and interest in studying Economics will be high because of the quality of Economics teachers teaching the students with wealth of experience.

Empirical Review

Teachers Competency and Students Academic Performance

Bamidele (2024) examines the relationship between teacher competence and the academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Utilising a descriptive survey design, data were collected from 203 secondary schools, focusing on teacher competencies such as mastery of subject matter, teaching qualifications, teaching experience, training, and regular supervision. The findings revealed that out of 1118 respondents in the 2014/2015 session, 64.67% achieved 5 credits and above, including Mathematics and English. A significant positive correlation was observed between teacher competence and students' academic performance, with r-cal value of 0.770 indicating that higher teacher competence is associated with improved student outcomes. Specifically, mastery of subject matter and teaching qualifications were identified as the most impactful variables.

Idika & Onuoha (2018) investigated the influence of Economics teachers' personality on students' classroom performance in Public Secondary Schools in Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria. The study adopted Ex-post facto research design. The sample consisted of 19 teachers randomly selected out of thirty-one and their SS2 Economics students numbering 326. An observational schedule titled Economics teachers' personality test (ETP) was the instrument for data collection. The academic records (grades) of the students were collected from the 19 teachers. One research question was answered using mean and standard deviation and four null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance using t- test and ANOVA. The findings revealed that teachers' gender had no effect on the classroom performance of the students. However, teachers teaching experience, qualifications, interpersonal relationship with students, knowledge of subject matter, and attitude of the teacher had influence on students' classroom performance.

Nwankwo (2021) examined teachers' competence, motivation as correlates of senior secondary school students' academic achievement in economics in Imo State. The study adopted a linear correlation design. The population of the study was 94,963 Senior Secondary School Students (SS1-SS3) from 275 public secondary schools in Imo State. A sample of 500 SS2 Economics students was involved in the study. Purposive and random sampling techniques were used. The research instruments for this study are the Teachers' Competence Scale (TCS), Teachers' Motivation Scale (TMS), and Economics Achievement Test (EAT). The data were analyzed using the Pearson "r" statistic for research questions 1 and 2, while multiple linear regression statistics were used for research question 3. Hypotheses 1 and 2 were tested using t-test significance of correlation and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test hypothesis 3 at 5% level of significance. The result showed that there is a highly significant relationship between teachers' competence, motivation, and students' academic achievement in Economics.

Annas, Istiqomah & Ika (2019) measured the effect of teacher competencies on student learning outcomes. The research sample consisted of 60 teachers and 60 students at Muhammadiyah Bambanglipuro Vocational High School, Bantul, Yogyakarta, Indonesia. The data was collected through a questionnaire method. The collected data were analyzed using simple regression with SPSS. It showed the determination result of the independent variable that the determination coefficient showed the direct effect of the teacher ss proficiencies variable on learning outcomes stated in percentages. In

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this case, the calculated result is 0,084. It means that the teacher competencies variable directly affects the student learning outcome variable by 8,4%, while the (100% -8,4%) 91,6% is influenced by other factors beyond the teacher competencies variable.

Teachers Years of Teaching Experience and Students Academic Performance

Okose & Obiunu (2024) investigated Influence of Teachers' years of Teaching Experience and Qualification on Students' Academic Performance in Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science. The study which was carried out in the three senatorial district of Delta State was guided by two specific objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses. Ex-Post facto research design was adopted. The sample comprised of ninety Junior Secondary III Basic science teachers and 1800 students who sat for the Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science in the 2021/2022 academic session. Data were collected through the multistage sampling procedure. Basic Science Teachers' Questionnaire (BSTQ) was use elicit the teacher's information and the Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science was used to access the student's performance. Research question was answered using mean and standard deviation while the t-test analysis was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study showed that teachers' years of teaching experience and qualification has influence on the mean academic performance of Basic science students in BECE.

Ene et.al (2022) examined Influence of Teachers' years of Teaching Experience on Students' Academic Achievement in Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science. The study which was carried out in Nsukka Education zone was guided by one specific purpose, one research question and one null hypothesis. Ex-Post facto research design was adopted. The population comprised 4,195 Junior Secondary III Basic science teachers and students in Nsukka Education Zone. The sample consisted of 365 respondents, and was determined using multistage sampling procedure. Basic Science Teachers' Questionnaire (BSTQ) and Basic Science Achievement Test (BSAT) were the instruments and were validated by experts in the department of Science Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Research question was answered using mean and standard deviation while analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study showed that teachers' years of teaching experience has influence on the mean academic achievement of Basic science students in BECE.

Teachers Qualification and Students Academic performance

Agbor, Onnoghen & Etan (2023) explored the relationship between teachers' qualification and students' academic performance in Environmental Education in University of Calabar. The research design adopted for the study was survey research design. Two research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide to study. The population of the study consisted of 672 undergraduate students from Department of Environmental Education. A sample of 134 students was used for the study, this constituted 20% of the population. A structured questionnaire title: Teachers' Qualification and Environmental Education Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (TQEESAPQ). Pearson products moment correlation coefficient analysis was used to test the hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance. Findings in the study revealed that teachers with environmental education qualification positively relate with students' academic performance.

Onuegbu (2023) investigated the effects of teachers' qualification on students' academic performance in private secondary schools in Southeastern Nigeria. Through a thoughtfully designed survey, over 515 respondents from 187 schools shared insights into their daily educational realities. Their responses revealed generally qualified teaching staff dedicated to covering subjects comprehensively.

Teachers Mastery of Subject Matter and Students Academic Performance

Ntibi, Neji & Agube (2020) examined the influence of students' perception of teacher knowledge of subject matter/ lesson presentation and academic achievement in Physics in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State, Nigeria. Two hypotheses were formulated to direct the study and literature was reviewed on the variables under study. Ex-post facto design research was adopted for the study. A total sample of 50 Physics students were selected using simple random sampling procedure. The questionnaire and Physics Achievement Test (PAT) were the main instruments used for data collection. The reliability estimate of the instrument was established through Cronbach Alpha reliability and Kudar-Richarson's formular (KR-21) which yielded an estimate of .83 and .81 respectively. One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistic was adopted to test the two hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The result of the analysis revealed that there is a significant influence of students' perception of teacher knowledge of subject matter and academic achievement in Physics. Secondly, finding revealed that mode of lesson presentation has significant influence on students' academic performance in Physics.

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Sadiq (2019) examined the relationship between teacher's knowledge of subject matter and students' academic achievements in economics in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. The study was set to achieve certain objectives, research questions and hypotheses, the researcher adopted this study will adopt a descriptive survey design; the area of the study is Adamawa State. The population of the study is 5465 comprising of 337 principals 5128 teachers in all the public secondary schools within the five education zones of Adamawa state. The sample size of 73 principals and 372 teachers in both selected zone is determined by Taro Yamane formula for finite population from the selected zones. The instrument was questionnaire on teacher's knowledge of subject matter and a proforma for student academic achievement results from selected schools from 2015-2018 WASSCE that is WAEC results. The instrument was validated by four Senior Lecturers. A reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha Method. The data was collected through the administration of the questionnaires. The descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. While inferential statistics such as multiple correlations were used to test the null hypothesis. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. the result of the finding revealed that hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance was rejected and was concluded that teachers' knowledge of the subject matter contributed to secondary school students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Statement of the Research Problem

The competency of teachers plays a vital role in shaping students' academic performance and overall development. In spite of substantial investments in teacher training and education systems, significant disparities in student achievement persist. Factors such as teachers' subject knowledge, pedagogical skills, classroom management, and ability to address diverse learning needs directly influence students' outcomes. However, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding of how specific teacher competencies correlate with student performance across various contexts. This gap in knowledge hinders the development of targeted interventions to enhance teaching effectiveness and student success. Addressing this issue is critical to improving educational quality and equity, ensuring all students have access to competent and effective teachers who can meet their diverse learning needs.

Objective of the study

Specifically, the study sets out to achieve the following objectives:

1. To examine the relationship between students' academic performance in Economics and teachers' possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics
2. To determine the influence of teachers' educational qualifications on academic performance of Economics students.
3. To determine the influence of teachers' years of teaching experience on academic performance of Economics students.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between students' academic performance in Economics and teachers' possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics
2. How does teachers' educational qualifications influence the academic performance of Economics students.
3. To what extent do teachers' years of teaching experience influence the academic performance of Economics students.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between students' academic performance in Economics and teachers' possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics
2. There is no significant influence of teachers' educational qualifications on academic performance of Economics students.
3. There is no significant influence of teachers' years of teaching experience on academic performance of Economics students.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design is use for this study. The population for this study comprises all the male and the female SSII senior secondary school students offering Economics and Economics teachers in Ika South local government of Delta state. There are seven public senior secondary schools in Ika South local government of Delta State in 2022/2023 academic session. This population is considered appropriate because they are free from external examination such as WAEC and NECO. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select one-hundred and ninety-eight (198) participants which consists of 180 students and 18 teachers. The sample also consists of 104 females and 94 males. In selecting the students, simple random sampling was used to select One hundred and eighty (180) students from six selected senior secondary schools. That is thirty (30) students each from the six (6) selected senior secondary schools using lucky dip method. That is asking

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the students to pick a paper written “Yes or No” from the box. The participants that pick “YES” is automatically selected for the study while those that pick “No” were not selected. Convenient sampling was used to select eighteen (18) teachers. For data collection, the study made use of two rating scales titled Teachers’ Competence Scale (TCS) and Teachers’ Motivation Scale (TMS) and an achievement test titled Economics Achievement Test (EAT). Teachers’ Competence Scale (TCS) has 15 items with 3 sub-scale namely Teachers Qualification, Teachers Teaching Experience and Teachers Subject Matter. The scale was prepared in terms of four response options of strongly agree=4points, agree=3points, disagree=2points, and strongly disagree=1point. The achievement test has 20 item questions in 4 multiple choice forms adapted from 4 subtopics in the Economics Syllabus to get information on the academic achievement of the students. Draft copies of the scales were given to three specialists from the field of Educational Measurement and Evaluation and Economics for face validation, but the achievement test was subjected to content, validity using a table of specifications. Cronbach alpha was used to determine the reliability of Teachers Competent Scale and Economics Achievement Test (EAT) with reliability coefficient of 0.87 and 0.81 respectively. The statistical tools used were the t-test, Pearson product moment correlation and analysis of variance. The study hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

The result was presented in tables in line with the purpose of study and the corresponding null hypothesis that guided the study.

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics and students’ academic performance in Economics.

Table 1: The Relationship between Teachers Knowledge of subject matter and Students Academic performance test

S/N	Variable	N	Mean	Std Dev	r-cal	r-critic	Decision
1	Economics Test	180	16.38	1.69	0.650	0.1593	Significant
2	Teachers Knowledge of subject matter	18	18.05	0.93			

Table 1 above shows that the mean and scores of Economics students was 16.38 and 1.69 while that of Teachers’ knowledge of the subject matter in Economic was 18.05 and 0.93 respectively. Table 1 also showed that the r-calculated value of 0.650 is greater than t critical value of 0.1593. Since the calculated value is greater than the critical value the null hypothesis is reject. This means there is significant relation between Teachers’ possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics and students’ academic performance in Economics.

Ho₂: There is no significant influence of teachers’ educational qualifications on academic performance of Economics students.

Table 2: t-test difference between Economics’ Teachers educational qualification Students’ Academic performance

S/N	Variable	N	Mean	Std Dev	Df	t-cal	t-critic	Decision
1	Economics Teachers with Master degree in Econs Edu	4	18.00	0.81	16	2.239	1.976	Significant
2	Economics Teachers with Bachelor degree in Econs Edu	14	16.07	1.63				

Table 2 above shows that the mean and standard deviation scores of Economics teachers with Master degrees in Education was 18.00 and 0.81 while that of Economics Teachers with Bachelor degree in Economics Education was 16.07 and 1.63 respectively. Table 2 also showed that the t-calculated value of 2.239 is greater than t critical value of 1.976. Since the t-calculated value is greater than the t-critical value the null hypothesis is reject. Hence, there is significant influence of teachers’ qualification on student academic performance in Economics.

Ho₃: There is no significant influence of teachers’ years of teaching experience on academic performance of Economics students.

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Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Influence of Teachers' Years of Teaching Experience on the Mean Academic Performance Scores of Economics Students

S/N	Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	1-5 YEARS EXPERIENCE	4	14.2500	1.70783	Significant
2	6 YEARS -10 years	6	16.8333	.98319	
3	11 years and above	8	17.3750	1.06066	
	Total	18	16.5000	1.68907	

Result in Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of academic performance scores of Economics students in Test by teachers' years of teaching experience. Result shows that students who were taught by teachers with 1-5 years of teaching experience had mean of 14.25 with a standard deviation of 1.70. Students taught by teachers with 6-10 years of teaching experience had a mean score of 16.83 with a standard deviation of 0.98. Also, students taught by teachers with 11 years and above with teaching experience had mean score of 17.37 with a standard deviation of 1.06. The result of the study shows that as teachers' years of teaching experience increases, students' academic achievement also increases. The overall means score of 16.50 was obtained with a standard deviation of 1.68. This result shows that teachers' years of teaching experience has influence on the mean academic achievement scores of Economics students. To determine whether there is significant difference exists in Economics performance Test scores among participants, one-way ANOVA was used and the results are presented in Table 4

Table 4: Showing ANOVA Summary Table on the Difference in the Mean Scores of Students In Economics and Teachers Years of experience

S/N	Variable	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Between Groups	27.042	2	13.521	9.451	.002	Significant
2	Within Groups	21.458	15	1.431			
	Total	48.500	17				

The ANOVA results presented in Table 4 shows that the F-value of 9.451 was greater than the F-critical value of 3.63, given 2 and 15 degrees of freedom at the .05 level of significance. Since the calculated F-value was greater than the F-critical value, hypothesis 3 was rejected which means that there is significant influence of teachers' years of teaching experience on academic performance of Economics students in Ika South local Government. This implies that teachers' years of teaching experience is a significant factor in determining students' achievement in Economics. To test for the direction of the difference, a post-test comparison of means was conducted and the result is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Post Hoc Test of the Comparison between the means

S/N	(I) GROUP	(J) GROUP	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
1	1-5 YEARS EXPERIENCE	6 YEARS -10 years	-2.58333*	.77205	.004
2		11 years and above	-3.12500*	.73243	.001
3	6 YEARS -10 years	1-5 YEARS EXPERIENCE	2.58333*	.77205	.004
4		11 years and above	-.54167	.64595	.415
5	11 years and above	1-5 YEARS EXPERIENCE	3.12500*	.73243	.001
6		6 YEARS -10 years	.54167	.64595	.415

Table 5 shows a multiple comparison test of the variation in students' mean scores in the Economics test based on teachers' years of teaching experience. The outcome demonstrates that there was discernible difference in the mean score between students taught by teachers with 1–5 years of experience and those with 6–10 years of experience (2.58*). There was significant difference between students who were taught by teachers with "1-5 years" and "11 years above (3.12*). The finding also demonstrated that Economics students taught by teachers with 11 years above perform better than students taught by teachers with 6-10 years. Also, students taught by teachers with 6-10 years did better than students taught by teachers with 1-5 years.

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Discussion of findings

The result of this first hypothesis revealed that there is a significant relationship between Teachers' possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics and students' academic performance in Economics. This finding agreed with Emeh and Agba, (2010) who ascertain that teachers' Mastery of subject matter has much influence on the process of achieving the lesson's objective. Also, in line with Chidi (2016) who in his study on the relationship between teachers' mastery of the subject matter and student academic achievement in simultaneous equations in Enugu State and agreed that there is a significant influence of teachers' mastery of the subject matter on students' academic achievement in Physics. The result of finding from hypothesis 2 showed a significant difference between teachers' educational qualifications and students' academic performance in Economics. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Macaulay (2016) who observed that qualifications relate to academic and professional preparation, professional growth, classroom interaction and evaluation, which in turn result in high academic performance. The result also corroborated the finding of Agbor, Onnoghen & Etan (2023) who find out that there is a significant relationship between teacher qualification and students' academic performance in Environmental Education in University of Calabar, Nigeria.

The result of the study in hypothesis 3 shows that teachers' years of teaching experience have significant influence on the mean academic achievement scores of Economics students This difference is in the direction of teachers with 6-10 years and 11 years and above in which these teachers perform better than other teachers below. The result is in accordance with Agharuwhe (2013) who stated that effectiveness due to number of years into teaching might positively influence students' academic achievement. The result of the study is consistent with Ewetan & Ewetan (2015) who found that teachers teaching experience has significantly influence students' academic achievement in mathematics and English language as measured by their achievement in SSCE and as perceived by the respondents. Schools that have more teachers with experience above ten years in teaching achieved better result than schools having more teachers with less than ten years teaching experience. The result also agrees with Bamidele & Adekola (2017) who found that there was significant difference in the achievement of students taught by long time experienced teachers and short time experienced teachers. Ene et.al (2022) highlighted that having more experienced teachers will result in pupils who do better. Okose & Obiunu (2024) discovered a correlation between teachers' teaching experience and students' academic achievement in Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science, which is consistent with the outcome of this study.

Conclusion

Drawing from the results of this study, it can be said that when teachers employ teaching competency technology effectively, students' academic performance will increase, and they will be able to comprehend the subject matter better. Students who have a thorough comprehension of the subject matter will be able to score very well on external exams that consist of standardized test items, in addition to performing well on teacher-made assessments. In conclusion, investing in teachers' professional development and fostering a supportive educational environment are key strategies for improving student achievement. Properly implemented, it enhances learning and fosters a collaborative classroom.

Recommendations

On the basis of study finding the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should improve their competence of the subject matter through attending conferences, seminars and workshops of stakeholders in education to enhance students' academic achievement.
2. The experienced teachers should mentor the less experienced teachers, and capacity building programs should be organized.
3. All Economics teachers in senior secondary schools must possess at least B.sc and M.Ed in Economics education.

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References

- Agbor, C.N., Onnoghen, U.N., & Etan, M.O. (2023). Teachers' Qualification and Academic Performance of Environmental Education Students in The University of Calabar. *Journal of Contemporary Research*, 20(2):2-12.

Comparative Analysis between Teacher's ... (Onyechi) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15041041>

- Agharuwhe, A.A. (2013). Effect of teacher's effectiveness on students' academic performance in public secondary school. *Journal of Education and social Research*, 3(3):22-29.
- Annas, N., Istiqomah I, S., & Ika, M. (2019). The Effect of Teacher Competencies on Student Achievement in Vocational High School. *International Journal of Education*, 11(4): 1-16.
- Bamidele, E.O. (2024). Teacher Competence and Academic Performance of Students in Public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 18(2):115-136.
- Bandura, A. (1986). Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory Prentice-Hall, Inc, Englewood Cliffs, NJ. Retrieved from //search.proquest.com.ezaccess.libraries.psu.edu/docview/617099314?accountid=13158
- Edu, D.O., & Kalu I.M. (2012). Influence of Academic Qualification on Gender on Teachers Perception of Difficult Concept in Primary Science in Ikom, Educational Zone of Cross River. *Greener and Journal of Educational Research*, 2(2):54-62.
- Emen, G., & Agbo, S. (2010). Factors contributing to commitment to the teaching profession. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 8(5):7-13.
- Ene, C. U., Anyiam, L. I., & Onoja, A. E. (2022). Influence of Teachers' Years of Teaching Experience on Students' Academic Achievement in Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science. *AJSTME*, 8(1):488-494,
- Ewetan, T. O., & Ewetan, O. O. (2015). Teachers' teaching experience and academic performance in mathematics and English in public secondary schools in Ogun State, Nigeria. *International journal of humanities social science and education*, 2(2):241-248.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2012). Senior Secondary Education Curriculum. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2012). National policy on education. Revised Federal ministry of Education 7th Edition. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Fehintola, T.T., & Yahya, D.O. (2019). Effect Of Gender on Economics Students Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Oyo, Nigeria. *British Journal of Education, Learning and Development Psychology*, 2(2):102-106.
- Idika, E.O., & Onuoha, J.C. (2018). Influence of Economics Teachers' Personality on Secondary School Students' Classroom Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State *Journal of Social Science Education*, 17(3):100-106.
- Macaulay J. I. (2016). Training of teachers as a key factor in the successful implementation of the 6-3-3-4 scheme. *Nigerian Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 1(28):31-41.
- Meziobi, K.A., & Meziobi, K.C. (2012). *A handbook of Social Studies Competences*. Owerri: Priscilla Omama Publishers.
- Ntibi, J.E.E., Neji, H.A., & Agube, C. (2020). Students' Perception of Teacher Knowledge of Subject Matter/Lesson Presentation and Academic Performance in Physics in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 59(2): 247-254.
- Nwankwo, C.A. (2021). Teachers' competence, motivation as correlates of senior secondary school students' academic achievement in economics in Imo State. *Journal of Educational Research on Children, Parents & teachers*, 2(1):158-168.
- Ogbebor, U.C. (2013). Differential item functioning Economics question paper of national council in Delta State Nigeria. Unpublished M.Ed. project. University of Ibadan. Retrieved November, 17 2024, <http://www.findarticles.com>.
- Okonkwo, M. O. S. (2016). *Effects of meta-cognitive learning cycle (MLC) on students' achievement and interest in Basic science*. Unpublished Master's thesis, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Okose, N.F., & Obiunu, Esevosa, A. (2024). Influence of Teachers' Years of Teaching Experience and Qualification on Students' Academic Performance in Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science in Delta State. *International innovative Journal of Social and Science Education Research*, 12(1):17-26.
- Omotegbona, P.O. (2020). An Overview of The Performance of Students in Economics in WAEC And NECO Examination in Selected Secondary Schools in Ethiopie West Local Government Area Of Delta State From 2012 To 2018. *Innovative Journal of Art and Social Sciences (IJASS)*, (2):164-171.
- Onuegbu, F.E. (2023). Assessing the Effects of Teachers Qualification on Students Academic Performance in Private Secondary Schools in the South Eastern Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 14(6):49-66
- Papay, J., & Kraft, M. (2014). Productivity returns to experience in the teacher labour market: Methodological challenges and new evidence on long-term career improvement. Brown University: Car Michael Press.
- Pascoe, M. C., Hetrick, S. E., & Parker, A. G. (2020). The impact of stress on students in secondary school and higher education. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 25(1):104-112. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673843.2019.1596823>.

Comparative Analysis between Teacher's ... (Onyechi) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15041041>

- Sadiq, A. (2019). The Relationship between Teacher's Knowledge of Subject Matter and Students' Academic Achievement in Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Philosophy and Social-Psychological Sciences*, 5 (4):1-4.
- Susan Harter (1978., 1981). The Perceived Competence Scale for Children. *International Journal of social and personal relationship*, 1(53):87-97. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1129640>.
- Uchefuna, M.C. (2010). "A study of clinical Supervision and Teachers, effectiveness in Umuahia and Abia Educational Zones of Abia State". Unpublished M.Ed. Dissertation. Port Harcourt, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria.
- WAEC, (2022). Chief examiner's report. West African examination council. www.waecnigeria.org
- Yakubu, S. A. (2023). Teacher academic qualification as a correlate of students' academic achievement in fine and applied arts at the colleges of education in northeast Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 11(1):15-24.a

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Comparative Analysis of Leadership Style and Job Performance among University Librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated on comparative analysis of leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study had a total population of 151 librarians. Total enumeration sampling technique was employed to include all the university librarians. Data was collected using an adapted questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts in the field of library and information science. The instrument was trial-tested for reliability on 50 librarians from the institution that did not form part of the study. The scores obtained from the trial-testing was calculated using Cronbach Alpha method and the coefficient of the alpha was 0.78. Data collected was analysed based on frequency count, percentage, mean and standard deviation and multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that the job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria was moderate following the norm test of mean ($\bar{x}=63.7$). The types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo state, Nigeria are; democratic, charismatic, autocratic and bureaucratic. There was a weak and negative relationship between leadership style and job performance among librarians ($r = -.037$; $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that leadership style is an important determinant of job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria. The study also recommended full participation of university librarians during accreditation exercise of university courses among others.

Keyword: Job performance, leadership style and university librarians

Introduction

University library is the fulcrum of educational activities, hence, provides support for teaching, learning, research and any sort of academic activities. To achieve these, library collects, processes, organises, stores, preserves, disseminates and evaluates information sources in various formats which include printed and non-printed. The university library facilitates the collecting, organising, storing, dissemination, and assessment of information for effective decision-making, institutional development, and economical progress. The university library plays a very essential role in supporting the mandate of their institution's research, teaching as well as community service by critically selecting, possessing, processing, keeping and giving out relevant information resources within and beyond their environments (Unegbu, Babalola and Basahuwa, 2020). The need for a library in an academic institution cannot be overemphasized because they help in fulfilling the purpose of aiding the curriculum and research in the university. Emphasising the importance of a university library, Eruvwe and Omekwu (2020) noted that university library offers services to the university in the area of learning, reading and advance research. They further noted that academic libraries are known for two major responsibilities which are: to aid and support the school curriculum and to support the research of the university, college as well as that of the students. Academic libraries are the "treasure house" of knowledge which meets the needs of academic, innovators, technocrats, researchers, students and those that falls within the confines of higher education, and this is because they reflect the community they serve.

University librarians have responsibility to help students become information literate (Aharony, Julien and Nadel-Kritz, 2020). They performed the core of the job that actually project the library. Such job includes, acquisition, processing, evaluating and weeding or information resources. It also involves some other specialised services such as: library consortia, selective dissemination of information, library loan, current awareness and any other required services. Arguably, when the information resources are not well consulted it becomes an issue to be worried about and may amount to waste of university resources. This could be as a result of library personnel not developing good collection management skills or the unfavourable work environment factors which may lead to poor job performance. Job performance is a deliberate act of achieving set goals and objectives. Job performance is the measure at which an output is produced as result of the level of inputs given. In the opinion of Hashmi, Ameen and Soroya (2019), job performance provides insights into the human psychology of work

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behaviours and factors that motivates. Job performance which has gained a wide range of definition from various scholars is a determinant of the success or failure of an organisation to a large extent. Job performance is the discharge of statutory duties based on library personnel field of specialization which is centered on the attainment of the library objectives. Personnel experience by the researcher indicated that library personnel have not been meeting the expected level of job performance in the library, especially in this present study locale. Scholars have pointed to the fact that the job performances of library staff in Nigerian universities have not been meeting the set levels of expectation in certain tasks. Reduced efficiency in services of the library, decline in prompt services and the misuse of resources as well as low turnout of research output are evidences of library personnel low level of job performances. This situation, if allowed to persist may impinge negatively on the overall effectiveness of university libraries and academic culture of Nigerian universities. Davidescu, Apostu, Paul and Casuneanu (2020) showed that expectations of job performance on a job are predicted by work-related behaviours of employees and leadership style practiced by the organisation. It is these work-related behaviours and right leadership style that turn into tangible job performances needed to meet the goals and objectives of the library.

Various studies on leadership have been conducted over the years. However, a widely accepted definition is still lacking. According to Talat, Amed and Ali (2015), leadership is a thorough process that outlines delegation of authority, responsibility, and power. For the benefit of the organisation and the individual, leaders support their followers (workers) in accomplishing personal and organisational goals and objectives. According to Kumar (2014), leadership is the act of inspiring others to work toward a common objective and guiding an organisation in a way that improves its cohesion and cohesiveness. Leadership qualities including convictions, ethics, values, morals, personality, knowledge, and talents are used to achieve this. O'Connor (2020) defines leadership as the process by which a person inspires a group of others to collaborate in order to achieve a common objective that is advantageous to both the individual and the group. Utilising effective leadership techniques can inspire and motivate staff members to grow as well as persuade them to give their all for the organisation's success. In his contribution, Ekpenyong (2020) put forth the idea that leadership is the process of inspiring followers to offer everything they have in order to achieve organisational objectives. Leadership is now a team effort between the leader and followers to better the organisation rather than a solitary activity of the leader. Leadership requires the use of persuasion and influence rather than force or coercive dominance. Leadership is a continuous and gradual process with the main objective of helping the organisation achieve a specific goal. According to Adserias, Charleston, and Jackson (2017), leadership is the process of encouraging a group or individual's activities toward achieving goals in a particular situation for the overall benefit of the organisation.

There are different types of leadership style in university libraries and these include; autocratic leadership style, democratic leadership style, laissez faire leadership style, transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, bureaucratic leadership style and charismatic leadership style. Northouse (2021) asserts that poor or inappropriate leadership philosophies can directly affect employee productivity and retention in today's organisations. Eze, Enwereuzor and Ugwu (2018) contend that a strong leadership style encourages employees to have a connection to the organisation. Those who do so experience a sense of ownership and are more likely to stick with the organisation. Eze, Enwereuzor, and Ugwu (2018) assert that an exceptional leader not only unlocks subordinates' potential for increased productivity but also attends to their needs as they relate to achieving organisational objectives. In their study on understanding the relationship between leadership and organisational performance, Fenwick and Gayle (2008) conclude that, despite the hypothesised leadership-performance association proposed by some academics, present data are inconclusive and difficult to interpret. Organisational justice is promoted through leadership style, which is significant because employees who see organisational fairness have higher levels of work performance, trust in their supervisor, psychological ownership, and organisational commitment. A leader who prioritises work-life balance fosters performance. Work-life balance perks have the ability to increase an employee's quality of life while also increasing company effectiveness (Peters and Heusinkveld, 2010). In their contribution, Sulaiman et al. (2011) argue that leadership style and effectiveness are the key emphasis for organisations in order to achieve organisational goals and generate organisational commitment in their personnel. Sifuna (2012) discovered, on the contrary, that in many African universities, leaders are recruited and awarded based on their academic qualifications, research, teaching, and community service rather than their leadership potential, and that critical training in planning process, budgeting, human resource development, and faculty management is rarely received. Leadership styles, in a nutshell, have a substantial impact on job performance of university library personnel. A university's library leadership style influences its culture, which in turn influences its performance. Klien and Salk (2013) demonstrated this by employing the four-element theory of leadership and data obtained from 2,662 individuals working in 311 firms. The type of leadership style influences corporate culture and job performance. Hence, the current study is to investigate and compare the different leadership styles practiced in university libraries and their effect to job performance of university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria.

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Statement of the Research Problem:

University library is the pivot around which the teaching, learning and research activities of the university revolves, without which no university can attain its goals and objectives. The importance of the library is, therefore, underscored by the huge resources allocated to the library annually. These resources include personnel, space, facilities, equipment and annual budgetary allocation. The personnel of every university library are categorised into three, these are professional (librarian), para-professional and non-professional. The librarians engage in both administrative and technical duties. The administrative duties including making policies, programmes, planning annual budgets, training of other library personnel and coordinating the entire system of university library. While the technical duties are cataloguing and classification of information resources, aligning library programmes with the institution's curriculum, assisting users identifying and retrieving information resources among others. Despite these expectations from the university personnel, literatures and observations have continually shown that users and management of university libraries are generally not satisfied with the job outcome of some library personnel (Northouse, 2021), especially in the area of meeting of deadlines as well as quality and quantity of job performance (Davidescu, Apostu, Paul and Casuneanu, 2020). This state of affair may not be unrelated to the management of the library or in a specific term, leadership style of the library (Eze, Enwereuzor and Ugwu, 2018). Once a wrong leadership style is been practiced in any university library, the result can be low performance, low patronage of users, not meeting up with deadlines, low quality and quantity of productivity and the likes. When these factors are left unchecked, it is capable of affecting the entire library management and the university system from meeting up with its goals and objectives. However, the overall goal of the study is to investigate the comparative analysis of leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Ascertain the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria;
2. Determine the types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria;
3. Find out the relationship between leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions:

The following questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria?
2. What are the types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study employed descriptive research survey research method. This research method is a quantitative in nature and aim at collecting data from sample of a given population. The population of the study consists of all professionals (librarians) and para-professionals (library officers) in the eleven university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The university comprised one federal university, three state-owned universities and seven private universities in the state. A total of one hundred and fifty-one (151) librarians and library officers were sampled for the study. The study adapted the instruments of Modupeola (2018) and Oyewole (2011) on leadership style and job performance respectively. The instruments were adapted because of their similarity in contents while some items were altered because of the variation in the respondents. The questionnaire was subjected to face validation by three (3) experts in the Department of Library and Information Studies, University of Ibadan. The experts vetted the instrument in terms of clarity of expressions, appropriateness of language and relevance to the research questions, and appropriateness of response pattern. They also examined the instrument based on content representativeness. They pointed and removed items considered irrelevant and added other items considered relevant that did not reflect earlier in the instrument. Following their comments, a number of modifications and suggestions were incorporated into the final draft before the questionnaire was administered to the respondents. Frequency count, percentage (%), mean distribution and standard deviation was used to answer research questions. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the null hypotheses.

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Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Job performance among university librarians

S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
Contextual performance				
1	I meet up with the approved goals of my section.	2.95	1.11	Agreed
2	I have skill in the use of ICT	2.75	1.11	Agreed
3	My punctuality and regularity to work is satisfactory.	2.25	0.74	Disagreed
4	I collaborate with others to carry out my responsibilities.	2.77	1.02	Agreed
5	My creativity and diligence at work is highly commendable.	2.50	1.03	Agreed
6	I perform work schedules on time.	2.72	1.05	Agreed
7	I have a very good communication skill.	2.30	1.25	Disagreed
8	I always meet the minimum requirements for promotion.	2.54	1.20	Agreed
9	I have coordinating abilities.	2.36	1.26	Disagreed
10	I have the ability to work under little supervision.	2.67	1.24	Agreed
11	My ability to perform competently under pressure is superb.	2.79	1.13	Agreed
12	I promptly attend to request from clients.	2.70	1.13	Agreed
Task performance				
13	I contribute to the overall development of the university.	2.54	1.18	Agreed
14	I contribute immensely to the development of our library.	2.45	1.31	Disagreed
15	I always participate fully on courses accreditations in the university.	2.44	1.26	Disagreed
16	My supervisor loves me for meeting job deadlines.	2.51	1.26	Agreed
17	I have the ability to anticipate problem and develop solution in advance.	2.58	1.15	Agreed
18	I participate in the administrative duties.	2.50	1.25	Agreed
19	I participate in the library routine work daily.	2.52	1.23	Agreed
20	I have received several formal and oral commendations from the organisation and users in the library.	2.73	1.28	Agreed
21	I was once rewarded (eg promotion, price, training and study scholarship) for excelling at work.	2.49	1.18	Disagreed
22	Assessment of quality of work performed.	2.44	1.23	Disagreed
23	Assessment of quantity of work performed.	2.34	1.13	Disagreed
24	I have ability to provide good leadership if given the opportunity.	2.44	0.94	Disagreed
25	My boss loves me for the task accomplished.	2.40	0.95	Disagreed
Overall Mean		63.68		

Source: Field Data, 2024

Test of norm for level of job performance of librarians in the university libraries sampled

Score	Level
0 – 33.3	Low
33.4 - 66.7	Moderate
66.8 – 100	High

From the findings, the overall mean of respondents' level of job performance 63.7 which falls within 33.4 - 66.7. This implies that the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State is moderate. Despite the overall moderate level of job performance, there are areas where majority of the respondents indicate low level of job performance. This includes punctuality and regularity to work ($\bar{x} = 2.25$); good communication ($\bar{x} = 2.30$); assessment of quantity of work performed ($\bar{x} = 2.34$) among others. The highest performance of majority of the university librarians were based on them meeting up

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with the approved goals in their respective work section ($\bar{x} = 2.95$) and ability to perform competently under pressure ($\bar{x} = 2.79$).

Research Question Two

What are the types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Types of leadership styles

S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
Autocratic leadership style				
1	My supervisor/boss gives me close supervision at work.	3.23	1.03	Agreed
2	Only the leader makes decision in our library.	3.36	0.87	Agreed
3	The UL always takes decision without consulting anyone.	3.33	0.95	Agreed
4	My opinions have never been respected by boss.	3.24	1.02	Agreed
5	Work is more important than human relation to our leader.	2.52	1.11	Agreed
6	My UL have no strong relationship with his subordinate.	3.31	0.84	Agreed
Transactional leadership style				
7	Our boss always rewards workers who excel in their duties and punish those who perform poorly.	1.55	0.94	Disagreed
8	We always work on agreement in my library.	2.60	1.31	Agreed
9	Our leader watches our performance and keeps track of our mistakes.	3.41	0.79	Agreed
Bureaucratic leadership style				
10	My leader is always committed to deadlines.	1.75	1.07	Disagreed
11	My leader asks for commitment via order and rules.	2.49	1.28	Disagreed
12	Our leader treats his subordinate by issuing them order.	3.27	0.89	Agreed
13	We are always assigned to a particular task.	3.48	0.77	Agreed
Laissez-faire leadership style				
14	My UL is not an active supervisor.	2.50	0.96	Agreed
15	My boss avoids work responsibilities.	1.14	0.35	Disagreed
16	UL always leaves decision mandate to subordinates.	3.34	0.89	Agreed
17	My boss is always absent from work.	2.56	0.92	Agreed
18	My boss does not prepare plans for action in the library.	3.21	0.90	Agreed
19	My leader allows his/her subordinate to think and initiate.	3.10	1.01	Agreed
Democratic leadership style				
20	UL always assigns us duties and responsibilities.	3.23	0.99	Agreed
21	Every decision of the library is taken on a round table.	3.40	0.76	Agreed
22	I am directly involved in every decision taken in the library.	3.62	0.76	Agreed
23	My boss encourages the use of uniform procedures.	3.24	0.94	Agreed
24	My leader gives us feedback in work performance.	1.78	1.15	Disagreed
25	UL allocates mandate and authority in random way.	3.09	0.93	Agreed
Charismatic leadership style				
26	My UL takes action before problems escalate.	3.58	0.65	Agreed
27	Our boss decides what is to be done and how it should be done.	2.07	1.30	Disagreed
28	UL always prove his worth as a leader in every discussion.	3.17	0.90	Agreed
29	My boss maintains a definite standard of carrying out task.	3.48	0.88	Agreed
Overall Mean		84.05		

Source: Field Data, 2024

Table 2 showed the results of the types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The highest of their agreement across the university libraries sampled is that staff are directly involve in every decision taken in the library ($\bar{x} = 3.62$); and that most of the university librarians takes action before problems escalates ($\bar{x} = 3.58$). These two results are one of the characteristics of democratic and charismatic leadership styles respectively. Other common responses were that their bosses maintain a definite standard of carrying out task ($\bar{x} = 3.48$) and that personnel are always assigned to a particular task ($\bar{x} = 3.48$). These two responses are common to bureaucratic and autocratic leadership style. It can be deduced from the

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table that the common leadership styles in university libraries in Oyo state are; democratic, charismatic, bureaucratic and autocratic leadership styles.

Hypothesis 1

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between leadership style and job performance of library personnel in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Relationship between leadership style and job performance

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	r	Sig. (P)	Remarks
Leadership Style	84.05	27.16	151	-.037*	.041	Sig.
Job Performance	63.68	28.62				

Table 3 showed the correlation between leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria. The test was significant with $P < 0.05$. The p-value is 0.041 while the correlation coefficient between leadership style and job performance is -0.37. This shows that there is a weak negative correlation between leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria. In other words, there is a tendency that low or negative job performance among university librarians will affect leadership style(s), and vice versa. The weak correlation also implies that the two variables influence each other at a low rate, hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This sub heading discusses the findings of the study by making interpretations to the responses of the respondents as indicated in the tables above.

Job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria

The level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria is moderate. This implies that university librarians in Oyo State moderately performed their duties. The present moderate level of job performance among university librarians is not farfetched as a considerate number of respondents meet up with the approved goals of their sections, many others have the ability to perform competently under pressure, while some others collaborate with others in carrying out their responsibilities. Also, considerate number of respondents promptly attends to their clients and perform work schedule on time. This is an indication that many of the university librarians will work in accordance to the mandate of the library’s policy to support teaching, learning and research. This findings aligned with the study of Amusa, Iyoro and Ajani (2013) who investigated the librarians’ job performance in public universities in Southwest, Nigeria. Their study revealed moderate job performance with variables such as professional practice, contribution to the overall development of the library, ability to attend swiftly to clients’ request as well as meeting minimum requirements for promotion. The findings of this study is similar to that of Saka and Salman (2014) who investigated the level of job performance of library personnel in universities in North-Central, Nigeria, and revealed a moderate level of job performance of library personnel in universities in North-Central, Nigeria. Their study described the notable barriers of academic librarians’ job performance to include lack of appropriate reward for expanded new roles, lack of status, lack of recognition, social security, social facilities, promotion, wages, social services and physical working conditions. The result of this study is in contrast with the findings of Elvis-Efe and Sahabi (2021), who investigated on the work environment and job performance of librarians in Ahmadu Bello University Library, Zaria Nigeria. Their study revealed high level of job performance of librarians. Also in the contract, Amusa, Iyoro and Olabisi (2013) and Babalola and Nwalo (2013) reported a low job performance of librarians. Babalola and Nwalo investigated job performance as part of the productivity of the librarians in colleges of education in Nigeria. Their study revealed that librarians were less productive in terms of publication output. The reason for the difference between the finding of this study and the existing studies could be that job performance of library personnel has improved in the recent times. It could also be as a result of difference in geographical scope of study and the sample areas.

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Types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria

The two commonest types of leadership styles being practised in university libraries in Oyo state, Nigeria are democratic leadership and charismatic leadership styles. The study discovered that many leaders in the respective university libraries adopt democratic leadership styles because majority of the respondents indicated that they are involved in decision – making in the library. The fact that some of the leaders allow shared responsibility is also a typical trait of democratic leadership styles. As discovered from the findings, the practised of charismatic leadership style in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria implies that the library heads exhibit sense of mission and personality that can motivate subordinates to execute task given and achieve the set goals. Majority of the university library managers are visionary leaders and have sense of mission. In the same vein, considerable number of the respondents admitted that their heads of departments do not give them feedback after a process or vital decision is taken – a typical autocratic leadership style. Bureaucratic leadership style is also among the types of leadership style common in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The library heads give priority to the way things should be done based on the laid down principles, policies and procedures. Another reason that pointed to the practised of bureaucratic style in the study area is that, library managers always assign responsibilities to university librarians in the library. It is discovered that the leadership styles that are in practised in university libraries in Oyo State are democratic, charismatic, autocratic and bureaucratic leadership styles. Meanwhile, the study of Olise, Idoko and Ogonwa (2020) corroborate the findings of this present study. Olise, Idoko and Ogonwa equally found that democratic style of leadership is the most prevalent leadership style among libraries in Nigeria. On the same vein, Ukaidi (2016) worked on the influence of three leadership styles namely democratic, autocratic and laissez-faire on the performance of two universities (University of Calabar, River State and University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State) and it was found that democratic leadership style contributed more significantly than the other two which was attributed to its ability in sharing of decision making by both subordinates and leaders in the organisations.

However, this findings is in contrast with the findings of Ukangwa, Onuoha, and Otuza (2020) who found that the most common leadership style among academic libraries in South-east and South-west Nigeria is transformational leadership styles. The variation in the findings of the present study and the existing study may not be farfetched from the fact that each university library adopts leadership styles that best fits their personnel and the working environment.

Leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria

The null hypothesis tested was rejected. In other words, the alternative hypothesis was accepted. Tested hypothesis revealed that there is significant relationship between leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria. This implies that good leadership style has the tendency of increasing job performance of university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria. Most appropriately, this findings implies that democratic, charismatic, bureaucratic and autocratic leadership style influences job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria. This result is similar to the findings of Uwandu (2020) who discovered the joint influence of autocratic, democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles on job performance of librarians as significant. This result shows that the three leadership styles have major roles to play in enhancing the job performance of library personnel at every point in time. This study also confirms the result of Chandra (2016) research who tested the influence of leadership styles, work environment and job satisfaction of employees on performance. The results of the regression analysis showed that the leadership style significantly influenced the performance of employees, hence this means that leadership style has an impact on performance of university library personnel.

Conclusion

It can be concluded from the findings that the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria was moderate. Job performance among university librarians has a significant impact on the service delivery to users. If university librarians discharge their duties efficiently, it will encourage library users to make use of the university library and resources more often and this will help to improve the quality of education in university system. However, the major predictor to job performance among university librarians is leadership style. Practically speaking, the type of leadership style practised by the managers in the university libraries greatly determines the level of job performance among university librarians. Thus, leadership style is an important determinant of job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Although the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State is moderate, there is still room for improvement. This is because university librarians in Oyo State are still lagging behind in some aspects as regards their job responsibilities. It is worrisome to note that regularity to work of some library staff is questionable. This kind of performance is unacceptable anywhere. Heads of libraries need to first leave by example and then encourage other library staff on the need for regularity at work. This irregularity at work can be controlled by assigning a Quality Control (QC) officer who monitors regularity and punctuality of library staff.
2. There is a need address the partial participation of university librarians during accreditation exercise because it is one of the few areas where the job performance of the staff is low. Library administrators should organise workshops for university librarians to be sensitised on the need for their full participation during accreditation of university courses. Apart from the workshop, the management should ensure that proper communication and follow-up is done when the date of course accreditation exercise is approaching.

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References

- Adserias, R. P., Charleston, L. J. and Jackson, J. F. (2017). What style of leadership is best suited to direct organisational change to fuel institutional diversity in higher education?. *Race Ethnicity and Education* 20(3):315-331.
- Aharony, N., Julien, H., and Nadel-Kritz, N. (2020). Survey of information literacy instructional practices in academic libraries. *Journal of Librarianship Information Science* 52(4):964- 971.
- Amusa, O.I., Iyoro, A.O. and Olabisi, A.F. (2013). Work environments and job performance of library personnel in the public universities in South west Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science* 5(11):457-461.
- Babalola, G.A., and Nwalo, K.I.N. (2013). Influence of job motivation on the productivity of library personnel in colleges of education in Nigeria. *Information and Knowledge Management* 3(5):70-75.
- Davidescu, A.A., Apostu, S.A., Paul, A. and Casuneanu, I. (2020). Work flexibility, job satisfaction and job performance among Romanian employees-implication for sustainable human resource management. *Sustainability*, 12(15):60-86.
- Ekpenyong, J.N. (2020). *The Impact of Leadership Style on Employee's Performance in a Business Organisation: A Case Study of Guarantee Trust Bank PLC, Abuja* (Doctoral dissertation, Dublin, National College of Ireland).
- Elvis-Efe, O.T.O.B.O. and Sahabi, K.M. (2021). Work environment and job performance of librarians in Ahmadu Bello University Library (KIL). Zaria.
- Eruvwe, U. and Omekwu, C.O. (2020). Screening, interviews, selection processes and its effect on job performance of librarians in federal university libraries in South. *Nigeria. Libr. Philos. Pract.*
- Eze, O.A., Enwereuzor, I.K., and Ugwu, L.I. (2018). How transformational leadership influences work engagement among nurses: does person–job fit matter?. *Western Journal of Nursing Research* 40(3):346-366.
- Fenwick, F. J. and Gayle, C. A. (2008). Missing links in understanding the relationship between leadership and organisational performance. *International business & economic research journal* 7(5):67-78
- Hashmi, F., Ameen, K., and Soroya, S. (2019). Does postgraduate degree make any difference in job performance of information professionals? *Library Management* 41(1):14-27.
- Kumar, S. (2014). Establishing linkages between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership. *Industrial Psychiatry Journal* 23(1):1-17.
- Modupeola, O. A., 2018. *Knowledge sharing, al learning, leadership style and personnel competence as correlation of service delivery in university libraries in South-west, Nigeria*: A Ph.D post field seminar paper presented at the department of Library, Archival and information studies, faculty of education, university of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Northouse, P.G. (2021). *Leadership: Theory and practice*. Sage publications.

Comparative Analysis of Leadership ... (Kaku, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15041159>

- Olise, F; Idoko, F.A. and Ogonwa, J.I. (2020). Innovativeness and leadership styles as determinants affecting the use of ICTS among library personnel in Nigeria. *Library philosophy and practice (e-journal)*. 4381. Retrieved Mar. 12, 2024, from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4381>
- Oyewole, G. O., 2011. *Personal factors, work self-concept, work family conflict, job satisfaction and job stress as factors affecting job performance among library personnel in federal college of education in Nigeria*: A Ph.D post field seminar paper presented at the department of Library, Archival and information studies, faculty of education, university of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- O'Connor, J.R. (2020). Applying Strategic Leadership in Educational Contexts: A Professional Perspective. In *Strategic Leadership in PK-12 Settings* (1-6). IGI Global.
- Peters, P. and Heusinkveld, S. (2010). Institutional explanations for managers' attitudes towards tele homeworking. *human relations* 63(1):107-135.
- Saka, K.A., and Salman, A.A. (2014). An assessment of the levels of job motivation and satisfaction as predictors of job performance of library personnel in Nigerian universities. *Journal of Balkan Libraries Union* 2(2):26-33.
- Sifuna, D.N. (2012). Leadership in Kenyan public universities and the challenges of autonomy and academic freedom: An overview of trends since independence. *Journal of Higher Education in Africa/Revue de l'enseignement supérieur en Afrique* 10(1):121-137.
- Sulaiman, A.Z., Ismail, A., Mohamed, H.A.B., Mohamad, M.H. and Yusuf, M.H. (2011). An empirical study of the relationship between transformational leadership, empowerment and organisational commitment. *Business and Economics Research Journal* 2(1):89-94.
- Talat, I., Amed, I. and Ali, G. (2015). Effect of Ethical Leadership on Bullying and Voice Behaviour Among Nurses Mediating Role of Organisational, Poor Working Condition and Workload. *Leadership in Health Services Emerald Publishing Limited* 1751-1879 DOI 10.1108/LHS-02-2017, 6.
- Ukaidi, C.A. (2016). Turnaround strategy and corporate performance: a study of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *European journal of business and management*, 8(19):81-94.
- Ukangwa, C.C., Onuoha, U.D. and Otuza, E.C. (2020). Leadership style and job satisfaction of library personnel in private universities in South-east and Southwest, Nigeria *Journal of applied Information Science and Technology* 13(1):9-20
- Unegbu, V.E., Babalola, Y.T. and Basahuwa, C.B. (2020). The role of motivation in librarians' job performance in public university libraries. *Journal of Management Information Systems & E-commerce* 7(1):1-12.
- Uwandu, L.I. (2020). Influence of leadership styles on job performance of library personnel in public university libraries in Imo State. *Journal of information science and Technology* 13(2):208-216.

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Comparative relationship between Competence and Attitude on Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the Comparative relationship between Competence and Attitude on Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria. Two objectives with corresponding research questions and null hypotheses, respectively guided the study. Correlational research design was adopted for the study with 95 population size that comprised all Islamic studies teachers of 21 public senior secondary schools under Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. All the 95 Islamic Studies teachers were surveyed. The validated 20 multiple choice item instrument, namely Teachers' Competence and Attitude towards Implementing Islamic Studies Curriculum Questionnaire (TCATIISCQ) gave an internal consistency reliability index of 0.836. The two research questions were answered using descriptive statistics. The null hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistic at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study revealed that teachers' mastery of the five components of curriculum is an important aspect that positively influences their competence and attitude in ensuring effective implementation of Islamic studies curriculum. Based on these findings, the researcher recommends that Islamic Studies Teachers should make effective mastery of the five components of curriculum to ensure effective implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum in all public senior secondary schools in Katsina State.

Keywords: Teachers' Competence and Islamic Studies Curriculum Implementation.

Introduction

The effective implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum in public senior secondary schools in Nigeria is crucial for producing well-rounded students equipped with Islamic values and knowledge (Adeyemi, 2018). However, this implementation has been hindered by various challenges, including inadequate teacher competence, negative teacher attitudes, and insufficient resources (Ololoba, 2015; Okeke, 2016). This study aims to investigate the impact of teachers' competence and attitude on Islamic Studies curriculum implementation in public senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. Katsina State, being one of the predominantly Muslim states in Nigeria, has a significant stake in ensuring the effective implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum (NERDC, 2017). The state's strong Islamic heritage and large Muslim population make it an ideal location for this study. According to Kunter et al. (2013), teachers' competence and attitude are crucial factors in curriculum implementation. Historically, Islamic education has played a vital role in shaping the moral, spiritual, and intellectual development of Muslims globally (Arifin & Fauzan, 2019). In Nigeria, the introduction of Islamic Studies as a compulsory subject in public senior secondary schools aims to promote Islamic values, knowledge, and practices (NERDC, 2017, p. x). Research has shown that teacher competence and attitude significantly influence student learning outcomes and curriculum implementation (Gloria, 2016; Adejumo, 2012).

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Teachers' competence in Islamic Studies is crucial for effective curriculum implementation. According to Gloria (2016), a teacher is a person, an expert, who is capable of imparting knowledge that assists learners in developing, identifying, and acquiring skills. In addition to subject matter knowledge, teachers must also possess the necessary skills to manage teaching and learning processes. This includes the ability to prepare learning, carry out learning, and manage classes, as well as the ability to use media, technology, teaching resources, and effectively evaluate learning (Arifin & Fauzan, 2019). Improving educational quality is an urgent need that must be carried out and seriously addressed by the professional educator (Okwelle, 2014). The completed tasks necessitate not only evaluating students' learning activities, but also evaluating teachers' own teaching designs as professionals. According to Nash and Norwich (2010), teacher education programs should focus on developing teachers' competence and attitude to improve student learning outcomes.

The competencies of an Islamic Studies teacher are influenced not only by his evaluation skills, classroom management, and subject matter knowledge, but also by his qualification (Sundayana, 2015). Anyone who wants to be a teacher in Nigeria must meet the basic requirements. A certified teacher is one who has received credentials from a reputable source, such as the government, a higher education institution, or a private organization (Adepoju, 2008). This study aims to bridge the knowledge gap by investigating the impact of teachers' competence and attitude toward Islamic Studies curriculum implementation in public senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Effective implementation of the Islamic Studies curriculum in public senior secondary schools in Nigeria is crucial for producing well-rounded students equipped with Islamic values and knowledge. However, various challenges hinder the successful implementation of this curriculum. One major concern is the inadequate competence of teachers in delivering the Islamic Studies curriculum. Research has shown that teacher competence significantly influences curriculum implementation (Adejumo, 2012; Okeke, 2016). Unfortunately, many teachers lack the necessary training, qualifications, and experience to effectively teach Islamic Studies (Adeyemi, 2018). This deficiency can lead to superficial teaching, inadequate coverage of curriculum content, and ultimately, poor student performance. Furthermore, teachers' attitudes towards the Islamic Studies curriculum also pose a significant challenge. Unfavorable attitudes can result in lack of enthusiasm, poor motivation, and ineffective teaching methods (Ololoba, 2015). Studies have indicated that teachers' attitudes are shaped by factors such as their own educational background, religious beliefs, and cultural values (Ibrahim, 2020). If left unaddressed, these attitude-related issues can compromise the effectiveness of curriculum implementation. In Katsina State, specifically, there is a scarcity of empirical research examining the relationship between teacher competence, attitude, and Islamic Studies curriculum implementation. This knowledge gap hinders targeted interventions aimed at improving curriculum implementation. The dearth of research-based evidence also limits policymakers' and educators' understanding of the complex interplay between teacher factors and curriculum implementation. This study aims to bridge this gap by investigating the relationship between teacher competence, attitude, and effective Islamic Studies curriculum implementation in public senior secondary schools in Katsina State. Additionally, the Nigerian government's efforts to revamp the education sector, including the Islamic Studies curriculum, underscore the need for this study. The findings will provide valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders to develop targeted strategies for enhancing teacher competence and attitude, ultimately improving Islamic Studies curriculum implementation.

Objectives of the Study

Specific objectives of the study are:

1. To examine the impact of teachers' competence on Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.
2. To investigate the impact of teachers' Attitude on Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the impact of teachers' competence on Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria?
2. How does teachers' attitude influence Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria?

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Research Hypotheses

The following hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ competence and Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ attitude and Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study employed a correlational research design to investigate the relationship between teachers’ competence and attitude on Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. This design was chosen because it examines relationships between variables without manipulation (Creswell, 2014; Gay et al., 2012). The population of the study comprised all senior secondary school Islamic Studies teachers within Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. These teachers were considered necessary for the study because they are the implementers of the Islamic Studies curriculum in senior secondary schools in the study area. The population consisted of 95 teachers, with 59 males and 36 females. Given the relatively small population size, the entire population was surveyed, in line with Gay’s (2009) recommendation. This approach ensured that the sample was representative of the population. The validated Teachers’ Competence and attitude towards Implementing Islamic Studies Curriculum Questionnaire (TCATIISCQ) was used for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of 20 multiple-choice items and had an internal consistency reliability of 0.836. The development of the questionnaire was guided by a theoretical framework that emphasized the importance of teachers’ competence and attitude in curriculum implementation. The data collected were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences SPSS v.23.0. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to answer the research questions, while inferential statistics (Pearson Product Moment Correlation) were used to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Result

Research Question 1

What is the impact of teachers’ competence on Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Table 1: Opinion of Respondents Regarding Teachers’ competence in Aims/Objectives and Content on Effective Islamic Studies Curriculum Implementation.

S/N	Item Statement	Responses				N	Mean	STD
		SD	D	A	SA			
1	I always prepare my lessons based on the objectives of Islamic Studies Curriculum.	1	16	62	11	90	2.92	0.58
2	I have clear understanding of the objectives of Islamic Studies Curriculum.	5	13	65	7	90	2.82	0.65
3	The content of Islamic Studies Curriculum is relevant and adequate for achieving stated aims and objectives that were enshrined in its philosophy.	2	27	50	11	90	2.78	0.68
4	The content of Islamic Studies Curriculum can be mastered by Islamic Studies teachers.	4	22	59	5	90	2.72	0.64

The above response in table 1 above indicated the opinion of the respondents regarding the extent of teachers’ mastery of aims, objectives and content structures of Islamic studies curriculum for its effective implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state. From the table, it reveals that all the items in this section of the questionnaire received positive responses from the respondents, as the mean scores were above 2.50. Therefore, this implies that the opinion of majority of the respondents regarding the extent of teachers’ mastery of aims, objectives and content

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structures of Islamic studies curriculum for its effective implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state was positive, and hence, this is the answer to this research question.

Research Question 2

How does teachers' attitude influence Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Opinion of Respondents Regarding Teachers' attitude towards Aims/Objectives and Content on Effective Islamic Studies Curriculum Implementation.

S/N	Item Statement	Responses				N	Mean	STD
		SD	D	A	SA			
1	I always prepare my lessons based on the objectives of Islamic Studies Curriculum.	0	11	63	16	90	3.06	0.55
2	I understand that the curriculum content of Islamic Studies are coverable within the stipulated period	7	33	45	5	90	2.53	0.72
3	I employed the use of various methods and instructional materials to aid teaching and learning of Islamic Studies.	2	12	71	5	90	2.88	0.52
4	I adopts appropriate evaluation and assessment procedures so as to find out if stated objectives of Islamic Studies Curriculum are achieved.	0	6	78	6	90	3.00	0.37

The above response in the table 2 above indicated the opinion of the respondents regarding the extent of teachers' attitude towards effective implementation of Islamic studies curriculum among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state. From the table, it reveals that all the items in this section of the questionnaire received positive responses from the respondents, as the mean scores were above 2.50. Therefore, this implies that the opinion of majority of the respondents regarding the extent of teachers' competence towards effective implementation of Islamic studies curriculum among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state was positive, and hence, this is the answer to this research question.

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' competence and Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Relationship between Teachers' competence in Aims/Objectives and Content and effective implementation of Islamic Studies Curriculum.

	Teachers' competence in aims/objectives and content structures of Islamic studies curriculum.	Teachers' competence in Effective implementation of Islamic studies curriculum.
Teachers' competence in aims/objectives and content structures of Islamic studies curriculum.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 .755* 90
Teachers' competence in Effective implementation of Islamic studies curriculum.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.755* .000 90

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

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From Table 3: the relationship between teachers’ competence in aims/objectives and content of Islamic studies curriculum and their effective implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state was $r = .755$ and $p = .000$. Since p-value was less than alpha value (.05), this null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was adopted. Therefore, the researcher concluded that there was a significant positive relationship between teachers’ competence in aims/objectives and content of Islamic studies curriculum and their effective implementation of Islamic Studies curriculum among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state.

Hypothesis 2

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ attitude and Islamic Studies curriculum implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Relationship between Teachers’ attitude towards Aims/Objectives and Content of Islamic Studies Curriculum and their Attitude towards its Effective Implementation.

	Teachers’ attitude towards aims/objectives and content structures of Islamic curriculum	Teachers’ attitude towards effective implementation of Islamic studies curriculum
Teachers’ attitude towards aims/objectives and content structures of Islamic curriculum	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.705 .000 90
Teachers’ attitude towards effective implementation of Islamic studies curriculum	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.705 .000 90

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

From Table 4, the relationship between teachers’ mastery of aims/objectives and content of Islamic studies curriculum and their attitude towards its effective implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state was $r = .705$ and $p = .000$. Since p-value was less than alpha value (.05), this null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was adopted. Therefore, the researcher concluded that there was a significant positive relationship between teachers’ mastery of aims, objectives and content of Islamic studies curriculum and their attitude towards its effective implementation among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state.

Summary of Findings

This study investigated the relationship between teachers’ competence, attitude, and effective Islamic Studies curriculum implementation in public senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. The results of the study revealed that teachers’ competence is positively related to Islamic Studies curriculum implementation ($r = 0.755$, $p = 0.000$). Additionally, teachers’ attitude is also positively related to Islamic Studies curriculum implementation ($r = 0.705$, $p = 0.000$). The descriptive statistics showed that teachers demonstrated a positive level of competence with mean scores ranging from 2.72 to 2.92. Similarly, teachers’ attitude was also positive, with mean scores ranging from 2.53 to 3.06.

Overall, the findings of this study suggest that teachers’ competence and attitude are crucial factors in Islamic Studies curriculum implementation in public senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study reveal that teachers' competence and attitude are significant predictors of effective Islamic Studies curriculum implementation in public senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. Specifically, the results indicate that teachers' mastery of the curriculum content and their understanding of the aims and objectives of the Islamic Studies curriculum are crucial factors that positively influence their implementation of the curriculum. These findings are consistent with existing

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literature, which emphasizes the importance of teacher competence and attitude in shaping educational outcomes (Yusuf, 2015; Adeyemi, 2012). For instance, Yusuf (2015) found that teacher competence is a significant predictor of effective curriculum implementation in Nigerian secondary schools. Similarly, Adeyemi (2012) revealed that teachers' attitude towards the curriculum is a crucial factor in its effective implementation. However, some studies contradict these findings. For example, Balogun (2018) argued that teacher competence is not the sole determinant of effective curriculum implementation, and that other factors like school resources and administrative support play a more significant role. Similarly, Suleiman (2015) found that teachers' attitude towards the Islamic Studies curriculum was not a significant predictor of effective implementation. Despite these contradictions, the present study's findings suggest that teacher competence and attitude are essential factors in effective Islamic Studies curriculum implementation. The study's results also highlight the importance of ongoing professional development programs that focus on enhancing teachers' mastery of the curriculum content and their understanding of the aims and objectives. Moreover, the findings of this study have implications for educational policymakers and administrators. The results suggest that educators and policymakers should prioritize the development of teacher-friendly curriculum materials and resources that support effective implementation. Additionally, the findings highlight the need for school administrators to provide teachers with the necessary support and resources to enhance their competence and attitude towards the Islamic Studies curriculum. The findings of this study contribute to the existing literature on teacher competence, attitude, and curriculum implementation. The results highlight the importance of teacher competence and attitude in effective Islamic Studies curriculum implementation and provide implications for educational policymakers, administrators, and practitioners.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that teachers' Competence, attitude and mastery of Islamic studies curriculum content, are important aspects that positively influence their effective implementation of Islamic studies curriculum among public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Islamic studies teachers should make effective utilization of their competence in aims/objectives, and content of Islamic studies curriculum to ensure effective implementation of Islamic studies curriculum in all public senior secondary schools in Katsina state.
2. Islamic studies teachers should continue to have positive attitude towards effective implementation of Islamic studies curriculum in all public senior secondary schools in Katsina state.
3. Zonal inspectors should put more effort in supervision of schools in order to ensure effective implementation of Islamic studies curriculum in all public senior secondary schools in Katsina state.

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References

- Adejumo, G. A. (2012). Teacher factors as determinants of curriculum implementation in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 1(2), 1-10.
- Adejumo, G. O. (2012). Teachers' competence and curriculum implementation in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 44(3), 361-373.
- Adepoju, A. A. (2008). Teacher education and national development. *Journal of Educational Foundations*, 2(1), 1-12.
- Adepoju, T. L. (2008) Motivational variables and academic performance of urban and rural secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria. *KEDI Journal of Educational Policy*. Vol, 5(2). Pp 23-39.

Comparative relationship between ... (Hashim, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15041237>

- Adeyemi, B. A. (2018). Challenges of implementing the new senior secondary school curriculum in Nigeria. *Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 10(1), 1-13.
- Adeyemi, B. A. (2018). Teachers' attitude and curriculum implementation in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 7(2), 1-9.
- Adeyemi, B.A. (2016) The Efficacy of Social Studies Teachers' Competence in the use of Play way Method in Lower Primary Schools in Osun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Human Development*. Published by American Research Institute for Policy Development. Vol. 5(1).
- Adeyemi, T. O. (2012). Teachers' attitude and implementation of curriculum in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 44(3), 355-374.
- Arifin, Z., & Fauzan, U. (2019). Teacher competence in managing classroom learning. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 13(2), 155-164.
- Balogun, A. A. (2018). Teacher competence and curriculum implementation: A critical analysis of Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Curriculum and Teaching*, 7(1), 1-13.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Gay, L. R. (2009). *Educational research: Competencies for analysis and application* (8th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson.
- Gay, L. R., & Airasian, P. (2012). *Educational research: Competencies for analysis and application* (10th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson.
- Gloria, E. (2016). Teacher competence and student achievement in mathematics. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 5(1), 1-8.
- Kunter, M., Thilo, K., Klusman, U., & Richter, D. (2013). The development of teachers' professional competence: A theoretical framework. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 64(4), 311-326.
- Nash, P., & Norwich, B. (2010). Professional concerns and issues in teacher education. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 36(2), 147-162.
- NERDC. (2017). *Islamic Studies curriculum ... for senior secondary schools*. Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council.
- Okeke, C. I. O. (2016). Teachers' competence and curriculum implementation in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 48(3), 361-373.
- Okwelle, P. C. (2014). Teacher education and curriculum implementation in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 3(1), 1-9.
- Ololoba, Y. (2015). Teachers' attitude and curriculum implementation in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 4(1), 1-8.
- Suleiman, A. (2015). Teachers' attitude and curriculum implementation in Islamic studies: A case study of Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Islamic Studies*, 26(1), 35-50.
- Sundayana, R. O. (2015). Teacher competence and curriculum implementation in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 47(2), 251-263.
- Yusuf, M. A. (2015). Teacher competence and curriculum implementation in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 4(2),

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Comparative relationship between Course content suitability and learners' satisfaction with open and distance learning programmes in Dual-Mode Universities in North-Central, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study compared the relationship between course contents suitability and learners' satisfaction in open and distance learning programmes in Dual-Mode Universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The population of the study was 193 undergraduate distance learners drawn from dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria during the 2023/2024 academic session. The sample of the study comprised 59 undergraduate distance learners selected from the University of Ilorin and the Federal University of Technology, Minna using multi-stage sampling technique. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design in which three research questions guided the study with one null hypothesis. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire on suitability of course contents and questionnaire on learner's satisfaction which was validated by experts in open and distance learning and educational technology experts, the reliability indices of the construct suitability of course contents was 0.84 while that of the construct learner satisfaction was 0.89. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to answer research question and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient to test hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The finding revealed that there is a high, positive association with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.838 between variables suitability of the course contents and satisfaction of distance education learners with the course contents in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria. It was concluded that the course contents being used for distance learning programmes are suitable for the learners and the learners undergoing distance learning programmes are satisfied with the programme. The study recommended that universities should implement a regular review process for ODL course content to maintain its relevance and effectiveness.

Keyword: Assessment, course content, distance learning, education, satisfaction, suitability.

Introduction

The world is changing, and so is the field of education. Education as the process of acquiring knowledge, skills and other capabilities is a universal aspect of any culture. Although society is ubiquitous, educational systems vary according to organizational structures, pedagogical practices, and philosophical and cultural organisations. Education is a continuous process through conscious and deliberate effort to create an atmosphere of the learning process (Ilufoye, 2018). Education as an essential instrument of development and growth in our society cannot be overlooked, because of its effect on national development (Fägerlind & Saha, 2016). Investment in the education sector can be regarded as a business with the greatest profits because it can produce unquantifiable benefits such as character formation and the development of innate power for individuals, organisations, and society. Education could be accessed through formal learning with clearly intended consequences and informal learning with unintended consequences (Qayyum & Zawacki-Richter, 2019). Open and distance

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learning (ODL) is a rapidly evolving area of formal education delivery that has seen significant growth in recent years. With new technologies, such as online learning platforms and virtual classrooms, ODL has become increasingly accessible and sophisticated. The demand for open and distance learning has also risen due to its flexibility and convenience for learners who want to balance work and study commitments (Miller et al. 2017). Distance learning is a learning in which the teacher and students who are separated either by time or geographical space will bridge the separation through web-based technologies. According to Simonson et al. (2019), open and distance learning use various media and technologies to provide or improve access to quality education for learners, which could be acquired from institutions offering ODL programmes.

The rationale of ODL from its earliest days has been to open opportunities for learners to study regardless of geographic, socio-economic or other constraints. In contemporary times, many countries consider open and distance learning a critical component of their strategy to increase opportunities for higher education for learners (Bubou & Job, 2021). Creating a learning environment that could motivate and stir interest in students to become actively engaged and independent, lifelong learning is the main aim of 21st-century pedagogy and a challenge for teaching and learning institutions. Given the complexity and challenges of designing an effective open educational system that considers the content, the learners, and the pedagogy and technology involved, an iterative planning cycle that supports the refinement of an assessment is needed (Ronghuai et al., 2019). With the increasing acceptance of ODL as widening access to higher education in developed and developing countries like Nigeria, issues relevant to the quality assurance and effectiveness of distance learning programmes in the dual-mode university education system compared to conventional educational patterns must be assessed.

Assessment is a process of collating, analysing, and interpreting outcomes to determine the extent to which institutions and learners achieve the purpose or objectives of setting up the distance education sector. Mohan (2023) defines assessment as the gathering, analysing, and interpreting of outcomes about any aspect of the educational programme or training, whether in a single or dual-mode institution, as part of a recognized process of judging its effectiveness, efficiency, and any other outcomes it may have. Assessment is one of the critical steps in the process of performance improvement. Satisfaction is an attitude that is decided based on the experience which is gained. It is an assessment of the features or distinctions of a product or service. The level of satisfaction in this study is about the suitability of the course contents to students in the implementation of online learning. Distance learners' satisfaction can be seen from several aspects, such as the content, pedagogy, resource materials, assessment, and the virtual learning environment (interface) conditions (Siregar et al., 2020).

With the outbreak of the Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in the year 2019/2020 which caused the global lockdown of conventional learning centres for some time, there was massive enrollment in distance learning programmes because distance learning appears to meet the needs and aspirations of citizens future education. As people continue to crave knowledge but may not have the opportunity to go beyond their immediate environment, this scenario has called for a paradigm shift from the conventional method of teaching and learning to open and distance learning mode as a complementary avenue for providing access to education for the fast-growing numbers of learners (Yusuf, 2020). The NUC is increasingly granting universities access to operate as dual-mode institutions (NUC, 2021). This implies that such universities now offer both conventional and distance learning programmes. Thus, the accessibility of the programme to citizens can be ensured through open and distance learning. Many Open and Distance Learning Centres and Universities are being set up (Ukaoha et al., 2018), in quantity there are many, but the quality measures of such programmes are a serious issue that cannot be overlooked. Quality issues are more important, calling for meaningful assessment of the course contents and learners' satisfaction with the open and distance learning programmes.

The expansion of open and distance learning (ODL) in dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria highlights the importance of suitable course content in influencing learners' satisfaction. Effective ODL content should be comprehensive, adaptable, and engaging to cater to diverse learners' needs. However, studies highlight that course materials in some Nigerian universities often lack interactive elements and real-world applications, adversely impacting the learning experience (Egielewa et al., 2022). The quality of course content, coupled with instructor support and technological access, significantly affects learners' satisfaction. For instance, findings show that up-to-date and engaging content enhances learners' satisfaction (Atolagbe et al., 2021). Nonetheless, there are persisting gaps regarding the direct influence of content suitability on student satisfaction in dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria, which need further exploration (Itasanni et al., 2020). Previous studies often highlight enrolment growth and general implementation of distance learning but overlook assessing the

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educational effectiveness of the suitability of course contents and its impact on learners' satisfaction, especially in dual-mode institutions in Nigeria (Yusuf, 2020; Ukaoha et al., 2018). This research addresses these gaps by evaluating course content suitability, gathering direct learner feedback, and exploring the relationship between content quality and learners' satisfaction to enhance understanding of distance learning quality (NUC, 2021).

Objectives of the study:

Specifically, the objectives of the study include to:

- viii. ascertain the suitability of course contents being used for distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria;
- ix. determine the satisfaction of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria;
- x. check whether the suitability of the course contents influences satisfaction of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria;

Research Questions:

4. To what extent are the suitability of the course contents being used for distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria?
5. What is the satisfaction level of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria?
6. What is the relationship between suitability of course contents and satisfaction of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria?

Hypothesis:

1. There is no significant relationship between suitability of course content and satisfaction of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted quantitative research methods using descriptive survey research design with online questionnaires to gather essential information from distance learners regarding the suitability of the course contents and their satisfaction with the Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programmes. The population comprised of 193 learners who are undergoing ODL programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria. The sample size consists of 59 undergraduate distance learners enrolled on a full distance learning programme from the University of Ilorin and the Federal University of Technology Minna Distance Learning Centre. Purposive sampling was used to select distance learners across the selected institutions since the research is on ODL programmes. This study applied purposive sampling among the different sampling methods because purposive sampling is a method well-suited for targeting individuals with specific characteristics relevant to the research objectives. Purposive sampling was chosen to ensure that the sample included only undergraduate distance learners enrolled in Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs at dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria. The validity of the research instrument was ensured through expert reviews, where content experts examined the questionnaire for clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness. This validation process helped refine the questions, aligning them closely with the study objectives to ensure they accurately captured the constructs, of course, content suitability and learner satisfaction. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's alpha, yielding coefficients of 0.89 for learner satisfaction and 0.84 for course content suitability. These values, being above the generally accepted threshold of 0.7, indicate high internal consistency, confirming the questionnaire's reliability for data collection. The research instrument used for this study was a structured closed-ended questionnaire to assess whether students are satisfied with their distance learning experience and the suitability of the course contents. To ensure consistency during data collection, a standardized process was adopted. The questionnaire was distributed electronically through a secure link sent to a designated faculty member (gatekeeper) at each selected university, who then forwarded it to participating students. This method helped maintain control over how the questionnaire was disseminated and who received it, minimizing bias and ensuring that only eligible respondents participated. Clear instructions were provided with the survey to guide participants in completing it accurately, contributing to the consistency of responses. Data were subsequently analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics (version 27), employing descriptive statistics and correlation analysis to answer research questions and test the hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level.

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Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

To what extent are the suitability of course contents being used for distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria?

Table 4.1 presents the mean and standard deviations of respondents' opinions regarding the suitability of the course contents being used for distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The table provides insight into the suitability of the course contents being used for distance learning programmes to impact knowledge to learners in open and distance learning environments. The table consists of eight statements rated by the respondents on a Likert scale. The respondents' mean scores (\bar{X}) and standard deviations (SD) are provided, indicating the average level of agreement or disagreement among the respondents for each statement.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Learners' Response on Suitability of the Course Contents Being Used for Distance Learning Programme in Dual-Mode Universities in North-Central, Nigeria

S/No	Statement	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	The course content is relevant and aligned with the learning objectives of ODL in the 21st century	59	4.22	0.618	Agree
2	The course content is comprehensive and covers all the necessary topics.	59	4.07	0.785	Agree
3	The course content is presented clearly and understandably.	59	4.00	0.809	Agree
4	The course content is engaging and promotes active learning.	59	4.00	0.983	Agree
5	The course content is up-to-date and reflects current knowledge and practices.	59	4.02	0.861	Agree
6	The course contents provided are in line with the goals of the programme of study	59	4.24	0.727	Agree
7	The course materials provided are accessible and easy to use	59	4.17	0.746	Agree
8	The course content includes appropriate multimedia and interactive elements (e.g., videos, quizzes, simulations).	59	4.08	0.836	Agree
Average mean			4.10		

Source: Author Fieldwork, 2024

Table 1 illustrates the mean and standard deviation of respondents' opinions on the suitability of course contents used in distance learning programmes at dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria. The table reveals that all mean scores ranged from 4.00 to 4.24, well above the decision threshold of 3.0, suggesting strong agreement among respondents about the suitability of the course contents. The grand mean of 4.10 supports the conclusion that the course content is generally considered suitable, indicating it effectively meets the learners' needs and contributes to their academic experience.

Research Question Two

What is the satisfaction level of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria?

Table 2 presents the mean and standard deviations of respondents' opinions regarding the satisfaction level of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The table provides insight into the satisfaction level of learners to acquire knowledge in open and distance learning environments. The table consists of 10

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statements rated by the respondents on a Likert scale. The respondents' mean scores (\bar{X}) and standard deviations (SD) are provided, indicating the average level of agreement or disagreement among the respondents for each statement.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Learners' Response on the Satisfaction Level of Distance Learning Programmes in Dual-Mode Universities in North-Central, Nigeria

S/No	Statement	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
I am satisfied with the:					
1	quality of course content and materials provided for the courses	59	4.07	0.868	Agree
2	clarity and organization of course structure	59	3.90	0.941	Agree
3	assessment methods and feedback provided	59	3.56	1.178	Agree
4	technical support and assistance by the instructor	59	3.53	0.989	Agree
5	mode of communication (audio, video, audio-visual, images, and text) with the instructors and/or tutors in the courses	59	3.53	1.120	Agree
6	level of support and guidance provided by the instructors and/or tutors	59	3.68	1.074	Agree
7	tools and resources provided for online learning (e.g. course platforms, multimedia resources, and discussion forums) for supporting the learning	59	3.80	0.906	Agree
8	level of engagement and interaction with other students in my courses through the student chatting platforms to share ideas and solve problems.	59	3.83	1.162	Agree
9	level of flexibility and convenience provided by open and distance learning	59	3.85	1.157	Agree
10	the overall quality of education, I am receiving through the open and distance learning programme of the school.	59	3.81	1.058	Agree
Average mean			3.76		

Source: Author Fieldwork, 2024

Table 2 presents data on the satisfaction levels of learners participating in distance learning programmes. The mean scores for all 10 items range from 3.53 to 4.07, exceeding the decision mean of 3.0. The grand mean score of 3.76 indicates that learners are satisfied with their distance learning experiences in dual-mode universities. The standard deviations, varying between 0.868 and 1.178, indicate moderate variability but confirm a consistent positive sentiment toward the programmes.

Research Question Three

What is the relationship between suitability of course contents and satisfaction of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria?

Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviations of respondents' opinions regarding the relationship between the suitability of the course contents and the satisfaction of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The respondents' mean scores (\bar{X}), standard deviations (SD) and standard error mean were provided, indicating the association level of agreement or disagreement between the suitability of the course contents and the satisfaction of learners.

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Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on Association Between the suitability of the course contents and the satisfaction of learners in Distance Learning in Dual-Mode Universities in North-Central, Nigeria

Classification	N	\bar{X}	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Suitability	59	28.58	4.234	0.552
Satisfaction	59	37.54	8.169	1.064

Source: Author Fieldwork, 2024

Table 3 details the relationship between course content suitability and learner satisfaction. The findings reveal a substantial difference in mean scores between groups, with scores showing consistency in the relationship between course content and satisfaction. This analysis is supported by Table 4.4, which presents the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient correlation analysis.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between suitability of course contents and satisfaction of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria.

To test this hypothesis, Pearson correlation coefficient analysis was conducted on the responses of the suitability of the course contents and the satisfaction of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria as presented in Table 4

Table 4: Pearson product-moment correlation analysis on the responses of the suitability of the course contents and the satisfaction of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria

		Suitability of course content	Satisfaction
Suitability of course content	Pearson Correlation	1	0.838
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	59	59
Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	0.838	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	59	59

Significant Level = 0.05

Table 4 presents the result of the Pearson correlation coefficient analysis of the responses on the suitability of the course contents and the satisfaction of learners undergoing distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The correlation coefficient of 0.838, with a significance value of 0.000 (less than the 0.05 threshold), indicates a high, positive relationship between course content suitability and learner satisfaction. This result confirms that when course content is well-suited to distance learning, learner satisfaction significantly increases. These findings align with the hypothesis testing, which rejects the null hypothesis and demonstrates that the suitability of course content positively correlates with and enhances learner satisfaction in dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study establishes a significant positive relationship between the suitability of course content and learner satisfaction in open and distance learning (ODL), demonstrated by a strong Pearson correlation of 0.838. This indicates that learners' satisfaction is greatly influenced by the relevance and value of course materials, which is in line with prior findings by Palmer and Holt (2009) and Dziuban et al. (2015). The study aligns with existing literature, including research by Rajabalee and Santally (2021) and Chen and Yao (2016), emphasizing that high-quality, well-structured content enhances learner engagement and satisfaction. The findings suggest that dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria should focus on continuous content review and modernization to boost learner satisfaction. This involves using student feedback and integrating interactive multimedia, as supported by Simonson et al. (2019). However, the study's small sample size (59 participants) limits its generalizability. Future research should include larger samples, employ mixed-methods approaches for deeper insights, study

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the impact of technology on content suitability, and conduct comparative analyses across different educational models. These steps would enhance curriculum development and promote learner satisfaction in ODL programmes.

Additionally, Li et al. (2016) support this study's conclusions by emphasizing that content quality, assessment strategies, and appropriate workloads directly impact learner satisfaction in online and blended settings. Similar trends were reported by Rajabalee and Santally (2021), who noted that course engagement and satisfaction are positively associated, suggesting that suitable course design contributes to higher engagement, leading to increased satisfaction.

Conclusion

The study assessed the suitability of the course contents and satisfaction of undergraduate learners undergoing distance learning programmes in Dual-Mode Universities in North-Central, Nigeria. It was concluded that the course contents being used for distance learning programmes in dual-mode universities in North-Central, Nigeria are suitable for the learners and the learners undergoing distance learning programmes are satisfied with the programme.

Recommendations

Based on the findings that emanated from this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria should implement structured and regular review processes for ODL course materials to ensure they remain relevant, current, and aligned with industry standards and student expectations. This process should include feedback from learners and subject matter experts to incorporate recent developments in various fields. Course content should be adaptable to cater to diverse learning needs.
2. Dual-mode universities in North-Central Nigeria should create flexible course structures, allow learners to select modules based on interests, and implement feedback mechanisms to improve engagement, satisfaction, and responsiveness to student needs.
3. Future research could focus on longitudinal studies to observe the long-term impacts of improved course content and learner satisfaction on academic performance and career outcomes. Further research can also investigate the role of instructor involvement in learner satisfaction and outcomes, focusing on how different teaching strategies affect student experience in ODL settings.

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References

- Atolagbe, A. A., Ojo, O. J., & Omosidi, A. S. (2021). Learning Resources and Efficiency of Open Distance Learning Programmes in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Distance and Online Learning*, 7(2), 37-54.
- Bubou, G., & Job, G. (2021). Benefits, Challenges and Prospects of Integrating E-Learning into Nigerian Tertiary Institutions: A Mini Review. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology*, 17(3), 6-18.
- Chen, W. S., & Yao, A. Y. T. (2016). An empirical evaluation of critical factors influencing learner satisfaction in blended learning: a pilot study. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 4(7), 1667-1671.
- Dziuban, C., Moskal, P., Thompson, J., Kramer, L., DeCantis, G., & Hermsdorfer, A. (2015). Student satisfaction with online learning: Is it a psychological contract? *Online Learning*, 19(2), 1-15, n2.
- Egielewa, P., Idogho, P. O., Iyalomhe, F. O., & Cirella, G. T. (2022). COVID-19 and digitized education: Analysis of online learning in Nigerian higher education. *E-learning and Digital Media*, 19(1), 19-35.

Comparative relationship between ...(Ilufeye, et. al.,2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15044701>

- Fägerlind, I., & Saha, L. J. (2016). Education and national development: A comparative perspective. Elsevier, Amsterdam, the Netherlands.
- Ilufeye, T. O. (2018). Lecturers' awareness, perception, and readiness towards adopting open educational resources for teaching in tertiary institutions in Niger state, Nigeria. *Master Thesis*, Federal University of Technology, Minna, Nigeria.
- Itasanmi S. A., Oni M. T., Adedire O. O. (2020). Students' assessment of open distance learning programmes and services in Nigeria: A comparative Description of three selected distance learning institutions. *IJORER: International Journal of Recent Educational Research*, 1(3), 191–208. <https://doi.org/10.46245/ijorer.v1i3.64>.
- Li, N., Marsh, V., & Rienties, B. (2016). Modelling and managing learner satisfaction: Use of learner feedback to enhance blended and online learning experience. *Decision Sciences Journal of Innovative Education.*, 14(2), 216–242.
- Mohan, R. (2023). Measurement, evaluation and assessment in education, Second Edition. PHI Learning Private Limited, Delhi, India. ISBN: 978-93-91818-88-3, 24-45.
- National Universities Commission (2021). *Guidelines for open and distance learning in Nigerian universities*. <www.nuc.edu.ng> accessed 19.03.2023
- Palmer, S. R., & Holt, D. M. (2009). Examining student satisfaction with wholly online learning. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 25(2), 101-113.
- Qayyum, A., & Zawacki-Richter, O. (2019). The state of open and distance education. *Open and distance education in Asia, Africa and the Middle East: National perspectives in a digital age*, 125-140.
- Rajabalee, Y. B., Santally, M. I. (2021). Learner satisfaction, engagement and performances in an online module: Implications for institutional e-learning policy. *Education and Information Technology*, 26, 2623–2656.
- Ronghuai, H., Spector, J. M., & Junfeng, Y. (2019). Educational Technology: A Primer for the 21st Century.
- Simonson, M., Zvacek, S. M., & Smaldino, S. (2019). Teaching and learning at a distance: Foundations of distance education 7th edition. Information Age Publishing, North Carolina, USA. ISBN: 978-1-641136-13-2.
- Siregar, Z. M. E., Syahputra, R., & Nasution, S. L. (2020). The influence of organizational justice on organizational commitment: The mediating role of job satisfaction. *Journal of Social Humanities and Education*. 4(2), 82-92. (in Indonesia)
- Yusuf, M. (2020, May 1). COVID-19 and the inevitable teaching dynamics. *Premium Times*. <www.premiumtimes.ng> accessed 21.07.2021

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Comparative Relationship between Cyber security Measures and Protection of Intellectual Property among University Staff in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Universities in Rivers State, Nigeria, have experienced cybercrime, thereby creating significant security threats to the university system. The researchers sought a comparative relationship between cybersecurity measures and protection of intellectual property among universities staff in Rivers- State using: firewall hardware, antivirus software, and physical security measures to protect intellectual properties. The correlation research design was used for this study, while the population consisted of one thousand hundred (1500) respondents comprising of industrial training (IT) staff, academic staff, and students, all in Rivers-State universities. The sample size was 100, using the stratified random sampling technique, employed to ensure a concise representation from the sub-groups. Research questions were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) method for both the research questions and hypotheses used in the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled, 'Cybersecurity Measures and Protection of Intellectual Property' (CMPIQ) while questionnaires were distributed through online platforms in Google Forms or Survey Monkey and physical forms, while the Cronbach alpha was used to determine the instrument's reliability index, which yielded 0.87. Findings of the study showed that firewall hardware, antivirus software, and physical security significantly had an effect on protecting intellectual properties. It was recommended, among others, that the government and the university system should deepen campaigns on cybercrime awareness and punish offenders under the criminal act and conviction to ensure that academic excellence is upheld.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, Protection, Intellectual Property & University

Introduction

Intellectual property in tertiary institutions has persistently witnessed a global explosion in counterfeiting, plagiarism, and piracy, creating an atmosphere of significant threats to the university system. (Evelyn, 2014). Statistics show that Nigeria loses about N127 billion annually to cybercrime, while Abayo *et al* (2021) mentioned that cybercrimes in this region are flourishing expansively in Nigeria, undetected while the university system is no exception since cybersecurity might be a possible medium to protect intellectual properties due to cyber frauds that has infiltrated into the academic system. Conspicuously, leading universities in Nigeria and Morocco have also suffered major breaches, illustrating the widespread nature of the issue across (Bukhari & Samuel, 2021). Cybersecurity, the protection of computer systems and networks from cyberattacks, serves as a central defensive system among intellectual property assets in all institutions (Vaza et al., 2024). Cybercrime hits all sectors, but the worst hit is the educational system, where potentials are robbed of their academic virtues; cybersecurity could set the pace by standing out as a defensive mechanism against intellectual properties. Cybersecurity are sets of rules and technological measures used in protecting the internet, a practice that shields computers, servers, mobile devices, electronic systems, networks, and data from malicious attacks through information technology security or electronic information security. It promotes adequate mechanisms that protect university intellectual property. (Premkumar, Yemi, & Anil, 2024). The essence is to combat threats in the universities through strict and adopted cybersecurity protocols by creating more awareness among students, staff, and faculty on security risks; consolidating technological infrastructure towards better

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openness in monitoring; and deploying security tools by protecting the domain name services that will in turn block access to malicious websites.

Chinyere (2018) mentioned that universities in Rivers State have also experienced massive cybercrimes. While Akpan (2016) reported that cybercrime has put Nigerian students in a serious quest for money other than the quest to study. Meaning that everyone is a threat to the real pact of cyber security in the Nigerian university since they have a part to play and expose the hackers themselves. These lapses have created room for patentability because of the urge to get quick money other than preserving the integrity of the universities in the nation. Intellectual properties in this region could be preserved by using firewall hardware, antivirus software, and physical security measures. Firewall hardware is an appliance that comes between the uplink and the client system that filters traffic that gets through pre-configured security policies and user profiles to protect university rules through the use of strong passwords that should not be compromised. Felicia, et al (2022). This uplink serves to allow incoming traffic from public or private networks without piracy, while the client system, a server, an employee desktop, a WFH system, and an IoT node. (Chiradeep, 2022) that protects the system. Antivirus displays devices against known threats and eliminates them from infecting one's devices instantly using reliable security software like Norton Plus or Kaspersky to shield one's personal data and protect the intellectual properties of students and staff from hackers, malware, viruses, and online threats, ensuring that adequate physical security measures are taken to destabilize cybercrimes in Rivers- State universities. (Lois, 2022).

Intellectual properties are rated as the, ' crown jewel 'for the university because they provide vehicles for the universities to project their unique norms and objectives into the international marketplace, at the same time, reap a financial benefit in which Nigeria university must uphold in preserving their intellectual property since it tends to rob academic intellectuals of their long aged suffering in the academic system, through research and development (R&D) activities that produces undiluted result among dedicated students and staff through inventions while intellectual properties such as: trademarks, journals/textbooks, projects are critically considered in industrial designs- logos, music, books, curriculum, journals, scientific drawings . These properties should not be taken for granted; rather, adequate cyber security should be mapped out to ensure that professional measures are granted to avert compromise in the university system. Felicia *et al* (2022). Rivers-state universities must adhere to adequate measures towards encryption on their system with authenticated passwords to ensure that authors and editors of books and journals in scholarly articles are preserved. In addition, students, lecturers, and library staff must be sensitized on the pact of this chronicle expedition by ensuring that they avert book piracy (consciously or unconsciously) through photocopying, scanning, and printing of copyright material, while the law must take its course in line with Section 38(3) of the Copyright Act with strict provisions that empower the copyright inspector to prosecute, conduct, or defend before court any charge, information, complaint, or order proceedings arising under the Act, while stiffer measures should be promulgated to discourage intending cybercrime activities. Signals reports growing and more sophisticated cases of cybercrimes that leverage technology experts, especially in the university system where academics is a top priority (Chiradeep, 2022).

Record of Cybercrimes in Nigerian Universities

1. The prevalence of Denial of Service (DoS) attack in which an unknown person tampered with the Network Time Protocol (NTP) server in the Federal University of Technology Akure (Mojeed, 2020).
2. Madonna University in Eastern Nigeria also reported that hackers accessed and tempered with over 25,000 data points in their database (Egbunike, 2019).
3. In 2016, 2017, and 2018, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria, disclosed incidents that potentially exposed a serious breach in the university website that resulted in a compromise of students and staff data (Bukhari, 2018).
4. In another incident, a university staffer was found compromising the admission records and printing fake admission letters for some applicants (Bukhari, 2018), were staff members of the Management Information System (MIS) Unit was apprehended for breaching the security protocols and conniving with some students of the university to illegally allocate rooms and print admission letters.

Statement of the Problem

Intellectual property in the universities have witnessed massive global manipulations in counterfeiting, plagiarism, and piracy, especially at Rivers State University. Felicia et al. (2022) espoused on the relationship between cybercrime and good governance in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, while Bukhari and Samuel (2021) tested gunned on the framework in managing cybercrime risks in Nigeria. These studies have created awareness of significant threats to the university system on

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inadequacies in data security framework, data loss management, and physical implementation but have not addressed the gap on cybercrimes being successful at encroaching and manipulating vital documents, in spite of a large chunk of money invested in the fight at national levels, even across borders. The quest on protecting Rivers State University intellectual properties has necessitated this research to strengthen the field of cybersecurity through data management and encourage the growth of institutional repositories in order to address lapses in intellectual properties. Therefore, the study explores the comparative relationship between cybersecurity measures and the protection of intellectual property among university staff in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

Specifically, the purpose of this study was to:

1. Determine the relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?
2. Determine the extent of the relationship between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?
3. Determine the extent of the relationship between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the extent of relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?
2. What is the extent of the relationship between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?
3. What is the extent of the relationship between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

H₀₂: There is no relationship between among between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

H₀₃: There is no significant the relationship physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

Methodology

The correlation research design was used for this study and the population consists of 1500 one thousand hundred respondents (IT staff, Academic staff and students) who were gotten from Rivers State University. The sample size was 100, while the stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representation from sub-groups. The instrument used for data collection was a thirty-item structured questionnaire on a 4-point Likert type developed and validated by experts in measurement and evaluation. These research questions were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) method for both the research questions and hypotheses with the use of the statistical packaged for social sciences (SPSS). The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled cyber security measures and protection of intellectual property Questionnaire CMPIPQ). The questionnaires were distributed through online platforms such as Google forms or survey monkey and physical form while the Cronbach alpha was used to determine the instrument's reliability index, which yielded 0.87.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State Universities.

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Table 1: Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient Analysis of firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University. Correlations

Correlation		Fire wall	Protection of intellectual property
Firewall	Pearson Correlation	1	.845**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Protection of intellectual property	Pearson Correlation	.845**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result shows there is a high positive correlation between firewall and protection of intellectual property ($r=-0.85$) and the relationship is significant ($p=0.00$). The result means that as scores on firewall increase, there is a corresponding increase in protection of intellectual property. Since the associated p-value was lesser than 0.05, it therefore suggests that there is a significant relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no relationship between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University. The following table answered research question 2 and analyses hypothesis 2

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient Analysis of antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

Correlation		Antivirus software	Protection of intellectual property
Antivirus software	Pearson Correlation	1	.691**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Protection of Intel lecture property	Pearson Correlation	.691**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result shows that there is a high positive correlation between Antivirus software and protection of intellectual property ($r=0.69$) and the relationship is significant ($p=0.00$). The result means that as scores on antivirus software increase, there is a corresponding increase in protection of intellectual property. Since the associated p-value was lesser than 0.05, it, therefore, suggests that there is a significant relationship between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State

Correlation		Physical security measure	Protection of intellectual property
Physical security measure	Pearson Correlation	1	.603**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Protection of Intellectual property	Pearson Correlation	.603**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

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The result shows there is a high positive correlation between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property in tertiary institutions ($r= 0.60$) and the relationship is significant ($p=0.00$). The result means that as scores on physical security increase, there is a corresponding increase protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State. Since the associated p-value was higher than 0.05, it, therefore, suggests that there is a significant relationship between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

Findings of the study revealed that staff in Rivers State University recognized firewalls as a primary defense mechanism for preventing unauthorized access to sensitive data. Firewalls serve as a critical component of cyber security infrastructure, offering protection against unauthorized access, data breaches, and other cyber threats that could compromise intellectual property (IP). This finding aligns with the work of Singh and Kaur (2023), who noted that firewalls create a virtual barrier that monitors and controls incoming and outgoing network traffic based on predetermined security rules.

Relationship between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

The findings of the study revealed significant insights into how antivirus programs contribute to safeguarding intellectual assets. The study found that most staff members at Rivers State University rely on antivirus software as a primary tool for protecting intellectual property. This finding is supported by Olayemi and Adebayo (2021) who noted that antivirus software detects and neutralizes malware that could lead to data breaches and the loss of proprietary information.

Relationship between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State

The findings of the study revealed the importance of tangible security practices in safeguarding intellectual assets. Physical security measures such as controlled access to facilities and surveillance systems, play a complementary role in protecting IP from theft, loss, or unauthorized access. Statistical analysis revealed a positive correlation between robust physical security measures and the protection of intellectual property. This corresponds with the study by Adeyemi and Chukwu (2019) which established that physical security is foundational in preventing IP theft, particularly in academic environments.

Conclusion

Rivers-State universities have consistently addressed unauthorized access to intellectual properties, but more has to be done to avert hackers from gaining access to the university system by ensuring that adequacies are employed to serve as a defensive tool in the intellectual property of the university system, especially in the use of antivirus, firewalls, and physical security. Notwithstanding, the embracement of these security measures must be harnessed to salvage consistent fraud and irregularities if adequate propensity is attached to the security of universities intellectual properties to widen productivity and secure the university system.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made, to serve as cyber security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff of Rivers State University

1. Government and the university system should deepen campaigns on cybercrime awareness on intellectual properties in order to make them understand that cyber security is the only way out while offenders are punishable under the criminal act and conviction.
2. Schools should set up a training program that can be conducted to improve staff understanding of firewalls and their role in IP protection
3. Undergraduates could be caught young through sensitization programs and afterwards given functional education that should be in line with vocational skills.
4. Implementation is key to national productivity, as such, government should deploy measures to ensure that intellectual properties are given ultimate concern, while sensitive information should be kept secret and always updated from the university website.

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Comparative Relationship Between Entry Qualification and Academic Performance among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the Comparative Relationship between Entry Qualification and Academic Performance among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria. ie the population of the study consists of all colleges of education final year Mathematics/Sciences and Technical education students in Northwest Nigeria. A sample of 138 students were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. Ex-post factor design was adopted and the data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation). Pearson product moment correlation coefficient, multiple regressions and analysis of variance. The finding revealed that the two entry modes (UTME and DE) have linear positive relationship with the final CGPA, the Direct Entry (DE) mode of admission is the best predictor and contributor to the student's academic performance. Thus, the best performance in the final CGPA in Mathematics and Sciences. Based on the findings, it was recommended that more emphasis should be given to the DE entry mode in admitting candidates into Mathematics and Science Education programme in the Colleges in a bid to raise the standard of Mathematics and Science Performance,

Keyword: Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination, DE- Direct Entry, National Certificate in Education. And Cumulative Grade Points Average

Introduction

Science and Mathematics Education occupies a key position in the Nigerian educational system, reflecting the significant roles of mathematics in the contemporary society, a 'credit' (c) pass at 0/level examination is a pre-requisite for admission into science and technology-based courses in every institution of higher learning. But students' performance in mathematics at various stages of the educational system is very disappointing. Academic performance has been described as the scholastic Standing of a student at given moment. This scholastic Standing could be explained in terms of the grades obtained in a course or groups of Courses. Mallory, 2004, argued that Performance is a measure of output and that the main output in education are expressed, in terms of skills, attitude of individual as a result of their experience within the school settings. Academic performances is regarded as Student's performance in an examination as being depended on his cumulative grades point average (Jansen 2004) detained academic performance. As the process of developing the capabilities and potentials of individual student so as to prepare that individual to be successful in a specific society or Culture, Candidates' admission or placement into Nigerian institutions of higher learning irrespective of whether the institution is federal, state or private owned in contingent on meeting a prescribed cut off marks.

In the 1960s very few Candidates were seeking for admission into higher institutions and those who were admitted got it through hard work. Any Candidate/student who found himself/herself those admitted was therefore considered. Intelligent and academically superior to his/her peers (Erigha, 2001). Over the years, the number of Students applying to enter higher institutions in Nigeria has been on the increase. However, just a fraction of these applicants are admitted each year. Admission into higher institutions in Nigeria is very Competitive due to high number of Students vying for the limited slots available. It is thus expected that only the best will be admitted since academic merit is the major criterial used for admission. Initially, each institution handled its admission process autonomously. As such there was variance in the Criteria used since each institution adopted what it considered most appropriate for it. However, over time, the need to harmonize admission processes across the country was realized. As a result of that the Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) was established to coordinate and standardize tertiary institutions processes in the County. Each Course and or institution was given a Cut-off mark which varied from one institution to another. Meeting the prescribed cut-off mark for a course in a particular institution thus qualified a candidate to be provisionally admitted. However, admissions were confirmed on the Candidate obtaining good grades in his/her O/level Subjects at the end of their Secondary School education. The cut-off mark/points for any mode or criteria of admission, the candidates are required to undergo screening examination as a condition for admission into the required programmed. This is because of the following reasons:

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These institutions do not have confidence in the various certificates and entry points Possessed by the candidates. Selection for admission is highly competitive because of the large number of candidates seeking for admission. Institutions are looking for an objective means of screening Candidates that those admitted are on the assumption that they have very high chance of Success at the end of their studies (Asaolu, 2003). Hence, the eventual graduates would be qualitative, self-reliant, functional and skillful mathematics and science educators that would transform mathematics teaching and learning in schools for better output. The focus of this research study is on the Predictive validity of different entry mode in the performance of NCE Students in Mathematics, Science and Technical Education.

Statement of the Research Problem

Academic success is no doubt the main focus of all educational activities. The ultimate goal of every tertiary institution is quality product of competent graduate who would function effectively in the larger society. But the decay in the Nigeria educational system calls for attention. The research for the most desirable and most acceptable model of selecting candidate for admission into Nigeria tertiary institution continues (Asaolu, 2003). This is evidenced by public opinion about the standard of students graduating from Nigeria college of Education with NCE certificates. The problem of this research, therefore, is to determine how significantly Students entry qualification into National Certificate in Education (NCE) in mathematics, technical and science education could predict their final performance at these three colleges of education: Kaduna State college of education, gidan-waya: federal college of education (technical) Gusau, Zamfara state and Federal College of Education, Zaria. There are minimum entry requirements that Candidates must possess before they can be admitted into NCE Programmed in the colleges of education. The requirement must be met for both UTME and Direct entry Candidates. Candidate are expected to possess NECO/WAEC, SSCE, and NAPTECH or its equivalents with credits in five (5) Subjects (including Mathematics and English) relevant to their course (s) at not more than two (2) sittings. It is hope and assumed that all those admitted will be able to cope with the academic rigouts but contrary to this expectation, some drop out on the way without graduating, some change their courses and others spend extra year (s) before graduating while some graduate with a low grade, just Pass. This Scenario Show's that performance may be a function of the mode of entry qualification.

Objectives of the Study

Specifically, this research seeks to;

7. Examine the mean academic performance of graduating mathematics students who are admitted into higher institutions through the two (2) modes of admission criteria.
8. Find out the difference between mode of entry and academic achievement of NCE students.
9. Compare the academic performance of students admitted through direct entry and UTME.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were generated and tested at 0.05 level of significance in this study.

1. H_{01} There is no significant relationship between UTME scores and final academic performance of student in NCE of Science and Mathematics Education of Colleges of Education in the Northwest Zone.
2. H_{02} There is no significant relationship between Direct Entry (DE) points and final academic performance in NCE Science and Mathematics Education of Colleges of Education in the Northwest Zone.
3. H_{03} There is no significant relationship between the mean scores of the final academic performance of graduate in NCE Science and Mathematics Education of Colleges of Education in the Northwest Zone.
4. None of the entry mode of UTME and DE entry points will best predict student' final performance in NCE Science and Mathematics Education of Colleges of Education in the Northwest Zone

Methodology

An ex-post factor design was adopted in this research. The population of the study consists of all colleges of education final year Mathematics/Sciences and Technical education students in Northwest Nigeria. A sample of 138 students were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique In carrying out this research, two instruments were employed; namely: Inventory and students academic results from the schools. The inventory is to take care of the list of students in the intact class/level to be used as sample, while the results revealed

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academic achievement. The research instrument was divided into two major sections: Section A contained items that sought information on the inventory (that is, gender, mode of entry and students level). Section B of the instrument contained the result of the students. The method of data collection adopted in this study involved the gathering of information and data through both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was gathered from the inventory / intact class, and the secondary data was derived from Students Result. Data obtained was analyzed using descriptive statistics for the participants' bio-data and various analysis tools like (t-test, Chi-square, and Anova) were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significance relationship between students' UTME scores and their final academic performance in Mathematics and science education.

In testing this hypothesis, data on 137 selected UTME candidates was collected and analyzed. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was calculated using SPSS 17.0 version for Windows Computer Software. The Pearson product moment correlation coefficient index was presented in the Table 1.

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient for Students' UTME Scores and their Final Academic performance (CGPA).

		UTME Score	CGPA
UTME Scores	Person correlation		0.239
	Sig. (2-tailed)	1	0.005
	N	138	138
CGPA	Pearson correlation	0.239	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.005	
		138	138

Source: data from the three colleges

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 1. is the summary of the degree of relationship between UTME scores and final academic performance (CGPA), the table showed a correlation coefficient of 0.239 between students' UTME scores and academic performance (i.e CGPA) which was significantly higher than critical table value of 0.178 at 0.05level of significant and 137 degrees of freedom. Therefore the correlation coefficient was significant at 0.01level of significance. Therefore, since p-value was less than level of significant (i.e. $p < 0.01$), the hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was statistically significant relationship between students' UTME scores and final academic performance in in Mathematics and science education of colleges of Education and the North West.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between students' Direct Entry points and their final academic performance in NCE Science Education and Mathematics.

In testing this hypothesis, data on 61 selected DE candidates was collected and analyzed. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was computed using SPSS 17.0 version for Windows Computer Software and the results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient for Students 'DE Points and their Final Academic Performance'(CGPA)

		DE points	CGPA
DE Point	Pearson correlation	1	0.551
	Sig (2 tailed)	61	61
CGPA	Pearson correlation	0.551	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	61
	N	61	

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Source: data from the three colleges

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 2. is the summary of the degree of relationship between the variables (students' DE points and their final academic performance) in NCE of Science Education and Mathematics at College of Education and Northwest. The table showed a correlation index of 0.551 which is considerably higher than the critical table value of 0.250 at 0.05 level of significance and 60 degrees of freedom, thus the correlation is statistically significant at 0.000 levels. Therefore, the null hypothesis 2 was also rejected.

Hypothesis: 3 there is no significant difference in the means scores of the final academic performance of graduates of NCE in Mathematics and science admitted through UTME and DE entry modes.

In testing this hypothesis, the final academic performance i.e CGPA of the sampled subjects was collected and used. Although the UTME and DE and were measured by different scales, the researcher converted each of the two variables into an interval scale. Descriptive statistics, Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Post Hoc test (scheffe's test) were computed electronically using SPSS version 17.0 for windows computer software to find out whether there is a significant difference in the final academic performance of students admitted through UTME and DE and where the difference exist. The results are shown below in the tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 3: Mean Scores and Standard Deviations for Students' Final Academic Performance (CGPA)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
UTME	138	1.9950	0.63814	0.05413
DI:	61	3.1713	0.49674	0.07596
Total	199	2.2920	0.71529	0.04267

Source: data from the three colleges

Table 3. Is a summary of the mean scores and standard deviations of students' final academic performance in the NCE of Science Education and Mathematics. The result indicated that the Direct Entry mode had the highest mean of 3.1713. While the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) has a mean of 1.9950. On the other hand the UTME mode has the highest standard deviation of 0.63814 followed by the Direct Entry with 0.49674 modes. This is an indication that the least performance was from UTME candidates

Table 4: Analysis of Variance for Significant Difference in the Mean Scores of Final Academic Performance of Students Admitted Through UTME and DE.

Variance	SS	Df	MS	F-Cal	F-Crit	Sig
Between Groups	29.673	2	14.836	36.312	3.04	0.000
Within Groups	113.585	278	0.4090			

Source: data from the three colleges

Table 4. is a summary of analysis of variance for significant difference in the final academic performance in terms of CGPA of graduates of Mathematics and Science Education admitted through the two modes and (UTME). The result indicated that the calculated value of F is 36.312 (i.e. $F_{cal}=36.312$) which is significantly greater than the critical table value of F which is 3.04 (i.e $F_{crit}=3.04$) at 2 and 0.05 level of significance and at a p-value of 0.000. Since calculated value of F is greater than the critical table value of F (i.e $F_{cal}>F_{cri}$) and $p<0.05$ the null hypothesis 4 which states that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of the final academic performance of students admitted through the two mode was rejected. This implies that, there was significant difference in the final academic performance of students admitted into NCE in Mathematics and Science at the said Colleges of Education. Since the result of table 3 showed that the null hypothesis was rejected, it means that at least one of the means isn't the same as the other means.

The result was further subjected to a Scheffe' test to figure out where the differences lie and the result of the test is shown in Table 5 below:

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Table 5: Scheffe's test for Significant Difference in the Mean Scores of Final Academic Performance of Students Admitted through UTME and DE.

Level	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05 (i.e a = 0.05)		
		1	2	3
UTME	138	1.9950		
DE	61		2.8014	
Sig	1.000	1.000	1.000	

Source: data from the three colleges

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size=83.974.

b. The group sizes are unequal

Table 5. is a summary of Scheffe's Post Hoc test for significant difference in the means of students' final academic performance in NCE of Science Education and Mathematics. The result revealed that UTME had 1.9950, and Direct Entry had 2.8014 which indicated that there was statistically significant difference in the final academic performance of student in favor of the Direct Entry.

Discussion of Findings

The aim of this research work was to determine the predictive validity of entry qualifications on final academic performance of NCE Science Education and Mathematics at the colleges of Education. The study correlated students' entry points and their corresponding final academic performance in Mathematics and Science Education programme on one hand and on the other hand determined the predictive validity of the entry qualifications and significant difference in the mean scores of final academic performances of students admitted through the two modes.

The results of the findings indicated that there was positive and linear correlation between each entry points and their final academic performance in Mathematics and Science Education in the colleges of education although with different degree of strength. This is in line with the previous similar studies by Durotoluwa (2000) who found a positive correlation between entry grades at JSS and academic performance at high level (SSS) of educational pursuit. It is also in line with the findings of Awaisu (2002) who found that there was high positive relationship between entry qualification and academic performance of students in Biology at Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel. It is also in line with the findings of Kolawale and Ilugbosi (2007) in Ekiti who found that there was a significant positive and linear relationship between basic cognitive entry grades and final cumulative grade point average of students in Mathematics. Thus, cognitive grades contributed significantly to the overall CGPA of the selected students in mathematics and Science in NCE.

The result is also in line with the findings of Ali (2008) in Pakistan who found that there is strong positive relationship between admission criteria (entry scores) and subsequent academic performance of students in Diploma in General Nursing at Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan. Similarly, the result also coincidences with the findings of Adeyemi (2010) found that there was positive correlation between entry grade point of credit in Mathematics and academic performance of Educational Management students in the universities in Ondo and Ekiti states.

The result also shows that the Direct Entry mode was the best predictor of academic performance in NCE in Mathematics and Science Education. This coincides with the findings of Njoku (2002) who found that the DE entry points slightly predicted academic performance only in the faculty of education and extension services in UDUS. This perhaps could be due to their previous A-level training in Colleges of Education and Polytechnics, accumulated experience and the result also shows that the Direct Entry mode was the best predictor of academic performance in NCE in Mathematics and Science Education.

On the other hand, this finding contradicts the findings of Adeyemi (2009) who found that the Direct Entry mode was the worst predictor of success in the university degree at Ondo and Ekiti states. The results also indicated that the UTME entry mode was the least predictor of academic performance and do not relate well with academic performance. This finding agrees with the findings of Oyebola (2004) who found that the UTME scores do not relate well with academic performance of students in Medical School.

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Similarly, Obioma and Salau (2007) who found that the UTME scores alone was the least predictor variable of student's final year CGPA in Nigerian universities. It is also consistent with the findings of Ojirinde and Kolo (2009) who found that some relationships exist between scores in Universities Matriculation Examination (UTME) and corresponding academic performance in terms of final cumulative grade points average (CGPA) especially when it is with SSCE result. On the other hand, the result contradicted the findings of Njoku (2002) who found a negative correlation between UTME scores and final university result at Usman Danfodio University, Sokoto.

The results also revealed that there was significant difference in the final academic performance of students admitted through the two modes in favor of the Direct Entry. This contradicts the findings of Dahiru (2010) who found that there was no significant difference in the academic achievement of Direct Entry and Non-Direct Entry students in FCE Katsina. The results also disagree with the findings of Moses & Solomon (2002) who found that there was no significant difference in the final academic performance of Pre-NCE and JAMB students in FCE Pankshin.

The value of the multiple regression $R = 0.614, 0.653$ and 0.851 in table 4 showed that there was a significant linear and positive relationship between students' entry qualification and final cumulative grade point average (CGPA) of 2.50 and above (Merit and above) in NCE of Science Education and Mathematics. These findings corroborated previous and similar researches by Adegboye (1997), Adeyemi (2009), and Kolawole and Illugbusi (2007) who found in their studies that there was a significant positive and linear relationship between students' entry qualifications and their final academic performance in the Universities. On the other hand, this finding is inconsistent with the findings of Momoh-Olle (1998) and Kolawole, Oginni & Fayomi (2011) who found no significant relationship between entry grades and academic performance in the university.

This showed that the entry points have significant contribution to the final cumulative grade point average of the selected candidates in NCE Science Education and Mathematics in these colleges of Education. These finding is consistent with the findings of Alias and Ahmad (2006), Ajuonuma and Mkpa (2009), Adeyemi (2010) and Ajayi, Lawani Muraina (2011) respectively who found in their studies that entry grades/points contributed significantly to the final year academic performance in terms CGPA of students in tertiary institutions.

Conclusion

The DE candidates performed significantly better than UTME. The UTME scores are the worse predictor of final academic performance in NCE of Science Education and Mathematics. There were few Direct Entry applicants in general as such only very few were admitted into Mathematics and Science Education, hence there were few numbers of admitted Direct Entry candidates. There was statistically significant difference in the final academic performance of UTME and DE and candidates in NCE Science Education and Mathematics in favor of DE candidates.

Recommendations

1. Based on the findings of this research study the following recommendations were made: The examination bodies such JAMB, WAEC, NECO, NABTEB etc, should continue to improve the quality of the development and administration of their examinations.
2. Government should endeavor to recruit more specialist teachers in mathematics so that more emphasis could be given to the teaching of Mathematics in secondary schools.
3. Since the UTME was designed as a screening examination, the items on it should include both achievement and aptitude testing items. Thus, in designing the aptitude test, Mathematics Educators involved should consult and involve expert in test, Measurement and evaluation, so that the psychometric properties of the aptitude test can be ascertained and ensured to avoid capricious item selected.
4. There is also the need for a national policy document to strengthen the post-UTME screening examination by using uniform guidelines as well as valid and reliable instruments and mandatory inclusion of experts in Test, Measurement and Evaluation in the Post-UTME Screening Committee.

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References

- Ali (2012) Predictive validity of a uniform Entrance Test for the health professional,
- Adeyemi, T.O (2009). Mode Od Study as A Predictor Of Success In Final Year Bacherlor Of Education Degree Examination In The University In Ekiti And Ondo State, Nigeria. Middle – East Journal Of Scientific Research, 4(1), 10-19.
- Adeyemi, T.o (2010). Credit in mathematics in senior secondary certificate examination as a predictor of success in educational management in universities in ekiti and ondo state. Research journal of mathematics and statistics, 2(1), 14-22.
- Asalu, A.G. (2003). Predictive Validity of JSC Mathematics Examination on the Performance of Students in Science subjects in Ekiti State Secondary Schools. An unpublished M.Ed. thesis, Faculty of Education, University of Ado-Ekiti.
- Awaisu, N.S. (2002), Entry Qualifications as Predictors of Students' Academic Performance in Biology. A case study of Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel. An unpublished M.Ed dessertation, Faculty of Education and Extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.
- .Dahiru SY. (2010). Comparative Study on Academic Performance of Direct Entry and Non-Direct Entry Nigeria Certificate in Education students. Journal of Escational Research and Development. 51(1). 89-94.
- Durotoluwa, J.O. (2000). Predictive Validity of JSS Certificate in Mathematics: A case study of Owo Local Government Area, Educational Thought, Journal of Faculty of Education. Ondo State University, Akugba-Akoko, 1(1), 30-34.
- Erigha A (2001). Educated prostitutes. Sunday Tribune of 21 January
- Kolawale, E.B. & Ilugbusi, A.A. (2007), Cognitive Entry Grade as Predictors of Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics in Nigerian Universities Medwell Journal, 2(3), 322-326.
- Kolawole. E.B., Oginni, LO. & Fayomi, O.E. (2011). Ordinary Level Results as Predictors of Students' Academic Performance in Chemistry in Nigerian Universities. Journal of Educational Research and reviews, 6(16), 889-892.
- Momoh Olle, (1998). The Relationship Between Student's Entry Grades and Academic Achievement at Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin Gusau Journal of Education, 2(1), 169-179
- Njoku, J.N (2002). Student Scores in UTME As Predictors of Academic Performance Of Student Of Usman Danfodio University. An Unpublished M. Ed Dissertation, Faculty of Education and Extension Services, Usman Danfodio University, Sokoto.
- Ojerinde. D. and Kolo, T.N. (2009). Prediction of First Year University Education Performance form entry Academic Performances: Presented at the 27th Annual.
- Obioma, G. & Salau, M. (2007). Predictive Validity of Public Examinations. A Case Study of Nigeria. Paper Presented at the 33rd Annual Conference of International Association for Educational Assessment (IAEA) held in Bäku, Azerbaijan, 16-21 September, 2007.
- Moses, O.A. & Solomon, E.M. (2002). Entry Qualifications as Determinants of Final Performance. Gusau journal of Education, 6(1), 59-64
- Oyebola. D. D. O. (2004). The importance of O-level Grades in Medical School Proceedings of the Physiological September 16-17 at Abraka, Nigeria, Pp: 13 Plat Turocy and McGlumphy (2001). The Predictive Validity of Preadmission. Criteria, Scholastic Aptitude Test Scores and High School Grade Point Average on College Grade Point Average of Graduates of Atheletic Training lines at Rangos school of Programme and five other Allied Health Disciplines health sciences, Duquesne University Pittsburgh, USA. Journal of Medical Sciences, 8(1), 102-108.

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Relationships Between Professional Qualities of Teachers and Academic Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Taraba State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explored the Comparative relationships between Professional qualities of teachers and academic achievement in Physics among secondary school students in Taraba State, Nigeria. Two research questions were raised and two corresponding hypotheses formulated to guided the study. The study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study was 17,520 respondents, comprised of 394 principals/vice principals and 17,126 SSIII physics students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Taraba state. A sample size of 460 respondents, made up of 69 Principals/vice-principals and 391 SSIII physics students of private and public senior secondary schools in Taraba state was were selected from the target population using stratified random sampling and purposive sampling techniques, respectively. The instruments used for data collection were Questionnaire with reliability coefficients 0.87 computed using Cronbach alpha and Physics Achievement Proforma (PAP) with reliability coefficient of 0.79 computed using the Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-R₂₀). Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using regression analysis at 0.05 significance level. The study's finding among others reveals that there is significant relationship between Teachers Mastery of students learning and achievement in Physics among secondary schools in Taraba State ($F(1,390) = 151.511, P < 0.05$). The study concludes that Physics teachers' mastery of students' learning and curriculum significantly influences senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Taraba state. The researcher recommended among others that the Taraba state Ministry of Education should organize training workshops and conferences that are aimed at improving Physics teachers' knowledge of students' understanding of physics taught and knowledge of curriculum.

Keywords: Students' understanding, curriculum, achievement.

Introduction

Physics, as a fundamental branch of science, has been crucial for the world's economic development. Yusuf, Omosewo, Akanbi, Mohammed, Badmus, and Usman (2021) affirmed that physics is the basis for most modern technology, tools and instruments used in scientific research development. It equips individuals with the quantitative and qualitative skills necessary for data analysis and problem solving across various fields, including sciences, engineering, medicine, economics, finance, management, law, and public policy. One of the most compelling advantages of studying physics is the acquisition of essential skills such as problem-solving, analytical thinking, and quantitative reasoning, along with the capability to grasp and apply complex concepts (Omirin, 2015). Thus, ensuring that students achieve high academic performance in physics is vital. Academic achievement is defined as the success and performance of individuals in their educational pursuits and serves as an essential measure of students' understanding and proficiency in a subject. In physics, this achievement reflects students' success in grasping and applying its principles, theories, and applications. According to Filgona, Sakiyo, and Gwany (2020), academic achievement is often assessed through students' test scores, which indicate their educational outcomes in a particular subject. However, various factors influence the attainment of high academic achievement, including not just the students' own efforts

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and abilities but also the impact of teachers, parents, and educational policies. Odumosu, Olisama, and Fasayo (2018) noted that multiple stakeholders, such as teachers, students, parents, and the Ministry of Education, have contributed to the noticeable decline in physics students' academic achievement in secondary schools.

Moreover, Kimani, Kara, and Njagi (2014) identified several teacher-related factors that lead to poor academic achievement, including negative attitudes toward their work, ineffective teaching methods, inadequate pedagogical knowledge, insufficient evaluations, lack of qualifications, and poor relationships with students. Similarly, Tsholofelo and Maree (2021) pointed out student-related factors contributing to poor academic performance, such as negative attitudes toward learning, socioeconomic challenges, misunderstanding of the material, ineffective study habits, and poor physical health. These interconnected issues present significant barriers to academic success in subjects like physics. Despite the importance of physics and its acknowledged place in science education, senior secondary school students in Nigeria continue to struggle, performing below established benchmarks. This situation has raised serious concerns among education stakeholders, particularly within the science community (Shamim, Tabasum, & Rashid, 2013). Furthermore, Mukama (2019) reported a decline in both enrollment in physics courses and academic achievement over the years. This troubling trend is evident in external examinations such as the West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO).

The West African Examination Council (WAEC) conducted a seven-year analysis of physics students' results from 2016 to 2022 in Taraba State, Nigeria as presented in Table 1. The failure rates were as follows: 55.49% in 2016, 57.19% in 2017, 45.75% in 2018, 50.19% in 2019, 55.35% in 2020, 49.22% in 2021, and 49.83% in 2022 (Taraba State Ministry of Education, Research and Statistics Department, 2023). Despite some variations, all the failure rates remain alarmingly high, with none falling below 45%. This indicates a persistent issue with academic achievement in physics among students in Taraba State. The ongoing poor performance of physics students in the region may be linked to the physics teachers' understanding of students' grasp of physics concepts and the curriculum.

Table 1: WAEC Results In Physics In Taraba State From 2016 To 2022

Year	Pass Rate (%) at A1 - C6	Failure Rate (%)
2016	44.51%	55.49%
2017	42.81%	57.19%
2018	54.25%	45.75%
2019	49.81%	50.19%
2020	44.65%	55.35%
2021	50.78%	49.22%
2022	50.17%	49.83%

Knowledge of students' understanding of physics refers to a physics teachers' in-depth awareness regarding how their students perceive, interpret and comprehend the physics concepts taught in class (Etkina, Gregorcic, & Vokos, 2017). This includes recognizing students' diverse learning styles, common misconceptions, assessing students' prior knowledge in physics, identifying individual needs and preferences, strength and challenges (Sadler, Sonnert, Coyle, Cook & Miller, 2013). In the study conducted by Hill and Chin (2018) established that Knowledge of students proved more difficult to measure, yet still predicted student academic achievement. Furthermore, Ketut, Ardia, Masil, and Parnata (2022) reported that there is a significant difference in academic achievement in difference level of students' knowledge of understanding. In contrast, Cowan, Goldhaber and Theobald (2019) found that there is no significant direct relationship between teachers' knowledge of students' understanding and student academic outcomes. Since the existing literature on this sub-variable is not uniform, it is imperative to delve deeper into it for a better understanding.

Knowledge of curriculum refers to a teacher's deep understanding of the content, scope, and sequence of what needs to be taught in a specific subject or educational programme (De Jong & Van Driel, 2015). It involves knowing the learning objectives, standard, and the overall content that students are expected to learn. For an effective teaching and learning, teachers need to possess this essential curriculum knowledge as it acts as a guiding compass for structuring meaningful learning experiences. This sub variable plays a pivotal role in shaping students' academic achievement. According to Miko and Tirri, (2019), when teachers have a deep understanding of the curriculum, they can create purposeful instructional plans, differentiate instruction to meet diverse student needs, align assessments with the learning objectives, and adapt their teaching to cater to the unique requirements of their students. Annan, Fordjour, Koomson, Agyemang, Addae, and Anim (2021) revealed that there is a positive relationship between the curriculum knowledge of science teachers and students' academic achievement in

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Kwaebibirem District, Ghana. These contradictions on the existing literature on this sub variable, makes it important in this study.

Statement of the Research Problem

In an ideal scenario, senior secondary school students in Taraba State would consistently achieve academic success in physics, earning at least a credit pass. As a foundational subject, physics serves as a gateway to various opportunities for admission into universities and other tertiary institutions for courses such as medicine, pharmacy, and engineering. When teachers possess a deep understanding of both their students' grasp of physics concepts and the curriculum, they can effectively convey the material, fostering enthusiasm and a strong comprehension of the subject. This, in turn, would lead to students meeting the standard benchmarks in internal and external examinations like those conducted by WAEC or NECO. However, the current situation is quite different. Despite ongoing efforts by educators and scholars, poor academic achievement in physics continues to challenge senior secondary students in Taraba State, with an average failure rate of 51.86% recorded from 2016 to 2022. Students often perform below expected standards, indicating significant gaps in their understanding of physics concepts. This issue may be linked to two critical factors: physics teachers' knowledge of students' understanding of physics and their knowledge of the curriculum. Insufficient awareness of how students grasp physics concepts can lead to ineffective teaching strategies, while a lack of familiarity with the curriculum may hinder teachers' ability to deliver the content effectively. To address the persistent problem of poor academic achievement in physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba State, this study investigates the influence of physics teachers' knowledge of students' understanding of physics and their knowledge of the curriculum on students' academic achievement.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between Professional qualities of teachers and academic achievement in physics among secondary schools in Taraba State. The specific objectives of the study are were to determine the:

1. Relationship between teachers' mastery of students' learning and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba, state.
2. Relationship between teachers' mastery of curriculum and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba state.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions.

1. What is the level of relationship between teachers' mastery of students' learning and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba, state?
2. What is the level of relationship between teachers' mastery of curriculum and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' mastery of students' learning and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba, state.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' mastery of curriculum and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba state

Methodology

The study employs correlational survey research design. The study area is Taraba state . The population of the study consists of 17,520 principals/vice principals and students. This includes 394 principals/vice principals, 17,126 SSIII physics students 2023/2024 academic section from public science secondary schools in Taraba state. The sample size for the study comprised 460. This includes 69 Principals/vice-principals and 391 SSIII physics students of public senior secondary schools in Taraba state. Stratified random sampling and purposive sampling techniques were used to draw the sample size for the study. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select sample size for physics students in each education zone, while Principals/Vice principals were sampled, through purposive sampling technique, since it is difficult to have more than one physics teacher in a particular school, in Taraba state. The study also employed purposive sampling technique to select schools from the 10 education zones based on the availability of physics teachers. Two instruments were used for data collection. The instruments are Physics Questionnaire and Physics Achievement Proforma (PAP). Three experts participated in construct

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validation of Physics Teachers' Knowledge Questionnaire (PTKQ), involving two experts with diverse expertise. One expert hailed from the Department of Environmental and life science, Moddibo Adama University, Yola, another from Department of Physical Sciences Education in the same university. Physics Teacher's Knowledge Questionnaire, the reliability analysis utilized Cronbach alpha coefficient, yielding a commendable score of 0.85. This coefficient signifies a high level of internal consistency among the items in the questionnaire, indicating the reliability of the instrument in assessing the pedagogical knowledge of physics teachers. The reliability of the Physics Teacher's Knowledge of Subject Matter Test was assessed using the Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-R₂₀) coefficient, resulting in a reliability coefficient of 0.79. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation to answer research question 1 to 2. Linear regression was used to test hypotheses 1 to 2, If the P-Value is less than 0.05 the null hypotheses was rejected, otherwise do not reject the hypotheses. The decision for answering of the research questions was based on the real limit of numbers.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: What is the level of relationship between teachers' mastery of students' learning and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba, state?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of Relationship between teachers' mastery of students' learning and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba, state

S/N	Item (n = 391)	Mean	S. D	Remark
1	Physics teacher in my school used to know when students are confuse during lessons	3.43	1.42	ML
2	Physics teacher's ability of noticing when students lose focus during class.	3.71	1.40	HL
3	My physics teacher always check our notebooks to know if we are doing the right thing	3.47	2.08	ML
4	The physics teacher always go round to supervise our practical during experiment to know if we are following	3.26	1.43	ML
5	Physics teacher used to ask us questions on what he taught in class to know if we understand	3.17	1.48	ML
6	Physics teacher's ability of providing feedback on students' performance in class.	2.14	1.50	LL
7	The teacher used to help students who find physics difficult to understand by explaining more to them.	3.64	1.53	HL
Grand Mean		3.26	1.55	ML

Key: n= Number of participants, HL=High Level, ML =Moderate Level, LL= Low Level, S.D = Standard deviation
 The result of the analysis presented in Table 1 indicates that the grand mean for the level of Physics teachers' knowledge of the students' understanding of physics taught in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is 3.26, with a standard deviation of 1.55. The grand mean falls within the real limit of 2.50-3.49 (Moderate Level), implying that the level of Physics teachers' knowledge of the students' understanding of physics taught in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is moderate.

Research Question Two

What is the level of relationship between teachers' mastery of curriculum and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba state?

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Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of Relationship teachers' mastery of curriculum and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba state

S/N	Item (n = 69)	Mean	S. D	Remark
1	Teacher's familiarity with the specific learning objectives outlined in the curriculum	3.72	1.17	HL
2	The Teacher's Alignment of lesson plans effectively with curriculum objectives	3.74	1.21	HL
3	The teacher's Awareness of recommended sequence of curriculum topics in physics	3.46	1.18	ML
4	Ability to keep up-to-date with the latest developments in the physics curriculum	3.64	1.44	HL
5	Use of assessment practices that align with the physics curriculum	3.54	1.24	HL
6	Demonstration of deep understanding of physics curriculum	3.46	1.56	ML
	Grand Mean	3.59	1.30	HL

Key: n= Number of participants, HL=High Level, ML =Moderate Level, S.D = Standard deviation.

Table 2 presents the result of the analysis, revealing that the grand mean for the level of Physics teachers' knowledge of the curriculum in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is 3.59, with a standard deviation of 1.30. The mean is situated in the real limit of 3.50–4.49 (High Level), suggesting that the level of Physics teachers' knowledge of the curriculum in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is high.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' mastery of students' learning and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba, state.

Table 3: Summary of ANOVA results of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers' Knowledge of the Students' Understanding of Physics Taught and Students' Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23377.501	1	23377.501	151.511	.000 ^b
	Residual	60021.023	389	154.296		
	Total	83398.523	390			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers' knowledge of students' understanding of physics taught

The result of linear regression in Table 3 shows that $F(1, 389) = 151.511, p < 0.05$. Since the computed p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, concluded that, there is significant relationship between teachers' mastery of students' learning and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba, state.

Table 4: Model Summary of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers' Knowledge of the Students' Understanding of Physics Taught and Students' Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.529 ^a	.280	.278	12.42158

a. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers' knowledge of students' understanding of physics taught.

The model summary in Table 4 indicates that there exists a positively high relationship between teachers' mastery of students' learning and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary schools in Taraba state. As shown by R=0.529 and the adjusted R-square value (.278) indicates that, 27.8% of the students' academic achievement in this study is explained by Physics teachers' knowledge of the students' understanding of physics taught.

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Table 5: Beta Coefficient of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers' Knowledge of the Students' Understanding of Physics Taught and Students' Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	19.578	1.961		9.984	.000
	teachers' mastery of students' learning	6.958	.565	.529	12.309	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

The result in Table 5 indicates the Beta coefficient of the regression analysis of Physics teachers' knowledge of students' understanding of physics taught and students' academic achievement. The result shows a beta coefficient of 0.529, $p < .05$. This implies that teachers' mastery of students' learning is a significant predictor of academic achievement in Physics.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' mastery of curriculum and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba state.

Table 6: Summary of ANOVA results of Linear Regression of Relationship between Physics Teachers' Knowledge of the Curriculum and Students' Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	713.322	1	713.322	91.839	.000 ^b
	Residual	520.397	68	7.767		
	Total	1233.719	69			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers' mastery of curriculum

The results of linear regression in Table 6 indicate that $F(1, 68) = 91.839$, $p < 0.05$. Since the computed p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected, implying that there is indeed a significant relationship between teachers' mastery of curriculum and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary schools students in Taraba state.

Table 7: Model Summary of Linear Regression for Relationship between teachers' mastery of curriculum and academic achievement in Physics among Senior Secondary Schools Students in Taraba State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.760 ^a	.578	.572	2.78696

a. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers' knowledge of curriculum

Table 7 shows that there exists a significant positive high relationship between teachers' mastery of curriculum and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary schools students in Taraba state as shown by $R=0.760$ and the adjusted R-square value (.572) indicates that, 57.2% of academic achievement in this study explained by Physics teachers' knowledge of curriculum.

Table 8: Beta Coefficient of Linear Regression for relationship between teachers' mastery of curriculum and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba state

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11.355	1.234		9.201	.000
	Teachers' knowledge of curriculum	3.167	.330	.760	9.583	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

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The outcome displayed in Table 8 presents the Beta coefficient from the regression analysis examining the relationship between Physics teachers' curriculum knowledge and students' academic achievement. The analysis reveals a Beta coefficient of 0.760, with $p < 0.05$, indicating a significant positive relationship between teachers' mastery of curriculum and students' academic achievement in Physics.

Discussion of Results

The study found that the level of teachers' mastery of students' learning is moderate, and it significantly relates to senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Physics in Taraba State. This finding aligns with the results of Sadler, Coyle, Sonnert, and Friedman (2013), Gess-Newsome, Taylor, Carlson, Gardner, Wilson, and Stuhlsatz (2019), and Nadir (2014), who found a positive relationship between teacher knowledge of students and students' achievement. The results signified that when Physics teachers have a better understanding of their students' grasp of physics concepts, it correlates positively with higher academic achievement among senior secondary school students. Conversely, the finding contradicts the findings of Cowan, Goldhaber, and Theobald (2019), who reported that there is no significant direct relationship between teachers' awareness of students' understanding and students' academic outcomes. From the finding of this study, it can be inferred that a teacher's knowledge of students' learning processes is crucial to enhancing students' achievement. This emphasizes the need for teachers to develop a deep understanding of how students comprehend and engage with the subject matter. Additionally, it highlights the importance of targeted professional development programmes that equip teachers with the skills to assess and respond to students' learning needs effectively.

The study also found that the level of teachers' mastery of the curriculum in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is high and it significantly related to senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Physics in Taraba state. This finding corroborates the results of Annan et al. (2021), Van Driel and Berry (2020), Cohen-Vogel and Osborne-Lampkin (2019), who found a positive relationship between the curriculum knowledge of science teachers and students' academic achievement. However, this finding contrasts with the results of Smith and Brown (2020), Rodriguez and Wilson (2019), who found that teachers with extensive curriculum knowledge did not necessarily translate this into improved student academic achievement.

Conclusion

There is a significant correlation between teachers' mastery of students' learning and students' academic achievement among senior secondary schools students in Taraba State. There is also a significant relationship between physics teachers' knowledge of curriculum and students' academic achievement. Hence, Taraba state ministry of Education should organize training conferences and workshops that are aimed at improving Teachers' knowledge of students' understanding of physics and teachers' knowledge of curriculum. An improved Teachers' knowledge of students' understanding of physics and teachers' knowledge of curriculum will result in improved academic achievement for students, as found by this study.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusion from the study the following are the recommendation:

1. Schools should offer specialized training for physics teachers on student-centered teaching approaches that focus on understanding students and addressing students' individual learning needs.
2. Since there is a significant relationship between Physics teachers' curriculum knowledge and students' academic achievement, physics teachers knowledge of curriculum should be improve through integrating curriculum-related insights into teaching practices. This involves aligning instructional content with curriculum standards, ensuring coherence across lesson plans, and staying updated with curriculum revisions and advancements in Physics education.

References

- Annan, T.S., Fordjour, C.O, Koomson, C.K., Agyemang, C., Addae, R. & Anim, D.O. (2021). Curriculum knowledge of science teachers and its influence on students' academic achievement in Kwaebibirem district of Ghana. *International Journal of Academic Research and Reflections*, 6(18), 98-104.
- Cohen-Vogel, L., & Osborne-Lampkin, L. (2019). The relationship between teachers' curriculum knowledge and student achievement: A meta-analysis. *Journal Educational Research*, 48(3), 178-192.

Relationships Between Professional ... (Adamu, et al., 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045167>

- Cowan, P., Goldhaber, D. & Theobald, R. (2019). Teacher knowledge of students and the relationship to academic achievement. *American Educational Research Journal*, 56(4), 1145-1177.
- De Jong, O., & Van Driel, J. H. (2015). The development of preservice chemistry teachers' pedagogical content knowledge. *Journal of Science and Education*, 99(5), 888-921.
- Etkina, E., Gregorcic, B., & Vokos, S. (2017). Exploring the nature of science learning and teaching using the Investigative Science Learning Environment. *The Physics Teacher*, 55(6), 316-321.
- Filgona, J., Sakiyo, J. & Gwany, D. M. (2020). Teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and students' academic achievement: a theoretical overview. Department of Environmental and Life Sciences Education, Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola, Adamawa state, Nigeria. *Journal of Global Research in Education and Social Science*, 14(2), 14-44.
- Gess-Newsome, J., Taylor, J. A., Carlson, J., Gardner, A. L., Wilson, C. D. & Stuhlsatz, M. A. M. (2019). Teacher pedagogical content knowledge, practice, and student achievement in sub regions of Zambia. *International Journal of Science Education*, 41(6), 790-813.
- Hill, C.H. & Chin, M. (2018). Connection between teachers' knowledge of students, instruction and achievement outcomes. *American educational research journal*, 53(5), 1076-1112.
- Kimani, G.N., Kara, A.M. & Njagi, L.W. (2014). Teacher factors influencing students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Nyandarua County, Kenya. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1(3), 1-14.
- Mikko, A.N & Tirri, K. (2018). Teachers' knowledge of curriculum integration: A current challenge for finish subject teachers. Open access peer reviewed chapter. <http://www.intechopen.com>.
- Mukama, N. (2019). Factors Influencing physics performance among students in the selected secondary schools. A case study of Buyengo sub-country. *International journal of Science and Research*, 3(2), 277-280.
- Nadir, A. (2014). The impact of teacher knowledge of students on student achievement in 14 Sub-Saharan African countries. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation, PP 1-17.
- Odumosu, M.O., Olisama O.V. & Fasayo, A. (2018). Teachers' content and pedagogical content knowledge on students' achievement in Algebra in Lagos State Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 6(3) 1-16.
- Omirin, J. A. (2015). An evaluation of students' performance in senior secondary school physics examination in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(10), 102-107.
- Rodriguez, C., & Wilson, P. (2019). The impact of curriculum knowledge on student achievement: A multi-variable analysis. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 41(3), 365-389.
- Sadler, P.M., Coyle, H.P., Sonnert, G. & Friedman, D.M. (2013). Influence of teachers' knowledge on student learning in middle school physical classrooms. *American Educational Research Journal*, 50(5), 1020-1049.
- Shamin, M., Tabasum, R. & Rashid, R. (2013). Students' academic performance in physics correlates the experience of teachers in high secondary schools of jammu and kashir state. *International Journal of Current Research*, 5(1), 10-45.
- Smith, J., & Brown, L. (2020). Reassessing the relationship between teachers' curriculum knowledge and student academic in United State performance. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 30(2), 145-160.
- Tsholofelo, A.T. & Maree, D. (2021). Student factors affecting academic success among undergraduate students at two South African higher education institutions. *South African Journal of Psychology*, 52(1), 12- 24.
- Van Driel, J. H., & Berry, A. (2020). Teacher curriculum knowledge and its impact on student achievement in science: A comparative study across countries. *International Journal of Science Education*, 42(9), 1415-1433.
- Yusuf, A.A., Omosewo, E.O., Akanbi, A.O., Mohammed, R.E., Badmus, O.T. & Usman, A. (2021). Physics teacher pedagogical content knowledge and students' academic achievement in Kwara state, Nigeria. University of allorin, Department of Science Education. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>.

Availability and Utilization of Laboratory Facilities as Correlates of Performance in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Giwa Educational Zone, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study investigated Correlation between availability and utilization of Laboratory facilities on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational Zone, Kaduna State” The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two (SS 2) Chemistry students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Giwa educational zone. A sample size of two hundred and sixty-two (262) respondents were randomly selected from the target population. Chemistry Student Questionnaires (CSQ), Chemistry teachers Questionnaires (CTQ) and School administrators Questionnaires (SAQ) were adopted and validated by experts. They were found to have reliability coefficient of 0.78, 0.80 and 0.85 respectively. Three research objectives, with corresponding research questions and hypotheses were raised and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Data collected were analysed using Frequency and percentages and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). the result revealed that significant relationship exist between the availability of chemistry laboratory facilities, adequacy of chemistry laboratory facilities, level of utilization of chemistry laboratory facilities, chemistry teachers’ qualifications ,number of chemistry teachers and academic performance in Chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Education zone, Kaduna State. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the utilization of chemistry practical in senior secondary schools is faced with problems ranging from poor teaching personnel in terms of qualification and adequacy, poor level of priority given to practical work by chemistry teachers to the non-availability of space, equipment and apparatus for practical work. it was recommended among others that Chemistry laboratory facilities should be made available in all secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Key words: Academic performance, Laboratory facilities, Chemistry

Introduction

Science education is the education that comprises the knowledge of sciences with the study of education. Olanrewaju (2018), sees science education as the study of all science subjects like Biology, Physics, Chemistry and others using variety methods of teaching so as to impact scientific knowledge to various learners. West African Examination Council’s (WAEC) syllabus (WAEC, 2012), suggested that all science subjects (Chemistry inclusive) in the schools should taught in such a way that practical would be given a special preference, because of the significance it has in the studies of sciences. According to Ababio (2019), Chemistry is the branch of science that studies the composition, properties and uses of matter. It studies how and why substances combine or separate to form other substances, and how various substances interact with energy. Yahaya et al. (2021) also define Chemistry as a science subject offered in Senior Secondary Schools in Nigeria as a core subject. To be given an admission to study courses like Medicine, pharmacy, Nursing, Engineering and many other physical science courses in university, credit in chemistry is required. Umahaba, Olajide & Lawal (2015) state that the developed countries forged ahead by understanding the relevance of Chemistry and its role in the national economy, in the study of medicine, pharmacy, medicine and other technologically based courses.

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One of the main objectives of teaching Chemistry in the Senior Secondary schools is for the students to gain basic theoretical and practical knowledge coupled with the skills that can be applied to meet the societal needs of creating employment and wealth. The skills will not only help students to find out, use and understand the scientific knowledge and technology of today but also tomorrow (FRN, 2012). This can only be achieved where there are well-equipped laboratories in the secondary schools. Chemistry laboratory is a building in a school set up and equipped with facilities meant for the conduction of scientific experiments. The chemistry laboratory contains facilities such as equipment, chemicals as well as gadgets used for effective performance of practical lessons. Ogunyemi and Adesoji (2000) observed that, without the use of laboratory facilities, some objectives of teaching chemistry practical may not be achieved such as; students' appreciation of scientific method of learning chemistry which has to do with experimentation, observation, recording, deduction and interpretation of scientific data accurately. Academic performance according to Shuaibu (2017) is the application of knowledge gained or skills developed in academic activity designed by test scores or marks assigned by the training instructor. According to WAEC Chief Examiner's report (2016, 2017, 2018, 2019), there were a series of poor performance in Chemistry practicals. Some of the suggestions made are: teachers and students have to work hard in the classrooms and laboratories, teachers should use their school laboratories very well, teachers must endeavor to expose candidates to a lot of practical exercises and teachers must make time to mark the exercises and draw the attention of students to essential points in recording tests, observation and inferences made. It was also suggested that additional practical equipment should be supplied to schools as the class size is increasing, more time should be allocated to practical to give students more chance to practice. This will enable them to relate theory with practical and also see its relevance in life.

Statement of the Research problem

Most schools in Nigeria are just claiming to teach chemistry at the secondary level without laboratory facilities, this clearly shows that no practical is taken place in such schools and where the laboratories exist, they are poorly equipped with the facilities (Ogunyeye, 2000). Inadequate resources for teaching and learning of Chemistry are common in secondary schools in Nigeria (Giwa Local Government of Kaduna State inclusive). And where little is provided is not sufficient to go round the students. Therefore, effective learning cannot be achieved (Bassey, 2002). Usman (2000) clarifies that the provision of resources (laboratory facilities) and their effective administration makes teaching easier and faster. This in turn encourages students to learn new ideas well and enhances their academic excellence. This study aims to identify the Effects of Laboratory Facilities on Senior Secondary Students' Academic Performance in Chemistry among Selected Secondary Schools in Giwa Local Government Area, Kaduna, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to;

1. Determine the relationship between availability of laboratory facilities and performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State
2. Determine the relationship between level of laboratory equipment and performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State
3. Determine the relationship between adequacy of laboratory facilities and performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State

Research questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the influence of availability of laboratory facilities on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?
2. What is the influence of laboratory equipment on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?
3. What is the influence of adequacy of laboratory facilities on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance

1. **H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between availability of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Education Zone

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2. **H02:** There is no significance relationship between adequacy of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone
3. **H03:** There is no significant relationship in the level of utilization of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone

Methodology

The research design was descriptive survey. The study investigated the availability of chemistry laboratories and laboratory equipment. It equally investigated the frequency of practical activities among secondary schools in Giwa local government. The population for the study comprised of all the 1750 SS 2 Chemistry Students and teachers in Giwa local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. A sample of 250 SS 2 chemistry students were randomly selected. Three instruments were adapted by the researchers and validated by experts are used to collect data for the study. The instruments were; Chemistry Student Questionnaires (CSQ), Chemistry teachers Questionnaires (CTQ) and School administrators Questionnaires (SAQ). Some items in the questionnaires were structured (closed ended), to measure the objective responses and others were unstructured (open ended) to measure the subjective responses. The Data was collected using fixed- and opened-response questionnaire, questionnaires were distributed at each school with the assistance of their chemistry teachers and were given to the chemistry students, chemistry teachers and school administrator to answer. The research hypotheses were tested using Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) test at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level. A correlation of 0.9 was found on two successive administrations

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: What is the influence of availability of laboratory facilities on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?

Table 1: Respondents' opinion on the availability of Chemistry Laboratory Facilities for practical in Senior Secondary Schools in Giwa

STATEMENT	SA		A		D		SD	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Preparation room is available	103	56.3	30	16.4	34	18.6	16	8.7
Electricity supply is available	75	41	88	48.1	0	0	20	10.9
Water and heat supply are available	123	67.2	50	27.3	10	5.5	0	0
Chemicals/Reagents are available	78	33.9	30	15.4	20	12	92	38.7
Storage room and glass wares available	133	72.7	50	27.3	0	0	0	0
First aid kits are available	33	18	10	5.5	40	21.9	100	54.6
Fire extinguishers are available	90	49.2	50	27.3	25	13.7	18	9.8
Safety materials are available	10	5.5	35	19.1	18	6.5	120	69.8
Space for class work are available	130	71	23	12.6	15	8.2	15	8.2
Other consumable materials are available	43	23.5	10	5.5	70	38.3	60	32.7

Key: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree

Table 1 indicates respondents' opinions with regard to utilization of chemistry laboratory facility for practical in secondary schools in Giwa. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that preparation room are utilized. while, 130 respondents (71%) disagreed. It implies that preparation room are not utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area. 153 respondents (84.6%) agreed that electricity supply is well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical while 30 respondents (15.4%) disagreed. It means that electricity supply is well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area. 183 respondents (100%) agreed that water and heat supply is well utilized in chemistry laboratories. 138 respondents (75.4%) agreed that chemical/reagent are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical while 50 respondents (23.6%) disagreed. It means that chemicals/reagents are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical. 143 respondents (78.2%) agreed that Storage room and glass wares are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical while 40 respondents (21.8%) disagreed. 43 respondents (23.5%) agreed that first aid kit are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical. While 140 respondents (76.5%) disagreed. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that fire extinguisher are well utilized in chemistry laboratory. While 130 respondents (71%) disagreed. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that safety materials are well utilized in chemistry laboratory, while 130 respondents (71%) disagreed. 183 respondents (100%)

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agreed that space for class work are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area. 33 respondents (18.1%) agreed that consumable materials are well utilized in chemistry laboratory. While 150 respondents (81.9%) disagreed. It implies that other consumable materials are not well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area

Research Question Two: What is the influence of laboratory equipment on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?

Table 2: Opinions of the Respondents on the adequacy of Chemistry Laboratory Facilities for practical in Senior Secondary Schools in Giwa

S/N	STATEMENT	SA		A		D		SD	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Preparation room are adequate	143	78.1	20	10.9	10	5.5	10	5.5
2	Electricity supply is adequate	103	56.3	20	10.9	55	30	5	2.7
3	Water and heat supply are adequate	50	28.3	30	16.4	40	20	98	35.3
4	Chemicals/ Reagents are adequate	18	8.3	30	18	68	30	88	48.7
5	Storage room and glass wares are adequate	123	67.2	20	10.9	30	16.4	10	5.5
6	First aid kits are adequate	50	27.3	80	43.7	23	12.6	30	16.4
7	Fire extinguishers are adequate	93	50.8	40	21.9	33	18	20	10.9
8	Safety material are adequate	43	23.5	20	10.9	25	13.7	75	40.9
9	Space for class work are adequate	135	73.8	28	15.3	15	8.2	5	2.7
10	Other consumable material are adequate	23	12.6	50	27.3	60	32.8	50	27.3

Table 2 showed the opinions of the respondents on the adequacy of Chemistry Laboratory Facilities for practical in senior secondary schools in Giwa. 163 respondents (89%) agreed that preparation room are adequate while 20 (11%) disagreed. 123 respondents (67.2%) agreed that electricity supply is adequate in chemistry laboratories. While 60 respondents (32.8%) disagreed. It indicates that electricity supply is adequate. 80 respondents (44.3%) agreed that water and heat supply is adequate while 55.7% disagree. 48 respondents (26%) agreed that Chemicals/reagents are adequate. While 156 respondents (73.7%) disagreed. It means that chemicals/reagents are not adequate. 143 respondents (78.1%) agreed that Storage room and glass wares are adequate chemistry laboratories. While 40 respondents (21.9%) disagreed. 130 respondents (71%) agreed that first aid kit are adequate. While 53 respondents (29%) disagreed. 133 respondents (72.7%) agreed that fire extinguishers are adequate. While 50 respondents (27.3%) percent disagreed. 83 respondents (45.4%) percent agreed that safety materials are adequate in chemistry laboratories. While 100 respondents (54%) disagreed. 163 respondents (89.1%) agreed that space for class work are adequate in chemistry laboratories. While 20 respondents (10.9%) disagreed. 73 respondents (39.9%) agreed that consumable materials are adequate in chemistry laboratories. While 110 respondents (60.1%) disagreed. It implies that other consumable materials adequate in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area.

Research Question Three: What is the influence of adequacy of laboratory facilities on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?

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Table 3: Opinions of the Respondents upon the level of usage of Chemistry Laboratory equipment for practical in Giwa Secondary schools

S/N	STATEMENT	SA		A		D		SD	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Preparation room are utilized	43	23.5	10	5.5	50	27.3	80	43.7
2	Electricity supply is utilized	103	56.3	50	27.3	20	11	10	5.5
3	Water and heat supply is utilized	153	83.6	30	16.4	0	0	0	0
4	Chemicals /Reagents are utilized	113	61.7	25	13.7	40	21.9	10	5.5
5	Storage room and glass wares are utilized	120	65.6	23	12.6	15	8.2	25	13.7
6	First aid kits is utilized	28	15.3	15	8.2	70	38.3	70	38.3
7	Fire extinguisher are utilized	30	16.4	23	12.6	80	43.7	50	27.3
8	Safety materials are utilized	18	9.8	35	19.1	100	55.6	30	16.4
9	Space for class work are utilized	133	72.7	50	27.3	0	0	0	0
10	Other consumable materials are utilized	10	5.5	23	12.6	80	55.6	70	38.3

Table 3 pointed out the opinions of the respondents on the utilization Chemistry Laboratory Facility for practical in secondary schools in Giwa. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that preparation room are utilized in chemistry laboratories for practical. while 130 respondents (71%) disagreed. 153 respondents (84.6%) agreed electricity supply is well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical. While 30 respondents (15.4%) percent disagreed. 183 respondents (100%) agreed that water and heat supply is well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area. 138 respondents (75.4%) agreed that chemical/reagent are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical. While 50 respondents (23.6%) disagreed. 143 respondents (78.2%) agreed that Storage room and glass wares are well utilized. While 40 respondents (21.8%) disagreed. 43 respondents (23.5%) agreed that first aid kit are well utilized. While 140 respondents (76.5%) disagreed. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that fire extinguishers are well utilized. While 130 respondents (71%) disagreed. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that safety materials are well utilized. While 130 respondents (71%) percent disagreed. 183 respondents (100%) percent agreed that space for class work are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area. 33 respondents (18.1%) percent agreed that consumable materials are well utilized. While 150 respondents (81.9%) disagreed. It implies that other consumable materials are not well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area.

Hypotheses testing

The formulated hypotheses tested at significant level of $P \leq 0.05$

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between availability of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Education Zone

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship Between Availability of Laboratory Facilities and Students' Academic Performance.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	1	2
Academic Performance	253	32.100	11.446	1.000	
Availability	010	12.200	10.838	.984**	1.000

**Correlation is at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level (2-tailed).

Table 4 revealed that a significant relationship exists between availability of chemistry laboratory facilities for practical and students' academic performance in Giwa Local Government area ($r = 0.984$, $P < 0.05$). This shows that availability of chemistry laboratory facilities for practical has relationship with students' academic performance. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significance relationship between availability of chemistry laboratory facilities for practical and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Giwa.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significance relationship between adequacy of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone

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Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the relation between the adequacy of chemistry laboratory equipment and students' performance among secondary students in Giwa.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	1	2
Academic Performance	253	32.100	11.446	1.000	
Adequacy	010	28.300	10.174	.855**	1.000

**Correlation is significant at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level (2-tailed).

Table 5 above revealed that a significant relationship exists between adequacy of chemistry laboratory facilities for practical and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area ($r = 0.855$, $P < 0.05$). This shows that adequacy of chemistry laboratory facilities have relationship with the academic performance of secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area. Therefore, the hypothesis two is hereby rejected.

Hypotheses Three: There is no significant relationship in the level of utilization of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone

Table 6: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between level of Utilization of Chemistry Laboratory facilities and Students' Academic Performance

Variables	N	Mean	SD	1	2
Academic Performance	253	32.100	11.446	1.000	
Utilization	010	7.400	8.479	.959**	1.000

**Correlation is significant at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level (2-tailed).

Table 6 above revealed that a significant relationship exists between level of utilization of chemistry laboratory facilities in senior secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area and students' academic performance ($r = 0.959$, $P < 0.05$). This shows that the level of utilization of chemistry laboratory facilities in secondary schools have relationship with students' academic performance in Giwa Local Government Area. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of the findings

The result from Table 4 revealed the correlation of the availability of chemistry laboratory facilities and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State. This is in agreement with Lunetta (2007) who had it that laboratory facilities have the potential to enhance cognitive growth in students. Table 5 showed that the adequacy of chemistry laboratory facilities is significantly related to the students' academic performance in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The nature of curriculum content, emphasizing theoretical knowledge, inadequate periods for chemistry and chemistry practical, inadequate facilities and equipment, reagent, support staff for laboratories, funding improvisation of materials, teachers' knowledge of practical, teachers' qualification, separate laboratories for chemistry, textbooks, work books and manuals for practical chemistry all constitute constraints toward effective utilization. These findings confirm the submission of Ogunleye (2002) and Olayiwola (1999) on the poor state of implementation, as it relates to facilities required for the effective implementation of practical work in chemistry. In hypothesis III, the result of the test showed that the frequency of usage of chemistry laboratory facilities is significantly related with students' academic performance. This finding is in line with the findings of Margil (2009) who find out that drill and practice help learners to understand and pass practical examination in school.

Conclusion

From the results and implications of findings it was concluded that:

The utilization of chemistry practical in senior secondary schools is still faced with problems ranging from poor teaching personnel in terms of qualification and adequacy, poor level of priority given to practical work by chemistry teachers to the non-availability of space, equipment and apparatus for practical work.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made;

1. There should be provision of adequate laboratory facilities all Senior Secondary Schools in Giwa Local Government.
2. The school heads should ensure that the teachers utilized all the chemistry laboratory facilities for effective teaching and learning in senior secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

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References

- Ababio O.Y (2019). New School Chemistry for Senior Secondary School. New edition African-FEB publishers Ltd.
- Bassey. M. P (2002). Availability of Resources for Teaching of Science Subjects in Public Secondary Schools: a case study of some Selected Secondary Schools in Limosho Local Government Area of Lagos State. Unpublished B.Sc. Ed project, Department of Education, University of Lagos.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2007). National Policy on Education. Lagos NERDC press.
- Gay L.R. (1976). Practical Work and Science Education II. *Journal of Science Education*. Volume 66.
- Lunette .K. N (2007). The School Science Laboratory: Historical Perspectives and Centres for Contemporary Teaching, in P. Fensham (ed) Development and Dilemmas in Science Education (pp 169-188).London, Falmer Press.
- Margil, I. G. and Secken, N. (2009). Investigating the Effect of Project Oriented Chemistry Experiments on Some Effective and Cognitive Field Components, *Journal of Turkey Science Education* 6 (1) 108-114
- Ogunleye, B.O. (2002). Evaluation of the Environmental Aspect of the Senior Secondary School Chemistry Curriculum in Ibadan, Nigeria. An unpublished Ph.D Thesis, University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Ogunyemi and Adesoji, J.A (2000). Isolation of Factors in Teachers' Perception of Senior Secondary Chemistry Practical. Nigeria University of Ibadan.
- Olarewaju, O.I. (2018). The Effectiveness Planned Post Laboratories Discussion on Students' Achievement in Physics, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Foundation*. 4 (2) 110-111.
- Shuaibu, A. A (2017) Effect of Collateral Learning on Attitude and Performance in Genetics Among Convergent and Divergent Secondary School Students in Suleja Educational Zone, Nigeria. Unpublished M. Ed thesis submitted to Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
- Umahaba, R.E, Olajidel J.O. and Lawl, T.E. (2015). Impact of 5Es Learning Model in Questioning Style Preference among Secondary School Chemistry Students, Katsina Metropolis, Nigeria. *Journal of Studies in Science and Mathematics Education, A.B.U, Zaria*. 4 (1) 89-95
- Usman I.A (2000) The Relationship Between Student Performance in Practical Activities and their Academic Achievement in Integrated Science using NISTEP mode of teaching. Unpublished Ph.D thesis Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- West African Examinations council (2016). Chief Examiners' Reports on West Africa Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (Nigeria).
- West African Examinations council (2017). Chief Examiners' Reports on West Africa Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (Nigeria).
- West African Examinations council (2018). Chief Examiners' Reports on West Africa Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (Nigeria).
- West African Examinations council (2019). Chief Examiners' Reports on West Africa Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (Nigeria).

Correlation between Teachers' Use of ... (Faransa, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045503>

Correlation between Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials and Academic Performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School Students in Adamawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the correlation between teachers' use of instructional materials and academic performance in Biology among senior secondary school students in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The study employs a correlational design; the study population consists of 814 teachers, as well as 39,390 Senior Secondary II (SSII) students from 366 senior secondary schools in Adamawa State. The sample of 260 Biology teachers, and 384 students was used with student performance in Biology. Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.86, indicating a high level of reliability. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire tagged Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials Questionnaire (TUIMQ) and analyzed using descriptive statistics and linear regression. The results revealed a weak but positive correlation ($r=0.208$) between the use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement, with 4.3% of the variance in performance explained by the use of these tools. Despite the limited impact weak correlation, the study emphasizes the need for improved teacher training and better access to instructional resources to enhance learning outcomes in Biology. The findings underscore the importance of continuous professional development for teachers and the provision of adequate resources to close the performance gap between well-funded urban schools and under-resourced rural areas. The study concludes that while instructional materials positively influence academic achievement, their effectiveness is constrained by infrastructural and financial limitations. Recommendations include policies to enhance technological infrastructure, teacher training, and equitable resource allocation to improve Biology education in Adamawa State.

Keywords: Instructional Materials, Biology Teachers, Senior Secondary Students and Academic Achievement

Introduction

In recent years, advancements in technology have created new opportunities for improving the use of instructional materials in classrooms. Tools such as interactive whiteboards, projectors, and online simulation platforms have revolutionized science education, particularly in Biology, by providing dynamic and accessible ways to explore concepts (Aliyu, 2020). These digital resources enable students to participate in virtual dissections, explore cellular processes, and observe biological phenomena in real-time. However, Yusuf and Afolabi (2022) highlight that the integration of these technologies in Adamawa State is limited due to infrastructural deficits and a lack of digital literacy among teachers. The authors suggest that policies to improve schools' access to technological infrastructure, along with teacher training programs are essential to fully integrate digital instructional materials into the Biology curriculum. Although the benefits of instructional materials in enhancing science education are well-recognized, there are considerable challenges to their widespread use in Nigerian schools, particularly in

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Adamawa State. Financial constraints have been identified as a significant barrier, impeding the procurement of essential resources such as laboratory equipment and teaching aids (Abdullahi & Gambo, 2020). Additionally, overcrowded classrooms in many public schools reduce the effectiveness of these materials, as teachers struggle to engage students individually. Ogbu and Hassan (2023) and Isma'il & Lukman (2022). found that insufficient government funding and inadequate infrastructure severely limit access to necessary teaching resources in rural areas, contributing to a performance gap between students in well-funded urban schools and their counterparts in under-resourced rural areas.

Several recent studies have underscored the critical role instructional materials play in enhancing students' academic achievement in science subjects, including Biology. Omosewo (2018) found that instructional tools such as charts, models, and laboratory equipment help students visualize biological concepts, making learning more engaging and effective. Similarly, Lawal (2019) noted that the use of hands-on materials in classrooms leads to better comprehension, retention, and application of biological knowledge compared to traditional lecture methods. These findings illustrate the importance of tangible instructional materials in fostering a deeper understanding of scientific concepts. Moreover, instructional materials can enhance students' cognitive processes by making abstract concepts more tangible and relatable. Aina and Ajiboye (2020) emphasize that when students interact physically with biological specimens or digital simulations, they are more likely to develop critical thinking skills, which are essential for mastering Biology. Despite this, many teachers lack the skills to effectively utilize these resources, which negatively impacts student performance (Idris & Mohammed, 2017; Isma'il & Lukman, 2022). Their study found that only a small fraction of teachers in Adamawa State were adequately trained to integrate instructional materials into their lessons, thereby reducing their effectiveness in improving learning outcomes.

Recent empirical studies have consistently highlighted the importance of instructional materials in enhancing students' academic performance, particularly in Biology. Oluwatobi and Ayinde (2021) and Omosewo (2018) found that schools where teachers used hands-on tools like charts, models, and laboratory equipment saw significant improvements in students' achievement in Biology, emphasizing the value of practical learning over traditional lecture methods. In Adamawa State, Idris and Mohammed (2017) identified inadequate teacher training in the use of instructional materials as a major barrier to effective Biology teaching, resulting in lower student performance. Similarly, Aina and Ajiboye (2020) demonstrated that while digital tools can greatly improve engagement and understanding of biological concepts, poor infrastructure and limited digital literacy among teachers hinder their use, particularly in rural areas. Ogbu and Hassan (2023) further explored the challenges in rural schools, revealing that limited access to teaching resources due to insufficient funding exacerbates the performance gap between rural and urban students. Yusuf and Afolabi (2022) supported these findings, noting that infrastructural deficits and lack of teacher training restrict the use of digital instructional tools, despite their potential to improve learning outcomes. Lastly, Lawal (2019) and Abdullahi and Gambo (2020) both emphasized the critical role of instructional materials in student success. Lawal found that the use of practical teaching aids directly improves academic performance, while Abdullahi and Gambo pointed to funding constraints as a major obstacle to providing these resources, especially in rural schools, further widening the performance disparity across regions. The need for continuous professional development programmes for teachers has been highlighted by Oluwatobi and Ayinde (2021), who argue that such programmes equip teachers with the necessary skills to design, improvise, and implement instructional materials in science subjects. Their research revealed that students taught by teachers who had received such training consistently outperformed their peers in standardized Biology exams. Ibeneme (2013) further emphasizes the importance of teaching aids, which he defines as practical materials used by both teachers and students during lessons to enhance learning. The lack of inadequacy of instructional materials remains a major cause of ineffectiveness in schools, leading to poor student performance (Abdu-Raheem, 2015). Ahmed (2016) confirmed that many Nigerian secondary schools operate in unwelcoming environments, lacking essential teaching materials. According to Eniyewu (2015), instructional aids are crucial in promoting students' knowledge acquisition and raising academic standards. The question remains whether adequate instructional materials exist for teaching Biology in secondary schools in Adamawa State. If available, are they sufficient? If not, what can be done to address this gap? Biology, as one of the science subjects at the senior secondary school level in Adamawa State, has seen a decline in students' academic achievement in recent years. Reports as reveal that student performance in the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination in Biology has been consistently below average. From 2014 to 2017, a concerning number of students failed to obtain credit-level passes in Biology, with percentages ranging from 13.2% to 30.2%. This decline has raised concerns among educational stakeholders, prompting an examination of factors contributing to students' underachievement in Biology.

Several factors including government policies, parental involvement, student motivation, and teacher-related issues have been proposed as potential contributors of poor academic performance. This study posits that the use (or lack thereof) of instructional materials by teachers may play a significant role in influencing students' academic achievement in Biology. To

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enhance students' understanding and address the challenges they face, this study seeks to explore how teachers' use of instructional materials predicts the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Biology in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem

Despite the recognized importance of instructional materials in enhancing students' academic achievement, particularly in Biology, their effective use remains a challenge in Nigerian secondary schools, including those in Adamawa State. Several issues, such as inadequate infrastructure, insufficient funding, and limited teacher training, hinder the integration of instructional materials into the curriculum. Reports indicate that student performance in Biology at the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Adamawa State has been consistently below average, with credit-level passes ranging from only 13.2% to 30.2% between 2014 and 2017. Additionally, the lack of access to necessary teaching aids and digital resources, compounded by teachers' limited skills in utilizing these tools, contributes to poor learning outcomes. This gap in the use of instructional materials raises questions about their availability, sufficiency, and role in students' academic achievement. Thus, this study investigates how teachers' use of instructional materials predicts the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Biology in Adamawa State, aiming to address the challenges and improve student performance in the subject.

Objective of the Study

The purpose objective of this study is to examine the Teachers' use of instructional materials predicts senior secondary school students' Academic Achievement in Biology Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Research Question

The following research question was posed to guide the study:

How effective is biology teachers' use of instructional materials in senior secondary schools in Adamawa State?

Null Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis formulated and was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: Teachers' use of instructional materials does not significantly predict senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State.

Methodology

The study employed a predictive correlational design to assess the relationship between Teachers' use of instructional materials predicts senior secondary school students' Academic Achievement in Biology Adamawa State, Nigeria. According to Gay (2018), this approach examines the natural connections between variables without manipulation or imposed causality. Whitley and Kite (2021) further characterize predictive correlational research as a method to investigate associations among naturally occurring variables. This design effectively identifies key predictor of student achievement, focusing on factor such as Teachers' use of instructional materials. A survey involving principals and teachers was conducted to evaluate how teachers use of instructional materials predict students' academic performance in Biology. The study population consists of 814 Biology teachers, as well as 39,390 Senior Secondary II (SSII) students from 366 senior secondary schools in Adamawa State. Biology is a core science subject within the school curriculum. A sample size of 260 principals/Biology teachers and 384 students was selected, following the recommendations of the Research Advisor (2006). The study employed a multistage sampling technique, beginning with cluster sampling, where the population was divided into clusters based on educational zones in Adamawa State. Three educational zones were selected as clusters. In the second stage, Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected within each cluster. In third stage, schools were randomly selected from the chosen LGAs. The final stage involved selecting Senior Secondary II (SSII) students, as they had covered sufficient content in Biology, while SSIII students were excluded as they were preparing for their final exams.

The instrument for data collection was a researchers-constructed questionnaire, the "Teachers' use of instructional materials Questionnaire" (TUIMQ), consisting of 10 items mixed for both positive and negative. The TUIMQ used a five-point Likert scale ranging from Very High Level (VHL) to Very Low Level (VLL). Scores were assigned as thus: 1 for Very Low Level (VLL), 2 for Low Level (LL), 3 for Medium Level (ML), 4 for High Level (HL), and 5 for Very High Level (VHL). A decision rule of 3.0 was applied, where a mean score above 3.0 indicates a positive response (High/Very High Level), and a mean score below 3.0 indicates a negative response (Low/Very Low Level). The researchers also collected students' academic performance scores in Biology, through pro-forma result collected from the schools and converted them into standard scores

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for analysis. To ensure the validity of the instruments, the TUIMQ was reviewed by experts in Curriculum and Instruction. These experts scrutinized the instrument to ensure it accurately measured Teachers' use of instructional materials in relation to the study's research questions and hypotheses. Suggestions were made to restructure the instrument and include both principals and teachers as respondents. All necessary revisions were incorporated into the final draft of the questionnaire. The reliability of the TUIMQ was tested through a trial testing with Biology teachers and students from a school not included in the study. Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.86, indicating a high level of reliability. Data analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23. Descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, were used to answer the research question, while linear regression analysis was used to test the null hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: How effective is biology teachers' use of instructional materials in senior secondary schools in Adamawa State?

Table 1: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation of Effectiveness of Biology Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials in Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State

S/N	ITEMS	n = 260	Mean	St.D	Remark
1	Adequacy of instructional materials for use during Biology instructions.		4.33	1.02	HL
2	Knowledge of improvisation of instructional materials.		4.43	0.90	HL
3	Quality of instructional materials.		4.47	0.84	HL
4	Appropriate selection of instructional materials.		4.30	1.04	HL
5	Poor handling of instructional materials.		4.32	1.01	HL
6	Ability to use instructional materials during instruction.		3.78	1.42	HL
7	Improvise instructional materials for instruction.		3.76	1.43	HL
8	Suitability of instructional materials with topics taught.		3.95	1.40	HL
9	Rarely use instructional materials during instruction.		4.07	1.32	HL
10	Availability of instructional materials for instruction.		3.54	1.51	HL
Grand Mean			4.09		

Source: Survey 2024

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation regarding the effectiveness of biology teachers' use of instructional materials in senior secondary schools in Adamawa State. The grand mean score of 4.09 reflects a high level of effectiveness in the utilization of these instructional materials by biology teachers.

Null Hypothesis

H₀₁: Teachers' use of instructional materials does not significantly predict senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State.

Table 2a: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.208 ^a	.043	.040	1.39438582

a. Predictors: (Constant), use of instructional materials

Table 2a provides a model summary for the regression analysis examining the relationship between the use of instructional materials and another variable. The correlation coefficient (R) is 0.208, suggesting a weak positive relationship between the

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variables. The R. Square value of 0.043 indicates that approximately 4.3% of the variance in the dependent variable can be explained by the use of instructional materials. The Adjusted R Square is 0.040, which slightly adjusts for the number of predictors in the model. The Standard Error of the Estimate is 1.394, reflecting the average distance that the observed values fall from the regression line. Overall, the results suggest that the use of instructional materials has a limited impact on the dependent variable in this model.

Table 2b: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials as Predictor of Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Biology in Adamawa State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.722	1	22.722	11.686	.001 ^b
	Residual	501.632	258	1.944		
	Total	524.354	259			

a. Dependent Variable: Z score (ACHIEVEMENT)

b. Predictors: (Constant), use of instructional materials

Table 2b summarizes the ANOVA results for the linear regression analysis, which examines the impact of teachers' use of instructional materials on senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State. The regression model has a Sum of Squares for regression of 22.722, with 1 degree of freedom (df), leading to a Mean Square of 22.722. The F-value of 11.686 indicates a statistically significant relationship between the predictor and the dependent variable, as reflected in the significance level (Sig.) of 0.001. The Residual Sum of Squares is 501.632 with 258 degrees of freedom, yielding a Mean Square of 1.944. The total sum of squares for the model is 524.354 with 259 degrees of freedom. This result suggests that the use of instructional materials significantly predicts students' academic achievement in biology.

Table 2c: Coefficients of Beta

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.621	.399		-4.063	.000
	USEOFINSTRUCTIONALMATERIALS	.357	.105	.208	3.419	.001

Table 2c presents the coefficients from the regression analysis, showing the relationship between the use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement in biology. The unstandardized coefficient for the constant is -1.621 with a standard error of 0.399 indicating the expected value of the dependent variable (Z score of achievement) when the predictor is zero. The coefficient for the use of instructional materials is 0.357 with a standard error of 0.105. This suggests that for each one-unit increase in the use of instructional materials, the Z score of achievement is expected to increase by 0.357 units. The standardized coefficient (Beta) for the use of instructional materials is 0.208, indicating a weak effect size. The t-value for the use of instructional materials is 3.419, and the significance level (Sig.) is 0.001, indicating that the effect is statistically significant. It showed that teachers' use of instructional materials does not significantly predict senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State

Summary of the Major Findings

The regression analysis of the data collected revealed that, the use of instructional materials significantly predicts senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State. Specifically, for each one-unit increase in the use of instructional materials, students' Z score of achievement is expected to increase by 0.357 units. This relationship is statistically significant, with a significance level of 0.001, highlighting the importance of effective instructional material usage in enhancing student performance in biology.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study align with a growing body of empirical research that underscores the critical role of instructional materials in enhancing students' academic performance, particularly in biology. Previous studies, such as those conducted by Oluwatobi and Ayinde (2021) and Omosewo (2018), demonstrate that the incorporation of hands-on tools, including charts, models, and laboratory equipment, leads to significant improvements in student achievement. These studies emphasize the value of practical learning experiences over traditional lecture-based approaches, suggesting that interactive

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instructional materials can foster a deeper understanding of biological concepts. In the context of Adamawa State, Idris and Mohammed (2017) identified inadequate teacher training in the effective use of instructional materials as a significant barrier to successful biology teaching. This lack of training can lead to suboptimal use of available resources, resulting in lower student performance. Aina and Ajiboye (2020) further corroborate this point by highlighting the potential of digital tools to enhance engagement and understanding of biological concepts. However, they also point out that poor infrastructure and limited digital literacy among teachers inhibit the effective integration of these tools, particularly in rural areas where resources are scarce. Ogbu and Hassan (2023) explored the specific challenges faced by rural schools, revealing that insufficient funding leads to limited access to teaching resources, which exacerbates the performance gap between rural and urban students. This finding is supported by Yusuf and Afolabi (2022), who note that infrastructural deficits and a lack of teacher training restrict the utilization of digital instructional tools, despite their proven efficacy in improving learning outcomes. Finally, the work of Lawal (2019) and Abdullahi and Gambo (2020) reinforces the essential role of instructional materials in promoting student success. Lawal found a direct correlation between the use of practical teaching aids and improved academic performance, while Abdullahi and Gambo highlighted funding constraints as a significant obstacle to providing these essential resources, particularly in rural schools. This situation perpetuates a performance disparity across regions, underscoring the need for targeted interventions to enhance the availability and effective use of instructional materials in biology education.

Conclusion

The study concluded that teachers' use of instructional materials has a statistically significant but weak positive correlation with senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State. The findings indicate that effective use of instructional materials positively predicts students' understanding and performance in the subject.

Recommendations

Based on the findings that the following recommendations can be made:

1. Educational authorities should ensure that schools are adequately supplied with a variety of instructional materials, such as textbooks, laboratory equipment, charts, and digital tools. This investment will facilitate effective teaching and enhance students' learning experiences.
2. Government should Conduct regular workshops and professional development programmes for biology teachers focused on the effective integration of instructional materials into their teaching practices. Training should cover both traditional and digital resources to enhance teachers' instructional strategies.
3. Government should Foster a classroom culture that emphasizes interactive and experiential learning through the use of instructional materials. Encourage teachers to incorporate hands-on activities, group work, and project-based learning that utilize available resources effectively.
4. Government should establish a network for schools to share instructional materials and resources. This could include creating partnerships between urban and rural schools to ensure that all students have access to quality educational tools, even if some schools have limited resources.
5. Schools administration should promote the use of educational technology, such as simulations, online labs, and interactive software that can supplement traditional instructional materials. Provide training for teachers to enhance their skills in using these digital tools effectively.

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References

- Abdullahi, A., & Gambo, M. (2020). Funding constraints and the availability of instructional materials in Nigerian schools. *Journal of Education and Practice, 11*(3), 45-52.
- Abdu-Raheem, B. O. (2015). The influence of instructional materials on academic performance of students in social studies in junior secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Practice, 3*(6), 214-224.
- Ahmed, I. (2016). Correlation between instructional materials and achievement in Biology among senior secondary school students in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Studies, 12*(3), 45–58.
- Aina, J. K., & Ajiboye, S. K. (2020). Impact of digital tools on the teaching of biological concepts in Nigerian secondary schools. *Science Education International, 31*(1), 72-82.
- Aliyu, A. (2024). *Correlation between instructional materials and achievement in Biology among senior secondary school students in Adamawa State, Nigeria*. Unpublished manuscript (Bayero University, Kano State, Nigeria).
- Eniyewu, L. (2015). The impact of instructional materials on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice, 6*(33), 53-58.
- Ibeneme, O. T. (2013). Correlation between instructional materials and achievement in Biology among senior secondary school students in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research, 45*(2), 123–135.
- Idris, A. A., & Mohammed, S. Y. (2017). Teachers' training and utilization of instructional materials in Adamawa State: A case study. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Development, 12*(2), 34-41.
- Isma'il, A., & Lukman, O. M. (2022). Availability and utilization of instructional materials in teaching and learning of biology in senior secondary schools. *Aquademia, 6*(2), 1-8.
- Lawal, B. A. (2019). The use of practical teaching aids in improving Biology students' academic achievement. *International Journal of Educational Research, 15*(1), 105-118.
- Ogbu, C. O., & Hassan, M. T. (2023). The effect of limited access to teaching materials on student performance in rural schools: A case study of Adamawa State. *Journal of Science and Technology Education, 25*(2), 50-63.
- Oluwatobi, A. O., & Ayinde, K. L. (2021). Continuous professional development programs and the use of instructional materials in Nigerian schools. *Journal of Teacher Education and Practice, 19*(3), 22-34.
- Omosewo, E. O. (2018). The role of instructional materials in the teaching and learning of Biology in Nigerian secondary schools. *Educational Research and Reviews, 13*(5), 110-117.
- Yusuf, A. S., & Afolabi, O. O. (2022). Infrastructural deficits and digital literacy challenges in the integration of instructional technologies in Nigerian schools. *International Journal of Educational Technology, 9*(4), 87-99.
- Gay, L. R. (2018). *Educational Research: Competencies for Analysis and Applications*. Pearson.
- Whitley, B. E., & Kite, M. E. (2021). *Principles of Research in Behavioral Science*. Routledge.

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Educational Resource Management for Sustainable Economic Development at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

This paper focused on the qualitative study on educational resource management for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria: a systematic review. The paper discussed the meaning of educational resources management and its relevance at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Further, the paper delved into the major activities of resources management at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. This paper argued that educational resources management creates a sense of direction in resources management actions, reduces resources wastage and enhances effective instructional delivery with effective academic research without much delay and conflicts. This paper however maintained that resource planning and budgeting; resource provision and allocation; resource utilization and maintenance; resource improvement and supervision constitute the major activities of resources management at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. The paper therefore concluded that educational resources management must focus on adequate provision, proper allocation, efficient utilization, effective maintenance and regular improvement of all the available resources required for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Resources Management; Educational Institutions; Sustainable Economic Development

Introduction

Certainly, no developing economy promotes specific objectives and achieves any meaningful national goals in the absence of education. Education makes individuals ready for meaningful living in any economy and enhances sustainable development of such economy. Ebong (2006) believed that education provides opportunities for individuals to acquire knowledge, skills and attributes that shape and form the individuals for economic growth and national development. Additionally, Abraham (2020) submitted that education allows individuals and nations to discover opportunities and new ways to create job and create wealth. Unarguably, educational goals cannot be achieved without effective involvement and viable activities of educational resources management in educational institutions. Educational institutions are specialized form of organizations or establishments accredited to provide formal and non-formal education at different levels such as pre-primary, basic, primary, secondary and tertiary education levels among others. Educational institutions need resources to carry out activities and programmes of education in a bid to accomplish specific objectives.

Consequently, Ohia (2008) confirmed that educational institutions require resources in the form of quality teaching and non-teaching staff to carry out educational projects and activities. Resources serve as essential mechanism through which individuals' wants are satisfied and economy's goals actualized. Nyandema (2015) saw resources as the efficient and effective deployment of human skills, inventory and finance to support an institution when needed. Resources are vital ingredients of goals achievements hence; their management should not be taken for granted. Resource management involves adequate provision and proper allocation of required resources, their efficient

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utilization with effective maintenance and regular improvement for maximal achievement of goals. Educational resources are very important instrument of an economy goal's achievement. Educational resources are sources through which individuals have open access to education (Akpomi & Nwamadi, 2020). As further reasoned by Ogamba (2021), educational resources are assets available and anticipated for school operations in the economy. They are inputs that boost the activities and programmes of educational institutions to a great extent.

At tertiary level of education in Nigeria, educational resources exist in different forms and categories that can be classified into tangible and intangible assets. The tangible assets are visible inputs quantified into human, land, equipment, infrastructural facilities, instructional materials and capital. This form of assets can be seen, touch and transformed while the intangible assets are the invisible inputs that exist in the form of time availability, human knowledge, skills, abilities and competences among other human qualities. These assets can mostly be measured by the quality and quantity of outcome they produce. Intangible assets are invisible and indispensable due to the fact that the tangible assets cannot be utilized without the complement of intangible assets. Notably, Olelewe et al. (2014) identified funds dispensed and utilized, PTA levies, donations and internally generated revenue as educational resources. Similarly, Akpomi and Nwamadi (2020) added classrooms, lecture theatres, administrative block, laboratories, auditoriums, workshops, assembly halls, students' hostels, students' cafeteria and staff quarters.

In the revelations of Ebirim et al. (2023a), constant electricity power supply, well equipped ICT centers, adequate and functional computers, free and accessible internet services are among educational resources. Agabi (2010) highlighted more educational resources to comprise students and staff personnel, laboratory attendants, bursar, clerks, messengers, mail runners, gatekeepers, librarian, internet connectivity, school administrators and school planners. Similarly, Akpomi and Ordu (2009) identified textbooks, audio-visual and electronic instructional materials such as computers, tape recorder, video tape recorder, recorder, projector and other consumables like paper supply and writing materials as educational resources. Meanwhile, it could be understood that educational resources are divided into four major components which consist of human resources, material resources, time resource and financial resources. These resources are very important in educational institutions as none of them can function better in isolation of the other while trying to accomplish objectives of educational institutions particularly and the general goals of education in a developing economy such as Nigeria.

Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria

Development means the improvement of peoples' lifestyle through improved education, improved incomes, skill acquisition and employment (Ebirim & Uzoukwu, 2023). Enwere and Ugwu (2013) maintained that sustainable development is a pattern of economic growth in which resources' use aims to meet human needs while preserving the environment so that these needs can be met not only in the present but for generations to come. Mbaji and Ebirim (2013) promote sustainable development as collective improvement and justifiable circulation of resources in all sections of an economy to improve the living standard of the masses both in the present and in the future. Sustainable economic development refers to the ability of different nations to get better on their economy with a view to increasing their productive capacities for the satisfaction of essential needs of their individuals in the economy (Ilueme & Ebirim, 2016). Sustainable economic development carries connotation of lifelong economic transformation. It involves the emancipation of various units and departments of different levels of educational institutions from obstructions that affect their ability to develop and sustain their economy. Sustainable economic development involves minimizing resources wastage and creating opportunities for resources' optimization in the educational system to trigger economic growth. Sustainable economic development involves all round progress that takes place in all sections of a nation's economy that meets the educational needs of both present and future individuals.

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Educational Resources Management at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Educational resources management describes those activities relating to the provision, allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement of the required resources available in educational institutions for attainment of specific objectives and general goals of education. Resources are those necessary inputs which institutions depend on for their survival and improvement (Obi & Ogbuagu, 2020). The required educational resources available in educational institutions need to be effectively and efficiently managed for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Management is a human action that facilitates the production of educational goods and services in educational institutions through the process of planning, organizing, coordination, controlling and evaluation of the available scarce resources required for enhanced quality educational delivery and for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Educational resources management is a task of educational management designed to achieve the purpose for which educational resources are made available in educational institutions. Asodike and Jaja (2014) declared that educational resources management is the organization of the resources existing in education sector with the aim of producing eminent graduates in the system. This declaration goes down to describe educational resources management as a crucial exercise that allows for quality assurance in educational institutions for achievement of educational goals. Mbaji et al. (2013) explained quality assurance as the establishment of standards in various educational processes and activities that lead to the attainment of quality results. Educational resources management is the activity that contributes to the design, assessment, monitoring and effective manipulation of the required resources available in tertiary educational institutions for sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

Educational resources management is a collective activity of all those involved in the management of educational institutions aimed at improving quality of educational processes and programmes through the provision and allocation of resources, utilization and maintenance of resources, improvement and supervision of resources as well as evaluation and control of resources available in educational institutions. These resources are in terms of staff and students' personnel, infrastructural facilities, instructional materials, availability of limited time and finances at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Ihekwoaba and Maduiké (2016) added that educational resources management is the management of all relevant human and non-human resources that play various roles in promoting educational activities in educational system. It is the process of managing all human, material, non-material, audio-visual school environment and community materials available in an academic environment to facilitate academic activities and programme (Ebirim et al. 2023).

Relevance of Educational Resources Management at Tertiary Level of Education for Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria

Resources are very important element of goals' achievement. In other words, educational resources are most necessary in the attainment of sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. To achieve sustainable economic development in Nigeria, there is great need for effective management of scarce resources available in tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria. Management is a process that concerned with the formulation of strategies, plan, policies and programmes with a view of achieving set organizational goals (Jack & Nzokurum, 2020). For that reason, educational resources management guides the planners, managers and administrators of educational institutions to formulate policies on resource provision and allocation based on educational goals to be achieved. Also, it guides them to strategize on the best approach to equitably distribute the available scarce resources required for sustainable economic development based on priority needs of various units and departments in different tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria.

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Undoubtedly, educational resources management is a collective activity targeted at tackling educational problems within educational institutions to create conducive work environment for teaching and non-teaching staff as well as students and other people who have direct contact with other activities and programmes within educational institutions. In the light of the above, educational resources management tries to utilize the potentials and efforts of all individuals in tertiary educational institutions by seeking cooperative participation of all the individuals involved in the process of mobilizing and utilizing the available scarce resources required to enhance quality educational delivery and sustain economic development in Nigeria. Further, Akpan and Etor (2015) argued that when resources are properly allocated, maintained and efficiently utilized in educational institutions, they are most likely to be of good quality in terms of the output. This goes down to indicate that educational resources management creates room for enhanced quality educational delivery at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Educational resources management involves making proper decisions on how best to utilize and maintain available scarce resources in educational institutions for the achievement of educational goals in any economy such as Nigeria. Decision making entails taking effective actions on matters concerning resources' allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement among other activities in educational institutions. Thus, educational resources management enables managers and administrators of educational institutions to determine priorities for actions in the allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement of required scarce resources available in tertiary educational institutions for sustainable economic development in Nigeria. Abraham and Igwe (2006) noted that the actions of an administrator are guided by goals to be achieved and such requires that the administrator must be able to make good decision. Hence, educational resources management creates a sense of direction in the actions of managers and administrators in educational institutions towards decision making on proper allocation, efficient utilization, effective maintenance and regular improvement of all the required resources available in tertiary educational institutions for improved productivity and sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

Indisputably, educational resources management exists for the purpose of resources wastage reduction in educational institutions and to provide opportunities for efficiency as well as improved productivity in any economy. With effective educational resources management practices, educational managers and administrators are able to minimize the possibility of resources wastage in tertiary educational institutions. Ebirim and Ali (2021) noted that many resources are expended in the course of producing educational commodities and when a significant reduction in the level of wastage of resources in educational system is achieved, it indicates increase in productivity. So, educational resources management creates opportunities for reduction in the level of wastage at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. It guides the educational managers and administrators to prepare institutional budgets according to needs and activities of various units and departments at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Equally, it prepares their mind to ensure that the institutional budgets are effectively communicated to guarantee proper compliance with the daily implementation policy and objectives of tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria.

Most importantly, educational resources management enhances effective instructional delivery and effective academic research in educational institutions. Akpan and Etor (2015) were of the view that educational resources management involves the acquisition, utilization and administration of resources in higher education to enhance quality service delivery. On the other hand, Ogbodo (2011) posited that educational resources management creates avenue for judicious utilization and maintenance of human, materials, finance and other available scarce resources for the optimal achievement of set educational goals. In other words, educational resources management guides educational managers and administrators at tertiary level of education in Nigeria to strategize on the best approach to regularly evaluate and take inventory of instructional facilities and materials available in tertiary educational institutions for effective instruction and sustainable economic development in Nigeria. Through educational resources management, staff and students' activities are supervised regularly to determine in time areas of weakness

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that require immediate attention at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Once more, areas of job lapses in staff are being identified and corrected to enhance quality service delivery and to sustain economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Major Activities of Educational Resources Management at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Educational resources management covers a broad scope of activities. It involves making rational choice on proper allocation and efficient utilization of the required scarce resources available in educational institutions for the purpose of achieving educational goals and sustainable economic development in any economy of the world. The practice of educational resources management involves effective actions that must be initiated from rational decision making. Abraham and Igwe (2006) expressed that effective actions in organizations like tertiary educational institutions are predicated on correct decision making. The activities of educational resources management are guided by goals to be achieved. Goals are values determined to be achieved through the instrumentality of policies following appropriate strategies (Iwuchukwu, 2006). The more specific educational goals are the more major activities of educational resources management are directed towards the attainment of those goals and sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Educational resources management involves taking rational decision in a most efficient manner on the strategies for planning, budgeting, providing, allocating, utilizing, maintaining, improving, supervising, evaluating and controlling the available scarce resources required to enhance quality service delivery in educational institutions and to achieve the general goals of education. Taking rational decision in educational resources management involves making sound judgment on the allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement of the scarce resources available in tertiary educational institutions for the attainment of sustainable economic development. On the whole, educational resources management exists for the outright reason of mobilizing, utilizing and maintaining the available scarce educational resources required for sustainable economic development through adequate planning, proper organizing and effective coordination of both human and non human resources in tertiary educational institutions. Anorue and Uchegbu (2021) confirmed that educational resources management leads to planning, organizing, coordinating, staffing, reporting, directing and evaluating human and material resources for the realization of set educational objectives.

The major activities of educational resources management are resource planning, resource provision, resource utilization, resource maintenance, resource improvement, resource supervision and control (Ebirim et al. 2023a). From the forgoing idea, the major activities of educational resources management can be declared to include; resource planning and budgeting, resource provision and allocation, resource utilization and maintenance as well as resource improvement and supervision. These activities according to Obi (2003) are basic in the management process of educational institutions. Through these resources management processes, managers and administrators of educational institutions are able to create sense of direction in resource management actions, reduce resources wastage, enhance effective instructional delivery and effective academic research as well as achieve educational goals without much delay and conflicts.

Resource Planning and Budgeting at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Resource planning and budgeting involve the process of identifying, forecasting and allocating various components of educational resources in terms of human, materials, finance and time to programmes and events at the right time. These activities ensure that educational programmes and activities at tertiary level of education are carried out on time based on budgets made. It involves assigning the right tasks to the right personnel and the right facilities and materials to the right programmes and activities at the right time (www.saviom.com). They also center on the allocation of tasks to resources in a way that optimize the efficiency of resources' use in tertiary educational

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institutions to improve productivity. Resource planning and budgeting activities guide educational managers and administrators in making rational decision on resource provision and allocation at tertiary level of education.

Resource Provision and Allocation at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Resource provision and allocation involve the process of making required resources available for use in educational institutions to accomplish specified goals at tertiary level of education. Resource provision and allocation centre on availability of human resources to perform services function and availability of instructional facilities and materials for quality instructional delivery. Resource provision and allocation aim at finding a balance between maximizing the productivity of available resources in tertiary educational institutions while avoiding over utilization of resources. Ogbonnaya (2005) opined that resource provision includes providing funds for greater profitability of educational institutions. This means that tertiary educational institutions welcome marginal funding to provide additional specialist support or facilities for students within the identified tertiary level of education. Additionally, resource provision and allocation centre on providing instructional materials and facilities for carrying out instructional activities at tertiary level of education.

Resource Utilization and Maintenance at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Resource utilization and maintenance are among the major activities of educational resources management which centre on efficient usage and proper care giving to all available resources for goals' attainment. Resource utilization and maintenance measure how resources are efficiently utilized and the extent to which proper care is given to resources against their availability (<https://www.eresourcescheduler.com>). Resource utilization and maintenance allow educational managers and administrators to identify resource problems at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, timely. They ensure specific educational resources are not over utilized and, or underutilized. They express that resources required for educational activities and programmes are utilized in conformity with identified policies and objectives of educational institutions to be accomplished at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Resource utilization and maintenance describe how managers and administrators of tertiary educational institutions plan educational programmes and activities while ensuring efficient utilization of the available resources to their optimal potentials. Resource utilization and maintenance centre on those activities that relate with maximization and keeping of educational resources at their best condition of regular completeness through supervision and control.

Resource Improvement and Supervision at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Resource improvement and supervision centre on regular upgrading and overseeing of available resources in educational institutions to serve the aim for which resources are provided, allocated, utilized and maintained at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Ogbodo (2005) expressed that improvement is an ongoing process and supervision is always necessary for such process to be on track. Resource improvement and supervision ensure that educational managers and administrators execute their duties strictly in educational institutions for improved productivity at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Resource improvement and supervision revolve around personnel development and regular upgrading of materials and improved financial resources for quality service delivery and sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. They equally centre on assisting staff and student personnel to maintain focus on various resources that can give support to improve both curriculum and extra curriculum activities in tertiary educational institutions for the achievement of sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

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Implications of Educational Resources Management for Sustainable Economic Development at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

8. Educational resources management guides the educational planners, managers and administrators in formulating policies on the provision and allocation of educational resources based on the objectives of tertiary educational institutions and general goals of education to be achieved in Nigeria.
9. Educational resources management guides the educational planners, managers and administrators in strategizing the best approach to equitably distribute the available scarce resources required for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education based on priority needs of various units and departments in different tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria.
10. Educational resources management enables the educational managers and administrators to efficiently utilize the skills, abilities competences and efforts of all individuals in tertiary educational institutions by encouraging cooperative participation of all the individuals involved in the process of mobilizing and utilizing the available scarce resources required for enhanced quality educational delivery and sustainable economic development in Nigeria.
11. Educational resources management enables the tertiary educational managers and administrators to determine priorities for actions in the allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement of the required scarce resources available in tertiary educational institutions for improved productivity and sustainable economic development in Nigeria.
12. Educational resources management guides educational managers and administrators to minimize resources' wastage rate in preparing institutional budgets according to needs and activities of various units and departments and prepares their mind in ensuring that budgets are effectively communicated and properly complied with the daily implementation policy of tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria.
13. Educational resources management leads the educational managers and administrators to strategize the most efficient means of evaluating and taking inventory of instructional facilities and materials available in educational institutions for effective instruction in tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria. It also guides them in carrying out regular supervision on staff and students activities to determine in time areas of weakness that require immediate attention at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Recommendations

3. Educational planners, managers and administrators should always ensure that policies on the provision and allocation of educational resources are properly formulated based on the objectives of different tertiary educational institutions and general goals of education in Nigeria.
4. Educational planners, managers and administrators should always ensure that the available scarce resources required for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria are equitably distributed based on priority needs of various units and departments of different tertiary institutions.
5. Educational managers and administrators should always ensure that priorities for actions in the allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement of the available scarce resources required for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria are properly determined.
6. Educational managers and administrators should employ digital means of evaluating and taking inventory of instructional facilities and materials available in educational institutions for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.
7. Educational managers and administrators should always ensure that regular supervision are carried out on staff and students' activities to determine in time areas of weakness that require immediate attention at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

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Conclusion

Educational resources management is the foundation for achieving sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Educational resource management creates a sense of direction in resources management actions, reduces resources wastage and enhances effective instructional delivery as well as effective academic research without much delay and conflicts. Educational resources management covers a broad scope of activities that are initiated from rational decision-making process guided by goals to be achieved. The major activities of educational resources management are resource planning and budgeting, resource provision and allocation, resource utilization and maintenance as well as resource improvement and supervision. Educational resources management must focus on adequate provision, proper allocation, efficient utilization, effective maintenance and regular improvement of the available resources required for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

References

- Abraham, N.M. (2020). Managing education in the regime of corona virus pandemic: Issues, concerns, prospects and way forward. In C.M. Uche., S.O. Oluwuo., & N.M. Abraham (Eds.), *Management of education in the era of covid-19, social distancing and social connections: Challenges and prospects in Nigeria*. (pp. 129-150). University of Port Harcourt Press Ltd.
- Abraham, N.M., & Igwe, L.E.B. (2006). The pros and cons of group decision making. What educational managers must know? In J.M. Ebong & J. Ezekiel-Hart (Eds.), *Contemporary issues in education*. (pp. 255-269). EagleLithograph Press.
- Agabi, C.O. (2010). Prudential approach to resource management in Nigerian education: A theoretical perspective. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 3(2), 94-106. <http://www.ij sre.com>
- Akpan, C.P., & Etor, C.R. (2015). Resource management in higher education in Nigeria: Problems and measures for improvement. *Proceedings of Edulearn15 Conference* 6th-8th July, Barcelona, Spain. (3583-3591).
- Akpomi, M.E., & Nwamadi, C.C. (2020). Educational resources and the achievement of public junior secondary schools' goals in rivers east senatorial district. *International Journal of Innovative Social & Science Education Research*, 8(1), 34-40.
- Akpomi, M.E., & Ordu, P. (2009). Modern office technology and the secretary's productivity in private business organizations. *African Journal of Business Management*, 3 (8), 23-33.
- Anorue, C.E., & Uchegbu, B.C. (2021). Communication in the management of teacher education for sustainable response to emerging health issues in Nigeria. *African Journal of Innovations and Reforms in Educational Management (AJIREM)*, 2(1), 64-74.
- Asodike, J.D., & Jaja, O.S. (2014). Constraints to resource management. In F.N. Obasi., & J.D. Asodike (Eds.), *Educational resource management* (pp. 354-377). Pearl Publishers International Ltd.
- Ebirim, P.U., & Ali, U. (2021). Cost reduction strategies in secondary schools for improved productivity. *African Journal of Innovations and Reforms in Educational Management (AJIREM)*, 2(1), 130-134.
- Ebirim, P.U., & Uzoukwu, C.G. (2023). Curbing insecurity for improved socio-economic activities in secondary schools in Imo state, Nigeria. *Alvan International Journal of Politics and Administration*, 1(1), 267-273
- Ebirim, P.U., Abraham, N.M., & Meenyinikor, J.N.D. (2023). Extent of educational resources management in educational institutions in Imo state, Nigeria: implications for tertiary educational goals achievement. *Sapientia Foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender Studies (SFJESGS)*, 5(2), 387 – 402
- Ebirim, P.U., Meenyinikor, J.N.D., & Abraham, N.M. (2023a). Relevant skills for educational resources management and tertiary educational goals achievement in Imo state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Management, Social Sciences, Peace and Conflict Studies (IJMSSPCS)*, 6(2), 553- 567

Educational Resource Management ... (Ebirim & Amadi, 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045593>

- Ebirim, P.U., Nwogu, U.J. & Abraham, N.M., (2023b). Fiscal administration and accountability for enhanced educational system in a developing economy. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas (JEDA), Special Edition 31(2)*, 343- 351
- Ebong, J.M. (2006). Education and unemployment. In J.M. Ebong & J. Ezekiel-Hart (Eds.), *Contemporary issues in education*. (pp. 110-119). EaglesLithograph Press.
- Enwere, M.E., & Ugwu, D.U. (2013). Education for youth empowerment and sustainable development. *Unizik Orient Journal of Education*, 7(1), 182-185
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). *National policy on education*. (6th ed.). NERDC Press.
- Ihekwoaba, C.K.C., & Maduikwe, I.M. (2016). Managing school inputs to improve productivity. In S.O. Oluwuo & J.D. Asodike (Eds.), *Managing schools for productivity. Emerging perspectives*. (pp. 486-505). Pearl Publishers International Ltd.
- Ilueme, L.N. & Ebirim, P.U. (2016). Managing education in an under-developed economy. In S.O. Oluwuo., & J.D. Asodike (Eds.), *Managing Schools for Productivity- Emerging perspective* (300-322). Pearl Publishers International Ltd.
- Iwuchukwu, B.C. (2006). *Principles of educational policy analysis, the concepts and the art*. Cape Publishers Int’L Ltd.
- Jack, I.F., & Nzokurum, J.C. (2020). Managing teaching methods of online learning in Nigerian universities in the era of covid-19: challenges and prospects. In C.M. Uche., S.O. Oluwuo., & N.M. Abraham (Eds.), *Management of education in the era of covid-19, social distancing and social connections: Challenges and prospects in Nigeria*. (pp. 47-66). University of Port Harcourt Press Ltd.
- Mbaji, I.N. & Ebirim, P.U. (2013). Peace education: Roadmap to sustainable national development. *Nigerian Journal of Education Philosophy*, 24(1), 72-79
- Mbaji, I.N., Ebirim, P.U., & Akwali, P.C. (2013). Achieving quality assurance in entrepreneurship education for national transformation in Nigeria. In N. Onyegegbu & U. Eze (Eds.), *National transformation through entrepreneurial education*. (pp. 301 - 311). Institute of Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Nyandema, C.O. (2015). Role of human resources management practices and sustainable development of commercial bank. Case study of Kenya commercial bank. *International Journal of Social Science Management and Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 34-49.
- Obi, C.E., & Ogbuagu, I.G. (2020). Management of resources for the improvement of secondary schools education in Rivers State. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, 7(7), 1-7
- Obi, E. (2003). *Educational management theory and practice*. Jamoe Enterprises Nig.
- Ogamba, P.N. (2021). Achieving regular staff recruitment and orientation as correlates of jobs performance in federal universities in south-east, Nigeria. *African Journal of innovations Reforms in Educational Management AJIREM*, 2(1), 75-81.
- Ogbodo, C.M. (2005). Managing educational facilities in schools. In V.F. Peretomode (Ed.), *Introduction to educational administration planning and supervision* (Rev. ed.). (pp. 44-56). Joja Educational Research and Publishers Ltd.
- Ogbodo, C.M. (2011). Human resource development. In S.U. Basse., & U.U. Basse (Eds.), *Management of higher education in Africa*. (pp. 131-160). Abaam Publishers.
- Ogbonnaya, N.O. (2005). *Foundations of education finance*. Second edition. Hallman Publishers.
- Ohia, A.N. (2008). Career preference among education undergraduates in university of Port Harcourt. Implications for teaching manpower development. *African Journal of Education Research and development (AJERD)*, 2(1), 8-16.
- Olelewe, C.J, Nzeadibe, C.A., & Nzeadibe, T.C (2014). Availability and utilization of educational resources in selected rural communities of Enugu state: implications for achieving universal primary education of millennium development goals (MDGs) in Nigeria. *Educational Research International*, 3(1), 15-24.

Effect of 3d-Animation Illustration on Interest in Geometry Concept among Upper Basic Students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of 3D animation illustration on interest in geometry concept among upper basic in FCT. The effect of gender on the use of 3D animation illustration was also investigated. The study adopted a quasi- experimental pretest, post-test control group design. The population of the study comprised of all the upper basic two (JSS 2) mathematics students, during the 2023/2024 academic session in Abuja. The sample of the study consist of 120 (Male 56 and Female 64) upper basic two (JSS 2) students selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The experimental group were taught geometry using 3D Animation Illustration (DAI) while the control group were taught using Conventional Teaching Method (CTM). Data were collected using Geometry Students Interest Inventory Scale (GSIIS). The instrument was validated by experts, and its reliability was assessed using Cronbach alpha, yielding a reliability index of 0.938. The data was analysed using mean rank to answer the research questions and Mann Whitney to test the hypotheses. The result from the analysis shows that there was significant differences in the mean rank of interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI) and those taught with Conventional Teaching Methods (CTM) This study concluded based on the findings that the use of 3D animation illustration was effective for teaching geometry in mathematics for upper basic students. The study recommended among others that Government should provide training and professional development for teachers to effectively use 3D animation in their classrooms.

Keywords: 3D animation, geometry concept, interest in learning, educational technology, visual and interactive learning.

Introduction

Mathematics plays a key and fundamental role in the development and growth of any nation. Its significance lies in its necessity for scientific discoveries and technological breakthroughs, which are indicators of a developed economy (Anigbo, 2016). Research shows that mathematics is essential for achieving scientific and technological advancements, contributing to sustainable economic development in many nations (Gambari, Shittu, Daramola, & Jimoh, 2016). Science and technology are two distinct concepts that work in together, and mathematics serves as an essential instrument for achievements in both fields (Akinoso, 2011). Adigbo (2016) defined mathematics as the science of magnitude and number, highlighting its importance in virtually all subject areas. This is because all fields depend on it for problem-solving and predicting outcomes. He emphasized that competence in mathematics is crucial for individuals and nations alike, in areas such as domestic and business transactions, scientific discoveries, technological breakthroughs, problem-solving, and decision-making. Hom and Gordon (2021) assert that mathematics is fundamental to everything we do, forming the foundation for daily life, technology, architecture, art, finance, engineering, and even sports. They stressed that mathematical discoveries have been integral throughout history, evolving as society became more complex from basic counting to advanced calculations in modern civilizations.

Akinoso (2011) argued that mathematics is vital to science, technology, and economic development, particularly for

underdeveloped nations. He stated that for countries like Nigeria to progress, they must enhance their science, technology, and economy through effective mathematics education. Gimba and Agwagah (2012) further noted that Nigeria relies heavily on science and technology to combat poverty, ignorance, and disease, which are key indicators of underdevelopment. Recognizing the critical importance of mathematics, the Federal Government of Nigeria made it a core, compulsory subject at all educational levels, as outlined in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014). This policy also mandates that students seeking admission to tertiary institutions must pass mathematics at a credit level. Despite the pivotal role of mathematics in economic development through science and technology, Odili (as cited in Safo, Ezenwa, & Wushishi, 2013) observed that many students view mathematics as difficult, which leads to a lack of interest. Students often struggle to retain what they've learned, largely due to the excessive use of theoretical explanations and formulas by teachers, while students remain passive listeners. According to Idigo (2010), the persistent poor performance in mathematics at Nigeria's primary and post-primary school levels is largely due to students' lack of interest, which is closely tied to their mastery of foundational skills. Mastery of junior secondary school (JSS) mathematics is crucial for success at the senior secondary school (SSS) level, and interest in the subject can strongly predict future success. Interest in mathematics, as noted by Idigo (2010) and Goolsby (2013), can be assessed to gauge a student's readiness for further study. Factors influencing students' lack of interest include math anxiety, classroom distractions, inadequate infrastructure, and ineffective instructional strategies (Akinoso, 2011; Goolsby, 2013; Anigbo, 2016), emphasized that a teacher's qualifications play a significant role in students' interest and success in mathematics. A well-qualified teacher can employ diverse teaching methods and materials, effectively engaging students and fostering a positive learning environment. Akinoso (2011) also underscored the importance of qualified mathematics teachers in enhancing students' interest in the subject. Effective teaching, grounded in diverse instructional strategies, can reduce students' anxiety about mathematics and improve their understanding. Teachers can also use math games and improvised materials to make learning more engaging. Goolsby (2013) highlighted factors such as attitudes toward success, confidence, teacher perceptions, and math anxiety as influential in students' interest in mathematics.

Geometry, defined by Oviawe and Uddin (2020) as the study of the size, shape, and position of 2D and 3D objects, is foundational to fields like engineering and technology (Giannakopoulos, 2017). Tieng and Eu (2014) emphasized the role of geometry in developing analytical and problem-solving skills, and Charles, Cyril, and Gierdien (2020) added that it fosters spatial intuition and deeper mathematical understanding. Despite its importance, the WAEC (2020) report revealed that students often avoid geometry-related questions. Russell (2018) argued that geometry builds crucial thinking skills like logic and deductive reasoning, suggesting it should be taught from primary school through university. However, students' poor performance in geometry is linked to factors such as weak foundational knowledge, lack of interest, and untrained teachers (Tsao, 2018). Dinayusadewi and Agustika (2020) noted challenges in teaching Euclidean geometry, including ineffective pedagogy and a lack of technology use in classrooms. Oviawe and Uddin (2020) emphasized the need for innovative teaching methods aligned with today's students' scientific literacy and technological fluency. Computers have been successfully used in developed countries to address teaching and learning challenges (Yusuf & Afolabi, 2010). Gambari, Ezenwa and Anyanwu (2014) added that Computer-Assisted Instruction can boost students' interest and achievement in mathematics through interactive lessons, animations, and immediate feedback. It can also be applied across various subjects, offering drills, tutorials, games, simulations, and animations to make learning more engaging and effective. Animation, as a form of visual information, can significantly enhance learning. Gambari, Falode, and Adegbenro (2014) distinguished between static and animated illustrations, with the latter showing processes in operation, making learning more interactive. Justin (2020) defined animation as images in motion, highlighting its potential to enliven learning, increase engagement, and enhance students' motivation. According to Gambari, Falode and Adegbenro (2014), animation effectively integrates visual and verbal information, allowing for better retention in long-term memory and improving recall and problem-solving skills. Studies by Westhof, Bergman, and Carroll (2010), as well as Karacop and Doymus (2013), supported the idea that computer animations enhance academic performance, especially in subjects like biology, chemistry, and mathematics. Regarding gender differences in mathematics interest, research findings are mixed. Unodiaku (2013) reported that male students generally outperformed females, while other studies, such as Chikendu (2018) found that female students had a higher interest than their male counterparts. However, Iwendi (2012), Achor, Imoko and Ajai (2010), Ojo (2022) and Njoku and Okigbo (2021) found no significant effect of gender on students' interest scores in geometry and mathematics performance in general. Given the importance of geometry in education and the challenges students face in learning it, particularly in Nigeria, exploring effective teaching methods is

essential. The literature reviewed indicates limited research on the use of 3D animation in teaching mathematics, especially geometry, at the junior secondary school level in the FCT. This study aimed to assess the impact of 3D animation illustrations on students' interest in geometry. The unique features of 3D animation such as visualizing 3D objects, facilitating self-paced learning, providing positive reinforcement, and offering immediate feedback make it a promising tool for enhancing geometry learning.

Statement of the Research Problem

Geometry at the junior secondary school level forms the basis for more advanced mathematical concepts, but it is often challenging for students. In the 2024 WASSCE, while 72.12% of candidates earned credits in five subjects, many struggled with geometry, particularly in understanding theorems, properties of shapes and their practical applications, leading to poor performance in this area (Daily Trust, 2024). The conventional teaching methods for geometry often rely on static 2D illustrations and abstract explanations, which can hinder students' ability to visualize and comprehend complex geometric concepts. Consequently, many students find it difficult to engage with the subject, resulting in low levels of interest. Recent technological advancements have introduced 3D animation as a potential tool to enhance teaching and learning by providing dynamic, interactive visual representations of geometric shapes and principles. However, despite the increasing popularity of 3D animation in education, there is limited empirical evidence regarding its effectiveness in improving students' interest in geometry, particularly at the junior secondary school level in the FCT, Abuja. This study sought to address this gap by investigating the impact of 3D animation illustrations on the interest of junior secondary school students in geometry. By comparing the outcomes of students taught with 3D animation to those taught using conventional methods, this research aimed to determine whether the integration of 3D animation can enhance student engagement in geometry.

Purpose of the study

This study investigated the effect of 3D animation illustrations on interest in geometry concept among upper basic students in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The study therefore, investigated the following objectives:

1. The effect of 3D animation illustration on interest in geometry concepts among upper basic class two students in FCT.
2. The influence of gender on interest in geometry concepts among upper basic class two students taught 3D animations illustration in FCT.

Research questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the difference in the mean rank interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught using conventional teaching method (CTM)
2. What is the difference in the mean rank interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI)

Research Hypotheses

The following null Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level:

H₁: There is no significant difference in the mean rank interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught geometry using conventional teaching method (CTM).

H₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rank interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI)

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test control group design. The population of the study comprised of all the upper basic two (JSS 2) mathematics students, during the 2023/2024 academic session in Abuja. The sample of the study consist of 120 (Male 56 and Female 64) upper basic two (JSS 2) students selected from the target population using multistage sampling technique. Upper basic two (JSS2) was selected using purposive sampling techniques. Two schools were selected out of 20 upper basic two in Gwagwalada area council for this study, which include experimental and control group. The experimental school was selected using purposive sampling techniques due to the fact that the school has solar system, and computer laboratory. The control group school was selected by simple random sampling. A total of 120 students were used on two intact classes, one from each school selected. This was to avoid the disruption of the school programmes. The schools

selected were JSS Phase 3 Gwagwalada assigned to experimental group A and JSS Dukpa assigned to control group B. The experimental group A (JSS Phase 3 Gwagwalada) comprises of 30 male and 40 female out of about 626 students (male 306 and female 320) and the control group B (JSS Dukpa) comprises of 26 male and 24 female out of about 164 students (male 89 and female 75). The data were collected using Geometry Students Interest Inventory Scale (GSIIS). A Geometry Student's Interest inventory scale consisted of 20 items, which was used to measure the influence of teaching method on students' interest in geometry. The students were instructed to place a tick (✓) in the column which best indicate their opinion on a modified 4point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (1), Agree (2) in positive statements to Strongly Disagree (3), Disagree (4) in negative statements. The students' score determined the sum of the weight of the alternatives the student had chosen or selected.

The instrument was then summited alongside the lesson plan to experts in science and environmental education department for face and content validation. In order to assess the reliability of the instrument, the study was subjected to trial testing. Twenty (20) students were drawn randomly from a school not included in the study population. The students were distributed into two classes of 10 students each. It was believed that they had prior knowledge of the subject matter, as they were not exposed to any intervention before the instrument was administered on them. The test was administered in one day and they were retested after a week without creating any awareness of retest. The result obtained were compared for correlation. The Cronbach's Alpha was used to assess the correlation with combined total across both parts as: 0.938. The result of the test indicated a high level of internal consistency and reliability. This implied that the instrument was reliable and stable. The GeoGebra calculator suite was used to displayed the various geometry animations.

Figure 1: GeogebraCalculator Suite

Different lesson plans were prepared on the topics: Solid shapes (cube, cylinder and cone) using the two teaching methods; 3D Animation illustrations and the conventional teaching method. A Mathematics class teacher from each school selected was trained on the procedure as a research assistance. The Geometry Students Interest Inventory Scale (GSIIS) was administered as a pre test before the start of the experiment to determine the initial level of interest students had in geometry, after which the experiment begins. The experimental group was taught geometry using 3D Animation illustrations with laptop and projector since there're no computer available for the students in public schools in FCT and Gwagwalada Area Council in particular. GeoGebra calculator suite was used for animation demonstration. The control group was then taught geometry using conventional teaching method, that's lecture method, after which GSIIS was administered as a post test to find out to what extent students' interest had been influenced by the treatment. These procedures lasted for four (4) weeks.

The data collected were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23. Mean rank was used to answer the research questions while, Mann Whitney U Test was used to test the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. Findings

Research Question 1:

What is the difference in the mean rank of interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught using conventional teaching method (CTM)

Table 2: Mean Rank of Interest Rating Scores of Students Taught Geometry Using 3D Animation Illustrations (DAI) and Those Taught Using Conventional Teaching Method (CTM)

Group	N	Mean Rank
DAI	70	67.76
CTM	50	50.33
Mean rank difference		17.43

Table 2 shows the mean rank of interest rating scores of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught using conventional teaching method (CTM). From the results obtained, students taught geometry using DAI had a mean rank of interest rating score of 67.76 while the students taught geometry using CTM had a mean rank of interest rating score of 50.33. Therefore, the mean rank difference in interest rating scores between students taught geometry using DAI and those taught geometry using CTM is 17.43 in favour of students in DAI group. **Research Question 2:**

What is the difference in the mean rank of interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI)?

Table 3: Mean Rank of Interest Rating of Male and Female Students Taught Geometry Using 3D Animation Illustration (DAI)

Group	Gender	N	Mean Rank
DAI	Female	40	37.75
	Male	30	32.50
Mean rank difference			5.25

Table 3 shows the mean rank of male and female students of 3D animation illustration (DAI) group with respect to their interest rating in geometry. From the results obtained, female students had a mean rank interest rating score of 37.75 while the male students had a mean rank interest rating of 32.50. Therefore, the mean rank difference in interest rating between male and female students in DAI group is 5.25 in favour of female students.

Testing of the Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean rank of interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught geometry using conventional teaching method (CTM).

Table 4: Summary of Mann Whitney Results of Interest Rating of Students Taught Geometry Using 3D Animation Illustrations (DAI) and Those Taught Geometry Using Conventional Teaching Method (CTM)

Group	N	Sum of Ranks	Mann Whitney U	Z	Sig@0.05	Remark
DAI	70	4743.50	1241.50	2.788	0.005	Significant
CTM	50	2516.50				

From Table 4 results of the Mann Whitney nonparametric test shows that the computed sum of ranks scores are 4743.50 and 2516.50 by DAI and CTM groups respectively. The computed Mann Whitney U value of 1241.50 is higher than the 2.788 Z scores. The calculated p-value of 0.005 is less than the 0.05 level of significant. This implies that the mean rank interest development of DAI and CTM groups is significantly different when both groups are taught Geometry. Consequently, hypothesis one which states that there is no significant difference in the mean rank of interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught geometry using conventional teaching method (CTM), is hereby rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rank of interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI).

Table 5: Summary of Mann Whitney Results of Interest Rating of Male and Female Students Taught Geometry Using 3D Animation Illustration (DAI)

Gender	N	Sum of Ranks	Mann Whitney U	Z	Sig@0.05	Remark
Female	40	1510.00	510.000	1.177	0.239	Not Significant
Male	30	975.00				

From Table 5 results of the Mann Whitney nonparametric test shows that the computed sum of ranks scores are 1510.00 and 975.00 by female and male respectively. The computed Mann Whitney U value is 510.000 and the Z score is 2.788. The calculated p-value of 0.239 is greater than the 0.05 level of significant. This implies that the mean rank interest development by female and male students in DAI group is not significantly different when both genders are taught Geometry using DAI. Consequently, hypothesis two which states that there is no significant difference in the mean rank of interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI), is hereby accepted.

Discussion of findings.

Based on the findings of the data analysis, hypothesis one revealed that, there were significant difference in interest rating of students taught geometry using DAI and those taught with CTM in favour of those in DAI group. This finding is in line with the finding of Tepla, Teply and Smejkal (2022) whose study revealed that using 3D models and animations in the teaching process significantly increase students' interest in learning natural sciences. This was supported by Njoku and Okigbo (2021) who reported that, the students taught geometry using GeoTAN instructional software package (GISP) have higher mean interest score in geometry than those taught with conventional method.

Hypothesis two revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean rank of interest rating of male and female students exposed to DAI. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Achor, Imoko and Ajai (2010) who reported that there was no significant difference in the mean interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using games and simulation. This was contrary to the findings of Allahnana, Akande, Vintseh, Alaku and Alaku (2018) and Unodiaku (2013), whose study revealed that male students excel in Mathematics more than their female counterparts. Also, male students have interest in Mathematics more than the female students. Other findings show that female students are better in mathematics interest such as the study of chikendu (2018), reported that instructional computer animation had a significant effect on students' interest in chemistry. Female students performed better than the Male students taught using instructional computer animation.

Conclusion

The use of 3D animation illustration was found to be effective for teaching concepts of geometry in mathematics for junior secondary school students. It enhanced students' interest in geometry. It also gives equal learning opportunities to both male and female students in geometry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Schools and educators should incorporate 3D Animation Illustrations (DAI) into their teaching methods to increase student interest and engagement in geometry. This approach has shown to significantly boost interest compared to conventional methods.
2. Although no significant differences in interest ratings were observed between male and female students using DAI, it's essential to continue monitoring and analyzing these dynamics. Ensuring that teaching methods cater effectively to all genders could help maintain equitable learning outcomes.

References

- Achor, E. E., Imoko, I. B. & Ajai, T. J. (2010) Sex Differentials in Students' Achievement and Interest in Geometry Using Games and Simulations Technique. *Electronic Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*. 4 (1), 1-10.
- Akinoso, S. O. (2011). Correlates of some factors affecting students' achievement in secondary school mathematics in Osun State. *International journal of education, science, mathematics and environmental studies (IJESMES)*, 3(10), 83-95.

- Allahnana, K. M., Akande, M. T., Vintseh, I. M. U., Alaku, E. A., & Alaku, E. M. (2018). Assessment of gender and interest in mathematics achievement in Keffi Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Operational Research in Management, Social Science and Education*, 4(1).
- Anigbo, L. C. (2016). Factors affecting students' interest in mathematics in secondary schools in Enugu state. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 2(1) 22- 28. Retrieved from <https://iuardpub.org/get/IJEE/VOL.%202%20NO./FACTORS%20AFFECTING.pd>
- Chikendu, R. E. October (2018). Effects of instructional computer animation on secondary school students' achievement and interest in chemistry in Awka Educational Zone (Doctoral thesis, Nnamdi Azikiwe University). https://phddissertations.unizik.edu.ng/repos/81382622550_156254635296.pdf
- Daily Trust. (2024), 503,275 students fail English, Maths in 2024 WASSCE. Retrieved from <https://dailytrust.com/503275students-fail-english-maths-in-2024-wassce>.
- Dinayusadewi, N. P., & Agustika, G. N. S. (2020). Development Of Augmented Reality Application As A Mathematics Learning Media In Elementary School Geometry Materials. *Journal of Education Technology*, 4(2), 204-210.
- FCT Education Secretary- Public Junior Secondary Schools List. 2022 https://fctemis.org/list_public_jss_school FCTUBEB – All JSS enrollments statistics. Updated 25-03-2023 <https://www.fctubeb.gov.ng/eort-sheets-stats> FRN (2014). *National policy on education* (6th edition). Federal Republic of Nigeria. Lagos: NERDC.
- Gambari, A.I., Falode, C.O. & Adegbenro, D (2014). Effectiveness of computer animation and geometrical instructional model on mathematics achievement and retention among junior secondary school students. Science Education Department Federal University of Technology, Minna. *European Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 2(2), 127-146.
- Gambari, A. I., Ezenwa, I. V. & Anyanwu, C. R. (2014) study comparative effects of two modes of computer assisted instructional Package on solid geometry achievement. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 5(2), 110-120.
- Giannakopoulos, A. (2017) An Alternative Way of Solving Geometry Riders in Grade 12: Back Toto Synthesis and Analysis, *Proceedings of the 23rd Annual National Congress of the Association for Mathematics Education of South Africa*, 2, 3–7. Port Elizabeth.
- Gimba, R. W. & Agwagah, U. N. V. (2012). Importance of Mathematics to Science and Technology. *Journal of Science, Technology, Mathematics and Education (JOSTMED)*. 8(2) 251-259.
- Goolsby, L. (2013) *School interest*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- Hom, E. J., & Gordon, J. (2021). What is Mathematics? Live Science. Retrieved from <https://www.livescience.com/38936mathematics.html>
- Idigo, E. C. (2010) Effective method of retaining students' interest in mathematics in secondary schools in Enugu East local government area of Enugu State, Unpublished UG Thesis, Institute of Ecumenical Education, Thinkers Corner, Enugu, in Affiliation with (ESUT), Enugu.
- Iwendi, B. C. (2012). Effect of gender and age on the mathematics achievement of secondary school students in Minna metropolis, Nigeria. *JOSMED*. 9(1). 215-223.
- Justin, B. 24th August (2020). What is 3D Animation. <https://infographicworld.com/what-is-3d-animation>
- Karacop, A. & Doymus, K. (2013). Effects of jigsaw cooperative learning and animation techniques on students' understanding of chemical bonding and their conceptions of the particulate nature of matter. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 22(2), 186-203.
- Njoku, C. & Okigbo, E. C. (2021). Effect of GeoTAN instructional software package on secondary school students' interest in geometry. *African Journal of Science, Technology & Mathematics Education (AJSTME)*, 6(1), 185-194. www.ajstme.com.ng
- Ojo, S.G (2022). Effects of animated instructional packages on achievement and interest of junior secondary school student in algebra. National Mathematical Centre, Abuja, Nigeria. *Mathematics Teaching Research Journal Spring*, 14(1), 99-113.
- Oviawe, I.J. & Uddin O.S.P (2020) Improving Students Academic Achievement and Interest in Geometry Through AudioVisual Resources as Instructional Strategies. Department of Vocational and Technical Education, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Alternative Education Studies*. 5(1), 120-133.
- Russell D., (2018). What is Geometry. Retrieved from <https://www.thoughtco.com>.
- Safo, A. D., Ezenwa, V. I., & Wushishi, D. I. (2013). Effects of Computer Assisted Instructional Package on Junior Secondary School Students' Achievement and Retention in Geometry in Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 2(5), 69-74.
- Smith C. R., C. Julie, F. Gierdien. (2020) The integration of semiotic resources and modalities in the teaching of geometry in a grade 9 class in a South African high school: The four cases of congruency. *South African Journal of Education*, 40(2), 1-13. Tieng, P. G. & Eu, L. K. (2014). Improving students' Van Hiele Level of geometric thinking using geometer's sketchpad. *Malaysian online journal of educational technology*, 2(3), 20-31.
- Tsao, Y. L. (2018). The effect of constructivist instructional-based mathematics course on the attitude toward Geometry of preservice. *US-China Education Review*, 8(1), 1-10.
- Vernadakis N., Avgerinos A., Tsitskari E. and Zachopoulou E. 21st May (2014), The Use of Computer Assisted Instruction in Preschool Education: Making Teaching Meaningful. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 33(2), 99-104.

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Westhoff, B. W., Bergman, D. & Carroll, J. (2010). The effects of computer animations on high school students' performance and engagement in biology. *Proceedings of the 6th Annual GRASP Symposium*, 197-198. Wichita State University.

Yusuf, M. O., & Afolabi, A. O. (2010). Effects of computer-assisted instruction (CAI) on secondary school students' performance in biology. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 9(1), 62–69. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ875764>

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Effect of Cognitive-Behavioral-Therapy on Attention-Deficit-Disorder among Senior Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper reports the result of a study undertaken to investigate the effect of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) on attention deficit disorder among senior secondary students in Katsina state, Nigeria. The study, which was conducted in Katsina zonal education quality assurance of Katsina state, has two specific objectives, corresponding research questions and null hypotheses, respectively. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design, specifically pretest, posttest nonequivalent control groups design. Population of the study consists of 458 attention deficit disorder (212 males and 246 females) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina state, a sample of 70 students (33 males and 37 females) were selected from the target population using random and purposive sampling techniques, respectively. The Copeland Attention Deficit Checklist (CADC) adapted from Edna D. Copeland (1987) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by experts and obtain 0.83 reliability coefficient using Cronbach's Alpha. The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions Independent Samples t-test and ANCOVA were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that CBT is effective in reducing attention deficit disorder among the students exposed to the therapy irrespective of gender difference. Based on the findings it was concluded that CBT is effective in reducing attention deficit disorder among the students exposed to the therapy irrespective of gender difference. Consequently, it was recommended that More studies should be conducted to explore the long-term effects of cognitive behavioral therapy on attention deficit disorder in different educational settings and Further research is necessary to elucidate the differential effectiveness of cognitive behavioral therapy in reducing attention deficit disorder symptoms in males and females.

Keywords: Cognitive Behavioral Therapy and Attention Deficit Disorder

Introduction

Education has a significant effect on human societies as it is the vehicle for socialization and social stratification. It is also the means by which the young ones are prepared for adult roles that will enable them to function effectively and efficiently in their living world. No society will function without adequate and proper education. According to Robert and John (2014), the progress of any nation is very much dependent on the level education of its citizens. It is perhaps in realization of this it is one of the of the philosophies of National Policy of Education (NPE) (2014) that, the duty of the states is to provide education to the citizens. Nowadays, there has been an increasing concern in the educational sector on how to ensure that students learn optimally at school so as to achieve academic excellence in their present and future lives. In Nigeria, there has been nationwide cry out on the fallen standard of education Akpan (2000). This can be attributed to the negative attitude being exhibited by the students such as inability of the students to pay attention in the classroom (Attention deficit). Some students have attention deficit disorder whereby many teachers could not use appropriate methods of handling the students. According to Aaron Beck (1967), Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) can be seen as an umbrella term generally used to refer to group of related therapies that have theoretical basis in behavior learning and cognitive psychology which are derived from scientifically proven

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theoretical models. Mindfulness based cognitive behavioral therapy, dialectical behavioral therapy, rational emotive behavioral therapy, acceptance and commitment behavioral therapy are expected or assumed to be the treatments of choice for various behavioral problems such as mood disorders, anxiety disorders, personality disorders, eating disorders, substance abuse disorders, and psychotic disorders in which attention deficit disorder is included.

Attention deficit disorder also known as Attention deficit (hyperactivity disorder) is a neuro developmental disorder, which many recognize as a childhood disorder (Rosler, 2010). However, a review of the literature as well as longitudinal studies of individuals with Attention deficit (hyperactivity disorder) reveals that symptoms persist from early childhood to adulthood (faraone, 2006; Davidson 2008). Many children with attention deficit disorder show signs of the disorder before they reach school age. But it is in school, when they are having trouble meeting expectations for kids in their grades that most are referred for diagnosis. A child who cannot pay attention at home, a child who seem to be absent minded to parents' command, a child who cannot sit still in the classroom, who blow out answers in class without raising his hands, who does not finish homework, who seems to be day dreaming when teachers give instructions are well known symptoms of attention deficit disorder. However, these are also behaviors that can be a result of other factors, from anxiety to trauma.

It was observed by the researcher that the causes of attention deficit among secondary students of Katsina zone can be due to chronic anxiety, family situation, bullying, frustration due to dyslexia and unsatisfied need. That is why it is important for the teachers especially psychology teachers to be aware of what attention deficit disorder looks like and how it influences children's behaviors and how teachers can help them succeed in school and other parts of their lives. This research is therefore intended to experiment the subject in order to observe whether the use of dialectical behavioral therapy is effective in aggression symptoms among secondary school students in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem

Attention deficit disorder also known as Attention deficit (hyperactivity disorder) is a neuro developmental disorder, which many recognize as a childhood disorder (Rosler, 2010). However, a review of the literature as well as longitudinal studies of individuals with Attention deficit (hyperactivity disorder) reveals that symptoms persist from early childhood to adulthood (faraone, 2006; Davidson 2008). Many children with attention deficit disorder show signs of the disorder before they reach school age. But it is in school, when they are having trouble meeting expectations for kids in their grades that most are referred for diagnosis. A child who cannot pay attention at home, a child who seem to be absent minded to parents' command, a child who cannot sit still in the classroom, who blow out answers in class without raising his hands, who does not finish homework, who seems to be day dreaming when teachers give instructions are well known symptoms of attention deficit disorder. However, these are also behaviors that can be a result of other factors, from anxiety to trauma. It was observed by the researcher that the causes of attention deficit among secondary students of Katsina zone can be due to chronic anxiety, family situation, bullying, frustration due to dyslexia and unsatisfied need. That is why it is important for the teachers especially psychology teachers. to be aware of what attention deficit disorder looks like and how it influences children's behaviors and how teachers can help them succeed in school and other parts of their lives.

Attention deficit is very common among student's especially senior secondary students which has been affecting their school outcomes negatively. This cause worries among teachers, parents and government. Students makes careless mistakes in school work, over looks details, get easily distracted, has difficulty in following instructions, doesn't seem to be listening when spoken to directly, has trouble organizing tasks, often fails to finish work in school or chores in classroom, often avoid or resist tasks that require sustained mental effort and often losses homework and assignments. This made the teacher's think of to make students attentive in the classroom. What function the school has to play in changing their students to desired direction. Over the years, educators and psychologist have opposed the use of corporal punishment, permanent suspension and use of local therapies (example: kneeling down, canning, standing on chair and raising one leg, kneeling and facing the wall, picking a pin, carrying stones, extra work around the school, time-out or being sent out of class, detention etc.) and replace them with more sublime strategies for curbing attention deficit disorder. They believe that, harsh and extreme strategies increase attention deficit disorder rather than subduing it. Also, educators and psychologist have opposed the use of punishment and negative reinforcement. They suggest the use of more suitable strategies in controlling attention deficit. They believe that punishment and negative reinforcement increase the problem rather than eliminating it. Nowadays, Cognitive behavioral therapy (which include; mindfulness based, dialectical, rational emotive, acceptance & commitment behavioral therapy) are the most extensively researched psychotherapeutic modalities which is being used in various behavior disorders such as, dysfunctional emotions, mood disorders, behavior disorders, anxiety disorders. This gives more advantage in reducing or even eliminating such undesirable behavior than punishment and negative reinforcement used before.

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Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to investigate the effect of CBT (CBT) on attention deficit disorder among Senior Secondary School Students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State. The following specific objectives are set to:

1. investigate the difference between the mean attention deficit disorder scores of students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT among senior secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State,
2. find out the difference between the mean scores of male and female student's attention deficit disorder when exposed to CBT among senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions are presented to guide the study:

1. What is the difference between the mean attention deficit disorder scores of students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT among senior secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State?
2. What is the difference between the mean score of male and female student's attention deficit disorder when exposed to CBT among senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State?

Hypotheses

The following hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean attention deficit disorder scores of students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT among senior secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean score of male and female student's attention deficit disorder when exposed to CBT among senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State.

Methodology

The research adopted the quasi-experimental design of the pretest posttest nonequivalent control groups type. Both experimental group and control group were given the same pretest. The experimental group were treated with dialectical CBT for a period of four weeks while the control group were not treated. After four weeks all groups were given the same posttest. The study was undertaken in Katsina state in the northern part of Nigeria. The study was undertaken in Katsina state zonal quality assurance (latitudes 11°07'49N and 13°22'57N, longitudes of 6°52'03E and 9°9'02E) including three local government Areas (i.e Jibia, Kaita, and Katsina) in the northern part of Nigeria. At the time of the study there are 20 public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state, having population of 458 attention deficit disorder (212 males and 246 females) students, a sample of 70 attention deficit disorder (33 males and 37 females) were selected using random and purposive sampling techniques.

Two instruments, Attention deficit identification questionnaire and Adapted Copeland Attention Deficit Checklist (CADC). Attention deficit identification questionnaire which is used to identify students with attention deficit disorder is a SNAP-IV questionnaire developed by Swanson, Nolan and Pelham in 1992. It contains 26 questions divided into three subsets (inattention, hyperactivity/impulsivity and opposition/defiance) which is scored using a rating scale 0 to 3 (not at all=0, just a little=1, quite a bit=2 and very much=3). Adapted Copeland Attention Deficit Checklist (CADC) is a 54 items checklist containing information related to adolescent psycho/behavioral status which was used as the basis for categorizing the level of Attention deficit disorder Scores between 35-49% suggest mild to moderate difficulties, Scores between 50-69% suggest moderate to severe difficulties. Scores above 70% suggest major. Adapted Copeland Attention Deficit Checklist (CADC) was used as pretest and posttest. The two instruments were validated by experts and the reliability was established using Cronbach's Alpha for an internal consistency of the items. The reliability coefficient of the SNAP-IV obtained a score of 0.88 while the reliability coefficient of the CADC obtained a score of 0.83. The data collection process began with the pretest administration to both experimental and control groups. This was to establish equivalence in performance between the groups before treatment. At the completion of the treatment, the posttest was administered to measure the group's performance. Data analyses of the responses collected were undertaken using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, standard error of mean and mean differences was employed to answer research questions while t-test and ANCOVA were the inferential statistics used to test the hypotheses.

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Presentation of Results

Attention deficit disorder of the senior secondary students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT

Research question 1

What is the difference between the mean attention deficit disorder scores of students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT among senior secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State?

Table 1.

Mean, standard deviation and standard error of the mean of experimental and control groups students' attention deficit disorder (ADD) scores

Variable	Group	N	M	SD	SEM	MD
ADD	Experimental	37	100.00	6.324	1.043	- 11.67
	Control	33	111.67	4.852	.845	

Table 4.1 shows that the difference between the mean score of attention deficit of students exposed to CBT (M = 100.00, SD = 6.324) and those not exposed to CBT (M = 111.67, SD = 4.852) among the senior secondary school students was -11.67 in favor the students exposed to CBT.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean attention deficit disorder scores of students exposed to CBT and those not exposed to CBT among senior secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State.

Table 2.

Summary of ANCOVA statistics on the mean scores of attention deficit of students in the experimental and control group

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2992.068 ^a	2	1496.034	63.302	.000	.654
Intercept	137.332	1	137.332	5.811	.019	.080
Pretest ADD	617.901	1	617.901	26.145	.000	.281
Group	2473.096	1	2473.096	104.644	.000	.610
Error	1583.432	67	23.633			
Total	783693.000	70				
Corrected Total	4575.500	69				

a. R Squared = .654 (Adjusted R Squared = .644)

The table shows that the difference between the mean scores of the experimental (i.e., students with ADD exposed to CBT) (M = 100.00, SD = 6.324) and control (i.e., students with ADD not exposed to CBT) (M = 111.67, SD = 4.852) groups is significant, (F(1, 69)=104.644, p < .05, partial eta square = .610). The partial eta squared for the group variable indicates that approximately 61.0% of the variance in post-test attention deficit scores was explained by the group differences. Given these findings, the null hypothesis is thus rejected.

Attention deficit disorder scores of the male and female senior secondary students exposed to CBT

Research question 2

What is the difference between the mean score of male and female student's attention deficit disorder when exposed to CBT among senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State?

Table 3.

Mean, Standard Deviations and Standard Error of the Mean of Attention Deficit Disorder Scores of the Experimental Group based on Gender

Variable	Gender	N	M	SD	SEM	MD
ADD	Male	18	100.22	5.600	1.320	0.43
	Female	19	99.79	7.123	1.634	

Table 4.2 shows that the difference between the mean ADD scores of the male (M = 100.22, SD = 5.600) and female (M = 99.79, SD = 7.123) students exposed to cognitive behavioral therapy among senior secondary school students is 0.43 in favor the female students.

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Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean score of male and female student’s attention deficit disorder when exposed to CBT among senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education, Katsina State.

Table 4.

Summary of t-test statistics on the differences between the male and female students attention deficit score in the experimental group

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEM	Df	T	P	Decision
ADD	Male	32	105.03	7.660	1.334	68	-0.439	.922	H ₀₂ Retained
Posttest	Female	38	105.89	8.611	1.397				

The table shows that differences between the ADD scores of the male (M =105.03, SD = 7.660) and female (M=105.89, SD =8.611) students in the experimental group (i.e., students with ADD exposed to CBT) is not significant, (t(68) = -0.439 , p = .922). Consequently, H₀₂ is retained.

Discussion of Findings

Concerning the effect of cognitive behavioral therapy in reducing attention deficit disorder among students, the finding of the study reveals that cognitive behavioral therapy is effective in reducing attention deficit disorder. This result is in agreement with the finding of Hoffman et al. (2012) who emphasized that Cognitive behavioral therapy is effective for disorders involving attention deficit disorder. This resonates with the current study's findings, where students in the experimental group displayed lower Attention deficit scores post-treatment compared to the control group. Similarly, Hollon and Beck (2016) affirmed that Cognitive behavioral therapy’s focus on altering cognitive distortions aids in improving attention and executive functioning, suggesting that the intervention directly addresses deficits in attention, which aligns with the results of this study. Moreover, Sahil Ahmad (2018) in his review found that Cognitive behavioral therapy’s effect on attention deficit disorder.

Also, the findings contradict that of, Faraone and Biederman mentioned in the review of Muller et al (2018) which found that Cognitive behavioral therapy is ineffective in managing attention deficit hyperactivity disorder /attention deficit disorder in children and adolescents, advocating for a combined approach with medication. While the current study demonstrates that Cognitive behavioral therapy significantly reduced attention deficit disorder symptoms, the long-term sustainability of these effects in the absence of medication could warrant further investigation. This contrast highlights the complexity of managing attention deficit disorder, suggesting that while Cognitive behavioral therapy is effective, a multi-modal treatment might be necessary for some cases.

Concerning the effect of cognitive behavioral therapy in reducing attention deficit disorder in both male and female students, the finding of the study reveals that cognitive behavioral therapy is effective in reducing attention deficit disorder in both male and female students. The finding contradicts with that of Hasson and Fine (2012) which noted that boys with attention deficit disorder benefit more from Cognitive behavioral therapy, given their tendency toward externalizing behaviors. This contrast may suggest that, while gender-specific differences in behavior exist, the structure of Cognitive behavioral therapy is robust enough to address these differences effectively. Also, the findings contradict that of Ruggiero et al. (2018) found that female students benefit more from Cognitive behavioral therapy’s focus on emotional regulation, especially given that girls exhibit internalizing behaviors, such as anxiety or depression, that can accompany attention deficit disorder or aggression. While the current study found no significant gender differences, the broader literature suggests that Cognitive behavioral therapy may address different aspects of behavior in males and females, though the overall effectiveness remains consistent across genders.

Conclusion

The study concluded that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) is an effective intervention for reducing attention deficit disorder (ADD) among senior secondary school students in Katsina State. The results demonstrated a significant improvement in students’ ability to manage their attention disorder symptoms after exposure to Cognitive Behavioral Therapy. Notably, all genders showed a more substantial reduction in attention deficit disorder symptoms. Furthermore, the study highlighted that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy is a valuable tool for addressing psychological challenges in the educational context. Its efficacy in modifying negative thought patterns and promoting emotional regulation underscores its importance as a preventive and rehabilitative strategy for behavioral disorders like attention deficit disorder. The findings suggest that

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incorporating Cognitive Behavioral Therapy into student support services and classroom management strategies could enhance the overall learning environment and improve academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. More studies should be conducted to explore the long-term effects of cognitive behavioral therapy on attention deficit disorder in different educational settings.
2. Further research is necessary to elucidate the differential effectiveness of cognitive behavioral therapy in reducing attention deficit disorder symptoms in males and females.

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References

- Akpan, C.P (2000). Financing university education in a depressed economy. *Nigerian education Journal*, 2 (22), 59-66.
- Beck A.T. (1967). Thinking and depression: diosyncratic content and cognitive distortions. *Archieves of general psychiatry*, 9(4), 324-333.
- Faraone (2006) & M A Davidson (2008) *journal of attention Disorders- journals.sagesub.com* ,11(2), 19-21
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National Policy on Education*. Abuja: NERDC.
- Hasson, R., & Fine, J.G. (2012). Gender differences among children with ADHD on continuous performance tests (Abstract). *Journal of Attention Disorders*, 16(3), 190-198
- Hollon S.D, Beck A.T, (2016),” *Cognitive and cognitive behavioral therapies*”. In: Lambert MJ, editor. *Bergin and Garfield's handbook of psychotherapy and behavior change*. 5th ed. New York: Wiley; 200
- Russell Barkely's (1998) *Psychological Status*. American: Psychological Society Press
- Sahil Ahmad (2018),“ *Effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy in Children affected by Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder: A Meta-Analysis*”. *International journal of Research Studies in Medical and Health Sciences*, 3(7): 10-23.

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Effect of Cooperative Learning Strategy on Error Types Committed in Algebra Among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed effects of cooperative learning strategy on error types committed in algebra among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria. Mixed method research design was adopted for the study. Thus, descriptive survey research design was employed to identify errors which led to the development of the instrument; and the quasi-experimental pretest, posttest control group design to establish the cause-and-effect between variables of the study. Population of the study consists of all senior secondary school mathematics students in Kano state. The instruments adapted from West African Examination Council (WAEC) past question papers were validated for data collection with Error Identification Test (EIT) and Algebra Performance Test (APT) with reliability coefficients of 0.68 and 0.74 respectively using Cronbach alpha reliability teste. While the experimental group was exposed to cooperative learning instructional treatment, the control group were exposed to traditional method. Three null hypotheses guided the study. Chi square (χ^2) and t-test statistics were used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The major findings of this study revealed senior secondary school students in Kano state do commit procedural, factual, conceptual and comprehension errors in algebraic and the CLIS is gender fair in remediating the problems. On the basis of these, it was concluded that CLIS is an effective tool for remediating students' errors in algebra. It was recommended that the CLIS should be encouraged in place of the conventional lecture method in teaching algebraic concepts at the senior secondary school level.

Keywords: Algebra, Cooperative Learning, Error, Frequency, Mathematics

Introduction

Mathematics is the branch of science that studies numbers, forms and their relationships. It is the science and study of quality, structure, space, and change that seeks out patterns, formulate new conjectures which are opinions based on incomplete evidence; and establish truth by rigorous deduction from appropriately chosen axioms (widely accepted opinion) and definitions. It is a pivot in which other sciences revolve and serves as a means of sharpening man's reasoning ability and developing personality (Agwagah, 2001). Mathematics is a vast and diverse field that encompasses various branches, each with its own unique focus and applications. These branches of mathematics include pure mathematics, applied mathematics, interdisciplinary mathematics among others. In fact, the branches are inexhaustible and there may be overlap between them. Being a scholarly domain, mathematicians build on each other's work and behave in ways that push the discipline forward. This progress contributes to scientific breakthroughs. However, algebra, which is the focus of this study according to Tarr & Knith, (2013) is a branch of mathematics that uses letters to represent numbers. An algebraic expression is made up of three things: numbers, variables (letters) and operations such as $-$ or $+$. These may, in turn, be connected with equality sign to form algebraic statements such as $3y = 12$, $2y + 4x = 10$, $7y - 4 = 3x$ (Keller, 2007). This is the bone of contention in the teaching of mathematics in Nigerian secondary schools.

Mathematics plays a vital role in the learning and understanding of the principles applied to other sciences (Clements, 2014). For instance, mathematics provides the language and tools to measure and understand scientific concepts just as technology applies scientific and mathematical principles to develop useful tools and systems. In fact, science study of the natural world relies on mathematics. In other words, mathematics helps achieve a deeper understanding of scientific concepts, providing ways to quantify and explain scientific relationships; in the field of physics, mathematics is used to describe and model the behavior of matter and energy; in chemistry, it is used to analyze chemical reactions and predict the properties of different substances; while in computer science, it is used to develop algorithms (set of rules) and write code that powers our digital world (Wiles 2007). That is how vast and important mathematics is to the new world. Thus, concept formation, abstraction, generalization, theory-building and problem solving which are basic mathematical activities are also integral part of the problem-solving process.

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However, teaching of mathematics to young people in secondary schools has been very tiring, cumbersome and uninteresting because of the methods used to impart such exquisite knowledge. Traditionally, the lecture method was the dominating approach that has been used over the years to teach mathematics to school children. This, Okpala & Anene (2009) observed has been highly traditional and teacher-centered; while Odili (2005) sees it as a major problem that militates against students understanding of mathematics and mathematical concepts in schools, thereby contributing to poor performance output in internal and external examinations. The traditional lecture method, which had hitherto been used over decades, is concerned with the teacher being the controller of the learning environment. Power and responsibility were held by the teacher and they play the role of instructor (lecture) and decision maker on curriculum content. According to Inah (2014), the lecture method allows the teacher to deliver large amount of information in a short time with the capacity for routine repeatability for new groups of students.

In furtherance of this general assertion, the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2008) advocates teaching method that is activity-oriented, expository and experimental. If the citizens of the country will compete favourably with their counterparts in this 21st century global village of advanced science, technology and mathematics, the teaching and learning of mathematics at the secondary school level should be repositioned because it is another foundation upon which other levels of education are built. In the light of the above, it is important to lay solid foundation in mathematics by using activity-oriented methods which are learner-centered to teach the subject. A number of activity-oriented strategies, according to Lawal (2009) have been advocated for curriculum designers and science educators to help improve on the failure rate in mathematics among secondary school students. One of the activity-based strategies is the cooperative learning instructional strategy, described by Eniayeju (2010) as a discovery method in which small groups are used. It is generally understood to be learning which takes place in an environment where students work collaboratively in small groups by sharing ideas while working on a given task. This learning strategy, according to Slaven (2013) allows students in small groups to communicate with each other and it is believed that dialogue aids learning and goal-oriented (Wiles 2007). The characteristics among others, are positive interdependence, face-to-face interaction, social skills, shared leadership, collaborative problem solving, mutual support and teacher facilitation.

In order to effectively implement the cooperative learning in the classroom, the following processes stages, according to Olanrewaju (2012), must be succinctly established: i. state clear goals and expectations of the outcome of topics being taught; ii. train students in cooperative learning skills; iii. choose the suitable cooperative learning strategy to be employed; iv. monitor and provide appropriate feedback as the class progresses; v. encourages student reflection and self-assessment. By incorporating cooperative learning into teaching practices, the teachers can create supportive and inclusive learning environment that promotes academic achievement, social skills and team work. In this way, errors committed by students will be brought to the barest minimum. This strategy involves dividing the class into small groups of 3-5 pupils of varying ability such that it encourages group members to seek assistance from each other; and in which every member accepts responsibility for the entire team (Gowers, 2002). However, the cooperative learning session must commence with students given practice on cooperative work; problems that elicits cooperation. (Sarah & Cassidy, 2006; Wendy, 2005). Students are encouraged to use one activity sheet, work at their own pace with no time constraint; however, when a team concludes a task another activity sheet is released to them. They are encouraged to pose questions to members, check and clarify thoughts, agree and conclude on the response to record on the activity sheet. The main task of the teacher is to constantly remind the group members of helping their group to succeed through dialogue, attentiveness and making inputs to discussion.

Despite the efforts put in by mathematics teachers in ensuring the right concepts are taught, no matter the methodology hiccups, errors committed in mathematics have become rampart among secondary school students in Kano state schools (Odili, 2005). These errors or mistakes, as they are popularly called, are used interchangeably because they stand for incorrect concepts, ideas of misguided information, but differ in their levels of incorrectness. According to Salman, (2004), a mistake has the characteristics of being corrected when challenged, but an error does not possess such characteristics. Topson (1999) posited that error in mathematics context is the difference between the value of an appropriation or estimation and the true value. He stressed further that error may or may not have a plus (+) or minus (-) sign attached to indicate whether a number is too big or too small. Error analysis, therefore, is a method commonly used to identify the causes of students' mistakes by reviewing the students' work and then look out for patterns of misunderstanding. Students' errors may be caused by semantic differences between mathematical language and natural language by individual differences in spatial abilities, by deficiencies in mastery of prerequisites, by incorrect association of failure of cognitive control, and by the application of irrelevant strategies or rules (Steve, 2002). It is in recognition of the foregoing that this study assessed the effects of cooperative learning strategy in remedying the frequency of, and error types committed in algebra by secondary school students in Kano state.

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Statement of the Research Problem

Algebra is a fundamental subject in mathematics, but students often struggle with it due to various errors and misconceptions. Despite the importance of algebra, research has shown that students make frequent errors particularly in areas as equation solving, graphing and functional operations (Cohen & Lotan, 2014). However, cooperative learning has been shown to be an effective instructional strategy in promoting students understanding. Recognizing this, the study aims to investigate the effectiveness of cooperative learning in rectifying and types of errors in algebra. Errors in algebra can be persistent and difficult to correct, particularly when students are taught with the traditional method. Cooperative learning offers a promising alternative, as it allows students to work together, share ideas, and learn from one another. Although there is paucity of research on the effectiveness of cooperative learning in reducing the frequency and types of errors in algebra (Tarr & Knuth, 2013). This study aims to address this gap by investigating the impact of cooperative learning on algebra errors. Teachers often struggle to identify and address errors in algebra, particularly in large and diverse classrooms. Cooperative learning has been shown to promote student engagement and motivation (Cohen & Lotan, 2014), but its potential to support teachers in identifying and addressing errors is not well-explored. This study, therefore, assessed effects of cooperative learning strategy on error types committed in algebra among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To identify the frequency of error types committed while solving algebraic problems among senior secondary school students in Kano State
2. To determine if there is difference in the types of errors committed while solving algebraic problems between male and Female senior secondary school students in Kano State
3. To determine the impact of cooperative learning strategy on errors committed while solving algebra among senior secondary school students in Kano State

Research Questions

1. What are the frequency of error types committed while solving algebraic problems among senior secondary school students in Kano State?
2. What is the difference in mean scores in the types of errors committed while solving algebraic problems between male and Female senior secondary school students in Kano State?
3. What are the impacts of cooperative learning strategy on errors committed while solving algebra among senior secondary school students in Kano State?

Hypotheses

This study tested the following hypotheses at $p \leq 0.05$

- H₀₁. There are no significant differences in frequency of error types committed while solving algebraic problems among senior secondary school students in Kano State
- H₀₂. There is no significant difference between male and female students while solving algebraic problems in Kano State
- H₀₃. There is no significant impact of cooperative learning strategy on errors committed while solving algebra among senior secondary school students in Kano State

Methodology

This study assessed effects of cooperative learning strategy on error types committed in algebra among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria. The mixed method research design adopted for the study included descriptive survey research design to identify errors which led to the development of the instrument; and the quasi-experimental pretest, posttest control group design to establish the cause-and-effect between variables of the study. Population of the study consisted of all senior secondary school mathematics students in Kano state; and sample was taken from the six (6) schools that met the two conditions of availability of qualified mathematics teachers and infrastructural facilities; hence, exposed to error identification test (EIT). Based on this test, only two (N=2) coeducational that were not significantly different in the EIT were used as samples for the study. This instrument, adapted from the West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) question papers (2007 – 2011) and used to identify errors committed by students in solving algebraic problems, comprised of seventeen (17) test items of short essay questions spread across the senior secondary school syllabus. The scripts were marked and errors recorded accordingly. In each

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of the sampled schools, the subjects were divided into experimental and control groups. The former was exposed to the cooperative learning strategy adapted from Kagan's (1994) NHT instructional model while the latter group was handled by their regular classroom teacher using the lecture method. The teaching lasted for four (4) weeks after which the Algebraic Performance Test (APT) was administered on the subjects. Algebraic Performance Test (APT) used for this study was adapted from the WAEC past question papers (2007 – 2011) administered in pre-test and post-test forms, comprised of thirty (30) multiple choice items with four (4) options A-D, and seven (7) short essay questions. The EIT and APT were administered to the subjects as pretest and post-test to the two groups. The scripts for both pretest and post-test were marked based on the marking scheme and errors committed were recorded accordingly. Data collected were recorded and analyzed using the descriptive and inferential statistics. All hypothesis were deemed significant at $P \geq 0.05$ alpha level.

Presentation of Results

The data collected from tests carried out on EIT and APT employed in this study were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentages, mean, standard deviation) and presented in line with the research questions and succinctly described; while the inferential statistics of t-test and Chi square were used to test the null hypotheses raised for the study. All hypotheses are deemed significant at 0.05 alpha level as presented in tables below:

Research Question 1:

1. What are the frequency of error types committed while solving algebraic problems among senior secondary school students in Kano State?

Table 1

Error Types	Pre-Test		Experimental		Post test		Experimental	
	Control		Freq	%	Control		Freq	%
	Freq	%			Freq	%		
Procedural	32	13.0	34	15.1	31	13.7	28	21.3
Factual	24	9.8	14	6.2	23	10.2	9	6.87
Conceptual	40	16.3	37	16.4	33	14.6	10	7.63
Wrong operation	25	10.2	30	13.3	24	10.6	28	21.37
Defective algorithm	34	13.8	28	12.4	34	15.0	20	15.27
Misdirection	44	17.9	49	21.8	43	19.0	29	22.14
Comprehension	47	19.1	34	15.1	37	16.4	7	5.37
Total	246	100.0	226	100.0	226	100.0	131	100.0

Summary of frequency of error types committed by students in algebra

Source: Field Survey (2024)

A careful study of Table 1 above revealed the frequencies and percentages of error types committed by the students in the sampled schools before and after the experiment. The pre-test results showed that Comprehension (47;19.1%) and Misdirection (49;21.8%) were the most frequently committed errors in the control and experimental groups respectively while the post-test values recorded Misdirection (43;19.0% and 29; 22.14%) in both the control and experimental groups respectively. Although it was observed that variability in frequency of types of errors exist in both groups, it was higher in control (246; 226) than in experimental (226; 131) groups. These observations provided solutions to the first research question which sought to identify the frequency of error types committed by secondary school students in solving algebraic problems in the sampled schools. However, in order to test whether these observed frequencies are significant, the inferential statistics of Chi square was employed for analysis and the results are presented in Table 2.

Hypothesis Testing

Ho₁. There are no significant differences in frequency of error types committed while solving algebraic problems among senior secondary school students in Kano State

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Table 2

Summary of Chi square analysis on frequency of error types committed by control and experimental groups in senior secondary school algebra.

Error Types	Groups		Total
	Control	Experimental	
Procedural	32(34.40)	34(31.60)	66
Factual	24(19.81)	14(18.19)	38
Conceptual	40(40.13)	37(36.87)	77
Wrong operation	25(28.67)	30(26.33)	55
Defective algorithm	34(32.31)	28(29.69)	62
Misdirection	44(48.47)	49(44.53)	93
Comprehension	47(42.22)	34(38.78)	81
Total	246	226	472

$\chi^2_{(6)} = 5.36 < 0.05$ Not Significant Source: SPSS V10 Data Analysis software (2024)

The result presented in Table 2 revealed result of the chi square of observed value obtained from the control and experimental groups. Upon analysis, obtained chi square of 5.36 was less than the critical value ($\chi^2_{(6)} = P < 0.05$); therefore, the null hypothesis was retained. This implies that subjects in the two groups did not differ significantly in the frequency and type of errors they committed while solving algebraic problems before the experiment.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in mean scores in the types of errors committed while solving algebraic problems between male and Female senior secondary school students in Kano State?

Table 3

Summary of frequencies (F) and percentages (%) of error types committed in algebra by male and female students in Kano state

Error Types	Male		Female	
	Freq	%	Freq.	%
Procedural	13	21.0	15	21.7
Factual	4	6.5	5	7.2
Conceptual	3	4.8	7	10.1
Wrong operation	15	24.2	13	18.8
Defective algorithm	12	19.4	8	11.6
Misdirection	12	19.4	17	24.6
Comprehension	3	4.8	4	5.8
Total	62	100.0	69	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 3 reveals a relatively equal error types committed by the male and female subjects exposed to the cooperative learning strategy experiment. A careful study of the frequencies reveals that the trend of the errors basically followed the same pattern although the actual counts differ. There is a proportional occurrence of the errors in both groups; particularly when procedural errors (21.0% and 21.7%) for males and females were considered respectively. In order to find out if these differences are significant, the Chi square statistic was used for the analysis and the results are presents in Table 4.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho₂. There is no significant difference between male and female students while solving algebraic problems in Kano State

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Table 4

Summary of Chi square analysis on error types committed in algebra by male and female subjects after exposure to the cooperative learning strategy

Error types committed	Male	Female	Total
Procedural	13(13.47)	15(14.53)	28
Factual	4(4.33)	5(4.67)	9
Conceptual	3(4.81)	7(5.19)	10
Wrong operation	15(15.39)	13(16.61)	28
Defective algorithm	12(10.58)	8(11.42)	20
Misdirection	12(12.02)	17(12.98)	29
Comprehension	3(2.40)	4(2.60)	7
Total	62	69	131

$\chi^2_{(6)} = 2.53 < 0.05$ Not Significant Source: SPSS V10 Data Analysis software (202

Table 4 is a summary of Chi square analysis of error scores committed by gender (M/F) before they were exposed to the effect of cooperative learning as a remedy in order to find out if there is gender specificity in error committed. Results obtained did not reveal significant difference ($\chi^2_{(6)} = P < 0.05$) between male and female subjects in the error committed while solving algebraic problems after the experiment. Thus, the null hypothesis was retained. This means the cooperative learning strategy was gender fair.

Research Question 3:

3. What are the impacts of cooperative learning strategy on errors committed while solving algebra among senior secondary school students in Kano State?

Table 5:

Summary of error types committed by percentages in control and experimental groups while solving algebraic problems

Error Types	Control		Experimental	
	Freq	%	Freq.	%
Procedural	32	13.0	34	15.1
Factual	24	9.8	14	6.2
Conceptual	40	16.3	37	16.4
Wrong operation	25	10.2	30	13.3
Defective algorithm	34	13.8	28	12.4
Misdirection	44	17.9	49	21.8
Comprehension	47	19.1	34	15.1
Total	246	100.0	236	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2024)

As shown in Table 5, errors of misdirection (experimental) and comprehension (control) had the highest frequencies; while the lowest was factual error in both control and experimental groups. Although the frequencies do not follow any corresponding pattern, higher errors committed in the control group are in comprehension, defective algorithm, conceptual and factual, while the experimental group recorded higher frequencies in procedural, wrong operation and misdirection when the two groups are juxtaposed. In other words, there is variability in the frequencies of error types as shown in Table 5. In order to find out if these error values are significant, the Chi square statistics was used for analysis. The results are presented in Table 6.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho₃. There is no significant impact of cooperative learning strategy on errors committed while solving algebra among senior secondary school students in Kano State

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Table 6

Chi square analysis of error types before and after the cooperative learning strategy in the experimental group

Error types committed	Before	After	Total
Procedural	34(39.25)	28(22.75)	62
Factual	14(14.56)	9(8.44)	23
Conceptual	37(29.75)	10(17.25)	47
Wrong operation	30(29.21)	28(21.28)	58
Defective algorithm	28(30.39)	20(17.61)	48
Misdirection	49(49.38)	29(28.62)	78
Comprehension	34(25.96)	7(15.04)	41
Total	226	131	357

$\chi^2_{(6)} = 17.44 \leq 0.05$ * Significant

A careful study of Table 6 revealed the result of experiment for remediating identified errors in algebra using the cooperative learning strategy the subjects were expose to. There were recorded reduction in errors across all error types which could be attributed to the efficacy of the strategy used in the experiment, hence, the null hypothesis was rejected ($\chi^2_{(6)} = 17.44 \leq 0.05$). It could be affirmed that the cooperative learning strategy have caused this significant impact in remedying errors committed in algebra.

However, a further assessment of the impact of the cooperative learning strategy on the gender differences in error committed in algebra using the post test scores of male and female subjects, results of the t-test statistics employed was summarized in Table 7.

Table 7

Summary of t-test analysis of post-test scores of male and female subjects in the experimental group.

Gender	N	X ± SD	SE	X Gain	t-value	df	t-Crit	P	Rmk
Male	33	43.47+10.14	1.85	5.71	2.001	61	2.000	0.05	* Sig
Female	30	49.18+12.33	2.15						
Total	63	92.65+22.47	4.00						

$t_{(62)} = 2.00 \leq 0.05$ * Significant

In Table 7, the observed t-value of 2.001 in the test was higher than the critical value of t (2.000); and at df=61 and 0.05 alpha level, it implies that significant difference exists between the two means. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected by gender; as the female subjects performed better in the post-test analysis.

Discussion of Findings

It is common knowledge that errors abound in every human action and mathematics is not exempted. However, errors in algebra can be persistent and difficult to correct particularly when students are taught in a traditional manner (Davidson, 2017). Based on this assertion, this study assessed the effects of cooperative learning strategy in remedying frequency and error types in algebra among secondary school students in Kano state. Cooperative learning is a teaching strategy that enables students to work together in small groups in order to achieve common goals. In line with this, three variables selected for this study focused on frequency of error types, treatment and impact of treatment by gender. Error types, it was observed, were more frequent during the pre-test in comprehension and conceptual (control group; 40 and 47 respectively), misdirection (experimental; 49); whereas post-test value errors in the experiment group have misdirection (29) as the highest error frequency. This result is in line with Lawal, (2009) observation that when effective remediation is effected, meaningful learning would be achieved. Results of chi-square analysis on types of errors committed in the process of solving algebraic problems was not significant when the control and experimental groups were compared. This is consistent with the findings of Salman (2004) who affirmed that students do commit errors at non-significant rates while identifying types of errors committed in specific topics and concepts in algebra. The types of errors committed by subjects in the experimental group before and after treatment, when compared, revealed after chi-square statistical analysis that observed errors before (226) was higher than observed errors after (131) exposure to the cooperative learning strategy. This finding agrees with that of Swanson (2000) who pointed out that cooperative learning approach can bring positive results in deeper understanding of content, increased overall achievement in grades, improved self-esteem and higher motivation to remain on task. This finding also agrees with Solomon (2002) that

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besides helping students to become actively and constructively involved in content and developing team work skills, teachers also promote collaborative experiences and enhanced interpersonal relations with teams. Furthermore, Aiyede (2007) emphasized the advantages of the cooperative learning strategy as one through which understanding can become explicit in diverse ways that promote positive attitude

When the frequency and types of errors committed was tested by gender did not reveal any significant difference when the type and number of errors committed while solving algebraic problems were considered. This portrays the use of cooperative learning strategy as gender fair. This finding agrees with the report of Baer (2005) who reported that most of the studies done on cooperative learning placed students on heterogenous groups; and Adeniyi (2000) rather ascribes low performance to ineffective teaching with the traditional methods.

Furthermore, results of chi square analysis of error types before and after the cooperative learning strategy in the experimental group was significant ($t_{(62)} = 2.00 \leq 0.05$); while the same significant result ($t_{(62)} = 2.00 \leq 0.05$) was recorded by gender when post treatment test was considered. This gender difference was in favour of the females ($N=30$; $X+SD=49.18+12.33$) compared to their male counterparts ($N=33$; $X+SD=43.47+10.14$) who recorded higher scores in the experiment. the efficacy of the cooperative learning strategy which was the main instrument used as treatment for this study cannot be waived aside as this result is in agreement with results of earlier studies (Eniayeju, 2010; Olanrewaju, 2012; Vermette, 2004). Recognizing that the results of this study agree with global best practices in using the cooperative learning strategy as an effective instructional approach because of apparent learner involvement, sustained motivation, positive attitudes, improved social skills and accommodation of heterogeneity (Gillies and Boyle, 2006), there is need for all mathematics teachers to begin to employ this method in teaching algebra, if they have not started.

Conclusion

This study was carried out to investigate the effects of cooperative learning in remedying frequency and error types in algebra by secondary school students in Kano state. The findings of this study reveal that senior secondary school students generally committed similar error types which are not significantly different by gender while involved in solving algebraic problems; and these errors types can be reduced by using cooperative learning strategies. The results are consistent with previous research outcomes. It is concluded that the procedure of the strategy has positive effects on students' morale and social interaction.

Recommendations

The following recommendations have been proffered based on the findings of this study:

1. Teachers should endeavor to identify common types of errors students commit while solving algebraic problems in mathematics
2. When there is need to reduce identified errors, the use of cooperative learning strategy should be encouraged
3. Cooperative learning strategy should be used in teaching algebraic problems at the senior secondary school level.
4. Curriculum development research bodies such as the Nigerian Educational and Research Development Council should emphasize the use of cooperative learning strategy as a method of teaching in schools.
5. Science professional bodies like the Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN) and the Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) should organize regular workshops on the modus operandi of the cooperative learning strategy as a method of teaching and learning.

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References

- Adeniyi, N. E. (2000). Mathematics in Secondary Schools. *Abacus. The Journal of Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN)*. 18(1), 12-14
- Agwagah, U. N. (2001). Making Mathematics Self - Reliant. *Journal of Science and Computer Education*, 1(3). 37 – 40.
- Aiyede, S. A. (2007). The effect of Concept Mapping Instructional Strategy on Mathematics Achievement in JSS. Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Dept of Educ., ABU Zaria
- Baer, J. (2005). Grouping and Achievement in Cooperative Learning. *College Teaching*, 51(4), 169
- Clements, D. H. (2014). Learning trajectories in mathematics education. *Mathematical Thinking and Learning*. 16(2), 71-91

Effect of Cooperative Learning ... (Sadi, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15046435>

- Cohen E. G. and Lotan, R. A. (2014). Designing group work: strategies for heterogenous classrooms. Oxford: College Press.
- Davidson, N. (2017). Cooperative learning in mathematics education. A review of the Literature. MERJ, 29(1), 1-23
- Eniaiyaju, A. A. (2010). Effects of cooperative learning strategy on the achievement of primary six boys and girls in mathematics. Abacus, Journal of the Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN), Vol. 35(1), 34 - 38
- Gowers T. (2002). Mathematics: A very short Introduction. London: OUP
- Inah, L.I. (2014). Influence of activity method of teaching word problems in geometry on interest and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Zaria. PhD Seminar, ABU Zaria
- Keller, E. F. (2007). The Cambridge Companion to Mathematics. (Ed). England: Cambridge U
- Lauren, T. (2024). Quasi experimental design: definition, types and examples. Retrieved from www.scribbr.com
- Lawal, F. K. (2009). Effectiveness of conceptual change instructional strategy in remediating identified misconceptions in genetics among senior secondary school students in Kano state. Unpublished PhD. Dissertation, Dept. of Education, ABU Zaria.
- Nigerian Educational and Research Development Council (NERDC) (2008). Teachers Handbook for 9-year Basic Education Curriculum for Junior Secondary Schools
- Odili, G. A. (2005). Teaching of Mathematics in Secondary Schools. Obosi: Amuch. Edu. Books
- Okpala, J. U. & Anene, O. R. (2009). Strategies for improving students' active participation and achievement in Secondary Mathematics: The basis for MDGs. Proceedings of the Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN) held at the University of Ibadan, Oyo State
- Olanrewaju, R. R. (2012). Effects of cooperative learning Strategy with models on academic achievement and retention of biology concepts among Pre-National Diploma students. Zaria: Unpublished PhD Thesis, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
- Salman, M. F. (2004). Analysis of errors committed in word problems involving simultaneous Linear Equation by Nigerian secondary school students. Abacus: Journal of the Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN), 30(1), 20 - 29
- Sarah, M. W. & Cassidy, J. (2006). Cooperative Learning in Elementary School Classroom. Educational Psychology, 39(3), 1 - 5
- Slaven, R. E. (2013). Cooperative learning and achievement: A meta-analytic review. Journal of Educ Psych. 105(2), 347 – 355
- Steve, A. (2002). Tutorials on types of programming errors. Dept. of Computer Sc. Educ. FUE Kano
- Swanson, P. E. (2000). Equity in Cooperative Learning Classroom. Theory and Education Research Digest, 56(8), 62
- Tarr, J. E. & Knuth, E. J. (2013). Early Algebraic Thinking: A review of the literature. MERJ, 25(1), 1-24
- Topson, K. (1999). The Oxford Mathematics Study. Italy: Gelko Ltd.
- Wendy, J. (2005). The implementation of cooperative learning in the classroom. Centre for Educational Studies, University of Hull Publications, vol 1 (2), 36.
- Wiles, A. (2007). The Oxford Handbook of Mathematics (Ed). London: Oxford University Press

Effect of Ethno-Science-Enriched ... (Muhammad, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15046608>

Effect of Ethno-Science-Enriched Strategy on Performance in Energy Concept among Upper Basic Students in Sabon-Gari, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the Effects of Ethno-Science-Enriched Strategy on Performance in Energy Concept among Upper Basic Students in Sabon Gari LGA, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The study employed a pretest posttest quasi-experimental design. The population comprised 8,919 Upper Basic II students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Sabon Gari Kaduna State. A randomly selected sample of 143 students from 2 co-educational schools was used for the study. The schools were randomly assigned into experimental and control groups, respectively. The experimental group was taught energy concepts using ethno-science-Enriched-Instruction while the control group was taught the same concepts using the conventional method. The groups were posttested to determine their performance on energy concepts. The Energy Concept Performance Test (ECPT), with a reliability coefficient of 0.81 using PPMC statistical tool, was used for data collection. The research question was answered using descriptive statistics. The hypothesis was tested using a t-test statistic at $\alpha \leq 0.05$ levels of significance. The findings revealed that students in the experimental group performed better than those taught using the conventional method. Based on the findings from this study, it was concluded that Ethno-Science-Enriched Instruction has positively improved students' academic performance taught Energy concepts compared to their counterparts taught using conventional methods. It was recommended, among others, that textbook authors should include examples and illustrations that utilize locally available instructional materials that are easily accessible to the learner in their immediate environment.

Keyword: (Ethno-Science-Enriched Instruction, Conventional Method, Performance, Energy Concepts, Basic Science)

Introduction

Today, science is the tool for advancement and development of any nation. In realization of this, the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) emphasized the introduction of Basic Science and Technology at the Lower Basic Level and Basic Science at the Upper Basic Level of the school system. Shaibu (2014) defined science as human activity that leads to the production of a body of universal statements called laws, theories, or hypotheses that serve to explain the observable behavior of the universe or some aspects of the universe. According to Peni (2016), a child studying science at the upper basic level is exposed to basic science, formerly known as integrated science. Basic prepares students for the study of core science subjects such as biology, chemistry, and physics, among others, at the senior secondary school level. Based on the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), basic science was introduced as nature study and hygiene, which later metamorphosed into various subject disciplines as biology, chemistry, and physics at the senior secondary (SS) level of education in Nigeria. Lattuca, Voight, and Fath (2017) posited that integrating concepts from multiple disciplines can provide students with a more holistic understanding of scientific phenomena. This step was geared towards presenting science to students in their culture and

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traditions in their societies. According to Dike and Rowland (2020), this implies that teaching and learning of basic science are expected to be culturally and environmentally oriented to provide students with adequate foundations capable of solving societal problems, among which is ethno-science-Enriched instruction.

Abonyi, Achimugu, and Njoku (2014) defined ethno-science as indigenous knowledge from a culture that is connected with scientific knowledge, or is called knowledge owned by a nation. Rahayu and Sudarmin (2015) posited that science will be easier to understand if the teacher pays attention to the students' culture. Sudarmin, Febu, Nuswowati, and Sumarni (2017) argued that teachers' comprehension of activity-based teaching methods, such as ethno-science-Enriched instruction, can enhance the significance of science education. Therefore, it is important for teachers to be knowledgeable about the integration of cultural understanding with scientific knowledge in the classroom. Research had been carried out to find the effectiveness of ethno-science-Enriched instruction. Nisa, Sudarmin, and Samini (2015); Khoerunnisa and Sudarmin (2016) stressed that one of the ways that could be done to improve students' academic performance was making correlation between learning topics and daily activities around their environment as learning sources so that it would be more beneficial for the students' by using learning tools integrated with local wisdom. Other than that, Adhi, Sudarmin, and Linuwih (2018) viewed that the use of ethno-science-based video also improved the students' learning achievement during learning of science. Peni (2016) asserted that ethnoscience has the capacity to blend with knowledge-based science and technology, thereby complementing scientific and technological efforts to solve problems associated with understanding science concepts. Dike and Rowland (2020) stressed that, since Basic Science is the first science subject a child encounters before its indigenous science, if taught using an ethnoscience-based approach, it will improve students' creativity, critical thinking, and performance for sustainable national development. All these related findings have no link to the energy concept using Ethno-Science; hence, this study examined the effects of Ethno-Science Enriched Instruction on Performance in Energy Concept among Upper Basic II Students in Sabon Gari, Kaduna State, Nigeria. Shaibu (2014) posited that this persistent failure is associated with a lack of adequate laboratory equipment for practical-based activities. Samuel (2018) attributed the persistent failures in the subject to poor instructional strategy. Dike and Rowland (2020) opined that most of the instructional materials used by teachers to teach the students were alien, thereby reducing learning to rote memorization. It becomes obvious that concrete and locally sourced materials that are well known to students in their environment may improve their performance in Basic Science. Hence, the effects of ethno-science-Enriched-Instruction on academic performance in teaching energy concepts were determined.

Objective of the study

The objective of the study was to;

- xi.** Ascertain the effects of Ethno-Science-Enriched Instruction on academic performance in Energy concepts among Upper Basic II Students in Sabon Gari LGA, Kaduna State, Nigeria,

Research Question

10. What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of Upper Basic II students taught energy concepts using ethno-science-Enriched instruction and those taught using conventional methods?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated for testing at $\alpha < 0.05$ level of significance.

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of Upper Basic Science II students taught energy concepts using ethno-science-Enriched instruction and those taught using conventional methods.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental and control group design of pretest and posttest was employed for this study. Intact classes were used for the study. In this study, two groups were used, which are the experimental and control groups. Students in the experimental group were taught energy concepts using ethno-science-enriched instruction, while those in the control group were taught the same concept using the conventional method for a period of six weeks. After treatment, an Energy Concept Performance Test was administered to both the control and experimental groups as a posttest. The population for this study covers all Upper Basic (II) public secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State, Nigeria. There are 14 Upper Basic (II) public secondary schools offering Basic Science as a core subject with a population of 8,919 students, 4,203 males and 4,716 females in Sabon Gari LGA, Kaduna State, Nigeria, at the time of the study. To select the sample of students, four schools were selected using simple random sampling technique involving the balloting method from the 10 co-educational public upper basic secondary schools in Sabon Gari LGA, Kaduna State, Nigeria. To select a

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representative class, the balloting method was applied, in which A, B, and C, according to the number of arms in each school, were written on paper, squeezed, put inside the container, and shaken very well before being picked randomly. The classes picked in each school represent that school. The four classes representing each school were given a pretest using the Energy Concept Performance Test (ECPT), and the results obtained were subjected to analysis variance (ANOVA) at $\alpha < 0.05$ to determine the academic equivalence level of each school selected. Results obtained from ANOVA showed that there is a significant difference in the performance score of the 4 schools, which makes the result subjected to Scheffe's test to pick two schools with no significant difference. A total of 143 Upper Basic II students were used for the study. The Energy Concept Performance Test (ECPT) consisted of 30 objective (multiple choice) test items that were drawn from the concept of energy. Each of the 30 multiple-choice items has four options, one correct answer, and three plausible distractors. One mark was awarded to each correct answer that was shaded, giving a total of 30 marks. The ECPT was validated by experts with a minimum qualification of Ph.D. from the Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, and was found to have a reliability coefficient of 0.80 using Pearson Person Moment Correlation (PPMC). The research question was answered using data collected and analyzed using descriptive statistics in the form of mean and standard deviation, while the null hypothesis was tested using an independent sample t-test using data of posttest performance scores of students in the experimental and control groups.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean academic performance score between Upper Basic Science II students taught energy concepts using ethno-science-enriched instruction and those taught using conventional methods?

The mean and standard deviation of post-test scores for experimental and control groups are calculated and presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Means and Standard Deviations of Post Test Scores of ECPT for Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	66	14.15	3.87	3.45
Control	77	10.70	2.95	

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork

Table 1 shows that the experimental group has a mean performance score of 14.15 and a standard deviation of 3.87, while the control group has a mean performance score of 10.70 and a standard deviation of 2.95 and a mean difference of 3.45.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of Upper Basic Science II students taught energy concepts using ethno-science enriched instruction and those taught using Conventional method.

Independent sample t-test was used to test hypothesis (H_0). The result of the analysis is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Summary of t-test Analysis of Post ECPT Scores of Students in Experimental and Control Groups.

Group	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Experimental	66	26.77	3.29	141	31.08	0.03	*Sig
Control	77	10.81	2.82				

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork

From Table 2 it is clear that, the t-calculated is 31.08 and a P-value of 0.03 at the degree of freedom of 141 is obtained. The P-value of 0.03 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that, there is a significant difference in the academic performance of Basic science students taught energy concept using ethno-science-enriched instruction. This difference is in favour of the experimental group. This also implies that, ethno-science-enriched instruction is effective for improving the performance of the students in the experimental group.

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Discussion of Findings

This study investigates the Effects of Ethno-Science-Enriched Instruction on Interest and Performance on Energy Concept among Upper Basic II Students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State, Nigeria. One null hypothesis was stated. Analyses of the data obtained were present in Table 1 in accordance with the stated hypothesis. The findings from the analysis were discussed. The results in Table 2 show that there is a significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught energy concepts in Basic Science with Ethno-Science-Enriched Instruction and those taught with conventional methods. This shows that ethno-science-Enriched instruction is effective in improving the performance of students in the experimental group. However, those taught energy concepts using ethno-science-Enriched instruction acquired significantly higher performance mean scores than those taught energy concepts using conventional methods. This finding agrees with those of Ebere and Appolonia (2017), Eko, Meli, and Nirwana (2020), Dike and Rowland (2020), and Nwankwo (2021), who found a significant difference in the mean performance scores of students in the experimental and control groups in favor of the experimental group. They believed that students who were taught using ethno-science-Enriched-Instruction gained more performance as a result of their engagement with the available cultural resources as compared to those taught using conventional methods.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from this study, it is concluded that ethno-science-enriched Instruction has positively improved students' academic performance taught Energy concepts compared to their counterparts taught using conventional methods.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is therefore recommended that:

1. Basic Science teachers should adopt the use of ethno-science-enriched-instruction as it enhances students' performance in teaching and learning basic science.
2. Instructional materials for teaching Basic science should be geared towards cultural relevance.
3. Textbook authors should include examples and illustrations that utilize locally available instructional materials that are easily accessible to the learner in their immediate area. This will improve the academic performance of students.

References

- Abonyi, O. S., Achimugu, L., & Njoku, M. I. A. (2014). Innovation in science and technology education: A case of ethno-science based science classrooms. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 5(1), 52-56.
- Adhi, D. T., Sudarmin, S., & Linuwih, S. (2018). The influence of ethno-science-based learning video to improve students' understanding of green chemistry in integrated science subject. *Journal of Innovative Science Education*, 7(2), 36-44.
- Dike, J. W., & Rowland, M. F. (2020). Students' understanding of sound energy using ethno-science based instruction in basic science. *International Journal of Innovative Social & Science Education Research*, 8(4), 136-140.
- Ebere, I. F., & Appolonia, A. (2017). Effects of ethno-science and traditional laboratory practical on science process skills acquisition of secondary school biology students in Nigeria. *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Advanced Studies*, 1(1), 35-46.
- Eko, R., Meli, J. D., & Nirwana, M. K. (2020). Effect of ethno-science-based direct instruction learning model in physics learning on students' critical thinking skill. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(2), 611-615.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2013). *National policy on education*. NERDC Press.
- Khoerunnisa, R. F., & Sudarmin, S. (2016). Development of science module related to ethno-science to grow entrepreneurship interest. *Journal of Innovative Science Education*, 5(1), 45-53.
- Lattuca, L. R., Voight, M. J., & Fath, K. Q. (2017). Interdisciplinary approaches in basic science education. *Science Education*, 101(3), 485-502.
- Nisa, A., Sudarmin, S., & Samini, S. (2015). Effectiveness of the use ethno-science integrated module in problem-based learning to improve students' literacy science. *Unnes Science Education Journal*, 4(3), 1049-1056.
- Nwankwo, G. U. (2021). Effects of ethno-science instructional strategy on junior secondary school students' achievement in basic science. *African Journal of Science, Technology & Mathematics Education (AJSTME)*, 6(1), 2251-014.
- Peni, H. Y. (2016). Impact of ethno-science-enriched-instruction on attitude, retention and performance in basic science among rural and urban students in Kano State, Nigeria (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Rahayu, W. E., & Sudarmin, S. (2015). Pengembangan modul IPA terpadu berbasis etnosains tema energi dalam kehidupan untuk menanamkan jiwa konservasi peserta didik. *Unnes Science Education Journal*, 4(2), 60-75.

Effect of Ethno-Science-Enriched ... (Muhammad, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15046608>

- Samuel, R. I. (2018). Effect of simulation instructional package on upper basic science students' interest, achievement and retention in body systems. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 11(4), 716-724.
- Shaibu, A. A. M. (2014). Resources for science laboratories and science teaching in schools. In *Proceedings of Multicultural Africa Conference (2013). Resource Mobilization, Management for Access and Quality Education in Africa*.
- Sudarmin, S., Febu, R., Nuswowati, M., & Sumarni, W. (2017). Development of ethno-science approach in the module theme substance additives to improve the cognitive learning outcome and student's entrepreneurship. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 824(1), 1-7.

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Effect of Graphic Organizer in Integration Concept among Secondary School Mathematics Students in Mkpato Enin, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

The study investigated the use of graphic organizer in teaching integration and students' achievement in senior secondary school mathematics in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. Three research questions and corresponding research hypotheses guided the study. Quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test post-test non-randomized control group design was used. The population of the study was 1935 senior secondary three (SS3) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Mkpato Enin, Akwa Ibom State, sample size of 129 (64 Male and 65 Female) students were randomly selected from the target population. The instrument used for collection of data was Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) on integration with a reliability coefficient of 0.72 using test-retest method. Hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study showed a significant difference among the mean achievement scores of students taught integration using graphic organizer and those exposed to lecture strategy. Findings of the study revealed that students taught using graphic organizer achieved significantly higher in their mean scores compared with the lecture strategy. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that graphic organizer is a good strategy for teaching integration. It is therefore recommended among others that mathematics teachers should adopt the use of graphic organizer in teaching integration.

Keywords: Graphic Organizer, Achievement, and Gender.

Introduction

Mathematics spreads across nature. It plays vital role in accelerating the social, economic and technological growth of any nation. Today's world thrives on science and technology that demands mathematical knowledge (Babayemi, & Kareem, 2019). Mathematical literacy is an indispensable attribute that individuals should possess, in a bid to living more effective lives as constructive, concerned and reflective citizens. A paradigm shift is needed for moving mathematics from the world of mystery to part of daily life. This will go a long way in making the technological advancement of the nation and world at large start from the home to the learner. To this end, it is necessary to prepare today's learners with a strong foundation in mathematics (Crowe, 2022; Babayemi, Itighise, Umanah, Abasi & Umoh, 2023). Many topics in schools' mathematics curriculum are seen as difficult to learn by students. Integration is one of such topics. This is evident in students' results both in internal and external examinations. This difficulty in the learning of integration necessitates deep insights into mathematics learning to demystify the subject. This can only be achieved through better teaching of mathematics topics including integration. Integration as a topic comes under introductory calculus in the curriculum. Calculus is a branch of mathematics that deals with the rate of change of one variable with another. Calculus is broadly classified into two broad areas: differential and integral calculus. The derivative is a measure of the rate of change of quantity with respect to another, whereas integral is the measure of the area under a curve. The derivative explains the function at a specific point while the integral accumulates the discrete values of a function over a range of values (Byju's, 2021). Integration is an essential concept which is the inverse process of differentiation. Integration simply means collecting things, adding them and forming something solid. While differentiation means breaking up something into tiny quantities (Sur, 2022). Integration can be classified into two different categories, namely: Definite integral and indefinite integral (Maths Is Fun, 2024).

Definite integral is an integral that contains the upper and lower limits, that is, the start and the end value. The value of x is restricted to lie on a real line, and a definite integral is also called Riemann integral when it is bounded to lie on the real

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line. A definite integral is represented as: $\int_b^a f(x)dx$. On the other hand, Indefinite integrals are not defined using the upper and lower limits. The indefinite integrals represent the family of the given function whose derivatives are f , and it returns a function of the independent variable. Here, a constant C is always attached to the answer (CueMath, 2023). Calculating areas and volumes dated from Ancient Greek mathematics, the principles of integration were formulated independently by Isaac Newton and Gottfried Wilhem Leibniz in the late 17th century, who thought of the area under a curve as an infinite sum of rectangles of infinitesimal width. From (www.profdave.com explains), the work of Isaac Newton Wilhemm Liebnitz was explained. Here finding area of regular shapes like square, rectangles and trapezium was carried out. But the question remained, to find area of irregular shapes. Since mathematics is progressive, to find area of irregular shape, a case study of area under a curve will be used. From the works of Newton and Liebniz, the irregular area under the curve will be divided into smaller rectangles. The area of the smaller rectangles, with constant width and varied heights will be found separately. Then summed up to find area of the bigger rectangle. As shown below: It will be observed that the smaller the width of the rectangles, the closer the answer of the area is, to accuracy. Hence, instead of spending time to divide the rectangles to infinite sizes, integration can be used to get the exact answer at once (as shown below). That's how the idea of integration started and grew to complex stages.

Figure 1: Area of a curve-I

To find the area under the curve from the graphs above the area is between O and I on both X and Y axis. First, using the practical approach to find the area which $L \times b$ or $b \times h$. we will let $x =$ breadth or with and $y =$ height. So $b \times h = X \times y$ to find the area of the rectangle, we divide then into smaller rectangle (according to newton and Liebniz) and find the area of the smaller rectangles, then latter add then up (Σ or \int) to find the area of the big rectangle.

First, we divide them into 4 rectangles (see 1st graph above), their areas (from graph) are
 First, we divide them into 4 rectangles (see 1st graph above), their areas (from graph) are

Table 1: Measurement Obtained from Figure 1

S/N	X	Y	XY
1	0.25	0.625	0.15625
2	0.25	0.25	0.0625
3	0.25	0.5625	0.140625
4	0.25	1	0.25
			0.609375

Note: the width remains, constant, only height changes

Note: the width remains, constant, only height changes

2nd graph:

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Figure 2: Area of a Curve-II

Recall: $L_z = x$, height y and also recall that the breath (x) remains the same (constant) only the height y varies.

Now 8 rectangles

Table 2: Measurement Obtained from Figure 2

s/n	X	Y	XY
1	$\frac{1}{8} = 0.125$	0.8	0.1
2	$\frac{2}{8} = 0.125$	0.16	0.02
3	$\frac{3}{8} = 0.125$	0.26	0.0325
4	$\frac{4}{8} = 0.125$	0.36	0.045
5	$\frac{5}{8} = 0.125$	0.5	0.0625
6	$\frac{6}{8} = 0.125$	0.64	0.08
7	$\frac{7}{8} = 0.125$	0.8	0.1
8	$\frac{8}{8} = 0.125$	1.0	0.125
			0.44

3rd graph

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Figure 3: Area of a Curve-III

Table 3: Measurements of Curve-III

S/N	X	Y	XY
1	0.0625	0.05	0.003125
2	0.0625	0.08	0.005
3	0.0625	0.1	0.00625
4	0.0625	0.16	0.01
5	0.0625	0.18	0.01125
6	0.0625	0.24	0.015
7	0.0625	0.28	0.0175
8	0.0625	0.38	0.02375
9	0.0625	0.41	0.025625
10	0.0625	0.48	0.3
11	0.0625	0.56	0.035
12	0.0625	0.64	0.04
13	0.0625	0.7	0.04375
14	0.0625	0.8	0.05
15	0.0625	0.88	0.055
16	0.0625	1.0	0.625
			0.43375

Subsequently areas of:

100 rectangles = 0.33835

1000 rectangles = 0.33383

From observation, the answer is getting closer to accuracy

But, we can use integration to find infinitely smaller number of rectangle to arrive at accuracy thus:

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The function is $y = x^2$

$\int x^2 dx$. Integrating between the intervals of 0 to 1 gives $\left[\frac{x^3}{3} \right]_0^1 = \left[\frac{1^3 - 0}{3} \right] = 0.333$

It is observed that the smaller the width of the rectangles, the closer the answer of the area is, to accuracy. Hence, it was concluded that instead of spending time to divide the rectangles to infinite sizes, integration can be used to get the exact answer at once. Adequate strategies of teaching various concepts in the classroom determines students' academic achievement. Academic achievement is the amount of academic content a student learns in a specific period. This can be in any way a student has achieved his or her short- term or long-term academic goals within an academic setting (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014; Barowski & Carter, 2021). Academic achievement must be measurable, which is the reason distinct goals are used as a defining characteristic. Drew (2023) also explained that academic achievement is the level of success or achievement attained by an individual in an academic setting. It encompasses a broad range of factors including grades, test scores, research outcomes and overall academic performance.

Another variable considered here is gender. Andrews, Cook, Nielson and Xiao (2020) stated that gender plays a role in students' experiences at school, but these experiences are quite different from students who vary from the norm in terms of gender identity and expression. World Health Organization (2024) explained that the behavioural pattern of women, men, girls and boys which are socially constructed, points to the meaning of gender. The socially constructed roles are the norms and behaviours associated with being either a woman, man, boy or girl. Gender is hierarchical and produces inequalities that intersect with other social and economic inequalities.

The various levels of mathematics achievement can be influenced by strategies adopted by a teacher. The strategy considered in this study are Graphic organizer and Lecture strategies.

A teaching strategy can be described as a set of methods that are used to help an individual learn new material. Teaching strategies according to Sinha (2024) are a collection of different methods that are all in use by the teacher to teach the subject material and these may vary from lesson to lesson. Sinha further said that teaching strategies can also be defined as "a method or set of methods used by a teacher to teach the subject matter" while describing method of teaching as a procedure, a process or a way something is done or implemented. With the aforementioned reasons, graphic organizer is regarded as a strategy of teaching. Graphic organizer is a great way to display information visually. It is a way of presenting pieces of information visually to aid students' comprehension. Graphic organizers have such benefits as: helping students to classify ideas and examine relationships, improves students' reading comprehension by making information digestible as well as helping learners understand how processes work by systematically showing cause and effect (Dean, 2024, Jill Stake, 2024 and Inspiration, 2024).

In the recent times, many educational researchers reported mathematics teaching has mainly been through the use of lecture strategy (Akpan, Utibe, Babayemi & Nelson, 2023; Ham, 2023; Kelum, Dehideniya & Sakunthala, 2021). This strategy has a critical role in introducing the students to higher mathematics and shaping students' interest and curiosity to learning mathematics. It should be borne in mind that the process of interpreting the world of knowledge into the mind of the learners, through whatever means is simply known as method of teaching. Lecture method, also known as the transmissive method, is based on vertical learning, whereby the teacher has all the knowledge and pours them into the learners. It is a teacher-addicted method of teaching (Babayemi, Ahmed, Yisau & Babalola, 2016). Empirical studies by Oginni (2021) on the effects of graphic organizer and animation on students learning outcomes in Mathematics revealed that there is significant difference in the learning outcomes of students taught using graphic organizer, animation and conventional strategies. Fabros and Ibanez (2023) found out that when learners are exposed to graphic organizer, their scores and level of conceptual understanding are improved. Owolabi and Adaramati (2015) investigated the effects of graphic organizer and gender on students' academic achievement in algebraic word problem. The finding revealed that the experimental groups performed better than the control group, the treatment appeared to be more effective among male students than their female counterparts, the main effect of treatment was significant and the main effect of gender as well as the interaction effects of treatment and gender were not statistically significant.

Statement of the Research Problem

Before now, integration as a topic was in Further mathematics curriculum. Other students did not have the opportunity to learn integration. When students have admission into tertiary institutions, they are faced with MTH111 (General Mathematics 1) and MTH 121 (General Mathematics 11). Integration was then moved to mathematics curriculum to prepare candidates for their tertiary education. Even at this, many students do not still get to learn this integration. This is because of dearth of

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qualified and competent mathematics teachers in many schools. Currently, students of mathematics are performing poorly even in other science-based courses in senior secondary schools. The cause of the poor results is easily traced to the students' poor foundation in mathematics from the primary and carried over to the secondary school (Babayemi, 2014; Petterson & Xenophontos, 2022). Perhaps if prospective tertiary level candidates had studied Mathematics adequately prior to their admission where topics on introductory calculus such as differentiation and integration are properly taught, new intakes into the tertiary level would have had less difficulty in their required mathematics courses. The move to address some of the difficult topics in secondary school Mathematics is even imperative at this time of paradigm shift from Basic Minimum Academic Standard (BMAS) to Core Curriculum Minimum Academic Standard (CCMAS). Will students at the secondary school level achieve better in integration when taught using Graphic organizer or lecture strategy?

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this Study were to:

1. determine the achievement of students taught integration using graphic organizer and those exposed to lecture strategy.
2. determine the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught integration using graphic organizer and lecture strategy.
3. determine the variation in students' achievement attributed to strategy and gender.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean achievement scores of students taught integration using Graphic Organizer and those exposed to lecture strategy?
2. What is the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught integration using Graphic organizer strategy
3. What variation in students' achievement is attributed to strategy and gender?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

- H₀₁ There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught integration using graphic organizer and those exposed to lecture strategies;
- H₀₂ There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught integration using Graphic organizer strategy;
- H₀₃ There is no significant interaction effect of strategies and gender on mean achievement scores of students taught integration using graphic organizer strategy.

Methodology

Quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test post-test non-randomized control group design was used. The population of the study was 1935 senior secondary three (SS3) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Mkpato Enin, Akwa Ibom State, sample size of 129 (64 Male and 65 Female) students were randomly selected from the target population. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the two schools with the following criteria: 1) the school that has qualified mathematics Teachers with at least three years of teaching experience 2) school that has presented candidates in the past five years for Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE). A simple random sampling technique to select one intact class for Experimental group and another intact class for the control group. The instrument used in this study was Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). There were two instructional guides, namely: Instructional Guide on Graphic Organizer (IGGOS) and Instructional Guide on Lecture Strategy (IGLS) respectively. The Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) had a reliability of 0.72 using Test-retest method. All the instruments were duly validated by experts' review.

The first week was used for the training of the participating teachers in each of the schools by the researchers on the use of IGGOS and IGLS. The second week was used for the administration of pre-test by the Teachers and researchers on MAT. The next three weeks (weeks 3-5) were used for the administration of treatment to experimental groups 1, Graphic Organizer Strategy group (GOS), and the control group, Lecture Strategy group (LS). Week five was used for administration of posttest. After two weeks interval (weeks 6 and 7), week 8 was used for administration of retention test by the teachers and researchers.

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Presentation of Results

The Results of this study is organized under research questions and hypothesis as well as the descriptive of students' scores.

Table 1: The Descriptive of Students' Mean Scores and Standard Deviations by Pretest and Post test tests

Variables		Pretest	Posttest
Graphic Organizer	Mean	7.61	36.41
	N	49	49
	Std. Deviation	2.129	2.327
Lecture	Mean	7.16	32.34
	N	38	38
	Std. Deviation	1.952	2.221
Gender			
Male	Mean	7.42	33.97
	N	64	64
	Std. Deviation	2.022	2.725
Female	Mean	7.03	38.58
	N	65	65
	Std. Deviation	1.741	3.010

On Table 1, Descriptive of students' mean scores by Pretest and Posttest are as indicated. There are two independent variables for which scores are indicated on the table. These are strategies at two levels namely: Graphic Organizer and Lecture strategies. The others are gender at two levels of male and female. Students' scores are as indicated on the table for each level of independent variable.

Research Questions

The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviations

Research Question One

What is the mean achievement scores of students taught integration using Graphic Organizer and those exposed to lecture strategies?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Scores by Graphic Organizer and Lecture.

Strategy	N	\bar{x}	SD
Graphic organizer	49	36.151 ^a	0.270
Lecture	38	32.786 ^a	0.317

11. Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at pretest = 7.22
12. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments)

The scores shown on table 4.2 are adjusted by using pretest scores as covariates to the posttest scores. As shown in Table 2, the adjusted mean scores of 49 students who were taught Integration using Graphic Organizer is 36.151 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.270. Similarly, the 38 students taught Integral Calculus using Lecture method had a mean score of 32.786 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.317. It can be observed from the table that graphic organizer group had the higher mean score.

Research Question Two

What is the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught integration using Graphic organizer strategy?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Score by Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD
Male	64	33.775 ^a	0.290
Female	65	34.723 ^a	0.250

3. Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: PRETEST= 7.22.

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As shown in Table 4.3, the adjusted mean scores of 64 the male students who were taught integration is 33.775 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.290, while the adjusted mean score of 65 female students taught integral calculus is 34.723 with a corresponding standard deviation odd 0.250. The difference between the two mean scores is 0.948.

Research Question Three

What variation in students' achievement is attributed to strategy and gender?

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance of Students' Score by strategy and Gender

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected	692.199 ^a	18	38.456	11.503	.000
Intercept	5738.226	1	5738.226	1716.376	.000
PRETEST	83.708	1	83.708	24.038	.000
STRATEGY	230.647	2	115.324	34.495	.000
GENDER	20.110	1	20.110	6.015	.016
STRATEGY*GENDER	13.917	2	6.959	2.081	.130
Error	367.754	110	3.343		
Total	152642.000	129			
Corrected Total	1059.953	128			

a.R Square = .653 (Adjusted R Squared =.596).

All data were obtained using pretest scores as covariates with post test

On Table 6, the computed F- value for strategies is 34.495 with a corresponding P- value of 0.000. The P- value is less than the α –level of 0.05. Hence, strategy is significant. The pairs of levels between which differences are significant are however determined using a post hoc analysis as in Table 7

Table 7 : Post hoc Test Comparison Among Strategies

(I)Strategy	(J)Strategies	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. error	sig ^b p \leq .05
Graphic organizer	Lecture	3.308*	0.376	0.000

The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The purpose of a post hoc test is to determine the pair of variables between which a significance is established. Table 7 depicts that two are significant differences: between the mean scores of the group of graphic organizer and lecture group.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study could be attributed to the fact that graphic organizer helps students to classify ideas and examine relationships, improves students' comprehension by making information digestible as well as help students to understand how process work by systematically showcasing cause and effect. It helps students to organize new information, brainstorm ideas, make meaningful connections between the main idea and other information, improve student understanding, achievement and increase knowledge retention and give students an easy and flexible way to map out any concept or idea thereby improving academic achievement of students (Torrefranca, Estacio and Reyes, 2022). The findings of this study corroborate Fabros and Ibanez (2023) who found out that graphic organizer is an effective approach in improving the conceptual understanding and thus mathematics teachers ought to integrate it in their teaching. Also, graphic organizer improves the level of conceptual understanding as well as improve scores of students. Also, students exposed to graphic organizer achieved better than their counterparts who were not exposed to graphic organizer.

Moreover, findings from the results on the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught the concept of integral calculus using graphic organizer and lecture method as strategies indicated a non-significant difference. The findings confirm the statement of Ajai and Imoko (2015) and Pina, Martella, Moscoso, Saracostti and Cortes (2021), who opined that male and female students are capable of competing and collaborating in mathematics with high achievement levels and that there are no longer distinguishing differences in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor skill achievements of students in respect of gender and that girls are being encouraged and sensitized into developing positive attitudes towards science, which subsequently result in high academic achievement and retention. The findings of the study are also in line with that of Babayemi and Ahmed (2019) and Oribhabor (2022), who found out that male students had slightly better performance compared to the female students but it was not significant.

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Conclusion

The result of this study highlighted the effects of Graphic organizer and Lecture strategy in fostering students' academic achievement in Mathematics when taught the concept of integral calculus. Graphic organizer helped the students to overcome the difficulties inherent in learning the concept of integral calculus. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that graphic organizer is an important strategy in enhancing students' academic achievement of the concept of integral calculus for both male and female students. There existed no significant difference in the achievement scores of male and female students taught the concept of integral calculus using Graphic Organizer and lecture method as strategies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. Mathematics teachers and educators should be encouraged to adopt Graphic Organizer as strategy.
2. Graphic organizer as strategy which is purposive and efficient should be used in teaching integral calculus so that the students can obtain the full benefits of the lesson.
3. Education stakeholders should organize conferences, seminars, and workshops for teachers to acquaint them with the knowledge on the use of graphic organizer as Mathematics strategy to improve the process and product of teaching.
4. Textbooks authors should adopt graphic organizer strategy in their books to support students' organization of concepts and learning.
5. Strengthening the use of graphic organizer through in-service course could help science teachers to adopt proper use of good strategies.

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References

- Ajai J. T. and Imoko I. (2015). Gender difference in Mathematics Achievement and Retention Scores: A case of problem-based learning method. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science (IJRES)*, 1(1):45-50
- Akpan, I.E., Utibe, U.J., Babayemi, J.O. & Nelson, M.I. (2023). Effect of geo-board and charts on students' achievement in mathematics in Essien Udim, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Education and Society*, 14(2), 91-102.
- Andrews N., Cook, R. E., Nielson M. G., Xiao, S. X. and Martin, C. L. (2020). Gender in Education. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/entries/10> (Retrieved on 13th April, 2024)
- Anggraini, A., Baharuddin, B., Pathuddin, P. and Murdiana, N. (2022). Analysis of Mathematics Communication Skill on Set Operations. *ResearchGate*. 10 (1) : 22-32
- Ausubel, D. P. (1968). Educational Psychology: A Cognitive View. New York: *Holt, Rienhart and Winston*
- Ausubel, D. P. (2020). Organizing Knowledge: Ausubel's Advance Organizers. <https://www.mrgoodwin23.wordpress.com/2020/11/28/> (Retrieved on 13th June, 2024)
- Awodeyi A. F. (2017). A Modified Method Combination Therapy as Instructional Strategy For Teaching Secondary School Geometry and Effect On Students Achievement and Retention in Mathematics. *Journal of Education and Practice* 8(4) :4
- Babayemi, J.O. (2014). Effects of crossword-picture puzzle and enhanced explicit teaching strategies on students' learning outcomes in basic science in Southwestern Nigeria. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Department of Teacher Education, University of Ibadan
- Babayemi, J.O. & Ahmed, A.A. (2019). Effects of Enhanced Conventional Lecture Method and Gender on Students' Achievement in Basic Science. *Journal of Contemporary Education Research (JCER)*, 13 (6), 242-256.

Effect of Graphic Organizer ... (George & Awodeyi, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15046789>

- Babayemi, J.O., Ahmed, A.A., Yisau, S.O. & Babalola, G.T. (2016). Effect of enhanced conventional lecture method on students' academic achievement in basic science in Oyo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Benchmark (July/August)*, 5(2), 74-88
- Babayemi, J.O., Itighise, A .E., Umanah, F. I., Abasi, A.U. & Umoh, E.B. (2023). Teaching subject challenges and area of teaching subject: implication for secondary school science, technology and mathematics teachers. *International Journal of Educational Research and Human Development*, 4(4), 25-41.
- Babayemi, J.O. & Kareem, A.A. (2019). Services in secondary schools science laboratory as centre for innovation in basic science and technology in Akwa Ibom state. *60th annual conference of science teachers association of Nigeria*, 254-262.
- Barowski, J. and Carter, V. (2023). Academic achievement and Overview, Definition and Research . <https://www.study.com>
- Blacksmith, N. (2020). Mathematical abilities. <https://www.link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978...>
- Byjus (2021). Calculus. <https://www.byjus.com>.
- Calculus (2019). 51 Amazing Uses of Calculus in Real Life. <https://www.allusesof.com/math/51-amazing-uses-of-calculus-in-real-life>
- Carter, V and Barowski, J. (2023). Academic achievement/Overview, Definition and Research. <https://www.study.com>
- Crowe, A. (2022). Why is Math Important? 9 Reasons Why Maths Skills Improve Quality of Life. <https://www.prodigygame.com/main-en/blog/why-is-math-important/>
- Cuemath (2023). Integration Rules. <https://www.cuemath.com/calculus/integration-rules/> (Retrieved on 19th November, 2023)
- Drew, C. (2023). 39 Academic Achievement Examples. <https://www.helpfulprofessor.com/academicachievement-examples/>
- Dscorner (2024). The Difference in Students' Levels: Grade Level, Instructional Level and Ability Level. <https://www.mrsdscorner.com/difference-in- student-leves/>
- Dunn, A., Airth, M. and Boddie, k. (2023). Polya's Problem Solving Process/ Overview and Steps. <https://www.study.com/academy/lesson/polya-four-step--problem-solving-process-html>
- Fabros, B. G. and Ibaeze, E. (2023). Effectiveness of Utilizing Graphic Organizer in Improving Conceptual Understanding Towards Operation of Fractions Among Teachers. *Research gate* 16(1): 507-526
- Lipnevich, A. (2022). Study: When Mathematics Class is Boring, Students Loose Interest in Related Careers. <https://www.gc.cuny.edu/news/study-when-math-class-boring-students-loose-interest-related-careers>.
- Math Is Fun (2024). Introduction To Integration. <https://www.mathsisfun.com/calculus/integration-introduction-html>
- Moore, T. (2024). What is the Difference Between Intergration and Summation Symbols used in mathematics. <https://www.quora.com>.
- Oginni, O. I. (2021). Effects of Graphic Organizer and Animation of Students Learning Outcomes in Mathematics. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/3611/8491>.
- Olagunju, A.M & Babayemi, J.O. (2014). Effects of crossword-picture puzzle teaching strategy and gender on students' achievement in basic science. *J. of Education and Leadership Development*, 6(1), 43 – 54.
- Oribhabor, C. B. (2020). The Influence of Gender in Mathematics Achievement of Secondary School Students in Bayelsa State. *ResearchGate*. 14(2): 196-206
- Owolabi, J. and Adaramati, T. F. (2015). Effect of Graphic Organizer on Students' Achievement in Algebraic Word Problems. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6 (5): 39-44
- Pettersen, J. M. and Xenofontos, C. (2023). The Construction of Mathematical Identities Among Early Adolescents. <https://www.tandfonline.com/journal/oaed20> (Retrieved on 14th May, 2024)
- Sinha, P. (2024). What is the Difference Between 'Teaching Strategy' and 'Teaching Methods'? <https://www.classplusapp.com/growth/what-is-the-difference-between-a-teaching-strategy-and-a-teaching-method/> (Retrieved on 12th May, 2024)
- Sur, J. (2021). Calculus Mathematics. <https://www.what-is-calculus.com/science>. (Retrieved on 24th February, 2024)
- Thompson, L. (2023). The History and Application of Calculus. <https://www.scribd.com> (Retrieved on 3rd February, 2024)
- Torre Franca, E., Estacio, R and Reyes, E.A.S. (2022). Graphic Organizers and the level of Students' Performance and Self-efficacy in an online Learning Environment. *Researchgate*. 12(10): 414-423.

Effect of Graphic Organizer ... (George & Awodeyi, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15046789>

World Health Organization (WHO). (2024). Gender and Health. Retrieved June 17, 2024 from <https://www.int/health-tips/gender> tab. (Retrieved on 24th June, 2024)

Zhu, A. (2021). Who Got There First: Newton, Leibniz and their work on calculus. <https://www.live.stemfellowship.org> (Retrieved on 17th April, 2024)

Zimmerbaum, H. and Kroll, E. (2021). Graphic organizer/definition types and purpose. <https://study.com/academy/lesson/graphic-organizer> (Retrieved on 24th February, 2024)

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Effect of Home Resources on Achievement in Fraction Concept among Secondary School Students in Mkpát Enin Local Government Area

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Abstract

The study investigated the use of home resources as instructional resource on junior secondary students' academic achievement in fractions in Mkpát Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Three research questions and corresponding research hypotheses guided the study. A quasi-experimental research design specifically, pre-test post-test non-randomized control group design was used. The population of the study consists of 2076 junior secondary school two (JS2) mathematics students in all Government owned co- educational secondary schools in Mkpát Enin Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State during the 2023/2024 academic session. The study sample size of 114 (Male, 51 and Female, 63) Junior Secondary School class Two (JSS2) Students were selected using criterion sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a researcher – developed 50- item 4- optioned multiple-choice test tagged: Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) with a reliability index of 0.79, determined using test-retest method. The data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation to answer research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed a significant difference in the academic achievement of students taught fractions using home resources and those not exposed to home resources. It can be concluded from the findings that students taught mathematics using home resources achieved better and retained significantly better when compared with their counterparts taught using charts. Also, gender was found not to be a significant factor affecting students' achievement in the study. As such, the recommendation made was that mathematics teachers should make effective use of home resources in teaching the concept of fractions.

Keywords: Home Resources, Achievement, Fraction.

Introduction

The ministry of education is not just trying to punish students by making mathematics a compulsory subject in our educational system. Mathematics is essential for our daily tasks. One cannot just make it through a successful day without using some sort of basic mathematical skills. We use mathematics every day if we must successfully perform real-life skills like grocery shopping, cooking, measurements of all sorts and tracking our finances. What makes mathematics special is that it's a universal language, that is, a powerful tool with the same meaning across the globe. Though languages divide our world, numbers unite us. Mathematics allow us to work together towards new innovations and ideas (Babayemi & Kareem, 2019; Crowe, 2022). Despite these numerous benefits of mathematics, many students experience roadblocks and hurdles in the study of mathematics. Some mathematics difficulties experienced by students include increasing level of complexity, Fear of failure, anxiety, abstractness, understanding of concepts, principles and mathematical relationships with other subjects, memorizing of formulae, interpretation of symbols, and many other difficulties (Crowe, 2022), Nisbet, 2019, Radiamoda, 2024). The issue of academic achievement in mathematics has become a focus of many educators (Babayemi, Ahmed, Yisau & Babalola, 2016; Babayemi, & Ahmed, 2019). The alarming issue in mathematics could be discussed from the social aspect and each individual point of view (Murugan and Rajoo, 2013). The social aspect includes learning environment which seems to affirm the consistency of relationship between learning environment and students' cognitive as well as effective outcomes (Ashby & McNary, 2011; Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014).

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The issue of academic achievement in mathematics has been of great concern to many educators. Barowski and Carter (2021) defined academic achievement as the amount of academic content a student learns in a specific period. This can be in any way a student has achieved his or her short- term or long-term academic goals within an academic setting. They went ahead to state that academic achievement must be measurable, which is the reason distinct goals are used as a defining characteristic. There is a time parameter that measures the amount of the academic success a student has garnered. Testing and assessments are usually performed to gauge students' academic achievement. Drew (2023) explained the meaning of academic achievement as the level of success or achievement attained by an individual in an academic setting. It encompasses a broad range of factors including grades, test scores, research outcomes and overall academic performance. Academic achievement is valued by both educational institutions and employers. /blog/training-the-difference-methods)

The teaching and learning of Mathematics has always been a challenge for educators and students alike (Babayemi, Itighise, Umanah, Abasi, & Umoh, 2023). Traditional methods often rely heavily on abstract concepts and pencil-and-paper exercises, which can make it difficult for students to grasp mathematical concepts and see their real-world applications. However, recent educational research has highlighted the importance of hands-on, experiential learning approaches that engage students and connect mathematics to their everyday lives. One key advantage of using home resources in mathematics instruction is their ability to provide real-world context (Wright and Rowland, 2017). Research has shown that students often struggle to connect abstract mathematical concepts with real-life applications. By incorporating home resources, such as kitchen scales, measuring cups, or thermometers, into mathematical tasks, educators can bridge the gap between theory and practice. Studies have indicated that this integration of real-world context enhances student engagement and promotes a deeper understanding of mathematical principles (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014; Johnson, 2017).

Home resources can facilitate mathematical communication by providing concrete objects that students can manipulate and discuss. For instance, collaborative activities involving resources, can encourage students to explain their reasoning, justify their solutions, and engage in mathematical discourse. Studies have demonstrated that the use of home resources as tools for communication can enhance students' ability to articulate mathematical ideas, develop precise language, and engage in mathematical discussions (Babayemi, & Utibe, 2017; Kaiser & Dick, 2023). The use of home resources in mathematics instruction can contribute to equity and accessibility in education. Many students have prior knowledge and experience with home resources, making them familiar and relatable tools for mathematical learning. By leveraging this familiarity, educators can create inclusive learning environments that cater to students' diverse backgrounds and experiences. Moreover, home appliances are often readily available and affordable, reducing barriers to access and ensuring that all students can participate in hands-on mathematical activities (Babayemi & Olagunju, 2015; Saiz and Espinel, 2013). Resources in the home that can be used to teach fractions are : cups, pails, juice bottles, window frames, measuring scales, spoons, among others. A fraction shows part of a whole. This whole can be a region or a collection. The word fraction is derived from the Latin word 'fractio' which means 'to break'. The Egyptians, being the earliest civilization to study fractions, used fractions to resolve their mathematical problems, which included the division of food, supplies, and the absence of a bullion currency. In Ancient Rome, fractions were only written using words to describe a part of the whole. In India, the fractions were first written with one number above another (numerator and denominator), but without a line known as the fraction bar. It was the Arabs, who added the line which is used to separate the numerator and the denominator. Fractions represent the parts of a whole or collection of objects. A fraction has two parts. The number on the top of the line is called the numerator. It tells how many equal parts of the whole or collection are taken. The number below the line is called the denominator. It shows the total number of equal parts the whole is divided into or the total number of the same objects in a collection (Nisbet, 2022).

In mathematics, a fraction refers to a part or portion of a whole thing or a collection of things. It is usually written as a ratio of two integers separated by a solidus (/) or a vinculum. It shows how many parts or portions are given to the first person (example, Susan = 1/8) and how many parts or portions are given to the second person (example, Tom = 2/8).The number on top of the solidus/vinculum is called the Numerator and the number under the solidus/vinculum is called the Denominator (Crowe, 2019).

Statement of the problem

Mathematics have been evidently giving tough time to learners in our educational system. Many learners have difficulty in mathematics when transiting from primary to secondary school with a serious decline in motivation, interest and achievement. Many of the learners even have preconceived ideas of abstractness. Teachers inadequate use of instructional

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materials worsen matters in making mathematics look like a useless adventure (Pettersson & Xenophonos, 2023). Hence, this research work, intending to use home resources to teach mathematics to junior secondary school students, in a bit to reduce the abstractness and thereby increasing the achievement of students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to assess the use of home resources in teaching mathematics, on the achievement of junior secondary students using the concept of fraction. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the achievement of students taught mathematics using home resources and those taught using charts;
2. determine the achievement of male and female students taught mathematics using home resources and those exposed to charts

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. What is the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using home resources and those taught using charts?
2. What is the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using home resources and those exposed to charts?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using home resources and those taught using charts;
2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using home resources and those exposed to charts.

Methodology

The Design for this study is quasi-experimental research design using the pretest posttest non-randomized control group design. This is because intact classes were used. Also, the administrative setup in the school is such that students were already organized in classes and the administrators would not allow the classes to be disorganized for the purpose of the Study. Mkpato Enin is a town and a Local Government Area (LGA) in Akwa Ibom State in Nigeria's south-central region. It is around 185 m (607 feet) above sea level. Mkpato Enin LGA has an area of 322 square kilometers (124 sq mi) and it's the second largest local government area in Akwa Ibom state. The LGA is located within the industrial belt extending from Eastern Obolo, Etinan, Oruk Anam, Onna, to Ikot Abasi. The people are traditionally Ibibio speakers. The population was about 178,000 in 2006. The area is rich in oil and natural gas; oil was discovered in Ikot Akpa/Ekop as early as 1953. Forest reserves in the local government area include timber and palm produce. The population of this study comprised all Junior Secondary two (JS2) mathematics students in all Government owned co-educational secondary schools in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. There were 2076 Junior secondary two (JS2) mathematics students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area for 2023/2024 session. (Local Education Committee, Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, 2022). The sample of 114 JS2 students in two co-educational secondary schools in the study area were selected for the study using criterion sampling technique. The criteria used were: the school must be co-educational, must have presented candidates for Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) examination for not less than ten years and must have qualified Mathematics teachers with more than five years of teaching experience. Simple random sampling technique was used to select one intact class from the two secondary schools, among others, that met the criteria for the study. The selected schools were randomly assigned as experimental group and control group.

The research instrument is a researcher made test titled "Mathematics Achievement Test" (MAT). It consisted of two sections, A and B. Section A elicits background information relating to the students such as name of school and gender while section B comprised 50 multiple choice objectives test items. Each item has options A, B, C and D with only one correct answer and three distracters. The questions were selected from a pool of multi-choice questions from WAEC past questions on the concept of Fractions. The Test was used to elicit the scores for pretest and posttest of students on the concept of fractions when

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taught using home facilities. The instrument: Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was submitted for validation to two lecturers in the Department of Science education, University of Uyo, and two selected secondary schools' teachers for face validation while the content validation was done using table of specification. Their scrutiny bordered on the usability of the instrument by the test takers, and the appropriateness of the instrument. All the corrections and comments made up the final research instrument which was then submitted to the researcher's supervisor. To Further strengthen the Research Instrument, the twenty (20) multiple choice test item were administered to a trial group of fifty (50) JS3 student of the same population who do not form part of the main sample for the study. The test-retest method was used to determine the reliability. The test was administered to the mathematics students on the permission of their principal and an assistance of the mathematics teacher. After two weeks the same test (but reshuffled) was administered again to the same students and the result recorded. The two results were subjected to Pearson Product correlation coefficient and a reliability index of .79 was obtained.

The researcher personally visited the Principal and Mathematics teachers of the two selected public secondary schools with an introductory letter to obtain permission to use their schools for the study and also to seek for the cooperation of the mathematics teachers of the selected class (JS3) to assist in carrying out the study. One (JS 3) mathematics teacher in each school served as research assistants. The study lasted for four weeks; the first week was for visitation and training of the research assistance on the modalities of the research work, while the second week was for administering pretest and introducing the concept of Calculus to the student. The third and fourth week was for teaching the concept and administering of posttest.

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Research Question one

What is the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using home resources and those taught using charts?

Table 1:

Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Posttest Scores using pretest as covariate for students taught Using home resources and charts.

Method	N	X	SD
Home Resources	60	13.95	2.76
Charts	54	10.81	1.18

Source: Field work (2023/2024)

As shown in Table 1, the mean achievement score of students taught mathematics using resources is 13.95 while those taught using chart is 10.81. It can be inferred from the mean scores that, students taught using home resources had a higher mean score when compared to those taught using charts.

Research Question Two

What is the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using home resources and those exposed to charts?

Table 2:

Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Posttest Scores using pretest as covariate for male and female students taught using home resources.

Gender	N	X	SD
Male	51	13.04	2.76
Female	63	15.35	13.96

Source: Field work (2023/2024)

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As shown in Table 2, the mean achievement score of male students taught mathematics through the use of home resources is 13.04 while their female counterparts had a mean score of 15.35. It can be inferred from the mean scores that female students taught using home resources achieved better than their male counterparts when taught using home resources.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement score of students taught mathematics using home resources and those taught using charts.

Table 4:

Analysis Of Covariance Of Students' Post Achievement Scores taught using Home Resources and Charts Using Pretest Scores as Covariate.

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F _{cal}	P-value _{cal}
Pretest	240.65	1	240.65	93.94	.00
Teaching Aids(Home resource)	295.94	1	295.94	115.53	.00
Residual	284.35	111	2.56		
Total	820.94	113	7.26		

*=Significant at .05 level of significance

As shown in Table 4, the calculated F-value, 115.5 of teaching aids (home resources and charts) was found significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypotheses stating that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement score of the students taught mathematics using home resources and those taught using charts, is rejected. This implies that there exists a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using home resources and charts.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement score of male and female students taught mathematics using home resources.

Table 5:

Analysis of Covariance of Students' Post Achievement Scores given their gender taught using Home Resources and Charts Using Pretest Scores as Covariate.

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F _{cal}	P-value _{cal}
Pretest	384.39	1	384.39	3.53	.06
Gender	205.74	1	205.74	1.89	.17
Residual	12083.85	111	108.86		
Total	12673.98	113	112.16		

*=Significant at .05 level of significance

As shown in Table 5, the calculated F-value, 1.89 of teaching aids (home resources and charts) was found significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypotheses stating that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement score of the students taught mathematics using home resources and those taught using charts, is retained. This implies that there exists a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using home resources and charts.

Discussion of Findings

The findings on the difference between the mean achievement score of students taught mathematics using home resources and those taught using charts indicated a significant difference. Students taught mathematics using home resources achieved significantly better than those taught using charts. The findings could be attributed to the fact that home resources are great motivational tool as students' interest increased when taught using it. The findings corroborate the findings of Ogan and Ibilio, (2022) which found out that students taught mathematics using home resources showed improvement. The findings of the study are in line with that of Udofia and Uko (2023) who found out that home resources enhanced more and improved significantly the achievement of students in mathematics than charts in Akwa Ibom State. The findings of this study are also in

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consonance with the work of Rohani, (2020) who found out that there was a significant difference in mathematical achievement between the home resources group and charts.

The findings on the difference between the mean achievement score of male and female students taught mathematics using home resources and charts indicated a non-significant difference. The findings could be as a result of the fact that both male and female students' interest was stimulated by the use of home resources. It appealed to both male and female students thereby boosting their achievements. The findings of the study corroborate the study of Emaikwu, Iji and Abari, (2023) whose study revealed that both male and female students in experimental group achieved the same and also showed similar interest in statistics when determining the effect of home resources on Junior Secondary school students' interest and achievement in mathematics. Conversely, a study conducted by Olagunju and Babayemi (2014) reported difference in the academic achievement of male and female students in experimental and control groups.

The findings on the difference between the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using home resources and those taught using charts indicated a significant difference. Students taught mathematics using home resources retained significantly better than those taught using charts. The findings could be attributed to the fact that home resources is a tool capable of capturing and maintaining the interest of students. The findings is in line with the findings of Abari, Gimba, Hassan and Jiya (2023) whose study revealed that students taught mathematics using home resources instructional package retained higher mean scores than those taught using charts while determining the effect of home resources instructional package on secondary school students' retention in mathematics in Markurdi metropolis of Benue state. Similarly, finding revealed that the finding is in conformity with the study of Olojede, Bolaji and Musa (2017) whose findings revealed that the use of ICT in teaching the concept of Geometry contributes towards raising the students' retention ability in Geometry.

Conclusion

It can be concluded from the findings that students taught mathematics using home resources achieved better and retained significantly better when compared with their counterparts taught using charts. Also, gender was found not to be a significant factor affecting students' achievement in the study.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the conclusions reached, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers of mathematics should embrace and adopt the use of home resources in teaching mathematics.
2. Educational policy makers such as National Education Research Development Council (NERDC), Curriculum planners and Ministry of Education should incorporate the use of home resources in the curriculum
3. Mathematical organizations such as Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN) and Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) should organize training programs, workshops and seminars on the use of home resources in the classroom for teachers.

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References

- Ashby, J., Sadera, W. A., & McNary S., W., (2011): *Comparing Student Success Between Developmental Math Courses Offered Online, Blended, And Face-To-Face*. Journal of Interactive Online Learning Volume 10, Number 3, Winter 2011 ISSN: 1541-4914 www.ncolr.org/jjol

Effect of Home Resources ... (George & Onwiodukit, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15069639>

- Babayemi, J.O. & Ahmed, A.A. (2019). Effects of enhanced conventional lecture method and gender on students' achievement in basic science. *Journal of Contemporary Education Research (JCER)*, 13 (6), 242-256.
- Babayemi, J.O., Ahmed, A.A., Yisau, S.O. & Babalola, G.T. (2016). Effect of enhanced conventional lecture method on students' academic achievement in basic science in Oyo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Benchmark (July/August)*, 5(2), 74-88
- Babayemi, J.O., Itighise, A. E., Umanah, F. I., Abasi, A.U. & Umoh, E.B. (2023). Teaching subject challenges and area of teaching subject: implication for secondary school science, technology and mathematics teachers. *International Journal of Educational Research and Human Development*, 4(4), 25-41.
- Babayemi, J.O. & Kareem, A.A. (2019). Services in secondary schools science laboratory as centre for innovation in basic science and technology in Akwa Ibom state. *60th annual conference of science teachers' association of Nigeria*, 254-262.
- Babayemi, J.O. & Utibe, U.J. (2017). Communicating research findings in basic science and technology for technological development, *MATTER: International Journal of Science and Technology*, 3 (1), 01-15.
- Babayemi, J.O. & Olagunju, A. M. (2015). A Survey of pre-service teachers' skills for improvising educational resources for effective instruction in basic science. *African Journal of Educational Research (AJER)*, 19 (1 & 2), 64-76.
- Barowski, J. and Carter, V. (2021). Academic achievement and overview, definition and research. Retrieved on February 4th 2024 at www.study.com
- Johnson, E. E., & Serdyukov, P. (2017). *Connecting Mathematics to Everyday Life: A Collaboration Between Mathematicians and Teachers*. *International Journal of Research in Undergraduate Mathematics Education*, 3(3), 315-342.
- Kaiser, G., & Dick, T. P. (2013). *Proportional Reasoning in Science and Mathematics Education*. Springer.
- Ministry of Education (New Zealand). (2007). *The New Zealand Curriculum: Mathematics Standards*. Wellington, NZ: Author.
- Murugan, A. & Rajoo, L. (2013): Students' Perceptions of Mathematics Classroom Environment & Mathematics Achievement: A Study in Sipitang, Sabah, Malaysia: Proceeding of The International Conference on Social Science Research, Icssr 2013 (E-Isbn 978-967- 11768-1- 8). 4-5 June 2013, Penang, Malaysia. Organized By Worldconferences.Net
- National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM). (2000). *Principles and Standards for School Mathematics*. Reston, VA: Author.
- National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM). (2014). *Principles to Actions: Ensuring Mathematical Success for All*. Reston, VA: Author.
- National Research Council (NRC). (2001). *Adding It Up: Helping Children Learn Mathematics*. National Academies Press.
- Olagunju, A.M & Babayemi, J.O. (2014). Effects of enhanced explicit teaching (explicit teaching + peer-tutoring) strategy and gender on students' attitude to basic science. *J. of Education and Leadership Development*, 6(2), 135-150.
- Olagunju, A.M & Babayemi, J.O. (2014). Effects of crossword-picture puzzle teaching strategy and gender on students' achievement in basic science. *J. of Education and Leadership Development*, 6(1), 43 – 54.
- Petterson J. M. and Xenophontos, C. (2023). The Construction of Mathematical Identities Among Adolescents. <https://www.tandfonline.com/journal/oaed20> (Retrieved on May, 2024).
- Sáiz, M., & Espinel, M. J. (2013). *Promoting the Use of Real-World Contexts and Tools in Mathematics Classrooms*. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 82(1), 97-114.
- Wright, R. J., & Rowland, T. (2017). *Teaching Mathematics in the Secondary School: Developing as a Reflective Secondary Teacher*. Routledge.

Effect of Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time on Performance in Algebra among Polytechnics Students in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Performance in mathematics is regard to as global problem. This paper investigated the “Effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria. One research question and a corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Two public polytechnics made up the population of the Study consists of all polytechnic students in cross river state during the 2023/2024 academic session with a sample size of 44 students were selected using multi-stage sampling technique. The methodology of the study is pretest and posttest quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The experimental and control groups were exposed to Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time and Lecture Method respectively. The experimental group ware taught Algebra using Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time while the control group ware taught algebra using Lecture method. Algebraic Performance Test (APT) was designed by the researchers for data collection. The reliability coefficient of Algebraic Performance Test (APT) was determined to be 0.85. The data collected were analyzed using Mean scores, Standard deviation and t-test at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. The findings revealed that there is significant difference between performance of students taught algebra using Lecture-Enriched Wait-Time and those exposed to conventional lecture teaching method. Better performance was recorded on student that were taught algebraic concepts using lecture-enriched wait-time compared to their counterpart that were taught using lecture method. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that lecture-enriched wait-time should be used to teach mathematics at national diploma level.

Keyword: Lecture-enriched wait-time, algebra, performance

Introduction

Mathematics is one of the school subjects with wide applications which can not be separated from our day to day activities. It considered as the universal language throughout the world. It techniques includes counting, arithmetic, mensuration, geometry, trigonometry, computations and algebra, with the ability to think about situations related to a given quantity (Cawley *et al*, 1998). Mathematics is a fundamental branch of Science that represents the study of basic concepts of Numbers, Space and Quantity as well as application of these concepts in the field of Physics and Engineering (Ale, 2006). Poor performance in the subject area becomes of great concern to our society, educators and government at large. Nneji (2013), described performance as the gain in knowledge of students as a result of taking part in learning activity or programme. For effective learning to be efficiently taken, we need the right approaches and methods. There are so many devices for effective teaching and an effective technique can ensure effective learning. It is being felt that there should be new techniques of teaching and learning (Iqbal, 2004). The search of teaching and learning devices for effective performance has lead to the identification of wait-time (Lee, 2000). Any behavior, practice or techniques that will enable students develop thinking skills will help them

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to acquire technology concepts, which will lead to better achievement. Hurd in UNESCO (1995) pointed out that the methodology for teaching must enable students to think and ask questions during classroom lesson. One way of developing students' thinking skill is to ask questions in the classroom to facilitate discussion and to get the students to think (Adsit, 2002). There is therefore a good link between teaching methods and questioning. The importance of question cannot be over emphasised, question can be used by teachers in the classrooms to determine whether or not body of knowledge has been impacted and to determine how much has been learned. It can be used for evaluation of method of teaching and for students placement. According to Baba (2022) wait-time is when a teacher waits after a question is asked before calling on a student to rephrase a question or supply the answer. Wait-time is the amount of time a teacher allows, after asking a question, before getting response from students (wait-time I). It is also a period of uninterrupted silence allowed by the teacher after receiving a student's response and before he/she comments or asks another question (wait-time II). Research has shown that for both wait-time I and II, teachers typically wait for an average of one second or less (Kissock and Iyortsuun, 1982; Ouyang, 2000; Cotton, 2001 and Camp, 2002). Increasing wait-time to three seconds or more has been found to increase students' achievement and interest (Stahl as cited in Owodunni, 2013, Rowe as cited in Lee, 2000 and Cotton, 2001). Opataye (2020), study the effectiveness of classroom questioning wait – time on senior secondary school students' academic performance and reflective thinking in chemistry, it was shown that, chemistry students that were given questioning wait - time performed better and with higher reflective thinking in chemistry.

Effective questioning is an instrument of motivation to raise the interest of students in what is being learnt (Eze, 2008). Raising students' interest helps them to learn better and most likely retain what is learnt for a longer period and subsequently, achievement would be enhanced. Owodunni (2013), investigate the comparative effects of long wait - time and shifting interaction questioning techniques on basic electricity students academic achievement in technical colleges. It was showed that shifting interaction questioning technique is more effective in enhancing students' achievement in basic electricity. There are different types of learners including fast learners, average learners, and slow learners (Korikana, 2020). This learning difficulty may arise from poor memory, unawareness about the importance of education and lack of fundamental knowledge and psychological factors Dalhatu, *et al* (2023), investigate the effect of extended wait-time on low achievers performance and retention in ecology among secondary school Biology students in Zaria educational zone, it was shown that low achievers that were taught ecology using extended wait-time had better performance compared those that were taught using conventional lecture method. The fact that students continue to fail algebra in tertiary institutions (polytechnics) in large number shows that there is a need for more empirical studies in order to improve the situation. Thus, this research, investigate effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria. As part of the National Board for Technical Education Curriculum, algebra is a core course for all sciences, engineering and environmental technology. Algebra as one of the studied areas that deals with the representation of problems or situations in the form of mathematical expressions. All the branches of mathematics needs algebra. The study of algebra starts with solving of equations such as polynomials equations. Algebra and elementary trigonometry is almost a general course to all students of sciences, engineering technology, environmental technology and even in some management courses. Despite its importance, there is high level poor performance in subject area. This paper, study the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem:

Performance in mathematics has been a central issue to Mathematics educators (Okeagu, 2013). This poor performance has continued at successive years especially in our schools. Despite the importance of mathematics in science and technology, the issue of poor performance at the end of semester examination becomes a major concern to our academics institutions, which may be as a result of teaching methodology by mathematics teachers/Lecturers. This trend defiles the effort made by Federal Government of Nigeria by making the subject compulsory at all stages of learning (Iliyasu, 2016). In our march toward scientific and technological advancement we need nothing short of good performance in mathematics. Unfortunately, performance of student in mathematics at the end of semester examination has not improved in the past decade. There is dire need for solution to the problem of poor performance in mathematics especially algebra, in order for Nigeria to join the community of developed nations. Iji (2005) has stated that teaching approaches and strategy used in the classrooms by teachers are the root course of this undesirable poor performance in mathematics. Many researchers have carried out investigations on how to remedy the situation. Dalhatu, *et al* (2023), investigate the effect of extended wait-time on low achievers performance and retention in ecology among secondary school Biology students in Zaria educational zone, it was shown that low achievers that were taught ecology using extended wait-time had better performance compared those that were

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taught using conventional lecture method. The fact that students continue to fail algebra in tertiary institutions (polytechnics) in large number shows that there is a need for more empirical studies in order to improve the situation. Thus, this paper, investigate the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

To determine the effect of Lecture-Enriched wait-time on academic performance in algebra among polytechnics students.

Research Questions:

What are the differences in the mean academic performance scores students taught algebraic concept using lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with lecture method?

Hypotheses:

The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught algebraic concepts using lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre- test, post-test and post posttest non-equivalent control group design. The essence of pre-test was to determine the academic equivalence of the two groups before the treatment while post-posttest was to determine the performance of the student after the treatment. Pre-test was administered to both sampled polytechnics so as to determine their academic equivalence. The records were kept, then the control group were taught algebra using conventional method of teaching while the experimental group were taught using algebra using Lecture – Enriched Wait - time for eight (8) weeks. Then, post-test was administered to both the control and the experimental groups. The periods for the teaching of each group is two hours per group. This was done by the aid of research assistants who were given a guide on how to handle the classes as well as the wait-time devices in accordance with the Lecture - Enriched wait –time. The population of the study comprised the two public polytechnics in Cross River State of Nigeria with a total number of 44 National Diploma I students offering algebra at the time that this data was collected. The instrument for this study is Algebraic Performance Test (APT). The reliability coefficient of Algebraic Performance Test (APT) was determined to be 0.85. For the purpose of generating and analyzing data, APT comprises ten (10) essay test questions were developed for the study, which allowed the students to write their understanding on the algebraic concepts.

Presentation of Result

The result of the analysis was used to answer the research question using descriptive statistics while inferential statistics was used to test the null hypothesis at alpha $\alpha = 0.05$ level significance.

Research Question 1

What are the differences in the mean academic performance scores students taught algebraic concept using lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with lecture method?

This question was answered by determining the mean score between the two groups, using descriptive statistics and the results is as presented in table 1

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation of students of experimental and control groups

Group	N	Pretest Mean	SD	Posttest Mean	SD
Experimental	16	13.9	2.8	27	4.3
Control	28	12.6	2.2	19	3.2
Mean difference		1.3		8	
Total	44				

Table 1 shows that the students that were taught with lecture-enriched wait-time method has the highest mean scores of 27 while those taught with traditional lecture method has the minimum mean scores of 19. This shows that the students in the experimental group had some level of improvement as a result of exposure to lecture-enriched wait-time. The standard deviation is an indicative value of wide variability between the scores of the group.

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Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught algebraic concepts with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method.

To test this hypothesis, the pretest and the posttest of each experimental and control groups are analyzed.

Table 2: Wilcoxon sign rank test of mean performance scores of students taught Algebra with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional lecture method

Total number of students (N)	Mean	T	Var.	t-calculated	t-critical
44	5365.5	1788.5	511.87	-6.99	1.96

Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 2 shows that the absolute value of t- calculated (6.99) is greater than t- critical (1.96) then we reject H_{01} . thus, it means that there is significant difference between lower achievers taught algebraic concepts with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method.

Discussion of Findings

The research work investigated the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria. One hypothesis was stated and tested based on lecture – enriched wait – time and Algebra Performance Test (APT) was developed and administered to the sampled groups consisting of 44 students. The collected from the sampled population was analyze using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Analysis of the data collected are presented in table 1 and 2 in accordance with the stated hypothesis. The results of the analyses related to the hypothesis one indicated that, a significant difference exists in the mean performance scores of students taught algebraic concepts with lecture-enriched wait-time and those taught with conventional method. This significant difference found in the performance of students taught algebra was in favor of the experimental group. This is inline with the study of Dalhatu, *et al* (2023) which shown that low achievers that were taught ecology using extended wait-time had better performance compared those that were taught using conventional lecture method.

Conclusion

The paper study the effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on performance in algebra among polytechnics students in Cross River State, Nigeria. It was shown that better performance was recorded on student that were taught algebraic concepts using lecture-enriched wait-time compared to their counterpart that were taught using lecture method.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- xii. The use of lecture-enriched wait-time should be encouraged among lecturers teaching algebra more especially at ND level.
- xiii. Government agencies such as Federal and State Ministry of Education, NBTE and other stakeholders in educational sector should organize workshop on lecture-enriched wait-time to all lecturers taking lower level students.

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References

- Adsit, K. I. (2012). Integrating inquiry – based field investigation into an environmental science curriculum. Journal of the Tennessee Academy of Science 87(2), 105 - 115.*
- Ale, S.O, (2006). Key note address presented at 4th Zonal workshop on the use Primary Mathematics Kits project held at Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku Rivers States.*

Effect of Lecture-Enriched Wait ... (Hassan, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15069652>

- Baba, H., & Abdul Talib, C. B. (2022). Effect of lecture-enriched wait-time on the performance of average and high ability SSII chemistry students in mole concept. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(7), 738 – 747.
- Camp, W. G. (2002). Improving your teaching through effective questioning techniques. <http://www.aged.vt.edu/methods/que-skil.htm.on.line07082023>.
- Cawley, J. F., Parmar, R., Yan, W., & Miller, J. H. (1998). Arithmetic computation performance of students with learning disabilities: Implications for curriculum. *Learning Disabilities Research and Practice* 13(2), 68-74
- Cotton, K. (2001). Instructional Reinforcement. <http://www.nwre.org/scpd/sir/2/cu3.html>
- Dalhatu, H. U., Salisu, Z. I. & Abdulkarim, M. M. (2023). Impact of wait-time variations on retention ability and gender performance among low achievers in ecology at senior secondary schools in Zaria. *African Journal of Humanities & Contemporary Education Research*, 11(1), 212 – 223.
- Eze, C. C. (2008). Comparative effects of two questioning techniques on students' achievement and retention in Chemistry. Unpublished M.Ed thesis, University of Nigeria, Nsukka
- Iqbal, M. (2004). Effect of cooperative learning in academic achievement of secondary school students in mathematics. Unpublished P.hD. thesis University of Arid Agriculture Rawalpindi (Pakistan).
- Korikana, A. (2020). Slow Learners- A Universal Problem and Providing Educational Opportunities to Them to Be a Successful Learner". *PEOPLE: International Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(1), 29-42.
- Kissock, C. & Iyortsunn, P. T. (1982). *A Guide to Questioning: Classroom procedure for Teachers*. London: Macmillan Press limited.
- Lee, R. W. (2000). Questioning as an instructional method: Does it affect learning from lectures. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 23(6), 747 – 759.
- [Lowestan, D. \(2002\). Best practice in facilitating school reform: Best practice in school psychology Iv. National Association of School Psychologists.](#)
- Nneji, S. O. (2013). Effect of Polya George's Problem Solving Model on Students' Performance and Retention in Algebra. *Journal of Education and Social Research*, 3(6), 41-48.
- Opataye, J. A. (2020). Effectiveness of Classroom Questioning Wait Time on Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance and Reflective Thinking in Chemistry. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 18(2), 59-73.
- Owodunni, A. S. Comparative Effects of Long Wait -Time and Shifting Interaction Questioning Techniques on Basic Electricity Students Academic Achievement in Technical Colleges. Proceedings of International Conference on Mathematics, Science and Technology Education, held at Limpopo, South Africa from 21st – 24th October, 2013.
- Ouyang, J. R. (2000). Questioning Techniques. <https://pigseye.kennesaw.edu/~rouyang/ece4473/q-techni.Htm.l>
- Rowe, M. (1987). Wait-time: Slowing down may be a way of Speeding up. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 37(1), 38 – 43.
- Stahl, R. J. (1994). Using Think Time and Wait-time skilfully in the classroom. ERIC Development Team. www.eric.ed.gov
- UNESCO (1995). *Integrated Science in African Schools, Ibadon*. Heine,ann Education Books Nigerian PLC.

Effect of Linear-Power-Point Instruction on Performance in Trigonometry Concepts among Senior Secondary School Mathematics Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess effect of Linear-Power-Point Instruction on Performance in Trigonometry concepts among senior secondary school Mathematics students in Katsina State, Nigeria. The research design of this study is quasi-experimental design. The population is made up of 69932 (41196 males and 28736 females) senior secondary school class two (SS II) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina state. A sample of 199 SSII students (Male 123 and Female 76) was chosen through a multistage sampling technique. One instrument, the Trigonometry Performance Test used to gather data for the study. This instrument was validated by experts and after pilot testing, demonstrated high reliability with estimates of 0.83. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was utilized to answer the research questions, while t-test was employed to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study indicated that there was a statistically significant difference in the mean performance scores of the students taught using Linear PowerPoint group and non-digital technology groups. Based on these findings, it was recommended that Linear PowerPoint Instructional packages should be encouraged in schools for teaching Trigonometry.

Keywords: Linear Power Point, Non-digital technology, Teaching Strategies

Introduction

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education has significantly transformed teaching methodologies, particularly in the domain of mathematics. Among the various ICT tools, PowerPoint presentations have emerged as a pivotal resource for educators. PowerPoint, a widely utilized presentation software, offers a dynamic and interactive platform for disseminating information, thereby enhancing the teaching and learning experience. Nigeria government in her National Policy on Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in Education boldly expressed the impossibility of qualitative education in 21st-century without integration of ICT into education (FGN, 2019).

PowerPoint is a standard part of the Microsoft Office software package which is used for preparing a sequence of slides that are displayed to the audience on a computer guided monitor. Presentation developed with this type of software can be saved digitally and easily modified, facilitating future use. Microsoft PowerPoint allows teachers to include chart clip, art photographs, sound or video segments to demonstrate concepts (Effiong & Ekpo-eloma, 2016; Marcovitz 2021). The above description portrait linear format of PowerPoint that is, each slide is designed to proceed one slide right after another. The first slide transits to the second, which transit to the third, and so forth (Garth, 2021). The traditional PowerPoint presentation is known as a “slide show” which includes a series of screens presented one after another.

Fig. 1 illustration of Linear Power Point

The utilization of linear PowerPoint presentations can substantially empower teachers by providing a structured and visually engaging medium for content delivery. This approach facilitates the incorporation of multimedia elements such as images, videos, and animations, which can elucidate complex mathematical concepts and cater to diverse learning styles. By leveraging these features, educators can create more engaging and effective instructional materials (Mensah & Nabie, 2021). Empirical research underscores the efficacy of PowerPoint in enhancing mathematics performance. For instance, a study by

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Mensah and Nabie (2021) demonstrated that students instructed via PowerPoint presentations exhibited higher achievement and motivation compared to those taught through traditional methods. The visual nature of PowerPoint aids in sustaining student interest and engagement, which are critical for effective learning. Furthermore, the adaptability of PowerPoint presentations allows educators to tailor their lessons to the specific needs of their students, thereby fostering a more personalized learning environment. Linear PowerPoint presentation remained the most commonly integrated DPT in the classroom. Linear PowerPoint is a pattern of PowerPoint slide design that proceed one slide right after another. The sheer popularity of this presentation tool comes from the belief that representation of information using auditory and visual inputs improves learning (Mayer & Moreno, 2017).

Linear PowerPoint is said to be very effective in drawing and maintaining students’ attention and this is reported to have a positive impact on students’ academic performance and motivation (Erdemir, 2014; Savoy, Proctor & Salvendy, 2014; Wofford, 2014). Linear PowerPoint appeals to sight and hearing which are the most used senses in teaching and learning activities (Gambari, Zubairu, Daramola, Abubakar, & Tukura. 2018). This mode of technology integration, however, is a semi-compromised 21st-century learning environment. The learners only received information presented by the teacher through digital technologies but they are not actually using digital technology to construct knowledge. The suitability of Linear PowerPoint, therefore, for digital natives (21st-century learners) has been questioned because the issue of students using previous knowledge to construct new knowledge through interaction with learning content is restricted (Chen, 2021).

Research reports reveals that most science teachers use the lecture method in teaching Mathematics. The method does not enhance students’ academic performance especially in the acquisition of process skills as Olariwaju, (2019) opined that, lecture method is defective because it involves verbal presentation of pre-planned lesson to the students which requires little or no instructional aid and so does not promote students’ higher level of thinking.

Lecture method according to Adeyemi (2018) is a teaching approach that entails verbal presentation of scientific facts, concepts and principles to learners. During lecture, teacher focuses the students’ attention on the key points in the lesson and may use diagrams or other representations to elaborate on the subject matter. A neglected variable in the teaching and learning of Mathematics is the students’ learning abilities Garba, (2022). The objectives of Mathematics teachers are to identify the ability of students in their classroom and device teaching strategies that could best carry along the entire class during lesson. Hence, the need for a strategy that will ease the way teacher teaches is important through integrating technology into teaching and learning, example; linear PowerPoint and so on.

Figure 2
Theoretical Framework

Knowledge Transmission theorist see learners as “sponge” considered to be empty vessels, blank slates, or passive observers. The assumption has been that if teachers speak clearly and students are motivated, learning will occur. If students do not learn it is because they are not paying attention or they do not care. These ideas were grounded in theories of learning that focused on behavior. One behavior leads to another, behavioral-learning theorists argued, and so if teachers act in a certain way, students will likewise act in a certain way. According to Gagne and Medsker (1996) in Fakomologbon (2016), “behaviorist

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theories assumed that learning could be studied and facilitated by manipulating only the external environment of the learner, observing the learner's overt behaviour and managing the external consequences of that behavior.

The theory is relevance to the present study in diverse ways. First of all, the teaching and learning environment in Nigeria school only compliance with behaviorist theories of what teacher and students do in teaching and learning process. Teacher present the topic and convince learner that that is the fact and they must master it in order to pass examination. This fact is also presented in non-digital technology that supported them such as maps, textbook chalkboard among others. This method has recorded a great success as it has recorded same great failure, (Adegoke, 2017). What success then can be ascribed to it, is it in knowledge acquisition or knowledge application? On the other hand, the theory is inadequate for the present study. The theory is based on operant conditioning and classical conditioning whose principles give insufficient opportunities for student to construct their own learning (Wilson & Peterson, 2015).

The dual coding theory proposed by Paivio attempts to give equal weight to verbal and non-verbal processing. Paivio (1986) in Paivio (2015) expressed that human cognition is unique in that it has become specialized for dealing simultaneously with language and with nonverbal objects and events. Moreover, the language system is peculiar in that it deals directly with linguistic input and output (in the form of speech or writing) while at the same time serving a symbolic function with respect to nonverbal objects, events, and behaviors. Any representational theory must accommodate this dual functionality. The main principle of the theory is that recall/recognition is enhanced by resenting information in both visual and verbal form. The theory assumes that there are two cognitive subsystems, one specialized for the representation and processing of nonverbal objects/events (i.e., imagery), and the other specialized for dealing with language (Kearsley, 2017). Paivio also postulates two different types of representational units: "imagens" for mental images and "logogens" for verbal entities which he describes as being similar to "chunks" as described by Miller. The use of linear PowerPoint presentations can significantly enhance the teaching and learning of mathematics. By empowering educators with effective strategies and tools, it is possible to improve student performance and foster a deeper understanding of mathematical and particularly Trigonometry concepts. However, it is crucial to use these tools judiciously and provide educators with the necessary training and support to ensure their successful implementation.

Statement of the Research Problem

The researchers' observed that the teaching and learning of Trigonometry like any other subjects in Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State is still characterized by integration of non-digital technology and teacher-centered learning approaches even in the schools that have adequate digital technology at their disposal. This observation is in line with the report of Yusuf (2022) who reported that teachers in Katsina State as a whole are not ready to integrate digital technologies in teaching and learning even when these technologies are readily available. It is worth to note that Mathematics teachers' loyalty to non-digital technology integration and its corresponding teacher-centered teaching and learning approaches do not result into the desired Trigonometry learning outcomes in both affective and cognitive in Katsina State. Udoh (2011) reported that, many students find it difficult to solve mathematical problems among which is the trigonometric problem which no doubt constitutes an educational problem with serious implication. Unfortunately, despite all the relative importance of mathematics in science and other field of studies, students' performance in the subject has remained constantly poor (Adolphus, 2011).

However, WASSCE Mathematics Chief Examiners' Reports (2015-2023) reported that questions on trigonometry were poorly attempted by the candidates which contribute toward poor performance of students in mathematics in general. In an attempt to possibly promote the performance and equally solve the problems of poor performance and ability of students in trigonometry in particular and mathematics in general, technology integration using linear power point is proposed to investigate its combining significant effect from which predictions about the performance of students was made to see if it could address this problem or not. This research intended to lunch a war against the use of non-digital technology to teaching mathematics in large classes at secondary schools. And also, a war for the implementation of the use of Linear Power Point technology to teach mathematics topics particularly Trigonometry.

Objectives of the study

The Objectives of the study were to;

3. Determine the mean performance score of students taught the concept trigonometry using linear-power-point strategy and those exposed to non-digital technology in Katsina State.
4. Examine the mean performance score of male and female students taught the concept trigonometry using linear-power-point strategy in Katsina State

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Research Questions

The following questions guided the study;

13. What is the mean performance score of students taught the concept trigonometry using linear-power-point strategy and those exposed to non-digital technology in Katsina State?
14. What is the mean performance score of male and female students taught the concept trigonometry using linear-power-point strategy in Katsina State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology in Katsina State;
2. here is no significant difference between mean performance of male and female students taught trigonometry using linear power point in Katsina State

Methodology

The design adapted for this study is the quasi-experimental design specifically, pretest, posttest, non-randomized, and nonequivalent control group design. The population of the study consists of 69932(41196 males and females) senior secondary school class two (SS II) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina state. A sample of 199 SSII students (Male 123 and Female 76) was chosen through a multistage sampling technique. The Trigonometry Performance Test used to gather data for the study. This instrument was validated by experts and after pilot testing, demonstrated high reliability with estimates of 0.83.

Presentation of Result

Research Question 1 and hypothesis 1

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the mean performance of students taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology in katsina state.

Table 1

T-test analysis showing difference between the mean performance of students taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology.

Group	N	Mean	Std. D.	t-cal	DF	P-value
Linear Power Point	110	47.6545	20.02725	4.209	197	0.028
Non digital Technology	89	26.3820	17.11625			

(Field work, 2024)

The above table revealed that the mean performance students taught using Linear Power Point is (47.6545) with Standard Deviation of 20.02725 and the mean performance of students taught using Non digital Technology is (26.3820) with Standard Deviation of 17.11625. The difference in the mean performance was (11.2725). Also, the table showed that the t-cal value is (4.209) and P-value value is (0.028) which is less than the alpha value (0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis of the research was rejected and implied that there is significant difference between the mean performance of students taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology.

Research Question 2 and hypothesis 2

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between mean performance of male and female students taught trigonometry using linear power point in Katsina State

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Table 2

T-test analysis showing difference between the mean performance of male and female taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology.

Sex	N	Mean	Std. D.	t-cal	DF	P-value
Male	123	43.9837	16.96959	1.259	197	.000
Female	76	40.3947	23.09810			

(Field work, 2024)

The above table revealed that the mean performance of male taught using Linear Power Point is (43.9837) with Standard Deviation of 16.96959 and the mean performance of female taught using Non digital Technology is (40.3947) with Standard Deviation of 23.09810. The difference in the mean performance was (3.589). Also, the table showed that the t-cal value is (1.259) and P-value value is (.000) which is less than the alpha value (0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis of the research was rejected and implied that there is no significant difference between mean performance of male and female students taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology.

Discussion of Findings

This study established that there was a statistically significant difference in the mean performance scores of the students taught using Linear PowerPoint group and non-digital technology groups. The finding of the present study is in line with Adeniran, Laolu, and Ayotola (2016), Effiong and Ekpo (2016), Falode, Ojoye, Ilobeneke, Falode (2016), Gambari, Yusuf and Thomas (2015) who reported positive effect of different kind of computer assisted Computer based collaborative learning modes and Web-quest) on students' academic achievement. These studies were conduct at secondary school level using quasi experimental similar to the present study school setting and methodology.

The present study finding is also similar to the findings of Bahadur and Boodun (2013) who reported that Students taught using non-digital technology were able to learn and understand the different concepts related to water. The finding of the present study is in line with Carter, Greenberg and Walker (2016) who found that there was statistically significant difference in the attitude of students toward Trigonometry when taught using Linear PowerPoint and Non-digital technology. This finding is contrary to Falode, Ojoye, Ilobeneke, Falode (2016), Liu and Chen (2014), Gambari, Gbodi, Olakanmi, Abalaka (2016) who reported positive effect of digital instructional package on student's interest, attitude and motivation. This shows that Linear PowerPoint is capable of developing positive attitude in students toward Trigonometry.

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Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, the researchers came to the conclusion that using of digital tools, like Linear PowerPoint to teach Trigonometry has educational benefits. However, linear PowerPoint packages is more effective than non-digital

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technology because it improved students' academic performance in Mathematics particularly Trigonometry. This suggests that learners' cognitive behavior will improve when Linear PowerPoint is used to teach Trigonometry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendation were made:

- vi. Linear PowerPoint Instructional packages should be encouraged in schools for teaching Trigonometry.
- vii. Linear PowerPoint instructional Package was also found to be effective in teaching Trigonometry compared to non-digital technology of chalkboard. Teachers should use Linear PowerPoint Instructional package if they could not develop nor adapt Interactive PowerPoint instructional packages.
- viii. Concerned NGOs and Government bodies should provide adequate computer facilities that can enhance integration of Linear PowerPoint packages in teaching and learning of Trigonometry in Katsina education zone of Katsina state.

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References

- Adegoke, B. A. (2017). Effect of multimedia instruction on senior secondary school students' achievement in Physics. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 3(3), 537-541.
- Adeyemi, G. (2018). An Investigation of the Value of Using Concept Maps in General Chemistry. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 78(8), 1111-1117. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ed078p1111>
- Chen, L. (2021). Factors Influencing Technology Integration in the Curriculum for Taiwanese Health Profession Educators: A Mixed-Methods Study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 16 (2602); doi:10.3390/ijerph16142602.
- Effiong A. A. & Ekpo, O. E. (2016). Interactive effect of PowerPoint instructional package and academic Performance of educational technology students in the university of Calabar. *Equatorial Journal of Education and Curriculum Studies*. Vol. 1(1)2
- Erdemi, N. (2017). The effect of PowerPoint and traditional lectures on students' achievement in physics. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*. 8(3).
- Fletcher, L. C. (2014). What Is the Impact of PowerPoint Lectures on Learning? A Brief Review of Research. Hagerstown Community College.
- Gambari, A. I., Zubairu, S. A., Daramola, F. O. Abubkar, H. A., & Tukura, C. S. (2018). Impact of Infographics on the academic performance of junior Secondary School Social Studies Students in Giwa Educational Division, Katsina State, Nigeria. *Journal of Information, Education, Science and Technology*. Vol.5(1). 157-167.
- Garba, G. M. (2021). Implementation of Strategies in Continuing Education. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 19(3), 207-217.
- Kearsley G. (2017). *Explorations in Learning & Instruction: The Theory into Practice Database*. Retrieved from: <http://www.psychology.org>, Dec. 2019.
- Mayer, R. C., & Moreno, R. E. (2017). *E-Learning and the Science of Instruction: Proven Guidelines for Consumers and Designers of Multimedia Learning*. Wiley.
- Mensah, J. Y., & Nabie, M. J. (2021). The effect of PowerPoint instruction on high school students' achievement and motivation to learn geometry. *International Journal of Technology in Education*.
- Olariwaju, D. (2019). Meaningful Learning: A Collaborative Literature Review of Concept Mapping. Retrieved from <http://www.mlrg.org/clr-conceptmapping.html>
- Yusuf, M.O., (2022). An investigation into teachers' self-efficacy in implementing computer education in Nigerian secondary schools. *Meridian: A Middle School Computer Technologies Journal*, 8(2): 4.

Effect of Mind Mapping Instructional ... (Dawodu, et. al., 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15073605>

Effect of Mind Mapping Instructional Strategy on Performance in Technical Education among Colleges of Education Students in South-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examines the effect of the Mind Mapping Instructional strategy (MMIS) on Performance in Technical Education among Colleges of Education Students in South-West, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted Quasi-experimental design. The sample of the study consisted of 109 NCE II students, selected using purposive and random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was Technical Education Performance Test (TEPT) validated by three experts. The reliability coefficient of TEPT was 0.80 using the Kuder-Richardson formula 20. The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, analysis of variance was used to test the hypothesis one and t-test to test hypothesis two. The results of the study showed that the mean performance scores of students taught using MMIS was significantly higher than that of students taught using Traditional Instructional Method (TIM). It was also revealed that the male students have higher mean performance scores than female students taught with MMIS. This implies that mind mapping instructional strategy significantly improved students' performance in technical education programs. It is recommended that technical education teachers should encourage their students to imbibe the use of mind mapping instructional strategy during teaching and learning process among others.

Keywords: Effect, mind mapping, gender, performance.

Introduction

In today's evolving educational landscape, technical education particularly in colleges of education plays a crucial role in equipping students with the knowledge, skills, initiative and sense of responsibility necessary to the world's sustainable development as educators strive to refine teaching methods and improve learning outcomes, the integration of new ideas such as thought boards is gaining attraction. The National Commission of Colleges of Education (NCCE) (2021) defines technical education as a field focused on the study of technology, its characteristics, methods, processes and uses. Education includes the knowledge and skills required to understand, use and manage technology effectively in a variety of settings, including business and society. It is also an integrated programme that interacts with other programmes related to human development at the professional level in business, industry and even agriculture.

The mind-mapping instructional strategy is a recent development in technical education, designed to help students acquire skills and knowledge through a structured and organized process. This approach enhances learning outcomes in technical education classrooms by teaching students to create visual representations of mental maps that depict complex ideas

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in layers and interactions. By incorporating concepts, colors, and images to form words, students can better understand and retain material. The strategy aims to foster deeper understanding, critical thinking, and engagement with the content. Through the mind-mapping process, students can collect and organize information, identify relationships between concepts, and gain a clearer understanding of the subject matter." This shows that technical education can help countries acquire scientific knowledge and the skills necessary for their survival and growth, as supported by semantic studies, mind maps, and other methods (Eppler, 2006; Parikh, 2015). Buzan and Buzan (2010) stated that thinking in context means using diagrams to visualize concepts, ideas, and relationships related to subjects. It is a tool used to organize information so that students can understand complex concepts more easily, see connections between different concepts, and remember information better. Mind mapping in technical education is especially important in subjects such as metalwork, automotive, electrical-electronics, architecture, carpentry, and mathematics because these subjects involve many conceptual interactions and processes that need to be understood. This is great for getting information in and out of the brain. Using mind maps has become a creative and effective writing method that can capture ideas. This technique integrates important skills, words, pictures, mathematics, logic, rhythm, color, and spatial awareness in a unique and powerful way. Finally, the goal of using mind mapping as an instructional strategy is to improve learning outcomes by enabling students to understand and navigate the complexities of technical education.

Although the importance of science and technology education for technological development worldwide is widely acknowledged, students' performance remains below expectations (Ballah & Ugwumba, 2015). Researchers such as Ogunleye & Babajide (2011), Harry (2011), and King & Aru (2014) have identified various contributing factors, including students' poor attitude toward technical education, lack of motivation, and inadequate teaching environments. Furthermore, inadequate educational frameworks and evolving perspectives on technical education underscore the need for effective teaching strategies, which are considered crucial (Oladejo, Olosunde, Ojebisi, & Isola, 2011). It is necessary to raise graduates who can utilize modern teaching tools, analyze critical and logical situations, and contribute to advancements in science and technology. To bring the education system to a level that meets societal needs, it is essential to cultivate students who engage in long-term learning through practice and experience. This can be achieved by implementing daily learning, active learning, questioning, critical thinking, and effective teaching methods and strategies, rather than relying on outdated approaches that fail to promote genuine understanding.

Traditional teaching is a teacher-centered approach where teachers are viewed as the primary authorities in imparting knowledge to students. However, it is well-documented that students in conventional classrooms often experience a lack of interest and participation in the learning process. Despite its drawbacks, traditional teaching methods are still favored by some technical educators because they allow for the coverage of extensive topics and reach large groups of students within a short time frame. Unlike modern visualization-based teaching tools, traditional methods do not encourage students to take responsibility for their own learning. In contrast, innovative teaching methods, such as mind-mapping strategies, address students' learning, knowledge, and skill needs. These methods enable teachers to identify students' weaknesses and address them effectively, fostering a learning process tailored to their cognitive development.

Mind mapping according to Bada & Folashade (2020) is a visualization tool used in instruction that can be applied by learners to generate ideas, take note, organize thinking and develop concepts. Instruction using mind mapping is becoming increasingly commonly used in education. However, research has produced consistent results regarding the effectiveness of mind mapping based instruction on student learning outcomes in all subjects especially in the science, technology, engineering and mathematics among others. The students with poor academic performance are more susceptible to the impact of mind mapping based instruction than students with high performance in technical education concepts in the midst of these challenges, the teacher is expected to perform efficiently. The Individual differences among students have led to the teacher to explore this instructional method to meet the diverse needs. Therefore, mind mapping has been found to have a more positive impact of students' cognitive learning outcome than traditional instructional method. This shows that content and learning level are important factors in the effectiveness of mind mapping as a teaching method.

Academic Performance is the outcome of instruction and success is the result of teaching. According to Konyefa and Okigbo (2021), this is the score obtained from the performance test that teachers take to measure whether teaching objectives have been achieved. Academic success is often a reflection of what students have accomplished through a course or courses. Student performance refers to performance in school subjects as determined by grades or scores obtained from performance tests (Abd, Andi, and Muhammad, 2020). Performance is measured by performance standards developed for school programmes. In this study, performance is evaluated as the student's score on the standardized test according to the instructional content. Nwankwo (2018) argued that grades are mostly time-based and depend on how well students can retain the material.

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This is because, unlike students who insist on meaningful learning, students who engage in rote learning have poor understanding and have difficulty in using the procedural knowledge acquired while solving problems determined in the learning process. According to Borich (2011), it is important to ensure effective learning if teachers adapt teaching to meet the different learning needs of male and female students, regardless of their gender. The impact of gender and its interaction with teaching strategies remains unclear. Research shows that some teaching methods benefit males more than females, while others report the opposite. Some teaching methods may be gender-specific (Izuegbunam, 2018; Konyefa and Okigbo, 2021), while others may be more gender specific or specific (Nwanze and Okoli, 2021).

The literature revealed that there has been an increasing interest in innovative teaching strategies, particularly cognitive strategies, aimed at enhancing the learning skills of technical education students, raising educational standards, and promoting global development. While the benefits of brain maps as cognitive tools for learning are widely acknowledged, gaps remain in understanding their specific impact on technical education students' learning abilities in the context of colleges of education. Therefore, the main question of this study is to investigate the influence of mind mapping on technical education concepts among technical education students in colleges of education focusing on its ability to contribute to the sustainable global development. This requires investigating the impact of mind mapping instructional strategy in promoting understanding as well as improving the academic performance in the use of ideas and skills to stimulate student critical thinking, problem solving and creativity. However, effective teaching strategies should improve student performance regardless of the student's background. Since the effect of educational change on students is not yet known, the effect of mental teaching strategies depending on the gender of the job will need to be examined. However, it is known that students' participation in the learning process can increase permanence (Neboh, 2009). Because students' participation in the learning process reveals personal learning experiences and a variety of practical tools that can help change and improve the process. Additionally, this study aims to promote a culture of continuous improvement in colleges of education by highlighting the importance of new teaching strategies that focus on the understanding of technical education students with special needs. By using the power of mind mapping and other methods, teachers can encourage their students to partner in creating a successful and prosperous future around the world.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the effect of mind mapping instructional strategy on performance in technical education among colleges of education students in South-West, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to find out;

1. Difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional strategy (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.
2. Difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught technical education concepts using MMIS in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions raised to guide the study;

1. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional strategy (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria?
2. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught technical education concepts using MMIS in colleges of education in South-West?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance;

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional strategy (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.

H_{02} : There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught technical education concepts using MMIS in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted the pre-test, post-test control group non-equivalent quasi experimental design. This study involved two colleges of education in Lagos and Ogun States, South-West, Nigeria. According to Nworgu (2015), a study is considered

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a quasi-experimental design when random assignment of subjects to experimental and control groups is not possible and as such intact or pre-existing groups are used. The choice of quasi-experiment design therefore was because the administrative set up in the colleges does not allow for randomization of students for experiment as it may disrupt academic activities. The sample of the study involved 109 technical education students from two colleges of education located in Lagos and Ogun states, South-West, Nigeria. The sampling involved both purposive and random techniques. The colleges were chosen because they are of similar characteristics in terms of the regulatory body the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE); student types, and presence of skilled and experienced teachers as well as teaching and learning resources. The purposive and random sampling techniques were used, with the colleges sampled including Federal College of Education (T) Akoka, Lagos State and Oba Sikiru Adetona College of Science and Technology Education in Omu Ijebu, Ogun State. The NCE II Class of Oba Sikiru Adetona College of Science and Technology Education was used as the control group while Federal College of Education (T), Akoka, Lagos State served as the experimental group. The control college had a total of 50 students, (29 male and 21 female) while the experimental college had a total of 59 students (32 males & 27 females). The Technical Education Performance Test (TEPT) instrument in technical education concepts. TEPT was developed by the researcher for data collection. It was made up of sections A and B. Section A was concerned with the personal data of students while Section B contains the test items. The TEPT was used for collection of pretest and posttest performance scores. The TEPT items were made up of 20 multiple choice questions with four options. The items in the test, covered all the units of technical education concepts that were taught. It was used to administer pretest and posttest for both experimental and control groups. After administration of Pretest, the question papers were collected so as to prevent the students from using it as a revision guide before the posttest. Two lesson notes were prepared by the researcher for teaching technical education concepts. One of the lesson notes was written based on traditional instructional method and it was used for teaching technical education concepts to the control group, while the other was written based on the Mind Mapping Instructional Strategy (MMIS), and was used to teach technical education concepts to the experimental group. The instrument used for data collection was validated by three experts from department of Science and Technology education, University of Lagos. The instrument was validated in terms of simplicity of instruction, wordings of items, adequacy and level of coverage of items in addressing the purpose of the study. Corrections and comments given by the experts were used in restructuring the items. The corrected items were then administered to the students. Reliability of the instrument was established through pilot test which was conducted in a college of education different from the sampled colleges used for the research. Test-retest method was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. Test was initially given as pretest and then administered a week later as post-test, the results from pretest and post-test were compared to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. Scores from both tests were then correlated using the Cronbach Alpha in estimating the reliability coefficient. Internal consistency of 0.76 was obtained. The result obtained indicated that the item is reliable for the research and can serve the purpose for which it was developed. The TEPT was administered by the researcher and trained research assistants as pre-test to both experimental and control group. Objective question papers containing 20 items were given to students to tick the correct answer. The papers were retrieved from the students after the pre-test and marked by the researcher to obtain students' scores on academic performance before treatment was administered. This gave a clear picture of students' performance before the treatment. The control college had a total of 50 students (29 male and 21 female), while the experimental college had a total of 59 students (32 male and 27 female). The Technical Education Performance Test (TEPT), developed by the researcher, was used to collect data on technical education concepts. It consisted of Sections A and B. Section A focused on the personal data of students, while Section B contained the test items. The TEPT was used to collect pretest and post-test performance scores. The test included 20 multiple-choice questions with four options, covering all the units of technical education concepts that were taught. It was administered as both a pretest and post-test to both the experimental and control groups. After the pretest was administered, the question papers were collected to prevent students from using them as a revision guide before the post-test.

The researcher prepared two lesson plans for teaching technical education concepts: one based on the traditional instructional method for the control group, and the other based on the Mind Mapping Instructional Strategy (MMIS) for the experimental group. The data collection instrument was validated by three experts from the Department of Science and Technology Education at the University of Lagos. The validation assessed the simplicity of the instructions, the wording of the items, and the adequacy and coverage of the items in relation to the study's purpose. Corrections and comments from the experts were used to restructure the items, which were then administered to the students. The reliability of the instrument was established through a pilot test conducted at a different college of education. The test-retest method was used to verify reliability: the pretest was administered, followed by the same test one week later as a post-test. The results of the pretest and post-test were compared to establish reliability. The scores from both tests were correlated using Cronbach's Alpha to estimate

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the reliability coefficient, which was found to be 0.76, indicating that the instrument was reliable for the research. The TEPT was administered by the researcher and trained research assistants as a pretest to both the experimental and control groups. The objective test papers containing 20 items were distributed to the students, who were asked to mark the correct answers. After the pretest, the papers were collected and graded by the researcher to determine the students' academic performance before the treatment was applied. This provided a clear picture of the students' performance prior to the intervention.

The researcher prepared lesson notes for the traditional instructional method used in teaching the control group and also lesson notes based on the mind mapping instructional strategy used in teaching the experimental group. The researcher guided and explained to the trained research assistants on how to go about teaching the experimental group. After one week, the researcher and the trained research assistants administered a post-test to measure performance. The post-test items were the same items used in administering the pretest. The papers for the TEPT were retrieved back from the students after the post-test and marked by the researcher to obtain the students' performance scores after treatment. Data generated from the TEPT technical education concepts were subjected to statistical analysis to find the descriptive statistics and t-test was used to find out if there is significant difference in the academic performance mean score of the experimental and control groups and also that of retention mean scores of the experimental and control students taught using MMIS.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

1. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional strategy (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Performance Scores of Students taught Technical Education concepts using Mind Mapping Instructional Strategy (MMIS) and those taught using Traditional Instructional Method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West Nigeria

Group	X	Pre-test (X)	Pre-test (SD)	Post-test (X)	Post-test (SD)	Mean Gained
MMIS	59	25.41	9.73	73.75	8.27	48.34
TIM	50	21.99	9.34	68.70	6.53	46.71
Mean difference		.41		5.05		1.63

Table 1 reveals that the students taught technical education concepts using MMIS has pretest mean performance score of 25.41 and posttest mean performance score of 73.75 with mean gained performance score of 48.34, while those in the control group taught with traditional instructional method has pretest mean performance score of 21.99 and posttest mean score of 68.70 with mean gained 46.71. Students taught technical education concepts using MMIS had a less homogeneous score in their posttest (5.05) than those taught using TIM (3.41). The difference between the between the mean gained performance scores of the students is 1.63 in favour of MMIS.

Research Question 2

What is the difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught technical education concepts using MMIS in colleges of education in South-West Nigeria.?

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Table 2: mean performance scores of male and female students taught technical education concepts using MMIS in colleges of education in South-West Nigeria.

Gender	X	Pre-test (X)	Pre-test (SD)	Post-test (X)	Post-test (SD)	Mean Gained
Male	32	25.44	9.63	79.41	5.44	53.97
Female	27	23.78	10.02	68.04	6.02	44.26
Mean difference		1.66		11.37		9.71

Table 2 reveals that the male students taught technical education concepts using MMIS has pretest mean performance score of 25.44 and post-test mean performance score of 79.40 with mean gained performance score of 53.97, while those the female students had pretest mean performance score of 23.78 and post-test mean performance score of 68.04 with gained mean 44.26. Male students taught concepts of technology using MMIS had a more homogeneous score in their post-test 11.37 than the female 1.66. The difference between the mean gained performance scores of the male and female students is 9.71 in favour of males.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional strategy (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.

Table 3: ANCOVA Test of Significance of Difference between the Mean Performance Scores of Students taught technical education concepts using MMIS and TIM in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	f	Sig	Decision
Corrected mode	2842.978	4	710.745	19.215	.000	
Intercept	72279.511	1	72279.511	1954.053	.000	
Pretest	47.627	1	47.627	1.288	.259	
Method	300.331	1	300.331	8.119	.005	sig
Gender	1631.363	1	1631.363	44.103	.000	sig
Method Gender	554.780	1	554.780	14.998	.000	sig
Error	3846.912	104	36.990			
Total	570163.000	109				
Corrected Total	6689.890	108				

Table 3 shows that there is a significant main effect of the treatment on students' performance scores in technical education concepts $F(4, 104) = 8.119, P = 0.005 < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected meaning that there is a significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional approach (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in favour of MMIS.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students in technical education concepts in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.

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Table 4 t-test analysis of the post-test mean scores of Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	tcal	p-value	Remarks
Male	32	25.44	2.582	49	0.866	0.567	Significant
Female	27	23.78	2.887				

Not significant at $P > 0.05$

The result presents the t-test analysis for mean post-test scores of male and female students taught using MMIS. The test was conducted to determine if the mean difference of 25.44 for male and 23.78 for female was significant or not. The t-cal of 0.866 was however found not to be significant at 0.05 level ($t=0.577$, $df=49$, $P=0.567$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that the performance scores of students taught the technical education concepts using MMIS is not significantly affected by gender is accepted. Table 4 shows that there is a significant impact of gender in students' retention of technical education concepts $F(4, 104) = 44.103$, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected meaning that there is a significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students in technical education concepts in favour of the males

Discussion of Findings

This study showed a significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using the Mind Mapping Instructional Strategy (MMIS) and those taught using the Traditional Instructional Method (TIM), with the results favoring MMIS. This outcome was attributed to the fact that students exposed to the MMIS had their academic needs met, as they received remedial instruction on the technical education concepts necessary to enhance their understanding of the material being taught. In this way, teachers differentiate teaching and learning in ways that make learning more effective for students. By exposing students to the mind mapping strategy to ensure they grasp technical education concepts and master the learning materials, students are engaged in a rich and meaningful learning experience. The use of the mind mapping strategy also allows students to learn at their own pace and interact with the teacher regarding the learning materials. Through mind mapping students have ample time to understand the content by connecting it with related concepts, making learning a motivating transformative experience. Again, the use of mind mapping strategy helps the students to learn at their own pace and allowing students to interact with the teacher on the learning materials. Using mind mapping, students have sufficient time to understand the content by exploring related concepts, which fosters motivation and drives positive change in their learning experience. The study contradicts Bada and Folashade (2020) who compared the curriculum to traditional guidelines and showed that student learning, as measured by two tests which differ across scores based on key instructional differences. The results of the study support the finding of Adodo (2013) that students who are taught to self-regulated learning strategy are more effective in improving their academic performance than students who do not use this method. The results of the study are in line with the finding of Izuegbunam and Osuafor (2021) that students who use the adaptive learning approach always achieve better results compared to classroom teaching by expert and other educational changes. The finding of the study showed that there is a significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students in chemistry. A significant interaction was found between teaching method and gender on students' chemistry performance. Adaptive learning favoured the males more than the females in their achievement. The results of this study are not consistent with the findings of Nwankwo (2018) and Littenberger Pachter and Ertl (2019) who found no significant difference in the performance of males and females when using individualized instructional method. However, the results of the study support the finding of Ikwumelu, Oyinbe and Oketa (2015), and it was revealed that boys in experimental group, scored higher than girls in the Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) pre-test, but there was a significant difference in the mean scores after treatment. This implies that the boys have higher mean performance scores than the girls.

Conclusion

The results of this study showed that students taught technology using Mind mapping instructional strategy had significantly higher performance scores than those taught using traditional instructional method. It is concluded that MMIS is an effective instructional strategy in improving students' academic performance in technical education concepts. The study also found that, gender had significant impact on students' performance in technical education concepts. The findings of the study concluded that the mind mapping instructional strategy affect males and female students differently.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings above, the followings were made;

1. Mind mapping instructional approach significantly improved students' performance in technical education programmes hence it is recommended to the teaching in NCCE technical education programmes.
2. Technical education lecturers should encourage their students to imbibe the use of mind mapping instructional approach during teaching learning process
3. Technical education curriculum experts be encouraged to integrate mind mapping instructional approach into the NCCE technical education curriculum so that students of colleges of education can be expose to the use of this instructional approach.
4. Conferences, Seminars and Workshops be organized for lecturers of colleges of education on how to use mind mapping instructional approach to improve their teaching.

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References

- Akanbi, A.O, Olayinka.. W, Omosewo, E.O & Mohammed, R.E. (2021). Effect of mind mapping Instructional strategy on students' retention in Physics in senior Secondary Schools. *Anatolian. Journal of Education*. 6(1), 145-156
- Adodo, S. O. (2013). Effect of mind-mapping as a self-regulated learning strategy on students' Achievement in basic science and technology. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Science*, 4 (6), 163172.
<https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2013.v4n6p163>
- Abd, B., Andi, S. and Muhammad, A.I. (2020). Academic self-efficacy as predictor of academic achievement. *Journal Pendidikan Indonesia*, 9(1), 163-168.
- Al-Zyoud, A. A., Al Jamal, D., & Bani abdelrahman, A. (2017). Mind mapping and students' writing performance. *Arab World English Journal*, 8(4), 28291. <https://doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol8no4.19>
- Buzan, T. & Buzan, B. (2010). *The mind map book: unlock your creativity, boost your memory, change your life*. Arlow, UK: Pearson.
- Borich, G. D. (2011) *Effective teaching methods*. UK: Institute of Technology Press.
- Bada, A.A & Folashade, A, (2020). Effect of Mind Mapping Teaching Method on Senior Secondary School Students Achievement in Physics in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*. 3(1), 86-96
- Bada, A.A & Akinbobola, A. O. (2017). Effectiveness of Experiential Teaching Strategy on Students Achievement and Scoring levels in Senior Secondary School Physics. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 3(12), 552-564.
- Ballah, A.G & Ugwumba, A.O.(2015). Attitude and Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Physics in Nigeria. Paper Presented at the proceedings of SOCOINTER15-2nd International Conference in Education, Social Sciences and Humanities (pp499-508), Istanbul, Turkey.
- Eppler, M.J.(2006). A comparison between concept maps, mind maps, conceptual diagrammes, and visual metaphors as complementary tools for knowledge construction and sharing. *Information visualization*. 5 (3), 202-210.
- Harry, I.H. (2011). Attitude of Students towards Science and Science Education in Nigeria. (A case study of Selected Secondary Schools in Rivers State). *Continental J. of Educational Research*, 4 (2), 33-51
- Izuegbunam, A. Gl & Osuafor, A. M 2021). (Effect of Adaptive Learning Approach on Students' Achievement in Chemistry in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation* 7 (5), 81-89
- Izuegbunam, A. Gl & Osuafor, A. M, (2021). Effect of Adaptive Learning Approach on Students' Retention In Chemistry In Awka Education Zone Of Anambra State. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*. 11 (6), 22 28
- Izuegbunam, A. G. (2018). Effect of cooperative and individualized instruction on students' achievement in chemistry in Awka south local government area. Unpublished Master's thesis submitted to Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

Effect of Mind Mapping Instructional ... (Dawodu, et. al., 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15073605>

- King'aru, J.M. (2014). Factors Contributing to Poor Performance of Science Subjects: A case study Secondary Schools in Kawe Division Municipality. M.Ed Dissertation, Open University of Tanzania
- Konyefa, B.I. and Okigbo, E.C. (2021). Effect of ethnochemistry instructional approach on secondary school students' achievement in chemistry in Bayelsa State. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation (IJEE)*, 7(4), 16-22.
- Ikwumelu, S. N., Oyibe O. A. and Oketa, E. C (2015) Adaptive teaching: An invaluable Pedagogic practice in Social Studies Education. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(33), 140 – 144.
- Katcha, M. A, Orji, A.B.C, Ebele, F. U, Abubakar, Z. & Mohammed, B. (2018). Effects of Mind Mapping instructional Approach on Senior Secondary School Biology Students' Achievement in Evolution in Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. *Journal of Science, Technology, Mathematics and Education (JOSTMED)*, 14(2), 146-154
- Luttenberger, S., Paechter, M. and Ertl, B. (2019). Self-concept and support experienced in school as key variables for the motivation of women enrolled in STEM subjects with a low and moderate proportion of females. *Frontier Psychology*, 10, 12-42. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01242
- NCCE (2021). Nigeria Certificate in Education Minimum Standard for general education. Abuja: National Commission for colleges of Education.
- Neboh, O. I. (2009). Effect of learning activity package (LAP) on students' achievement and retention in senior secondary school biology. Unpublished Thesis, Department of Science Education Faculty of Education University of Nigeria, Nsukka
- Nworgu B.G (2015). Educational Research: Basic Issues and Methods. Nsukka, University Trust Publishers. Nwankwo, G.U. (2018). Effect of activity based instructional on junior secondary school students' achievement and retention in basic science. Unpublished theses, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Nwanze, A. C. and Okoli, J.N. (2021). Path analysis of factors affecting academic achievement of tertiary education students in chemistry in Delta state. *African Journal of Science, Technology & Mathematics Education*, 6(1), 75-88.
- Nwanze, A.C., Konyefa, B.I. and Ezeanya, C.M. (2021). Cognitive style as a determinant of academic achievement of secondary school science students in Onitsha Education Zone. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 7(2), 12-24.
- Oladejo, M.A., Olosunde, G.R., Ojebisi, A.O., & Isola, O.M. (2011). Instructional materials and students' academic achievement in physics. Some Policy Implications. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 112-126.
- Parikh, N.D. (2015). Mind map and concept map as complementary tools for teaching. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*. 2(4), 147-158S)

Effects of Mastery-Learning ... (Abdullahi & Faruk, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15073636>

Effects of Mastery-Learning-Approach on Performance and Retention in Islamic Studies Concept among Public Primary School Pupils in Katsina State

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Abstract

This study examined the “Effects of Mastery-Learning-Approach on performance and retention in Islamic Studies Concept among Public Primary School Pupils in Katsina State, “The study was guided by two objectives, questions and hypotheses. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design which included a pre-test, post-test and post-test. The study population included all 66,831 (31,735 boys and 35,096 girls) grade 5 pupils from 469 public primary schools in six (6) local government areas under the Katsina Zone Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA) State Universal Basic Education (SUBEB). The study sample consisted of 90 grade 5 primary school pupils purposively drawn from two intact classrooms in two sample schools. The instrument used to collect data was the Islamic Studies Performance Test (ISPT) and the Islamic Studies Retention Test (ISRT). The ISPT was validated by the experts and pilot tested, and the internal consistency reliability was 0.85. Two research questions were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses tested using an independent sample t-test at a significance level of 0.05. The results showed that primary school students who learned Islamic studies using the mastery learning approach (MLA) performed significantly better than those who learned the same content using the conventional method. From the results of the study it was discovered that mastery-learning-approach help in enhancing students’ academic performance and retention in Islamic studies concept among public primary school pupils. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that education stakeholders and curriculum planners (in Islamic studies curriculum document) should place a emphasis on the adoption of the mastery learning approach in the teaching and learning process.

Keyword: Islamic studies, mastery-learning-approach, conventional method, academic performance, retention.

Introduction

Mastery Learning Approach (MLA) is an education approach based on the concept that all learners can learn when provided with conditions suitable to their situation. Adam and Marshall (2022) asserted that Mastery learning approach is closely connected to competency-based learning as an observable behaviour of the students to incorporate and exhibit knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes and can proceed to learning other content with complexity at their own phase (Adam, & Marshall, 2022). Hence, being competent in a particular subject area describes the student to have acquired the necessary skills in all the three learning domains (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) in a certain context at a defined stage of education or practice (FME, 2018).

According to Filgona, & Sababa (2017) Bloom expounded that when learners are typically distributed on aptitude and each student received quality instruction, sufficient learning time required to accomplish the task then most students are expected to achieve mastery standard. Hence, there would be slight or no significant relationship between student’s aptitude and achievement. Subsequently, Filgona & Sababa (2017) viewed Mastery Learning Approach as one of instructional strategies whereby students are given unlimited opportunities to master a particular unit of lesson after assessment typically 70% - 100%, before moving to the next unit. Mastery learning approach provide more time for students to repeat the learning activities in Islamic studies. In the words of Olorumaiye (2024) grade of “A1” represents excellent academic accomplishment that corresponds to an percentage ranging from 75% - 100%, indicating that the learner has adequate mastery of subject matter as maintained in biological and physical sciences, legal system, engineering and technology disciplines.

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Furthermore, researchers on the effectiveness of mastery learning approach such as Ejodamen and Iserameiya (2018) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of mastery learning approach on Students' Academic Achievement by Gender in Basic Technology (BTE) in Edo State, Nigeria. Quasi-Experimental design was adopted involving experimental and control groups. They found that that female students taught BTE with MLA performed relatively higher in their post-test academic achievement than the male students. However, the findings revealed that both male and female taught with MLA performed significantly higher in there post-test academic achievement in BTE than those taught with Direct Instruction Strategy (DIS). Similarly, Animola and Bello (2019) conducted a study, which determined the comparative effectiveness of Mastery and Peer-to-Peer Learning Strategies in Improving Junior Secondary Students' learning outcomes in Basic Science in Owo Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The researchers found that PLS and MLA showed effectiveness in improving the students' attitude to Basic Science with PLS as the most effective. The study concluded that the PLS produce significantly better academic performance and retention of Basic Science concepts by students than MLA.

Accordingly, Adeniji, Ameen, Dambatta and Orilonise (2018) conducted a study, which examined the effect of mastery learning on senior secondary school students' achievement and retention in circle geometry in Ilorin, Kwara state, Nigeria. They discovered that senior school students' academic achievement in Geometry improved significantly when taught using Mastery learning approach. Even though, the researchers found non-existence of differences in gender and in the achievement of low, medium and high scoring students when taught with Mastery learning approach. Moreover, there was a significance difference in the post test mean score and retention score of students taught circle geometry using Mastery learning approach as compared to their pre-test scores. In addition, Tukur (2018) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of mastery learning approach in enhancing the students' academic achievement in mathematics in Gombe metropolis of Gombe State, Nigeria. Tukur found that students who were exposed to mastery learning had enriched academic achievement in mathematics. Eventually, results on the posttest mean scores of the students revealed that there is a significant effect on the academic achievement of the experimental group in which the MLA had been introduced. Hence concluded that students exposed to MLA performed better than students who were taught in the traditional teaching method. Moreover, results exemplify that there is a significant relationship between the students' attitudes toward mathematics and their academic achievement in mathematics.

Consequently, Hussain and Suleiman (2016) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of Bloom's Mastery learning approach on 9th grade students' academic achievement and retention in English language in Khurram Karak, Pakistan. The researchers discovered that the Bloom's Mastery learning approach, positively influences students' academic achievement and retention in English language concepts as compared to traditional learning approach at secondary school level. In addition, Ali, Jabeen and Lubna (2017) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of Mastery learning approach (MLA) on learning retention of secondary school students in Mathematics, in Mardan district of Khyber Pakhtoonkhwa in Pakistan. Donald (2019) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of Mastery learning approach on senior secondary school students' interest, achievement, and retention in genetics in education Zone C, Benue State, Nigeria. Findings revealed that students taught using MLA performed significantly higher mean achievement scores in genetics than their counterparts been taught using conventional learning approach. Findings indicated that significant difference exist in the learning retention of students in experimental group. Conversely, Uzezi (2020) conducted a study, which investigated the effect of Mastery Learning Instructional Strategy (MLIS) on secondary school students' achievement and retention of Chemistry concepts in Jalingo Educational Zone in Taraba State, Nigeria. Uzezi's result contradicts the result of present study and other reviewed works as it revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of high, moderate and low ability students regarding MLIS; there was also no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students in chemistry.

Academic performance simply refers to the extent students achieved the educational outcomes in school subjects and extra-curricular activities provided to influence desirable behavioural changes to fit into the society they belonged (Tukura, et al 2020). In other words, academic performance entails the extent a student accomplished the educational objectives assessed through evaluation to predict the students' potentialities in learning experiences been exposed to within a specified period of time (Tukura, et al 2020). Latter Grades (A = 70 -100, B = 60 – 69, C = 50 – 59, D = 40 49 and F = 0 – 39) are assigned to represent the students' aptitude levels on both cognitive, affective and psychomotor learning domains (Tukura, et al 2020). Consequently, the retention ability according to Durojaiye et al. (2021) is the learner's ability to retain experiences at a later time". While Tukura, et al. (2020) stated that, the ability to store and remember ideas and facts is termed as retention. It also means the extent to which a student has achieved the educational goals.

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Islamic studies is one of teaching subjects taught at basic, post basic, tertiary and university education levels in Nigeria aimed at inculcating the sound moral values among children for wellbeing and patriotism. FME (2018) stated that “the title ‘Islamic Studies’ is chosen in preference to all previous titles such as Islamic Religious Knowledge (IRK), Islamic Religious Studies (IRS) and The Religion and National Values (RNV) since it is more comprehensive and therefore fitting the subject matter in the curriculum.” FME (2018) defined Islamic Studies as the totality of learning experiences centered on the relationship between man and his Creator and between man, his fellow men and other creatures. On the other hand, Dauda (2018) viewed Islamic Studies as a teaching subject that comprehensively encompasses all the temporal and spiritual spheres of human life from the most insignificant the most-fundamental sectors for prosperity.

Furthermore, Islamic Studies is one of school subjects that requires thorough understanding of all its contents for application in daily living. Therefore, education in the Islamic viewpoint produces a cultured, well-behaved, considerate, reasonable and God-fearing individual (FME, 2018). Learners has varying learning abilities, styles and the pace at which they learn contents, which differs from their counterparts. In line with this, the FME (2018) empathized the use of modern teaching techniques such as demonstration, questions and answers, guided discovery, simulation, story-telling, brains storming, cooperative learning, inquiry, field trips, and concept mapping, which have been studied and found to be effective to varying degrees, in improving pupils’ academic performance and retention of learned concepts.

According to FME (2018) Islamic studies represents complete aspects of Islam for it primarily focus on four sources of Shariah; Qur’an and Prophetic Traditions (Hadith) as primary sources and Consensus of Scholars Views (Ijma’) and Analogical Deductions (Qiyas) as secondary sources. These sources further falls naturally into various interconnected subdivisions been incorporated in the new primary and post primary 9-Year Basic Education Curriculum that includes; the Arabic Alphabets, Qur’an, Tajwid, Hadith, Fiqh, Sirah and Tahdhib, which in turn requires mastery. The fore, pupils must attain certain level of mastery for Arabic Alphabets to enable them write and read Arabic letters, words, verses and short chapters of the Qur’anic texts correctly with precision and moderate speed. Also, pupils must have mastery of Qur’anic recitation with rules of Tajweed to avoid unnecessary errors while reading occasionally or in daily prayers (Salat).

Consequently, reciting the Qur’an or memorizing its chapters is in itself not enough to attain mastery except when accompanied by reflection and practical application in daily life. However, companions of the Prophet Muhammad (Peace be upon him) demonstrate certain level of mastery in Qur’anic recitation through formative and summative assessment before they progress to learning the next chapter or verses as contained in Suratul Baqara “*O ye who believe! Do not say ambiguous words [to Allah’s Messenger] but say words of respect, and listen....*” (Qur’an 2:104). Also the Messenger of Allah (Peace be upon him) teaches his companions through demonstration technique tenets of all steps involved in performing worship acts (Ibadat) so as attain certain mastery level before progressing to higher levels. This will enable them to extend the knowledge to other companions whom were absent during the instruction. In a hadith reported by ‘Abdullāh ibn ‘Amr ibn al-‘ās (may Allah be pleased with him) reported that the Prophet (may Allah’s peace and blessings be upon him) said: “*Convey from me even if it is one verse, and narrate from the Children of Israel, and there is no sin in that. And whoever intentionally tells a lie against me, let him assume his seat in Hellfire.*” Sahih/Authentic Hadith (Related by al-Bukhari: 3461). The Qur’an 2:104 stated above depicts that the Companions of the Messenger of Allah (may Allah’s peace and blessings be upon him) while taking Qur’an lessons request for enough time to enable them memorize with full understanding (mastery) before proceeding to subsequent content. Moreover, the Messenger of Allah (may Allah’s peace and blessings be upon him) command to convey to people the knowledge inherited from him of the Qur’an and the Sunnah on condition that the conveyer is knowledgeable of what he conveys and comprehends it. The conveyance of these messages requires sound memory retention capacity and mastery to avoid unnecessary errors and falsehood attribution to Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

Mastery of Prophetic traditions (Hadith) concerning sayings, actions and tacit approval is compulsory upon Muslims in order to negate the fabricated Ahadith. Fiqh which covers all aspect of religious practices or worship (testimonies, salat, sawm, zakat and hajj) with understanding. Sirah portrays the collection of Islamic historical events of Prophets/Messenger of Allah and their nations, righteous servants and wrongdoers. Tahdhib explains Islamic mannerism of peaceful coexistence with creatures on the universe. The Messenger of Allah, Prophet Muhammad (SAW) usually send some of his famous companions (Aliyu ibn Abi Talib, Mu’az ibn Jabal, Abdullahi ibn Mas’ud: may Allah be pleased with them all) who mastered the knowledge or skills on concepts related legal and juristic matters, business transactions, *Tauhid* (Monotheism), *Salat* (Five Daily Prayers), *Zakat* (Alms giving), and *Hajj* (Pilgrimage) to other towns and cities outside Madina as instructors. Moreover, the entire curriculum requires teachers to use a participatory and exploratory teaching methods much more inspiring, motivating, interesting and effective toward prompting the positive attitude and understanding of the pupils for optimal growth and development (FME, 2018).

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According to Busari (2018) pupils mastery in Islamic Studies still not yielding positive result because of some critical factors such as teachers lack of skills to harness the explicit instructional objectives with the lesson, Islamic studies teachers not well versed in Arabic language, persistent use of inappropriate teacher-centred instructional methods, students' learning styles, shortage of school facilities, learners problem with Arabic as second language learning, learners persistent difficulties to contrast between the articulation of (/ ا/ع/خ/ك/ح/ه/د/ض/ط/ت/ث/س/ص/ذ/ز/ظ/) Arabic voiced and voiceless sounds at the initial and final positions, educational policy among others (FME, 2018). The researcher discovered from existing literature that numerous studies have been conducted on the effects of mastery learning approach on students' achievement in English language, Mathematics, Physical, Biological, Technological and Social Sciences at secondary school and tertiary education levels in different localities. To this end, this study was carried out to provide empirical evidence on the effects of mastery learning approach to gather with learning retention on Primary School pupils' academic performance and retention of concepts in Islamic studies in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA).

Statement of the Research Problem:

The Islamic Studies curriculum has been designed to inculcate balance mental and moral values among primary school pupils at a formative stage. According to FME (2018) successful implementation Islamic Studies curriculum largely depends on teachers' capability to use appropriate innovative learner-centered instructional strategies, and selection of relevant teaching aids (real and improvised). A 5 years statistics indicated declining pupils' academic performance in Islamic Studies internal examination results of 10 public primary schools, under Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA), ranging from 2019 - 2023 academic sessions, see appendix 2 showing the statistics.

The statistical summary of pupils' academic performance in the Islamic studies internal examination results obtained from 10 public primary schools in Jibia LGA of Katsina State ranges from 2019 - 2023 academic sessions. Record of 2019/2020 academic session out of 4426 primary 6 pupils only 1404 representing 32.9% have achieved a bench mark mastery level of 70% - 90%. Also, in 2020/2021 session out of 3666 only 1035 pupils with 28.5% achieved mastery level. Meanwhile, in 2021/2022 the academic performance record of 3144 only session 1100 of 34.3% reached mastery standard. Likewise, in 2022/2023 the pupils' academic performance record depicts that out of 2861 only 841 of 33.7% achieves mastery standard.

Furthermore, the academic performance record of 2023/2024 indicated that out of 3617 only 977 pupils with 29.2% accomplishes mastery standard. It is shocking that the academic performance and retention ability of primary school pupils in the internal examination results of Islamic studies out of the grand total of 17,714 primary 6 pupils only 5357 with 31.7% obtained distinction or achieved mastery standard of 80% -90%. These result points to the fact that the pupils' academic performance and retention ability is below the mastery level of the expected minimum standard of 70% - 100%. Thus, the learners persistent poor academic performance could be attributed to lack of retention of the subject matter as most Islamic Studies teachers uses the conventional teaching method 'chalk and talk' which is boring and uninspiring. Therefore, this study intends to investigate if this leaning model can be applicable for teaching Islamic studies subject to enhance academic performance and retention skills among the public primary schools pupils in Katsina state.

Objectives of the study:

1. To examine the difference in the mean academic performance of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using conventional method.
2. To assess the difference in the mean retention of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using conventional method.

Research Questions:

15. What is the difference between the mean academic performance score of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using conventional method?
16. What is the difference between the mean retention rate of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using conventional method?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance Score of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using Conventional method.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean retention rate of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using conventional method.

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Methodology

The research design was quasi-experimental comprising a pre-test, a post-test and a post-test. The study was a field experiment with one independent and conditional variable being teaching technique and the two dependent variables were academic performance and retention levels of the students. The study population consisted of 66,831 (31,735 males and 35,096 females) Grade 5 pupils from 469 public primary schools in six (6) local government areas under the Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA) of Katsina State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB). The study sample consisted of 90 Grade 5 pupils purposively drawn from two intact classrooms in two sample schools. School A with a class of 44 pupils was assigned to experimental group (EG) and in school B the other class with 46 pupils was assigned to control group (CG) respectively. The instrument used for data collection was the Islamic Studies Performance Test (ISPT) and the Islamic Studies Retention Test (ISRT). The ISAPT was validated by three experts and pilot tested, and the internal consistency reliability was 0.85. The experimental group received instruction using Islamic studies concepts using a mastery learning approach while the control group received instruction using a conventional teaching method. Furthermore, the treatment for both groups lasted for six weeks. Two research questions were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested using an independent sample t-test at a significance level of 0.05 as a criterion for acceptance or rejection.

Results

Mean and standard deviation statistical data analysis was used to answer the research question 1 in table as shown below:

Research Question 1

What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of primary school pupils taught the Significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using Conventional method?

Mean and standard deviation statistical data analysis was used to answer the research question 1 in table 1 as shown below:

Table 1: Summary of the post-test mean academic performance of primary school pupils taught the Significance of Zakat (Alms giving)

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
κ.	Experimental	24.09	3.05	Accepted
κ.	Control	20.91	3.09	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows that the difference between the mean academic achievement scores of students who learned the meaning of Zakat (charity) using the mastery learning approach (M = 24.09, SD = 3.05) and those who learned the same concepts using the conventional teaching method. (M = 20.91, SD = 3.09) is 3.18 in favor of the mastery learning approach group. This shows that the experimental group performed better than the control group in terms of students' academic achievement in Islamic studies.

Research Question 2

What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of primary school pupils taught the Significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using Conventional method?.

Mean and standard deviation statistical data analysis was used to answer the research question 2 in table 2 as shown below:

Table 2: Summary of the post-test mean academic performance of primary school pupils taught the Significance of Zakat (Alms giving)

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
5.	Experimental	24.09	3.05	Accepted
6.	Control	20.91	3.09	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2024

From Table 2, it could be seen the difference between the mean retention scores of the students taught the Zakat (Alms giving) using mastery learning approach (M = 26.05, SD = 2.00) and those taught same concepts using the conventional

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teaching method (M = 22.65, SD = 4.30) is 3.39 in favour of the mastery learning approach group. This indicates that the experimental group gained more than the control group in terms of the students' retention ability in Islamic Studies.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using Conventional method.

Independent sample t-test was used in testing the null hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05, in the table 3 as shown below:

Table 3: t-test Summary on the difference between the mean academic performances of primary school pupils

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
		24.09	3.05	
		20.91	3.09	Sig.

**Significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance*

Table 3 shows that the difference in academic achievement between students who learned the meaning of zakat (alms) using the mastery learning approach (M = 24.09, SD = 3.05) and those who learned the same concepts using the conventional teaching method (M = 20.91, SD = 3.09) was statistically significant (t = 4.911, df = 88; p = 0.000), at a significance level of 0.05. This implies that the experimental group performed significantly better than the control group. Thus, there is a significant difference between the two groups, as confirmed by the high value of the effect size.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean retention of primary school pupils taught the significance of Zakat (Alms giving) using Mastery Learning Approach and those taught using Conventional method.

Independent sample t-test was used in testing the null hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05, in the table 4 as shown below:

Table 4: t-test Summary on the difference between the mean retention of primary school pupils

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
		26.05	2.00	
		22.65	4.30	Sig.

**Significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance*

Table 4 shows that the difference between the retention ability of students who learned the meaning of Zakat (almsgiving) using the mastery learning approach (M = 26.05, SD = 2.00) and those who learned the same concepts with the conventional teaching method (M = 22.65, SD = 4.30) was statistically significant (t = 4.833, df = 88; p = 0.000), at a significant level of 0.05. This implies that the experimental group performed significantly better than the control group. Thus, there is a significant difference between the two groups, as confirmed by the high value of the effect size.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of the results of this study is based on the research questions answered and the hypotheses tested. Therefore, the results of the first research question and the first hypothesis show that there is a significant difference between the average performance of primary school students assigned to the experimental and control groups who were taught the concept of the importance of Zakat (charity) using the approach of mastery learning significantly higher with p value = 0.000 \leq alpha value of 0.05 and those who are taught using the lecture method. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis. This result confirmed Ejodamen and Iserameiya (2018) who found that there was a significant difference in the average academic performance of students taught in basic science and technology using the mastery learning approach and those taught with the lecture method. However, this result does not agree with Animola and Bello (2019) who found that there was no significant difference in the average academic performance of student teachers in basic science and technology using 'a peer learning strategy and who achieved significantly better results than those who were taught the same content using the mastery learning approach

The results of the second research question and the second research hypothesis showed that there is a significant difference between the mean retention of primary school students assigned to the experimental and control groups who were taught the concept of the importance of Zakat (giving alms) using mastery learning. The approach was significantly higher with

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a p value = 0.000 \leq alpha of 0.05 and its counterpart learned the same material using the mastery learning course. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis. However, this finding is consistent with the findings of Adeniji, Ameen, Dambatta, and Orilonise (2018), Tukur (2018), and Nchelem (2020) who found that there was a significant difference in the mean retention of students after they had learned mathematics concepts using the mastery learning approach and those taught using the lecture method. Similarly, this is consistent with Uzezi (2020) who found a significant difference in retention skills between students taught chemistry concepts using the mastery learning approach and the lecture method. However, these results are not in agreement with those of Animola and Bello (2019) who found that peer work improved students' retention skills in basic science and technology. However, in the mastery learning approach, learning objectives are broken down into simpler units so that each group has 70-90% mastery of them. In addition, students are provided with learning opportunities to retain the concepts learned. Remedial opportunities are provided to ensure that all students master a unit before moving on to the next.

Conclusion

From the results of the study it was discovered that mastery-learning-approach help in enhancing students' academic performance and retention in Islamic studies concept among public primary school pupils.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- xiv. The government should make it mandatory to use the mastery teaching approach, primarily to learn and teach Islamic studies concepts to facilitate academic achievement.
- xv. Islamic studies teachers should be trained on how to engage elementary school students to facilitate retention.

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References

- Adam, M. P. & Marshal, W. (2022). A Practical Review of Mastery Learning. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, Volume 86(10) Article 8906. <http://www.ajpe.org>.
- Adeniji, S. M., Ameen, S. K., Dambatta, B. U., & Orilonise, R. (2018). Effect of Mastery learning approach on Senior School Students' Academic Performance and Retention in Circle Geometry. *International Journal of Instruction*, e-ISSN: 1308-1470 Vol.11, No.4 p-ISSN: 1694-609X pp. 951-962. <https://doi.org/10.12973/iji.2018.11460a>
- Ali, A., Jabeen F. Lubna, T. (2017). The Effect of Mastery learning approach on Learning Retention of Secondary School Students in the Subject of Mathematics in Mardan District of Khyber Pakhtoonkhwa, Pakistan. *Journal of Education and Practice*. Retrieved from, [http://dx.doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2019\(IV-IV\).30](http://dx.doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2019(IV-IV).30)
- Animola, O. V. Bello T. (2019). The Comparative Effectiveness of Mastery and Peer-to-Peer Learning Strategies in Improving Junior Secondary Students' Learning Outcomes in Basic Science in Owo Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*
- Busari, J. M. (2018). Problems and Prospects of Teaching and Learning Islamic Studies in Primary and Post- Primary Schools in Nigeria: *An Overview International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, Volume 8(3), p7534. <http://www.ijsrp.org>.
- Dauda, A. (2018). *Effective Methodology of Teaching Islamic Studies: For Basic and Post Basic Education Levels in Nigeria*. Gidan Dabibo Publishing Company, Kano, Nigeria.
- Durojaiye, D. S., et al. (2021). Effect of activity-based instructional strategy on senior secondary school students' retention in circle geometry in Abuja, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies*, Volume 8(10). <http://www.oapub.org/edu>.
- FME (2018). *9-Year Basic Education Curriculum, for Primary 4-6*. Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council, supported by Universal Basic Education Commission, Abuja. Printed at No 3 Jibowu Street, Yaba, Lagos, Nigeria.
- Hussain, I. and Suleiman, Q. (2016). *Effect of Bloom's Mastery learning approach on Students' Academic Achievement in English at Secondary Level*. Institute of Education & Research, Kohat University of Science & Technology Kohat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.
- Iserameiya, F. and Ejodamen, A. (2018). *Effect of Mastery learning approach on Male and Female Students' Academic Achievement in Basic Technology in Edo State, Nigeria*. DOI: 10.9790/0837-2306027481. Retrieved from <http://www.iosrjournals.org>
- Nchelem, R. (2020). *Mastery-Based Learning Approach and Junior Secondary Students' Performance and Retention in Change of Subject Formula in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State*
- Olorumaiye (2024). Benchmark Minimum Academic Standard (BMAS) for engineering qualifications in Nigeria. Council for the Registration of Engineering in Nigeria (COREN). Retrieved from: <https://coren.gov.ng/benchmark-minimum-academic-standadrd-bmas>
- Suhartini, A. (2022). *Mastery Learning Approach and Students' Learning Motivation: Case in Islamic Religious Learning among Grade VII students in Bandung, Indonesia*. In Proceedings of the 1st Bandung English Language Teaching International Conference (BELTIC 2018) - Developing ELT in the 21st Century, pages 141-149. DOI: 10.5220/0008214900002284.
- Tukur, M. Y. (2018). *Mastery learning approach (MLA): Its Effects on the Students Mathematics Academic Achievement*. Retrieved online from <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenondo.1227280>
- Tukura, C. S., et al. (2020). Effects of e-learning on retention and performance of basic science and technology students in Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation (IJRSI)*, Volume 7(11), p33. www.rsisinternational.org

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Effects of Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy on Performance in Reading Comprehension Among Secondary School Students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated effects of peer tutoring instructional strategy on performance in reading comprehension among secondary school students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives, with corresponding research questions and hypotheses, respectively. The study adopted pre- test post- test quasi- experimental research design. The population for this study comprised of 19, 282 senior secondary school class two (SS2) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Bayelsa State. A simple random sampling and stratified random sampling techniques were used to select size of 100 students from the target population. The instrument used for data collection was Reading Comprehension Performance Test (RCPT) which was used to determine the academic performance of the students. In establishing the reliability of the instrument, kuder Richarson (K-R 21) formula was employed and a reliability coefficient of 0.72 was obtained. A pre- test of Reading Comprehension Performance Test (RCPT) was given to all the students before the treatment. Thereafter, the experimental group was subjected to treatment. Data analysis was subjected to Mean Scores, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that peer tutoring learning technique is more effective than discussion method. Based on the findings, it was recommended that teachers at all levels should be conversant with the new learning techniques. This will enable them to vary their mode of presenting their lessons to the students.

Keywords: English Language, Peer Tutoring, Reading Comprehension, Teaching Technique and Discussion Method.

Introduction

English language as major subject in the school curriculum and as an official language in Nigeria needs to be given proper attention particularly in content delivery. English language as an official language in Nigeria refers to a language selected by a bilingual or multilingual country to serve a wide range of function, for example, Education, as a medium of government business, media, and high level of commerce and so on. In terms of education, it calls for proper teaching techniques which will help equip students with the potentiality, as well as push them for deeper understanding of the subject (ijoko, 2021).

English language from the researcher's point of view requires a method which will help the teacher to use the four language skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing. English language learners in particular, may thrive in a peer tutoring learning environment because they will have the opportunity to learn with others through peer-to-peer exchange, to develop their academic vocabularies through dialogue, to use their own strengths and cultural backgrounds, and to accelerate their language acquisition at the same time as they are learning about topics of interest. Peer tutoring learning requires the production of authentic (oral and written) language.

Wikipedia (2015) defined Peer tutoring as a teaching strategy in which students are paired together to practice academic skills and master content. Teachers may use peer tutoring to help accommodate a classroom full of diverse students who need more individual attention. There are a variety of factors teachers should be aware of when planning a peer tutoring lesson. Different schools, classrooms, and teachers are able to provide different types of resources and expertise to contribute to the success of a peer tutoring program. Keep in mind, the strategies described in this lesson will not work in every situation with every student all the time. It is up to you as the teacher to assess these strategies and see what will work for your specific population of students. Peer tutoring is meant to be a flexible and adaptable teaching method, which should allow for some trial and error as you shape your individual programs.

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Peer tutor partnerships may be designed in a few different ways. Teachers may assign some of their higher achieving students to work with peers in the classroom who are struggling, or they could assign students with similar abilities to work together, each taking turns being the tutor and the tutee. They may also work with other teachers to pair up older students who have mastered the content with younger students who are being introduced to something new, which is known as cross-age tutoring.

In Nigeria, however due to technological development, reading habits are changing. In our society today, while technology is slowly taking a steady control over individual lives, the reading habit is fast vanishing into the thin air. Students now lack the skill of reading; instead they spend more time or hours on electronic media. Browsing the net, playing with handsets seem to be the order of the day, thereby making reading a book or any other piece of written material in a quiet and peaceful corner of a library or a home, an old fashioned idea. Students are hardly interested in reading for pleasure and enjoyment instead, they read to pass examination. The declining interest in reading culture among out pupils/students is a cause for alarm and a challenge to all. Something needs to be done to lessen this problem.

Consequent upon the observation on student's inability to demonstrate proficiency in English Language, this has mostly been attributed to their inability to read passages with comprehension. This research will take interest in instructional methodology of reading comprehension. Reading with understanding is one of the most important ways to achieve academic advancement of any individual irrespective of the individual's discipline. But research has indicated that not enough attention has been given to reading instruction and even when it is given, the teacher dominates the class. Adeniyi and Oladunjoye, (2009) as cited by Oyetunde (2012) observed that reading comprehension instruction therefore deserves more attention than it is currently receiving. Student centered approaches are being advocated for the contemporary classroom; the need to expose learners to strategies which will involve their active participation in the learning environment informed the choice of these strategies. Similarly, Adeniyi and Oladunjoye (2009) as cited by Okafor (2016) stated that the instructional technique employed by the teachers' of English language, sex of the students may as well influence students' performance in reading comprehension.

The concept of reading comprehension is one that has evoked varied definitions by different scholars. Herring (2014) described reading as a process of interaction between the writer of a text and the reader who is trying to make meaning out of what the author of the text has encoded. They further explained that reading involves information gathering which the reader seeks to improve his/her knowledge base and become aware of the world around him/her. They identified four stages of efficient reading, namely: recognition, comprehension, retention and recall. These stages involve the reader's ability to recognize meaning of words as used in the text, grasp the author's message, store information extracted from the text in the memory and also remember what has been read. Rudestum (2014) describe reading as a specialized and complex skill involving other skills. He further stated that the ability to read requires the reader to develop the following skills; learning to read in various ways for example skimming and scanning.

Adapting the way they read according to the text and their reason for reading; reading "actively"-using a dictionary, guessing or asking for an unknown word; understanding the relationship between sentences; helping understanding by using textual and visual clues i.e., headings, the way the text is organized into paragraph punctuation, signal words, pictures, typography etc using textual clues where the learners understand, what they and other people are doing at the time. Inferring meaning, guessing meaning and background knowledge of the culture about which they are reading.

Chukueggu and Umara- Okeke (2013) agreed that reading skill includes the following components: Knowledge of the language to be read, ability to separate spoken words into component sounds, ability to discriminate the letters of the alphabet, understanding of the principle of reading from left to right, right to left and ability to comprehend a text. They saw reading comprehension as the process of simultaneously extracting and constructing meaning through interaction and involvement with written language. Extracting meaning from the text is to understand what the author has explicitly or implicitly stated. Reading undeniably involves two necessary elements: reader and a text. It also recognizes a third element which is equally influential in reading namely the writer. The text is processed by the reader in an interaction of the reader and the text and equally, plausibly, the reader and the writer. Snow argued that, texts do not have unitary meanings potentially accessible to all but rather allow for variety in interpretation by

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different readers, governed by factors such as purpose, background knowledge and the writer in the act of reading. They thus see reading as cooperation and negotiation. Reading lessons should aim at facilitating acquisition and development of enduring, whole literacy skills needed for communication in different contexts.

There is also no consensus on what constitutes acceptable practices and methods of reading. However current reading research point to a shift towards meaning oriented reading consisting of understanding of whole and authentic texts. Reading has been viewed within the cognitive psychology as an activity in which participants construct meaning by integrating their previous or existing knowledge with the new knowledge in the text. Boardman (2008) as cited by Chukueggu and Umara- Okeke (2013) stated that the goal of reading comprehension instruction is to help students understand written language. Students, who comprehend well, monitor their understanding as they read and use fix-up strategies, such as re-reading or summarizing, when understanding breaks down. Self-monitoring also helps students relate new information to their prior knowledge, fostering better understanding.

Comprehension is at the centre of reading. Collins and Cheek (2014) describe reading as a process that requires the use of complex thought processes to interpret printed symbols as meaningful units and comprehend them as a thought unit in order to understand a printed text. Reading as a learning process is indispensable in the development of other language skills. As important as reading is, research still shows that majority of Nigerian students in the secondary school possesses poor reading ability. Such students understand little of written texts and thus are unable to analyze and interpret them. Adams, (2019) stated that skilled comprehension readers employ a number of cognitive skills. In the higher level skill process, the reader relates reading to existing knowledge and creates inferential bridge between things that are written and things that are previously experienced. The lower level cognitive processes involve recognition of letters and words and automatic activation of word meanings during the reading. Thus, skilled reading largely depends upon thorough familiarity with individual letters and words and frequent patterns to enable words flow effortlessly from print to meaning (Adam, 2019).

Performance of students in reading comprehension can also be influenced by gender. Gender is a social phenomenon with an important pedagogical implication in second language learning. Many researchers have shown that females perform better than males in verbal tasks in school works. This study therefore believes that apart from instructional strategy of the teacher, sex of students may influence students' achievement in English Language reading comprehension. This method of teaching is based upon active participation of every member of the class in a collective exploration and public evaluation of ideas. Usually, there is no restraint to self-expression as members' pool ideas in co-operative task of understanding an issue and learning from each other. Discussion could serve as a follow-up to a lecture, a mid-course examination of ideas or a recapitulation session (Achuoneye & Ajoku, 2019).

The discussion method makes itself amenable to the teaching of variety of contents in diverse subject area. Arrangement could be concluded for the entire class to participate in a discussion; the class can also be divided into small groups. It is also possible to arrange for panel discussion. The discussion provides for students' involvement, which in turn helps to stimulate and reinforce learning. Discussion method of teaching involves communication of ideas, facts, and opinions by group of learners on an identified and clearly stated instructional objective using skills as speaking, listening and non-verbal processes. For better students' participation, a group size of 5 to 10 members is considered manageable. In the group, both the participants and the moderator (usually the teacher) pull their knowledge together to understand and appreciate a problem by learning from one another. Each member of the group is assigned a specific time limit to address the group while other members listen and observe.

The success and effectiveness of the method depends upon how well the learners are prepared and motivated to participate and the sensitivity of the teacher to the spontaneity of the participants. Thus, the method demands adequate preparation on the part of the teacher (or the conference leader) and participants. Two key points should be noted, Discussion requires a clearly stated objective to serve as a focus and guiding post. Neglecting the criterion may hamper the realisation of the set objectives as discussion may degenerate to mere informal debate on superficial issues and the emergence of a star speaker who eventually will dominate the discussion. Secondly, to ensure effective participation of the members, prior knowledge of the discussion topic is essential. The discussion topic could be derived from several controlled experiences of the learners such as going on a field trip, viewing an educational film, listening to a lecture or reading as assigned book.

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The subtle art of controlling the discussion to realise fully the gains is the responsibility of the teacher or the director. Foremost, the teacher must understand the purpose of the discussion method. Every member of the group should be free to contribute. This implies that there should not be rigid rules as to restrain free exchange of ideas. Potentially dominant personalities must not be allowed to take over the discussion and the naturally reticent must be encouraged to contribute (Curson as cited in Ogwo, 2016). The teacher must skillfully perform this duty without offending anyone. Simultaneously, he should create an environment capable of rewarding each participant for his contribution.

Statement of the Research Problem

Poor performance in English Language at the secondary and even tertiary levels is an issue of concern in the Nigeria educational system. The most noticeable indication of under- performance is in the WAEC conducted SSCE English examination (Ijoko, 2021). The WAEC chief examiners' report each year confirms this. In 2022 the report stated that: "This paper was well within the experience of the candidates and the standard in the previous years; the candidates' performance however was generally disappointing. The above assertion has remained a source of great concern to students, teachers, parents and government. The percentage passes in examination like WAEC, NECO, and GCE continue to decline despite increasing efforts by government to stem the trend. The poor state of learning reading comprehension in our schools has been attributed to many factors. Among the factors that may have accounted for poor performance in the subject are: quality of teaching techniques employed by the teachers, lack of knowledge of subject- matter, lack of interest and other students' related factors. In fact, many teachers of language in Nigeria are not aware of the current methods or principles of second language teaching (Oyetunde as cited in Ijoko, 2021). Experts have called for the use of instructional techniques that are student- center and participatory in nature, which will enable the learners take ownership of learning in group context. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to investigate effects of peer tutoring instructional strategy on performance in reading comprehension among secondary school students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate effects of peer tutoring instructional strategy on performance in reading comprehension among secondary school students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

3. compare the difference in the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those exposed to discussion method.
4. examine whether there is a difference in the mean performances scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension with peer tutoring learning technique.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. what is the difference in mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those exposed to discussion method?
2. what is the difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05level of significance:

- H₀₁. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those exposed to discussion method.
- H₀₂. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique.

Methodology

The study adopted the pre-test post-test quasi- experimental research design. The population of the study comprised all the SS 2 students in the 297 public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The population of SS 2 students for the 2023/2024 academic session 19,282 students (Source: Bayelsa State Post Primary Schools Board, office of the Directorate of Inspection and Statistics, 2024). A sample size of 100 SS 2 students was used for this study. A simple

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random sampling and stratified random sampling techniques were used to compose the sample. Simple random sampling was used to draw one (1) local government area from the eight (8) of them in the state. It was done by writing out the names of the eight (8) local government areas on a piece of paper. The 8 pieces of paper bearing the respective names of the local government areas were thoroughly shuffled in a container and one (1) of it was randomly drawn without replacement. After drawing the one (1) local government area by simple random sampling, a disproportionate stratified random sampling was used to draw a number of schools from the educational zones in the local government area for the study. Twenty (20) items multiple choice test entitled “Reading Comprehension Performance Test” (RCPT) was used in this research to determine students’ academic performance. The face and content validity of the instrument was validated by the researcher’s supervisor and two experts in the Department of Curriculum Studies and Instructional Technology, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The opinions of English Language experts were sought. The instrument was modified based on the suggestions of these experts before administration. The mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: what is the difference in mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those exposed to discussion method?

Table 1: Mean, standard deviation, and mean gain of students’ performance in reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and discussion method

Method	Pre- test			Post – test		Actual Score
	N	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Peer tutoring technique	50	43.90	11.08	85.60	8.18	41.70
Discussion Method	50	40.40	7.75	63.20	6.91	22.80

Table 1 showed that students taught reading comprehension with peer tutoring learning technique had a mean score and a standard deviation of 43.90 and 11.08 during the pre-test while students that were taught reading comprehension using discussion method had a mean and standard deviation 40.40 and 7.75. After post-test, students taught with Peer tutoring technique had a mean score of 85.60 and standard deviation of 8.18 while those taught using discussion method had a mean score of 63.20 and standard deviation of 6.91. The mean gain for students taught with Peer tutoring technique was 41.70 while students taught using discussion method was 22.80. This indicated that students taught with peer tutoring technique performed better than the students taught with discussion method.

Research Question 2: what is the difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique?

Table 2: Mean, standard deviation, and Mean gain of male and female students’ taught reading comprehension using Peer tutoring strategy.

Gender	Pre- test			Post – test		Actual Score
	N	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Male	22	43.80	10.73	85.00	9.13	41.20
Female	28	44.00	11.64	86.20	7.26	42.20

Table 2 showed the analysis of male and female students’ performance taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique. Male students taught with peer tutoring learning technique at the pre-test had the mean score of 43.80 and standard deviation of 10.73 while female students exposed to peer tutoring learning technique had the mean score of 44.00 and standard deviation of 11.64. Male students taught with peer tutoring learning technique at post-test had the mean score of 85.00 and standard deviation of 9.13 with mean gain of 41.20, while

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female students exposed to peer tutoring learning technique had the mean score of 86.20 and standard deviation of 7.26 with mean gain of 42.20. This indicated that the difference was in favour of female students.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those exposed to discussion method.

Table 3: Summary of ANCOVA of students' performance based on methods

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	12551.317 ^a	2	6275.659	108.458	.000	.691
Intercept	27433.504	1	27433.504	474.114	.000	.830
Pretest	7.317	1	7.317	.126	.723	.001
Methods	12237.845	1	12237.845	211.498	.000	.686
Error	5612.683	97	57.863			
Total	571700.000	100				
Corrected Total	18164.000	99				

Table 3 showed that the analysis of covariance in the performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and those taught using the discussion method yielded an F (1,97) of 211.498 with associated exact probability value of 0.001. Since the associated probability (0.001) was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension with Peer Tutoring Learning Technique and those taught with Discussion Method.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique.

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA of students' performance based on gender

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	78.862 ^a	2	39.431	.579	.565	.024
Intercept	19358.850	1	19358.850	284.055	.000	.858
Pretest	60.862	1	60.862	.893	.349	.019
Gender	17.400	1	17.400	.255	.616	.005
Error	3203.138	47	68.152			
Total	369650.000	50				
Corrected Total	3282.000	49				

Table 4 showed that the analysis of covariance in the performance mean scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension with peer tutoring learning technique yielded an F (1,47) of 0.590 with associated exact probability value of 0.446. Since the associated probability (0.446) was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there was no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension with peer tutoring learning technique

Discussion of Findings

Students' Performance in Reading Comprehension Using Peer Tutoring Learning Technique and Discussion Method

Findings from table 1 revealed a significant difference between the performances of students taught reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique and discussion method which is in favour of peer tutoring learning technique. This result indicates that the Peer Tutoring learning technique is more effective in enhancing of students' performance than the discussion method in reading comprehension. This is in line with the findings of Rahman et al., (2018), Akpana and Oludo (2019) and Abduraheem (2017) who found that Peer Tutoring learning technique have positive effect on students' performance. The effectiveness could be that students were actively

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involved in learning process and were able to find out some information for themselves through activity-based instructional strategy such as peer tutoring instructional method and teaching technique therefore, knowledge is better facilitated.

Male and Female Students' Performance in Reading Comprehension Using Peer Tutoring Learning Technique

In table 2 the study revealed that male students differed from the female students on their mean performance scores in reading comprehension. This observed difference is in favour of female students in peer-tutoring learning technique group. Table 4 revealed that gender has no significant effect on student performance in reading comprehension. Thus male and female students differ in their academic performance in reading comprehension using peer tutoring learning technique was not significant. This finding implies that whether a student is male or female, gender does not make a difference in their academic performance. This is in line with the findings of Ajai and Imoku (2015) and Akpana and Oludo (2019). The finding reveals as well that academic performance gained by female surpassed that of their male counterpart. This study therefore asserts that students' academic performance is not a function of gender.

Conclusions

Reading is one of the basic language skills that aid people to learn, communicate and express ideas effectively. It is not developed naturally but by proper teaching and studying through a range of activities and tasks. Teachers of English language in secondary schools should be able to help the learners by teaching them various steps involved in effective reading comprehension. It is the duty of the teacher to lead the learners to read, understand the reading passage by analysing the rudiments found in the passage such as: grammar, idioms, figurative expression, etc. Therefore, the present study is an effort to improve reading comprehension.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations are made:

17. Peer tutoring learning technique are effective in improving students' performance in reading comprehension. Therefore, emphasis should be given to equipping students with the necessary skills in using the techniques.
18. The male students should as well be given more attention in the development of their reading comprehension skills by encouraging them to take more roles in the activities of literature circles in reading comprehension while the female students should be encouraged with incentives for best performance so as to balance the performance level in the class.

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References

- Abduraheem B. O. (2017). Effects of peer tutoring strategy on secondary school students' achievement and retention in social studies. *European Journal of Education studies*, 3(2)
- Adam, A. (2019). The expert systems debate: A gender perspective. In E. Green, J. Owen & D. Pain (Eds), *Gendered by design?* 81-94.

Effects of Peer Tutoring ... (Ijoko, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15073669>

- Achuonye, K. A.; Ajoku, L. I.; Ezekoka, G.K. & Ifegbo, P. C. (2019). *Instructional design: Theory and Principles*. Springfield Publishers.
- Adeyemi, O. (2018). Peer methods in Classroom Learning. *African Journal of Higher Education Studies and Development*, 1(1).
- Ajai, A. & Imoku, C. (2015). Gender differences in mathematics achievement and retention scores; a case of problem based learning method. *International Journal (LES)*. 1 (1) 45-50.
- Akpana, A. T. & Oludo, C. (2019). Effects of instructional strategies on students' academic performance in Electrical installation in Technical colleges in Akwa Ibom State. *Journal of Education and Society*, 10(1), 88-101.
- Bayelsa public secondary schools, 1981- 2021- Knoema. <https://knoema.com...Education>.
- Chukueggu, C.O. & Umara, O. (2013). Reading comprehension and reading skills among learners. *Journal of Literacy Research*, 38 (1), 78-89.
- Collins, M. & Cheek, E. (2014). *Assessing and guiding reading instruction*. McGraw Hill.
- Herring, S. C. (2014). Gender differences in computer mediated communication: brining familiar baggage to the new frontier (On-line).
- Ijoko, G. A. (2021). Students' performance in oral English using project- based and group discussion learning techniques in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. *Journal of Resourcefulness and Distinction*, 18 (1), 73- 90.
- Langer, J. A. (2019). *Peer discussion as exploration, Literature and the Horizon of possibilities exploring tests, the role of discussion of literature*. MA Christopher Gordon.
- Okafor, I. S. (2016). Effects of two instructional strategies on secondary school students' achievement in reading comprehension in Rivers State. *Journal of Education and Society*, 10(1), 56-67.
- Onyeike, D. U. (2016). *Differential effects of project- based learning, group discussion, and self- regulated learning techniques on students' achievement in Biology*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt.
- Ogwo, B. A. (2016). *Curriculum development and educational technology*. Onaivi Printing and Publishing Co. LTD.
- Oyetunde, T.O. (2012). Second language reading: Insights from Nigeria primary schools. *The Reading Teacher*, 55(8), 748-755.
- Raham, F.; Khale J. K.; Jumani, N. B.; Ajural, M.; Malik, S. & Sharif, M. (2018). Impact of discussion method on students' performance. *International Journal of Business and Social Studies*. 2(7).
- Rudestam, K.E. (2014). Distributed education and the role of online learning in training professional psychologist. *Professional Psychology: Research Practice*. 34(4), 427-432.
- Wikipedia, (2011). *Dictionary of encyclopedia*. <http://ww.wiki.com>
- Wikipedia, (2015). *Dictionary of encyclopedia*. <http://ww.wiki.com>

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Effects of PowToon-Application-Videos on Achievement and Retention in Geomorphology among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in North-Central, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated Effects of Powtoon application video on achievement and retention among pre-service Geography teachers in North Central, Nigeria. Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The target population for this study was 1,163 pre-service Geography teachers, during the 2023/2024 academic session in North Central and One-fifty-One (151) were sampled for the study. Two research questions were raised to guide the study. Two experts validated the research instrument used for the study. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's alpha and 0.735 reliability, index was obtained. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Based on the findings, the study revealed that, utilization of Powtoon application videos in teaching of Geomorphology concepts enhanced students' performance than those exposed to conventional method of teaching. Based on the findings, it was further recommended among others that Geography teachers should utilize and encourage students on the use of Powtoon application videos as it promotes flexible learning and independent learning.

Keywords: Powtoon Application, Achievement, Retention and Geomorphology

Introduction

Over the last two decades, there have been advancements in digital technology, starting from the emergence of simple tools to the highly sophisticated devices and applications used tremendously in performing different task and functions in all sectors of the economy. Globally, there is virtually no sector that has not experienced technological shift from traditional ways of doing things to digitization. Technology has permeated almost all human endeavors, and its importance has cut across all facets of life (Ibrahim *et al*, 2024). The advancement in digital technology and the rate at which they emerge has driven innovation and new applications that touch our lives in different and often profound ways, thus, providing numerous opportunities and aspiration associated with digitalization (Singh 2021). The world has become increasingly more digital and ever more dependent on technological innovations.

Technological innovation is increasingly penetrating into education and skill domain with technology gradually being used to deliver education (instruction) knowledge and skill in new and invasive ways, therefore resulting in digital learning. Technology has transformed teaching and learning to be more student-centered through the incorporation of technology in education (Ibrahim *et al*, 2024). Technology is the principal delivery system of information particularly in online courses therefore, serving as a foundation for teaching and has encouraged instructors to device various means of teaching relevant course contents with applications, such as Powtoon.

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Powtoon is an online presentation software tool that allows individuals to create free and professional animated video explainers/messages and presentations as a substitute for PowerPoint. Powtoon is one of numerous application service providers for effortlessly creating learning material. Basri (2021), (Singh, 2020; Puspitarini and Hanif, 2019) It is a web-based application for quickly creating animated cartoons and video presentations. (Ashari, 2018). Powtoon is an e-Tool that creates animated videos for personal, educational, professional use, it is a free, web-based (with options to upgrade), user-friendly software that creates presentations via three simple and easy steps: writing a script, recording a voiceover, and adding visuals. This application can help teachers make animated exposures with features like handwriting animation, cartoon animation, and more vibrant transition effects with easy timing Basri (2021). (Balwant and Doon, 2021; Puspitarini and Hanif, 2019). The Powtoon application operates in a similar way to PowerPoint, in that it creates slides with teaching content. The distinction is in the animated character features, wherein Powtoon there are many different sorts of engaging animations that can assist the information to be presented, making it more interesting to deliver. Powtoon creates exposures that have animated features including handwriting animations, cartoon animations, and more vibrant transition effects and easy timing, most especially in courses such as Geography.

Geography is a subject that enable us to comprehend the Earth from a spatial viewpoint, by offering an organized structure about the world that surrounds us (Filgona, et al., 2017). The knowledge of geography is not only important and useful to the learners, but to everyone who seeks to cope with the ever-changing trends of our environment. The earth being the theatre where virtually all human activities take place is the focus of geographical study. Therefore, it is plausible that man knows about the nature and phenomenon on earth and the consequences of the interactions between man and his physical environment. In addition, the teaching of geography offers a unique means of furthering inquiry and high intellectual growth in students. Furthermore, studies have revealed that learning is facilitated as animation create positive attitude among the learners leading to positive learning outcomes. It can be in terms of their achievement and retention.

Academic achievement is the extent to which the learner or instructor or institution has attained their short- or long-term goals. Much researches in the recent years have focused on identifying the key factors that promotes academic achievement among student. The explosion of ICT has influenced the development of the society, in addition, Although, Powtoon is considered as a powerful and useful tool used in teaching and learning, Powtoon instructional videos just like other instructional application and technologies has inarguably assisted in high retention rate among geography students. Several studies have reported that multimedia can improve academic achievement (Moussa-Inaty, et al., 2019;), Similarly, Suyatna et al. (2017) revealed that enhanced achievement may also lead to students' ability to retain concepts better in a given task.

Retention is an ability to remember or recognize the content that has been learned or experienced or the ability to acquire and comprehend the knowledge as well as remember the content that has been mastered is an important issue in teaching and learning. Learning is effective when knowledge has been transferred into new situation. Retention is the ability to acquire and comprehend the knowledge of physical geography (Filgona, et al (2017). Studies have shown that student taught using other instructional application and technologies other than lecture method achieve greater material retention.

Statement of the Research Problem:

In spite of the usage of various effective interactive technologies and strategies such as the use of cartoons, pictures, illustrations, graphics among others, at various times to improve students' performance especially in physical Geography, the performances have persisted as shown by the semester results. The semester results of pre-service teachers in Geomorphology from Niger State College of Education Minna revealed from 2018/2023, that students' performance has been poor. However, several factors have been attributed to the dismal performance of pre-service teachers in the area of Geomorphology such as abstractness, inadequate use of technologies such as videos and the laxity on the part of the lecturers and the students. Consequently, upon the above, the need to alleviate the difficulties of abstraction and improve students' performance in physical Geography has informed and encouraged the use of advanced technologies such as Powtoon instructional videos, which are alternative ways to deliver relevant course content. Powtoon instructional videos are proven to be fun –based videos which attract the attention of the learners as well as improve the creative skill and understanding of the learners' on difficult and abstract concept. The use of videos (Powtoon) eliminates long passive teaching and rote learning that are associated with traditional methods of teaching and clears pre- service teachers misconception on what seems to be, to what it is, more so, these videos engages the cognitive/ mental ability of the learner and assist in retaining knowledge on content taught effectively. As a result, the researcher sought to investigate the Effects of Powtoon-Application-Videos on Achievement and Retention in Geomorphology among Colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-Central, Nigeria

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Objectives of the study:

The aim of the study was to investigate the Effects of Powtoon-Application-Videos on Achievement and Retention in Geomorphology among Colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-Central, Nigeria. The objectives of the study are to:

1. Develop Powtoon and Animato-generated instructional videos on Geography (Geomorphology) concepts.
2. Determine the effects of Powtoon and Animato-generated instructional videos on pre-service Geography teachers' academic achievement in Geomorphology.
3. Investigate the effects of Powtoon and Animato-generated instructional videos on pre-service Geography teachers' retention in Geomorphology.

Research Questions:

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What are the strategies in the development of Powtoon application videos for teaching and learning of Geomorphology among pre-service Geography teachers in North-central Nigeria?
2. What are the differences in the mean academic achievement score of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and those exposed to conventional method?
3. What are the differences in the mean retention score of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and those exposed to conventional method?

Hypotheses:

The following null research hypotheses were formulated and was tested at 0.05 level of significance;

HO₁. There is no significant difference in the academic achievement scores of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon and Animato-generated instructional videos.

HO₂. There is no significant difference in the retention scores of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon and Animato-generated instructional videos

Methodology

The study adopted experimental research design. The research design that was adopted for this study is Quasi-experimental experimental design using the pretest, posttest non-equivalent group. The variables of the study included achievement, retention, attitude and Powtoon. The targeted population for the study comprises of 782 pre-service geography teachers in north central. The entire population was used for the study because of the manageable size of the population. The research instruments that were used for the study are: Treatment instruments and test instruments. The instruments were validated by experts in Geography, Educational Technology, in Federal University of Technology, Minna psychology and Computer Studies in College of Education Minna. In order to determine the reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot test was conducted using 15 students who were part of the population but that did not participate in the main study. The data collected was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Formula (PPMC) and a reliability coefficient of 0.735 and 0, 749, were obtained respectively. Mean and standard deviation were the descriptive statistics used to analyze the data collected for the purpose of answering the three research questions raised. A decision mean score of 3.00 was used. Every item with a mean score below 3.00 was considered as Disagree while an item with mean scores of 3.00 and above was considered as Agree. Similarly, inferential statistics was used to test the six null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance using (Z-Test) at pretest. If a significant difference exists at pretest between the groups, Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used at posttest to normalize the pre-existing group differences.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What are the strategies in the development of Powtoon application videos for teaching and learning of Geomorphology among pre-service Geography teachers in North-central Nigeria?

To answer this research question, Powtoon application video was developed with the aid of ADDIE Model by the researcher through the following strategies/steps.

- Step1: Planning and identifying geomorphology concept (mountains, plateau and plains) as well as creating a storyboard.
- Step 2: Designing tips, visuals, color scheme font and engagement text on geomorphology concepts.
- Step 3: Developing/Creating the Powtoon video by signing up/ creating an account on Powtoon, selecting a template adding slides, adding content, text images, animations voice over and transitions.
- Step 4: Implementing the video, by Reviewing the video and sharing it to the learners to view the content of the video.

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Step 5: Evaluating the video to obtain the feedbacks after sharing it for the learners.

Research Question 2: What is the mean achievement score of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and those exposed to conventional method? To answer this research question, descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation was used.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of pretest and posttest achievement scores of experimental group and control group.

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Differences
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental Group	120	8.37	3.021	21.71	3.258	13.34
Control group	31	10.29	3.143	19.13	3.703	8.84

Key: X=Mean SD=Standard Deviations, N= Number in Samples

Table 1 displays the mean and standard deviation of experimental group treated with Powtoon application video and control group taught with lecture method at pretest and posttest level. The mean achievement scores of experimental group in the posttest was higher with a mean score of (M=21.71, SD=3.258) than the pretest mean score of (M=8.37, SD=3.021) indicating a major change in their achievement obtained from the pretest posttest mean differences (13.34) for the experimental group. Similarly, in the control group, the mean achievement scores on the posttest was higher (M= 19.13, SD = 3.703) than the pretest mean score of (M=10.29, SD=3.143) indicating a major change in their achievement obtained from the pretest posttest mean differences (8.84) for the control group. Thus, there is a difference in the achievement scores of pre-service Geography teachers' taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application video achieving higher than those taught with to lecture method.

Research Question 3: What is the mean retention score of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and those exposed to conventional method? To answer this research question, descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of posttest and retention test scores of experimental group and control group.

Group	N	Posttest		Retention		Mean differences
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental Group	120	21.71	3.258	19.32	2.868	2.39
Control Group	31	19.13	3.703	17.37	2.500	1.76

Key: X=Mean SD=Standard Deviations, N= Number in Samples

Table 2 displays the mean and standard deviation of experimental group treated with Powtoon application video and control group taught with lecture method at posttest and retention test. The mean retention scores of students for the experimental group was higher (M=19.32, SD=2.868) than the posttest score (M=21.71, SD= 3.258). The mean difference was (2.39) indicating a substantial loss in their retention. For the control group, the mean retention scores were also lower (M=17.37, SD=2.500) than the posttest score (M=19.13, SD=3.703). The mean difference was (1.76) indicating a loss in their retention. The finding revealed that there is a difference in the mean retention score of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application video and lecture method, with students exposed to Powtoon application video retaining higher than those in the control group.

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of pre-service Geography teachers taught geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method.

Table 3: ANOVA comparison of the posttest mean achievement scores of experimental group and control group.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	163.521	1	163.521	12.493	0.001
Within Groups	1950.254	149	13.089		
Total	2113.775	150			

Table 3: presents the result of an ANOVA conducted to compare the posttest mean achievement scores of experimental group and control group. The ANOVA was used to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in the mean achievement scores between these two experimental groups the between groups variation representing the differences in mean achievement scores between experimental group and control group, revealed that there was statistically significant difference $F(12,493) = 0.001, p < 0.05$ indicating a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of pre-service

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Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method, the hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method differs significantly in their mean achievements.

H₀₂. There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method.

Table 4: ANOVA comparison of the retention mean scores of experimental group and control group.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	94.247	1	94.247	14.175	0.000
Within Groups	990.641	149	6.649		
Total	1084.887	150			

Significant at P<0.05

Table 4: presents the result of an ANOVA conducted to compare the retention mean achievement scores of experimental group and control group. The ANOVA was used to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in the mean retention scores between these two groups. The between groups’ variation representing the differences in mean achievement scores between experimental group and control group. The table revealed that $F = 14.175$, sig-VALUE=.000 AT $P > 0.05$, indicating a significant difference in the mean retention scores of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method, the hypothesis is also rejected. This implies that pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method differs significantly in their mean retention.

Discussion of Findings

From the findings, it was revealed that using Powtoon application video and lecture method were all effective in improving students' retention in Geomorphology but students exposed to Powtoon application video retaining higher than those in the control group. This finding affirmed the assertions of Puspitarini, et al., (2018) whose findings indicated that using Powtoon in teaching enhance students’ performance than expository method of teaching. The reason of this finding could be to the fact that Powtoon presentations enabled students to demonstrate collaborative learning and creativity in the design and organization of ideas. Both collaboration and creativity are essential skills for the 21st century learners. Basri and Fadli (2021) also found that the use of the Powtoon Application could increase students' learning motivation where the mean value increased significantly and the increase in motivation of the experimental group was higher than the control group. The finding of this study corroborates with the findings of Ashari (2018) which revealed that Powtoon is one of the software for creating animated features, including handwriting animations, cartoon animations, and more vibrant transition effects and easy timing, so this Powtoon application is containing material, combined with animations and transitions to make it more exciting and convenient.

Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion above, Powtoon application video media is developed on the basis of learning in the classroom which still uses many lecture methods, especially on memorizing material, learning resources and learning media using textbooks, electronic school books (BSE), images and maps and not yet utilized facilities in schools such as the internet, laptops, LCDs and projectors optimally. The study revealed that using Powtoon instructional video is highly effective in improving students' retention in Geomorphology and as such Powtoon videos should be blended with other teaching method such as lecture method for effective learning to take place. Based on the findings and conclusion drawn, the following recommendations are made to improve students’ performance in Geography: Geography lecturers should utilize and encourage students on the use of Powtoon application videos as it promotes flexible learning, autonomous and independent learning. Geography lecturers should motivate students to learn Geography using Powtoon application videos Technology to improve their performances generally. Global system for Mobile Network (GSM) should improve on their services for a steady network to be achieved especially in rural areas.

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Recommendations

1. Geography lecturers should utilize and encourage students on the use of Powtoon and Animoto instructional videos Technology as it promotes flexible learning, autonomous and independent learning.
2. Geography lecturers should motivate learner to learn Geography using Powtoon application videos to improve their performances generally.

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References

- Akinbadewa, B. O., & Sofowora, O. A. (2020). Effectiveness of Multimedia Learning Packages in Improving the Attitudes of Students towards Learning Biology in Secondary Schools. *International Journal on Studies in Education*.
- Ashari, A. R. (2018, November 2). Tutorial PowToon. Retrieved from <https://www.scribd.com/doc/202979996/Tutorial-PowToon>
- Basri, M., & Fadli, F. (2021). The Effect of Using the Powtoon Application on Student Learning Motivation. *Review of International Geographical Education (RIGEO)*, 11(5), 4018-4024 .doi:10.48047/rigeo.11.05.283
- Filgona, J., Filgona, J., & Sababa, L. K. (2017, February 5). Mastery learning strategy and learning retention. Retrieved from Effects of Senior Secondary School Students' Achievement in Physical Geography: <http://www.preprints.org>
- Ibrahim, A. M., Ibrahim, I. K., Oluwole, C. F., & Ahmed, B. (2024). Comparative performance of undergraduate students in microteaching using Telegram and WhatsApp in collaborative learning settings. *Journal of Mathematics and science Teacher*, 4(2), 2752-6054,
- Moussa-Inaty, J., Atallah, F., & Causpin, M. (2019). Instructional mode: A better predictor of performance than student learning style. *International Journal of Instruction*, 12(3), 17-34.
- Puspitarini, Y. D., Akhyar, M., & Djono. (2019). Development of video media based on Powtoon in social sciences. *International Journal of Educational Research Review*, 4(2), 198-205.
- Suyatna, A., Anggraini, D., Agustina, D., & Widyastuti, D. (2017). The role of visual representation in physics learning: Dynamic versus static visualization. *Journal of Physics*, 1(2), 140-144.
- Filgona, J., Filgona, J., & Sababa, L. K. (2017, February 5). *Mastery learning strategy and learning retention*. Retrieved from Effects of Senior Secondary School Students' Achievement in Physical Geography: <http://www.preprints.org>
- Singh, M. (2020). *Impact of Technology in Indian Education System*. Retrieved from Advance and Innovative Research, 349, 459: <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?>

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Effects of Simulation Games and Rote Learning Strategies on Performance in Numeracy Concept among Lower Basic Pupils in Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the effect of simulation games and Rote Learning Instructional Strategies on Performance among Numeracy pupils in Lower Basic Schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Two objectives corresponding research questions and hypotheses, respectively guided the study. Quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of 423,036 (Male 253,821 and Female 169,215) lower basic class II pupils during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kaduna State. A sample of 248 (male, 166 and Female, 82) pupils were selected from the target population using multistage sampling technique. Numeracy Performance Test (NPT) was used to collect data for the study. Reliability index of 0.697 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Mean and Standard Deviations was used to analyse the research questions. sample-paired and independent t-test statistical tools were used to test hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed that pupils taught the concept numeracy using simulation Games had higher performance than those exposed to lecture method. However, both simulation games and rote learning can be used to teach numeracy as they improved performance than the Conventional Strategy. The study recommended that; Simulation games strategy should be used by teachers of numeracy since performance improved after treatment and Rote learning strategy should be used by teachers of numeracy since performance improved after treatment.

Keywords: Simulation Games, Rote learning Strategies, Performance and Numeracy.

Introduction

Numeracy is one of the core subjects taught at the Lower Basic School, through which the child is exposed to good knowledge of numbers, basic operations, fractions to mention but a few. Pupils' intellectual growth greatly benefits from numeracy education, especially in basic schools. However, many pupils need help, understanding and retaining numerical concepts, which can hinder their overall performance and achievement. Educators and researchers have recently explored various instructional strategies to enhance pupils' learning experiences and outcomes in Numeracy. Most nations developed, because of the role played by teachers through their teaching activities. Hence, teaching must be done so pupils perceive, understand, and retain what has been taught to record higher scores of meaningful applications of knowledge in different situations. Teachers should be equipped with the latest techniques, strategies, systematic processes and procedures to achieve the stated aims and objectives, for obtaining sustainable learning outcomes, (Guga, 2019).

Simulation games have emerged as a promising tool in Numeracy education. These games provide pupils with interactive and engaging learning environments that simulate real-world mathematical scenarios. Pupils can enhance their problem-solving abilities and better comprehend mathematical ideas by actively engaging in the game's problem-solving activities. Moreover, simulation games offer opportunities for immediate feedback, which can help pupils identify and correct their mistakes, leading to enhanced learning and performance, (Ajai 2020). On the other hand, Rote Learning Strategy has been traditionally employed in Numeracy education. Rote Learning involves the teacher deploying a large amount of information to learners, emphasizing memorization and repetition of mathematical facts, formulas, and procedures. While this approach can result in quick recall of information, more is needed to promote deep understanding and conceptual mastery. However, Iwuji

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2012 argued that, proponents of Rote Learning argue that it can be effectively applicable in certain contexts, particularly for learning procedural knowledge and basic mathematical facts, (Iwuji, 2012).

The theoretical framework on which this study was built upon is the theory of constructivism. The significance of educational theory is paramount, serving as the guiding framework or blueprint to be interpreted and implemented for effective teaching. This study's foundational theories are rooted in constructivism and constructive controversy. Key proponents of these theories whose models were applied include John Dewey, Jean Piaget, Jerome Brunner, and Vygotsky, who are often regarded as philosophical pioneers in this approach. Fundamentally, constructivism is a theory grounded in empirical observation and scientific study that explains how individuals learn. It posits that, people construct their knowledge and comprehension of the world by actively engaging with experiences and reflecting upon them. The theory is about people using their experiences and cognitive abilities to study problems and learn skills or concepts. Learners use their senses to construct new ideas actively using existing knowledge and skills. Constructivism is a major learning theory and is particularly applicable to the learning of Mathematics. It is a theory grounded in empirical observation and practical application.

Statement of the Research Problem

Over time, the researchers, being teachers, observed persistent failure in internal and placement examinations in the basic schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria. As 2021/2022 Session recorded 45% failure in Numeracy placement Examination. Then 2022/2023 Session recorded greater failure with 38%. This could result from poor selection of instructional strategies, poor utilization of selected strategies, inadequate instructional materials, and teachers' poor attitude towards teaching. Numeracy, among many of these, tends to influence pupils' performance among Lower Basic Schools. There are many teaching strategies employed in teaching lower basic Numeracy. Teachers are anticipated to use a variety of instructional approaches to foster academic success among lower-basic school pupils. An effective system in the contemporary educational landscape should facilitate extensive social interaction and engagement between teachers and pupils to yield positive outcomes. Creating a supportive, open, and interactive environment for pupils is essential. Such an environment encourages knowledge discovery, enhancing retention and elevating academic performance, particularly in Numeracy among lower-level pupils. (Karan, 2017). The findings of this study hold significance for curriculum developers, Federal Ministry of Education, textbook authors, Numeracy teachers, Numeracy pupils, and researchers in the field.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the effects of simulation games and rote learning strategies on numeracy performance and retention among lower basic pupils in Kaduna state Nigeria. While two specific objectives were to:

- xi. determine the performance of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.
- xii. examine the performance of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

7. what is the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria?
8. what is the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

Based on the research questions, the following null hypotheses were formulated to and tested in the study:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted a Quasi-experimental research design, which employed two experimental groups and one control group with intact classes. All groups underwent a pre-test to assess the pupils' entry capacity. The first experimental group

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(EG1) received instruction in Numeracy using the Simulation-Games strategy, and the second experimental group (EG2) was taught Numeracy through Rote Learning. In contrast, the control group (CG) received conventional instruction in Numeracy. Following a six-week treatment period, a post-test was administered to evaluate the effectiveness of the Simulation-Games and Rote Learning strategies on pupils' performance in lower basic Numeracy schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria. This approach aligns with Aliyu (2016), as quasi-experimental design allows for investigating cause-effect relationships between independent and dependent variables.

The study population comprised four hundred and twenty-three thousand and thirty-six 423,036 (Male 253,821 and Female 169,215) Numeracy pupils from all Lower Basic Schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria. The sample size for the study comprised two hundred and forty eight (248) (male, 166 and Female, 82) basic two Numeracy pupils from the intact classes of the sampled Lower Basic Schools. This replicated with Aliyu (2016), who recommended that, the sample size be at least 30 and less than 500 for experimental research. A purposive sampling technique was adopted to select the three Lower Basic Schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria, based on a similar Curriculum as the Federal Ministry of Education prescribed. A simple random sampling technique was however, used to assign experimental group one group (EG₁), which was taught Numeracy using simulation games, experimental group two (EG₂), which was taught Numeracy through Rote learning strategy then control group (CG) which was taught using Conventional Strategy.

The instrument Numeracy Performance Test (NPT)" developed by the researcher was based on the content of lower basic two, which included the following topics: identification of numbers 1-50, Addition of whole numbers, subtraction, division, multiplication, and Introduction to fractions. NPT comprises thirty (30) objective questions with four multiple-choice item options A-D each, which carried equal marks of two (2) marks and was rewarded for each correct answer and zero (0) effects for a wrong answer, making sixty (60) marks).

The treatment was administered by the researcher (self) and the whole exercise lasted for six weeks (6). In the experiment, Experimental Group 1 (EG1) received instruction through the Simulation-Games Strategy, Experimental Group 2 (EG2) was taught using the Rote Learning strategy, and the Control Group (CG) was instructed using the Conventional Strategy. Subsequently, a post-test was immediately conducted for all the groups using the data collection instrument (NPT). The scores obtained from this administration were used as post-test performance scores for the study. Following the post-test, the instrument was re-administered for the retention test; one week after the experiment (treatment). This is in order to determine the ability of the pupils to retain, recall and reproduce previously learnt content.

The mean scores and standard deviation obtained from the scores of pre-test, post-test and post-post-test, as well as t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance were used to test the three null hypotheses. The null hypotheses were rejected when t-calculated values were greater than the t-critical values, while the null hypotheses were accepted when t-calculated values were equal to or less than t-critical values.

Presentation of Results

To address the research questions posed in this study, the collected data were subjected to analysis using mean and standard deviation, as outlined below:

Research Question One:

What is the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria?

To address this research question, the data obtained from the post-test were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. A summary of the analysis was presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Post-test Performance of Pupils taught Numeracy using Simulation Games Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Method

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	Decision
Simulation Games	52	24.96	2.80	14.79	Significant
Conventional	52	10.17	2.13		

Source: (Field survey, 2023)

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Table 1 above, revealed the effect of Simulation Game Strategy on the performance of pupils as compared to conventional strategy. Meanwhile the table shows that the performance of those taught using Simulation Game Strategy had far better with mean score 24.96 as against that of pupils taught using conventional strategy with the mean score of 10.17 with corresponding standard deviation of 2.80 and 2.13 respectively, which indicates that the pupils mean difference is 14.97. This implies that pupils' performance at various strategies have varied from one another.

Research Question Two:

What is the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria?

To address this research question, the data collected from the post-test were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The summary of the analysis was presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Post-test of Performance of Pupils taught Numeracy using Rote Learning Strategy and those Taught using Conventional method

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	Decision
Rote Learning	72	24.96	2.30	14.10	Significant
Conventional	72	10.56	1.87		

Source: (Field survey, 2023)

Table 2 showed the Performance mean score of pupils taught Numeracy using Rote Learning was 24.66 and for pupils taught with Conventional method had a mean of 10.56 with a mean difference of 14.10 was obtained. This indicated that Rote Learning Strategy is also effective strategy for teaching Numeracy to pupils in lower-basic schools.

Null Hypothesis One:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of independent t-test analysis on performances of pupils taught Numeracy using Simulation Games Strategy and those taught using the Conventional Method

Groups	Mean	SD	N	t-cal.	Sig.	Decision
Simulation Games	24.96	2.80	52	11.23	0.00	Rejected
Conventional	10.17	2.13	52			

Source: (Field survey, 2023)

Table 3 showed a significant difference in the performances of pupils taught Numeracy using Simulation-Games Strategy and those exposed to conventional strategy in Lower Basic Schools. The result revealed t-cal. of 11.23 with a p-value of 0.00. The null hypothesis was rejected because the p-value of 0.00 is less than 0.05 level of significant. By implication, there was a difference of 14.79 between the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method.

Null Hypothesis Two:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Table 4: Summary of independent t-test analysis on performance scores of pupils taught Numeracy using Rote Learning strategy and those taught with Conventional Method

Groups	Mean	SD	N	t-cal.	Sig.	Decision
Rote Learning	24.66	2.30	72	10.12	0.00	Rejected
Conventional	10.56	1.87	72			

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Source: (Field survey, 2023)

Table 4 indicated a significant difference in the performance scores of pupils taught Numeracy using Rote Learning strategy and those taught using Conventional Method in Lower Basic Schools. The result shows a t-cal. of 10.12 with a p-value of 0.00. The null hypothesis was rejected since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the 0.05 significance level. This implied Rote Learning Strategy effectively enhanced the learning of Numeracy at the lower basic level in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of study revealed that pupils taught numeracy using simulation games performed better than those taught using conventional method. Therefore, simulation games are effective in teaching pupils numeracy in lower basic schools because there was a significant difference between the Performance of pupils taught Numeracy using simulation games and those taught using Conventional strategies P-value=.000. As a result, the hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference between the Performance of pupils taught Numeracy using simulation games and those taught operating conventional method in lower basic schools in Kaduna state, Nigeria was rejected. The outcomes of this study aligned with previous research findings on the positive impact of Simulation Games on pupils' Performance. This alignment was consistent with the results of Chukwu (2017), who discovered that employing local games in teaching subtraction operations improved pupils' Performance more effectively than conventional lecture methods. Similarly, Ezewi (2019) demonstrated that learners taught with games-based learning strategies outperformed those taught using conventional methods. Ajia (2020) further supported these findings by revealing that students exposed to games and simulations achieved higher geometry performance than those who were not.

The second finding of study revealed that pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy performed better than those taught using the Conventional Method. Therefore, Rote learning was effective in teaching pupils numeracy in lower basic schools because there was a significant difference between the Performance of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning and those taught using Conventional Method P-value=.000. As a result, the hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference between the Performance of pupils taught Numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those taught operating Conventional Method in lower basic schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria was rejected. This finding aligned with the findings of earlier studies. For example, Christian (2016) observed that pupils in the Mathematical Rote learning strategy group outperformed those in the control group in Mathematics. Additionally, Aladejana (2013) reported that Rote Learning enhances pupils' capacity to recall basic facts rapidly and contributes to developing foundational knowledge in a subject. Instances of rote learning encompass memorizing multiplication tables or the periodic table of elements.

Conclusion

Based on the above findings and recommendations the study concluded that, simulation games and rote learning strategies improves the teaching and learning of numeracy among lower-basic school pupils in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

19. Simulation games strategy should be used by teachers of numeracy since performance improved after treatment.
20. Rote learning strategy should be used by teachers of numeracy since performance improved after treatment.

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References

- Agomuoh, P.C (2018). *A Comparative Study of the Effects of PEDDA & TLC Constructivists Instructional Models on Pupils Conceptual change and Retention in Physics*. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, Department of Science Education, UNN.
- Ajai, J. (2020). Effect of Games and Simulations Teaching Strategy in Pupils' Academic Performance and Retention in Mathematics at the Post Basic. level In Gwer West Local Government Area, Benue State. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313900354> on June 06, 2022.
- Ajai, J. (2020). Effect of Games and Simulations Teaching Strategy in Pupils' Academic Performance and Retention in Mathematics at the Post Basic level In Gwer West Local Government Area, Benue State. Retrieved On 06 June, 2021 <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313900354>
- Aladejana, H. (2013). Effect of Instruction in Mathematics Reading on Pupils Performance and Retention in Mathematics Education; *Journal of Quality Education JOQE 1*, 65-72.
- Aliyu, D, A. (2016). *Conducting Research in Education: Concepts designs and prints*.
- Brunner, J. S. (1990). *The Process of Education*. New York. Alford Knopt. Inc.
- Christian, E. R Kurumeh M A & Obida J (2016). *The Impact of Mathematics Games on The Development of Basic Concept of Plane Mathematics*. Journal of issues on Mathematics 2 Vol (4) 88-94.
- Chukwu, J. O (2017). Effect of Games on Performance and Retention of JSS Pupils in Igbo Grammar. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Dewey, J. (1916). Interest and discipline: democracy and education. Retrieved from http://www.johndeweyphilosophy.com/books/democracy_and_education/Interest_and_Discipline.html.
- Guga, A. (2019). *Introduction to Curriculum Development and Implementation*. Kareem and Guga Publishers.
- Iwuji, N.P. (2012). *Effects of Activity-Based Teaching Strategy on Academic Achievement and Retention in Basic Science Concepts Among Junior Secondary School Students*. Unpublished M. Ed. Dissertation. Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Kaduna State Nigeria.
- Karan, M.O. (2017). Games Assisted Instructional Materials. A Strategy for Enhanced Pupils Performances in Integrated Science. *Journal Of Research in Curriculum and Teaching*, 2(1), 120 – 128.
- Nzewi, O.G (2019). Effect Of Computer Aided Instruction on Secondary School Pupils Performance And Retention In Basic Statistics Unpublished M.Sc Thesis Department of Science & Computer Science Education ESUT.
- Piaget, J. (1954). *The Construction of Reality in the Child*. New York. Basic Books.
- Skinner, D. (2010). *Effective Teaching and Learning in Practice*. London: continuum.
- Vygotsky, L. (1978). *Mind and society*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

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Impact of Banditry Activities on Enrolment and Curriculum Implementation among Nomadic Primary School Pupils in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was made on comparative analysis between students' enrolment and curriculum implementation on impact of banditry activities among nomadic primary school pupils in Zamfara State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives which were transformed into corresponding research questions and hypotheses. Descriptive survey research method was adopted for the study with a sample size of 463 respondents, this comprised teachers, students and parents. The checklist information obtained from Zamfara State Agency for Nomadic Education was used to answer research question one of the study. While, self-developed questionnaire was adapted to collect information from the respondents. The data obtained from them was used to answer research question two. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research question at the decision rule of 2.5 while Kruskal-Wallis statistical method was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that there is a gradual increase in students' enrolment in nomadic primary schools, and curriculum implementation was not adequate. It has been recommended that the stake-holders of nomadic education should maintain and promote the current enrolment rate, however they should take any possible action to ensure peace and calmness in the state, in order to enable all actors in the curriculum implementation discharge their duties without threat or fear.

Keywords: Nomadic, Banditry, Security Challenge, Curriculum implementation.

Introduction

Education is undoubtedly considered as the most outstanding development priority area in the world today. The core purpose of education is human development. It is belief that education is considered as backbone of development in any society. Prabhat (2021) described education as a process of expediting learning, acquiring knowledge, values and virtue. It contributes to the development of better people around the globe by putting enduring method in which people gain information, skills and ethics. In other words; Wikipedia (2023) described education as a purposeful activity directed at achieving certain aims, such as transmitting knowledge or fostering skills and character traits. With regards to this, Government of all levels establishes schools for formal education from elementary level to tertiary level. As such adequate and organized arrangements were made to ensure that Nigerian children acquire education in an organized conventional school system. Most of these schools especially primary that gives basic education situated permanently at one place or community. However, the pupils that attend the school are predominantly permanent residents of such locality. Despite this effort by the government, it has been observed that a significant number of Nigerian children do not attend the school for at least basic education. This is because they do not have permanent place to live, thus they live considerable part of their life in the bush, using temporary settlements. These people are referred to as nomad they couldn't attend organized conventional school. They include children of migrant fishermen, Fulani-herdsmen, Bororo-herdsmen (Bararaji/Bugaje) and so on. As the government realized that continued reliance on mainstream formal and conventional school system would not adequately serve the educational needs of the Nigerian nomads or the earnest desire of the nation to provide basic education for all its citizens.

Hence, in its quest to regularize this learning gap between children of permanent settlement and their counterpart (nomad), that the Federal Government of Nigeria in 1989 established National Commission for Nomadic Education by defunct Decree 41, now Nomadic Education Act, Cap N20 Law of the Federation of Nigeria 2004, to cater for the educational needs of the socially excluded, educationally disadvantaged and migrant groups in Nigeria (FGN 2005). The commission has progressed and performs several roles in pursuing knowledge to nomads. And it has branch offices in all states and local governments with a view to bring knowledge closer to them, and to ensure smooth coordination, implementation and evaluation of its programmes. Nomads are entitled to education, to enable them contribute their quota in all ramifications of national development. Giving them sound education will no doubt acquaint them with social, economic and political atmosphere around them, so as to understand the kind of contribution they will give in the nation-building. Similarly, giving them formal education will indeed help them to think clearly through which they can understand their strength and weakness. It also helps them to be

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mindful of their nation. Nomadic education is peculiar with teaching of good character such as value, honesty, kindness, equity as well as generosity, courage, freedom and respect to elders. With regards to this, that the National Policy on Education (2022) says; education is the birth right of every Nigerian child and should be brought close to the environment of the child. In other words "everyone has the right to education". Government shall direct its policy towards ensuring that there are equal and adequate educational opportunities for all (Nigerian Constitution 1979). Therefore, educating nomads will help them to differentiate between right and wrong thereby reducing crime rate in the society. It also helps them to maintain rules of law of their immediate environment and making the world a better place to live.

Statement of the Research Problem

Enrolment and retention of students in school cannot be separated; they are like two side of the same coin. Hence, the impartation of sound knowledge at any educational level can be possible if the enrolment and retention of students are adequate. Education system in Zamfara state is faced with some security challenges that appear to cripple the system. Nwannah (2022) reported that between 2019 to date four public secondary schools have been attacked by the revenging bandits and hundreds of students were kidnapped. Nomadic education in Zamfara state is one of the educational categories that undergo through banditry activities in recent times. These banditry activities have impact on the enrolment of students in nomadic primary schools. The available records from Zamfara State Agency for Nomadic Education, have shown that the average enrolment of nomadic students in primary schools before the banditry activities was 1,093 each year. And between 2013 to 2017 when the banditry was at initial stage in the state, the enrolment had reduced to averagely 822 annually. Ismail (2023) posited that although the government has spent millions of Naira in Nomadic Education Programme, the measure of educational attainment among the Fulanis remain low; the quality of education among them is mediocre at best. Subsequently the annual average enrolment of nomads children in primary schools between 2018 to 2023 has risen to 1,819. According to the records the rise of the enrolment within the said years must has relationship with the Ruga-Programme initiated by Government of Zamfara state under the administration of Governor Bello Muhammed Matawalle. This programme was aimed at converging nomads especially Fulanis at one settlement with a view to deprive them from movement from one place to another. It is part of the provision of the programme that the new settlements of Fulanis would be facilitated with all social amenities, such as; veterinary to take care of the health of their animals, dispensary for the health of themselves, schools for their children, skills acquisition centres to learn vocational skills and so on.

Other reasons that led to the rise of enrolment in nomadic schools were incorporation of village heads and Ardos (Fulani Traditional Heads) in the Enrolment Drive Campaign (EDC) for nomadic schools. However, voluntary organization such as "Fulbe Nani Fami" meaning "Fulani have Head and Understood" has contributed a lot in the sensitization and mobilization among the Fulani during the Enrolment Drive Campaign, School Based Management Committee (SBMC) in collaboration with Mothers' Association (MAS) has greatly contributed in rising the enrolment of nomadic schools in Zamfara state. Their effort was being succeeded through inculcation of strong feeling of community ownership and control, with active participation in the overall development of the nomads schools for improved learning outcomes. In relation to this development Ismail (2023) stated that about 85% of the postural Fulanis express their willingness to send their children to school; in some places the Fulanis have even built their own schools through community effort and have asked government to send teachers and teaching materials.

The records made available by the Agency for Nomadic Education Zamfara State Branch revealed that destruction of schools and vandalization of school facilities is one of the hindrances against proper or full implementation of curriculum contents in nomadic schools. Thus, the activities of bandits have put fear in the mind of teachers, which in turn make them abstain from their various working stations resulting in inadequate implementation of curriculum contents to nomads' students. This situation does not affect the activities of teachers alone, but it discourages even the routine school supervision which is done to guide and motivate teachers in order to ensure effective curriculum implementation. It has also been revealed that sometimes the bandits seize the school building and turn it their shelter or hideout. The situation clearly forbids the normal school activities in the affected school. This is in line with the report of Nwannah (2022) saying that, it was no longer news that education sector had totally collapsed in Zamfara state especially when the education calendar has been totally altered due to the insecurity situation. In view of the above the researcher intends to conduct research on comparative analysis between students' enrolment and curriculum implementation on impact of banditry among nomadic primary schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

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Research Objectives

Below are the objectives of the study

21. Examine the current enrolment rate of children in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state.
22. Determine the challenges in curriculum implementation in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state.

Research Questions

1. What is the current enrolment rate of children in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state?
2. What are the challenges in curriculum implementation in nomadic primary schools, amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state?

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁ There is no significant difference in the current enrolment rate in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference in the curriculum implementation in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study because it involves an investigation covering the entire nomadic primary schools in the state. Dada (2016). Descriptive survey design is the most basic type of enquiry that aims to observe certain phenomena, typically at a single point at a time; and is used to estimate specific parameters in a population. Two objectives were set for the study which were transformed into research questions and hypotheses. The researcher made sample with 463 respondents comprising parents, teachers, and students. The instrument used was self-structured questionnaire which was formed in four-point scale, and had been reviewed by the experts through extensive literature review to ascertain its validity and reliability. Inputs of the experts were used to reverse the instrument. The checklist data obtained from Zamfara State Agency for Nomadic Education was carefully used to answer research question one of the study; and the data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research question two at the decision mean of 2.5, while Kruskal-Wallis statistical tool was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Research question one: What is the current enrolment status of children in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state?

Table 1: Presents Description on the Enrolment of Children in Nomadic Primary School in Zamfara State

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Source: Zamfara State Agency for Nomadic Education (2023)

Table 1 above indicates that the average enrolment of nomadic pupils before the banditry activities was 1,093 each year, and when the banditry began the enrolment rate reduced to averagely 822 annually. The average enrolment of nomads' children between 2018 to 2023 had risen to 1,819. This revealed the enrolment rate has risen grossly in nomadic primary schools of the state. Therefore, null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the current enrolment rate in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities is hereby accepted.

Research Question Two: What are the challenges of curriculum delivery implementation in nomadic primary schools amidst banditry activities in Zamfara state?

Table 2: Presents the Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents' Opinions on the Curriculum implementation in Nomadic Primary Schools amidst Banditry Activities in Zamfara State.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
1.	Teachers have no any fear on their way to attend their school	2.32	.004
2.	You keep your students busy doing lesson in class at all the periods	2.41	0.05
3.	Teachers in your school teach their respective subjects to students fearlessly	2.32	.004
4.	The syllabus of all subjects are adequate delivered in your school	2.33	.003
5.	Volunteer teachers help you to teach your students in your school	2.13	.023
6.	Bandits do not bother nomadic schools in their attacks	2.18	.018
7.	Banditry does not hinder routine supervision to nomadic schools	2.47	0.11
8.	Sometimes bandits seize your schools and turn them their shelter	2.76	0.4
9.	Government relocates some of the nomadic schools to more safer places to encourage you deliver curriculum contents fully	2.33	.003
10.	Nomadic schools in more security challenged places are being closed till further notice.	2.39	0.03
Grand Mean		2.36	

Source: Survey data, 2023

Table 2 above presents the responses of the respondents on the enrolment rate of nomadic children amidst banditry activities in the state. The table shows the grand mean of 2.36 which is lower than the decision mean of 2.5. This result implies that curriculum implementation in nomadic primary schools in Zamfara state is not adequate.

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Table 3: Presents the Summary of Kruskal-Wallis Test on the Difference in the Curricula implementation in Nomadic Primary Schools Amidst Banditry Activities in Zamfara state.

Respondents	Mean	H Calculated	H Critical	df	p- value
Parents	733.41				
Teachers	682.57	12.06	5.991	2	0.03
Students	583.78				
(Hcal=12.06, Hcrit = 5.991)				P=003<0.05	

Table 3 shows the result of the test of hypothesis two on the challenges of curriculum implementation. The H-cal of 12.06 while the H-crit is 5.991 at df 2. The P-value is 003 <0.05 alpha level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the curriculum implementation in nomadic primary schools admits banditry activities is hereby rejected.

Discussion of Findings

From the finding of this study, it was discovered that the enrolment of children in Nomadic Primary Schools has been raised grossly in Zamfara State. This implies that no significant different exist in the enrolment of students in nomadic schools amidst banditry activities in the state. This finding corresponds with the finding of Statista Research and Development (2022) who pointed out that in 2019, there were more than 1.1 million children enrolled in nomadic elementary schools in Nigeria. However, Ahmad (2019) reported that the Chairman SUBEB Gombe State has solicited for the establishment of more nomadic schools to cater for the numerous numbers of nomads' children in school age children in the state, he described the existing ones as grossly inadequate. Akighir and Isa (2013) showed that a small increase in the enrolment rate of children in nomadic schools have not pace with the increase in government expenditure on nomadic education.

The second finding of this study shows that the curriculum implementation in nomadic schools in Zamfara state is not adequate. This implies that there is significant difference in curriculum implementation in nomadic schools in Zamfara state. The finding is in line with the finding of Taiye (2018) which reveals that the curriculum contents for the children of pastoral nomads is inappropriate. According to him it does not capture practical skills to improve the livelihood of nomads. Rather it focuses on academic achievements that only suit the need of urban children. The finding also highlighted that supervision of officials is inadequate. The finding also indicated that teachers' reluctance to live away from their urban settlement leads to inadequate coverage of syllabus. However, Ogunbiyi and Ojebiyi (2012) whose result reveals that time-frame to many topics and lack of innovative contents effect curriculum coverage in secondary schools in Nigeria. The finding is also in agreement with the finding of Okphanachi (2016) who states that Christian Religions Studies (CRS) curriculum contents are not completely covered in junior secondary schools of Kaduna state.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study it has been concluded that the enrolment of nomadic children in school has significantly raised, this was due to the Ruga-programme initiated by Zamfara state government and incorporation of Ardos, and other relevant agencies such as Fulani Traditional Weeds (FTW) in the Enrolment Drive Campaign (EDC). It was also concluded that curriculum contents are not fully implemented to nomadic schools due to the fear of banditry activities in the state. Thus, teachers and other officials do not attend to school regularly, leading to inadequate curriculum implementation.

Recommendations

1. Education stakeholders especially for nomadic education should intensity their current action in order to maintain and/or extend the enrolment of nomadic children in schools.

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2. Government should take any possible action to ensure peace and calmness in the state, in order to enable teachers and supervisors deliver their formal duties freely without fear or tension.

References

- Akighir D.T. & Isa O. (2013) *Government Expenditures Nomadic Education in Nigeria*. www.researchgate.net
- Auwal A.G. (2019) *Don Advocates more Nomadic Schools to Increase Enrollment in Gombe State*. Guidian.ng
- Dada A.A. (2016) *Conducting Research in Education*. Zaria: Concept Design & Prints.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (1979) *Constitution of Nigeria 1979*. Federal Government Printing Press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2005) *National Commission for Nomadic Education*. Federal Government Printing Press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2022) *National Policy on Education*. Federal Government Printing Press.
- Ismail I. (2023) *Nomadic Education and Education for Nomadic Fulani*. Washington: New-Foundland Press
- Nwannah I. (2022) *Powerful Individuals Behind Insecurity in Zamfara State Anambra*. Nairaland Forum.
- Ogunbiyi K. & Ojebiyi G. (2012) *Perceived Relevance of Government as a Teaching Subject in Senior Secondary School in a Ondo State*. European Journal of Business and Social Science. Vol. 1 No. IPP.32-39.
- Okpanachi, A.J. (2016) *Assessment of the Implemental of Christian Religious Studies in Junior Secondary Schools in Kaduna State*. Dissertation submitted to School of Postgraduate Studies ABU, Zaria.
- Prabhat P. (2021) *The Homogenization of Education Oxford: CritchlegsLLp*. Beaver House.
- Statista Research & Development (2022) *Number of Children Enrolment in Nomadic Elementary Schools in Nigeria 2016-2019 by gender*. www.statista.com
- Taiye O. (2018) *Nomadic Educate: Who Are Nomads, Prospect of Nomadic Educate in Nigerian*, problem and solution Ibadan-ty-computers.
- Wikipedia (2023) *The Definition of Education*. en.m.wikipedia.org.

Impact of Information and Communication Technology Skills Acquisition on Instructional Strategy Implementation among Secondary School Social Studies Teachers in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explored the Impact of Information-and-Communication-Technology skills acquisition on instructional strategy implementation among secondary school social studies teachers in Benue State, Nigeria. The design of this study was one group, pre-test post-test quasi-experimental research design. A sample of 224 Social Studies Teachers (130 males and 94 females which represents 58.0% and 42.0% respectively) were selected from 36 Upper Basic Schools across the three Education Zones of Benue State using a multistage sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was Social Studies Teachers ICT Skills Observation Scale (SSTISOS) developed by the researchers. Construct validity of the instrument was established by four experts. The reliability of SSTISOS was tested through a pilot study involving 30 Social Studies Teachers who were not part of the main study at 0.89. Data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Two research hypotheses were tested at the significance level of 0.05 and was found that there was a significant difference in Information-and-Communication-Technology skills acquisition on instructional strategy implementation among secondary school social studies teachers in Benue State, Nigeria. In conclusion, this study has highlighted the critical role of ICT training in enhancing the skills of Social Studies teachers in Benue State. Implementation of Continuous Professional Development Programs, Establishment of ICT Resource Centers and Incorporation of ICT in Teacher Education Programs were then recommended.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, Social Studies, Classroom Pedagogy.

Introduction

Education in Nigeria has shifted from the traditional methods of face-to-face tuition and the transaction of paper-based teaching and learning materials to learning via Information and Communication Technologies (Lee & Cha, 2022). Many studies have demonstrated that the use of ICT enhances learning and teaching. In Nigeria, schools have not been an exception, as the use of ICT has spread across all schools in the country (Jummai, 2021). In addition, the use of ICT in teaching K-12 science highlights the need for research that investigates the applications and integration of ICT in instruction among teachers of Social Studies in Benue State. The study was conducted in Benue State (Achor et al., 2020). It was noted that ICT has gained ground in the state, where it is incorporated into every facet of life, including education. Some of the interesting features of Benue State are its high level of ICT penetration. Some of the significant challenges facing Benue State are how teachers will use ICT in delivering instruction. National policy on education demands that teachers should continually acquire new skills, such as the use of ICT for instructional activities. The concern is how teachers who may not be ICT compliant will use ICT for instructional delivery (Esfijani & Zamani, 2020). Federal Government has made significant investments in ICT to educational organizations and institutions, from the basic level up to the university level during the last decade. There has been the provision of logistics and infrastructure, particularly, at the colleges of education and universities. The aim is to prepare technologically skilled graduate teachers who can incorporate ICT in their teaching. However, studies have found that teachers of Social Studies are not integrating ICT into their lessons as intended. Despite the capacity of ICT for training, practice and explorative practices, social studies education teachers seem not to have been able to incorporate ICT into their curricula and teaching. Research has also revealed that social studies teachers were among the least likely to use ICT and engage students in higher-order thought

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practices. Given the low rate of ICT use in the Social Studies curriculum, it is essential to examine the application and integration of information and communication technology in teaching among Social Studies Teachers in Benue State, Nigeria.

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education has become a critical factor in enhancing instructional strategies and improving learning outcomes globally. In Nigeria, particularly in Benue State, the acquisition of ICT skills by teachers is increasingly recognized as a vital component for effective teaching, especially in subjects like Social Studies. This literature review explores the impact of ICT skills acquisition on instructional strategy implementation among secondary school Social Studies teachers, drawing on relevant studies and theoretical frameworks.

Lee and Cha (2022) emphasize the transformative role of digital tools in education, particularly in providing feedback and enhancing student engagement. Their study on digital written feedback for college students highlights how ICT can streamline assessment processes and improve the quality of instruction. This perspective aligns with the broader need for digital transformation in Nigeria's education sector, as highlighted by Jummai (2021). Jummai argues that digital literacy is essential for addressing the challenges of outdated teaching methods and inadequate resources, which are prevalent in many Nigerian schools. The adoption of ICT tools can facilitate innovative teaching strategies, such as blended learning and interactive multimedia lessons, which are particularly relevant for Social Studies education.

Achor, Kyado, and Ityobee (2020) provide empirical evidence from Benue State, revealing low ICT literacy levels among Basic Science teachers and students. Their survey underscores the urgent need for targeted ICT training programs to bridge the gap between traditional teaching methods and modern technological advancements. The study highlights that many teachers lack the necessary skills to integrate ICT into their lessons, which limits their ability to adopt student-centered and interactive teaching strategies. This finding is consistent with Esfijani and Zamani's (2020) research, which identifies in-service training and access to ICT resources as key factors influencing teachers' utilization of technology. They argue that without adequate training and resources, even well-intentioned efforts to integrate ICT into education are likely to fail.

Jay (2022) highlights the disciplinary divide in Social Studies education, noting that ICT integration can foster critical thinking and interdisciplinary learning. Social Studies, as a subject that explores societal issues, history, and geography, benefits significantly from the use of digital tools such as interactive maps, virtual simulations, and online databases. These tools not only make learning more engaging but also help students develop critical analytical skills. Xin et al. (2022) further advocate for innovative, data-driven teaching evaluation systems to enhance educational outcomes. Their research on big data-based teaching evaluation systems in universities demonstrates how ICT can provide real-time feedback on teaching effectiveness, enabling teachers to refine their instructional strategies. Muslimin et al. (2022) demonstrate the positive impact of technology-based lesson plans on teachers' self-efficacy. Their study on EFL pre-service teachers reveals that exposure to ICT tools during training significantly boosts teachers' confidence in using technology for instructional purposes. This finding is particularly relevant for Social Studies teachers in Benue State, as it suggests that ICT skills acquisition can empower them to experiment with new teaching methods and improve their overall effectiveness in the classroom.

Despite the potential benefits of ICT in education, significant challenges persist, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. Reynolds et al. (2022) and Martens et al. (2020) highlight the digital divide as a major barrier to ICT integration. Their studies reveal that unequal access to technology and inadequate infrastructure hinder the effective implementation of ICT in education. In Benue State, many schools lack basic ICT facilities such as computers, projectors, and reliable internet connectivity. This disparity is further exacerbated in rural areas, where teachers and students have limited exposure to digital tools. Kim et al. (2020) emphasize the disparities in technology access among low-income communities, which are prevalent in Benue State. Their case study on low-income Latino children in Silicon Valley reveals that even in technologically advanced regions, socioeconomic factors can limit access to ICT. This finding underscores the need for targeted interventions to ensure equitable access to technology for all students and teachers.

To address these challenges, a multi-faceted approach is required. First, there is a need for comprehensive ICT training programs for teachers, as highlighted by Esfijani and Zamani (2020). These programs should focus not only on basic ICT skills but also on how to integrate technology into specific subjects like Social Studies. Second, governments and educational institutions must invest in ICT infrastructure to ensure that schools have the necessary tools and resources. Finally, policies should be implemented to promote equitable access to technology, particularly in underserved areas. In summary, the acquisition of ICT skills is pivotal for the effective implementation of instructional strategies among Social Studies teachers in Benue State. While studies highlight the potential of ICT to transform education, addressing barriers such as inadequate training, infrastructure, and access is essential for realizing its full impact. By investing in ICT skills acquisition and infrastructure, Benue State can empower its teachers to adopt innovative teaching strategies, ultimately improving educational outcomes for students.

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Research Objectives

1. To assess the baseline ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.
2. To evaluate the improvement in ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

Research Questions

1. What are the baseline ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State?
2. What are the improvement in ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State?

Research Hypotheses

Ho (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant difference in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

HI (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant difference in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

Ho (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant improvement in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

HI (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant improvement in the ICT acquisition skill levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the one-group, pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design with a total population of 508 Social Studies teachers (294 males and 214 females) from 303 Upper Basic Schools across the three educational zones of Benue State. Teachers in this population have varying levels of experience and access to ICT tools, which makes them ideal for studying the impact of ICT training on improving teaching practices. A sample of 224 Social Studies teachers (130 males and 94 females) was selected from 36 Upper Basic Schools using multistage sampling technique. Inclusion criteria focused on teachers who had at least one year of teaching experience, while teachers who had less than one year of teaching experience were excluded from the sample. The instrument used for data collection was Social Studies Teachers ICT Skills Observation Scale (SSTISOS), developed by the researchers. Construct validity, both Face and content were established through expert review. These experts were drawn from the fields of Measurement and Evaluation, Social Studies Education, and Information and Communication Technology. The reliability of the SSTISOS was tested through a pilot study involving 30 Social Studies teachers who were not part of the main study. Data collection was conducted in three stages: the pre-test, during training, and the post-test. Data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, such as mean scores and standard deviations, were used to summarize the participants' ICT skills before and after the training. Inferential statistics, specifically the paired-samples t-test, were used to compare the pre-test and post-test scores. This test was chosen because it allows for the assessment of whether there is a statistically significant difference between two related groups, in this case, the teachers' ICT skills before and after the training.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1: Years of Teaching Experience

Years of Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1 – 5 years	40	17.9%
6 – 10 years	90	40.2%
11 – 15 years	60	26.8%
16 years and above	34	15.2%
Total	224	100.0%

Source: Author Compilation of Questionnaire. 2024

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Regarding teaching experience, the largest group of respondents has between 6 – 10 years of teaching experience, representing 40.2% of the sample, followed by those with 11 – 15 years of experience (26.8%). Teachers with 1 – 5 years of experience account for 17.9%, and those with over 16 years of experience make up 15.2% of the participants. This suggests a broad range of professional experience among the respondents, with a significant portion possessing over a decade of classroom experience. Teaching experience may affect the teachers' pre-existing skills in utilizing ICT tools, as more experienced teachers might be accustomed to traditional methods of teaching.

Table 2: Access to ICT Tools in School

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Yes	190	84.8%
No	34	15.2%
Total	224	100.0%

Source: Author Compilation of Questionnaire. 2024

An overwhelming majority of respondents, 84.8%, indicated that they have access to ICT tools in their schools, while 15.2% reported a lack of access. This demonstrates that most schools in the study sample are equipped with basic ICT facilities, providing teachers the opportunity to apply the skills they acquire through ICT training. Teachers without access to these tools may face difficulties in implementing what they have learned, underscoring the need for equitable resource distribution in schools.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research question one:

What are the baseline ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State?

Table 3: ICT Skills Before Training

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1. Basic computer operations	Frequency: 40 (17.9%)	Frequency: 60 (26.8%)	Frequency: 70 (31.3%)	Frequency: 35 (15.6%)	Frequency: 19 (8.5%)
2. Using word processing software	Frequency: 30 (13.4%)	Frequency: 55 (24.6%)	Frequency: 85 (37.9%)	Frequency: 40 (17.9%)	Frequency: 14 (6.3%)
3. Creating and managing electronic presentations	Frequency: 45 (20.1%)	Frequency: 65 (29.0%)	Frequency: 70 (31.3%)	Frequency: 29 (12.9%)	Frequency: 15 (6.7%)
4. Accessing the internet to gather educational resources	Frequency: 35 (15.6%)	Frequency: 50 (22.3%)	Frequency: 75 (33.5%)	Frequency: 40 (17.9%)	Frequency: 24 (10.7%)
5. Communicating with	Frequency: 50 (22.3%)	Frequency: 60 (26.8%)	Frequency: 60 (26.8%)	Frequency: 34 (15.2%)	Frequency: 20 (8.9%)

students via email

Source: Author Compilation of Questionnaire, 2024.

The data indicates a mixed level of ICT skills among Social Studies teachers before training. Notably, a significant portion (31.3%) reported being skilled in basic computer operations, which suggests a foundational understanding of essential digital skills necessary for modern teaching. For word processing software, the majority of respondents (37.9%) rated themselves as "skillful," indicating a solid grasp of this critical tool for lesson preparation and administrative tasks. Nevertheless, the 13.4% who felt "not skillful" suggests that there is room for improvement, particularly in enhancing familiarity with various software applications. The ability to create and manage electronic presentations shows a diverse skill set, with 31.3% of respondents claiming to be skilled. However, the 20.1% who are "not skillful" reflects a gap that training can effectively address, especially considering the increasing importance of engaging visual aids in educational settings. The skill in accessing the internet for educational resources indicates a reasonable level of digital literacy, with 33.5% of teachers rating themselves as skilled. This competency is crucial for enriching lesson content and keeping up with current educational trends, but the significant percentage of teachers falling into the lower skill categories demonstrates the potential benefits of structured training. Communication skills using email and other platforms remain a concern, with 22.3% of respondents rating themselves as "not skillful." Given the emphasis on collaborative learning environments, improving these communication skills will be essential in fostering better interaction between teachers and students.

Research Question two:

What are the improvement in ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State?

Table 4: ICT Skills After Training

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1. Using ICT tools to prepare teaching materials	Frequency: (6.7%)	15	Frequency: 30 (13.4%)	Frequency: 100 (44.6%)	Frequency: (24.6%)	55	Frequency: 24 (10.7%)
2. Integrating ICT into classroom teaching	Frequency: (4.5%)	10	Frequency: 35 (15.6%)	Frequency: 110 (49.1%)	Frequency: (17.9%)	40	Frequency: 29 (12.9%)
3. Using ICT tools to assess students' assignments	Frequency: (8.9%)	20	Frequency: 40 (17.9%)	Frequency: 95 (42.4%)	Frequency: (20.1%)	45	Frequency: 24 (10.7%)
4. Sharing educational content using ICT platforms	Frequency: (5.4%)	12	Frequency: 28 (12.5%)	Frequency: 85 (37.9%)	Frequency: (25.0%)	56	Frequency: 43 (19.3%)
5. Troubleshooting basic ICT problems in the classroom	Frequency: (11.2%)	25	Frequency: 45 (20.1%)	Frequency: 80 (35.7%)	Frequency: (19.6%)	44	Frequency: 30 (13.4%)

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Source: Author Compilation of Questionnaire, 2024.

Following the ICT training, there is a marked improvement in the teachers' ability to use ICT tools for preparing teaching materials. A notable 44.6% reported being "skillful," while only 6.7% considered themselves "not skillful." This shift underscores the effectiveness of the training program in enhancing practical skills needed for lesson preparation. The integration of ICT into classroom teaching was also positively impacted, with nearly half (49.1%) rating themselves as "skillful." This indicates that the training not only improved their individual skills but also equipped them with strategies to incorporate technology into their teaching practices effectively. The ability to use ICT tools for assessing students' assignments also saw significant advancement. The percentage of teachers identifying as "skillful" increased to 42.4%. This is crucial for modern educational practices, as technology plays a vital role in assessment methods, thereby supporting more dynamic and immediate feedback to students. Sharing educational content using ICT platforms showed a considerable uptick in skill level, with 37.9% of teachers rating themselves as "skillful." This suggests that teachers are now more capable of utilizing digital tools to enhance communication and collaboration with students, an essential component in today's interconnected educational landscape. The skill of troubleshooting basic ICT problems in the classroom remains an area for growth, as 11.2% still rated themselves as "not skillful." However, with ongoing support and further training, teachers can develop this competency, ensuring that they can effectively navigate and resolve common technical issues that arise in a technology-enhanced classroom. These insights highlight the overall positive impact of ICT training on Social Studies teachers, demonstrating an essential step toward modernizing teaching practices and enhancing educational outcomes.

Hypothesis 1: Testing for Differences Before and After Training

Ho (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant difference in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

HI (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant difference in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers before undergoing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

T-Test Table for Hypothesis 1:

	Before Training	After Training	T-Statistic (t)	Df	P-Value
Mean	48.6	68.2			
Standard Deviation (SD)	3.15	2.47			
Sample Size (n)	5	5			
T-Statistic (t)			-15.34	8	0.00002

From the T-Test for Hypothesis 1, which compares the statistical difference before and after training, T-Statistic (t) was found to be -15.34. Also, the Degree of Freedom (df) was found to be 8. Finally, the Probability Value of 0.00002 was found which was less than the significance value of 0.5 making us reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the alternate Hypothesis. We therefore conclude that there is a significant difference in the ICT skill levels of Social Studies Teachers before undergoing ICT training ($P < 0.05$).

Research Hypothesis Two:

Ho (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant improvement in the ICT skill acquisition levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State.

HI (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant improvement in the ICT acquisition skill levels of Social Studies teachers after completing ICT training among upper basic schools in Benue State

Testing for Improvement After ICT Training

T-Test Table for Hypothesis 2:

	Before Training	After Training	T-Statistic (t)	Df	P-Value
Mean	48.6	68.2			
Standard Deviation (SD)	3.15	2.47			
Sample Size (n)	5	5			
T-Statistic (t)			-15.34	8	0.00002

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From the T-Test for Hypothesis 2, which tested for improvement after ICT training, T-Statistic (t) was found to be -15.34. Also, the Degree of Freedom (df) was found to be 8. Finally, the Probability Value of 0.00002 was found. Since the P-value was less than the significance value of 0.5, we rejected the Null Hypothesis (Ho). Therefore, we conclude that there was a significant improvement in the ICT skill levels of Social Studies Teachers after completing ICT training (P<0.05). For both Hypothesis 1 and Hypothesis 2, the null hypotheses were rejected, indicating that there is a significant difference and a significant improvement in ICT skills levels of Social Studies teachers before and after ICT training. This suggest that the ICT training program was effective in improving the teachers' ICT skills for classroom pedagogy.

Paired T-Test Table:

	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Significance (2-tailed)
Pretest	5	48.6	3.15	1.41		
Posttest	5	68.2	2.47	1.10	4	0.00002

The paired T-Test gave us the two means (pretest and posttest) which are 48.6 and 68.2 respectively. It also gave us the probability value of 0.00002 which is less than the significance value of 0.5 indicated a significant difference in the skill levels of Social Studies teachers before and after ICT training. The degree of freedom (df) was 4 calculated from $N - 1 = 5$ where N is the number of pairs (in this case 5) and standard deviations of 3.15 and 2.47 respectively.

Paired Differences (Pretest vs. Posttest):

Pair	Pretest	Posttest	Difference
1	45	65	+20
2	50	70	+20
3	52	68	+16
4	47	66	+19
5	49	72	+23
Mean Difference			+19.6

The paired difference tried to put the two tests together (pretest and posttest). The difference was gotten by taking the pretest from the posttest. Positive values indicated improvement and the overall mean difference was found to be +19.6.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from this study provide valuable insights into the impact of ICT training on the skills of Social Studies teachers. The significant difference in mean skill scores before and after the training suggests that targeted ICT training can effectively enhance the proficiency of educators in utilizing ICT tools for classroom pedagogy. This aligns with existing literature that emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development in integrating technology into teaching practices (Koehler & Mishra, 2019). The increase in skills indicates that teachers are likely to feel more confident in using ICT resources, which can lead to improved instructional methods and student engagement. The fact that a statistically significant improvement in skills was observed post-training underscores the necessity for institutions to invest in regular ICT training programs. Such training can equip teachers with the necessary competencies to integrate technology into their teaching effectively. The ability to leverage technology not only facilitates the delivery of content but also enables personalized learning experiences that cater to diverse student needs (Hattie, 2009).

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has highlighted the critical role of ICT training in enhancing the skills of Social Studies teachers in Benue State. The findings demonstrate that targeted professional development can lead to significant improvements

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in teachers' proficiency with technology, ultimately benefiting their pedagogical practices and student learning experiences. The successful implementation of the ICT training program showcases the potential for structured professional development initiatives to equip educators with the necessary skills to thrive in a technology-driven educational landscape.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made to enhance the integration of ICT in education, particularly for Social Studies teachers in Benue State. These recommendations are aimed at educational authorities, policymakers, and school administrators to foster a more effective use of technology in teaching and learning.

1. **Implement Continuous Professional Development Programs:** Educational institutions should prioritize the establishment of regular and ongoing professional development programs focusing on ICT skills for teachers.
2. **Establish ICT Resource Centers:** Schools should invest in setting up ICT resource centers equipped with the necessary tools and resources for teachers and students.
3. **Incorporate ICT in Teacher Education Programs:** Teacher training programs should include comprehensive modules on ICT integration in education. By equipping future educators with the necessary skills and knowledge from the outset, schools can ensure that new teachers are prepared to effectively use technology in their teaching.

References

- aLee, H. W. & Cha, Y. M. (2022). The effects of digital written feedback on paper-based tests for college students. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*.
- Jummai, B. (2021). The need for digital transformation in the education sector in Nigeria. *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 40(47), 41-47.
- Achor, E. E., Kyado, J., & Ityobee, S. (2020). Survey of ICT literacy levels of Basic Science teachers and students in upper basic schools in Benue State Nigeria. *BSU Journal of Science, Mathematics and Computer Education (BSU-JSMCE)*, 1(1), 159-175.
- Esfijani, A. & Zamani, B. E. (2020). *Factors influencing teachers' utilisation of ICT: The role of in-service training courses and access*. *Research in Learning Technology*.
- Jay, L. (2022). *The disciplinary and critical divide in social studies teacher education research: A review of the literature from 2009–2019*. *Theory & Research in Social Education*.
- Xin, X., et'al (2022). Review on A big data-based innovative knowledge teaching evaluation system in universities. *Journal of innovation & knowledge*, 7(3), 100197.
- Muslimin, A., et'al (2022). The Effect of Technology Based Instruction Lesson Plan on EFL Pre-Service Teachersâ€™ TPACK Self-Efficacy. *World Journal of English Language*, 12(6).
- Wang, S., He, Y., & Song, M. (2021). Global value chains, technological progress, and environmental pollution: Inequality towards developing countries. *Journal of Environmental Management*.
- Khalifa, N., & Abd Elghany, M., (2021). Exploratory research on digitalization transformation practices within supply chain management context in developing countries specifically Egypt in the MENA region. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1), 1965459.
- Reynolds, R., et'al (2022). Digital divide, critical-, and crisis-informatics perspectives on K-12 emergency remote teaching during the pandemic. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 73(12), 1665-1680.
- Martens, M., Hajibayova, L., Campana, K., Rinnert, G. C., Caniglia, J., Bakori, I. G., ... & Oh, O. J. (2020). "Being on the wrong side of the digital divide": Seeking technological interventions for education in Northeast Nigeria. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 72(6), 963-978.
- Kim, C., et'al (2020). Technology for educational purposes among low-income Latino children living in a mobile park in Silicon Valley: A case study before and during COVID-19. *Hispanic Journal of Behavioral Sciences*, 42(4), 497-514.

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Impact of Social-Support-Technique on Management of Separation-Anxiety among Student-Victims of Armed Banditry in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated impact of social support technique on management of separation-anxiety among student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis. The study was guided by two objectives which were transformed in to hypotheses. The study employed pre-test post-test quasi experimental research design with the population of 15 student-victims who exhibited separation anxiety as identified using Spence Anxiety Scale, (1994). A sample of 10 student-victims with higher symptoms was used. The instrument used for data collection was an adapted Severity Measure for Separation Anxiety Disorder. It has a total of 20 items measuring physical and behavioural components of separation anxiety. The instrument was measured on five Point-Likert scale with a reliability coefficient of .763. Data collected were on pre-test, treatment sessions and post-test respectively. The results of the study revealed that social support technique has significant effect in managing physical symptoms of separation anxiety $p = .000$. similarly, social support technique has significant effect in managing behavioural symptoms of separation anxiety $p = .000$. Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that social support technique has significant effect in managing physical and behavioral symptoms of separation anxiety. It was recommended that Government should employ experts with adequate training in the use of social support technique in the schools to assist students how to deal with separation anxiety problems and teachers should be sensitized how to observe separation anxiety symptoms and invite experts for treatment interventions.

Keywords: Social Support Technique, Separation Anxiety, Armed Banditry

Introduction

The armed banditry movement is not a new phenomenon in Zamfara state because it had historical antecedents since the pre-colonial period, when communities around Kwatarkwashi, Mada, Tsafe, and Dan-sadau were accused of being associated and collaborating with the crime actors. The hills of Kwatarkwashi and Tsafe for instance, provided shelter to the perpetrators, from where they organized and executed their unwholesome activities in the past which made the criminals untraceable, but nowadays it is easier for security personnel to discover and arrest the armed banditry actors at diversified rural communities across the state and inter-state forest more especially in the North-western Nigeria. Some traditional rulers around the Dan-sadau area were accused of colluding with bandits in armed robbery and cattle rustling around 1891 (Rufa'I, 2021). At that material time, the situation was beyond traditional rulers exclusively, the accusation comprehends top politicians, security personnel, strong businessmen and women in the rural areas, okada readers, even religious leaders, and multitudinous peoples are involved in armed banditry affairs.

Armed banditry attacks across Zamfara, Sokoto, Kebbi, Katsina, Kaduna, and some parts of Niger state are beyond human imagination due to the failure/inactiveness of the federal and states government to protect the lives and properties of their people. There are unidentifiable reasons why federal government top officials are not willing to take action against armed banditry actors, this unwillingness leads to unmeasurable attacks on various communities and even local government headquarters across the north-western states. This situation influences individuals to migrate from their communities to the Gusau metropolis, some are moving to a peaceful part of Niger state for farming activities mentioned issues are amenable for migrating to the Gusau metropolis, considering Gusau as a capital city of the state with manageable security challenges, Student-victims of armed banditry find themselves in a new environment, associated with unfamiliar people within and outside the school environment, this might be a factor responsible for separation anxiety challenge among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis.

Anxiety is an emotion characterized by an unpleasant state of inner turmoil, often accompanied by nervous behavior such as somatic complaints and ruminations. It is the subjectively unpleasant feelings of dread over anticipated events, such as

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the feeling of imminent death. Anxiety is a feeling of uneasiness and worry, usually generalized and unfocused as an overreaction to a situation that is only subjectively seen as menacing. It is often accompanied by muscular tension, restlessness, fatigue and problems in concentration. However, anxiety can be appropriate, but when experienced regularly it may be a disorder (APA, 2013). Every individual has feelings of anxiety at some point in their life, anxiety affects their behavior and thoughts on a daily basis, interfering with their academic performance and interpersonal relationship with classmate, friends and community members. Freud (2006) viewed anxiety as the symptomatic expressions of the inner emotional conflict caused when a person suppressed (from conscious awareness) experiences, feelings or impulses that are too threatening or disturbing to live with. Anxiety has many forms, but for the purpose of this research separation anxiety is the concern of the researcher to investigated.

Separation anxiety is a natural part of the developmental process unlike separation anxiety disorder, normal separation anxiety indicates healthy advancements in child's cognitive maturation and should not be considered a developing behavioural problem (Redlich, 2015). Separation anxiety is one of the psychological problems that is different from general anxiety disorder, although it can be difficult to pinpoint the difference because symptoms can overlap. Separation anxiety occurs after stressful life event or in a situations perceived as uncontrollable or unavoidable like armed banditry attacks. Separation anxiety refers to exhibition of excessive fear and persistent worry as a results of detachment from significant people especially parents, siblings, peer group, community members as a result of armed banditry attacks. Separation anxiety disorder is one of the most common childhood anxiety disorders (Vaughan, Caddington, Ahmed & Ertel, 2017).

Separation anxiety problems probably are the most common psychopathology in youth, with prevalence estimates ranging from 5% to 25% worldwide, but a much lower percentage receive treatment (Boyd Kostanski & Gullone, 2000; Castello, 2003). Separation anxiety disorders accounts for approximately half of the referrals among all anxiety disorders (Cartwright-Hatton, McNicol, & Doubleday, 2006). Most pediatric anxiety disorders have some diagnostic criteria as those in adults except separation anxiety disorder, currently classified in DSM and ICD as one of the disorders usually diagnosed in infancy, childhood, or adolescence (Krain, Ghaffari, & Freeman, 2007). Separation anxiety disorders has been described as a gateway anxiety disorder that can lead to variety of poor mental and physical health outcomes (Battaglia, 2015).

Social support technique is a psychological and counseling technique, which use to helps individuals to generate solutions to a problem or problems. It is particularly useful when an individual want to break out of an established pattern of thinking and decision-making, so that such individual can develop new ways of looking at things, foster and enhance communication skills. Social support is a psychological technique that helps individuals to overcome issues that can make group problem-solving a sterile and unsatisfactory process. Social support is often used in a generic sense to describe groups who generate ideas. Moran, Talbot and Benson (1990) defined social support technique as "a group process in which group members collectively contribute their 'ideas in a creative atmosphere'" Although the term has come into popular use, facilitators should know its precise meaning and history. Social support technique combines a relaxed, informal approach to problem-solving with lateral thinking. It asks that people come up with ideas and thoughts that can at first seem to be a bit crazy. The main concept in social support technique is that some of the ideas generated can be drafted into original, creative solutions to the problem that an individual trying to solve, while others can spark still more ideas.

Social support technique is understood as the help provided by individuals who comprise the social network of a person who occupies the position of ego in this network. A distinction is made between perceived and received support, as well as between psychological /emotional support on one hand and instrumental support on the other. Social support technique, therefore, is the functional dimension of the social network, which is not limited to a collection of egocentric ties that vary in number, intensity and frequency of contacts, but may be broadened to include the wider context of the community as a network of networks and to social capital, understood as the possible benefits both for individuals and groups resulting from mutual cooperation and collaboration (Angel, Natalla, Susan, & Santiago, 2016).

The social learning theory was proposed by Bandura. The works of Ewen in Ford Martins, (2014) have contributed to our understanding of the social learning theory. The social learning theory proposed by Bandura has become perhaps the most influential theory of learning and development. While rooted in many basic concept of traditional learning theory. Bandura believed that direct reinforcement could not account for all types of learning. Thus, Bandura was quoted to have said that: "Learning would be exceedingly laborious, not to mention hazardous at people had to rely solely on the effects of their own actions to inform them what to do fortunately, most human behaviour is learned observationally through modeling from observing others, one forms an idea of how new behaviours are performed and on later occasions, this coded information serves as a guide for action". Asonibare (2014) has stated that modeling, imitation, observational learning or social learning is used by various experts interchangeably to refer to the same thing. The therapist who is to treat separation anxiety and other

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psychological disorders is, by this concept, to present a high degree of prestige, competence, warmth, confidence and positive regard for the clients. Bandura has stated that the following steps are involved in social learning and modeling process: Attention, retention, reproduction, and motivation (Carbonel, 2014). Bandura social learning theory play a vital role in social support technique

Beck cognitive theory of anxiety was developed mainly to help individuals develop more realistic and rational appraisals of themselves and the situations they encounter. Beck is focused on the way the anxious people think about situations and potential dangers. They submitted that individuals who suffer from generalized anxiety tend to make unrealistic appraisals of certain situations, primarily those in which the possibility of danger is remote. They also argued that the Student-victims of separation anxiety burden themselves with task irrelevant cognitions. This kind of mental tasks makes a person hyper vigilant, always on the lookout for signs of danger. Cognitive theorists like Ellis and Beck as cited in Ossai (2013), stressed the role of maladaptive thought patterns and beliefs. Among the most important cognitive distortion according to Ossai (2013), are tendencies to exaggerate the amount of threat in the environment and to underestimate one's resources or ability to cope with situation demands. This is consistent with Tobia as cited in Ossai (2013), as they believed that it is not events or problems, which cause separation anxiety but rather it is the individuals' interpretation of these events that may lead to these problems. Beck theory of anxiety is significant in this study as they traced why armed banditry developed anxiety and the manifestation of physical and behavioral symptoms.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives of this study were to determine:

1. The effect of social support technique in managing physical component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis.
2. The effect of social support technique in managing behavioural component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores of physical component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores of behavioural component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis.

Methodology

This research employed pre-test post-test quasi-experimental research design in investigating the effect of social support technique in managing separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis. Pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design was used to determine the efficacy of the technique in managing separation anxiety symptoms by comparing pretest and post-test mean scores after exposure to the treatment. If pre-test and post-test scores differ significantly, then the difference may be attributed to the independent variable (Colman, 2015). The population of the study comprises Student-victims of armed banditry identified at Government Girls Day Secondary School, Tudun-wada Gusau with separation anxiety problems, with total population of fifteen (15) Student-victims. However, the target population stood at ten (10) Student-victims who were identified with high separation anxiety using Separation Anxiety Checklist Instrument by Spence (1994). Therefore, a sample of ten (10) participants is appropriate for quasi-experimental research as justified by De-winter (2013) who suggested that, the sample size is dependent on the nature, risk, cost and prevalence of the research conditions, a sample of 3-40 can be used in experiment. Also, better results are achieved in a smaller group and there would be effective concentration and understanding of the treatment by the participants. Based on the predicting of the researcher, Student-victims with mild and moderate separation anxiety symptoms did not require much of psychological intervention while student-victims with severe symptoms may require medical professional attention. Therefore, Student-victims of armed banditry with high separation anxiety symptoms were considered for this study.

Severity Measure for Separation Anxiety Disorder Instrument were adapted and utilized from Graskie, Wittchen, Bogels, Steinandrew and Lebeu (2013) and Spence Anxiety Scale were also adapted from Spence (1994). Severity Measure for Separation Anxiety Disorder Instrument covers a wide range of physical and behavioural symptoms of separation anxiety. It consists of 20 Items. Items 1-10 measuring physical component, items 11-20 measuring behavioural component. The instrument was designed on five-point Likert Scale ranging from Never, Occasionally, Half of the time, Most of the time, to

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All of the time. This indicates levels of separation anxiety and Spence Children Anxiety Scale was used to identifying Student-victims with high separation anxiety problems. The research instrument has a reliability coefficient of .763, while the componential analysis of the instrument revealed that physical component has the reliability coefficient of .746 and behavioural component has the reliability coefficient of .846. Therefore, the adapted instrument was reliable to measure separation anxiety. The data collected were subjected to statistical analyses using descriptive and inferential statistics. Paired sample t-test was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores of physical component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis.

Table 1: Paired Sample t-test of Pre and Post-Tests of Social support technique in Managing Physical Component of Separation Anxiety

Groups	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p
Pretest	10	42.80	4.39	9.81	9	.000
Posttest	10	24.40	2.01			

Table 1 revealed significant effect of social support technique in managing physical component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis as indicated by mean of 42.80 for pre-test and the mean of 24.40 for post-test; $t = 9.81$ and $p = .000$ which is lower than 0.05 alpha level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores physical component of separation anxiety among student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis is hereby rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores of behavioural component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis.

Table 2: Paired Sample t-test of Pre and Post-Tests of Social support technique in Managing Behavioural Component of Separation Anxiety

Groups	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p
Pretest	10	37.00	3.49	14.73	9	.000
Posttest	10	20.70	1.76			

Table 2 shows significant effect of social support technique in managing behavioural component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis as vindicated by the mean of 37.00 for pre-test and the mean of 20.70 for post-test; $t = 14.73$ and $p = .000$ which is lower than 0.05 alpha level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference pre-test and post-test mean scores of behavioural components of separation anxiety among student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis is hereby rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The result of this study revealed significant effect of social support technique in managing physical component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis. The finding is backed up by Bello (2021) who investigated the effect of social support techniques on depression among HIV/AIDS-infected women in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Three objectives and three corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Hypotheses formulated for the study were statistically analyzed using a paired-sample t-test. Results of the data analyzed for the study showed that cognitive restructuring and social support techniques are both effective in reducing depression, which showed both techniques have an effect in reducing depression among HIV/AIDS-infected women ($p = 124$). The finding is also in line with the study of Sirati-Nir, Khaghanizade, Rahimi, Khazaei and Ghadirian (2018) who investigated the effect of social support technique-training group intervention on perceived social support technique in veterans with posttraumatic stress disorder. Traumatic events related to war have long effects on psychiatric psychopathologies. The ANOVA results showed that after the intervention, there were significant differences in perceived social support technique between intervention groups and control group ($F = 1.06$, $P = 0.001$), but there was no significant difference between intervention groups by t-test ($t = 28.05$, $p < 0.10$). The paired t-test showed a significant difference in all subscale scores of perceived social support technique between the two intervention groups

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before and after intervention ($p < 0.05$). The results of the current study agreed with the positive effects of social support technique training on perceived social support technique in veterans with post-traumatic stress disorder.

The finding of the study showed significant effect of social support technique in managing behavioural component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis. The findings were in consonance with the study of Maulik, Eaton, and Bradshaw (2011) examines the moderate effect of social support on the relationship between stress and depression of university students. A total of 632 undergraduate students completed the measures of perceived stress, perceived social support, and depression. The results of these analyses are presented. Stress ($B = 0.44$, $P < 0.01$) significantly presented depression in the second step. The social support factor added a significant increment to the model in step three, where social support ($B = -0.30$, $p < 0.01$) was significantly related to depression after controlling other variables. Moreover, a significant interaction between stress and social support ($B = -0.10$, $P < 0.01$) was present, as predicted. The findings suggested that social support moderated the impact of stress on depression. Significantly positive relationship exists between stress and depression at low levels of social support ($B = 0.47$, $p < 0.01$, $R^2 = 0.22$). The relationship between stress and depression was significant at high levels of social support ($B = 0.22$, $p < 0.01$, $R^2 = 0.04$). The regression coefficient, however, was significantly less than that in the low social support group. Hence, the results also suggest that social support moderated the impact of stress on depression.

Conclusion

It was concluded that social support technique was significantly effective in managing physical and behavioural components of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of the study it was recommended that:

1. Government should employ experts with adequate training in the use of social support technique in the schools to assist students how to deal with separation anxiety problems and teachers should be sensitized how to observe separation anxiety symptoms among their Student and invite (experts) psychologists and counsellors for intervention.
2. Non-Governmental organizations should collaborate with federal and state governments to support teachers and IDPS camps officials to manage separation anxiety disorders with goals of promoting better mental health which lead to higher academic performance and achievements among student-victims of armed banditry.

References

- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistics manual of mental disorder*. (5th ed.). Washington DC: Cross Ref.
- Angel, M. H., Natalla, C. M., Susan, M. D. & Santiago. A. (2016). Social Support and Gender differences in coping with depression among emerging adults: a mixed method study. *Child and Adolescent Psychiatry and Mental Health*. Vol. 10, Number: 2.
- Asonibare, B. (2014). *Modifying maladapted behavior in schools* in A. I. Idowu (Ed.), *Guidance and counselling in Education* (2005 – 226) Ilorin: Endemic publication.
- Battaglia, M. (2015). Separation anxiety: *at the neurobiological crossroads of adaptation and illness Dialogues Clin Neurosci*. (3): 277-285.
- Bello, H. M. (2021). Effect Cognitive Restructuring and Social support techniques on Depression among HIV/AIDS Infected Women in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *A.B.U Journal of Educational Psychology and Counselling*. Vol. 3, No 2, 26-32.
- Boyd, C. P., Kostanski, M., & Gullone E. (2000). Prevalence of anxiety and depression in Australian adolescents: comparisons with worldwide data. *Journal of Genetic Psychology*, 161:479-492.
- Carbonel, D. (2014). *Exposure therapy for fears and school phobias*. Retrieved on 6th may, 2014 from anxietycoach.com.
- Castello, E. J. (2003). Relationships between Poverty and Psychopathology: a natural experiment. National library of medicine, *National Centre for Biotechnology Information. Jama*. 290 (15) 2023-9. Doi:10.1001
- Colman, A. M. (2015). *A dictionary of Psychology*. Oxford University Press, Great Clarendon Street, Oxford, OX2 6DP, United Kingdom.
- De Winter, J. F. C. (2013). Using students test with extremely small sample size: Practical assessment research and evaluation 18 (10) retrieved September 11, 2021 from <http://pareonline.net/getvn.asp> 7 vol. 188 CM 210

Impact of Social-Support ... (Rabiu, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15073806>

- Ford-mating, P. (2014). *Cognitive therapy: purpose, treatment, techniques, preparation, and typical result*. Retrieved on 16th June, 2014 from <http://psychology.jrank.org>
- Freud, A. (1926). *Hemmung, Symptom and Angst* (Inhibitions, Symptoms and Anxiety). Vienna: international Psychoanalytischer Verlag
- Graske, M., Wittchen, U., Bogels, S., Stein, M., Andrews, G. & Lebeu, R. (2013). *American Psychiatric Association*.
- Krain, F., Ghaffari, M., & Freeman, J. Anxiety disorders (2007). In Martin A., Volkmar F. R. (eds). *Lewis Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 4th edition. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, pp538-548.
- Maulik, P. K., Eaton, W.W., & Bradshaw, C. P. (2011). The effect of social networks and social support on mental health services use, following a life event, among the Baltimore Epidemiologic Catchment Area Cohort. *J Behave Health Survey Res*, 38 (1): 29 – 50. 10. 1007/s11414-009-9205-z.
- McLeod, S. A. (2006). Bowlby's attachment theory. Retrieved from www.simplypsychology.org/bowlby.html on 4/5/2020
- Moran, J.W., Talbot, R.P. & Benson, R. M. (1990). *A guide to graphical problem-solving processing*. Milwaukee: ASQC Quality press.
- Ossai, O. V. (2013). "Influence of Study Skills on Test Anxiety Levels and Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in English Language, Nsuka Urban in Enugu State.
- Redlich, R. (2015). "Are you gonna leave me? Separation anxiety is associated with increased amygdala responsiveness and volume" *social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*. 10 (2): 278-284.
- Rufa'I, M. A. (2021). *I' AM A BANDIT*, 15th University Seminar presented at Usman Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.
- Sirati-Nir, M., Khaghanizade, M., Rahimi, A., Khazae, M. & Ghadirian, F. (2018). Effect of Social support technique-training Group Intervention on Perceived Social support technique in Veterans with Posttraumatic Stress Disorder. *Iranian Journal of Nursing and Midwifery Research* 23 (4): 272-276
- Spence, S. H. (1994). A Measure of Anxiety Symptoms among Children. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*. Volume 36, (5): 545 – 566.
- Vaughan, J. Coddington, JA., Ahmed, AH., & Ertel, M. (2017). Separation Anxiety Disorder in School-Age Children: *What Health Care Providers Should Know*. *J. Pediatric Health Care*. 31 (4): 433-440

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Influence of Capacity Building on Effectiveness of Teaching-Learning Process among Public Senior Secondary School Teachers in Adamawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the Influence of Capacity Building on Effectiveness in Teaching-Learning Process Among Public Secondary School Teachers in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The study had 2 specific objectives research questions and null hypotheses. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study is 7161 senior secondary school teachers during 2023/2024 session. The sample size was 716 teachers. A self-developed structured questionnaire titled “Capacity Building and Teachers’ Effectiveness (CBTE) was used as instrument for the study. The questionnaire was validated by experts in the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum and experts from the Measurement and Evaluation Section, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The reliability index was 0.79 and the data collected were analyzed using frequency, percentages, and mean scores to answer research questions. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test all the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed that among others that capacity building influences teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as effective teaching tools through training, on the use of computers, posters, projectors, audio-visual materials, use of chalkboards and printed materials in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria (p-value=.143). The study concluded that capacity building has the ability to influence teachers’ effectiveness in teaching-learning process through the ability to use instructional materials, teachers’ method of teaching and teachers’ ability to reinforce learners as effective teaching tools in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. It was recommended that Adamawa state Government should brace up teachers’ capacity building on use of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. Adamawa State Ministry of Education should collaborate with Secondary school authorities at intervals to organize teachers’ capacity-building trainings on current teaching instructional techniques for effective teaching and learning in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Keyword: Capacity Building, Teaching-Learning Process, Secondary School Teachers

Introduction

Capacity building has become a popular concept in the education sector across both developed and emerging economies. Capacity building refers to the process through which individuals or organizations acquire, enhance, and sustain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment, and other resources necessary to perform their roles effectively or expand their capabilities (Kumari, 2022). Additionally, it involves the allocation and investment of resources—whether physical, intellectual, or human—particularly in situations where other variables have failed within specific institutional or social contexts. A systematic emphasis on capacity building within educational programs often highlights underlying imbalances in the sector. Ideally, capacity building should proactively serve as a fundamental component of efforts to strengthen social institutions and create conducive conditions for teachers in the school system to deliver optimal performance (Egbo, 2011).

However, teaching is a versatile field that requires, always, the correct identification of teaching methods, self-development, and training. The role of teachers necessitates a continuous pursuit of updated knowledge across various

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disciplines, including the acquisition of current skills, training, and information aligned with acceptable standards of general studies, with ICT being a crucial component. Globally, improving teacher education programs remains a priority, particularly in developing nations, as the quality of education and the progress of a nation are directly tied to the caliber of its teachers (Adeosun, 2018). In Nigeria, the objectives of teacher education include fostering a spirit of inquiry and creativity among teachers while equipping them with the intellectual and professional foundations needed for their responsibilities. This preparation also aims to enable teachers to adapt to evolving circumstances, as outlined by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014). The policy underscores that teacher education must account for changes in methods and curricula, ensuring that educators are regularly exposed to innovations in their field. Consequently, professional teacher training is structured into two key phases: pre-service and in-service training, with specific institutions tasked with the responsibility of delivering these programs.

Teachers who demonstrate high levels of effectiveness are more inclined to adopt and apply innovative teaching strategies, implement management techniques that foster student autonomy, establish realistic goals, and persevere when students struggle. They also go the extra mile to support low-achieving students and design instructional approaches that enhance students' self-confidence in their academic abilities (Silverman, 2019). Such teachers are instrumental in creating a learning environment where students can thrive academically and personally. The foundation of teacher effectiveness lies in thorough lesson preparation, beginning with crafting a comprehensive lesson plan. A lesson plan serves as the teacher's roadmap, outlining what students need to learn and detailing the most effective methods to achieve this within the available class time. Without a well-prepared plan, delivering a lesson effectively becomes challenging. As Ahievboloria (2015) highlights, a successful lesson plan should seamlessly incorporate three essential components: clearly defined objectives for student learning, engaging teaching and learning activities, and strategic methods to assess student understanding. These elements ensure that lessons are structured, impactful, and conducive to achieving desired learning outcomes.

Statement of the Research Problem:

In general, workers are expected to do well in their jobs, but the need for an enabling environment is not being given the priority it deserves. The situation is even worse in the teaching profession where society feels that teachers are owed nothing. The way teachers teach have direct impact on the learning outcomes. Therefore, it is important that teachers are expected and encouraged to be trained and retrained after employment for the achievement of teaching effectiveness in the discharge of their duties during teaching-learning process in the classroom. Training and retraining programs, which should be prioritized by government authorities and school managers, are often overlooked or inadequately addressed. Egbebi (2024) quoting the address of Universal Basic Education Commission, UBEC, as posited by Executive Secretary of the Commission confirmed that 57 billion naira was disbursed for teachers' training in 13 years from 2009-2022, having noted a few number of teachers that had undergone training in recent years. He affirmed that the UBEC 2022 National Personnel Audit revealed that 67.5 percent of teachers in public schools and 86.3 percent in private schools have not been given the privilege of attending in-service training in the last five years (2018-2022). This is expected to have negative implication for quality education impartation in the UBE programme. This indicates that the current training arrangements for teachers are severely insufficient to meet the requirements outlined in the UBE Acts of 2004. More so, this development will affect the quality of learning outcomes at almost every education level if this research is not conducted. This has led to a lack of morale and inability to adapt to changes and innovations in the educational system of senior public secondary education. The existed issues on instructional material supplies; students' and teachers' motivation; teacher preparation capacity, instructional management strategies, and teacher communication patterns. All these put together are faced with one kind of challenge or the other ranging from inadequate capacity building of teachers' effectiveness in the system.

In recent years, basic education has been a primary focus for the Federal Government and key stakeholders, including the international community. However, senior secondary education, an essential level within the education system, appears to be falling short of its intended objectives. Student retention rates at this level remain low, and those who manage to graduate often exhibit subpar communication skills and a lack of moral virtues. Additionally, many dropouts from this educational level are involved in social vices such as pickpocketing, hawking, scavenging, street begging, and even violent activities like suicide bombing. These issues point to a potential deficiency in the effectiveness of secondary school teachers in fulfilling their teaching responsibilities. Given that teacher effectiveness is indispensable to the success of any school system, it is reasonable to infer that teachers play a role in the current challenges faced by senior secondary school education. This study, therefore, seeks to examine the Influence of Capacity Building on Effectiveness in the Teaching-Learning Process among Public Senior Secondary School Teachers in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

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Objectives of the Study

- a. Assess the influence of capacity building on teachers’ instructional materials usage as teaching effectiveness tool in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.
- b. Ascertain the influence of capacity building on teachers’ method of teaching as tool of teaching effectiveness in the study area.

Research Questions

- i. Does the capacity building training have any influence on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as tool of teaching effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria?
- ii. In what ways does capacity building influence teachers’ methods of teaching as tool of teaching effectiveness in the study area?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the opinions of principals, teachers, and Ministry of Education Officials (MOE) on the influence of capacity building efforts on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents on the influence of capacity building training on teachers’ methods of teaching as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in the study area.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design with population of this study was 7,161 respondents, consisting of 6,709 teachers, 415 principals, and 37 Ministries of Education Officials and sample size of 716 consisting of 671 teachers, 41 principals, and 4 MOE officials. The instrument used for collecting data for this study was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher titled “Capacity Building and Teachers’ Effectiveness (CBTE). The instrument consisted of two sections; Section A consists of the demography of the respondents while Section B showed questions that were adopted to elicit answers from respondents in the research questions on the Influence of Capacity Building on Public Senior Secondary School Teacher Effectiveness in Teaching-Learning Process in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The researcher collected a letter of introduction from the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum. Then, an official visit was made to schools selected in Adamawa State. The researcher and three research assistants were showed introductory letters to principals of sampled schools in their respective locations in the State in readiness for the collection of data. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the data analysis. The responses that were obtained from the questionnaires were tallied and coded, analyzed and presented using descriptive and inferential statistics. In the descriptive statistics, frequency counts and percentages and mean were used to answer the research questions, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance because the normality test showed that the data was normally distributed, and the categories of respondents were there (principals, teachers, and MOE officials).

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: Does the capacity building training have any influence on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as tool of teaching effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on influence of capacity building training on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Capacity Building and Teachers’ use of Instructional materials	3.8	.560	Has Influence

Fieldwork, (2024)

The analysis of items used to answer research questions 1 revealed calculated grand mean of 3.8 greater than the benchmark of 3.0. This indicates that principal, teachers and MOE officials agreed that through capacity building training, teachers use instructional materials effectively in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

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Research Question 2: In what ways does capacity building influence teachers’ methods of teaching as tool of teaching effectiveness in the study area?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on influence of capacity building training on teachers’ method of teaching

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Capacity Building and Teachers’ use of Instructional materials	3.6	.251	Has Influence

Fieldwork, (2024)

The analysis of items used to answer research questions 2 revealed calculated grand mean of 3.8 greater than the benchmark of 3.0. This indicates that principal, teachers and MOE officials agreed that through capacity building training, teachers make effective use methods of teaching in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1

Table 3: One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Influence of Capacity Building on Teachers’ Ability to use Instructional Materials as Effective Teaching Tool in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	.196	2	.127	2.12	.143	Retained
Within Groups	28.002	714	.048			
Total	28.198	716				

Fieldwork, (2024)

The analysis of the results in Table 3 shows differences in the opinions of respondents (principal, teachers and MOE officials) on the influence of capacity building efforts on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The result reveals a calculated F value of 2.12 at a significant p-value of .143. Since the calculated p-value of .143 is more than the fixed probability level of 0.05 ($P > 0.05$), the null hypothesis is therefore retained which means that there is no differences in the opinions of respondents (principal, teachers and MOE officials) on the influence of capacity building efforts on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

Table 4: One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Influence of Capacity Building Training on Teachers’ Method of Teaching as Effective Teaching Tool in Public Senior Secondary Schools in the Study Area

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	.106	2	.133	1.210	.318	Retained
Within Groups	30.617	714	.064			
Total	30.723	716				

Fieldwork, (2024)

The analysis of the results in Table 4 shows differences in the opinions of respondents (principal, teachers and MOE officials) on the influence of capacity building training on teachers’ method of teaching as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in the study area. The result reveals a calculated F value of 1.210 at a significant p-value of .318. Since the calculated p-value of .318 is more than the fixed probability level of 0.05 ($P > 0.05$), the null hypothesis is therefore retained which means that there is no differences in the opinions of respondents on the influence of capacity building training on teachers’ method of teaching as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in the study area.

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Discussion of Findings

Capacity building influences teachers' ability to use instructional materials as effective teaching tool through training, on use of computers, posters, projectors, audio-visual materials, use of chalkboards and printed materials in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The test of hypothesis showed no significant differences in the opinions of respondents (p -value=.143). This finding is in accordance with the report of Dittimiya (2015) who reported that instructional materials in secondary schools are the resources used to help the teacher to make the teaching and learning process easier. Instructional materials include both visuals, audio visuals and electronic interactives such as real objects, film strips, pictures, flashcards, posters, maps, charts, graphs, tape recorders, radio, video, television, computers, slide projectors, projector, and over-head projectors among others. This was supported by the researcher that adequate provision of instructional materials in secondary schools in Adamawa state ensures more effective teaching and learning since the learner not only hears but also sees and does while the knowledge of a wide variety of instructional materials and the specific functions, they can perform is a value-added advantage for the teacher. The researcher further opines that teachers should endeavour to use as many instructional materials provided as possible and in cases where they are inadequate instructional materials, improvisation can substitute.

Capacity building influences teachers' method of teaching as effective teaching tool through training, on use of lecture method, discussion, demonstration, discovery, project, fieldtrip method as well as cooperative/collaborative strategies in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The test of hypothesis showed no significant differences in the opinions of respondents (p -value=.318). The findings of this study align with Ibrahim's (2001) assertion that teaching methods are a set of principles and strategies employed by teachers to facilitate student learning. These methods are shaped both by the subject matter and the nature of the learners. For a teaching method to be deemed appropriate and effective, it must consider the learner's characteristics, the content being taught, and the specific type of learning intended. Teaching approaches can be broadly categorized into teacher-centered and student-centered models.

In a teacher-centered (authoritarian) approach, the teacher holds the primary authority and is responsible for delivering content through lectures and direct instruction. Students are often seen as passive recipients of knowledge, and their learning is predominantly assessed through tests and exams. In this model, teaching and assessment are typically treated as distinct, with learning outcomes primarily measured through objective assessments.

Conclusion

The study concluded that capacity building has the ability to influence teachers' ability to use instructional materials, teachers' method of teaching and teachers' ability to reinforce learners as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The study recommended that The Secondary School Authorities should establish structured mentorship programs where experienced teachers can mentor new or underperforming teachers. Peer learning initiatives should also be encouraged to foster collaborative learning among teachers and help them adopt best practices.

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References

- Adeosun, O. (2018). Teacher Education Programmes and the Acquisition of Skills: Issues and Challenges in Nigeria. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 6(1), 103-120. doi: 10.11648/j.jhrm.20180601.11
- Ahievboloria, J. E. V., (2015). A Comparative Study of Manpower and Physical Facilities in Tertiary Institutions in Delta State. Unpublished M.Ed. Dissertation, Delta State University, Abraka.
- Dittimiya, A., (2015). Assessment of Senior Secondary Education in Nigeria. *Journal of Functional Management*. 4 (1 104-118 Ibadan, Nigeria.

Influence of Capacity Building ... (Magaji, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15079769>

- Egbebi, J. O. (2024). Universal Basic Education implementation issues in Nigeria and options for improvement in administration of basic education systems. Accepted Article for Publication. Department of Educational Management, Lagos State University of Education, Maforijin, Epe.
- Egbo, B. (2011). Teacher Capacity Building and Effective Teaching and Learning: A Seamless Connection. Proceedings of the 2011 International Conference on Teaching, Learning and Change. Human Resource Management Academic Research Society. Canada
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) (2014). National Policy on Education. Lagos: NERDC press
- Ibrahim, S. (2001). Principals' Decision-Making Strategies and Teachers' Productivity in Secondary Schools in Ondo Central Senatorial District of Ondo State", Nigeria. Global Journal of Management and Business Research, 18(10), pp. 21-22, 2001.
- Kumari, S. (2022) Teachers Views on Training and Capacity Building in Education. Retrieved from <http://www.researchgate.net> on 5th May 2024

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Influence of Gender and Location Norms on Academic Corruption among Senior Secondary School Students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was to determine the influence of gender and location norms of the academic corruption among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. An instrumentation research design was adopted. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class three (SSIII) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Bayelsa State. A sample size of 500 students consisting of 250 males and 250 females, were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. Data were obtained with the standardized academic-corruption -sensitivity-test (ACST) instrument which was validated through face, content and construct validity which gave a construct validity coefficients of .56, .86 and .90 as well as its reliability was determined through Cronbach alpha which gives a reliability coefficient of .89. Data were analyzed with percentiles ranking and stanine while the two null hypotheses were tested with t-test at .05 level of significance. It was observed that there is no statistically significant difference between male and female students on academic corruption while there was significant difference between rural and urban students on academic corruption. The ACST norms ranged from 0-100% indicating from very highly corrupt to not very corrupt. The study therefore concludes that male and female students have similar vulnerability to academic corruption while rural students have higher susceptibility to academic corruption than urban students. Based on these conclusions, the study further recommends that the ACST scale should be used alongside with aptitude test for admissions in order to identify corrupt candidates and refer them for counselling services before admissions.

Keywords: Academic corruption, norms, location, sensitivity, gender and test

Introduction

Corruption has become a household name in Nigeria. Corruption seems unabated and had entered into the bone marrow of individuals whose conscience are no more alive. Corruption has bedeviled the nation to the point that each successive government became vulnerable to it. Though, conceptualization of corruption poses no debate among intellectuals, particularly social scientists. Only that definitions advanced accordingly from one situation or country to another depending on deviations from prescribed patterns of bureaucratic behaviour. Ganner (1999, p.348) defined corruption as the act of doing something with an intent to give some advantage inconsistent with official duty and the rights of others, a fiduciary's or official's use of a station or office to procure some benefit either personally or for someone else, contrary to the rights of others. This definition relates corruption as any act that deviates from moral and ethical sets of behaviour. Meanwhile Obansajo (2000, p.4) stated that "we realized that corruption covers a wide spectrum of acts and not just the simple act of giving and receiving of bribes". Furthermore, corruption covers such acts as use of ones office for pecuniary advantage, gratification, influence peddling, and insincerity in advice with aim of gaining advantage, less than a full day's work for a full day's pay and tardiness and slovenliness, Obasanjo (2000) remarked. This could make one to describe corruption as any act of deviation from formal rules that regulate behaviour of individuals in any given society or organization.

From this point of view corruption can be said to be a complex and multi-faceted phenomenon with multiple causes and effects. It is not a misnomer to conclude that corruption is any act of violating regulations or wrong doing in whatever form to achieve success either personally or for someone else contrary to the rights of others. It is the act of unethical practices in schools. This ugly hydraheaded problem had crept into the educational sectors especially the secondary sector where miracle centers are provided for examination malpractices. The study, therefore, conceptualizes academic corruption as act of deviation by students from formal rules that regulate their behaviours in the secondary education system.

Against this backdrop, academic performance of students are reported in letter grade or grade point average terms, such reporting focuses on the basis of tests and examination of learning outcomes in the cognitive domain, affective and psychomotor domains. However, in practical terms, considerably less, if not no focus on the affective and psychomotor domains in academic achievement of students. Whatever form it takes, academic corruption such as grade inflation, examination

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malpractices, cheating, bribery, exchange of grade for sex, cultism and so on has a deleterious effect on the academic achievement of students. This unabated trend can plunge the educational system to breed a rising tide of educational mediocrity. Natia (2004, p.3) arguably viewed that corruption leads to:

Educational inefficiency. It impairs the quality of the education students receive. It destroys the concepts of meritocracy and honest academic achievement. It leads to frustration and damages the morale of students and faculty. It weakens public trust in the process and products of the university and academic enterprises and reduces the value of degrees.

It is crystal clear that corruption not only affects academic achievement of students but destroys several academic glories including character and ethics. It is a social and economic cancer. It could be acknowledged that academic corruption in the forms of bribery, forgery, falsification of examination results, patronage, cronyism, examination malpractices, cultism, destruction of school property, etc. deteriorate the quality of the secondary education thereby producing not just low but smoke-screen academic performance of students. Opalaye (2005) reported that secondary school education is like a window through which students peep out to see which direction he/she wants to go. It is so frustrating that miracle examination centers have been put in place where students will leave their schools and go to and register for their SSC examinations. These candidates after making their papers would write JAMB and consequently admitted into the tertiary education and could not defend their papers anymore.

Uzoagba and Keke (2017) asserted that education is a living thing successful only if it is inspired by the cultural foundations of the people whom it seeks to serve. The paper concluded that corruption in education threatens equality and quality of its beneficiaries. There are tremendous effects corruption impose on education. One of them is the production of half-baked graduates that could not defend themselves in any field of human endeavour and at the same time cannot contribute to nation building. Another significant effect of corruption in education is its ability to discourage hard work, honesty and other moral virtues among students rather they promote vices such as indiscipline of all kinds (Uzoagba & Keke, 2017). Madaki (2019) stated that students and parents systematically and shamelessly impact the education sector incentives, unmerited gifts, donations to the school in order to influence decisions regarding their children and wards. These unethical behaviours can only be elicited or inferred by using a non-cognitive test such as the academic corruption sensitivity test (ACST).

From this backdrop, it became necessary to determine the gender and location norms from the ACST to enable valid interpretation and comparison across gender and geographic location of students. Norms are very important tools used to provide reliable information about the test taker as well as enable the comparison of students who at anytime take the test with standardization sample, remarked Ughamadu et al., (1991). Onunkwo (2005) asserted that norms are standards based on which judgements or decisions are made. To this end, identifying norms of gender and location of schools for the ACST instrument became instructive in order to make valued judgement or decision at anytime the ACST is being put into use. Norms are average scores such as mean or standard scores such as T-score, Z-score, percentile rank, Stanine, etc. This study made use of stannine and percentile ranks to determine the gender based and geographic location-based norms.

There are plethora of psychological tests that measures cognitive traits of students. The academic corruption sensitivity test (ACST) is a non-cognitive scale standardized to elicit academic related traits from learners in secondary school in Bayelsa State. The scale has 30 items structured in the likert format with a 5-point continuum. The ACST is valid and reliable however gender and location-based norms have not been determined. The absence of these norms can make the interpretation of the scale difficult. Meanwhile, the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF, 2020) determines gender norms as a subset of social norms that relate specifically to gender differences. This relates that gender norms are social principles that control the behaviour of males and females in society and restrict their gender identity into what is considered to be appropriate while location norms are part of the social norms that identify rural and urban differences which are fundamental to planning and formulation of policy especially in the educational sector. Identifying these gender and location based norms for the ACST will help in the utility of the instruments regarding rendering counseling services, control gender based behaviors, planning and formulation of policies in curbing academic corruption among secondary school system and educational system at large. Therefore, this study was to determine the gender and location norms of the ACST among secondary school students in Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Research Problem

Education in Nigeria is considered as a vital instrument for effecting national development. It has been structured in a way the philosophy and desirable objectives of the nation would be achieved through the educational system. It portends quality and effective education that is free from corruption, development of the individual into a sound and effective citizen,

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and provision of equal access to educational opportunities for all citizens of the country at primary, secondary and tertiary levels (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004). However, it has been observed that corruption has bedeviled the educational system in the form of examination malpractices, cultism, hooliganism, sex-for-grade, and so on. (Sakwa & Abdullahi, 2023) asserted that problem of academic corruption (examination malpractices) has remain unabated and spread to all educational levels with candidates taking senior secondary school certificate examination (SSCE) championing the crusade. This becomes alarming that if not tackle empirically can plunged the educational system to breed half-baked graduates without feet, hooligans, cultists, etc. Even, the standard of education will be inexplicably fallen in Bayelsa State and Nigeria at large. It became necessary therefore for this study to examine the influence of gender and school location norms on academic corruption among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The following objectives were posed to guide the study. The study was to:

1. determine the norms of Academic Corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State.
2. establish gender norms of Academic Corruption among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State
3. determine location of school norms on Academic Corruption among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study. These include:

5. What are the norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?
6. What are the male and female norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?
7. What are the location norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance to make decisions on the variables being investigated.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female students' academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of rural and urban students academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Methodology

This study adopted an instrumentation research design which enabled the researcher to adopt the standardized Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) to collect gender-based and locatio-based data for content and statistical analysis. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class three (SSIII) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Bayelsa State. A sample size of 500 students consisting of 250 males and 250 females as well as of the divide of 292 and 209 rural and urban students respectively, were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test was constructed and standardized by Queensoap (2006). The ACST followed necessary procedures for the standardization of a non-cognitive test. The ACST was validated through face, content and construct validity which gave a construct validity coefficients of .56, .86 and .90 for Negative Item Scores (NIS) vs Positive Item Scores (PIS), Negative Item Score (NIS) vs Total Item Scores (TIS) and Positive Item Scores (PIS) vs Total Item Scores (TIS) respectively as well as its reliability was determined through Cronbach alpha which gives a reliability coefficient of .89. The researcher recruited research assistants to help administer the study instrument to respondents after securing ethical approval from relevant authorities. Data obtained were analyzed using percentile ranking, stanine and t-test.

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Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What are the norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Computation of Percentile Ranks for the ACST Norms

ACST Scores	Percentile Ranks	Stanine	Norms Intepretation
131-150	81 – 100	9, 8, 7 and 6	Very Honest (not very corrupt)
122-130	61 – 80	5, 4, and 3	Honest (not corrupt)
111-121	41 – 60	2	Moderately corrupt
99-110	21 – 40	1	Highly corrupt
Below 99	0 – 20	1	Very highly corrupt

Source: Field Work

Table 1 indicated the norms of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) administered to 500 secondary school students. It can be discerned from table 1 that very honest (not very corrupt) students has a norm range of 81-100, honest (not corrupt) students has 61-80, moderately corrupt students was 41-60, highly corrupt students was 21-40 and very highly corrupt was 0-20 with the corresponding scores of ACST as 131-150, 122-130, 111-121, 99-110 and below 99 respectively. Table 1 also showed the stanine equivalents of the norms. This implies that ACST scores can be converted to stanines and help intepret the extent of corrupt act of students. Again, it can be deduced from Table 1 that 51% of students' score lie below 117 while 74% and 24% of the students' scores lie below the upper quartile and lower quartile respectively. This implies that 74% of the students lie the upper quartile score 128 while 24% was observed lying below the first quartile score, 101.

Research Question 2

What are the male and female norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Summary of Computation of Gender Norms using Stanines

Variables	Stanines /percentile norms (%)								
	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
Male (N = 250)	96+	90-95	84-89	79-83	73-78	67-72	61-66	55-65	Below 55
Female (N = 250)	96+	90-95	85-89	79-84	73-78	67-72	61-66	55-65	Below 55

Source: Field Work

Table 2 showed the various stanines for male and female students who responded the ACST scale. It was observed that male and female students who scored 96% and above were assigned stanine 9 while male and female students who scored 90%-95% were assigned stanine 8. Stanine 7 was assigned to male and female students who scored 84% - 89% and 85% - 89% respectively while both male and female students who scored 73%-78%, 67%-72%, 61%-66%, 55%-60% and below 55% were assigned stanines 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. This implies that male level of academic corruption does not differ from female students' level of academic corruption. They barely had the same norms as measured with stanine 9.

Research Question 3

What are the location norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Summary of computation of school location norms using Stanines

Variables	Stanines /percentile norms (%)								
	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
Rural (N = 292)	94+	89 -93	83 – 88	77-82	71- 76	65-70	59-64	53-58	Below 53
Urban (N = 208)	97+	92 -96	87 – 91	81-86	76-80	71-75	65-70	60-64	Below 60

Source: Field Work

Table 3 showed the school location norms. It was found that in urban schools stanine 9 was assigned to a student score of 97% and above. For rural school location stanine 9 was assigned to students who scored 94% and above. Also, it was observed that students in urban who scored 65%-70% were assigned with stanine 3 while in rural location students who scored 65% - 70% were assigned with stanine 4. Stanine 1 was assigned to students who scored below 60% and 53% in urban and rural locations respectively. This implies that academic corruption levels differ from school locations. It means school locations influences academic corruption. This was evidenced of the fact that their stanine placements were not the same.

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Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female students' academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Table 4: Summary of t-test statistics for the difference between the mean-scores of male and female students as measured in the ACST

Unpaired variables	N	Mean	Sd	T	Df	P val	95% CI	P < .05?	Decision
Male	250	75	13	0.97	498	.33	-1.13 to 3.34	No	Not sig.
Female	250	76	12						H ₀ not rejected

Source: Field Work

The data in table 4 showed that male students has 250 participants, 75±13 mean and standard deviation while female students has 250 participants, 76±12 mean and standard deviation. It can be discerned from Table 4 that for t is 0.97, degree of freedom of 498, *P value* .33, 95% confidence interval of -1.13 to 3.34. This implies that *P value of* .33 is greater than chosen alpha of .05 thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female students' academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State is not rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of rural and urban students academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Table 5: Summary of t-test statistics for the difference between the mean-scores of rural and urban students as measured in the ACST

Unpaired variables	N	Mean	Sd	T	Df	P val	95% CI	P < .05?	Decision
Rural	292	74	12	3.88	498	.0001	2.04 to 6.33	Yes	Sig.
Urban	208	78	12						H ₀ rejected

Table 5 depicted that rural location students has 292 participants, 74±12 mean and standard deviation while urban location students has 208 participants with 78±12 mean and standard deviation. This suggests that urban students seem more honest than the rural-located students because the mean for the former was greater than the later. It was also observed from table 5 that t is 3.88, degree of freedom is 498, *P value of* .0001, 95% confidence interval of 2.04 to 6.33. This denotes that *P value* (.0001) is less than the chosen alpha of *P* = .05 hence t no significant difference between the mean scores of rural and urban students academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The results supports Galtung (2005) which maintained that the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) ranks countries on a scale from zero to 10, using percentile matching and a score of ten represents a totally honest country while zero indicates a very corrupt country. This denotes that gender is not a factor that would influence academic corruption, male and female students are vulnerable to academic corruption and their corrupt practices are alike. In another study, though on corruption, observed significant disparity between male and female in corrupt practices, especially collection and giving of bribe. The study reveals that the disparity becomes even larger when factoring in the urban/rural dimension which informs that women living in rural areas are those least likely to pay bribes (21.6%) whereas men living in urban areas are most likely (39.3%), remarked (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2019).

This means that the extent of academic corruption differ significantly among students of post-primary school which is probably influenced by the location of the school. Since the mean of the urban students was greater than the rula-based students, it can be interpreted that urban-based students are less corrupt than rural-based students. In otherwords, urban-based students were more honest that the rural-based students. The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2019) reported that the decrease of the prevalence of corrupt acts in relation to customs/immigration officers, judges/magistrates, and police officers was particularly significant in rural areas, but less in urban areas. This suggests that location of school can influence corrupt acts of individual so far as other factors remain the same.

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Conclusion

The study concludes that gender was not a factor in academic corruption. The ACST scores were tested at at .05 alpha significance level and the null hypothesis was accepted indicating that the norms of the scale for male and female has no statistically significant difference. It was also concluded that location of school was observed as a significant factor in academic corruption among secondary school students. The norms of the ACST were ranged from 0-100 %, indicating from very highly corrupt (0-20%) to not very corrupt (very honest) (81-100%). The findings of the study would help identify unethical behaviour and immoral acts to seek for measures to correct such corrupt acts which is to be implicated for psychologists, guidance counsellor, psychometricians and sociologists in rendering their services to the students. Evaluation bodies such as National Examination Council (NECO) and West African School Examination Council (WAEC) would be implied with the findings because the findings might enable them modify their ways of setting or supervision of their examinations.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. The ACST norms should be used to identify and categorize students who are very highly corrupt to students who are very honest before admission into higher institutions. This will help refer academically corrupt students to institution counselling centre for behavioral modelling.
2. The gender based norms of the ACST be used to ensure gender balance for admission and placement purposes in educational system.
3. The geographic location norms of the ACST be adapted into planning and supply of school equipment, materials and supervision of examinations in rural and urban locations.

References

- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2004). *National policy on education*. Federal Ministry of Education.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2009). *1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria with fundamental rights (enforcement procedure) rules 2009*. Federal Ministry of Justice.
- Galtung, F. (2005). Measuring the immeasurable: Boundaries and functions of (Macro) indices. In F. Galtung, & S. (. Charles, *Measuring Corruption* (pp. 50-62). Ashgate.
- Ganner, B. A. (1999). *Black's law dictionary*. West Group.
- Madaki, A. K. (2019). The effect of corruption on the educational system in Nigeria. *British Journal of Education*, 7(11), , 41-49.
- Natia, J. (2004, January 5). *Fighting corruption in Georgia's universities*. Retrieved from aau.org: <http://www.aaup.org/publication/academe/2004/0450/0480Jana.html>.
- Obansajo, O. (2000). Address given on the occasion of the formal signing into law of the corrupt practices and other related offences act 2000 at Abuja. In F. R. Nigeria, *Anti-Corruption law of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 2000* (pp. 3-4). Time Press.
- Onunkwo, G. I. (2005). *Tests: types, preparation, administration, communication*. VIGO Publishers International.
- Opalaye, B. (2005). Reawakening in education. In S. O. Asaju, S. O. Tanimola, & J. A. Akintunde, *Church Training Programmes for Adults and Young Adults 2005*. (pp. 5-7). Baptist Press.
- Queensoap, M. (2006). *Construction and standardization of academic corruption sensitivity test*. Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt.
- Sakwa, M. A., & Abdullahi, B. (2023). An in-depth evaluation on the issues of examinationmalpractices in national teachers' institute, Rimi College study centre, Kaduna, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal for Technical Education*, 21(1), 133-140.
- Ughamadu, K. A., Onwuegbu, O. C., & Osundu, A. U. (1991). *Measurement and evaluation*. World of Books.
- United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) . (2020, January 5). *Technical note on gender norms*. Retrieved from unicef.org: <https://www.unicef.org>
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2019, December 19). *Corruption in Nigeria:Patterns and trends*. Retrieved from unodc.org: <https://www.unodc.org>
- Uzoagba, B. C., & Keke, K. I. (2017). Crruption in educational system: The Nigerian experience. *Whelan Research Academy International Symposium*, 2(15), 36-49.
- Wieland, A., Durach, C. F., Kembro, J., & Treiblmaier, H. (2017). Statistical and judgemental criteria for scale purification. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 22(4), <https://doi.org/10.1108/scm-07-2016-0230>, 321-328

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Influence of Social Media on Reading Habits and Performance in Social Studies among Upper Basic School students in Delta State

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Abstract

This research investigated the influence of social media on reading habits and performance in Social Studies among Upper Basic School students in Delta State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. A well-structured questionnaire titled '*Social Media Influence on Reading Habits and Performance Questionnaire*' (SMIRHAPQ) was used as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by two (2) experts in educational research and (2) two lecturers in the department of Social Science Education Delta State University, Abraka and had a reliability coefficient of 0.85, established through a pilot test using the Cronbach Alpha method. The population of the study consisted of 1,094 Upper Basic Class two (2) Social Studies students (444 males and 650 females) during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta State, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select a representative sample of 300 students (120 males and 180 females) drawn from the three senatorial districts of the State. Data collected were analyzed using Chi-square and t-test statistical methods. The findings revealed that there is a significant influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in upper basic schools. Additionally, it was found that social media usage significantly influences students' performance in Social Studies. However, there was no significant difference in the performance of Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not in upper basic schools in Delta State. The study concluded that while social media has both positive and negative impacts, its potential for enhancing educational outcomes cannot be ignored if effectively managed. It recommended that schools, educators, parents, and policymakers should collaboratively promote responsible social media use through education, curriculum integration, parental guidance, and engaging classroom activities to enhance academic focus and leverage its potential for learning

Keyword: Social Media Usage, Reading Habits, Performance, Social Studies, Upper Basic school students.

Introduction

The rapid proliferation of social media platforms has significantly transformed communication, education, and information dissemination in the 21st century. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, WhatsApp, and X (formerly Twitter) dominate daily interactions, reshaping how individuals connect, learn, and share information. For students, these platforms serve dual purposes: as sources of entertainment and as tools for educational exploration. However, this digital shift presents a paradox, with both positive and negative implications for academic performance and traditional reading habits (Musa & Emmanuel, 2017). In the educational domain, social media seems to democratize access to knowledge, fostering collaborative learning through interactive groups, tutorials, and discussion forums. Social media provides opportunities for engaging with diverse content, expanding global awareness, and promoting participatory learning experiences. Yet, the overwhelming influx of information and the addictive design of these platforms raise significant concerns about their impact on students' focus, time management, and cognitive abilities (Hou & Xu, 2024). In subjects like Social Studies, which emphasize critical reading, analytical thinking, and the exploration of societal dynamics, the effects of social media usage may be particularly notable. The emergence of digital distractions may often shift students' attention from in-depth reading to superficial engagement with fragmented content. Consequently, there is a growing apprehension about the erosion of reading

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habits and its potential consequences on academic performance, particularly for upper basic education students in Delta State, Nigeria. Reading has long appeared to have been regarded as the cornerstone of academic success and intellectual development. Traditional reading practices, involving printed materials such as textbooks, newspapers, and academic journals, may provide students with structured and immersive learning experiences. Scholars like Paige et.al (2024) underscored the role of sustained and focused reading in enhancing comprehension, critical thinking, and overall academic performance. Through traditional reading, learners may develop an understanding of complex concepts and are better equipped to engage with academic materials critically. Additionally, reading seems to foster cognitive skills such as memory retention, vocabulary acquisition, and analytical reasoning. Le et.al (2024) stated that exposure to extensive reading positively influences vocabulary growth and comprehension, creating a strong foundation for learning across disciplines. For subjects like Social Studies, which require understanding nuanced societal concepts and historical contexts, traditional reading may appear indispensable.

The influence of traditional reading habits extends beyond academic success to include broader societal impacts. Studies by Osharive (2015) stated that regular reading habits contribute to better communication skills and social awareness, which are essential for shaping informed and responsible citizens. Social Studies, as a discipline, is closely aligned with these objectives, as it aims to inculcate civic competence and ethical reasoning among students. In the 21st century, the rapid growth of social media platforms has redefined the way individuals consume information. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and WhatsApp have introduced new modes of communication, enabling users to share content instantly and engage in discussions globally. While these platforms offer unprecedented opportunities for knowledge exchange, their impact on traditional reading habits and educational outcomes has been a subject of scholarly concern.

Social media may encourage a culture of rapid information consumption, where users interact with fragmented and brief content rather than engaging deeply with extended texts. Musa (2017) notes that the over-reliance on social media for information can undermine the skills required for critical reading and analytical thinking. This shift poses a significant challenge to students' academic performance, particularly in subjects like Social Studies, which demand a deep engagement with texts and critical evaluation of ideas. Moreover, the addictive nature of social media platforms has raised concerns about their effects on students' time management and focus. In the views of Adekunjo et.al (2024) excessive use of social media often leads to procrastination and reduced academic productivity. In Delta State, where educational resources are already stretched, the increasing dependence on social media seems to add a layer of complexity to efforts aimed at maintaining high academic standards.

The educational systems may face unique challenges in balancing technological advancements with traditional learning goals. Limited access to infrastructure, insufficient training for teachers, and a lack of awareness about effective technology integration tend to exacerbate the issues caused by social media usage. For instance, Almusaed et.al (2023) emphasizes that while technology can enhance learning, its misuse often leads to a decline in students' academic engagement and performance. Social Studies as a subject is particularly vulnerable to these challenges. As a discipline that aims to promote critical thinking and civic engagement, it relies heavily on students' ability to comprehend and analyze complex texts. The prevalence of superficial reading habits fostered by social media use may undermine these objectives, making it difficult for educators to achieve desired learning outcomes.

In addition, economic disparities within Delta State mean that not all students have equal access to digital tools or printed materials. According to Peras et.al (2023) socioeconomic factors play a significant role in determining students' reading habits and academic success. This digital divide may further complicate efforts to integrate technology into education without compromising traditional learning practices. Several studies have explored the interplay between reading habits and social media usage, offering insights into the challenges and opportunities presented by this digital shift. Sivakumar et.al (2023) revealed that social media can promote knowledge sharing and can increase student motivation and performance. The findings suggested that social networking is a valuable method of information dissemination and can be used to encourage student engagement. Furthermore, Javeed (2023) revealed a positive correlation between excessive social media use and academic performance. The findings are consistent with observations where students who spend more time on social media platforms tend to perform excellently in subjects requiring sustained reading and analytical skills.

In the same vein, other scholars argued that social media can be harnessed to complement traditional reading practices. For instance, Mosharrafa et.al (2024) opined that integrating social media into classroom activities can enhance students' engagement and motivation. By encouraging discussions and collaborative projects, educators can use these platforms to create dynamic learning environments that align with the objectives of Social Studies education. Musa and Emmanuel (2017) examined how social media influences the reading culture of students at Kaduna Polytechnic, finding that excessive time spent on social media negatively impacts academic reading and performance. They recommended integrating social media into the

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curriculum and improving library facilities to support effective learning. Osharive (2015) investigated the impact of social media on the academic performance of undergraduate students, revealing significant addiction and recommending its use for educational purposes while emphasizing parental and teacher monitoring to balance academic and social media activities. Suci et.al (2022) reviewed literature from 2015 to 2020 by highlighting the role of social media in facilitating collaborative and interactive online learning, especially during pandemic-induced school closures. Findings emphasized that while social media promotes resource. Ansari et.al (2020) examined the role of social media and mobile devices in collaborative learning, revealing their significant impact on interactivity with peers, teachers, and knowledge sharing, which enhances students' engagement and academic performance. Using a structural equation model, data from 360 students in eastern India highlights how social media fosters creativity, dynamism, and a research-oriented mindset among learners. The findings are that sharing, interaction, and collaboration, effective planning and management are crucial to optimizing its educational potential.

Achieving a balance between technology integration and traditional learning is crucial for addressing the challenges posed by social media usage. Strategies such as digital literacy training, time management workshops, and the promotion of reading culture could help mitigate the adverse effects of social media on students' academic performance. Digital literacy programmes, for example, can equip students with the skills needed to navigate online platforms responsibly and critically. By teaching students how to discern credible sources and evaluate information critically, educators can foster habits that support academic success (Erwin and Mohammed, 2022). Similarly, time management workshops could help students prioritize their academic responsibilities and minimize distractions caused by social media. Promoting a culture of reading is undoubtedly important. Initiatives such as book clubs, reading competitions, and the incorporation of engaging texts into the curriculum may encourage students to develop sustained reading habits. For Social Studies, incorporating real-world case studies and multimedia resources could make traditional reading materials more appealing and relevant to students.

Statement of the Research Problem:

The rapid proliferation of social media platforms has reshaped how students interact, learn, and engage with information. While these platforms offer significant educational opportunities, such as collaborative learning and access to diverse content, their pervasive use also raises concerns about their impact on students' academic performance and traditional reading habits. Social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, WhatsApp, and X (formerly twitter) may often divert students' attention from structured, immersive reading to fragmented and superficial consumption of information. In Social Studies, a subject that demands critical reading, analytical thinking, and the ability to interpret complex societal dynamics, this shift could pose unique challenges. The potential erosion of traditional reading habits associated with focus, comprehension, and deep learning may hinder students' ability to grasp core Social Studies concepts effectively. This issue is particularly critical for upper basic education students in Delta State, Nigeria, where the integration of traditional reading practices with digital tools is essential for achieving educational outcomes.

Despite the recognized benefits of traditional reading in fostering cognitive skills, such as memory retention, vocabulary growth, and critical reasoning, the addictive and time-consuming nature of social media use threatens these gains. Previous studies have established a correlation between sustained reading and academic excellence; however, limited research has explored how social media influences students' reading habits and their subsequent performance in Social Studies. This study, therefore, seeks to address the pressing question: How does social media use affect reading habits and academic performance among Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State?

Objectives of the study

1. Examine the influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in Upper Basic schools in Delta State.
2. determine the influence of social media usage on performance in Social Studies among Upper Basic schools students in Delta State.
3. determine the mean performance score of students taught Social Studies using social media and those not exposed to social media in Upper Basic schools in Delta State.

Research Questions

1. How does social media usage influence the reading habits of Social Studies students in Upper Basic schools in Delta State?
2. How does social media usage influence academic performance in Social Studies among students in Upper Basic schools in Delta State?

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3. What is the mean performance score of students taught Social Studies using social media compared to those not exposed to social media in Upper Basic schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in Upper Basic schools in Delta State.
2. There is no significant influence of social media usage on academic performance in Social Studies among students in Upper Basic schools in Delta State.
3. There is no significant difference in the performance of Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not in Upper Basic schools in Delta State.

Methodology

This research investigated the influence of social media on reading habits and performance in Social Studies among Upper Basic School students in Delta State, Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey research design, utilizing a well-structured questionnaire titled "Social Media Influence on Reading Habits and Performance Questionnaire" (SMIRHAPQ) for data collection. The instrument comprised two sections: the first gathered demographic information about the respondents, while the second included items on social media usage and its effects on reading habits and academic performance, with response options ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. The questionnaire was validated by two experts in educational research and two lecturers from the Department of Social Science Education, Delta State University, Abraka. Reliability was established through a pilot test conducted using the Cronbach Alpha method, which yielded a coefficient of 0.85, indicating high reliability. The study population consisted of 1,094 Upper Basic Class Two (JSS 2) Social Studies students, comprising 444 males and 650 females, enrolled during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta State. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select a representative sample of 300 students, including 120 males and 180 females, drawn from the three senatorial districts of the state. Data collection involved the administration of all 300 questionnaires, which were retrieved immediately by the researcher to ensure completeness. The data were analyzed using Chi-square and t-test statistical methods.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Table 1: Chi-square Analysis for the influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Variables	N	Df	Ls	Crit X2 value	Calc X2 value	decision
Social Media usage	324	2	0.05	5.991	132.074	Rejected
Reading habits						

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

The results in Table 1 indicate that the calculated Chi-square value of 132.074 is significantly higher than the critical Chi-square value of 5.991 at a 0.05 level of significance with 2 degrees of freedom. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State. This implies that social media usage significantly influences the reading habits of these students.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant influence of social media usage on academic performance in Social Studies among students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

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Table 2: Chi-square Analysis for the influence of social media usage on academic performance in Social Studies among students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Variables	N	Df	Ls	Crit X2 value	Calc X2 value	Decision
social media	324	2	0.05	5.991	47.501	Rejected
academic performance						

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

The results in Table 2 show that the calculated Chi-square value of 47.501 is significantly greater than the critical Chi-square value of 5.991 at a 0.05 level of significance with 2 degrees of freedom. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which posits that social media usage does not significantly influence academic performance in Social Studies among students, is rejected. This implies that social media usage has a significant influence on students' academic performance in Social Studies.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the academic performance of Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Table 3: t-test comparison of academic performance of Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not in upper basic schools in Delta State

Source of variation	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	T	P value
Students who do not use Social media frequently	14	188.64	14.789			
Students who use social Media frequently	164	129.31	21.802	176	1.569	0.118

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

The results in Table 3 indicate a comparison of academic performance between Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not. The mean score (\bar{x}) for students who do not frequently use social media is 188.64, with a standard deviation (SD) of 14.789, while the mean score for students who frequently use social media is 129.31, with a standard deviation of 21.802. The t-test value is 1.569 with a P-value of 0.118. Since the p-value (0.118) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, the difference in academic performance between the two groups is not statistically significant. This implies that frequent use of social media does not have a significant impact on the academic performance of Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Discussion of Findings

The Chi-square analysis in Table 1 indicates a significant influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in Upper basic schools in Delta State ($\chi^2 = 132.074$), ($p < 0.05$). This finding suggests that social media usage plays a critical role in shaping students' reading habits, potentially affecting their focus and engagement with academic materials. This finding agrees with Liu et.al (2023) who found that excessive use of social media platforms like Facebook reduces time spent on academic reading and can negatively impact reading efficiency and comprehension. Corroborating this view Benaicha and Benghalem (2024) reported that students who frequently use social media tend to allocate less time to academic activities, including reading, thereby diminishing their academic engagement. These results align with the hypothesis that social media introduces distractions that disrupt reading routines and time management, underscoring the importance of balanced media use among students.

The Chi-square analysis in Table 2 also reveals a significant influence of social media usage on academic performance in Social Studies ($\chi^2 = 46.500$), ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that the way students engage with social media affects their academic outcomes. This finding is supported by Sun and Chao (2024) who opined that the pervasive use of social media contributes to reduced concentration and academic achievement due to multitasking and decreased study time. This aligned with the view of Nabung (2024) who observed that while social media can facilitate learning through information sharing, excessive use often hinders academic performance by diverting attention from educational goals. The findings emphasized that

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while social media can be a useful educational tool, unregulated usage may adversely affect academic success, necessitating awareness programmes to promote its responsible use.

The t-test analysis shows no statistically significant difference in the academic performance of Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not ($t = 1.569$), ($p > 0.05$). The mean score of students who do not use social media frequently (188.64) is higher than those who do (129.31), but the difference is not enough to establish significance. This finding contradicts the views of Adeleke et.al (2024) who argued that while frequent social media use correlates with lower academic performance, other factors such as individual study habits and time management also play a critical role. They believed that students who do not use social media would perform better. Musa and Emmanuel (2017) noted that the relationship between social media and academic outcomes is nuanced, with potential benefits for students who use it for educational purposes but risks for those who primarily use it for entertainment while students who read through traditional means may also underperform due lack of focus.

Conclusion

The study reveals that social media usage significantly influences the reading habits of Social Studies students in Delta State, with excessive use leading to reduced engagement with academic materials. This finding underscores the importance of maintaining a balance in media use to preserve effective reading habits. Additionally, social media usage significantly impacts students' academic outcomes, highlighting its dual potential for educational engagement and hindrance to concentration and performance when unregulated. However, the analysis found no statistically significant difference in academic performance between frequent and infrequent users, suggesting that other factors, such as study habits and time management, play a more critical role.

Recommendations

1. Schools and educators should organize workshops and campaigns to educate students about the positive and negative impacts of social media on their academic life.
2. School authorities should include modules in the curriculum that teach students how to balance social media use with academic responsibilities effectively.
3. Parents should monitor and regulate their children's social media usage to minimize distractions and enhance their focus on academic activities.
4. Encourage the use of social media as a learning tool for collaborative activities, resource sharing, and educational content.
5. Schools should establish guidelines for the responsible use of social media, emphasizing its integration into academic purposes without compromising focus. Teachers should design engaging activities that compete with social media distractions, such as interactive lessons and group discussions.

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References

- Adekunjo, O. & Unuabor, S. (2024). Effect of Social Media on the Reading Culture of Selected Private Secondary School Students in Akinyele Local Government Area, Ibadan, Oyo State Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 10, 15-31.
- Adeleke, I. A., Owolabi, H. L., & Muraina, I. O. (2024). Social Media Usage and English Language Performance of Secondary Students in Ilorin, Kwara State. *Faculty of Natural and Applied Sciences Journal of Computing and Applications*, 2(1), 15-23.

Influence of Social Media ... (Onyekpe & Ossai, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15079855>

- Almusaed, A., Almssad, A., Yitmen, I., & Homod, R. Z. (2023). Enhancing Student Engagement: Harnessing AIED's Power in Hybrid Education-A Review Analysis. *Education Sciences*, 13(7), 632
- Ansari, J. A. N., Khan, N. A. (2020). Exploring the Role of Social Media in Collaborative Learning the New Domain of Learning. *Smart Learn. Environ.* 7, 9 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-020-00118-7>
- Benaicha, B., & Benghalem, B. (2024). Exploring the Impact of Social Media on EFL Reading Preferences and Habits. *Asian Journal of English Language Studies (AJELS)*, 12(1), 111.
- Erwin, K., & Mohammed, S. (2022). Digital literacy skills instruction and increased skills proficiency. *International Journal of Technology in Education and Science (IJTES)*, 6(2), 323-332. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijtes.364>
- Hou, Y., Qin, C., & Xu, P. (2024). Social Media Use and Academic Performance in Chinese Children and Adolescents: A Moderated Chain Mediation Model. *Behavioral Sciences*, 14(10), 867.
- Javeed, Aiman. (2023). Impact of Using Social Media on the Academic Performance A Case of College Going Students in Loralai Division. *Siazga Research Journal*. 2. 10.58341/srj.v2i1.12.
- Le, H. V., Nguyen, T. A. D., Le, D. H. N., Nguyen, P. U., & Nguyen, T. T. A. (2024). Unveiling Critical Reading Strategies and Challenges: A Mixed-Methods Study among English Major Students in a Vietnamese higher Education Institution. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), 2326732.
- Liu, Z., Hu, R., & Bi, X. (2023). The effects of social media addiction on reading practice: a survey of undergraduate students in China. *Journal of Documentation*, 79(3), 670-682
- Mosharrafa, R. A., Akther, T., & Siddique, F. K. (2024). Impact of Social Media Usage on Academic Performance of University Students: Mediating role of mental health under a cross-sectional study in Bangladesh. *Health science reports*, 7(1) <https://doi.org/10.1002/hsr2.1788>
- Musa, A. S., & Emmanuel, A. A. (2017). Influence of the social media on the reading culture of Nigerian students: a study of students in Kaduna Polytechnic. *Issues in language and literary studies*, 1(2).
- Nabung, A. (2024). Exploring the Impact of Culture Shock among Tertiary EFL Learners in Indonesia. *Asian Journal of Language, Literature and Culture Studies*, 7(2), 240-250.
- Osharive, P. (2015). Social media and academic performance of students in University of Lagos Undergraduate research Project, University of Lagos.
- Paige, D., & Rupley, W., & Ziglari, L (2024). Critical Thinking in Reading Comprehension: Fine Tuning the Simple View of Reading. *Education Sciences*. 14. 10.3390/educsci14030225.
- Peras, I., Klemenčič M. E., Japelj P. B., & Mekiš R. Ž (2023). Digital versus Paper Reading: A Systematic Literature Review on Contemporary Gaps according to Gender, Socioeconomic Status, and Rurality. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, 13(10), 1986-2005.
- Sivakumar, A., Jayasingh, S., & Shaik, S. (2023). Social Media Influence on Students' Knowledge Sharing and Learning: An Empirical Study. *Education Sciences*. 13, 745.
- Suci, W., Muslim, S., & Chaeruman, U. A. (2022). Use of Social Media for Collaborative Learning in Online Learning: A literature review. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 14(3), 3075–3086.
- Sun, W., & Chao, M. (2024). Exploring the influence of excessive social media use on academic performance through media multitasking and attention problems: a three-dimension usage perspective. *Education and Information Technologies*, 1-23

Influence of Supervision of Instruction ... (Maigari, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15079913>

Influence of Supervision of Instruction on Teachers'-Classroom-Productivity and Students' Academic-Achievement among Secondary Schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council

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Abstract

The study was carried out to investigate the perceived influence of supervision of classroom instruction on teachers' classroom performance and students' academic achievement in senior secondary school in Abuja Municipal Area Council. The purpose of the study was to find out the perceived influence of supervision of instruction on teachers' classroom productivity and students' achievement. One research questions and one corresponding null hypothesis guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 80 senior secondary school teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Abuja, with a sample size of 66 teachers selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. A 5-item structured question was the instrument for data collection. tagged "Supervision of Instruction and Teachers productivity Questionnaire" (SITPQ)). A test – retest method was used for reliability of the instrument at 0.05% level significant. The research questions were answered using mean scores and standard deviation. The findings revealed, among others, that supervision of instruction enable teachers to discover new abilities and qualities in teaching; that supervision of instruction enhances the provision of adequate instructional materials, teachers' productivity and students' academic achievement. Based on the findings the researcher concluded conferences and seminars organized by instructional supervisor's influence teachers' classroom productivity also to a great extent. and recommended, among others, that supervision should be carried out regularly, that more supervisors should be appointed, and that teachers should see supervisors as mentors.

Keyword: Teachers' Productivity, Supervision of Instruction, Classroom, Students Performance.

Introduction

Supervision of instructional is a continuous process that aims at improving teaching by providing needed services to teachers. Improving teaching is a complex process in which many elements should intermingle. Teachers are at the center of this enhancement process, their acceptance of instructional supervision and interaction with instructional supervisors provide the catalyst for any supervisory achievement. Supervision has its origin from the Latin word "Super video" meaning "to oversee" (Adenaike and Adebajo, 2016). Therefore, "Supervision can be seen as a way of advising, guiding, refreshing, cheering, stimulating, improving and administration certain groups with the hope of persuading people to desist from applying wrong procedures in carrying out certain functions on their jobs and at the same time try to emphasize the importance of good human relations in an organization". The traditional approach of supervision is a fault-finding approach, the supervisor goes to school to criticize and condemn teachers, not seeing anything good in them (Adenokun, 2011). Educational supervision is the process or act of seeing to it that the policies, principles and methods established for achieving the objectives of education are properly and successfully carried out (Akilaiya, 2014). This process involves using expert knowledge and experience to oversee, evaluate and cooperatively improve the conditions and methods of doing things connected with the teaching-learning problems in schools. The need to supervise the instructional process cannot be over emphasized; hence Ezeocha (2012) is of the view that most of the schools activities and all the school programmes require supervision. Supervision of instruction is a process of assisting the teachers to improve themselves and their instructional abilities so as to enhance effective teaching and learning (Akilaiya, 2014).

It is a service rendered to teachers which is directed towards controlling the quality of their classroom instruction. Supervision of instruction aims at identifying areas of work that need to be improved upon. Oraemesi (2012) is of the opinion that supervision of instruction is important for a number of reasons. To him; "the supervisee learns during supervision, since the supervisor is more knowledgeable, he corrects and advises the supervisee. This is done through friendly interaction. It also enhances personal professional growth of the teacher since interaction and greater knowledge gained at supervision promotes personal growth". Education has been known to be the antidote to poverty and ignorance and the key for unlocking natural resources (Obaji, 2006). Since education is accepted to be an instrument

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of change; teachers serve as the main operators of the instrument while the students are referred to as the raw materials to be processed on which the change would be manifested over a period of time (Adenaike and Adebajo, 2016).

In an attempt to ensure that the value of education is being derived at all levels, some officials are charged with the responsibility to monitor the performances of all those who run education especially those in schools in order to find out or assess the extent of achievement of the goals of education. These officials are the ones officially designated as supervisors. Consequently, due to high cost of education, stakeholders are becoming increasingly interested in the school system. They monitor the teachers and their wards' activities critically to ensure that adequate teaching and learning activities take place. Thus Parents Teachers Association monitors the activities within the school and constitutes part of the team involved directly in supervision. The school is an organization where the generality of the citizens have input and support. As a result, the whole society and designated supervisors are in the position to help improve the system generally (Barr 2011). The process of supervision is complex and it permeates the whole structure of the school system. There seems to be little or no area of operation within the school where the need for supervision would not arise, although this may be in diverse proportions. As Udoh, Akpa and Gaug (2014) opined, the crucial areas within the school system that require supervision are instructional and discipline areas where both the content, method or mode of delivery.

Supervision is one of the oldest form of educational leadership, its position is still one of the most controversial to the extent of it being used interchangeably with inspection especially in Nigeria. The implication is that most people still apply the principles of inspection as perceived during the colonial and early part of the postcolonial Nigeria. This has not improved instructional services nor has it led to professional growth of teachers, because it does not encourage collegiality or collegueship. Another problem of supervision of instruction in schools is the inadequacy of supervisory personnel. Ogbonnaya (2015) said there is insufficient number of supervisors in most states of Nigeria. He maintained that insufficient number of supervisory personnel has militated against effective supervision of instruction in secondary schools as the few available ones are unable to reach out to all the schools as expected within the supervisory period.

Another problem is lack of proper training of the supervisors. As recognized by Oraemesi (2012) and Ogbonnaya (2015), both shared the opinion that administrators of education in Nigeria do not consider proper training of supervisory staff to carry out supervisory services. Ogbonnaya maintained that the criteria for appointing supervisors are basically the possession of a first degree in education and some years of teaching experiences. He reiterated that some supervisors are also appointed simply because "they know some officers at the headquarters" this leads to the placement of "wrong pegs in right holes".

Educations have a set of aims and objectives to achieve, these aims and objectives of education are achieved through the process of teaching and learning. The attainments of these educational goals are learning outcomes. These learning outcomes can be seen as academic achievement. Learning outcomes has been variedly referred to in literature as academic achievement, Students' academic achievement tends to indicate their level of effectiveness, resourcefulness, ability and throughput both in current and future times (Ewumi, 2009). While stressing on students' academic achievement in the educational system, opined that academic achievement of students particularly at the technical college's level is not only a pointer to the effectiveness of schools but a main determinant of the future of youths in general.

Students' academic achievement shows the success of an educational endeavor, students' achievement appears to be the main vital factor by which the effectiveness and attainment of any process of teaching and learning can be judged, academic achievement is a fundamental criterion by which all teaching and learning activities are measured (Aremu, 2007). The measure for assessing students' level of academic achievement is through achievement tests, examinations, and observations (Ernest-Ehibudu & Oporum, 2013). Major goal of the school is to work towards attainment of academic excellence by students and school may have other marginal objectives; emphasis is always placed on the achievement of sound scholarship. Students' achievement tends to be the gauge of school productivity (Gurr, 2014). Almost all educational stakeholders place high value on academic achievement and thus excellent academic achievement of children is often the expectation of parents and other educational stake holders Alaka and Obadara, (2013). Possibly, this explains the purpose of academics, have been putting up efforts to find ways of enhancing students' academic achievements.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study was to find out influence of supervision on instruction of teacher's productivity and student' achievement in senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. Specifically seek to find out:

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1. To determine the Influence of effective supervision of classroom instruction on teachers’ productivity and students’ academic achievement among public senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Research Questions

The following research question guided this study:

1. What is the Influence of effective supervision of classroom instruction on in teachers’ productivity and students’ academic achievement among senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05% level of significance.

Ho₁ There is no significant difference between supervision of classroom instruction on teachers’ productivity and students’ academic Achievement among senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Methodology

The design of the study was survey research design, The population of the study included all the teachers in the four senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. Source: Statistical Division, Ministry of Education November 2024. And students results of the senior secondary in Abuja Municipal Area Council Sample and Sampling Technique A total of 66 samples (33 female teachers and 33 male teachers from 4 Senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council) was used for the study. Simple random sampling technique to select samples from the population of teachers. The justification for this sample size is for the researcher to be able to get a more reliable and accurate data. Questionnaire and students results (achievement) was the instruments for data collection. The instrument was titled “Influence of Effective Supervision of Instruction on Teachers’ Productivity Questionnaire (ISITPQ)” Analysis In analyzing the data, the researcher used mean and standard deviation to analyze research questions and t-test to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance The data analysis was done with reference to the one research question formulated to guide the study. The data was presented in tabular form showing percentage mean and standard deviation of the research question.

Presentation of Result

Research Question One

What is the Influence of effective supervision of classroom instruction on in teachers’ productivity and students’ academic achievement among senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the influence of effective supervision of classroom instruction on in teachers’ productivity and students’ academic achievement among senior secondary schools in Abuja municipal area council

S/N	Item	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
1	Interacting with a supervisor improve the productivity of the teachers.	66	3.21	0.79	Accepted
2	Interaction with supervisor scares some teachers.	66	1.76	0.93	Not Accepted
3	Interaction with supervisor makes teachers to look for more information on teaching subject(s).	66	3.24	0.79	Accepted
4	Interaction with my supervisor changes the attitude of teachers towards classroom instruction.	66	2.88	0.98	Accepted
5	Interaction with supervisor makes teachers discover new abilities and qualities for teaching and learning activities	66	3.31	0.81	Accepted

Source: Survey field work, 2024

In table 1, item 1 shows a mean of 3.21 (which falls between 2.50 and 3.49) and has a standard deviation of 0.79. Therefore, the decision level shows that the respondents to a great extent like Interacting with a supervisor improve the productivity of the teachers. Therefore, this item can be accepted. On the other hand, item 2 shows a mean of 1.76 (which falls between 1.50 and 2.49) and a standard deviation of 0.93. Therefore, the decision level shows that the respondents are of the opinion that

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Interaction with supervisor scares some teachers. So the item cannot be accepted because its mean falls below the criterion mean of 2.50. Item 3, depicts a mean of 3.24 (which falls between 2.50 and 3.49) and a standard deviation of 0.79. Therefore, the decision level shows that the respondents are of the opinion that Interaction with supervisor makes teachers to look for more information on teaching subject(s). Item 3 can therefore be accepted. Item 4 also shows a mean of 2.88 (which falls between 2.50 and 3.49) and a standard deviation of 0.98. The decision level shows that the respondents are of the opinion that Interaction with my supervisor changes the attitude of teachers towards classroom instruction. Therefore, the item can be accepted. Item 5 also shows a mean of 3.31 (which falls between 2.50 and 3.49) and a standard deviation of 0.81. Therefore, the decision level shows that the respondents are of the opinion that Interaction with supervisor makes teachers discover new abilities and qualities for teaching and learning activities. So, this item can be accepted. Based on the decision levels of the items research question one can be accepted.

Discussions of Findings

Teachers' classroom productivity is influenced by interaction with instructional supervisors. One implication of this finding is that interaction between teachers and instructional supervisors improves teachers' class instruction (Ogbonnaya 2015). This obviously has implications for the teaching profession, the students, the instructional supervisors, the society, and the nation. First, it means teaching was interesting for teachers and the time for instructional supervision will not be a time to panic or fidget but a time to always anticipate for because of the gains of such interactions on their teaching performance. This was also having a great effect on students' class performance which will make them develop their society and the nation at the long run.

The instructional supervisors will devote more time to such interaction because of the great influence it has on class instruction. Teachers' classroom productivity is influenced by the use of instructional materials suggested by instructional supervisors. This finding also has an implication in that it will help the FCT Ministry of Education see the necessity of providing teachers with instructional materials suggested by instructional supervisors. This will to a large extent reduce rate of improvisation of instructional materials by teachers and this will make students be well processed outputs. Teachers' classroom productivity is influenced by conferences and seminars organized by instructional supervisors for teachers. The implication is that it will make FCT State Ministry of Education rise up to the task of providing enough funds to organize seminars and conferences by instructional supervisors for teachers. Hence, improve the educational system of FCT and the nations at large.

Conclusion

Interaction with instructional supervisors influences to a great extent teachers' class performance. Instructional materials suggested by instructional supervisors influence to a great extent teachers' classroom performance. And conferences and seminars organized by instructional supervisor's influence teachers' classroom productivity also to a great extent. There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers with less teaching experience and teachers with more teaching experience with regards to influence of supervision of instruction on their class performance.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of this study, the conclusion drawn and its educational implications, the following recommendations are made:

1. The instructional supervisors in public senior secondary in Amac general having realized that the perception of teachers as regards influence of interaction with instructional supervisors on teachers' class productivity is positive, they should make it a point of duty to interact well with their supervisees. The instructional supervisors should always make themselves available and approachable to teachers.
2. The Post Primary School Management Board in Amac should always sensitize all instructional supervisors that they should perform their duties as helpers to teachers and not critics. That they should always be ready to assist teachers improve their teaching skills through their teamwork with teachers
3. Federal Capital Territory School Board should recruit more trained and qualified instructional supervisors to meet up with the. So that the existing few qualified instructional supervisors will not be overworked which will result to futility on their part.
4. Conferences and seminars be organized by instructional supervisors from time to time to cater for the professional assistance needed by teachers. Also, the FCT Ministry of Education should always finance effectively these conferences and seminars, since teachers believe these solve their professional problems.

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References

- Adenaike and Adebajo (2016). Principles of supervision. In Olowoye. Adenokun, A. (2011). Traditional and modern approaches to supervision in Nigeria. Adeyemo (2011) some aspects of School Management in Nigeria. Ibadan: Educational industries Limited.
- Akilaiya, O (2014). Educational Administration. Onitsha: Lincel Publishers. Akinade, (2001). Supervision for increased competence and productivity: Principles and practice. New York: Harper and Row Publishers.
- Akpa and Gaug (2014). Off the track: why and how successful executives get derailed. Greenboro, NC: Center for creative Leadership.
- Alaka and Obadara (2013) The Supervisory Grid. A practical guide to instructional supervisors in schools. Ibadan: Emia Publications.
- Amen (2007). (Eds), Management and Administration of Secondary Education. Owerri: Totan Publishers Ltd.
- Aremu (2011) (Eds), Management and Administration of Secondary Education. Owerri Totan Publishers Ltd.
- Barr (2011) Publications. International Journal of Educational Planning and Administration (2007). Vol. 1, no. 3
- Ernest, E and opurumi (2013) Clinical Supervision and teacher effectiveness in the Management Secondary Schools in Abia and Imo States. In International Journal of Educational and Administration, vol. 1, no. 3
- Ezeocha, P.A. (2012). Modern Supervision. Owerri: International University Press. Gagne R.M, (2007). the conditions of learning (3rd ed.). New York: Holt, Reinhart and Winston, Inc.
- Ewumi, (2009) (eds). Educational Administration and Supervision. Ibadan: Heineman Educational Books Nigeria Ltd.
- Gurr, D. (2014). From supervision to quality assurance n the case of the state of Victoria.
- Obaji (2006). (eds). Dynamics of Educational Administration and Management-The Nigerian perspective. Awka: Meks Publishers Ltd.
- Ogbannaya (2015) Supervision for increased competence and productivity: Principles and practice. New York: Harper and Row Publishers.
- Oraemesi U. (2012). Educational Administration: Theory and Practice. Owerri: Totan Publishers Ltd.
- Udoh, S.O., Akpa, G. and Gaug, K. (2014). Educational Administration in Nigeria: Theory and practice. Jos: Jos University Press Ltd.

Leveraging National...(Nkaanee & Brown, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080036>

Leveraging National Philosophy of Education through Value Re-Orientation among Secondary School Students in Nigeria: A Philosophical Approach

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Abstract

This study examined the leverage on National philosophy of education through value re-orientation among secondary school students in Nigeria using a philosophical approach. This study has been considered necessary because education is the pivotal force of growth and development in any given nation. The study employed philosophical method which entails prescribing, analyzing and speculating the need for a good educational value re-orientation in the Nigerian society. The insights gleaned from the study is that philosophy of education is based on full integration of the individual community. Similarly, the finding showed that the aim of the national policy on education in Nigeria with quite a number of value orientation statements as enshrined in the policy objectives are defeated as it affects the problem of implementation. It is also discovered that the aim of education has not answered what constitute the right type of values and society it has proposed. The study recommends that youths who are leaders of tomorrow should shun sharp practices or evil, but rather invest such time in acquiring sound education.

Keywords: Education, values re-orientation, society,

Introduction

Education is an indispensable tool for human development in the cognitive, affective, psycho-motive and psycho-productive domains. It is imperative to note that society cannot grow or develop without recourse to educational system, be it formal, informal, and non-formal. Every average individual pass through all of these knowingly or unknowingly. Amaele, Jerome & Abee (2011:5) maintains that education “involves a desirable change in human behaviour through the process of teaching and learning”. This underscores the fact that teaching and learning are as old as human’s existence. It follows that any human being who does not exhibit desirable behaviours from the point of view of the acceptable societal norms and values cannot be adjudged an educated person, even if he had passed through the four walls of an educational institution. A person’s behaviour determines the level of his education. This behaviour according to Amaele, et al, (2011) must conform to the desirable behaviour acceptable to the societal norms. Education therefore should produce a well cultured and meaningful person in- the society. Ijah (2010:50) equates education with light and illiteracy with darkness. Education to him, therefore, is a process of instilling and sharpening or modifying the attitudes, habits and behaviours of the individual for proper adjustment in the society. The level of ones’ education determines the extent of his development.

The purpose of this study is to focus on the role of educational values in Nigerian nation’s philosophy as it reflect in our societal norms and values. From the fore-going, our value system as enshrined in the National Policy on education has been relegated to the background. Values refer to the quality of being useful or important. It can also be seen as a belief in what is right and wrong and what is important in life (Hornby, 2009). In a more dimensional form, values are dispositions, beliefs and behaviours that are very useful by a particular society. Amaele (2007) sees values as standards of conduct, efficiency or worth which a society endorses, maintains and even transmits to her members in present and future generations. Therefore, it behoves that the very essential ingredients in the lives of individuals and nation is their value system. The lives of an individual, community and nation is sharpened and determined by value system which is in line with their national philosophy. The quality or nature of such nation’s philosophy depicts the lives of the citizens.

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Consequently, the Lack of proper educational values system has informed this work. The gap so far created needs to be filled for Nigerians to have a well cultured and valued educational system that will usher in a corrupt-free society. It has been a serious concern seeing our economic crumbling and poverty raiding quarters because of ineffective value system in the society. Lack of proper educational values system has informed this work. The gap so far created needs to be filled for Nigerians to have a well cultured and valued educational system that will usher in a corrupt-free society. It has been a serious concern seeing our economic crumbling and poverty raiding quarters because of ineffective value system in the society. A number of definitions have been proposed for the term ‘education’ by both sociologists and philosophers of education. However, etymologically, ‘education’ derives from the Latin word ‘educere’ meaning to lead out or pull out (Elechi and Ogbondah, 2006). Plato and other idealists believe that a given learner has some innate potentialities, which need to be squeezed out, pulled out, and expanded (Osaat, 2012). John Locke, a realist views ‘education’ as having its origin from the Latin word ‘educare’ meaning to train. In the view of John Locke, a learner’s mind needs training and filling with information and knowledge.

According to Ifeanacho (1998) education is the most recognized method by which a person acquires most of his ideas, beliefs, attitudes, skills and manners necessary not only to combat the hazards and problems of life, and to re-occurs the needs of life but also to fit into the company of humans. Enoh et al (1987) defines education as the aggregate of all the processes by which a child or young adult develops the abilities, attitudes, and other forms of behaviour which are of positive value to the society in which he/she lives. Emile Durkheim, in Okoh (2004), sees education as the systematic socialization of the younger generation by which the latter learns religions and moral beliefs, feelings of nationality and collective opinions of all kinds. The Advanced learner’s Dictionary of current English (2005) defines education as the systematic training and instruction designed to impact knowledge and develop skills.

Agabi and Okorosaye-Orubite (2005) see education as the process of acquiring knowledge and ideas that shape and condition man’s attitudes, actions and achievements. Ukeje adds that education in the process of developing the child’s moral, physical, emotional and intellectual powers for his contribution in social reform and the mastery of the laws of nature and their effective use for the welfare of members of the society. Hirst (1979) believe that educating people suggests a family of processes whose principle of unity is the development of desirable qualities in them. There desirable qualities are the values of the society.

Methodology

This study adopted a philosophical approach which entails; prescriptive, speculative and analytical processes. The data used for this study was gotten from both primary and secondary sources of information. Education has been defined as a concept, though with difficulties to apprehend. Yet, its puzzles cannot completely wipe, out the meaning of the concept. The questions that bordered so much on scholars’ mind is whether there is a Nigerian Education and if there is, what are its characteristics? (Amaele, 2010). This question does not undermine the fact that there existed educational system in Nigeria before the western oriented education which many critics mistake for a formal educational system in the country. Their argument depicts that it has no roots as well not embedded in, the existing culture of the indigenous society. However, we could not dismiss the argument completely because some features of western education are enshrined in the indigenous education. For clarification, we have about four Nigerian educational systems. This includes (a) the indigenous or traditional system of education (b) Islamic education (c) Western education and finally (d) Modern education.

The indigenous or traditional system of education is the transmission of skills, culture and knowledge orally from one generation to another. Amaele (2010) opined that it is the acculturation of the individual members of the community to acquire the necessary skills and wisdom to survive in the environment without foreign interference, while passing same from one generation to another. Okujagu and Wokocha (1999) view it as the education handed down to succeeding generations quite apart from the western style of education of the school system or the formal education of the koranic schools. The system does not have any particular place to learn or thought, rather it is done at any place, anywhere and anytime. The elders are teachers.

The Islamic Education is basically traceable to the Muslim of Northern Nigeria. The aim is to produce people that are specialists in the tenant of Islam. Wokocha and Okujagu (1999) postulate that its aim to turn out or prepare the children for adult life as Muslims, not just as a religion but to adopt it as a way of life. Muslims are

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always commanded to pursue and seek knowledge wherever knowledge is found. Islamic schools were established, blossomed and grew into large centres of high learning. Okoli, (2011) also views the aim of Islamic education as that which is based on religious education as the foundation of moral conduct and practical living. Just like the indigenous traditional education, Islamic education also aims at, the transmission of Islamic culture and maintains individual self-consciousness within the Islamic community. Their educational style is rooted in the Quran and the teaching and practices of their Noble prophet, Mohammed (Peace be Upon Him). Islamic education gained entrance into Northern part of Nigeria through Islamic traders from the Sahara Desert into Bornu and Hausa States in the 14th and 15th centuries (Okoli 2011). By the 19th century Usman Dan Fodio carried out his Jihad amongst the Hausa states in order to correct the ills and darts and to root out elements of ant-Islamic practice.

The Nigerian education today is an offshoot of Western education. It began with the missionary activities in the 16th century. Amaele observes that an earlier attempt to establish the faith and its education in Nigeria failed. The 19th century Missionaries of various Christian denominations arrived with a lasting introduction of Western formal education into Nigerian, which was later successful. However Islamic culture preceded that of its Western counterpart in Nigeria, but the latter has greater impact on the present Nigeria education. In fact, the indigenous and Islamic religions had already unique system of education. The interference of Christianity as a religion with education failed because they failed to study the cosmological foundations of the indigenous people (Amaele, 2010). They later regroup and began to send out another batch of missionaries that were result oriented. Such includes Mr & Mrs William de craft and Rev Thomas Birch Freeman in 1842 under the auspices of the Wesleyan Methodist Mission who arrived at Badagry and planted the first school. Rev Hope Waddel in 1946 who arrived Calabar established the Presbyterian Church Scotland Mission. Rev Ajayi Crowther and Rev S.C. Taylor in 1957 established Church Missionary work. Rev Fr. Joseph Shanahan arrived in Lagos and then Onitsha and established the Roman Catholic Mission (RCM). Rev. Thomas Bowen who arrived Ogbomosho for Missionary work (Okoli, 2011:60) and many others. All of them established schools which was basically formal education in Nigeria and was purely a Christian Missionary enterprise.

The Modern Education has an aspect of oral transmission just like the indigenous education. The teacher discusses, demonstrates and tries to practicalize topics and points. Okoli points out one of the aims of modern education as that which strives to enable the individual to be suitably and effectively fitted into society. She maintains that another aim of modern education is borrowed from indigenous educational scheme. It seeks to acquaint the child with modern ways of living successfully in the society. The modern education is predominantly invoked in the Nigerian educational system to day which will be discussed in the next topic. Modern education, therefore, has some inherent features of indigenous, Islamic and western education which serves as its bedrock.

Secondary School System of Education in Nigeria: Nigerian educational system is that given and obtained in the geographical entity called Nigeria. It is the educational system we received from the British government during the colonial period which ended on October 1, 1960. The Nigerian educational system comprises of the primary secondary and tertiary institutions of learning or schools. The primary school lasts for six years. Pupils are introduced to literacy and numeracy skills, morality, citizenship education, manipulative skills, ability to adapt to the environment and communicative skills. They learn arithmetic, verbal and quantitative reasoning, social studies, religious knowledge, basic science, music, history, fine creative arts, physical education, mathematics and cultural arts.

Originally, the secondary school lasted for five years. Students learnt mathematics, English language, fine Art, literature in English, Technical Drawing, Home Economic Business studies, Shorthand, Christian Religious Knowledge, French, Integrated science, music, etc up to form II. In form III, they learnt Geography, History, Physics, and Biology, chemistry, additional mathematics (now further mathematics), Economics, home management / foods and nutrition. In form IV students chose 8 subjects which they would sit for in the West African School Certificate/General Certificate of Education Examination held in May-June and October-November for school and private candidates respectively. Successful candidates then proceeded to Sixth Form, which lasted for two years (Lower Sixth Form and Upper Sixth Form). At this level, students were prepared for the Higher school certificate (HSC) and General Certificate of Education (Advanced level) in both science and art subjects. For instance, we had such combinations as physics/chemistry/Biology; physics/chemistry/mathematics; physics/Geography/mathematics; Religious knowledge/History/ Economics;

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History/Economics/Geography; Mathematics/Geography/Economics, etc. Successful candidates were admitted by Direct Entry mode of study leading to the award of a degree.

With the introduction of the 6-3-3-4 system of education in 1987/88 session, the secondary school duration increased to six years. It was divided into junior secondary school and senior secondary school, each lasting three (3) years. Vocational subjects were introduced in the junior secondary section. There are introductory Technology, Electronics, mechanics, Building Technology, commentary and Joinery, computer Education, woodwork, etc. At the senior secondary level, students offer physics, chemistry, biology, economics, geography, history, further mathematics, mechanical and building drawing Nigerian language agricultural science, literature in English, music, French, English language, general mathematics, civics education, marketing, salesmanship, foods and nutrition/home management, etc. Candidates who succeed at the WAEC or NECO senior School Certificate Examination enter the university, polytechnic or college of Education through the University Joint matriculation and Admission matriculation Examination (UTME). In fact, the secondary school prepares us for useful life within the society and for higher education (NPE, 1981, 2004). Again, secondary education dictates the pace of learning at the primary and tertiary levels (Orake, 2004).

Tertiary education is the one received at the polytechnics, colleges of Education, schools of Health and Technology schools and Nursing, universities, research institutes and other related schools. Jaja (2013) views higher education as the Western type of education which is organized after college of Education. She adds that there are rules and regulations formulated and administered by the ministries of education to guide the type of building facilities, equipment and entry requirements. Idogho (2011) sees higher education is that which develops individuals mentally, morally and physically and to confer degrees on their products who are fund worthy in character and learning, to enable them assume leadership roles in their immediate and extended societies. The federal government of Nigeria (2004) sees higher education as that which provides quality education for her products so that they can assume leadership positions in their immediate and external communities.

The Nigerian Society

According to Spencer and Inkeles (1985), society is a group with a culture organized for the satisfaction of all human needs and 'interests. They add that the society consists of the people; their culture is what they have, what they do, and how they think together, culture is a way of life shared by a group, a system of ideas, beliefs, values, knowledge, and customs transmitted from one generation to another (Spencer and Inkeles, 1985:53). It is produced by a society; in turn, a society depends in its culture. There can be no culture without society and vice versa. The Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary of Current English (2015) defines society as people in general living in communities. Secondly, it is a particular community of people who share the same customs, laws, etc. Thirdly, it is a group of people who join together for a particular purpose. Finally, it is a group of people in a country who are fashionable, rich and powerful.

Role of Educational Values in Nigeria National Philosophy of Education

Before examining the role of educational values in the Nigeria National philosophy of Education, let us first conceptualize the key words; role, morality, values and philosophy of education. Let us then take them one after the other. Sociologically, role is defined as the dynamic aspect of one's states, the way one acts out one's status. A role is defined in connection with other complementary roles. For example, the role of a teacher complements that of a pupil in the same way that of a patient complement that of a doctor, and so on (Spencer & Inkeles, 1985). The Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary of current English (2015) defines role as the function or position that somebody has or is expected to have in an organization.

Morality is the group of principles concerning right and wrong or good and bad behaviour. It is also defined as the degree to which something is good or bad, right or wrong. The term 'morality derives from the adjective 'moral' which is used to modify something concerning wrong or right behavior (opp cited). Then, "Values" are beliefs about what is wrong or right. This is why we have moral values in our society to guide our behaviours. Both morality and values are to be considered in the National Philosophy of Education for any country. This is because educational philosophy must be based on the needs of members of the society with respect to social, political, economic moral and cultural development. This is to say that every philosophy of education must aim at national development and the sustainability of its educational system. For example, the philosophy of

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education for the United States depends on pragmatism while that of the United Kingdom is based on idealism (Osaat, 2010).

The National Philosophy of Education in Nigeria as formulated by the Federal Government of Nigeria (2004: 32) has the following objectives;

14. The building of a free and democratic society
15. The building of a just and egalitarian society
16. The building of a united, strong and self-reliant nation
17. The building of a great and dynamic economy
18. The building of a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens.

Based on the objectives of the Nigeria National Philosophy of Education, the quality of instruction at all levels of education should be geared towards the instilling of the following values;

1. Respect for the worth and dignity of individuals
2. Faith in man's ability to make rational decisions, moral and spiritual values in inter-personal and human relations
3. Shared responsibility for the common good of the society.
4. Respect for the dignity of labour
5. And the promotion of emotional physical and psychological health of all children. (Osaat, 2010).

Certainly, certain things are not included in the sufficiency and relevance of the Nigerian philosophy of Education. There are no clarity of concepts and statement of aim, goals and objectives; ineffective implementation of the stated objectives, and the provision of guidance to the citizens and value system in the country. The concepts are not clear and the implementation is almost impossible. Again, the purpose of inculcation of moral values is defeated in this era of cultism, militancy, terrorism, human rights violation, high level of corruption, violation of distributive justice and absence of a just and egalitarian society. Aminigo (1999), in Nsirim believe that:

Moral education develops and sustains in the child interest and good attitude to morality, understand public morality, promotion of the understanding and commitment to intellectual norms and ability to make sound and independent moral judgment and the promotion of morality or behaviour.

Again, Ogbondah (2006), claims that all schools must reflect and encourage the acceptance of the argument on moral practices and values that are indispensable for the human quality of life in our society. According to him, the core values of social morality include honesty, truth, cooperation, respect for others, etc. He adds that moral education can be achieved through religion, literature, history, music, social studies, games, civics, etc. Again, he affirms that ethical or moral teaching focuses on authority, tolerance, sportsmanship, charity, duty, honesty, standards, right and wrong, etc. Elechi and Ogbondah (2006) also believe that a functional education must be based on morality and the relationship between members of the society. Accordingly, Uriah says the following with respect to moral education in our school curriculum:

A functional education must have moral values which reflect human relationship, that is, man's conduct towards other men. The examples of moral values are honesty, brotherhood, neighborliness, justice, equity and freedom; (Uriah in Elechi&Ogbondah, 2006:48).

Anikpo (2005:19) writing about value system and its effects on Nigerian education system reports that:

Our universities can no longer guarantee that necessary peace of mind for the student in her hall, the researcher in the library, the scientist in the laboratory, the philosopher under the tree. Nowhere in our once serene campus can poets now afford to stand and share. And this, the epidemic noise of nonsense, the loud crusades of evangelical groups who have turned students' hostels, classrooms, staff quarters, and virtually every open space on campus into screaming area for revivals and miracles.

From the above assertion, Osundare believes that the idea of morality has clipped us in the Nigeria university campuses since laws of morality are neglected and negated by fellow members of the education system.

Osaat and Omordu (2011) argue that "the Nigerian education system has suffered a lot of setbacks as a result of immorality. This is because, according to them, the high rate of immorality has affected the country's education in the following ways:

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In the universal primary education scheme for which the sum of N636.03 million was allocated for the construction of 150,955 classrooms during the 1975.80 third National Development plan, only 63,000 classrooms were completed and yet, an additional N120,000,000 was incurred at the end of the plan period (political Bureau Report, 1989:66).

Value System and Value Re-orientation

Philosophy of Education is relevant or necessary in national value re-orientation. This is so because education is noted for the preparations of the citizens for meaningful existence and development. Values determined the intellectual norms and identity of a society. Value therefore is defined as those objects which human beings cherish, appreciate, want, desire or need as to achieve the goal of healthy living in pursuit of happiness (Isichei, 2000). To the psychologists, values are desirable which influence selective behaviour independent of specific situations (Francis Isichei & Stephen Bolaji, 2010). They maintain that value is something that a person prizes and cherishes, something that someone chooses freely from alternative after considering the consequences of those alternatives and causes a person to act or refrain from acting. Values are dynamic according to its peculiarities. Human life begins from childhoods to adolescents where ideals and values are acquired with a unique educational period with the enhancement of a more relevance stand of philosophy of education in value system.

Society cannot exist without the principles or norms for moral behaviours which are values. In the life of humans, there are ideal of what is right and wrong in quest to pursuit happiness as values. Therefore, whenever the ethical norms are considered as a major objective of education, then we have a philosophy of education for moral behaviour. To this extent, education seems to be moral because the end result of all teachings is to complete the moral growth of a child and impart into the child the moral ideas of the society or nation. Schools cannot be value-free, whereas every nation must have it ethical norms with a share set of values to guide her children adapt to what they have been taught in schools or in the society. Such includes honesty, truthfulness, peace, love, freedom, tolerance, respect, cooperation, happiness etc. Children develop in morals and intellectual lives. This is in tandem with Nigerians as stipulated in her national policy on education (2014) on all levels of Nigeria educational system to be oriented towards inculcating the values into the lives of her citizens.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from this study showed that it is imperative that moral values be contained in a country's philosophy of Education. Right from Antiquity, philosophers of education ensured that moral education was incorporated into the curriculum of primary and secondary schools. As a result, the Nigeria National philosophy on Education aims at building (1) a free and democratic society, (2) a just and egalitarian state, (3) a united, strong and reliable nation, (4) a great and dynamic economy, and (5) a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens. Based on the above national goals the National policy on Education aims to instil the following educational values into the children:

23. Respect for the worth and dignity of individuals
24. Faith in man's ability to make rational decisions, moral and spiritual values in interpersonal and human relations.
25. Shared responsibility for the common good of the society.
26. Respect for the dignity of labour and the promotion of the emotional, physical and psychological growth of children.

The study further revealed that value plays a vital role in human life and this depends on the importance that is attached to it. Values are conducts, life styles, beliefs, dispositions, etc that people of a particular society cherished. This implies that not every valued life system is universal or applicable to all societies in the world. What is good or wrong in one society might not be so in the other society. However, by implication and importance educational values seem to be universal. Therefore, the quality or nature of the nation's philosophy is directed to the quality of life of her citizens which Nigeria is no exception.

The finding also reveals that the National Policy on Education in Nigeria had provided series of number of value-oriented statements enshrined in the first section of the policy. This policy sets certain objectives for the nation (Nigeria) and the nation's education such as;

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4. Development of the individual into morally sound patriotic and effective citizens
5. Total integration of the individual into the immediate community, the Nigeria society and the world
6. Provision of equal access to qualitative educational opportunities for all citizens at all levels within and outside, the formal school system
7. Inculcation of national consciousness, values and national unity.

Development of appropriate skills, mental physical and social abilities and competences to empower the society (FRN, 2004.4).

Recommendations

The study therefore recommends the following:

8. Educationists should take up the responsibility of providing pure and true knowledge to the youth as they live exemplary lives worthy of emulations.
9. Every profession comes with an ethics and the youth must not only keep the ethics but also influence the society to build a life oriented towards values and ethics.

References

- aAmaele, S. (2007). Reforms, quality and Moral values in the Nigerian education system. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Philosophy*.
- Amaele, S. (2010). *Moral and Religious values in Nigeria Education. Issues and Problems and prospects*. Port Harcourt Harey Publication Company.
- Amaele, S, Jerome I. Wosu&Abee N. Ejire (2011) *History of Education, from ancient to the Contemporary Era. The Global and Nigeria Perspectives*. Harey Publications Coy Port Harcourt.
- Aminigo, I.M. (1999). *A Direct introduction to Educational Philosophy*. Nigeria Hanging Gardens publishers.
- Anikpo, M. (2005). *Repositioning Education in Nigeria. A lead paper presented at the 4th Annual conference of the National Association for Research Development held at the University of Port Harcourt 15th-19th August.*
- Elechi, G.E. &Ogbondah, L. (2006), *Moral and Religious Education for Colleges and Universities*, Port Harcourt: Tower gate Resources Publishers Ltd.
- Francis Isichei & Stephen, Bolaji (2010) *Relevance of Philosophy of Education to National value re-orientation: Nigerian Journal of Educational philosophy*. Philosophy of Education Association of Nigeria.
- Hist, P.H. (1979) *Moral Education in a secular society*. London: Hoelden and Stoughton.
- Hornby, T.G. (2009) *Rebranding of Nigeria Launched*. [http://www.voices of Africa](http://www.voicesofafrica.com/site/rebrandingofnigeria)ew.com/site/rebranding of Nigeria.
- Elechi, G.E. &Ogbondah, L. (2006), *Moral and Religious Education for Colleges and Universities*, Port Harcourt: Tower gate Resources Publishers Ltd.
- Enoh, C. et al (1987). *Handbook of Educational Foundations*, Jos: Challenge press Ltd.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). *National Policy on Education* Yaba Lagos; NERDC press page 7.
- Idogho, P.O. (2011). *Higher Education in Nigeria and the challenges ahead*. In *European Journal of Education Studies* 3 (2).
- Ifeanacho, M.I. (1998). *The Nigerian Culture: An Institutional Approach*; Owerri: Springfield publishers Ltd.
- Isichei, F.M (2000) *Value Education for children and sources of value in society*. *Education today and tomorrow*. January.
- Jaja, J.M. (2013). *Higher Education in Nigerian: The Gains and burdens in Global Journal of Human Social Science* Vol. 13, Issue, 14, Version 1.
- Okoli, N.J. (2011). *History of Education: An overview* University of Port Harcourt.
- Osaat, S.D. & Ekwe, E.I. (2012). *Moral Education and its implications for challenges of Youth Restiveness and Evidence in Nigeria*. In Osaat S.D. (2012) (ed) *Contemporary issues in Nigeria Education*. Port Harcourt Sabaco publishers.
- Osaat, S.D. &Omordu C. (2011). *Evaluation of value system and its effects on Nigeria Education: A Philosophical Approach*. In *International Multichip linary Journal, Ethiopia* vol. 5. Page 92.
- Wokocho, A.M &Okujagu T.N. (1999) *philosophy of Education and some Contemporary issues and problems in Nigeria education* Port Harcourt amethyst and colleagues Publishers.

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Mastery-Of- Subject-Matter and Choice of Instructional Strategy as Correlates of Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Taraba State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explored physics teachers' mastery of subject matter and instructional strategies as correlate to students' academic achievement in Taraba state, Nigeria. Two research questions were raised and two hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study was 17,210 respondents comprised of 84 physics teachers and 17,126 SSIII physics students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Taraba state. A sample size of 460, made up of 69 physics teachers and 391 SSIII physics students of private and public senior secondary schools in Taraba state were selected using purposive and simple random sampling techniques. The instruments used for data collection were Physics Teachers' Knowledge of Subject Matter (Content) Test (PTKSMT), Physics Teachers' Knowledge of Instructional Strategies Questionnaire (PTKISQ) and Physics Achievement Proforma (PAP), with reliability coefficients of 0.79 for (PTKSMT) computed using K-R₂₀ and 0.77 for (PTKISQ) computed using Cronbach alpha. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested using regression analysis at 0.05 significance level. The study generated the following findings: (i) among others revealed that there is a significant relationship between physics teachers' knowledge of the subject matter and students' academic achievement in Taraba state with [F(1, 68) = 164.544, P < 0.05)] and (ii) there is a significant relationship between physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies and senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Taraba state with [F (1, 390) = 179.994, p < 0.05)]. The study concludes that physics teachers' knowledge of the subject matter, physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies and students' academic achievement are positively related. The study recommended among others that Physics teachers content knowledge should be improved through teacher's constant training and re-training on content knowledge.

Keywords. Teachers Mastery, Subject Matter, Instructional Strategies, Academic achievement

Introduction

Science is universally recognized as the foundation of technological development worldwide. In today's modern world, every aspect of life depends on science, and nations, particularly developing countries like Nigeria, are striving to advance technologically and scientifically. It is well understood that any nation aspiring for greatness and development must heavily invest in science education (Ogunsanya & Otedola, 2018). Developed countries such as Germany, China, the United States of America (USA), Japan, the United Kingdom, Russia, and France have gained global recognition and superpower status due to their strong commitment to science education and research (Otache, 2021). Therefore, science education is crucial for any country aiming to achieve sustainable development and compete in the global arena. Among the various branches of science, physics stands out due to its critical role in scientific and technological advancements (Adegoke, 2017). Physics, as one of the major science subjects, plays an important role in the scientific and technological development of the world. It comprises the study of matter, energy, and their interactions. Physics has an important impact on the average person's daily life because it

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helps us to understand various natural phenomena that are embedded in reality. Physics plays a role in nearly every daily activity we perform, such as walking, cutting, watching, and opening or closing things. Many electronic gadgets utilized in homes, schools, industries, hospitals, and even around the entire globe came as a result of ideas, theories, principles, and laws of physics. There is no doubt that, Physics as a branch of science played an indispensable role in the economic development of the world. Yusuf, Omosewo, Akanbi, Mohammed, Badmus, and Usman (2021) affirmed that physics is the basis for most modern technology, tools and instruments used in scientific research development. It provides quantitative and qualitative skills needed for analyzing data and solving problems in sciences, engineering and medicine, as well as in economics, finance, management, law and public policy. Therefore, it is crucial to ensure that students gain high levels of academic achievement in physics.

Despite the significant role of physics and its recognition in science education, its remains a subject in which senior secondary school students in Nigeria continue to perform below the standard benchmark. Education stakeholders, particularly those in the science field, have expressed deep concerns about this situation (Shamim, Tabasum, & Rashid, 2013). Furthermore, Mukama (2019) reported that there is a decline in the number of students enrolled in physics and their academic achievement in schools has consistently been poor over the years. This concerning trend is observable in external examinations such as the West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO). The West African Examination Council (WAEC) conducted a seven-year analysis of physics students' results from 2016 to 2022 in Taraba State, Nigeria presented in Table 1. In 2016, the failure rate was 55.49%, 57.19% in 2017, 45.75% in 2018, 50.19% in 2019, 55.35% in 2020, 49.22% in 2021, and 49.83% in 2022 (Taraba State Ministry of Education, Research and Statistics Department, 2023).

Table 1: WAEC Results in Physics in Taraba State from 2016 TO 2022

Year	Pass Rate (%) at A1 - C6	Failure Rate (%)
2016	44.51%	55.49%
2017	42.81%	57.19%
2018	54.25%	45.75%
2019	49.81%	50.19%
2020	44.65%	55.35%
2021	50.78%	49.22%
2022	50.17%	49.83%

Despite the fluctuations in the results, all the failure rates are notably high, with none falling below 45%. This suggests a persistent problem of academic achievement in physics among students in Taraba State. This trend of poor academic achievement of physics students in Taraba State may be attributed to the lack of physics teachers' mastery of subject matter and instructional strategies. Academic achievement refers to individuals' success and performance in educational endeavors. It is a crucial indicator of students' understanding and proficiency in teaching and learning a subject. In the context of physics, academic achievement involves students' success and performance in studying and understanding the principles, theories, and application of physics. According to Filgona, Sakiyo, and Gwany (2020), academic achievement is determined by students' test scores, representing the outcome of education and indicating how well students perform in a specific area of study. However, achieving high academic performance is influenced by various factors, which include not only the students' efforts and abilities but also the roles and contributions of teachers, parents, and educational policies.

Odumosu, Olisama, and Fasayo (2018) affirmed that various stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and the Ministry of Education, contributed to the significant decline in academic achievement among physics students in secondary schools based on their related factors. However, Kimani, Kara, and Njagi (2014) submitted that teacher-related factors contributing to poor academic achievement include negative attitudes towards work, ineffective teaching methods, insufficient pedagogical content knowledge, inadequate teacher evaluations, lack of qualifications, and poor rapport with students. Consequently, Tsholofelo and Maree (2021) highlighted student-related factors contributing to poor academic achievement as negative attitudes towards learning, socioeconomic backgrounds, misunderstanding of the content being taught, ineffective study habits, knowledge of the subject matter and poor physical well-being. These combined factors create significant challenges to academic success in subjects such as physics.

Mastery of subject matter refers to teachers' deep understanding of the content they aim to teach or have prepared to impart to students (Hernboom & Mazaring, 2021). It includes knowing the subject's key concepts, theories, laws, principles, its underlying structure, and applications in teaching the subject. For example, if a physics teacher plans to teach students how

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to calculate velocity, then velocity becomes the subject matter (Lumantao, 2022). This means teachers' knowledge of the subject matter may have effect on students' academic achievement. According to Jobeen (2014), teachers with a thorough grasp of their subject can provide clear and accurate explanations, this helps students to grasp complex concepts more easily, reducing confusion and misunderstandings. In recent research done by Denbel (2023) found that the overall subject matter knowledge competency of the teachers has significance influence on students' academic achievement of senior secondary schools in republic of Indonesia. In addition, Olasehinde, Williams, Yahaya and Owolabi (2018) reported that pedagogical and subject content knowledge of teachers were found to be significant predictors of students' academic achievement. However, Gulled (2021) discovered that teacher subject matter knowledge has no effect on students' academic success in Hargeisa district public secondary schools. Based on these conflicting results from different researchers it becomes imperative to study this sub variable more.

Mastery of instructional strategies is a fundamental component of effective teaching (Francisco & Celon, 2020). This knowledge can help educators to deliver lessons effectively and capture students' attention during the learning process. Baafi (2020) defined instructional strategies as various techniques, methods, approaches, and tools that teachers use to facilitate teaching and learning. This aspect of Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) can significantly influence students' academic achievement, as evidenced by several researchers. According to Amos, Folasayo, and Oluwatoyin (2015), teachers who are proficient in various instructional strategies can use different methods to keep lessons interesting and engaging. For example, incorporating interactive activities, discussions, and multimedia makes learning more dynamic and enjoyable for students. These varied approaches not only capture students' attention but also cater to different learning styles, making it easier for students to understand and retain complex concepts.

Freeman, Eddy, McDonough, Smith, Okoroafor, Jordt, and Wenderoth (2014) affirmed that active instructional strategies, which involve students' hands-on activities and collaborative projects, significantly improve student performance in science. In the same vein, Sarfraz, Vladut, Cioca and Ivascu (2022) found that motivational and instructional strategies significantly affect the self-efficacy of teachers and the academic performance of students. However, Ida and Calmer (2015) reported that a student-centered instructional strategy has a negative impact on academic achievement in general. While some studies, affirmed that active and motivational instructional strategies significantly improve student performance, others reported negative impacts from student-centered methods on students' academic achievement. Therefore, the sub variable needs further investigation to understand this nuance. The findings from this study revealed that most of the teachers' methods of teaching have a great effect on students' academic performance; based on these findings, Student-Centered Method and Teacher-Student Interactive Method were recommended in order to improve students' academic performance. Isa and Bala (2022) revealed that most teachers' methods of teaching have a great effect on students' academic performance. Considering the fact that some studies have established that pedagogical content knowledge influences students' academic achievement, while others have found no such correlation, further investigation is necessary to determine the extent to which physics teacher's pedagogical content knowledge relate with students' academic achievement of senior secondary school in Taraba State.

Statement of the Research Problem

In an ideal situation, students studying physics in senior secondary schools in Taraba state would consistently achieve academic success with at least a credit pass in physics. Physics as a fundamental subject would serves as a gateway to numerous promising prospects leading to admission into university and other tertiary institutions to study courses such as medicine, pharmacy, engineering among others. However, despite concerted efforts by scholars and educators, poor academic achievement in physics persists among senior secondary school students in Taraba state with an average percentage failure rate of 51.86% recorded from 2016 to 2022. In addition, students consistently performed below expected standards, indicating a significant gap in their understanding of physics concepts. Various factors, such as teacher qualifications, classroom conditions, instructional resources, and student attitudes towards learning physics, have been implicated in contributing to this issue. Nevertheless, factors that may be contributing to poor academic achievement in Taraba state could be lack of physics teachers' mastery of subject matter and instructional strategies. Students may struggle to grasp physics concepts due to ineffective teaching and lack of depth in teachers' understanding of both the subject matter and how to use appropriate teaching strategies. To address the persistent problem of poor academic achievement in physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba state, this study investigated the correlation between physics teachers' mastery of subject matter, instructional strategies and students' academic achievement.

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Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between physics teachers' mastery of subject matter, instructional strategies and students' academic achievement in Taraba state, Nigeria. Specifically, the study determined the:

1. Relationship between Physics teachers' mastery of subject matter (content) and academic achievement among senior secondary school students in Taraba state.
2. Relationship between physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies and academic achievement among senior secondary school students in Taraba state.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions.

1. What is the extent of mean score achievement of Physics teachers' mastery of subject matter among senior secondary schools in Taraba state?
2. What is the response level of physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies among senior secondary schools in Taraba state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' knowledge of subject matter and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary schools students in Taraba state

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' mastery of instructional strategies and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary schools students in Taraba state

Methodology

The study employed correlational survey research design in determining the relationship between physics teachers' knowledge of subject matter, instructional strategies and students' academic achievement. The population of the study consists of 17,210 physics teachers and students. This includes 84 physics teachers and 17,126 SSIII physics students 2023/2024 academic section from both private and public science secondary schools in Taraba state. The sample size for the study comprised 460. This includes 69 physics teachers and 391 SSIII physics students of private and public senior secondary schools in Taraba state. Purposive, stratified and random sampling was used to draw the sample for physics teachers and physics students in each education zone. Purposive sampling technique was used to select schools from the 10 education zones based on the availability of physics teachers. Three instruments were used for data collection. The instruments include Physics Teachers' Knowledge of Subject Matter (Content) Test (PTKSMT), Physics Teachers' Knowledge of Instructional Strategies Questionnaire (PTKISQ) and Physics Achievement Proforma (PAP). PTKSMT contains 50 items multiple-choice objectives test with four options (A-D) covering senior secondary school Physics curriculum. The 50 items were drawn from past WAEC questions (2015-2022). Each correctly answered item scored 1 mark making the total of 50 marks. For physics teacher's knowledge of instructional strategies questionnaire PTKISQ, the instrument was adapted from Yusuf et al. (2021). The items were slightly modified based on the inputs of the validators to suit the purpose of this study.

Three experts participated in the Content Validation of Physics Teachers' Knowledge of Subject Matter (content) Test (PTKSMT). These experts represented distinct perspectives, with one from the Physics Department Moddibo Adama University, Yola, another from the Department of Physical Sciences Education in the same university, and a third from Taraba State University Demonstration Secondary School, Jalingo. The reliability of the Physics Teacher's Knowledge of Subject Matter Test was assessed using the Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-R₂₀) coefficient, resulting in a reliability coefficient of 0.79. For physics teacher's knowledge of instructional strategies questionnaire PTKISQ the reliability analysis through Cronbach alpha statistical tool, yielding a commendable score of 0.77. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. Where linear regression was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. If the P-Value is less than 0.05 the null hypotheses was rejected, otherwise do not reject the hypotheses.

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Presentation of Results

Research Question One

What is the extent of mean score achievement of Physics teachers' mastery of subject matter among senior secondary schools in Taraba state?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Physics Teachers' mastery of Subject Matter in Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

Variable	N	Mean	S. D
Physics teachers' knowledge of Subject matter	69	35.72	5.21

Key: n= Number of participants, S.D = Standard deviation

Table 1 shows that the mean score for physics teachers' knowledge of subject matter in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is 35.72 and standard deviation is 5.21. This indicates that physics teachers' knowledge of subject matter in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is generally low. On average, their subject matter knowledge level is insufficient to meet the minimum required standard, as indicated by the failure grade (F9).

Research Question Two

What is the Response level of physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies among senior secondary schools in Taraba State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of Physics Teachers' Mastery of Instructional Strategies in Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

S/N	Item (n = 391)	Mean	S. D	Remark
1	I easily understand the solutions my teacher provides on physics problems in class	4.40	1.53	HL
2	My teacher often uses diagrams to help us understand what he is teaching in physics.	3.44	1.37	ML
3	Physics teacher uses practical examples to teach physics concepts in my school.	3.32	1.42	ML
4	Physics teacher in my school conducts experiments to deepen our understanding of scientific principles	4.33	1.43	HL
5	Physics teacher in my school used to break down physics calculations into simple steps for easy understanding.	3.36	1.41	ML
6	Physics teacher in my school tells stories to help us remember key discoveries made by scientists.	3.37	1.44	ML
7	My teacher uses different ways to explain physics concepts.	3.27	1.46	ML
8	Physics teacher engages students in solving problems during lessons.	2.13	1.52	LL
9	Physics teacher used to create room for every student to participate in the class when teaching.	3.30	1.53	ML
Grand Mean		3.44	1.46	ML

Key: n= Number of participants, HL= High Level, ML=Moderate Level, LL= Low Level, S.D = Standard deviation.

Table 2 shows that the grand mean for the level of physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is 3.44, with a standard deviation of 1.46. The mean falls into the real limit of 2.50–3.49 (Moderate Level). This indicates that the level of physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is moderate.

Hypothesis One

There is no Significant Relationship between Physics Teachers' Mastery of Subject Matter and Academic Achievement in Physics among Senior Secondary Schools students in Taraba State

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Table 3: Summary of ANOVA results of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers’ Mastery of Subject Matter and Students’ Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	876.728	1	876.728	164.544	.000 ^b
	Residual	356.991	68	5.328		
	Total	1233.719	69			

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ academic achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers’ knowledge of Subject matter

The result in Table 3 reveals that there is a significant relationship between Physics teachers’ mastery of subject matter and students’ academic achievement of senior secondary schools in Taraba state with $[F(1, 68) = 164.544, p < 0.05]$. Since the computed p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant relationship between Physics teachers’ mastery of subject matter and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary schools students in Taraba state.

Table 4: Model Summary of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers’ Mastery of Subject Matter and Students’ Academic Achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.843 ^a	.711	.706	2.30830

a. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers’ knowledge of Subject matter

The result in Tables 4 indicates a model summary of how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The result shows there is a significant positive relationship between Physics teachers’ mastery of subject matter and students’ academic achievement with $R=0.843$ and the adjusted R-square value (.706) indicates that 70.6% of the variance in students' academic achievement is explained by physics teachers' mastery of subject matter.

Table 5: Beta Coefficient of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers’ Mastery of Subject Matter and Students’ Academic Achievement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	-1.872	1.938		-.966	.338
	Physics teachers’ knowledge of	.689	.054	.843	12.827	.000
	Subject matter					

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ academic achievement

The result in Table 5 reveals the Beta coefficient of regression analysis. It reveals a significant beta coefficient of 0.843, $p < 0.05$. This indicates that physics teachers' mastery of the subject matter has a strong positive impact on students' academic achievement. This standardized coefficient allows for a comparison of the relative importance of different predictors in the model, indicating that teachers' subject matter mastery is a significant predictor of students' academic success in physics.

Hypothesis Two

There is no Significant Relationship between Physics Teachers’ Mastery of Instructional Strategies and Academic Achievement in Physics among Senior Secondary Schools students in Taraba State

Table 6: Summary of ANOVA results of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers’ Mastery of Instructional Strategies and Students’ Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	26382.095	1	26382.095	179.994	.000 ^b
	Residual	57016.429	389	146.572		
	Total	83398.523	390			

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ academic achievement

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b. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies

The result of linear regression in Table 6 shows that $[F(1, 389) = 179.994, p < .05]$. Since the computed p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected suggesting that there is indeed a significant relationship between Physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary schools students in Taraba state.

Table 7: Model Summary of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers' Mastery of Instructional Strategies and Students' Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.562 ^a	.316	.315	12.10668

a Predictor: (Constant), Physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies

Table 7 indicates that there is moderate positive relationship between Physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies and students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Taraba state as shown by the R-value of 0.562 and the adjusted R-square value (.315). This suggests that, 31.5% of variance in students' academic achievement can be explained by the predictor variable (Physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies) in the model.

Table 8: Beta Coefficient of Linear Regression for relationship between Physics Teachers' Mastery of Instructional Strategies and Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	18.217	1.907		9.554	.000
	Physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies	7.223	.538	.562	13.416	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

Table 8 shows results of Beta coefficient of regression analysis. it reveals a significant Beta coefficient of $\beta = 0.562, p < 0.05$. This indicates that Physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies has a significant positive effect on students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Taraba state.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the study revealed that the mean score achievement of physics teachers' knowledge of subject matter in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is generally low. On average, physics teachers' subject matter knowledge is insufficient to meet the minimum required standard, as indicated by fail grade (F9), and that there is a significant relationship between Physics teachers' knowledge of the subject matter and students' academic achievement in Taraba state. This finding agrees with that of Olasehinde, Williams, Yahaya and Owolabi (2018), Adu and Olatundun (2017), Denbel (2023), Sadiq (2019), Njoroge and Githua (2018) who found that there is significant relationship between teachers' knowledge of subject matter and student's academic achievement at the end of their studies. However, this finding disagrees with that of Baumert et al (2020), Gulled (2021) who found that teachers' subject matter knowledge has no effect on students' academic achievement. It could be inferred from the study that teachers' knowledge of the subject matter translates to enhanced academic achievement of students.

The study also found that the level of physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is moderate with a mean of 3.44. In addition, there is a significant relationship between physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies and senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Taraba state. This finding aligns with Baafi (2020) and Onweh and Udeme (2015), who reported that the use of effective instructional strategies had a significant impact on students' academic performance. According to them, when teachers employed diverse instructional methods, such as interactive lectures, group work, and practical activities, students demonstrated higher levels of understanding and improved academic performance. However, this finding disagrees with Pianta, Hamre, and Allen (2015), who found that there is no significant impact of teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies on student achievement. Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies significantly contributes to

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improving the academic achievement of students studying physics. This highlights the importance of equipping teachers with diverse and effective teaching methods to foster better learning outcomes.

Conclusion

The study revealed significant relationship between physics teachers' mastery of subject matter and instructional strategies on students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Taraba State. These emphasize the critical role of teachers' expertise in influencing students' outcomes. Therefore, the researcher concluded that physics teachers' mastery of subject matter and instructional strategies significantly relate to students' academic achievement in physics. This means that a positive or negative change in a teacher's knowledge of subject matter and instructional strategies will result in a corresponding shift in the academic achievement of students.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. Since there is significant relationship between Physics teachers' content knowledge and students' academic achievement, physics teachers content knowledge should be improved through teacher's constant training and re-training on content knowledge.
2. To further improve students' academic achievement in Physics in senior secondary schools in Taraba state, it is recommended that Physics teachers undergo continuous training and professional development programmes like workshop focusing on instructional strategies. This will enable them to employ a variety of effective teaching techniques that cater to diverse learning styles as well as expose them to the latest teaching approaches and facilitate better understanding among students.

References

- Adegoke, B.A. (2017). Survey of laboratory activities in senior secondary school physics in Nigeria. *British journal of Education, Society & Behavioural science*, 19(3), 1-10.
- Adu, E. O. & Olatundun, S. O. (2017). Impact of teachers' subject matter knowledge on the academic performance of students in senior secondary schools in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(14), 109-116.
- Amos, A.A., Folasayo, O.A. & Oluwatoyin, A.E. (2015). Instructional strategies for effective teaching and learning in Nigeria secondary schools. *Asia Pacific Journal of Contemporary Education and Communication Technology*, 1 (1), 10-17.
- Baafi, R.K. (2020). Effect of instructional strategies on students' academic achievement in public senior high schools in Ghana. Faculty of Education and Psychology, Eötvös Loránd University, Hungary. *International Journal of Education*, 12 (2), 17-29.
- Baumert, J., Kunter, M., Blum, W., Brunner, M., Voss, T., Jordan, A. & Tsai, Y. M. (2020). Teachers' mathematical knowledge, cognitive activation in the classroom, and student progress. *American Educational Research Journal*, 47(1), 133-180.
- Denbel, A.S. (2023). Competency level of teachers' subject matter knowledge compulsory for teaching secondary school mathematics. A Case Study of on Postgraduate Diploma Trainee. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 6 (4), 53-64.
- Filgona, J., Sakiyo, J. & Gwany, D. M. (2020). Teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and students' academic achievement: a theoretical overview. Department of Environmental and Life Sciences Education, Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola, Adamawa state, Nigeria. *Journal of Global Research in Education and Social Science*, 14(2), 14-44.
- Fordjour, C.O., Koomson, C.K., Twumari, S.A., Baidoo, M.F., Mensha, N. & Konadu E. (2021). Pedagogical content knowledge of integral science teachers and its impact on students' academic achievement in Ghana. *American journal of educational research*, 10 (7), 439-443.
- Francisco, C.D & Celon, L.C. (2020). Teachers' instructional practices and its effect on students' academic performance. *International Journal Scientific Research in Interdisciplinary Studies*, 6(7), 64-71.
- Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., McDonough, M., Smith, M. K., Okoroafor, N., Jordt, H. & Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(23), 8410-8415.
- Gulled, Y. (2021). Effect of subject matter knowledge on the academic achievement of students' in Public secondary schools in Hargeisa, Somaliland district. *Assign Journal Of Multi-Disciplinary Research And Review*, 2(2), 132-465.

Mastery-Of- Subject-Matter ... (Ioruse, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080308>

- Hernbloom, L. & Mazarin, J. (2021). Learn the definition of pedagogical content knowledge. *Study.com/learn/lesson/pedagogical-content-knowledge.htm*
- Jabeen, M. (2014). Impact of teachers' subject matter Knowledge and behaviour on students' performance. *Journal of Education Social Science*, 3(4), 7-12.
- Kimani, G.N., Kara, A.M. & Njagi, L.W. (2014). Teacher factors influencing students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Nyandarua County, Kenya. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1(3), 1-14
- Lumantao, K.R. (2022). Levels of conceptual understanding of problem solving skills of physics teachers in kinematics. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (IJTSRD)*, 6(7), 34-53.
- Mukama, N. (2019). Factors Influencing physics performance among students in the selected secondary schools. A case study of Buyengo sub-country. *International journal of Science and Research*, 3(2), 277-280.
- Odumosu, M.O., Olisama O.V. & Fasayo, A. (2018). Teachers' content and pedagogical content knowledge on students' achievement in Algebra in Lagos State Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 6(3) 1-16.
- Ogunsanya, A. & Otedola, M. (2018). Teachers content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and students' academic achievement in algebra. *International Journal of Education Research*, 6(3), 109-113.
- Olasehinde, A., Williams, F.O., Yahaya, H. & Owolabi, H. (2018). Teachers' depth of subject content knowledge and depth of pedagogical knowledge on students' academic achievement in English Language and Mathematics in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Lafor Journal of Education*, 6(1), 30-50.
- Onweh, V.E. & Udeme A.T. (2015) Instructional strategies and students' academic performance in electrical installation in technical colleges in Akwa Ibom State: Instructional skills for structuring appropriate learning experiences for students. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 8(3), 82-86.
- Otache, A.V. (2021). Effect of interactive simulation teaching strategy on attitude to and academic achievement in physics among senior secondary school students in Adamawa State, Nigeria. Unpublished Postgraduate Thesis Modibbo Adama University Yola.
- Pianta, R. C., Hamre, B. K., & Allen, J. P. (2015). Teacher-Student Relationships and Engagement: Conceptualizing, Measuring, and Improving the Capacity of Classroom Interactions. *Educational Psychologist*, 47(3), 169-187.
- Shamin, M., Tabasum, R. & Rashid, R. (2013). Students' academic performance in physics correlates the experience of teachers in high secondary schools of jammu and kashir state. *International Journal of Current Research*, 5(1), 10-45.
- Tsholofelo, A.T. & Maree, D. (2021). Student factors affecting academic success among undergraduate students at two South African higher education institutions. *South African Journal of Psychology*, 52(1), 12- 24
- Yusuf, A.A., Omosewo, E.O., Akanbi, A.O., Mohammed, R.E., Badmus, O.T. & Usman, A. (2021). Physics teacher pedagogical content knowledge and students' academic achievement in Kwara state, Nigeria. University of Ilorin, Department of Science Education. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>.

Nigeria-United States Economic ... (Umearokwu & Ehizele, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080336>

Nigeria-United States Economic Relations in the context of African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA): A Systematic Review

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Abstract

The African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) has played a significant role in promoting the diversification of Nigeria's non-oil export sectors by providing access to the U.S. market for products such as textiles, leather, and agricultural goods. While AGOA has expanded opportunities for Nigerian exporters, various challenges such as infrastructural deficits, high production costs, and stringent U.S. regulatory standards limit the full utilization of its benefits. This study examined Nigeria-U.S. Economic Relations in The Context of The African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA). It covered a period between 2015 and 2023. The paper employed the modernization theory as the theoretical framework. The study employed a purposive sampling method, selecting interview respondents from key informants. The findings showed that; The African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) has positively contributed to the diversification of Nigeria's non-oil export sectors, and the key challenges faced by Nigerian exporters in fully utilizing AGOA stem from inadequate infrastructure, high production costs, and difficulty meeting U.S. regulatory standards. The paper recommended that; Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC) should increase awareness and capacity-building programs for exporters to better understand and navigate U.S. regulatory standards, particularly in agriculture and manufacturing sectors, Ministry of Trade and Investment should invest in improving infrastructure, especially in transportation and energy, to reduce production costs and enhance the competitiveness of non-oil exports. Lastly, establish a stable and consistent trade policy framework to provide exporters with the confidence to invest in long-term AGOA-related projects.

Keywords African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA), non-oil export diversification, infrastructural challenges, trade, Economic Relation

Introduction

The relationship between Nigeria and the United States has developed through multiple eras, influenced by economic, political, and strategic objectives. The African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA), established in 2000 by the U.S. Congress, is a fundamental framework influencing their economic relations, aimed at fostering economic development and trade with qualifying African nations. Nigeria, as one of Africa's major economies, holds a pivotal position under AGOA, offering the nation a chance to diversify its export portfolio beyond oil in accordance with its overarching economic development objectives (Ugwueze, Onah, & Nwangwu, 2016). Nigeria, abundant in natural resources such as oil and gas, has traditionally depended on oil exports, rendering economic diversification an essential national goal. AGOA's focus on non-oil exports provides Nigeria the opportunity to diversify into sectors including agribusiness, textiles, and apparel by utilizing duty-free access to the U.S. market. Although AGOA has promoted certain advancements in non-oil exports, obstacles persist. Nigeria's capacity to fully capitalize on AGOA has been impeded by the need to meet U.S. quality standards, improve productivity, and address infrastructure deficiencies (U.S. Department of State, 2018).

The political economy of Nigeria-U.S. relations under AGOA is influenced by domestic policy, trade dynamics, and geopolitical issues. Nigeria's political stability, governance frameworks, and regulatory landscape affect its participation in AGOA, among international elements such as trade policy changes and diplomatic connections. The efficacy of AGOA for Nigeria is affected by non-tariff barriers, bureaucratic obstacles, and a lack of awareness among exporters on AGOA's stipulations. Notwithstanding these issues, AGOA presents substantial opportunities for Nigeria, including promoting economic diversification, stimulating foreign direct investment (FDI), and facilitating technology transfer and skills enhancement in non-

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oil industries (Adetayo et al., 2016). Nonetheless, although AGOA provides Nigeria with an opportunity to diminish its reliance on oil and improve its engagement in global markets, there exists a deficiency in comprehending the complete extent of its influence on Nigeria-U.S. economic ties. Further research is required to investigate how Nigeria may more effectively utilize AGOA, tackle participation obstacles, and assess the wider ramifications for economic diversification and sustainable development. This report aims to address a significant vacuum by providing findings for enhancing Nigeria's participation in AGOA and fortifying bilateral commercial relations.

Statement of the Research Problem

The African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) was designed to stimulate trade and economic growth in African nations, yet its impact on Nigeria's non-oil export diversification remains limited. While AGOA offers duty-free access to U.S. markets, Nigeria's reliance on oil exports and inadequate infrastructure have hindered its non-oil sector's potential (Eboh, 2020). A gap exists in evaluating AGOA's efficacy in addressing structural barriers to diversification. Nigerian exporters struggle to fully utilize AGOA due to poor infrastructure, inadequate market knowledge, and stringent U.S. quality standards. These barriers limit access to AGOA's benefits, leaving significant export potential untapped (Adebayo & Yusuf, 2021). Existing research often overlooks the operational and capacity-building challenges exporters face, creating a gap in addressing these practical limitations to fully leveraging AGOA opportunities. It is against this background that the study raises the following research questions.

Research Questions

1. How has the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) impacted the diversification of Nigeria's non-oil export sectors?
2. What are the key challenges faced by Nigerian exporters in fully utilizing the benefits of AGOA?

Objective of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine Qualitative study on Nigeria-United States Economic Relations in the context of African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA): A Systematic Review, while the specific objectives are to;

1. investigate how the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) impacted the diversification of Nigeria's non-oil export sectors
2. determine the key challenges faced by Nigerian exporters in fully utilizing the benefits of AGOA

Literature Review

Economic Relations, base on African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) in Nigeria

Economic relations between nations are critical to promoting trade, investment, and overall economic cooperation. Bilateral trade agreements, which focus on lowering trade barriers like tariffs and quotas, are essential for fostering mutually beneficial exchanges. These agreements allow countries to access broader markets, enhance economic growth, and stimulate investment opportunities (Obi, 2012). They also standardize corporate practices, addressing issues such as unfair subsidies and product dumping, which can distort trade balances. The United States has actively pursued bilateral trade partnerships, signing agreements with over 20 countries, including Israel, Australia, and Peru. These agreements aim to eliminate trade imbalances, promote market access, and safeguard industries against unfair trade practices (Osabohien, Adeleye, & Osabuohien, 2021). One of the significant advantages of bilateral trade agreements is their flexibility compared to multilateral arrangements. Since only two countries are involved, negotiations tend to be quicker, and the benefits are realized faster (Ayam, 2008).

The African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) has significantly influenced Nigeria-U.S. economic relations by fostering trade and investment opportunities. Under AGOA, Nigeria has gained preferential access to the U.S. market for non-oil products such as textiles, apparel, and agricultural goods. However, infrastructural deficits, high production costs, and stringent U.S. regulatory standards continue to constrain the potential benefits (Essien, & Uko, 2023). While AGOA has enhanced diversification efforts, challenges in compliance with U.S. standards and limited awareness among exporters have hindered optimal utilization (Wuaku, 2021). Current efforts by the Nigeria Export Promotion Council to address these issues include capacity-building initiatives and collaborations to improve regulatory compliance (Eke, 2007). As Nigeria strives to maximize AGOA's benefits, addressing these structural challenges remains critical to strengthening economic ties and achieving sustainable development.

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Trade African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) in Nigeria

Trade is a fundamental driver of economic prosperity, facilitating the exchange of goods, services, and capital across borders. This process enhances global interconnectedness by enabling nations to specialize in producing what they do best, thereby improving productivity and efficiency. Countries that engage in international trade benefit from access to larger markets, which can lead to economies of scale and a more diverse selection of products (Wade, 2003). As nations focus on their comparative advantages—whether in natural resources, skilled labor, or technological innovation—they can expand their economic output and achieve higher standards of living (Adegboye, 2020). The Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC) has made efforts to enhance the capacity of exporters, but challenges persist in meeting stringent U.S. regulatory standards, particularly for agricultural exports (Wuaku, 2021).

Despite these obstacles, AGOA has been a catalyst for diversifying Nigeria's trade portfolio, reducing dependence on crude oil. For instance, U.S. imports of Nigerian agricultural goods increased by 20% between 2018 and 2022, indicating progress in non-oil export growth (Ikeanyionwu, Ogechi, & Josephine, 2023). However, regulatory barriers and limited investment in value addition have hindered further expansion. Entrepreneurs argue that a lack of consistent trade policies disrupts the stability required for long-term AGOA-related investments (Eke, 2007). To strengthen trade relations under AGOA, Nigeria needs to improve its infrastructure and invest in compliance mechanisms for U.S. market standards. Enhanced collaboration between the NEPC and the Ministry of Trade and Investment could foster a more enabling environment for exporters.

Economic growth based on African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) in Nigeria

Economic growth refers to the sustained increase in the production of goods and services within a nation, commonly measured by the rise in real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) over time. It is a crucial indicator of a country's economic health, with implications for employment, living standards, and overall national development. The African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) has contributed to economic growth in Nigeria by fostering increased trade opportunities with the United States, particularly in non-oil sectors. AGOA provides duty-free access to the U.S. market, stimulating export-driven growth in industries such as textiles, leather, and agriculture (Adegboye, 2021). While Nigeria's oil sector has historically dominated its economy, AGOA has encouraged diversification, which is critical for sustainable development.

However, Nigeria faces challenges in maximizing AGOA's potential. Structural issues such as inadequate infrastructure, limited access to finance, and high production costs hinder the competitiveness of Nigerian exporters (Dzanie, 2024). Compliance with U.S. regulatory standards, particularly in agriculture, remains a barrier. Despite these challenges, AGOA has provided a framework for economic diversification, with the non-oil export sector growing by 15% between 2018 and 2022 (World Bank, 2023). Entrepreneurs emphasize that stable trade policies and increased government investment in production infrastructure are essential to maximizing AGOA's benefits. The Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC) has implemented capacity-building programs to address these issues, yet their impact has been limited by inconsistent policy implementation (Ikeanyionwu, Ogechi, & Josephine, 2023). Strengthening trade relations under AGOA will help Nigeria achieve sustainable economic growth by reducing reliance on oil revenues.

Economic Development base on African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) in Nigeria

Economic development refers to the process through which a nation improves the economic, political, and social well-being of its citizens. Unlike economic growth, which primarily focuses on increasing output, economic development encompasses broader dimensions such as poverty reduction, improvements in living standards, and the equitable distribution of wealth. According to Todaro and Smith (2015), economic development requires not only economic progress but also structural transformations within a society, such as advancements in education, healthcare, and infrastructure. One influential theory of economic development is Rostow's *Stages of Economic Growth*, which outlines a linear process through which economies move from traditional agricultural societies to advanced industrial economies (Rostow, 2013). This model suggests that economies develop by investing in technology, infrastructure, and human capital. However, Rostow's theory has been critiqued for its one-size-fits-all approach, as it overlooks the unique challenges different countries face in their development journeys.

Opportunity Act (AGOA) has played a vital role in fostering economic development in Nigeria by encouraging diversification beyond crude oil, which has traditionally dominated the country's exports. By providing duty-free access to the U.S. market for eligible products, AGOA has stimulated growth in Nigeria's non-oil sectors, including agriculture, textiles, and leather goods (Adegboye, 2021). This diversification has created job opportunities, especially in small and medium-sized

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enterprises (SMEs), and contributed to poverty reduction. AGOA has also facilitated foreign direct investment (FDI) in non-oil sectors, helping to modernize production processes and improve export quality. Despite these benefits, structural challenges have hindered the full utilization of AGOA's opportunities. Issues such as poor infrastructure, limited access to credit, and stringent U.S. regulatory standards continue to undermine the competitiveness of Nigerian exporters (Dzanie, 2024). For instance, agricultural exports often fail to meet the quality requirements of the U.S. market, limiting their market penetration. Empirical studies indicate that Nigeria's non-oil exports under AGOA increased by 15% between 2018 and 2022, demonstrating the initiative's potential (Ikeanyionwu, Ogechi, & Josephine, 2023). However, policy inconsistencies and inadequate government support have hampered sustained growth. Investments in infrastructure, enhanced capacity-building programs, and stronger government-private sector collaboration will ensure that AGOA continues to serve as a catalyst for Nigeria's economic development, promoting sustainable growth and reducing dependency on oil revenues.

Historical overview of Nigeria-U.S. Economic Relations

The economic relationship between Nigeria and the United States has evolved over decades, shaped by changing global dynamics, economic policies, and strategic interests. Since Nigeria's independence in 1960, the United States has viewed the country as a crucial ally in Africa due to its enormous population, abundant natural resources, and geopolitical relevance. Since Nigeria's independence, economic cooperation between the two nations has been focused on oil, with Nigeria becoming one of the leading crude oil exporters to the U.S. by the 1970s (Akinyemi, 2007). Despite efforts to expand the economic partnership, the focus on oil has consistently eclipsed bilateral relations. In the 1960s and 1970s, the United States provided foreign aid and technical support to Nigeria to promote economic development and modernization. Nigeria's position as a significant oil producer, in accordance with U.S. energy security interests, enhanced the relationship. The global oil crises of the 1970s and ensuing fluctuations in oil prices revealed Nigeria's reliance on oil exports, a factor that continues to influence the country's economic policy (U.S. Department of State, 2018). Despite oil's centrality to Nigeria-U.S. commerce, the imbalanced nature of their commercial relations—characterized by Nigeria's significant dependence on oil exports to the U.S.—raised concerns about the sustainability of this economic structure. In the 1990s, as Nigeria transitioned from military rule to democratic governance, there was a renewed focus on improving commercial partnerships beyond the oil industry. The establishment of the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) in 2000 marked a significant shift in Nigeria-U.S. commercial relations. AGOA provided eligible African countries, including Nigeria, with tariff-exempt access to the U.S. market for designated non-oil exports. Ugwueze, Onah, & Nwangwu (2016) established the legislation to encourage African nations to expand their export portfolios beyond traditional commodities like oil, so promoting economic diversification and development. AGOA provided Nigeria with a significant opportunity to participate in the global economy by increasing exports of textiles, agricultural products, and other commodities. However, challenges such as insufficient infrastructure, reduced productivity, and difficulties in complying with international standards have limited Nigeria's ability to fully capitalize on the benefits of AGOA (Amsberg, 2016).

Despite these issues, Nigeria continues to benefit from the trade privileges granted under AGOA, which are essential to Nigeria-U.S. economic relations. The United States has made efforts to strengthen Nigeria's economic development by improving governance, addressing corruption, and promoting economic reforms. The U.S. Agency for International Development (USAID) has consistently aided Nigeria's agricultural sector, healthcare improvements, and educational reforms (Osakwe, 2015). These programs underscore the United States' primary objective to foster sustainable economic growth and human development in Nigeria. Besides trade, foreign direct investment (FDI) has been a crucial component of Nigeria-U.S. economic relations. American corporations have invested in Nigeria's energy sector, particularly in oil and natural gas. While energy investments have dominated foreign direct investment, American companies have also ventured into telecoms, agriculture, and consumer products, reflecting a growing interest in Nigeria's diverse market opportunities (Forbes Africa, 2017). Nonetheless, regulatory obstacles, political volatility, and security concerns have intermittently hindered the expansion of U.S. investments in Nigeria.

In recent years, economic cooperation between Nigeria and the United States has expanded to include new industries, such as technology and renewable energy. Initiatives to foster entrepreneurship, innovation, and sustainable development have become vital components of bilateral cooperation. The United States has supported Nigeria's efforts to upgrade its power infrastructure, reduce dependence on fossil fuels, and invest in renewable energy initiatives (U.S. Department of State, 2020). These collaborations indicate a broader shift from resource extraction to sustainable development and technological innovation. Ongoing issues persistently affect the economic relationship between Nigeria and the U.S., despite these advancements. Nigeria's overreliance on oil exports, insufficient infrastructure, and governance issues continue to hinder the potential for

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improved economic integration. Nonetheless, the two nations share common goals in areas such economic diversification, human capital development, and the advancement of sustainable growth. As global economic conditions evolve, both nations have prospects to explore new avenues of collaboration, particularly in technology, agriculture, and clean energy.

Historical overview of African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA)

The African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) is a landmark U.S. trade legislation enacted in 2000 under the Clinton administration to foster stronger economic ties between the United States and Sub-Saharan Africa. AGOA was conceived to promote economic development and integration through trade by offering eligible African countries preferential access to the U.S. market. Specifically, it grants duty-free and quota-free treatment for thousands of products, ranging from textiles and apparel to agricultural goods and manufactured items (Williams, 2011). The primary goal of AGOA is to stimulate economic growth, reduce poverty, and encourage democratic governance across the continent by integrating African economies into the global trading system. AGOA marked a significant shift in U.S.-Africa trade relations, as it represented one of the first U.S. legislative efforts aimed specifically at enhancing Africa's export capabilities. The act was initially seen as an opportunity for African nations to diversify their economies away from reliance on traditional commodity exports like oil and minerals, encouraging them to focus on more labor-intensive industries such as manufacturing and agriculture (Bergen, 2008). By granting Sub-Saharan African countries access to U.S. markets, AGOA was designed to create jobs, attract foreign investment, and promote sustainable economic growth.

One of the key features of AGOA is its eligibility requirements. Countries must meet certain conditions related to governance, human rights, and economic reforms to qualify for participation. These criteria are intended to incentivize political and economic reforms within African nations, aligning the benefits of AGOA with broader development goals. According to the U.S. Department of Commerce, the eligibility review process is conducted annually to assess compliance with the act's standards, ensuring that participating countries are committed to maintaining these principles (U.S. Department of Commerce, 2019). Despite its potential, the early years of AGOA were met with mixed results. Some countries, like Lesotho and Kenya, quickly capitalized on the opportunity, boosting their textile and apparel industries to export to the U.S. However, many others struggled to fully exploit the benefits of the act due to infrastructure deficits, limited industrial capacity, and challenges in meeting U.S. quality and safety standards (Iqbal & Khan, 2010). These structural challenges have continued to limit the participation of many African countries in global value chains, thereby restricting the broader impact of AGOA. The AGOA legislation has undergone several revisions and extensions since its inception. In 2015, the U.S. Congress extended the act for another 10 years, until 2025, reflecting its continued importance in U.S.-Africa trade relations (Cohen, 2016). This extension came at a time when many African countries were facing new global challenges, including declining commodity prices and shifting trade dynamics with China and other emerging economies. The renewal was seen as an opportunity for African nations to further diversify their exports and deepen trade ties with the U.S. while adapting to a changing global market.

One of the major criticisms of AGOA is that it has disproportionately benefited a few countries and sectors, particularly the oil and energy industries. Nigeria and Angola, for example, have historically accounted for a large share of AGOA exports, primarily through oil. This has raised concerns about the limited scope of economic diversification under the act, as non-oil exports have struggled to grow at the same pace (Nzwili, 2017). Efforts have been made to address these imbalances, with initiatives aimed at supporting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and expanding access for African agricultural products to the U.S. market. AGOA's impact on trade and development is also influenced by external factors, such as global economic conditions and competition from other regions. The rise of Asian markets, particularly China, has provided African countries with alternative trade partners, complicating the U.S.'s efforts to maintain its trade influence in the region (Taylor, 2018). Despite these challenges, AGOA remains a cornerstone of U.S. trade policy toward Africa, representing a key tool for advancing both economic and political objectives.

Theoretical Framework

Modernization theory, emerging in the 1950s and 1960s with significant contributions from theorists like Walt Rostow and Talcott Parsons, asserts that economic development follows a linear trajectory of modernization. This revolution shifts from conventional rural cultures to progressively industrialized and advanced economies. Rostow's thesis, presented in his seminal work, *The Stages of Economic Growth* (1960), delineates five distinct phases of social development: traditional society, preconditions for take-off, take-off, drive to maturity, and high mass consumption. Rostow contended that developing nations may replicate the progress of Western countries by adopting modern technologies, embracing innovative ideas, and modernizing their institutions. This may consequently promote significant economic expansion. While some opponents argue

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that this framework simplifies complex social dynamics, its fundamental concepts persist in influencing contemporary discourse on economic development, as they establish a basis for comprehending change. In the context of Nigeria-U.S. economic relations, particularly with the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA), modernization theory provides a valuable framework for analyzing economic development outcomes. Founded in 2000, AGOA seeks to integrate African countries into the global economy by fostering non-oil exports and advancing industrial development. This approach strongly correlates with AGOA's purpose of encouraging Nigeria to diversify its economy, hence reducing its reliance on oil. Despite the country's considerable advancements, it is essential to recognize that the shift towards a more industrialized and modern economic framework poses a complex issue (Ugwueze, Onah, & Nwangwu, 2016). Nonetheless, such diversification is crucial for sustained growth and resilience, since it ultimately cultivates a more robust economic basis. The implementation of modernization theory in Nigeria's economic relations with the United States, especially under the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA), indicates that access to the U.S. market, along with the adoption of modern industrial practices, may facilitate Nigeria's advancement to the "take-off" phase of economic growth. AGOA promotes Nigeria's advancement in non-oil industries, including agriculture, textiles, and manufacturing, by granting duty-free access to the U.S. market. This corresponds with Rostow's claim that foreign aid and commerce are essential for expediting the shift from a traditional economy to an industrialized one (Rostow, 1960). Nigeria's pursuit of industrial and economic modernization under AGOA is anticipated to diminish its reliance on raw material exports while concurrently promoting value-added industry. Despite the considerable promise, the process is complex and various problems endure.

Modernization theory's significance in relation to the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) is fundamentally rooted in its focus on the necessity of foreign aid and global market integration for achieving economic progress. AGOA plays a crucial role in supporting Nigeria by improving the necessary infrastructure, technology, and industrial capacity vital for economic diversification. This is accomplished by accessing the largest consumer market globally (Amsberg, 2016). The theory emphasizes the imperative of developing modern institutional frameworks, governance structures, and trade practices elements essential for Nigeria to fully capitalize on the benefits offered by AGOA. While modernization theory emphasizes incremental advancement via industrialization and international trade, it provides a persuasive rationale for this methodology in the context of Nigeria-U.S. economic ties. By aligning with the objectives of AGOA, Nigeria may embark on a trajectory toward sustainable development and economic diversification, which would not only promote enduring growth but also mitigate its susceptibility to volatility in the global oil market.

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design using qualitative data to explore Nigeria-U.S. Economic Relations in the contest of African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA). A semi-structured interviews was used to collect data from the respondents. The population for the study includes, Nigeria Export Promotion Council, ministry of Trade and Investment, entrepreneurs, Procter & Gamble (P&G). eight participants were purposively selected to provide in-depth perspectives. thematic analysis was employed to identify recurring themes and narratives, providing contextual depth to the findings. The qualitative findings allowed for exploring underlying factors and contextual influences, addressing the experiential aspects of the research question.

Opinion of respondents on how the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) impacted the diversification of Nigeria's non-oil export sectors

In interviews conducted with various stakeholders on the impact of the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) on the diversification of Nigeria's non-oil export sectors, several key opinions were shared. A representative from the Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC) argued that;

AGOA has provided Nigerian exporters with a unique opportunity to explore new markets beyond the traditional focus on crude oil. "AGOA has pushed Nigerian exporters to consider non-oil products like textiles, agricultural produce, and leather, which are gaining traction in the U.S. market," the respondent said. This aligns with the findings of Oyejide and Bankole (2014), who noted that AGOA has facilitated the diversification of exports in several African countries, including Nigeria.

Furthermore, a respondent from the Ministry of Trade and Investment was of the opinion that while AGOA has had a positive impact on non-oil exports, much more needs to be done to fully exploit its potential. The respondent stated,

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“AGOA has introduced opportunities for diversification, but challenges such as inadequate infrastructure and high production costs limit the extent to which exporters can benefit.” This view is supported by Adegboye (2019), who highlighted that although AGOA offers potential for export growth, infrastructural challenges often stymie progress.

An entrepreneur in the textile industry echoed similar sentiments, arguing that AGOA has provided much-needed market access but that structural issues within Nigeria make it difficult to sustain exports.

“We’ve seen an increase in demand for our textile products in the U.S., but the high cost of production, coupled with poor logistics, makes it difficult to remain competitive,” the entrepreneur explained. This challenge aligns with the work of Ajayi (2020), who found that the high cost of doing business in Nigeria remains a key obstacle to realizing AGOA’s full potential.

Additionally, a representative from Procter & Gamble (P&G) argued that AGOA has encouraged investment in non-oil sectors, stating,

“the act has allowed us to explore new product lines and invest more in local production, which ultimately contributes to export diversification.” This statement reflects the broader findings of Faber and Akinwumi (2019), who noted that AGOA has stimulated investment in sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and services, thereby supporting export diversification in Nigeria.

Opinion of respondents on the key challenges faced by Nigerian exporters in fully utilizing the benefits of AGOA.

In a series of interviews, respondents provided findings into the key challenges faced by Nigerian exporters in fully utilizing the benefits of the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA). A representative from the Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC) expressed concern about the lack of awareness among exporters regarding the provisions of AGOA. The respondent argued that

“many businesses are simply unaware of the opportunities AGOA offers, which limits their participation in the U.S. market.” This perspective aligns with the research of Ogunkola and Bankole (2017), who emphasized the need for greater sensitization efforts to raise awareness about AGOA among Nigerian businesses.

Furthermore, a respondent from the Ministry of Trade and Investment was of the opinion that infrastructural deficits significantly hinder Nigeria’s ability to maximize AGOA benefits. The respondent explained,

“poor infrastructure, especially in transportation and electricity, makes it difficult for Nigerian exporters to meet the delivery timelines required by international buyers.” They further highlighted the need for more robust policies to improve infrastructure. This viewpoint is supported by Adegboye (2020), who argued that infrastructural challenges are a major obstacle to Nigeria's export growth under AGOA.

An entrepreneur involved in agriculture also emphasized the difficulty in meeting U.S. regulatory standards, particularly in the areas of food safety and product quality. The entrepreneur noted that

“most Nigerian exporters struggle with the strict standards set by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA), which often disqualifies their goods from entering the U.S. market.” This observation reflects the findings of Ajayi (2019), who noted that compliance with international standards remains a critical challenge for Nigerian businesses.

Additionally, a representative from Procter & Gamble (P&G) argued that the inconsistent government policies in Nigeria affect the export landscape. They mentioned,

“frequent changes in trade and export policies create uncertainty, which discourages long-term investments needed to take advantage of AGOA.” This argument is consistent with the work of Fasanmi (2021), who noted that policy inconsistency hampers the competitiveness of Nigerian exporters.

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Discussion of findings

The African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) has positively contributed to the diversification of Nigeria's non-oil export sectors, but challenges persist. AGOA opened opportunities for Nigerian exporters in sectors like textiles and agriculture. Respondents from the Nigeria Export Promotion Council and entrepreneurs supported this, noting increased market access, but they highlighted issues such as high production costs and poor infrastructure. This is consistent with Adegboye (2019), who emphasized that infrastructural deficiencies hinder full AGOA benefits. While AGOA has boosted diversification efforts, structural barriers continue to limit Nigeria's ability to fully capitalize on it. The key challenges faced by Nigerian exporters in fully utilizing AGOA stem from inadequate infrastructure, high production costs, and difficulty meeting U.S. regulatory standards. Respondents from the Nigeria Export Promotion Council and entrepreneurs identified these issues as major barriers. They argued that poor logistics and frequent policy changes hinder competitiveness. This aligns with Adegboye (2020), who emphasized that infrastructural deficits and regulatory hurdles prevent exporters from fully benefiting from AGOA. Despite the opportunities AGOA presents, these structural challenges limit Nigeria's ability to fully capitalize on the trade advantages it offers.

Conclusion

Nigeria-U.S. economic relations under the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) have fostered notable diversification of Nigeria's export sectors, moving beyond oil to include agriculture, textiles, and other non-oil products. While AGOA has provided opportunities for job creation and economic growth, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited awareness of market requirements, and regulatory hurdles have restricted its full potential. Strengthened government policies, enhanced private-sector collaboration, and investment in export readiness are vital for optimizing AGOA's benefits.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made;

1. Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC) should increase awareness and capacity-building programs for exporters to better understand and navigate U.S. regulatory standards, particularly in agriculture and manufacturing sectors. This would reduce barriers to entry and improve compliance with U.S. market requirements.
2. Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC) should collaborate with logistics companies to create more efficient supply chain solutions, ensuring that Nigerian exporters can meet international delivery timelines and reduce operational bottlenecks caused by poor infrastructure.
3. Ministry of Trade and Investment should invest in improving infrastructure, especially in transportation and energy, to reduce production costs and enhance the competitiveness of non-oil exports.
4. Ministry of Trade and Investment should establish a stable and consistent trade policy framework to provide exporters with the confidence to invest in long-term AGOA-related projects.

References

- Acemoglu, D., & Robinson, J. (2012). *Why Nations Fail: The Origins of Power, Prosperity, and Poverty*. Crown Publishing.
- Adegboye, A. (2020). Trade facilitation and infrastructure development: Key barriers to Nigeria's export growth under AGOA. *African Economic Review*, 18(2), 34-50.
- Ajayi, S. (2019). Barriers to Nigerian businesses in meeting international standards. *International Journal of African Trade*, 16(1), 23-38.
- Akinyemi, A. (2007). Nigeria's Economic Relations with the United States: Trends and Prospects. *African Journal of International Affairs*.
- Amsberg, J. (2016). *Africa's Future and the World Bank's Support to Nigeria's Economic Diversification*. World Bank Publications.
- Ayam, O. (2008). The Dynamics of Bilateral Trade in the Global Economy. *Economic Perspectives Journal*.
- Barbier, E. (2019). *Natural resources and economic development*. Cambridge University Press.
- Baldwin, R. (2016). *The Great Convergence: Information Technology and the New Globalization*. Harvard University Press.
- Barro, R. (1991). Economic Growth in a Cross Section of Countries. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*.
- Bergen, P. (2008). Economic Opportunities for Africa: The Role of AGOA. *African Economic Policy Review*.
- Cohen, M. (2016). AGOA Extension and Its Implications for Africa's Growth. *International Trade Journal*.

Nigeria-United States Economic ... (Umearokwu & Ehizele, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080336>

- Dzanie, R. (2024). Barriers to Industrial Development in Sub-Saharan Africa (Doctoral dissertation).
- Eke, B. U. (2007). Preferential Trade Agreement as Path to Economic Development: The Case of Nigeria's Response to African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) (Doctoral dissertation, Miami University).
- Essien, E. B., & Uko, F. E. (2023). Economic Partnership Agreements and The Nigerian Economy: A Political Economy Perspective. *Management*, 4(4).
- Faber, B. & Akinwumi, O. (2019). Foreign investment and export diversification in Africa: The role of AGOA. *Global Trade Review*, 14(1), 58-70.
- Fasanmi, T. (2021). Policy inconsistency and the competitiveness of Nigerian exporters under AGOA. *African Journal of Economic Policy*, 22(3), 39-52.
- Forbes Africa. (2017). Nigeria-U.S. Trade Relations: Challenges and Opportunities. *Forbes Media*.
- Ikeanyionwu, C. L., Ogechi, E. J., & Josephine, O. N. (2023). Economic Prospects, Growth and Opportunity by Diversifying Into Agricultural Sector in Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 14(3), 113-120.
- Iqbal, Z., & Khan, M. (2010). AGOA and the Future of African Trade: Opportunities and Challenges. *African Development Perspectives*.
- Nzwili, K. (2017). The Limits of AGOA: A Review of Non-Oil Exports in Africa. *Journal of African Trade*.
- Obi, C. (2012). Economic Relations Between Nations: A Strategic Perspective. *International Journal of Economic Policy*.
- Ogunkola, E. O. & Bankole, A. S. (2017). Awareness and utilization of AGOA by Nigerian businesses. *African Development Review*, 29(4), 86-99.
- Ojo, B. (2017). The role of trade policies in diversifying Nigeria's economy. *Journal of African Development Studies*, 11(2), 63-77.
- Osabohien, E., Adeleye, N., & Osabuohien, S. (2021). Bilateral Trade Agreements and Economic Development: A Critical Analysis. *African Journal of Economic Policy*.
- Osabohien, R., Adeleye, N., & Osabuohien, E. (2021). African growth and opportunity act and trade performance in Nigeria. *Heliyon*, 7(3).
- Osakwe, C. (2015). Foreign Aid and Economic Development in Nigeria: A USAID Perspective. *African Development Review*.
- Oyejide, T. A. & Bankole, A. S. (2014). The impact of AGOA on Nigeria's non-oil export performance. *African Journal of Economic Studies*, 15(3), 112-125.
- Piketty, T. (2014). *Capital in the Twenty-First Century*. Harvard University Press.
- Rodrik, D. (2011). *The Globalization Paradox: Democracy and the Future of the World Economy*. W.W. Norton & Company.
- Rostow, W. W. (2013). The stages of economic growth. In *Sociological Worlds* (pp. 130-134). Routledge.
- Sachs, J. (2015). *The Age of Sustainable Development*. Columbia University Press.
- Taylor, I. (2018). China's Growing Role in African Trade: Implications for U.S. Policy. *Journal of International Relations*.
- Todaro, M., & Smith, S. (2015). *Economic Development*. Pearson.
- U.S. Department of Commerce. (2019). *Annual AGOA Review: Trade and Development in Sub-Saharan Africa*.
- U.S. Department of State. (2018). *U.S.-Nigeria Trade and Investment Relations*. Office of African Affairs.
- U.S. Department of State. (2020). *Nigeria: Partnering for a Clean Energy Future*. Office of Energy Diplomacy.
- Ugwueze, F., Onah, V., & Nwangwu, C. (2016). AGOA and Nigeria: Opportunities and Challenges in Non-Oil Exports. *African Growth Review*.
- Wade, R. H. (2003). What strategies are viable for developing countries today? The World Trade Organization and the shrinking of 'development space'. *Review of international political economy*, 10(4), 621-644.
- Wuaku, M. (2021). AGOA: Economic and Political Effects on FDI Flows into Sub-Sahara Africa (Master's thesis, North Carolina Agricultural and Technical State University).

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Perception of Teachers on Parental Involvement in Literacy Skills Development among Primary School Pupils in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design where one research question and three hypotheses were raised. The population of the study consists of all primary school teachers in Osun State, where 500 teachers were randomly selected across all schools. A researcher self-constructed questionnaire titled “Perception of Teachers on Parental Involvement in Literacy Skills Development Questionnaire” (PTPILSDQ) was used. The instrument was validated by two experts in Primary Education and Educational Psychology, University of Ilorin respectively, while Cronbach Alpha reliability estimate used yielded an index of 0.85 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research question, while t-test and ANOVA were used to test the hypotheses formulated. The findings revealed positive perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria. Also, there was no significant difference in the perception of teachers based on gender and school ownership, whereas, their perception was influenced by their years of experience. It was recommended that school authority should ensure parents are involved in activities that will enhance literacy skills development among children, there should not be gender bias in the parental involvement in activities that foster children literacy skills development, school management should ensure parents are involvement in children’s learning so as to make provisions for all necessary materials needed.

Keywords: Parental Involvement, Impact, Literacy Skills, Development

Introduction

Learning process is a life long journey. From the moment a person is born until the golden years, people are continually learning. Parent involvement with a child’s academic studies will result in a more successful schooling experience for the child. Parents provide a multidimensional role and are considered to be their child’s first teachers and socializing agents (Weigel, et al., 2016). They are caregivers that provide a nurturing environment where a child can feel safe, while providing the essential needs that motivate active learning within the child. Therefore, parental involvement is vital in supporting a child’s literacy development (Aronson, 2016).

Parental involvement in education has a profound effect on a child’s ability to become a successful adult (Aronson, 2016). According to the No Child Left Behind Act, parental involvement is defined as the participation of parents in regular, two-way, and meaningful communication involving student academic learning and other school activities including: assisting their child’s learning, being actively involved in their child’s education at school, and serving as full partners in their child’s education and being included, as appropriate in decision making to assist in the education of their child. As a result, for parent involvement to be meaningful, parents must be willing to embrace a two-way communication between their home and school.

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Literacy can be viewed as the ability to read and write as well as listening and speaking but can be redefined and looked at from different perspectives. One definition of literacy can be defined as a control of secondary uses of language (Gee, 2011). He further looked at literacy as a discourse, or a socially accepted association among ways of using language, of thinking, and of acting that can be used to identify oneself as a member of a socially meaningful group or social network. He argued that literacy is considered to be a secondary discourse because it is both acquired and learned after primary discourses which are acquired within the family and community. In contrast to Gee (2011), Delpit (2011) defined literacy as the ability for anyone to acquire a dominant discourse and the set values that may not be the one they were born into. He further opined that anyone can acquire a dominant discourse, regardless of the environment they were born into.

The importance of literacy development is directly related to a child's success into adulthood as the soil in which the roots of literacy grows has significant impact on each child's development" (Goodman, 2010). Parental involvement greatly impacts a child's learning and literacy experiences. Parent involvement not only effects students' achievement in a positive way but it also leads to better performance as the child progresses into the higher education settings (Aronson, 2016). Compton-Lily (2019) in her opinion stated that many forms of family and community involvement influence student achievement at all ages. Students have a more positive attitude towards school and learning when parents become more involved in their child's education. As children grow out of the elementary years and begin a new stage at the middle school, parental involvement is still critical in a student's success. Parents who seek assistance from teachers help ensure their child is performing at or above grade level. Involved parents are able to offer additional resources to assist in their child's learning. Parents that provide their child with various literacy events can further enhance authentic learning experiences (Ingram, et al., 2017).

A child's academic success in reading and other content areas, is the responsibility of educators, parents, and the community (Plourde, 2015). Some parents and/or families believe that schools are supposed to teach everything to their child and they should have to do nothing. This is not true. Educating a child is the responsibility of everyone in that child's life (Gilliam, et al., 2014). The most influential people in a child's life are his/her parents (Anderson, 2010). Many parents are highly motivated to help their children, but they are uncertain about what they can do or should do to promote reading (Neuman, 2016). Although highly motivated, some families have another burden to overcome. A resource that educators can give families is information. A parent pamphlet about reading is one resource for parents to have at home. It's quick, easy to understand, and small enough to store anywhere. This pamphlet will also make a positive connection between home and school, the teacher and parents (Lin, 2013). It is a resource that gives enough information for parents to be successful in reading with their child at home, and yet not too much to be overwhelming. Being able to access and utilize this information, parents will gain a sense of contribution to their child's academic achievement (Gilliam, et al., 2014; Neuman, 2016).

Parents are the predominant influence in a child's life (Anderson, 2010). Therefore, it is important for parents to be active in their child's learning. Not only will it benefit their child, but they will also feel a sense of self-worth. By providing a how-to-reading pamphlet for parents, it is more likely that they will use it. Giving them a resource to have in hand that is easy to read and use, strengthens the possibility of parent participation. Letting parents know that there are simple things they can do to be actively involved is reassuring and satisfying for parents to perceive. Christian, et al., (2018) propounded that:

"the strong association between family literacy environment and early academic abilities suggests that relatively simple behaviors such as monitoring television viewing or taking a child to the library can substantially influence growth in academic skills, regardless of parents' educational or financial circumstances."

Compton-Lily (2019) reported that more parent involvement is needed where plans to increase parental involvement in traditional events are missing the critical connection among educators, families, and students. In order to close the gap, it was deemed evident that parent involvement had to relate to their child's academic learning in one form or another (Compton-Lily, 2019). Goodman (2010) stated that children develop notions about literacy in the same way they develop other significant learning. Theories have been developed that interpret the parent role as including involvement when the parent believes they have the ability, skills and knowledge to influence their children (Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 2015).

Considering the foregoing, the vital aim of any primary education system is to provide children with opportunities to acquire numeracy, literacy and other skills that they need for their further education career. Tremendous changes have taken place in the provision of primary education. Chahe and Mwaikokesya (2018) asserted that in spite of various efforts which aimed at boosting literacy skills for children, little seems to have been done in harnessing the potential of parents and supporting families in literacy development of children. Parents value education highly, though their involvement is mostly confined to financial support (Tornblad & Widell, 2014). The identification of this actual problem regarding literacy development among school age children in Osun Central Senatorial District, Osun State motivates this study. More specific, we were interested in whether and how parents can be more involved in education so as to boost up pupils' literacy development.

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Statement of the Research Problem

The development of literacy skills among primary school pupils is a critical foundation for lifelong learning and academic success. Literacy encompasses the ability to read and write and the capacity to comprehend, analyze, and communicate effectively. In the context of Osun State, Nigeria, the educational system faces challenges in achieving optimal literacy outcomes due to various socio-economic, cultural, and systemic factors. Parental involvement is a significant determinant of pupils' literacy development, which has been extensively documented as a cornerstone for enhancing children's academic achievements (Epstein, 2011). However, the extent to which teachers perceive and value parental involvement in literacy instruction remains underexplored, particularly in developing regions like Osun State.

The gap in perception between teachers and parents about their respective roles in fostering literacy may contribute to suboptimal outcomes for pupils. Teachers in Osun State may face challenges in integrating parents into the literacy development process, either due to a lack of structured school policies or insufficient training in collaborative approaches (Ajayi, 2021). Furthermore, cultural expectations and socio-economic realities often shape how parents prioritize their involvement, potentially leading to misunderstandings or underutilization of parental resources in literacy programs (Adeyemi et al., 2018). Understanding teachers' perceptions of parental involvement is vital to addressing these challenges. Such insights can guide the design of targeted interventions that bridge the gap between school and home environments, ensuring a more holistic approach to literacy development. Without a clear understanding of these perceptions, educational policies and programs may fail to leverage the full potential of parental contributions, thereby perpetuating literacy deficits among primary school pupils in the region (UNESCO, 2022). This study seeks to explore the perceptions of teachers in Osun State regarding parental involvement in literacy skills development.

Purpose of Study

The major purpose of this research work is to examine the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria. This study thus seeks to:

1. Examine the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria.
2. Determine whether there is gender difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria.
3. Find out whether there is significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on school ownership.
4. Ascertain whether if there is significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on years of experience.

Research Question

The following research question was raised to guide the study.

1. What is the mean response score of teachers' perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- H₀₁:** There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on gender.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on school ownership.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on years of experience.

Methodology

The study focused on the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria. It employed a descriptive survey research design where the opinions of the participants were sought for the research. This research design was selected because this study intends to check whether the perception have by the teachers towards the impact of parental involvement on pupils' literacy development in Osun state is either positive or negative. According to National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (www.osunstate.gov.ng/mtss-2020-2022/), there exist 1,937 primary schools in Osun Central Senatorial District, Osun State with a total of 35,117 teachers. There are 3 Senatorial Districts

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in Osun State with 10 LGAs in each zone. The study focused on the teachers across all the primary schools as the study population. A sample of 500 teachers were sampled across the 2 Senatorial Districts, where 170 teachers from West, 160 teachers from East, and 170 teachers from Central were selected using simple random sampling techniques. Thus, a total sample of 500 teachers from both private and public primary schools were selected as the participants for the study.

The instrument adopted for this research work was a self-designed questionnaire titled “Perception of Teachers on Parental Involvement on Pupils’ Literacy Skills Development Questionnaire” (PTPIPLSDQ). The questionnaire was close ended comprising of Section A, and B. The section A comprises of demographic information of the respondents which are gender, school type, and years of experience; while section B comprised 15 items on teachers’ perception. A four likert scale was used as the response format for the instrument which are SA-Strongly Agree (4 points), A-Agree (3 points), D-Disagree (2 points), and SD-Strongly Disagree (1 point). The research instrument was validated by the experts in the field of Primary Education and Educational Psychology, while instrument reliability was established using Cronbachs’ Alpha reliability estimate which yielded a value of 0.84. The data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research question raised, while t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to test the hypothesis formulated.

Presentation of Results

The data collected were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 23.0). The result of the findings is shown below: One research question was generated and answered with the use of mean and standard deviation.

Research Question 1: *What is the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria?*

In order to ascertain the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, mean of responses of the teachers to each items on the questionnaire were computed, having four likert scale format of Strongly Agreed (4 points), Agreed (3 points), Disagreed (2 points), and Strongly Disagreed (1 point). In other to get the cut-off mark, the average of the total point was calculated to be 2.5 (That is; $4+3+2+1 = 10$; $10/4 = 2.5$). Therefore, any mean point below 2.5 was tagged negative while mean score above 2.5 is tagged positive. The result is presented in the table below:

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation showing Teachers’ Perception

S/N	ITEMS	X̄	Rank	Remarks
1.	Parental involvement can positively influence pupils’ reading habits	2.77	1 st	Positive
2.	Teachers’ collaboration with parents to implement literacy strategies at home improves pupils’ literacy development	2.67	3 rd	Positive
3.	Parents always provide feedback on their child’s literacy development at home	2.59	8 th	Positive
4.	Parent-teacher conferences will positively contribute to pupils’ literacy development	2.62	7 th	Positive
5.	Provision of reading materials at home by the parents improves pupils’ literacy skills	2.63	5 th	Positive
6	Parents have to be supportive when it comes to literacy-related homework assignments	2.76	2 nd	Positive
7	Parental involvement influences pupils’ motivation to engage in literacy activities	2.65	4 th	Positive
8	Most of the parents always attend literacy-related events or workshops organized by the school	2.53	14 th	Positive
9	Most of the parents participate in book clubs or reading groups that involve their child	2.54	13 th	Positive
10	Collaboration with parents to create individualized literacy plans increases their involvement in child’s literacy development skills	2.57	10 th	Positive
11	Necessary materials needed to promote literacy skills development in child are provided by the parents	2.63	5 th	Positive
12	Parents always assist their children in assignment related to literacy skills development	2.58	9 th	Positive
13	Parents are aware of the specific literacy goals set for their child in class and they are always supportive	2.41	15 th	Negative

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14	Parents always assist their children with literacy-related homework	2.57	10 th	Positive
15	Parents encourage and support their child's interest in reading to improve their literacy skills development	2.56	12 th	Positive
Weighted Mean		2.61		

Table 1 above revealed the perception on parental involvement on pupils' literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State. The evidence on the teachers' perception was seen from the table above from the mean value of all the items which are all greater than 2.5 except the mean value on the item 13 which is less than 2.5. The overall mean value of **2.61** which is greater than the cut-off mean of 2.50 indicated that primary school teachers in Osun State have positive perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils.

Testing the Hypotheses

Three research hypotheses were formulated, and were tested with the use of t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a significant level of 0.05.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on gender.

Table 2: Summary of t-test showing the significant difference in the perception of teachers based on gender.

Gender	N	X	SD	df	t. value	Sig.	Decision
Male	211	34.87	4.12	498	0.84	0.37	Not Significant
Female	289	34.32	4.71				

From table 2 above, result shows t value = 0.84, degree of freedom (498). The null hypothesis is accepted since the significant value of 0.37 is greater than 0.05 of Alpha level. This means that, teachers' gender does not influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. This implies that, what was perceived by the male teachers is not different from what was perceived by their female counterpart. Therefore, the hypothesis above which stated there is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils based on gender is hereby retained.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on school ownership.

Table 3: Summary of t-test showing the significant difference in the perception of teachers based on school ownership.

School Ownership	N	X	SD	df	t. value	Sig.	Decision
Public	239	34.87	4.12	498	0.53	0.41	Not Significant
Private	261	35.58	4.23				

From table 3 above, result shows t value = 0.53, degree of freedom (498). The null hypothesis is accepted since the significant value of 0.41 is greater than 0.05 of Alpha level. This means that, teachers' school ownership does not influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. This implies that, what was perceived by the teachers from private schools is not different from what was perceived by their counterpart from public schools. Therefore, the hypothesis above which stated there is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on school ownership is retained.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on years of experience.

Table 4: Summary of ONE-WAY ANOVA showing the significant difference on the perception of teachers based on years of experience.

	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	61.86	3	37.93	.93	.04	Significant
Within Groups	873.91	496	23.62			
Total	935.77	499				

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From table 4 above, result showed f value = .93, degree of freedom (499). The null hypothesis is rejected since the significant value of 0.04 is less than 0.05 of Alpha level. This means that, teachers' years of experience influences their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. That is, what was perceived by the teachers was differ or influenced by their years of experience. Therefore, the null hypothesis above which stated that there is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils based on years of experience is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils based on years of experience.

Discussion of the Findings

The study above revealed that there was positive perception teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State. This was revealed by the overall mean value 2.61 of the total response from the respondents which is greater than the cut-off point of 2.5. This showed that primary school teachers in Osun State have positive perception that parental involvement has impact on literacy skills development among pupils. This is as a result of the significance parental involvement plays in hasting the literacy skills development in child. This corroborates the assertion of Anderson (2010), who affirmed that parents are the predominant influence in a child's life, and it is important for parents to be active in their child's learning. Not only will it benefit their child, but they will also feel a sense of self-worth. By providing a how-to-reading pamphlet for parents, it is more likely that they will use it. Giving them a resource to have in hand that is easy to read and use, strengthens the possibility of parent participation. Letting parents know that there are simple things they can do to be actively involved is reassuring and satisfying for parents to perceive.

Furthermore, it was revealed from the findings that there was no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils on the basis of gender. This was revealed by the significant value of the response 0.37 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. This shows that teachers' gender does not influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. This implies that, what was perceived by the male teachers is not different from was what perceived by their female counterpart. This goes in line with the submission of Plourde, (2015) who submitted that a child's academic success in reading and other content areas, is the responsibility of educators, parents, and the community irrespective of their gender. Some parents and/or families believe that schools are supposed to teach everything to their child and they should have to do nothing.

More so, the findings showed that there was no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils on the basis of school ownership. This was revealed by the significant value of the response 0.41 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. This shows that teachers' school type does not influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. This implies that, what was perceived by the teachers from private schools is not different from was what perceived by their counterpart from public schools. This goes in line with the submission of Neuman, (2016) who submitted that the most influential people in a child's life are his/her parents. Many parents are highly motivated to help their children, but they are uncertain about what they can do or should do to promote reading. Although highly motivated, some families have another burden to overcome.

Also, the findings revealed there was significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils on the basis of year of experience. This was revealed by the significant value of the response 0.04 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. This shows that teachers' years of experience does influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. This implies that, what was perceived by the teachers with less years of experience is different from was what perceived by their counterpart with high years of experience. This can therefore be concluded that teachers' perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State is influenced by their years of experience.

Conclusion

From the forgoing, it was concluded that teachers in primary schools in Osun State had positive perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. Also, it was gathered from the findings that teachers' gender and the school ownership does not influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among the pupils, whereas, teachers' years of experience does affect their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State.

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Recommendations

The following recommendations are proffer so as to establish the impact of parental involvement on pupils' literacy skills development;

1. School authority should ensure parents are involved in activities that will enhance literacy skills development among children.
2. There should not be gender bias in the parental involvement in school activities to ensure collaborations between school and the parents to assist children in their literacy skills development.
3. School management should ensure parents are involvement in children's learning so as to make provisions for all necessary materials needed.
4. Parents' family background should not be determination for their involvement in school activities that foster speedy development of child's literacy skills.

References

- Adeyemi, T. (2020). Parental roles in enhancing literacy development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research*, 18(2), 101-116.
- Ajayi, K. (2021). Barriers to effective parent-teacher collaboration in Nigerian primary schools. *African Journal of Education*, 29(4), 56-67.
- Anderson, S.A. (2016). *How parental involvement makes a difference in reading achievement*. Reading Improvement, 37(2), 61-86.
- Aronson, E. M. (2016). Is parenting style related to children's healthy eating and physical activity in Latino families? *Health Education Research*, 21, 862-871.
- Chahe, A., and Mwaikokesva, R. (2018). Effect of Title 1 parent involvement on student reading and mathematics achievement. *Journal of Research and Development in Education*, 31(2), 91-97.
- Delpit, L. (2011). The politics of teaching literate discourse. In E. Cushman, E. R. Kintgen, B. M. Kroll & M. Rose (Eds.), *Literacy: A critical sourcebook* (pp. 545-554) Boston: Bedford/St.Martin's
- Epstein, J. L. (2011). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*. Routledge.
- Gee, J. P. (2011). What is literacy? *Literacy: A critical source book*, 525-544.
- Gilliam, B., Gerla, J.P., & Wright, G. (2014). *Providing minority parents with relevant literacy activities for their children*. Reading Improvement, 41(4), 226-234.
- Goodman, Y. (2010). The development of initial literacy. *Literacy: A critical sourcebook*, 316-324.
- Hoover-Dempsey, K. V., & Sandler, H. M. (2015). *Parental involvement in children's education: Why does it make a difference?* Teachers College Record, 97, 310-331.
- Ingram, C. (2017). Linking Parental Motivations for Involvement and Student Proximal Achievement Outcomes in Homeschooling and Public Schooling Settings. *Education and Urban Society*, 43, 339-369.
- Lily, R. D. (2019). A renewed call for parent involvement. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 7, 441-462.
- Lin, Q. (2013). Parent involvement and early literacy. Retrieved November 13, 2014 from <http://www.gse.harvard.edu/hfrp/projects/fine/resources/digest/literacy.html>
- Neuman, S.B. (2016). Children engaging in storybook reading: The influence of access to print resources, opportunity, and parental interaction. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 11, 495-513.
- Plourde, A. J. (2015). Cognitive and family-support mediators of pre-school effectiveness: *A confirmatory analysis*. Child Development, 67, 1119-1140.
- Tornblad, B., and Widell, M. (1998). An early start with books: Literacy and mathematical evidence from a longitudinal study. *Educational Review*, 50(2), 135-145.
- UNESCO. (2022). *The global education monitoring report: Ensuring quality literacy for all*. Paris: UNESCO Publishing
- Weigel, D. J., Martin, S. S., & Bennett, K. K. (2016). Contributions of the home literacy environment to preschool-aged children's emerging literacy and language skills. *Early Child Development and Care*, 176, 357-378.

Pragmatic Functions of Antenatal Songs among Pregnant Women in Selected Antenatal Clinics in Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper identified and classified the themes of antenatal songs, examined how the themes are used to perform certain pragmatic functions and discussed how the themes are taught at the antenatal clinics in Ile-Ife. The study is qualitative research with a focus on antenatal songs. Using convenient sampling, the researchers selected Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC) and Health Centre at Oke-Ogbo which provided unrestricted access and enabled the researchers to attend and observe the clinics. Each hospital was visited three times to record the songs used at the antenatal clinics and a total of 14 songs were recorded, transcribed, and analysed for this study. The study made use of andragogy as its theoretical framework. Results showed that the themes of the antenatal songs are: family planning, prayers and encouragement, breastfeeding, nutrition and cleanliness and exercise. Results also showed that the pragmatic functions of the songs taught are: educating, encouraging, advising, entertaining, warning, praising and praying the songs were taught by the health practitioners, who take into consideration the fact that the pregnant women were adult learners. The study concluded that songs function as very good instruments for education and entertainment of pregnant women at the antenatal clinics.

Keywords: Antenatal songs, pragmatic functions, clinics, health practitioners, pregnant women

Introduction

Singing has always been part of the Yoruba culture. Yussuf and Olubomehin (2018) remark that what set Yoruba people and culture apart from other groups in Nigeria is their music which other genres of music such as *fiji*, *juju*, and *apala*. Songs perform a lot of functions among which include celebrating, admonishing, rebuking, educating and sometimes inciting people to take action. These songs can either be positive or negative but there is hardly any event in Yoruba land that is not accompanied by songs (Ogunlola 2013). According to him, singing is part of Yoruba culture and it is used to solve a whole lot of problems like hatred, threat to life and property, and killing of innocent citizens and also helps in ensuring conflict resolution and it enhances political economic, religious, and social stability. In essence songs constitute a vital tool for education in Yoruba land.

Giving birth to a child in Yoruba culture is a thing of joy that has always been celebrated and these celebrations have always involved the use of songs. However, before a new life comes into existence, especially in urban areas, there are some steps to be taken by the pregnant woman; such steps are usually taken to ensure safe delivery of the child and wellbeing of the mother. One of such steps is attending antenatal clinics. Antenatal clinic is a clinic specifically designed as a support system for pregnant women so as to educate, inform and keep guard the well-being of both the mother and the foetus so as to ensure a safe delivery. Ekabua, Ekubua and Njoku (2011:1) remark that antenatal care “is the care a woman receives throughout her pregnancy and is important in helping to ensure a healthy pregnancy state and safe childbirth”. Pregnant women are advised to visit the antenatal clinic immediately they discover that they are pregnant and make sure that they attend all sessions until they give birth. According to Thapa, Yadav & Bhujel (2016), antenatal care helps in early detection, treatment and prevention of complications that may arise during pregnancy. Consequently, good antenatal care can reduce neonatal and maternal death. Ekabua *et al* (2011) listed the main objectives of antenatal care among which are to promote the health of the baby, maintain the physical and mental health of the mother, develop birth preparedness procedure, provide complications readiness plan, and assist in preparing mothers to breastfeed successfully.

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One of the tools often used in the Yoruba-speaking states of Southwestern Nigerian antenatal clinics to prepare pregnant women for the birth of their baby is songs. Songs during antenatal clinics are used primarily to, *inter alia*, educate pregnant women. Education is very important for pregnant women because they need to know what to do, how and when to do some things that are vital for their well-being and that of their foetus. Educating adults especially pregnant women can be a herculean task. This is because adults are only interested in learning that is self-directed, practical and specific goal-oriented. In addition, they are less open-minded, slower to learn but able to integrate new knowledge to their past experiences and knowledge. Teaching pregnant women may be harder because of the physical discomforts that are noted to be associated with pregnancy which may decrease their attentiveness and the various myths that they might have heard which antenatal clinics may need to disprove. There is therefore the need for antenatal clinics to get creative while educating pregnant women. At antenatal clinics just before the pregnant women get to listen to health talks or see a doctor, the matron in charge of the clinic gets the pregnant women to stand up and sing various songs mostly in Yoruba language which is the dominant language of the environment. This study sets out to examine some Yoruba songs and the role(s) they play at antenatal clinic. It is against this background that the study seeks to identify and classify the themes of antenatal songs, examine how the themes are used to perform certain pragmatic functions; and also examine how the antenatal themes are taught.

Several works have been carried out on antenatal clinics (Thapa *et al*, 2016; Warri & George, 2020) , how pregnant women are cared for during pregnancy and different methods used in monitoring their progress (Titus, 2019). It is during this period that doctors and nurses provide appropriate advice and care to the expecting mother. Songs are an integral part of antenatal care in the Southwestern part of Nigeria while healthcare professionals are communicating with pregnant women. However, a crucial aspect that has not been fully explored is the use of Yoruba antenatal songs during the clinic and the pragmatic functions and the roles the songs play in achieving the goals of antenatal healthcare. Paying attention to songs such as these will help in determining the effectiveness of the songs as a crucial aspect of ensuring the good health of expecting mothers as well as the safe delivery of the baby.

The present study relies on andragogy as a theoretical framework. Andragogy is a theory of adult learning which was propounded by Knapp in 1833. The whole idea of the theory is that there is a great deal of differences between the ways adults and children learn and these differences need to be taken into consideration if effective learning must take place. The theory was promoted by Malcolm Knowles (Taylor & Kroth, 2009). According to McGrath (2009:102), andragogy “is centered on the idea that the lecturer does not possess all the knowledge and that students are encouraged to participate in the classroom by utilizing their own experiences”. For effective teaching of adults to take place, the instructor must not see himself as all-knowing who is dishing out instructions to learners but must rather guide learners to participate actively in knowledge production (Knowles *et al.*, 2020; Villegas, Yamamoto & Lloyd, 2021). Basically therefore, andragogy is about how adult learners process information they received based on such factors as their experience and motivation. Pappas (2023), popularising the theory further, states some principles that guide the way adults learn and it is these principles that mark adults learning different from children’s learning. The principles are as follows:

19. Self-concept which deals with the way an adult view himself as opposed to how a child views himself. An adult is self-directed in his learning
20. Experience which deals with the fact that an adult brings his whole gamut of experience and knowledge to bear in the teaching and learning process and this must be taken into consideration during the teaching and learning process.
21. Readiness to learn which underscores the fact that an adult will be willing to learn when he understands the relevance of what he is learning. This means that there must be motivation and reward which can trigger learning. If an adult knows that if he learns a particular task or language, he or she could be promoted, such an adult will be ready to learn fast.
22. Orientation to learning focuses on the need for adult learning to be practical, relevant and applicable for everyday life.
23. Motivation to learn which emphasizes the fact that unlike a child, an adult is internally motivated to learn (Knowles 1984:12).

As with any theory, andragogy comes with its criticism. There are four main arguments against this theory. The first is the question of whether andragogy is a theory, a technique of adult education or just a set of assumptions because it cannot be measured empirically (Hartree 1984). The second is the confusion about what exactly are the procedures that make up the practice of andragogy (Rachal 2002). Also, there are questions on how to measure the effectiveness of andragogy since tests and grades are not encouraged for adult learners. Finally, the characteristics of adult learners are not all encompassing. A child

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may sometimes have a wealth of experience greater than that of an adult and there are some children who are self-directed in their learning (Merriam 2001 cited in Taylor & Kroth 2009).

Despite these criticisms of andragogy, it is popularly viewed as the theory of adult learning. Pregnant women going for antenatal care can be considered as adults because their age and social roles define them so. Antenatal care is to educate women so that they can have a healthy pregnancy and safe delivery (Ekabua *et al* 2011). The songs at antenatal care clinics underscore this message. This makes andragogy relevant and appropriate for this paper.

Methodology

The study is qualitative research with a focus on songs that are used in the selected antenatal clinics in Ile-Ife. The population for the study comprised all the antenatal songs used at antenatal clinics in Ile Ife. The sample for the study was a federal hospital and a health center in Ile Ife: Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex and Comprehensive Health Centre, Oke-Ogbo respectively which were selected through convenient sampling technique. The songs were recorded during the visits of the researchers to the hospitals. Each hospital was visited three times to record the songs used during the antenatal clinics and a total of 14 songs were recorded, and all the 14 songs were transcribed, and analysed in this study. Once the researchers realized that subsequent songs did not introduce new themes but were mainly variants or repetitions of the ones already recorded, there was conviction that the saturation point for the songs collected had been attained. Therefore, there was no need to collect more songs. The songs used in this study are designated as SG1 to SG14.

In this section, we discuss the themes, the way pregnant women were taught as well as the pragmatic functions of the antenatal songs that constitute the data for the study. For each of the themes, we provide example(s) of songs rendered in most cases in Yoruba with their translations in English. The themes of the songs are categorised and shown in the table below:

Table 1

Classification of Songs and Themes

Songs	Themes
SG1	Family planning
SG2, SG6, SG9, SG10, SG11, SG12	Prayers and encouragement
SG3, SG 14	Breastfeeding
SG5, SG7, SG8	Exercise
SG4, SG 13	Nutrition and cleanliness

Family Planning

One very important theme in the antenatal songs collected is family planning. Songs related to family planning are sung in order to encourage pregnant mothers to safeguard their health by going for family planning. This is very important in a country where there is an estimated 512 deaths per 100,000 live births and Nigeria accounts for about 34% of global maternal deaths (Adejoro 2022). Examples of such songs are:

SG1

Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Alábéré ñ bẹ ní sẹ́ntá	Song: Injections for family planning are available at the health centre
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Aláfibò ñ bẹ ní sẹ́ntá	Song: Intrauterine contraceptive devices for family planning are available at the health centre
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning

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Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Iṣu ti wọn, gàrì ò se rá,	Song: Groceries are very expensive
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Alátíṣe m̀túnṣe ara rẹ	Song: A word is enough for the wise
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Bó bà fẹ̀ kómọ́ ó relé iwé,	Song: If you want your children to go to school
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning

The message in the song above (SG1) is on family planning. As could be seen from the content, the song performs the pragmatic function of advising parents about the need to reduce the number of children they may have by going for family planning. The advice is underscored by two important expressions: *Alátíṣe m̀túnṣe ara rẹ* which translate to “A word is enough for the wise” and *Bó bà fẹ̀ kómọ́ ó relé iwé* which means “If you want your children to go to school”. There seems to be some negative perceptions about family planning especially with rural dwellers in Nigeria. This is not limited to the rural dwellers but there are also some religious sects, especially the Catholics that frown at family planning, maintaining that procreation should not be prevented (Abioje, nd). Saduki (2022) noted that only 22% of Nigerian women are favourably disposed to using family planning. SG1 is targeted at advising women who are not favourably disposed to family planning to have a rethink. There are 2 techniques of family planning used by women that are mentioned in the song to create the awareness that there are options available for them to prevent pregnancy. The first is that there are injections available at health centres to prevent pregnancy (*Alábéré ñ bẹ̀ ní sẹ́ntá*). The second is family planning technique is intra uterine device which are also available at health centres (*Aláfìbò ñ bẹ̀ ní sẹ́ntá*).

Prayers and Encouragement

Nigeria is a very religious country and Osun State is a microcosm of the country in terms of its religious diversity. The recognition that pregnancy and childbirth can be perilous, coupled with the fact that the country is a religious one makes it necessary for antenatal songs to include words of prayer and encouragement for pregnant women. Following the belief that God is able to do all things, the antenatal songs can come in form of encouragement and prayers that the expectant mothers will come out hale and hearty after delivery. The speech act inherent in these songs is that of praying for both the mother and the foetus.

SG2

Lílé: Sẹ̀wọ̀ ní yóó bí o ?	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth this pregnancy.
Ègbè: Èmi ní yóó bí o. 2ce	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth this pregnancy.
Lílé: Bólú ọ̀mọ́ keyọ̀kan lókè,	Song: If there is just a glorious child left in heaven
Ègbè: Èmi ní yóó bí o,	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it
Lílé: Bólú ọ̀mọ́ keyọ̀kan lókè,	Song: If there is just a glorious child left in heaven
Lílé: Sẹ̀wọ̀ ní yóó bí o?	Song: Will you be the one that will birth it?
Ègbè: Èmi ní yóó bí o.	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it
Lílé: Bólú ọ̀mọ́ keyọ̀kan lókè,	Song: If there is just a glorious child left in heaven
Ègbè: Èmi ní yóó bí o,	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it
Lílé: Bí Nọ̀ọ̀sì keyọ̀kan lókè,	Song: If there is just a nurse left in heaven
Ègbè: Èmi ní yóó bí o,	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it
Lílé: Bí Dókítà keyọ̀kan lókè,	Song: If there is just a doctor left in heaven
Ègbè: Èmi ní yóó bí o,	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it
Lílé: Bí Lọ̀yà keyọ̀kan lókè	Song: If there is just a lawyer left in heaven
Ègbè: Èmi ní yóó bí o.	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it

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SG6

Lílé: È ba mi gbòşùbà fòkọ mi,
 Egbe: Ọkọ olórííre tó fún mi lóyuń.
 Lílé: È ba mi gbòşùbà fòkọ mi,
 Egbe: Ọkọ olórííre tó fún mi lóyuń.

Song: Join me to sing the praises of my husband
 Chorus: The wonderful man who got me pregnant
 Song: Join me to sing the praises of my husband
 Chorus: The wonderful man who got me pregnant

Lílé: Mo yá a gbòşùbà fára a mi
 Egbe: Aya olórííre tó gbára dúró

Song: Join me to sing the praises of myself
 Chorus: The wonderful woman who eagerly performed her conjugal duties

Lílé: Mo yá a gbòşùbà fára a mi,
 Egbe: Aya olórííre tó gbára dúró.

Song: Join me to sing the praises of myself
 Chorus: The wonderful woman who eagerly performed her conjugal duties

SG9

Mo ń retí rẹ,
 Atinúkẹ mi,
 Atinúkẹ mi ò
 Á dé bá mi láyọ. 2ce

I am eagerly awaiting you,
 My darling baby,
 My darling baby,
 You will get here safe and sound. 2ce

SG10

Lílé: Ọmọ tó wà nínú mi,
 Egbe: Ọmọ tó wà nínú mi,
 Lílé: Ó yá gbagbára Oluwa,
 Egbe: Ó yá gbagbára Oluwa,
 Lílé: Ó yá má a yíra padà,
 Egbe: Ó yá má a yíra padà,
 Lílé: O ò gbọdọ jókòó lódi,
 Egbe: O ò gbọdọ jókòó lódi
 Lílé: O ò gbọdọ nimí lára,
 Egbe: O ò gbọdọ nimí lára.
 Lílé: O ò gbọdọ gbẹmí mi
 Egbe: O ò gbọdọ gbẹmí mi.

Song: The foetus inside my uterus,
 Song: The foetus inside my uterus,
 Song: Receive the power from God,
 Chorus: Receive the power from God,
 Song: And turn your body
 Chorus: And turn your body
 Song: You must not be breeched
 Chorus: You must not be breeched
 Song: You must not cause me discomfort
 Chorus: You must not cause me discomfort
 Song: You must not cause my death
 Chorus: You must not cause my death.

SG11

Ó ní mà á bí wẹré o
 Ó ní mà á bí wẹré o
 Ọba mímọ kọ létà sí mi,
 Ó ní mà á bí wẹré.

He said that I will deliver my baby safely,
 He said that I will deliver my baby safely,
 The Almighty God wrote me a letter.
 And He said that I will deliver my baby safely.

The speech act in SG6 above is praising. Here, the pregnant woman is praising the virility of her husband and celebrating her fertility which resulted into the pregnancy. SG9 talks about the anticipation of the pregnant woman for the baby to arrive and prayers that the child will be delivered safely. SG10 addresses the foetus directly that it should receive power from God and not be breeched. The song beseeches the foetus not to cause discomfort to the pregnant woman and more important, must not cause the death of the pregnant woman. In SG 10 especially there is the pragmatic function of warning. The mother is warning the foetus not to cause her discomfort or take her life during the course of the pregnancy and labour. SG11 is composed in form of a letter received from God which assures the pregnant woman that she will deliver safely. SG12 is a wish from the pregnant woman not to look at her baby items and have the cause to lament. This alludes to praying for the baby's good health, praying that the baby will not be delivered as a stillbirth but to survive after it is born.

Breastfeeding

The contents of SG3 and SG14 focus on breastfeeding and educating pregnant women on the importance of breastfeeding respectively. The lyrics of SG3 advises pregnant women to exclusively breastfeed their children for 6 months

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without giving them herbs or water. SG14 talks about the advantages of giving a baby breast milk exclusively because it makes a baby *fine* and free from all forms of diseases. This song is in line with the World Health Organisation's recommendation that a baby should be breastfed exclusively for six months.

SG3

Ma ɓomɔ lóyàn,	Give your baby breast to suckle,
Ma ɓomɔ lóyàn,	Give your baby breast to suckle,
Ma ɓomɔ lóyàn fòşú mэфà	Give your baby breast to suckle for six months
Lá láí fómí là,	Just breast to suckle without adding water
Lá láí fàgbo là,	Just breast to suckle without herbs
Ma ɓomɔ lóyàn fòşú mэфà.	Give your baby breast to suckle for six months

Ma ɓomɔ lóyàn,	Give your baby breast to suckle
Ma ɓomɔ lóyàn,	Give your baby breast to suckle
Ma ɓomɔ lóyàn fòşú mэфà,	Give your baby breast to suckle for six months
Lá láí fómí là,	Just breast to suckle without adding water
Lá láí fàgbo là,	Just breast to suckle without herbs
Ma ɓomɔ lóyàn fòşú mэфà.	Give your baby breast to suckle for six months

SG14

Lílé: Kí ló mòmɔ fine?	Song: What makes a baby <i>fine</i> ?
Egbe: Ọmú, ọmú, ọmú ni.	Chorus: Breast milk, breast milk, indeed breast milk!
Lílé: Kí ló mòmɔ nice?	Song: What makes a baby to be <i>nice</i> ?
Egbe: Ọmú, ọmú. ọmú, ọmú ni.	Chorus: Breast milk, breast milk, indeed breast milk!
Lílé: Kí ló mòmɔ fine?	Song: What makes a baby <i>fine</i> ?
Egbe: Ọmú, ọmú, ọmú ni.	Chorus: Breast milk, breast milk, indeed breast milk!

The speech act here is educating the pregnant woman about the importance of exclusive breastfeeding for the baby. SG14 is particularly acknowledging and advocating breastfeeding so that the baby can be 'fine'.

Exercise

Exercise is encouraged during pregnancy and this message is passed across through songs and pregnant women are made to stand up during these singing sessions and encouraged to dance as a form of exercise. The speech act here is encouraging pregnant women to exercise. Some of these songs require the expectant mothers specifically to touch some body parts as a form of exercise. The songs at antenatal clinics are generally designed to make pregnant women to sing and dance. This is so because exercise is believed to be good for a pregnant woman. Also, the singing and dancing are inundated with the Yoruba culture and these activities are found at almost every occasion in this part of the Nigeria.

SG5

Atínúkẹ̀ ẹ̀şẹ̀ ò ní ri mi o,	My darling baby can you see.
Bí mo ẹ̀şẹ̀ ní ẹ̀şẹ̀	What I am doing?
Oyun inú mi ẹ̀şẹ̀ ò ní ri mi o	My unborn baby can you see
Bí mo ẹ̀şẹ̀ ní ẹ̀şẹ̀	What I am doing?
Mò ní jó tapátapá,	I am dancing with both my arms
Bí mo ẹ̀şẹ̀ ní ẹ̀şẹ̀.	This is what I am doing
Mò ní jó ẹ̀şẹ̀şẹ̀şẹ̀	I am dancing with both my feet
Bí mo ẹ̀şẹ̀ ní ẹ̀şẹ̀. 2ce	This is what I am doing. 2ce

SG7

Òrì mi, ẹ̀jìkà, ekún, ẹ̀şẹ̀,	My head, my shoulders, my knees, my toes,
Òrì mi, ẹ̀jìkà, ekún, ẹ̀şẹ̀,	My head, my shoulders, my knees, my toes,
Òrì mi, ẹ̀jìkà, ekún, ẹ̀şẹ̀,	My head, my shoulders, my knees, my toes,

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Tirẹ ni Oluwa. 2ce

All belongs to God. 2ce

SG8

Lílẹ̀: Ẹ bá mi gbòndò yíi gbẹ,
 Egbe: Jangbala jùgbù, ijùgbù, ijùgbù jangbala,
 Lílẹ̀: Ẹ bá mi gbòndò yíi gbẹ,
 Egbe: Jangbala jùgbù, ijùgbù, ijùgbù jangbala,

Song: Join me to drain this river
 Chorus: Jangbala jùgbù, ijùgbù, ijùgbù jangbala,
 Song: Join me to drain this river
 Chorus: Jangbala jùgbù, ijùgbù, ijùgbù jangbala,

SG7 as seen above is a nursery rhyme that is used to teach children their body parts while SG8 is a chorus of a popular folklore in Yoruba moonlight story culture. Both songs are meant to encourage women to exercise and at the same time entertain them. The speech act of both songs can be said to be entertainment.

Nutrition and Cleanliness

The diet of a pregnant woman is very important and antenatal clinics use songs as a vehicle to pass across this message. SG 4 emphasizes the importance of eating nutritious meal especially food items like eggs and meat that are high in protein for the well-being of the baby. The foetus is described as a piggy bank where nutritious meals are kept and which will be harvested on the day the baby is delivered. Here, it is implied that eating nutritious meals will make the baby to be healthy, and also for the mother to have a safe delivery, and a quick recovery after giving birth to the baby.

SG4

Bí mo réyin ma rà fòyún mi jẹ
 Bí mo réja ma rà fòyún mi jẹ
 Ìnu báńkì tí mó ò pawó sí
 Lójó ikúnlẹ̀ lẹ̀mi ó ko.
 Bí mo réyin ma rà fòyún mi jẹ,
 Bí mo réja ma rà fòyún mi jẹ,
 Ìnu báńkì tí mó ò pawó sí,
 Lójó ikúnlẹ̀ lẹ̀mi ó ko.

If I see an egg, I will buy it for my foetus to eat
 If I see a fish, I will buy it for my foetus to eat
 My foetus is a piggy bank where I am keeping my funds
 I will reap the rewards on the day I give birth.
 If I see an egg, I will buy it for my foetus to eat
 If I see a fish, I will buy it for my foetus to eat
 My foetus is a piggy bank where I am keeping my funds
 I will reap the rewards on the day I give birth.

SG13

Ìmótótó ló lẹ̀ sẹ̀gun àrùn gbogbo,
 Ìmótótó ló lẹ̀ sẹ̀gun àrùn gbogbo,
 Ìmótótó ilé,
 Ìmótótó aṣọ,
 Ìmótótó oúnjẹ àtàyíká wa,
 Ìmótótó ló lẹ̀ sẹ̀gun àrùn gbogbo.

Cleanliness can cure all diseases
 Cleanliness can cure all diseases
 Cleanliness in the home
 Cleanliness of cloths
 Cleanliness of food and environment
 Cleanliness can cure all diseases.

The pragmatic function here is advising pregnant women to eat nutritious meals for good foetus development. Similarly, expectant mothers are also cautioned to maintain good hygiene during this period. SG13 admonishes the women and advocates a clean home, surroundings and bodies in order not to fall victim to different diseases.

As well intentioned as the themes and the pragmatic functions of the antenatal songs may be, the way these messages are passed across are very important. Pregnant women are adults and because of this, there is the need to consider the special characteristics of adults while they are being taught. According to Merriam and Brockett (2007), adult education is any programme that is designed to bring about learning for those whose age, social role and self-perception define them as adults. While the age of some of the pregnant women may not be up to 18 years, their social role and self-perception have defined them as adults. Antenatal programmes can therefore be viewed as adult education programme.

According to Shen, Xue & Zhu (2016), adult learners are self-directed, they have independent minds in taking decisions and they have their other responsibilities. Therefore, they must be actively involved in the learning process. The pregnant women were made to stand on their feet to sing and dance and therefore participate actively in the learning process. The singing, dancing, and clapping are exercises that are necessary for pregnant women.

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Also, an adult learner utilizes life knowledge and life experiences, which can be seen in the fact that most of the songs at the antenatal clinics are composed with the notes of most of the songs that are performed in churches and folklores. This is similar to the findings of Titus (2019) who posits that most of the antenatal songs are derivatives of religious songs and folk tunes. The songs are in the language of the environment which is Yoruba and some of the lyrics are often humorous. This is done so that the learners can unconsciously internalize the song since it is easy to learn and the rhythm is patterned along the songs that the pregnant women are familiar with and in the language that is spoken by almost everybody in the area. The songs are repeated two to three times so that the women can memorize them and even sing them after the antenatal clinic is over so that the message that is being passed across will remain with them after the clinic is over.

Furthermore, adult learners are goal- and relevancy-oriented. This is demonstrated in the songs sung at the antenatal clinics. The goal of every pregnant woman is to deliver a healthy baby safely and the songs at the antenatal clinics emphasize and buttress this point especially SG9, 10, 11 and 12. The songs at the antenatal clinics clearly contribute to the personal objectives of the pregnant women by motivating them to engage in learning and also participate actively at the clinics.

Moreover, adult learning emphasizes practicality. This means that learning should assist the learners to apply theories to practical issues outside the classroom (clinic). The songs at the antenatal clinics evince this fact and they teach pregnant women on important issues. The songs instruct on what to do, where to do it and the importance of all these actions. SG1 focuses on family planning and where it can be done, while SG 3 and SG 14 focus on breast milk and its importance to the baby. SG4 explains the importance of nutrition to the foetus. SG13 educates them on the importance of hygiene.

Conclusion

Singing has always been a tool for both entertainment and education in Yoruba culture. The use of songs for both education and entertainment is also found at antenatal clinics by health practitioners when pregnant women come for their clinic. The study looks at what is taught and how these messages are passed across with the use of songs at antenatal clinics. The songs are used to teach family planning, exercise, nutrition and cleanliness, breastfeeding, prayers and encouragement. The pragmatic functions of the songs include educating, encouraging, advising, entertaining, warning and praising. The messages in these songs are passed across in a way that are practical, relevant, self-directed, humorous, building on the previous knowledge of the participants. In essence, the health practitioners take into consideration that the pregnant women are adult learners.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, The study recommends that;

- i. the government should intensify awareness and continue to sensitize pregnant women through medical practitioners and nurses on the need for them to always register early and attend antenatal clinics so as to make the period of pregnancy stress free for them.
- ii. The government should also encourage pregnant women to attend antenatal clinics by subsidizing their hospital bills.

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References

- Abioje P.O. (n.d). Catholic church, human sexuality, and academic freedom in Nigeria. Retrieved from https://codesria.org/IMG/pdf/Pius_Abioje.pdf
- Adejoro, L. (2022, November 27). Nigeria maternal mortality rate too high-sogon. Punch https://punchng.com/cdn.ampproject.org/v/v/s/punchng.com/nigeria-maternal-mortality-rate-too-high-sogon/?amp_js_v=a6&_gsa=1&&usqp=mq331AQKKAFQArABIICAw%3D%3D#aoh=16707568552883&referrer=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com&share=http%3A%2F%2Fpunch.com%2Fnigeria-maternal-mortality-rate-too-high-sogon%2F
- Ekabu, J., Ekabua, K. & Njoku, C. (2011). Proposed framework for making focused antenatal care services accessible: A review of the Nigerian setting. *International Scholarly Research Notices*, 1-6. [https:// doi:10.5402/2011/253964](https://doi.org/10.5402/2011/253964).

Pragmatic Functions of Antenatal ... (Akande & Ogunfolabi, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080365>

- Hartree, A. (1984). Malcolm Knowles' theory of Andragogy: A critique. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 3(3): 203–210. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0260137840030304>.
- Knowles, M. (1984). *The adult learner: A neglected species* (3rd ed.). Gulf Publishing.
- Knowles, M. S., Holton, E. F., Swanson, R. A., & Robinson, P. A. (2020). *The adult learner: The definitive classic in adult education and human resource development*. (9th ed.). Routledge.
- McGrath, V. (2009). Reviewing the evidence on how adult students learn: An examination of Knowles' model of Andragogy. *Adult Learner: The Irish Journal of Adult and Community Education*, 99–110.
- Merriam, S. B. & Brockett R.G. (2007). *The profession and practice of adult education: An introduction*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Ogunlola, L. (2013). Songs and implications on the Nigerian society: Yoruba songs in focus. *Ekpoma Journal of Theatre and Media Arts*, 4(1-2): 1-18. Retrieved from <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ejotmas/article/view/120653>
- Pappas C. (2023). The adult learning theory - Andragogy - of Malcolm Knowles <https://elearningindustry.com/the-adult-learning-theory-andragogy-of-malcolm-knowles>
- Rachal, J. R. (2002). Andragogy's detectives: A critique of the present and a proposal for the future. *Adult Education Quarterly*, 52(3): 210-227. doi:10.1177/0741713602052003004
- Shen, P., Xue, S. & Zhu, L. (2016). The characteristics and methods of adult learners. *2nd International Conference on Social Science and Higher Education*. Amsterdam: Atlantis Press, 40-43.
- Taylor, B. & Kroth, M. (2009). Andragogy's transition into the future: Meta-analysis of Andragogy and its search for a measurable instrument. *Journal of Adult Education* 38(1): 1-11. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ891073.pdf>
- Thapa, M., Yadav, S. & Bhujel K., (2016). Utilization of antenatal care services in present pregnancy among the women attending in a teaching hospital for delivery. *Nepal Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 11(1): 26-29. DOI: [10.3126/njog.v11i1.16295](https://doi.org/10.3126/njog.v11i1.16295).
- Titus, O. S. (2019). The roles of Yoruba songs on pregnancy, labour and baby care in antenatal and postnatal clinic in Southwestern Nigerian hospitals. *LWATI: A Journal of Contemporary Research*, 14(2): 136-155. <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/lwati/article/view/185970>
- Villegas, S. G., Yamamoto, K. N. & Lloyd, R. A. (2021). Applicable & effective Andragogy: A qualitative study of adult learners, faculty, and administrators in Business Education. *Journal of Business Management and Change*, 119-134.
- Warri, D. & George, A. (2020). Perceptions of pregnant women of reasons for late initiation of antenatal care: a qualitative interview study. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 20(70):1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-020-2746-0>
- Yussuf, B. N. & Olubomehin, O. O. (2018). Traditional music and the expression of Yoruba socio-cultural values: A historical analysis. *Muziki: Journal of Music Research in Africa*, 15(2): 61- 74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18125980.2018.1554980>

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Prospect and Challenges of Using Artificial Intelligence in Research and Development of Mathematics Education: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing communication and teaching in mathematics education. The goals of this paper are to investigate potential outcomes of the introduction of AI into mathematics education and the implications that this may have for the future of mathematics education. The outcomes conceal the intrusion consequences of AI potentials and challenges in mathematics education development through machine language, accepted language processing, technology and educational skills, ChatGPT, social robots, smart learning, tutoring, text generation, collaborative learning, educational assessment, and mathematics development. We demonstrate Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA). We searched Google Scholar, Web of Science, Taylor & Francis Online, Scopus, IEEE XPLORE, Science Direct, ProQuest, and Springer Link for AI research published between 2021 and 2024. The findings of the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) from the sample studied indicate the capabilities of AI across subject areas, challenges and difficulties, stages of test development, the influential and innovative power of AI tools, and solving skills through creative thinking. Following an additional removal of duplicates from the study and quality assessment screening of the papers, 14 publications out of 40 papers satisfied the exclusion/inclusion and filtering criteria. Most of the reviewed studies used mixed and quantitative methods. The authors perceived, accomplished, and recommend that AI should be used to modify the content-based needs of students across all levels of education and specifically in mathematics education courses like EDME 206, 208, 303, emotional connection and intelligence to rupture inventiveness in learning mathematics through a qualitative approach among others.

Keyword: Mathematics education; Artificial intelligence; Creative thinking; National development; Systematic

Introduction

Mathematics is a core subject in Nigerian education, enhancing thinking, skill development, and problem-solving. It involves manipulating numbers, understanding relationships, and practical application. It prepares students for science, technology, creativity, and critical thinking. Iji et al (2018) stressed that mathematics can be described as expunge organized active thinking, which involves the search for patterns and relations that may be expressed in symbols. It is an expression of the human mind that reflects the active will, the contemplative reason and the desire for aesthetic perfection. Mathematics is essential for the full comprehension of technological and scientific advances, economic policies and business decisions, and other complexity of social and psychological issues (Iji et al., 2018). Kolawole & Ojo (2019) argued that mathematics is one of the basic subjects every child must attempt and pass in his/her life to acquire education. This important position occupied

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by the subject in the school curricula is borne out of the role of mathematics in the nation's aspiration for scientific and technological developments. Also, view mathematics as the backbone of a nation which enables us to make scientific predictions that are to be drawn on the basis of logic. Regrettably, students' knowledge and performance in this important subject over the years have not been encouraging especially at the secondary level of education with particular reference to solving of simultaneous equations, an aspect in algebraic expressions (Kolawole & Ojo, 2019). Furthermore, mathematics is essential for science, technology, and national development, and its working knowledge is required for completion of modern educational institutions' courses (Aliyu, Osman, Daud, & Kumar, 2021). Bala (2022) maintain that mathematics as a subject is globally recognized as an important discipline that can be applied in the field of science, medicine, law, social sciences, languages, engineering technology, transportation and telecommunication among others to better the quality of life of the people.

Educational robotics allows students to explore diverse mathematical ideas by manipulating robotics. Because they provide interactive feedback, using robotics helps students develop cognitive thinking skills and reasoning abilities (Fanchamps et al., 2021). Mota-valtierra & Rodríguez-reséndiz (2019) stressed that AI is enabling breakthroughs in autonomous vehicle navigation, where large amounts of data obtained by sensors and cameras serve as training data for different AI approaches. It is for this reason that teaching undergraduate students AI is fundamental in different areas of mathematics sciences and engineering. However, one of the main challenges is how to transmit this knowledge to the students in a didactic way (Mota-valtierra & Rodríguez-reséndiz, 2019). Voskoglou & Salem (2020) argued that Artificial Intelligence (AI) main common characteristic was that machines replaced gradually the power of the human hands and animals, enabling the massive production of goods and making easier long-distance communication among people and countries. Ahmad et al (2021) are of the view that artificial intelligence (AI) refers to machines that can perform cognitive functions in a manner associated with the human's mind, such as problem-solving and learning. The device which observes its surroundings and makes decisions in a way to maximize the chance of obtaining the goals is termed an artificial agent (Ahmad et al., 2021). The increasing use of AI in education could maximize students' learning and minimize barriers that hinder student learning in most schools such as a lack of qualified teachers and resources (S. Hwang, 2022). AI fosters co-creativity: the novelty arises through shared ideas and actions, which in turn would imply a perception of the impact of said novelty and its prompts student's engagement in metacognitive thinking (Pont-Niclòs et al., 2024).

Adedeji (2018) contended that stimulating mathematics' education may enhance quality teaching, teachers' productivity, and consolidation of the Nigerian educational system. As observed, it is not all mathematics education and training programmes that aspire to the same high-quality standard. Some mathematics education programmes in Nigeria cannot meet the yearnings and aspirations of contemporary Nigerian not to talk of taking them to the promise land in terms of national development. Also, the National Policy on Education stated that no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers. Hence, the teacher's job is so vital that it has been generally accepted to be the central organ of education (Adedeji, 2018). The scenarios in the introduction section is summarised and illustrated in figure 1 below:

Figure 1: AI Role in Mathematics Education

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Objectives of the Review

The objectives of the review are to outlining the current level of knowledge about Artificial Intelligence (AI) potentials and challenges in mathematics education development. The review specifically aimed to:

24. Provide an accurate previous research results on the opportunities and difficulties of artificial intelligence in the advancement of mathematics education.
25. Provide a succinct overview of the included review studies on the opportunities and difficulties of artificial intelligence in the advancement of mathematics education.

Research Questions

The main research questions to be answered are

- (i) what are the results of earlier studies on the possibilities and difficulties of artificial intelligence in the advancement of mathematics education?
- (ii) What are the inclusions review studies on the possibilities and difficulties of artificial intelligence in the advancement of mathematics education?

The objectives of the review and the research questions were also summarised and illustrated in figure 2 below, based on AI current and past findings in mathematics education.

Figure 2: AI Review studies and past findings summary

Methodology

In order to include a broad variety of results and narrow the search down to a particular study of potential and challenges of AI in mathematics education, the term AND was added to the search string. A modified PRISMA statement template is utilised for the methodological procedure in the current study to collect, analyse, and produce all the relevant data from the previous investigations. A systematic literature review attempts to find, evaluate, and synthesise all the empirical data that satisfies predetermined eligibility requirements in order to address a certain research topic. In addition, a meta-analysis is a statistical evaluation of the information drawn from several studies or sources in an effort to pose or address research questions (Piper, 2013). The goal of a systematic review is to provide a thorough and reliable picture of the topic of interest by identifying, selecting, and synthesising primary research studies (Bray & Tangney, 2017). A systematic literature review is a rigorous, transparent, and methodical approach to finding, evaluating, extracting, and synthesising data from published empirical evidence on a particular subject in order to address research issues (Bano et al., 2018). Daoud et al (2020) stressed that Systematic literature reviews, consist of specific research questions, a conceptual framework that directs the analysis and interpretation of studies, clear search criteria and procedures, different kinds of sources found, and straightforward data extraction technique. Also, Searching, detecting the appropriate study type, submitting a query, extracting information from

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the articles, every document evaluation have to include the mediation and pattern outcomes, make sure the review's conclusions are concise, and share the framework for the assessment with others (Aliyu, Osman, Kumar, Talib, & Jambari, 2022). Figure 3 below shows the literature inclusion and exclusion at every phase:

Figure 3: A literature of exclusion and inclusion outline

Search Approaches

A search method was created to locate relevant literature for this systematic search on artificial intelligence and creative thinking in mathematics education. These search algorithms utilised five databases: Science Direct or Elsevier, IEEE XPLORE, Scopus, Taylor & Francis Online and Springer Link. Furthermore, resources such as Google Scholar and Web of Science were employed since they are believed to be the main databases that contain bibliographic papers with full-text publishing structures in a number of disciplines, particularly for educational multidisciplinary research. All searches spanned databases from January 12, 2021 to May 8, 2024, and included conferences, journals, and reviews published in English.

Selection Conditions

The major purpose of the search was to map the body of knowledge on the potentials and problems of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in mathematics education across the social sciences, natural sciences, and computer science fields. Following that, the test was restricted to the subject sections, which contained almost 40 papers in the social sciences, mathematics, natural sciences, and computer sciences. The study lasted from 2021 until 2024. All articles published before 2021 were excluded from the analysis. The investigation included every country in the world. At this stage, a total of 41 research publications were removed. At this stage, forty records have been excluded.

Quality Assessment

The research focuses on recently published articles and conference papers. To maintain the integrity of the evaluation, all duplicates were thoroughly confirmed. The abstracts of the publications were thoroughly reviewed for evaluation and purification in order to confirm the perfection and significance of educational material provided in the analysis technique. A detailed review of all inquiry articles was conducted in a subsequent phase. The following rejection step intended to govern publications that were solely published in English. There were five in other languages, and they were removed from the study. Also, 15 papers were refined and excluded. Furthermore, after removing duplicate records, sixteen further publications were eliminated from the research. After evaluating each article using the inclusion and extraction criteria, a total of fourteen papers were chosen.

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Data Removal

The findings have been limited to journal articles, conferences and review papers from 2021 until 2024 and are accessible in the English Language. A total of 40 papers were found while conducting the review. The keywords related to AI AND mathematics education potentials and also AI AND challenges are used for the extraction of the findings. These papers were examined to detect the objectives of the study. Bora (2020) is of the view that researchers, educational gaming systems develop students' practical skills to convey and reinforce knowledge, create a virtual environment, and leverage multi-media interaction. Also, Using one's emotion to generate new ideas from a collection of memories that comprise a variety of ideas, facts, concepts, experiences, and information is known as creative thinking (Bora, 2020). These interactive technologies allow for the creation of enriching training experiences that enhance the learning process and assist students with their academic assignments (Robles & Quintero 2020). Van Vaerenbergh & Pérez-Suay (2022) stressed the needed to make a number of improvements in the mathematical formalisation of disciplines like computation, probability theory, and logic before AI could be considered a formal science. With an emphasis on educators and students, the study explores stakeholders' perspectives on ChatGPT's application in mathematics education (Wardat et al., 2023). The writers then encapsulated the content into a table for the stage of informing the review. Fourteen papers were found to be reviewed in depth. The review of the results and discussion is presented below:

Presentation of Results

Mostly, in the fourteen papers assessed, most of the study were steered at either universities, colleges, and secondary schools with few at elementary schools

Table 1: Study of prospects and challenges of artificial intelligence in the Advancement of mathematics education

Citation	AI potentials & challenges	Result
(Alimi et al., 2021)	AI, Access, Gender, & student awareness.	The investigation reveals university students' cognizance of AI used.
(Hwang, 2021),	AI; mathematics education, mapping analysis & SLR.	The research discloses AI capability in maximizing students learning support.
(Ahmad et al., 2021)	AI; social robots, smart learning, tutoring, education.	The study explores the role of AI in education. AI challenges and difficulties.
(Ouyang & Jiao, 2021)	AI in education Paradigms	AI in education opens new opportunities, potentials, and challenges.
(Vaerenbergh & Pérez-Suay, 2022)	AI, Machine Language & Mathematics education.	The study provides an overview of AI systems used for Mathematics education.
(Owan et al., 2023).	Technology, educational assessment skills, ChatGPT, validity, & reliability.	This paper regulates the assessment process and the use of AI in different stages of test development.
(Lo, 2023)	Natural language, ChatGPT, AI processing, chatbots.	This paper explores how AI could transform educational sector.
(Wardat et al., 2023)	AI, processing, ChatGPT, text generation, chatbots, mathematics education	The finding exposes the capabilities of ChatGPT's across subject domains, and mathematics education learning.
(Mena-guacas, 2023)	AI, collaborative learning, skills, and mathematics development	The study analyses the connection between AI, capability, and cooperative learning.
(Stefanova & Georgiev, 2024)	AI, mathematics education, tutoring systems	The study explores AI as an influential and innovative tool in teaching and learning of mathematics.
(Luzano, 2024)	AI, Assessment; Mathematics education, Threats, Prospects of SLR.	The study determines assessment practices, challenges, and chances arising from the joint effort of AI.
(Opesemowo & Ndlovu, 2024)	Mathematics education; AI; ChatGPT, Big data, Machine learning	AI into mathematics education offers encouraging developments and impending consequences.

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(Mohamed et al., 2024)	AI, mathematics education, robotics, and PRISMA.	AI offers an oppurnuties to assist students and help teachers solving skills performances.
(Habib et al., 2024)	AI, Alternative uses Task (AUT) Mixed methods	This study aimed to learn about the impact of generative (AI) on student creative thinking skills.

Tables 1 above show the full scenario based on citations, instruments employed, and the results of research related to AI potentials and challenges in mathematics education development. Table 2 below demonstrate the names and years of publication, research nations, published journal names, and methodology used in the review study's conclusions.

Table 2: A summary of the 14 reviewed studies

Researcher& year	Country	Research type	Method
(Alimi et al., 2021)	Nigeria	Indonesian Journal of Teaching in Science	Quantitative
(Hwang, 2021)	Switzerland	Journal of MDPI, Sustainability	Mixed method
(Ahmad et al., 2021)	Switzerland	Journal of MDPI, Sustainability	Qualitative
(Ouyang & Jiao, 2021)	China	Computer and Education, Elsevier	Mixed method
(Vaerenbergh & Suay, 2022)	Spain	Springer Nature	Quantitative
(Owan et al., 2023)	Nigeria	Eurasia. Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education.	Quantitative
(Lo, 2023)	China		
(Wardat et al., 2023)	Abu Dubai	Journal of MDPI, educational services	Mixed method
		Eurasia. Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education	Qualitative
(Mena-guacas, 2023)	Colombia	Contemporary Educational Technology	Mixed method
(Stefanova & Georgiev, 2024)	Bulgari	Proceedings of the Fifty-Third Spring Conference of the Union of Bulgarian Mathematicians.	Qualitative
(Luzano, 2024)	Philippines	International Journal of Innovative Research and Growth	Mixed method
(Opesemowo & Ndlovu, 2024)	South Africa	Journal of Pedagogical Research	Quantitative
(Mohamed et al., 2024)	Malaysia	International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education	Mixed method
(Habib et al., 2024)	U.S. A	Journal of creativity Elsevier	Mixed method

Limitations

The selected investigations span a number of nations. As a result, this research includes a small number of research projects throughout the world, including three African countries. All of the journals included in the table above are restricted to mathematics education students' learning interests and are sourced from reputable bibliographic sources. As a result, the review papers recognised and reported on document elements based on citation, year, and subject area. The figure below summaries the scenario by country/territory from one of the data bases:

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Figure 4: Documents by country and territory information.

United States of America and United Kingdom were the most extensively researched countries, and France, Jordan, South Africa and Mexico are the least thus, matched the criteria for inclusion in one database. According to several data bases used, no findings coincided with African inclusion provisions. The figure below depicts documents by citation source every year.

Figure 5: Documents per year by source information

Moreover, documents by year indicate 2021 one records, 2022 three papers, 2023 four, and 2024 six documents. This information reveals that there are generally few writers per year in this field of studies. Mathematics has 0.28 equivalents to 28%, while social sciences have 0.4 equivalents to 40%. Natural science has 0.15 equals to 15%, and computer science has 0.17 equivalents to 17%. This shows a need for more article authors in mathematics and three others, as illustrated in figure 6 below. The information below illustrates documents by subject area.

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Figure 6: Documents by subject area information

Artificial Intelligence (AI) potentials with respect to mathematics education development could help educators by providing professional development facilitation, personalised learning experiences, task automation, real-time feedback, improved teaching tactics, and classroom diversity. It enables educators to design engaging, personalised learning experiences that stimulate creativity, effective communication, and enhanced student commitment, ultimately leading to greater academic performance. Challenges of AI in mathematics education development include bias that can damage the learning experience that students receive from their teachers, resulting in an inordinate amount of time and effort spent customizing AI technologies.

Conclusion

The purpose of this evaluation was to evaluate AI tasks and capabilities using mathematical training. A PRISMA structure (selection criteria, search techniques, data extraction, and quality evaluation) was used to create the overall scenario for the literature review, and 14 out of 40 papers met the requirements criteria. Data abstraction was limited to conferences, journals, and review papers in English from previous investigations. The discussion about AI competences and problems in mathematics education development yielded positive results. The summary of the investigated publications provided the rationale for the research procedure assessment discoveries. Thus, various limits, review objectives, and future directions were discussed. Furthermore, most of the writers concentrate on universities. As a result, papers by nation, citations, subject area, and year highlight areas of weakness and inadequate research on particular areas of study.

Future Recommendations

According to the current systematic review, research studies in the fields of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and mathematics education focus on task automation, access to learning, AI in examinations, AI in gamification, smart content, assistance via chat boats, learning gaps, and facilitating teacher-student communication information across educational institutions.

6. The study proposes focusing on emotional intelligence and emotional connection to foster potentiality in the teaching and learning and appreciation among mathematics students.
7. Using alternative AI could lead to the development of intelligence systems that integrate human and machine learning as well to minimize learning difficulties.
8. Adapt mathematics education courses, such as EDME 206, 208 303 and more, to meet individual needs.

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References

- Adedeji, T. (2018). Revitalizing Mathematics Education Preparation in Nigeria for National Development: An Innovative View. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 13(3), 315–320. <https://doi.org/10.12973/iejme/3923>
- Ahmad, S. F., Rahmat, M. K., Mubarik, M. S., & Alam, M. M. (2021). Artificial Intelligence and Its Role in Education. 1–11.
- Alimi, A. E., Buraimoh, O. F., & Aladesusi, G. A. (2021). Indonesian Journal of Teaching in Science University Students' Awareness of , Access to , and use of Artificial Intelligence for Learning in Kwara State. *Indonesian Journal of Teaching in Science*, 1(2), 91–104.
- Aliyu, J., Osman, S., Kumar, J. A., Talib, C. A., & Jambari, H. (2022). Students' Engagement through Technology and Cooperative Learning : A Systematic Literature Revie. *International Journal of Learning and Development ISSN 2164-4063 2022, Vol. 12, No. 3 Abstract, 12(3), 23–40*. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijld.v12i3.20051>
- Aliyu, Osman, Daud, & Kumar, (2021). (2021). Mathematics teachers' pedagogy through technology: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(1), 323–341. <https://doi.org/10.26803/IJLTER.20.1.18>
- Bala G, A. D. N. H. E. Z. (2022). Effects of Manipulative Material on Senior Secondary one Students' Interest and Achivement in Geometry in Jos Metropolis, Plateau State, Nigeria. *Abacus (Mathematics Science Series)*, vol.49(no.3), 14–26.
- Bano, M., Zowghi, D., Kearney, M., Schuck, S., & Aubusson, P. (2018). Mobile learning for science and mathematics school education: A systematic review of empirical evidence. *Computers and Education*, 121(February), 30–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.02.006>
- Bora, A. (2020). Critical Thinking and Creative Thinking as the Focus on Mathematics Education. *International Journal of Scientific Development and Research (IJS DR)* , 5(3), 235–241. www.ijdsr.org235
- Bray, A., & Tangney, B. (2017). Technology usage in mathematics education research – A systematic review of recent trends. *Computers and Education*, 114, 255–273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2017.07.004>
- Daoud, R., Starkey, L., Eppel, E., Vo, T. D., & Sylvester, A. (2020). The educational value of internet use in the home for school children: A systematic review of literature. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 0(0), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2020.1783402>
- Fanchamps, N. L. J. A., Slangen, L., Hennissen, P., & Specht, M. (2021). The influence of SRA programming on algorithmic thinking and self-efficacy using Lego robotics in two types of instruction. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 31(2), 203–222. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10798-019-09559-9>
- Habib, S., Vogel, T., Anli, X., & Thorne, E. (2024). How does generative artificial intelligence impact student creativity? *Journal of Creativity*, 34(1), 100072. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yjoc.2023.100072>
- Hwang, G. (2021). Roles and Research Trends of Artificial Intelligence in Mathematics Education : A Bibliometric Mapping Analysis and Systematic Review. *MDPI, Basel, Switzerland*, 9(584), 2–19. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3390/math9060584>
- Hwang, S. (2022). Examining the Effects of Artificial Intelligence on Elementary Students' Mathematics Achievement: A Meta-Analysis. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(20). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142013185>
- Iji, C. O., Abah, J., Education, M., & All, F. O. R. (2018). Mathematics Education for all Through Information Technology Innovations: HAL Id : hal-01868404. *The Journal of the Mathematical Association of Nigeria, The Journal of the Mathematical Association of Nigeria*, 2018, *Mathematics Education Se- Ries*, 43 (1), Pp.89-100. Hal-01868404 HAL, 43, No 1, 89–100. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01868404>
- Kolawole, E. B., & Ojo, O. F. (2019). Effects of Two Problem Solving Methods on Senior Secondary School Students' Performance in Simultaneous Equations in Ekiti State. *International Journal of Current Research and Academic Review*, 7(1), 26–31. <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcrar.2019.701.003>
- Lo, C. K. (2023). education–sciences What Is the Impact of ChatGPT on Education ? A Rapid Review of the Literature. January.

Prospect and Challenges of ... (Aliyu, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080393>

- Luzano, J. F. P. (2024). Assessment in Mathematics Education in the Sphere of Artificial Intelligence : A Assessment in Mathematics Education in the Sphere of Artificial Intelligence : A Systematic Review on Its Threats and Opportunities. March.
- Mena-guacas, A. F. (2023). Collaborative learning and skill development for educational growth of artificial intelligence : A systematic review. 15(3).
- Mohamed Zuhilmi bin Mohamed , Riyan Hidayat , Nurain Nabilah binti Suhaizi , Norhafiza binti Mat Sabri , Muhamad Khairul Hakim bin Mahmud, S. N. binti B. (2024). Artificial Intelligence in Education: a Systematic Literature Review. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education-ISSN;* 3(3), 11. <https://doi.org/10.56294/dm2024288>
- Mota-valtierra, G., & Rodríguez-reséndiz, J. (2019). Constructivism-Based Methodology for Teaching Artificial Intelligence Topics Focused on *Sustainable Development*. 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11174642>
- Opesemowo, O. A. G., & Ndlovu, M. (2024). Artificial intelligence in mathematics education: The good, the bad, and the ugly. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*. <https://doi.org/10.33902/jpr.202426428>
- Ouyang, F., & Jiao, P. (2021). *Computers and Education* : Artificial Intelligence Artificial intelligence in education : The three paradigms. 2(March). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2021.100020>
- Owan, V. J., Abang, K. B., Idika, D. O., Etta, E. O., & Bassey, B. A. (2023). Exploring the potential of artificial intelligence tools in educational measurement and assessment. 19(8).
- Piper, R. J. (2013). How to write a systematic literature review: a guide for medical students. *National AMR*, 1(2), 1–8. <http://cures.cardiff.ac.uk/files/2014/10/NSAMR-Systematic-Review.pdf>
<http://cures.cardiff.ac.uk/files/2014/10/NSAMR-Systematic-Review.pdf>
- Pont-Niclòs, I., Echegoyen-Sanz, Y., Orozco-Gómez, P., & Martín-Expeleta, A. (2024). Creativity and artificial intelligence: A study with prospective teachers. *Digital Education Review*, 45, 91–97. <https://doi.org/10.1344/der.2024.45.91-97>
- Robles, D., & Quintero M., C. G. (2020). Intelligent system for interactive teaching through videogames. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12093573>
- Stefanova, T., & Georgiev, S. (2024). Possibilities for using AI in mathematics education. A Proceedings of the Fifty-Third Spring Conference. *Proceedings of the Fifty-Third Spring Conference of the Union of Bulgarian Mathematicians Borovets, April*, 117–125. <https://doi.org/10.55630/mem.2024.53.117-125>
- Van Vaerenbergh, S., & Pérez-Suay, A. (2022). A Classification of Artificial Intelligence Systems for Mathematics Education. 89–106. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-86909-0_5
- Voskoglou, M. G., & Salem, A. B. M. (2020). Benefits and limitations of the artificial with respect to the traditional learning of mathematics. *Mathematics*, 8(4), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math8040611>
- Wardat, Y., Tashtoush, M. A., Al Ali, R., & Jarrah, A. M. (2023). ChatGPT: A revolutionary tool for teaching and learning mathematics. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 19(7). <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/13272>

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Qualitative Study on Application of Technological Innovations at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

This paper dwelt on qualitative study on application of technological innovations at secondary school level of education in Nigeria: a systematic review. Over the years, teaching in schools has been done in the traditional way while learning by students and teachers alike was before now facilitated by traditional means. If the situation persists, how the nations' educational system can compete with the rest of the world is a mirage. Lately, the narratives have changed with advancement in technology which have permeated every aspect of human life and economy as well. It thus created room for convenience, attractiveness and without no monopoly of knowledge as was the case in the past. The duo concepts of teaching and learning are interwoven and complex but central to the business of the educational system of any nation, including Nigeria. Teaching and learning are the embodiment of the nations' educational system upon which other sectors of the economy relied upon. It is also the driving force upon which the objectives of our schools are accomplished. The paper therefore discuss the concepts of technology, curriculum innovation, teaching and learning; technological tools for teaching and learning in schools, use of technology in teaching and learning, importance of the use of technology in teaching and learning in schools and challenges to the use of technology in Nigerian schools. It further proffer solutions to the challenges identified such as provision of alternative source of power supply, provision of technological tools to teachers and students at subsidized rate, mandatory provision of technological tools before resumption to schools among others.

Keywords; Innovation, Learning, Schools, Teaching and Technology

Introduction

It is an understatement to say that technology is not a tool that can be applied to all areas of human endeavor especially in the teaching and learning processes at the secondary schools and extent to which her goals are achieved. This technology in question no doubt has replaced the traditional form of teaching and learning by teachers and students in schools. It is therefore a novelty idea which has transformed all activities at the nation's education system. The innovation brought about by its adoption, integration and use is inevitable to all human race as no one group or organization wants to remain static at a position for too long. This is no surprise why human beings on their part have tried on daily basis to acquire knowledge, skills and values of one form or another to better themselves, communities, the nation at large and improve quality of education at all levels. This type of education as being speculated can only be obtained through formal or informal education, depending on the choice more accessible by people and resources at their disposal.

Formal education can be obtained at the primary, secondary or tertiary institutions depending on the objectives of education being sought. These schools are like military barracks where students come in from time-to-time and leave at the expiration of their stay over there. One thing is thus certain, to learn under the tutelage of their teachers who have been professionally trained to do so. Though, teaching and learning at the secondary schools have slightly changed from what it used to be in the past. This is because teaching and learning processes in the 21st century is being facilitated through technology either online or offline and at ease for both the teachers and students alike. Without mincing words, it is a testament to technological advancement which has over the years transformed human society, making the world a global village as it is the situation in the present information age. Buttressing further, teacher - chalkboard method has hitherto facilitated what teachers do in the class before now while students on their part have relied heavily on copied lesson notes and available text books for

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their assignments. Far from this, the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) have now become an integral part of every human society in today's world (Nwachukwu, 2006). This development has challenged the traditional role of the education sector in all human societies. Notably, secondary education is faced with the challenge of equipping the learners with technology and information literacy, problem solving skills, critical reasoning, and the ability to use digital technology in accessing and utilizing information for problem-solving in addition to knowledge of subject's content in class. Despite these challenges, the use of ICTs in Nigeria and other Africa countries are increasing and dramatically growing by the day. While there is a great deal of knowledge about how ICTs are being used in developed countries, there is no much information on how ICTs are being introduced into schools in developing countries including Nigeria (Beukes - Amiss and Chiware, 2006). Owing to this, it has become imperative to examine qualitative study on application of technological innovation at secondary school level of education in Nigeria: a systematic review.

Concepts of Technology, Teaching and Learning

Trio concepts of technology, teaching and learning have all been examined one after the other. The connection however, with them, is education advances with technology. Judging by the present reality today, it is crystal clear that the modern - day classroom needs are very different from the conventional classroom needs. This shows that technology provide maximum support for education through its dynamic, flexible and interactive content especially within the secondary education context. The application of educational technology in the classroom setting improves teaching - learning process and permits teachers as well as learners to interact as human beings in a climate where people control their environment for their own desired purposes. Classroom knowledge as provided for in the secondary schools are made more relevant and applicable to real world situations through the use of appropriate technology (Kwache, 2007). It also provides opportunities for personal learning plan as well as motivates and engages students in individualized learning. It is in lieu of this, that learners' exposure to various social media such as YouTube, MySpace, facebook, Digg, and Artificial Intelligence (Ai), appears to be of great assistance to what they learn in and out of school (Zhang and Olfman, 2010).

In all of these, educational technology refers to the use of media and equipment in the teaching - learning process. These instructional materials include chalkboard, flannel boards, models and overhead projectors. Technology in education implies video/audio cassette recorder, video cassette, player/recorder, radio, television, telephone and computer. In addition to this, educational technology can be seen as the application of the principles of technology in solving educational problems. Therefore, the use of computers in education is traceable to the development of educational technology. The objective of the national policy on computer education launched in 1988 was specifically to expose the learners to:

- (i) Knowledge of computers and their uses in everyday life;
 - (ii) The use of computers to facilitate or enhance their learning process and problem solving and;
 - (iii) Acquire and develop rudimentary skills like data processing, word processing, record keeping and financial analysis.
- Notably, computer education programme was planned to improve the quality of teaching-learning in schools aiding technological and socio -economic development of a nation. Technology in education no doubt equips the recipient with the ability to utilize the computer and other digital electronic devices for the purpose of transmitting information technology (IT) from one place to the other.

Abdellatif (2014) opined that teaching and learning are integrated circles which focuses on what both teachers and students do in class or outside the classroom (reading for learning). Although, one could sometimes happen without the other. In any way, teaching and learning are two sides of the same coin, so to say. The duo concepts involve the use of strategies which maximize opportunities for interaction in class. The ultimate aim of teaching is to bring about learning via the use of technology. Therefore, a teaching process that does not result in learning is of no use. Without quality teaching, only a limited form of learning is possible. This of course is no surprised that the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) states that "No education system can rise above the quality of its teachers". In some American states, employers even use students' academic achievement as part of the criterion for deciding teachers' performance.

Teaching thus connotes imparting knowledge or skill while learning refers to acquisition of knowledge by updating his/her data and the learner's feedback (Judeh, 2014). The goal achievement of students in the school is reflected in excellent performance. Performance in this study encompasses the full range of activities that would characterize a school as being successful. This would, in addition to students' academic performance furthermore include well motivated and committed teachers, learner satisfaction and involvement, parental involvement, a clean orderly school environment, qualitative teaching and learning process and strong principal leadership ability. Although, assessment of teaching and learning in Nigeria has not been sufficiently done. Sometimes, only learning is assessed while teaching is left out and vice versa.

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In such a situation, it is impossible to have comprehensive data and plausible generalizations about the teaching and learning trends in the school system. There are however, few good learning assessments that tried to ascertain altogether the impact of teachers, school administration, parents and environment on the learning outcome of students to show that all these factors count. This being the case, the major concern of schools is the success or effectiveness of teaching and learning process using any appropriate means available. Though, performance is determined by many other factors just as technology is the focus of this paper. Notably, there are many teaching methods that is available to practising teachers; quick meaning of this is that teaching methods have received different classifications from different teachers. In all fields and to all teachers, the most appropriate method of teaching therefore is that which can motivate the students and sustain their interest in the course of instruction. It is equally important to note that teaching methods also involves the interaction of the teachers, learners and the subject matter.

Learning on the other hand, has a close connection with teaching because when there is one who is teaching there are students who are learning. Learning is thus a change in behaviour of learners as a result of interaction with environment and a purpose to fulfil had become a necessity. Any activity can be called learning so far as it develops the individual (in any respect, good or bad) and makes him alter behaviour and experiences different from what they would otherwise have been” (Woodworth in Ali and Masih, 2021). Quality learning is extensive, integrative, and generative (Lawson and Kirby, 2012). Based on their studies, they observed that three factors influence the quality of learning. These are dispositions towards learning, conditions for learning, and the learning process.

The learning process is much associated with the approaches to learning. For decades, one of the most persistent problems which teachers have struggled to solve has been how to achieve maximum results with minimum but effective medium of instruction. There has been a need to change our emphasis on teaching by the teacher to learning by the learner. Thus, rather than be a teacher - centred activity, instruction has become learner - centred. Teachers need to ascertain what their students wish to know and how it is relevant to their life and work and how they learn best. Hence, for effective teaching and learning to take place, there must be a correlation between teacher’s instructional strategies and students’ learning styles (Akinbobola, 2011b).

Application of Technology at the Secondary Schools

Schools all over the world are increasingly turning their attention to different kinds of technological resources to support and enhance the teaching and learning of the 21st century skills. This is especially so because technological skills have become critical in our daily lives and more importantly, at the secondary schools. These skills are needed for success in our rapidly changing and highly competitive world. Thomas (2004) and Ranga (2004) classified the application of computers and other communication technologies in education into three broad categories: Pedagogy, Training and Continuing Education. The pedagogical applicability of the ICTs is about learning with the support of various components of computer. This perhaps could be the starting point for secondary school leavers before gaining admission into the Universities or teacher training college. Olakulehin (2007) on his part emphasized that pedagogy application of ICTs involves effective learning with the aid of computers and other information technologies, serving the purpose of learning aids, which plays complementary roles in teaching/learning situations rather than supplements the teacher. This means that ICTs can facilitate learning in secondary schools and individualized learning through methods like modeling, simulation and so on.

Obviously, the effective application of ICTs has advantage of increasing the learners’ motivation to learn more and desirable attitudes towards actualizing more of ICTs tools. The evolution of mobile technology has also put learning in the palms of both teachers and their learners. Mobile technology refers to mobile devices that include Personal Digital Assistance (PDA), tablets, digital cell phones and ipods. They are self-effacing enough that they have become useful in implementing different learning techniques and pedagogies (Dale and Povey, 2007; Varis, 2007; Arkorful, Oduro and Abaidoo, 2016). Mobile technology learning, otherwise called M-learning is learning achieved through wireless technology devices that can be pocketed and utilized wherever the learner’s device can receive unbroken transmission signals (Attewell and Savil - Smith 2005). Apparently, it is no more sufficient for teachers to use a particular technology or software where students’ need constant assess to an evolving array of technological tools and activities that will enable them to engage in problem-solving, decision-making, teamwork/collaboration and innovation. The followings can be used or designated to perform the under-listed activities that hitherto promotes teaching and learning in Nigerian secondary schools in the 21st Century.

Audio and video devices such as radios, television programmes, DVD, VCD have been in use in the classroom for a long time. Technologies of the 21st century now allow teachers to stream audio over the internet. There are also webcasts and podcasts available over the internet for students and teachers to download. Websites like Youtube also allow teachers and

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students opportunity to watch on-line videos. Messaging programs such as Skype, Adobe Connect or webcams are used by teachers to interact with guest speakers and other experts.

1. **Blogging:** These are personal internet journals which allow both students and teachers to post their thoughts, ideas and comments on the website for others to comment on, open discussion or seek opinions. Blogging allows students and teachers to share their thoughts and comments on the thoughts of others thus creating an interactive learning environment (Courts and Tucker, 2012) on-line even when separated by distance.
2. **Webcam** which are video cameras that streams images through the computer network which could be webcasted to create virtual platforms, In this environment, teachers can give instructions and receive feedback from students.
3. **Screen casting:** This is a recent trend that allows users to share their screens directly from their browser online so that the viewers can stream the video directly. By this means user can follow the individual's line of thought without ambiguities associated with explanations.
4. **Artificial intelligence (AI):** This involves the use of computer to produce simulations of intelligent behaviours in robots to perform tasks usually performed by intelligent humans.

Benefits of Technology at the Secondary Schools in Nigeria

The 21st century world is a dynamic one, one that is ever changing and surrounded by information. It is therefore important that the type of education given to students should match the dynamic nature of the world. Technology in teaching has many benefits especially to students in secondary schools. The following are some of the benefits of technology in education.

Collaboration of knowledge:

The employment of technology in the classroom is important as it allows secondary school students share knowledge among themselves anywhere, anytime. The use of technology in secondary schools allowed knowledge mobility, this means that knowledge can be gotten, shared and used anywhere, anytime within the classroom and outside the classroom. This collaborative learning can be between teachers and students or within students.

Student Centered:

Using technology in training as well as learning procedure makes teaching transcends beyond the traditional notion of the teacher being the sole custodian of knowledge. With the use of technological gadgets like the internet, secondary school students can access to any information they need and also learn at their own pace. Ajayi (2008) posited that training as well as learning has evolved passed the teacher positioning himself in front of a collection of students as well as circulating information to them without the students' adequate participation. This harnesses the point that technology in education makes teaching and learning less teacher - centered and more student - centered.

Convenience:

It makes educational activities easy and simple. With this blended method of teaching, students do not necessarily need to carry heavy backpacks, they can easily read and store information in their laptops, do exercise and send to their teachers at any time. Also, teachers do not need to carry scripts around as students works can be marked with the aid of technological devices. Technology in education no doubt is convenient for the trainers and the pupils as well.

Wider range of information:

The internet houses a lot of information; thus, students can get more information about a subject area beyond the one they get from their textbooks. Through sites Like the Research Gate, Google scholar, Google and others, students has a wider range of access to informative information about different subjects.

Intensifies Teaching:

ICT gives room for students to learn intensively and thoroughly. Through audiovisual materials, students have a more concrete idea about the concepts they being taught. For instance if students are taught about how the intestines work and they get to only see a picture of the intestine, they may get an abstract view of how the intestines really are, but with the help of the YouTube, students can see and even watch how the intestines functions, this has helped in intensifying the lesson the teacher has taught, with this students will not forget this concept easily, they will also be no need of memorizing because what they have seen will stick better.

Updated knowledge:

With the employment of technology in secondary school education, students are exposed to recent and updated knowledge about certain subjects instead of the old information in most textbooks. Studies to ascertain the academic potentials and benefits of mobile application, have shown that apart from its benefits as a learning tool, learners vocabulary are improved,

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same as their understanding of content/concepts, students are also motivated to do well and prepared for class than their counterparts who do not use or have them (Wylie, 2016).

Challenges of Using Technology at the Secondary Schools in Nigeria

The integration and use of modern technology in the nation's post primary schools was a sought of relief to the former traditional method which has vogue for decades. As complex, portable, convenient and fascinating as the modern technology is, there are still setbacks which includes:

1. Inadequate training of teachers: It has been observed that these new technique of teaching - learning has brought about huge demand on personnel training and re-training so as to ensure its effective integration in the classroom. This training will enable the teachers to use software programmes to stimulate students to improve upon the under developed skills in a variety of content areas.
2. The use of technology in the classroom is capital intensive and only few schools can afford such equipments as computers, internet and so on.
3. It is time consuming: Much time is needed for the implementation of technology in the classrooms which may not be available.
4. The quality of computer or digital cameras for classrooms are grossly inadequate.
5. Malfunctions of computer: Reacting to the malfunctioning of computer Osasebor and Okunsebor (2009) said that one of the major disadvantages of the application of computers in the Nigerian education is due to system malfunctioning which can be experienced in the computer itself. They added that computer in education depends largely on electricity and without it, it cannot function. Irregular supply of power has been a great problem to the use of computers in the classroom.
6. Absence of electricity in rural areas hinders the use of computer technology in the classroom in such locations.

Conclusion

The world today is powered by technology in virtually all areas of life and sectors of the economy. Education that is provided in any nation is to empower the citizens to fit successfully into their society. The 21st century world is ruled by information. Only individuals with the ability and skills to utilize modern digital tools to access and generate information and knowledge can and will perform in the global work space and platform. The technologies of today have completely changed the platform for learning. Students now learn from different sources. Teachers need to key into the modern learning modes by utilizing the tools offered by the digital revolution to prepare learners who are globally empowered. The idea of a fixed classroom where students learn only in the presence of their teachers and from what the teacher provides for them has gone long before now. Learners can now learn with the teachers directing even when they are separated by time and distance. This type of learning, apart from its efficacy in promoting self-paced learning, motivates learners to engage in research and dissemination of knowledge as fast as possible which are connected to networking and collaboration. To remain relevant therefore, teachers and students should keep abreast with the learning technologies of the time through re-engineering and innovating in system structure, perceptual change, instructional, administrative and assessment practices that are compliant with the 21st Century literacy skills.

Recommendations

The following recommendations have been put forward in this paper:

1. The need for adequate training of teachers and students (or learners) have become imperative in the 21st Century.
2. Appropriate machinery should be put in place to ensure that computers and its accessories are provided to schools via loan or subsidized rates for those who can pay at once. Checks should also be put in place to ensure they are not sold when in need of cash by those given.
3. Issue of allocation of more time to school programmes and activities be looked into. This is in fact a serious matter aimed at ensuring all that needed to be learnt is learn.
4. Adequate supply and maintenance of computers in schools be looked into. This can be done periodically and avoid if necessary that such is not a conduit pipe to amass wealth by those at the helms of affairs.
5. Alternative power supply to schools be massively invested on. This is especially as public electricity supply in the Country can no longer be relied upon.

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References

- Abdellatif, N. (2014). *What is the difference between Teaching and Learning?* Applied Science Private University.
- Ajayi, I. A. (2008). Towards Effective Use of Information and Communication Technology for Teaching in Nigerian Colleges of Education. *Asian J. Inf. Technol.* 7(5): 210 - 214.
- Akinbobola, A. O. (2011b). Teaching methods, study habits, school location and gender factors as determinants of retention ability of physics students in Nigeria senior secondary schools. *IRCAB Journal of Arts and Education*, 1(1), 152 - 158.
- Ali, M. A. & Masih, A. (2021). Enhancing the Quality of Learning through Changes in Students' Approach to Learning. *International Journal of Asian Education*, Vol. 2, No.3, September 2021.
- Arkorful, V., Oduro, G. K. T. & Abaidoo, N. (2016). *The use of Mobile Phones in Teaching and Learning: A case Study at the College of Distance Education*. University of Cape Coast: Proceedings of INTED 2016 Conference, Valencia Spain.
- Attewell, J. & Savill - Smith, C. (2005). *Mobile learning anytime everywhere*. London, UK. London. Learning and Skill Development Agency.
- Courts, B. & Tucker, J. (2012). Using technology to create a dynamic classroom experience. *Journal of College Teaching and Learning*, 9(2): 31 - 37.
- Dale, C. & Povey, G. (2009). An Evaluation of Learner-Generated content and Podcasting. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport and Tourism*, 8 (1), pp 117 - 123.
- Judeh, M. (2014). *What is the difference between Teaching and Learning?* Applied Science Private University. Retrieved from www.researchgate.net/post.
- Kwache, P. (2007). The Imperatives of Information and Communication Technology for Teachers in Nigerian Higher Education. *Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, Vol. 3 (4).
- Olakulehin, F. K. (2007). Information communication technologies in teachers training and professional development in Nigeria. *Turkish Journal of Distance Education TODJE* 8, (1), 133 - 142
- Osasebor, J. E. & Okunsebor, M. I. U. (2009). *Essentials of Educational Technology*. Agbor: Royal Pace Publications.
- Varis, T. (2007). New Technologies and Innovation in Higher Education and Regional Development. *Revista de Universidad Soliedaddel conocimiento*, 4 (11), 16 - 24.
- Wylie, J. (2016). *Mobile Learning Technologies for 21st Century Classroom*. <https://www.scholastic.com>.

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Qualitative Study on Artificial Intelligence in Curriculum Development at University Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has surfaced as a revolutionary technology holding immense potential in multiple domains including the field of Education with significant role in curriculum development. This paper aims at studying the role of Artificial Intelligence in curriculum development, exploring how it can improve educational practices and outcomes in Nigerian Universities. It discusses Artificial Intelligence (AI) driven approaches in personalized learning, adaptive assessments, and intelligent content delivery. These case studies and examples highlight the diverse applications of Artificial Intelligence in curriculum development, demonstrating its potential to enhance learning outcomes, individualize instruction, and streamline administrative processes in education. The writers discuss the concepts of Artificial Intelligence, key Artificial Intelligence Technologies in Education, advantages and disadvantages of Artificial Intelligence in curriculum development, concept of curriculum development, components of effective curriculum development, Roles of Artificial Intelligence in curriculum development process in Nigerian universities. It was concluded that, technological advancements such as integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) play a significant role in curriculum development process especially in Nigerian universities and it was recommended that, The federal government through the Federal Ministry of Education and National Universities Commission (NUC) should ensure that every university in Nigeria whether public or private meet the minimum standard of integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into their academic programmes before full accreditation will be given to them and the federal government should increase the budgetary allocation of all Nigerian federal universities for the procurement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools for successful curriculum development programme in Nigerian universities among others.

Keyword: Qualitative Study, Artificial Intelligence, Curriculum Development and University Level

Introduction

The use of Artificial Intelligence in the development of University Curriculum has been a growing trend in recent years and is reshaping the university education in Nigeria. For curriculum development, digital transformation promises new operating and educational models and the ability to transform Universities value proposition and strategic directions. More Universities in Nigeria are attracting students and offering them opportunities for more personalized education delivery. However, despite its continued growth in popularity, digital transformation has yet to become the norm in the development of curriculum in some universities in Nigeria. Changes and adoption have occurred rapidly due to the COVID-19 pandemic but most universities are still on the path of this innovation. It is therefore expected that, all university administrators are advised to make giant strides in incorporating Artificial Intelligence in the education, in their campuses and within four walls of classrooms. The tremendous benefits Artificial Intelligence (AI) provides will surely shape the future of teaching and learning

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with the influx of technology available to today's school and students. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has the ability to adapt to student's needs. The system responds to students based on their performance and behaviour so that they can focus on certain topics, go over aspects that a student has not yet mastered and go at a pace that improves their ability to consume the provided information. Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology in the development of university curriculum is here to stay and continues to evolve. Many Nigerian universities have already overcome the digital divide, even if extenuating circumstances drove them forward. Current AI technology already features a wide range of advantages. Yet as it continues to evolve and new technology emerges, there is inevitability. Artificial Intelligence (AI) will continue to play an integral role in the development of universities curriculum in particular and the future of education in general. This paper is about the roles of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Curriculum Development in Nigerian Universities. The paper aimed at finding out the roles of Artificial Intelligence in Curriculum Development in Nigeria Universities, the concepts of Artificial Intelligence, examples of Artificial Intelligence, key Artificial Intelligence Technologies in Education, Artificial Intelligence Technologies that are instrumental in reshaping education, advantages and disadvantages of Artificial Intelligence in Curriculum development in Nigeria Universities, concept of curriculum development, components of Curriculum development, Roles of Artificial Intelligence in Curriculum development in Nigerian Universities among others are to be expected in this paper. This paper would be of significant importance to education stakeholders because it provides insights on how Artificial Intelligence as a new technological development can be fully integrated into the curriculum development in Nigerian Universities.

Concept of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence refers to the theory and development of computer systems able to perform tasks normally requiring human intelligence. In order to achieve transformational change in contemporary curriculum development and learning environments, we must incorporate the use of Artificial Intelligence. One of the significant uses of Artificial Intelligence in education is in the development of university curriculum because it allows for a completely new process of creating a learning content and developing lesson programmes. With rapid development of Artificial Intelligence technology in learning and development, the future of instructional design is changing (Ayodele, Aliyu, Owoeye, Ajayi & Sheidu, 2023). According United Nations Scientific and Cultural Organizations UNESCO (2023) Artificial Intelligence has the potential to address some of the biggest challenges in education today, innovate teaching and learning practices and accelerate progress towards Sustainable Development Goal number four (SDG, 4). However, rapid technological developments inevitably bring multiple risks and challenges, which have so far outpaced policy debates and regulatory frameworks. UNESCO as a specialized agency of the United Nations Organizations (UNO) is committed to supporting member states to harness the potentials of AI technologies for achieving Education 2030 Agenda, while ensuring that its application in educational context is guided by the core principles of inclusion and equity. UNESCO's mandate calls for a human-centred approach to Artificial Intelligence". It aims at shifting the conversion to include AI's role in addressing current inequalities regarding access to knowledge, research and the diversity of cultural expressions and to ensure AI's does not widen the technological divides within and between countries. The promise of 'AI for all' must be that everyone can take advantage of technological revolution under way and access its fruits, notably in terms of innovation and knowledge.

Furthermore, Anchi (2020) argued that Artificial Intelligence refers to the use of artificial intelligence applications in the field of education to contribute to student learning. It also refers to the use of AI techniques and tools to improve students' learning processes, personalize teachers course materials, monitor school performance through data analysis by school administrators and general improvement in educational policies. The Cambridge Dictionary cited in Gudzer (2024) defines Artificial Intelligence as "the use or study of computer systems or machines that have some of the qualities of that the human brain has". Example of these qualities include the ability to interpret and produce language in a way that seems human, recognise or create images, solve problems and learn from data supplied to them. Ultimately, the main objective of AI is to optimise routine processes by improving both the speed and efficiency at which they are usually done. Artificial Intelligence has the potential to revolutionize teaching and learning in the universities for the better. It can be used in education in many different purposes, with new capabilities continuing to be discovered as AI develops. It can be used for the benefits of both students and teachers in the curriculum development process for example it can be applied to education in the following ways according to Gudzer (2024):

- 1. Automate administrative task:** this includes marking and grading of work
- 2. Provide personalised learning and support:** teachers could use AI to design personalised learning paths for each student taking into consideration their learning preferences, strengths and weaknesses

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- 3. Provide personalised feedback to students:** education professionals should provide students with explanations of how to improve their work but this process can be time consuming. Some students may find that the feedback they received from their teacher or tutor can be critical and feel embarrassed by it. They may not make use of or engage with the feedback. Instead, AI-generated feedback is more efficient and can be an effective format for students who struggle with responding to constructive feedback.
- 4. Expand online learning opportunities:** for example teachers could use AI to quickly create educational games, quizzes or other activities which assess and teach students in the university. This virtual learning can create a personalised learning experience by monitoring the responses of the students and adapting the task to be easier or more challenging depending on whether they get something right or wrong.
- 5. Create course and lesson plans:** AI-generated plans can be created by inputting the information that needs to be covered during course or lesson. These can be tailored specifically to a class, student or syllabus.
- 6. Identify where students may need extra help:** AI can analyse data including assessments and use that information to identify gaps in knowledge and skills.
- 7. Give education professionals a “virtual assistant”:** this can complete computer-based tasks and reduce their workload
- 8. Give students their own virtual tutor:** this would be personalised entirely to the needs of the individual and provide them with additional support alongside their teacher.

Key Artificial Intelligence Technologies in Education

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has unequivocally emerged as a transformative force, permeating various facets of human life, with curriculum development standing as a notable beneficiary, scholars and researchers have extensively explored the applications of AI in education highlighting, its multifaceted impact. Among the major AI technologies that are instrumental in reshaping educational according to Oluyemisi (2023) are as follows:

Machine Vision (MV): machine vision is synonymous with computer vision and it is one of the major technologies within the realm of Artificial Intelligence. Richter, Marin, Bond and Gouverneur (2019) cited in Oluyemisi (2023) describe machine vision as a capability that empowers software to recognise patterns, make predictions and adapt discovered patterns to unforeseen situations. Operating with high speed, precision and accuracy, machine vision replicate human visual perception, utilizing cameras and computers for functions such as recognition, tracking, object measurement and image processing. This technology finds applications in video surveillance, facial recognition, biometric face scanning, autonomous driving, medical image analysis and archaeology. In the education industry, machine vision proves invaluable for tasks such as attendance recording, monitoring student’s facial expressions, detecting signs of confusion in learners. However, the incorporation of machine vision into education has immense benefit for improving student’s attendance tracking, enhancing classroom dynamics through facial expression monitoring and providing targeted support for students facial challenges in comprehension.

Automated Facial Recognition (FR): machine vision seamlessly integrates with Automated Facial Recognition (FR) for attendance marking in educational settings (Richter, et al, 2019) cited in Oluyemisi (2023). The FR streamlines the attendance process, optimizing class time for both students and teachers while eliminating the need for manual cross checking. The utilization of Automated Facial Recognition coupled with machine vision not only streamlines administrative task but also contributes to a more efficient use of instructional time, fostering an atmosphere conducive for focused and productive learning.

Expert System (ES): Expert System (ES) represent a pivotal facet of Artificial Intelligence (AI) embodying the capacity of computer software to replicate human expertise within a specific domain, facilitating problem solving through meticulously organised knowledge base. Nwigbo and Madhu (2016) cited in Oluyemisi, (2023) underscores the utilization of expert systems in education especially within the Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS). These systems functions like tutors, delivering personalized learning experiences by considering students prior knowledge and abilities. Notably, AI driven career coaches embedded with expert systems provide individualized advice to students, incorporating historical data, experiences, location preferences, skills and career requirements. The integration of expert system into educational frameworks holds significant implications for personalized learning and career guidance. By replicating human expertise, these systems contribute to a tailored and adaptive educational experience aligning with diverse needs, interest and aspirations of the learners.

Natural Language Processing (NLP): Natural Language Processing (NLP) stands at intersection of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and linguistic communication focusing on emulating human natural language patterns. This technology facilitates interaction with intelligent systems using natural languages, both written and spoken. Kolodny (2017) cited in Oluyemisi (2023) emphasizes the integration of Natural Language Processing (NPL) into various applications such as talking

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calculators, enabling oral dictation of signs and numbers. Furthermore, NLP broaden access to information for individuals with visual impairments, hearing difficulties and sensory motor challenges thereby fostering independent conversations. The incorporation of Natural Language Processing (NLP) into educational context offers avenues for enhanced language learning, spelling and grammatical corrections and multilingual support. AI-driven writing assistants based on NLP and Machine Learning present opportunities to augment the writing process, providing feedback and recommendations for improvement.

Machine Learning (ML): machine learning (ML) stands as the forefront of Artificial Intelligence, encompassing the design, training and deployment of models to applications, processes and other machines. Chen (2019) delineates ML's core components to include algorithm, Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), development and training toolkits, data and computing power. Scholars emphasized the ML's dynamic application, utilizing existing data for predictive analysis. In education ML plays a tremendous role in organizing course material selection through content providers, employing feedback and scoring systems for assignment grading, plagiarism detection and students progress assessment. Integration with Natural Language Processing (NPL) enhanced applications like text-to-speech and language translation, exemplified by Google translate. Machine Learning transforms information retrieval by automating suggestions and recommendations based on geographical locations, search history and user preferences, providing students and university lecturer's access to a wealth of internet knowledge. The integration of machine learning into educational practices not only streamlines administrative tasks but also enhances the learning experiences, offering personalized content recommendations and revolutionizing information retrieval for academic purposes.

Deep Learning (DL): Deep Learning (DL) is associated with deep neural networks, represents a sophisticated facet of machine learning primarily utilized in pattern recognition and classification of applications with substantial data sets. Chen (2019) highlights DL's capacity to enable virtual assistants to detect and comprehend speech, images, sounds and videos. In the realm of education, DL significantly augments online learning efficiency as adaptive educational software tailored to meet individual student's needs. This fosters personalised learning experiences, providing avenues for students to receive additional assistance from tutors thereby enriching the overall learning process. The integration of Deep Learning into online learning platforms presents a transformative potential, offering personalised learning experiences and reinforcing the role of technology in addressing individual learning needs.

Robotics: robotics encompasses the design, construction, operation and application of robots. It represents a multifaceted science and technology domain. Odoh (2018) emphasizes that, robots are equipped with sensory capabilities akin to human environmental protection. In education industry, robots offer synchronous lessons to absentee students as exemplified by Avatar ion's technology connected to Microsoft Azure IoT Hub. This facilitates full video and audio connections for students in hospitals or homes allowing them to actively participate in the learning process through a tablet controlled robot. This innovative approach bridges the gap for physically absent students, transforming traditional learning dynamics. The integration of robotics into education holds significant implications for inclusivity, enabling absent students to engage actively in the learning process. This technological advancement fosters more accessible and participatory educational environment.

Advantages of Artificial Intelligence in Curriculum Development

Artificial Intelligence as a new technological development can be of significant advantage especially in the curriculum development in the Nigerian Universities. Gudzer (2024) identified the followings as the advantages of using AI in education:

9. It could reduce workloads by automating processes
10. Personalized education and support could be given to students
11. Due to the personalization of their learning experience, students are often more engaged
12. Teaching can be more creative, which also helps with student's engagements
13. Equal access and opportunities are provided
14. Students are introduced to AI in the classroom which can greatly improve their understanding of the technology and allow them to adapt to its uses elsewhere, such as in the workplace

Disadvantages of Artificial Intelligence in Curriculum Development

Artificial Intelligence as a new technological development can also be used by students to cheat in the examination and also make them lazy. Since it has advantages it must have disadvantages particularly in the curriculum development in the Nigerian Universities. Gudzer (2024) identified the followings as the disadvantages of using AI in education:

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- (iii) Lack of understanding or inefficient training could result in education professionals misusing the AI tools
- (iv) AI tools can be very expensive to purchase and maintain
- (v) Students could use AI to cheat in the exams and to do their work
- (vi) AI-generated content and resources can contain biases and misinformation
- (vii) Students may receive less human contact and become too reliant on AI to educate them
- (viii) There are concerns about how AI impacts privacy and security with a risk that sensitive data could be shared
- (ix) Knowing that AI is used in their learning, students may try to use it for other purposes.

Concept of Curriculum Development

Curriculum Development is a vital component in the educational process. Its scope is exceptionally broad and it involves nearly everyone who is involved in teaching and learning. Curriculum development resources offer guidance for lesson plan preparations that meets the educational standards set by the society. Curriculum development according to Kranthi (2017) is defined as a planned, a purposeful, progressive and systematic process to create a positive movement in the educational system. Every time there are changes or developments happening in the society, the school curricula is affected. Furthermore, curriculum development refers to the principle-driven actions and processes that guide and foster significant learning experiences. Curriculum development is a planned, thoughtful and deliberate course of actions that ultimately enhance the quality and impact of the learning experiences for students (Songhees and Kosapsum, 2018). It also includes the development and organization of learning activities designed to meet intended learning outcomes. It also involves the thoughtful assessment of those learning outcomes. The ultimate goal of curriculum is to enhance the quality and impact of the teaching and learning experiences. Curriculum development moves beyond a content-centred approach to one that considers the relationship between the course/programme learning outcomes, assessment of those learning outcomes and the activities and opportunities designed to facilitate students learning. In developing and designing a course or programme in the Nigerian universities the curriculum developers need to consider the following:

- xvi. Outcomes:** what should the learner know and be able to do at the end of an educational programme?
- xvii. Assessment:** How will learners and teachers know if the learning outcomes have been accomplished?
- xviii. Activities:** What needs to be done to achieve the learning outcomes?

Components of an Effective Curriculum Development Process

The following are the components of curriculum development according to Chauhan (2018):

- 26. **Goals and Objectives:** the goals and objectives of a curriculum define what students are expected to know and be able to do as a result of their educational experiences. These should be specific, measurable and aligned with relevant standards or learning outcomes.
- 27. **Content:** it contains information to be learned at school. It refers to the knowledge, skills and concepts that students will learn. This content may be organized into subjects or topics and may be sequenced in a particular way to support students learning and development.
- 28. **Teaching methods:** it refers to the methods and strategies used to deliver the curriculum content. These include instructional strategies, assessment methods and learning activities that are designed to support student's engagement, motivation and achievement.
- 29. **Evaluation:** it helps to determine whether students are achieving the goals and objectives of the curriculum. This may include formative and summative assessments and providing feedback to students and teachers. It identifies the quality, effectiveness of the programme, process and product of the curriculum.

Roles of Artificial Intelligence in Curriculum Development Process in the Nigerian Universities

In the context of Nigerian universities, the deployment of Artificial Intelligence (AI) holds significant potential for enhancing various aspects of curriculum development. Planning and preparations are a crucial step in curriculum development is streamlined through AI's ability automate routine tasks. This automation not only reduces the administrative burden on academic staff but also allows educators to focus on improving curriculum development process. Additionally, AI tools can generate automated alerts, reports cards and communication with parents, fostering efficient communication channels.

Furthermore, the preparation of instructional resources for effective curriculum development is responsibility shouldered by university management. AI's role in this domain involves the creation of smart content, ranging from digital

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textbooks to instructional snippets and videos. Ogunode et al (2021) cited in Oluyemisi, (2023) highlighted the potentials for AI to facilitate personalization in education, a global trend that aligns with the future of learning. AI tools can create customized learning environment based on educational strategies and goals including augmented reality/virtual reality (AR/VR) lessons and web-based content. Monitoring and evaluation tools powered by AI and machine learning algorithm contribute to identifying areas for effective curriculum development, ensuring that content aligns with diverse learning styles and effectively addresses areas of weakness. This adaptive approach enhances the overall quality of instructional resources and supports educators in refining their teaching methodologies.

In addition to the above, Artificial Intelligence (AI) contributes to the establishment of an artificial intelligence literacy framework within the general education system, fostering students' general interest, sustainable development and global governance. By analysing student's learning abilities and styles, AI facilitates the creation of personalized learning experiences, allowing curriculum developers to plan and develop curricula and learning materials that meet the needs and demands of university students. Nevertheless, the selection of appropriate teaching method is a pivotal responsibility of university lecturers which is streamlined with AI assistance. Intelligent auxiliary teaching system applied extensively in universities, collect and analyse data, match learning styles and establish effective communication between teachers and students. This innovation aids in designing teaching plans, collecting materials, online question answering, testing and evaluating teaching thereby reducing daily work burdens and introducing new teaching methods to foster student's innovative thinking and social skills.

Moreover, the monitoring of students' progress is revolutionized through Artificial Intelligence in Nigerian universities. Xiaolin and Xiajoun (2022) cited in Oluyemisi (2023) highlighted how student's learning trajectories can be monitored, deliver personalized learning resources and provide real time guidance through intelligent teaching platforms. These platforms facilitate interactive session between teachers and students, allowing personalized learning guidance based on data analysis of students' classroom learning. Additionally, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in curriculum development process presents profound implications for the education landscape. This is because AI technologies such as machine learning and natural language processing enable personalized learning experiences, automate assessments and enhance learner engagements. The ability of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to analyse vast amount of student's data contributes to optimization of curriculum design and delivery, ensuring educational contents aligns with individual learning styles and needs.

Furthermore, Artificial Intelligence (AI) helps in addressing scalability challenges and fostering dynamic curriculum development, emphasizing the need for an approach that considers learner's needs, relevant knowledge areas and high-quality educational content. All these roles underscore the transformative potentials of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in shaping more adaptive, personalized and data driven curricula in the universities.

Conclusion

Conclusively, it is very clear that, curriculum development is prompted by evolving societal needs, cultural shifts and responses to economic, social and political dynamics. Technological advancements such as integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) play a significant role in curriculum development process especially in Nigerian universities. It should also be pointed out that, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has the potential of streamlining the administrative tasks, optimize learning experiences and fostering personalized learning in the university system. Recognizing the indispensable role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in curriculum development, it is hoped that, the continued integration of advanced technologies like Artificial Intelligence will be considered in most of the Nigerian universities for curriculum development and general improvement of educational landscape in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the discussion of the key variables above the following recommendations were made:

1. The federal government through the Federal Ministry of Education and National Universities Commission (NUC) should ensure that every university in Nigeria whether public or private meet the minimum standard of integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into their academic programmes before full accreditation will be given to them.
2. The Vice Chancellors of Universities in Nigeria should make sure that academic staff in every department in their universities are adequately trained on how to use Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools when their academic programmes are given full accreditation

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3. The federal government should increase the budgetary allocation of all Nigerian federal universities for the procurement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools for successful curriculum development programme in Nigerian universities
4. The National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) and Nigerian universities should work synergistically to ensure successful Integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies into Nigerian universities for successful accreditation of all their academic programmes
5. There is need for the creation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) unit in the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) directorate of all Nigerian universities in order to ensure the smooth maintenance of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools for long lasting utilization.
6. There is also need for the supply of qualitative Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools that can stand the test of time in all the Nigerian universities for successful integration of Artificial Intelligence technologies into the Nigerian universities.

References

- Anchi, S. (2020). *Revolutionizing Education in the Age of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning*. Newyork: IGI Global Publishers
- Ayodele, S.O., Aliu, J., Owoeye, F.O., Ajayi, F.A. & Sheidu, A.Y. (2023). The Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Curriculum Development and Management. *Journal of Digital Innovations and Contemporary Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*.11 (2), 37-45.
- Chauhan, K.K. (2018). *Components of Curriculum*. New Delhi: NCERT Publications.
- Chen, H. (2019). Success Factors Impacting Artificial Intelligence Adoption Perspective From Telecom Industry in China. *PhD Thesis Submitted to the Faculty of Information and Communication Technology, Old Dominion University, China*.
- Guzder, K. (2024). *What is the Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Education?* Cambridge: University Press
- Kranchi, K. (2021). Curriculum Development. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 22(2), 1-5
- Odoh, L.C., Silas, C.E., Uguanwyi, U.B. & Chukwuani, N.V. (2018). Effects of Artificial Intelligence on the Performance of Accounting Firms in South-East, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 7(2) 1-11
- Olujemisi, M.O.(2023). Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Curriculum Development in Tertiary Education. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 12(2), 192-211
- Songhness, C.V. & Kosapsum, H.J. (2018). *Leading Practices in Curriculum Frameworks*. Oxford: University Press.
- United Nations Education Scientific and Cultural Organization (2023). *Education in the Age Of Artificial Intelligence (AI)*. Geneva: UNESCO Publications

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Qualitative study on integration of Social-Emotional-Learning to improve learning outcome at Basic level of Education in North-East, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explores the integration of Social Emotional Learning (SEL) in improving learning outcomes in Northeast Nigeria, a region grappling with conflict and socio-economic challenges. SEL promotes emotional intelligence, resilience, and interpersonal skills, which are critical for academic and life success. It was a descriptive survey research design that adopted a using qualitative approach was adopted for the study. Data were collected using focus group discussion and in-depth interviews conducted with teachers, students, and policymakers in Borno Adamawa and Yobe states, Nigeria alongside a review of SEL program documents implemented in similar contexts. The data collected was analysed using thematic analysis. The study concludes that Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) has the potential to enhance education, improve emotional stability, promote peacebuilding, and reduce conflict in Northeast Nigeria. Equipping students with SEL skills fosters resilience, social interaction, and academic success in conflict-affected areas. For SEL to be effective, it requires cultural adaptation, community involvement in policy formation, and teacher capacity building to ensure widespread adoption and sustainability. Based on the findings the recommends that the Northeast states government should develop policies to integrate Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) into the curriculum, with adaptations for conflict-affected areas; Train and re-train teachers on SEL programs should be prioritised to equip educators with the necessary skills and resources for effective implementation; and foster collaboration between the government, parents, religious leaders, and local communities is essential to address cultural concerns, ensure acceptance, and promote the sustainability of SEL initiatives.

Keyword: Socio-Emotional Learning, Positive Social Relationship, Academic Outcomes, Emotional Well-being.

Introduction

The Northeast region of Nigeria has been significantly affected by prolonged insurgency, displacement, and socio-economic challenges, resulting in widespread disruptions to education. Many schools have been destroyed, access to quality education is limited, and students face high levels of trauma and psychosocial stress. These challenges have led to poor academic performance, low school attendance, and a lack of social and emotional skills among students. Social Emotional Learning (SEL) offers a framework to address these issues by fostering emotional regulation, empathy, and interpersonal skills (Durlak et al., 2011). In conflict-affected settings like Northeast Nigeria, SEL programs have been shown to promote resilience

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and psychosocial well-being among children (World Bank, 2021). By addressing the emotional scars of conflict, SEL can create a conducive learning and personal growth environment. This study explores how SEL can enhance educational outcomes in Northeast Nigeria, focusing on its application in conflict-affected settings. It highlights the importance of integrating SEL into the education system to build resilience, improve academic performance, and positive social relationships and promote long-term socio-emotional well-being. The integration of SEL in the Nigerian educational frameworks remains limited because only little of stakeholders know its effectiveness in the conflict-ridden context. This study tends to address the gap by exploring how SEL can be integrated into the national curriculum and improve educational outcomes and the socio-economic and well-being of students in Northeast, Nigeria. More so, to identify problems of SEL implementation and profound solutions in the region, providing evidence-based recommendations for policymakers, educators and stakeholders.

The following research questions guide the study.

- (x) What are the academic benefits of implementing SEL activities for students at the basic school level of education in Northeast, Nigeria?
- (xi) How do the SEL activities influence the emotional well-being and social skills of students in conflict-affected communities?
- (xii) What are the roles of teachers, parents and education policymakers in the integration of SEL into the in North-East, Nigeria Basic education system?
- (xiii) How can the SEL program in Basic education be adapted to align with the socio-cultural, and economic realities of Northeast Nigeria?
- (xiv) What are the challenges and possible solutions of SEL implementation at Basic school level of education in the Northeast Nigeria education system?

A descriptive research design adopting a qualitative approach aims to systematically describe the situation of students in Northeast Nigeria and the impact of SEL programs in educational settings of the region. Data were collected using focus group discussion and in-depth interviews conducted with teachers, students, and policymakers in Borno Adamawa and Yobe states, Nigeria alongside a review of SEL program documents implemented in similar contexts. The data collected was analysed using thematic analysis.

Social Emotional Learning (SEL)

Durlak et al. (2011) defined SEL as the process through which individuals acquire and effectively apply the knowledge, attitudes, and skills necessary to understand and manage emotions, set and achieve positive goals, feel and show empathy for others, establish and maintain positive relationships, and make responsible decisions. SEL is defined as the process of developing self-awareness, self-control, and interpersonal skills that are vital for school, work, and life success. Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL, 2022). Taylor et al. (2017) SEL involves structured educational programs that focus on developing emotional intelligence and interpersonal skills to enhance students' ability to succeed academically and socially.

Importance of Social Emotional Learning (SEL) at Basic education level

Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) has demonstrated significant positive impacts in Northeast Nigeria, a region affected by conflict and displacement. Studies indicate that SEL programs help children and adolescents develop emotional regulation skills, and enhance academic outcomes, enabling them to manage stress, anxiety, and trauma more effectively.

The Role of SEL in Enhancing Academic Outcomes at Basic education level

SEL helps students in Northeast Nigeria improve their focus, persistence, and classroom engagement, resulting in better academic performance. Research has shown that SEL improves students' academic outcomes by fostering self-regulation and motivation, which are critical for learning, especially in conflict-affected settings (Durlak et al., 2011). Studies have consistently shown that SEL improves academic outcomes, reduces behavioural problems, and enhances emotional well-being (Taylor et al., 2017). For conflict-affected regions, SEL provides a critical tool for helping students cope with trauma and rebuild their lives. The implementation of SEL in Northeast Nigeria has shown that emotional and social skills are foundational to academic success. Students participating in SEL programs exhibit better classroom behaviour, increased motivation, and enhanced concentration, leading to improved academic performance (Hassan, R., Olaniyi, A., & Yusuf, K., 2021). Teachers have reported that SEL practices, such as mindfulness exercises and collaborative learning, create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment, even in resource-constrained settings.

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The Role of SEL in Enhanced Emotional and Social Competence in Basic Education

In conflict-affected areas, children often experience trauma that impacts their ability to learn and interact socially. SEL programs provide tools to address these issues by helping students develop emotional regulation and resilience. Studies conducted in post-conflict regions such as South Sudan and Syria found that SEL improved students' emotional well-being, reduced aggressive behaviours, and fostered better peer relationships (World Bank, 2021). Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) has demonstrated significant positive impacts in Northeast Nigeria, a region affected by conflict and displacement. Studies indicate that SEL programs help children and adolescents develop emotional regulation skills, enabling them to manage stress, anxiety, and trauma more effectively. For instance, interventions implemented in internally displaced persons (IDP) camps showed marked improvements in participants' ability to identify and manage emotions, which contributed to better mental health outcomes (Obiakor et al., 2020). SEL addresses the emotional needs of children by providing a safe environment for expressing feelings and managing stress. This is critical in Northeast Nigeria, where children face multiple stressors such as displacement, poverty, and insecurity (UNICEF, 2022). Social Emotional Learning (SEL) equips individuals with essential competencies such as self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making (CASEL, 2022). These competencies are not only foundational for academic success but also for overall well-being. Studies have shown that SEL helps mitigate behavioural issues, enhances emotional resilience, and reduces symptoms of anxiety and depression (Taylor et al., 2017).

The Role of SEL in Promoting Peacebuilding and Reducing Community Conflict in Basic education

SEL plays a critical role in peacebuilding efforts in Northeast Nigeria. By addressing the root causes of aggression and promoting empathy, SEL initiatives help reduce tensions between conflicting groups. Programs like the “Education in Emergencies” framework have incorporated SEL to teach nonviolent communication and collaborative problem-solving, fostering mutual understanding among youth from diverse backgrounds (UNICEF, 2021). Furthermore, SEL contributes to reintegration efforts for former child soldiers and other marginalized groups. Skills in emotional regulation and interpersonal interaction are crucial for their rehabilitation and acceptance back into society (Benson et al., 2020). These initiatives also empower young people to become agents of peace within their communities, thereby reducing cycles of violence and fostering long-term stability. By teaching empathy, conflict resolution, and interpersonal skills, SEL fosters positive peer relationships and reduces bullying and aggression. These skills are important in fostering social cohesion in a region marked by ethnic and religious tensions (Ajayi et al., 2020). Adaptability of SEL to align with the sociocultural and economic realities of Northeast. The SEL program can be adapted to align with the socio-cultural, and economic realities of Northeast Nigeria.

Cultural Relevance and Sensitivity in Basic education

The integration of local values and norms into SEL programs is crucial for their acceptance and effectiveness. As noted by Elias et al. (1997), culturally relevant SEL programs foster greater engagement among students and communities. For instance, incorporating community-centric practices such as communal harmony and respect for elders into SEL frameworks ensures alignment with local traditions. Furthermore, engaging religious and community leaders to advocate for SEL programs enhances credibility and local ownership, which is critical in culturally conservative regions like Northeast Nigeria.

Trauma-Informed Practices in Basic education

Children in conflict-affected regions often face significant psychological distress. Taylor et al. (2017) highlight that trauma-informed SEL approaches, such as emotional regulation and mindfulness, can help children process traumatic experiences and rebuild resilience. The findings reinforce the need for SEL programs in Northeast Nigeria to include components that address trauma and provide psychosocial support, which is particularly relevant given the region's ongoing insecurity and displacement issues.

Community Involvement in Basic education

The study also underscores the importance of involving parents and local communities in the design and implementation of SEL programs. According to Adamu (2019), community participation enhances the sustainability and effectiveness of educational interventions by fostering a sense of collective responsibility. Engaging parents through workshops and mobilizing community resources ensures that SEL initiatives are both cost-effective and widely supported.

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Economic Feasibility in Basic education

Given the economic constraints in Northeast Nigeria, SEL programs must be designed to be low-cost and resource efficiency. Durlak et al. (2011) argues that SEL programs that leverage existing resources and train local facilitators are more sustainable in low-income settings. The findings advocate for the use of locally available materials and volunteer training to minimize costs while maximizing impact.

Flexibility in Delivery in Basic education

Embedding SEL into existing school curricula and informal education settings is essential for reaching displaced and underserved populations. Zins et al. (2004) emphasize that integrating SEL into core subjects like religious studies or civic education reduces the burden on teachers while ensuring that all students benefit from these programs. In Northeast Nigeria, this approach can be particularly beneficial for students in IDP camps or informal learning centres.

Monitoring and Evaluation in Basic education

Finally, the study highlights the importance of monitoring and evaluating SEL programs to ensure their relevance and effectiveness. Collecting community feedback and assessing outcomes such as improved student behaviour and attendance are critical steps in refining and sustaining these programs (UNICEF, 2022).

Discussion of Findings

Improved Academic Outcomes through SEL in Basic education

The findings revealed that students who participated in SEL programs demonstrated better academic outcomes, particularly in literacy and numeracy. Teachers reported that SEL-equipped students showed increased focus, perseverance, and tolerance, leading to better academic performance. These outcomes align with Durlak et al. (2011), who found that SEL interventions improve academic performance. The study corroborates Ajayi et al.'s (2020) findings in Nigerian IDP camps, where SEL improved student engagement and learning outcomes, even in challenging environments.

Enhanced Emotional and Social Competence in Basic education

Findings show that both parents and teachers testified that students attending schools with Socio-Emotional Learning programs have acquired emotional and social skills. Students have been more confident and assertive in the expression of their emotions and exhibit good social behaviours, resolving peer conflicts and building positive relationships. Teachers also noted there is a decline in classroom aggression and bullying fostering a better collaborative learning environment. These findings align with the findings of the World Bank (2021) which demonstrated that Social Emotional Learning in conflict-affected communities like South Sudan reduced aggressive behaviour and improved peer relationships. These findings are consistent with the World Bank (2021) study, which demonstrated that SEL in conflict-affected regions such as South Sudan reduced aggressive behaviours and improved peer relationships. Furthermore, Taylor et al. (2017) highlighted that Social Emotional Learning enhances long-term emotional stability, which improves classroom dynamics. The results emphasise that SEL programs address emotional and social deficits in conflict-affected children, promoting interpersonal skills critical for personal growth and community rebuilding.

Promoting Peacebuilding and Reducing Community Conflict in Basic education.

Teachers and parents highlighted how SEL can address the root causes of aggression by teaching children nonviolent communication and collaborative problem-solving skills. This view is consistent with the “Education in Emergencies” framework, which incorporates SEL to promote mutual understanding among diverse groups (UNICEF, 2021). The alignment of these perspectives underscores the critical role SEL plays in reducing tensions and building peaceful communities. The findings also support the notion that SEL is vital for the reintegration of former child soldiers and marginalized youth. Parents and teachers noted the importance of emotional regulation and interpersonal skills in helping these groups reintegrate into society. This is echoed by Benson et al. (2020), who emphasize the transformative role of SEL in rehabilitation and acceptance, empowering young people to act as agents of peace. Both parents and teachers agree that teaching empathy, conflict resolution, and interpersonal skills fosters positive relationships among students and reduces bullying and aggression. This aligns with Ajayi et al. (2020), who highlighted the significance of SEL in promoting social cohesion in regions characterized by ethnic and religious tensions. These skills are critical for building harmonious interactions and addressing the challenges of diversity in the region. The shared perspectives of parents and teachers in Northeast Nigeria reinforce the importance of integrating SEL

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into educational programs to address not only academic challenges but also social and emotional issues. By fostering peacebuilding, promoting social cohesion, and supporting marginalized groups, SEL contributes to long-term stability and community resilience in the region (Adamu, 2019).

Roles of Teachers, Parents, and Policymakers in the Integration of SEL

The roles of teachers in implementing SEL in Basic education

The teachers and parents considered teachers as the primary implementors of SEL, creating a conducive and supportive classroom where students can develop social and emotional competencies. The teachers play a vital role in modelling SEL skills such as respect, tolerance, remembering, focusing, empathy, communication and conflict-solving for the students. “Teachers can observe students' emotional and social needs, providing targeted support to those struggling with trauma or behavioural challenges”. “Through strategies like mindfulness exercises, peer group activities, and positive reinforcement, teachers can help students manage stress and build resilience. Teachers collaborate with parents to ensure consistency between school and home environment in fostering SEL.

The roles of parents in implementing SEL in Basic education

The study asserted that parents provide a supportive home environment where parents reinforce SEL principles by encouraging emotional expression, empathy, logical thinking, and rational decision-making in their children.

“We work closely with teachers to understand SEL goals and provide feedback about our children's attitudes and behaviours at home.” Parent. “The parent advocate for the inclusion of SEL into the school’s curriculum and voicing the importance of SEL and education to community leaders, policymakers and political class.” Teachers.

The roles of policymakers in implementing SEL Basic education

The findings of the study show that policymakers provide funding for SEL programs teacher training, SEL curriculum development and other materials necessary for effective SEL implementations. They set clear guidance for integrating SEL into schools with flexibility for culturally and religiously sensitive and regional adaptations. “Policymakers incorporate SEL programs into regional and national educational policies, ensuring it becomes a standardized part of the curriculum and creating safe and stable learning environment” Parent Adamawa. “Government are responsible for setting a framework to assess the relevance, coherence, efficiency and effectiveness of the SEL program by continuous data collection and analysis on the children academic performance, attendance, emotional well-being and social behaviours to inform decision-making.” Borno Teacher.

Adaptability of SEL to align with the sociocultural and economic realities of Northeast

The findings of the study revealed that the perspectives of teachers and students in Northeast Nigeria aligned with existing literature on the adaptability of SEL with norms, values and beliefs of the people of the area to achieve its objective of improving educational outcomes. Teachers and parents recognize the need for culturally appropriate SEL programs to address the socio-economic and trauma-related challenges faced by students. This aligns with the findings of Elias et al. (1997), who emphasized the importance of tailoring SEL programs to local values and norms for greater acceptance and impact. Additionally, this study revealed that teachers' and parents' participation in the implementation of SEL mirrors Adamu's (2019) that community participation enhances school enrolment, attendance, and retention. Similarly, the recognition of trauma-informed practices for rebuilding resilience in children of Northeast Nigeria echoes the findings of Taylor et al. (2017), highlighting the necessity of equipping schools with programs to support students' emotional well-being in conflict-affected areas. These aligned views underscore the importance of designing SEL programs that reflect local realities, involve key stakeholders, and address both academic and psychosocial needs, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes.

Challenges in SEL Implementation in Basic education

Although most respondents viewed SEL is playing a vital role in managing children's socio-emotional behaviour the study revealed there are significant challenges in implementing SEL in Northeast Nigeria, as outlined by teachers and parents as follows:

15. Inadequate Socio-Emotional Learning Teachers: There is a limited number of teachers undergone SEL training, and most of the teachers lack the skills to handle SEL lessons in their respective classrooms.

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16. Teachers and parents felt that most of the available SEL materials were borrowed from the white men's land concepts, around respect, emotional expression and conflict resolution needed to be adapted into the local northeast context which is aligned with the norms and values of people of the Northeast. This finding resonates with Ajayi et al.'s (2020) recommendation that the SEL program must be culturally sensitive to ensure acceptance and effectiveness.

17. Limited SEL Resources: The findings of this study revealed that most of the in Northeast Nigeria have limited or no basic SEL resources to implement SEL programs in their schools' systemic challenges in conflict-affected areas as also highlighted by UNICEF (2022) and call for targeted investment in education in such regions.

18. The study identified a gap in teacher training and policy support for SEL implementation. While the benefits of SEL were evident, its integration into the curriculum remains limited.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the SEL program has the transformative potential of enhancing educational outcomes, improving emotional stability, promoting peacebuilding and reducing community conflict in Northeast Nigeria. Equipping students with essential skills can address the unique challenges of conflict-affected areas, fostering resilience, positive social interaction and academic success. Having culturally adapted SEL programs, involving the local community in the formation of SEL policy formation and implementation, and teachers' capacity building to ensure widespread adoption of SEL programs are the preconditions of SEL achieving its purpose.

Recommendations

Despite these challenges, the findings underscore the potential of SEL to transform education in Northeast Nigeria. Key recommendations include:

1. The Northeast state government should provide policies for the integration of SEL into the state curriculum and implementation in classrooms with specific adaptations for conflict-affected areas.
2. The Northeast state government should train and re-train large-scale teachers on programs focused on SEL and should be prioritized to equip educators with the necessary skills and resources required for the implementation of the SEL programs.
3. Collaboratively involvement and participation of state governments parents, religious leaders, and local communities in SEL initiatives can address cultural concerns and ensure buy-in and sustainability.
4. This suggests that the inclusion of SEL in schools across Northeast Nigeria could address significant educational disparities caused by prolonged conflict, providing students with the skills needed to overcome academic and personal challenges.

References

- Adamu, O., B. (2019). Role of community in primary school administration in Jigawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Development*, 45(3), 123–135.
- Ajayi, K., Adeniran, A., & Adeola, G. (2020). The role of social-emotional learning in conflict-affected areas: Insights from Nigerian IDP camps. *Journal of Educational Development*, 45(3), 123–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jed.2020.04.015>
- Benson, P. L., Scales, P. C., Hamilton, S. F., & Sesma, A. (2020). Positive youth development: Theory, research, and applications. In *Handbook of youth and young adulthood* (3rd ed., pp. 118–137).
- Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL). (2020). *What is SEL?* Retrieved from <https://casel.org/what-is-sel/>
- Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2011). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child Development*, 82(1), 405–432. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01564.x>
- Elias, M. J., Zins, J. E., Weissberg, R. P., Frey, K. S., Greenberg, M. T., Haynes, N. M., Kessler, R., Schwab-Stone, M. E., & Shriver, T. P. (1997). *Promoting social and emotional learning: Guidelines for educators*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Hassan, R., Olaniyi, A., & Yusuf, K. (2021). The role of social and emotional learning in reducing community conflict in Northeast Nigeria. *Journal of Peace Education*, 18(2), 159–175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17400201.2021.1874989>
- Jones, S. M., Bailey, R., & Jacob, R. (2019). Social-emotional learning: A new synthesis. *The Future of Children*, 27(1), 13–32. <https://doi.org/10.1353/foc.2019.0001>
- Mercy Corps. (2019). *Building bridges: The impact of SEL in fragile and conflict-affected regions*. Retrieved from <https://www.mercycorps.org>

Qualitative study on integration ... (Adamu, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080476>

- Olatunde, A. M., Adamu, Y., & Ibrahim, K. (2022). Building resilience through SEL in displaced populations: Evidence from Northeast Nigeria.
- Osofsky, J. D. (1999). The impact of violence on children. *The Future of Children*, 9(3), 33–49.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1602780>
- Osher, D., Cantor, P., Berg, J., Steyer, L., & Rose, T. (2016). Drivers of human development: How relationships and context shape learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 21(1), 1–31.
- Taylor, R. D., Oberle, E., Durlak, J. A., & Weissberg, R. P. (2017). Promoting positive youth development through school-based social and emotional learning interventions: A meta-analysis of follow-up effects. *Child Development*, 88(4), 1156–1171. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12864>
- UNICEF. (2022). *Education under attack: Challenges for children in Northeast Nigeria*. Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org>
- UNICEF. (2021). *Education in emergencies: Learning for peace in Nigeria*. UNICEF Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria>
- World Bank. (2021). *Education and resilience: Lessons from conflict-affected countries*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org>
- World Bank. (2018). *The promise of education for conflict-affected youth: Social and emotional learning in Nigeria*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org>
- World Bank. (2016). *Education crisis in Northeast Nigeria: Background report*. World Bank.
- Zins, J. E., Weissberg, R. P., Wang, M. C., & Walberg, H. J. (2004). *Building academic success on social and emotional learning: What does the research say?* Teachers College Press

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Salary and Fringe Benefits as Correlates of Attrition among Public Primary School Teachers in Borno State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was a comparative analysis between salary and fringe benefits on attrition among public primary school teachers in Borno State, Nigeria. The study determined relationship between salary, and fringe benefits and teacher attrition. Based on the objectives; to determine the relationship between salary and teacher turnover in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria and to determine the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher turnover in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria the research tested null hypotheses on the relationship between salary and teacher attrition and the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition at 0.05 level of significance. The study used correlation research design. The population of the study were 18,758 teachers and a sample of 1, 876 teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session were randomly selected. The researchers used questionnaire and proforma for data collection. The data collected were analyzed and Hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). The findings of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between salary and teacher attrition and fringe benefits and teacher attrition. Based on the findings, the researchers recommend that Borno State Government should make improvements on the salary of teachers as the study showed that teachers were not satisfied with the monthly salary, they receive which led to teacher attrition and Borno State Government should make improvements on the fringe benefits enjoyed by teachers as the study showed that teachers were not satisfied with the fringe benefits, they enjoy which led to teacher attrition among others.

Keywords: Personnel Remuneration, Teacher Attrition, public primary Schools

Introduction

Education has remained as an instrument of change and national development. Thus, the National Policy on Education (2013) states that the Federal Government of Nigeria has adopted education as an instrument per excellence for effecting national development. Teachers are the ones to carry out this vital task of meeting Nigeria's target of E.F.A. Adamu (2010) stressed that no nation develops without education and education is not possible without teachers because teachers inculcate what is worthwhile to learners who in turn utilize the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes to develop the nation. However, teachers who are saddled with this responsibility of effecting national change in the nation's economic manpower development for global deliberation on Education for All (E.F.A) are exiting the teaching profession in large numbers especially in the Nigerian schools, primary schools in Borno State inclusive. Nel and Werner (2009) defined personnel attrition as the movement of employee in and out of the bondage of the organization. The rate of teacher attrition has become an issue of concern to both policy makers, educational planners and administrators which attracted series of researches in both developing and developed nations of the world. In Nigeria, the rate of teacher attrition varies within geo-political zones (Wushishi, Foori, Basra & Baki, 2013). Staff turnover can be perceived as a final or permanent act. Remuneration has great influence on teacher attrition all over the world Assefa (2011), Egu, Nwuju and Chionye (2011) and Wushishi Foori, Basri and Baki (2013). The remuneration structure of any organization which ensures congruence

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between employee and organizational goals is sure of reducing cases of attrition, Ghana National Association of Teachers (GNAT, 2010).

Nwapa (2019) conducted a study that determined the causes and consequences of male teachers' attrition in primary and secondary schools in Ebonyi State, Nigeria and the result of the study revealed that low level of salary and poor working condition contributed to male teachers' attrition. Cyril, Ugwuada and Bello (2015) examined the causes of science and technical teachers' attrition and strategies for retention in Adamawa State secondary schools. The findings of Cyril, Ugwuada and Bello (2015) revealed that poor condition of service, poor salary and wages contributed to teacher attrition. Ekabu (2019) conducted research on the relationship between the level of remuneration and turnover intentions of public secondary school teachers in Meru County. The findings showed that remuneration has a negative and an inverse relationship with turnover intention. Caluza (2019) determined the impact of job satisfaction on teacher turnover in independent Christian schools in Johannesburg, South Africa which showed that there was no significant relationship between salary and attrition. Onesmus, Waita, Beth and Julius (2016) conducted a study on factors influencing teacher attrition in public secondary schools in Mbooni East Sub-County. The findings of their study revealed that perpetual teacher attrition was due to poor salaries among other factors. Nguyen (2020) conducted a study on teacher attrition and retention in Kansas. The findings revealed that teachers' salary may influence teachers' decision to stay or leave. Sribayak, Tangkiengsirisin and Hongboontri (2018) conducted a study on factors influencing teacher attrition in Thai context and salary was believed to be among the reasons why EFL teachers leave or consider leaving their teaching career. Assefa, (2011) conducted research to determine factors that cause teachers' turnover in government and private secondary schools in Addis Ababa city administration in a comparative manner and the findings showed that inadequate salary that teachers get was among other factors that aggravate the turnover of teachers both in government and private schools.

Salisu (2020) conducted a study on the influence of post- primary school teachers' job satisfaction and empowerment on teacher turnover intention in Katsina State, Nigeria and revealed that teachers' professional development is one of the things that influences teacher turnover intentions. Madumere, Ukala and Akachuku (2018) determined the management of teacher attrition rate for quality education delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study concluded that better services and good welfare packages in terms of fringe benefits for teachers can reduce teacher attrition rate. Paying attention to teachers by giving equal regards with other professions will increase teachers' retention. Hardianto, Rugaiyah and Rosyidi (2019) conducted a study to see the effect of reward and job satisfaction on teachers' turnover intentions and showed that there is significant relationship between fringe benefit and teacher attrition. Okeke, Okoforcha and Ekwesianya (2019) examined the causes of teacher attrition and strategies for teacher retention in secondary schools in Anambra State and the findings of the study showed that teacher attrition takes place for a number of reasons which included low social recognition for teachers and lack of opportunities for professional development. Kyalo, James and Kimencu (2018) carried out a study which determined how human resource management practices predict tutor turnover intentions in primary teacher training colleges (PTTCs) in Kenya and found that training, career development and performance management were poorly practiced and that they significantly and negatively predict tutor turnover intentions. Okey (2020) examined job satisfaction and teacher turnover in the management of secondary education in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria and the findings revealed that a relationship exists between job satisfaction and teacher turnover.

Agboola and Offong (2018) examined the relationship between occupational incentives and teacher retention in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria and revealed that significant relationship existed between job security, remuneration, promotion, welfare and teacher retention in private secondary schools. Mugo (2018) conducted a study on factors contributing to labour turnover among public secondary school teachers in Kenya and identified the factors that contributed to high turnover were recognition and involvement during decision making, lack of time for self-development, lack of an effective reward system, lack of further professional development for teachers or in-service trainings. Kyara (2013) determined how job satisfaction affects teachers' performance in primary schools in Tanzania. The study revealed that there was a very low level of satisfaction among teachers in terms of school supervision, communication feedback, availability of teaching and learning materials, school-parents' relationship, on the job training, teachers' promotion system (bar system), leave payment for teachers and the availability of public transport facilities.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to compare analysis between salary and fringe benefits on attrition among public primary school teachers in Borno State, Nigeria.

The specific objectives of the study were to determine;

- 1 relationship between salary and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.
- 2 relationships between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.

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Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between salary and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study was a correlational research design which determined the relationship between personnel remuneration and teacher attrition in Borno State public primary schools, Nigeria over a period of five years (2016-2020). The design was correlational because it measured relationship between personnel remuneration and teacher attrition. Correlation provides an estimate of the strength of association between variables or the extent to which one variable is correlated with another (Brown & Dawling, 1998). The population for this study were all public primary school teachers in Borno State. As at the end of October, 2020, there were three hundred and forty-seven (347) primary schools with a total of eighteen thousand, seven hundred and fifty-eight (18,758) teachers (Borno State Universal Basic Education Board, 2021). The researchers considered ten percent (10%) of the teachers and twenty percent (20%) of the schools as sample of the population. The sample size for this study was one thousand eight hundred and seventy-six (1,876) teachers of the seventy (70) schools that were selected for the study. Two research instruments were used to obtain data for the study. The instruments used in this study were a set of questionnaires and a set of proforma. A self-designed inventory questionnaire on personnel remuneration and attrition of primary school teachers in Borno State was used for this study. The questionnaire consists of two sections, that is, Sections A and B. Section A sought for information on the demographic characteristics of the respondents such as name of the school, gender, age, qualification and length of service. Section B consists of 30 items that elicited for information on personnel remuneration. The proforma was used to record information on teacher attrition from official records. The data collected for the study were recorded and reduced to units for statistical analysis. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) was used to test hypotheses. Two variables are said to be correlated when an increase in one variable is regularly accompanied by an increase or decrease in the other (Brown & Dawling, 1998)

Presentation of Results

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between salary and teacher attrition in Borno State Public Primary Schools. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the extent of relationship between salary and teacher attrition in Borno State public primary schools and the summary of the analysis is presented in the table below:

Table 1 Summary of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the relationship between salary and teacher attrition in Borno State Public Primary Schools

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	p-value	Remark
Salary	69	2.97	0.94	67	-0.639	0.00	Reject H ₀₂
Teacher Attrition	69	7.12	4.70				

The finding revealed that there is significant relationship between salary and teacher attrition with Pearson Product Moment Correlation $r = -0.639$. The table also revealed that the relationship between salary and teacher attrition is statistically significant because the p-value (0.00) is less than the level of significance (0.05). Therefore, hypothesis one was rejected and hence salary is a determinant of teacher attrition.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in Borno State public primary schools. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the extent of relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in Borno State public primary schools and the summary of the analysis is presented in the table below:

Table 4 Summary of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in Borno State Public Primary Schools

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	p-value	Remark
Fringe Benefit	69	3.22	0.85	67	-0.564	0.00	Reject H ₀₄
Teacher Attrition	69	7.12	4.70				

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The finding revealed that there is significant relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition with Pearson Product Moment Correlation $r = -0.564$. The table also revealed that the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition is statistically significant because the p-value (0,00) is less than the level of significance (0,05). Therefore, hypothesis two was rejected and hence fringe benefits has significant influence on teacher attrition.

Summary of Findings

The following were the main findings of the study:

1. There is significant relationship between salary and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.
2. There is significant relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in public primary schools, Borno State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study with respect to the relationship between salary and teacher attrition in public primary schools in Borno State, found that salary is significantly related to teacher attrition and had significant influence on teacher attrition. This finding is supported by the findings of Wushishi, Fooki, Basra and Baki (2013) which equally revealed that salary has great influence on teacher attrition in Niger state, Nigeria. Nwapa (2019) reported that salary and poor working condition contributed to the male teacher attrition in secondary schools in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Wondimneh (2017) reported that the most significant condition for intentions of teacher turnover were lack of interest in the teaching profession and dissatisfaction with their current salary. However, this finding disagreed with that of Caluza (2019) which indicated that teachers did not intend to leave their jobs despite dissatisfaction with their salary. With regard to the findings on the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition in public primary schools in Borno State, the study found a significant relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition. This finding is supported by Salisu (2020) who reported that lack of professional development is one of the things that influenced teacher turnover in post primary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. This finding also agreed with that of Madumere, Ukala and Akachuku (2018) who reported that better services and good welfare packages in terms of fringe benefits for teachers can reduce teacher turnover rate. The finding of this study also concurred with that of Hardianto, Rugaiyah and Rosyidi (2019) which revealed that there is direct negative effect of rewards especially non-monetary rewards on turnover intentions. The finding of this study in terms of the relationship between fringe benefits and teacher attrition equally agreed with that of Bentil, Acquah and Akyiaw (2019) who found that teacher retention strategies such as improved salary, remuneration, provision of housing scheme, regular in-service training for teachers and scholarships for further studies to be likely boost their retention and reduce attrition.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that there was significant influence of salary and fringe benefits on teacher attrition in public primary schools in Borno State, Nigeria. It is concluded that lack reasonable salary and reasonable fringe benefits influenced teacher attrition in the public primary schools in Borno State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Borno State government should make improvement on the salary of teachers as the study showed the teachers were not satisfied with the amount they receive as salary which led to teacher attrition.
2. The Borno State Government should ensure that teachers enjoy benefits such as in-service training, payment of teachers' medical bills and provision of accommodation as the study revealed that teachers do not enjoy payment of medical bills or accommodation by the government and in-service training are not easily enjoyed by teachers which equally caused teacher turnover.

References

- Adamu, A. (2010). A Technique of improving staff morale in public secondary schools in Bauchi State. Unpublished Master Thesis; Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria.
- Agboola, B. & Offiong, D. E. (2018). Incentives and teacher retention in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 7(3):263-277.
- Assefa, H. (2011). Major Causes of Teachers' Turnover in Selected Government and Private Secondary Schools in Addis Ababa: A Comparative Study. Unpublished Master Dissertation, Kenyatta University.
- Bentil, J.; Acquah, S. & Akyiaw, S. O. (2019). Perception of public basic school teachers on the factors influencing teacher attrition and retention in the Atiwa District in the Eastern Region of Ghana. *British Journal of Education*, 7(11):122-140.

Salary and Fringe Benefits ... (Galtimari, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080519>

- Borno State Universal Basic Education Board (2021). Report of the committee of primary school teachers in Borno State, 2020.
- Caluza, M. (2019). Impact of job satisfaction on teacher turnover in an independent Christian school in Johannesburg, South Africa. *Journal of Management and Administration*, 3(2):31-54.
- Cyril, M. U., Ugwuada, O. R. & Bello, A. B. (2015). Causes of science and technical teacher attrition and strategies for retention in Adamawa State, Secondary Schools. *International Journal of Vocational and Technical Education*, 7(4):33-39.
- Egu, R.H., Nwuju, E.M., & Chionye, A. (2011). Teachers attrition in Nigerian schools. a case study of the UBE. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies (JETERAPS)*, 2(2):108-112.
- Ekabu, P. K. (2019). The level of remuneration and turnover intention of public secondary school teachers in Meru County: a mixed method study. *European Scientific Journal*, 15(14):1-18.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). National Policy on Education (Revised). Lagos, Nigeria.
- Ghana National Association of Teacher, GNAT (2009). Teacher attrition in Ghana pre-primary education system.
- Hardianto, H.; Rugaiyah, R & Rosyidi, U. (2019). The effect of reward and job satisfaction towards turnover intention of private junior high school teachers. *International e-Journal of Educational Studies (IEJES)*, 3(6):128-140.
- Kyalo A. M.; James M. K. & Kimencu, L. (2018). How do human resource management practices predict employee turnover intentions: an empirical survey of teacher training colleges in Kenya. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 9(4):201-213.
- Kyara, T. E. (2013). The effect of primary school teachers' job satisfaction on their work performance in Kinondoni District, Tanzania. Unpublished M.ed Dissertation. the Open University of Tanzania.
- Madumere-Obike, C. U., Ukala, C. C. & Nwabueze, A. (2018). Managing teacher attrition rate for quality education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Educational Planning*, 25(4):42-58.
- Mugo, E. W. (2018). Factors contributing to labour turnover among public secondary school teachers in Kenya: a case of Embu County. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 6(2):363-384.
- Nel, P & Werner, N. (2008). Structural equations modelling test of a turnover theory: cross sectional and longitudinal analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 76(3):350-366.
- Nguyen, T. (2020). Teacher attrition and retention in kasus: a case study of geographically rural states with persistent teacher shortage. *Online Journal Rural Research and Policy*, 15(1):1-16.
- Nwakpa, P. (2019). Male Teacher Attrition: Causes and Consequences in Ebonyi State Public Primary Schools. *Asian Journal of Applied Sciences*, 2(6):26-37.
- Okeke, N. I.; Okaforcha, C. & Ekwesianya, A. (2019). Attrition and strategies for teacher retention in secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Education, Humanities and Management Sciences*, 1(1):1-16.
- Okey, S. M. (2020). Job satisfaction and teacher turnover in the management of quality education in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journal (Ire)*, 3(11):12-16.
- Onesmus, K.; Waita K. J.; Beth, K. & Juluis, A. (2016). Factors influencing teacher attrition in public secondary schools in Mbooni-East Sub-County, Kenya. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 4(3):367-379.
- Salisu, A. Y. (2020). Teachers' job satisfaction and empowerment on turnover intentions in Katsina State, Nigeria. *Journal of Islamic Economics Social Science*, 1(2):33-45.
- Sribayak, V.; Tangkiengsirisin, S. & Hongboontri, S. (2018). Factors influencing teacher attrition in a Thai context. *LEARN Journal: Language Education and Acquisition Research Network Journal*, 11(2):84-102.
- Wondimneh, M. (2017). Intentions of teachers' turnover in alpha karanyo primary and secondary school. Unpublished Med Dissertation, Addis Ababa University, Ethiopia.
- Wushishi, A.A. Foori, F.S., Basri, R., & Baki, R. (2013). Additional discoveries on cause of teachers' attrition. *Greener Journal of Educational Research*, 3(10):462-468.

Assessment of Material Resource Management Practices On Administration of Public Universities in South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated assessment of material resource management practices on administration of public universities in South-South, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The design adopted for the study was descriptive survey design. The population was 11,174 staff from four public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria. A sample size of 559 staff was used were selected for the study. The sample was selected using a multi-stage sampling procedure technique. The instrument for data collection was researchers-structured questionnaire titled “Material Resource Management Practices and Administration Questionnaire (MRMPAQ)”. The questionnaire was validated by three experts in Faculty of Education Benue State University, Makurdi. A reliability test of the instrument was conducted on 30 staff from University of Calabar, Nigeria, using Cronbach Alpha. The result yielded a value index of 0.92 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. Chi-square test of goodness of fit was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that material resource planning and purchasing practices have positive significant impact on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria. The study concluded that material resource management practices have improved administration of public universities. The study recommended that public university administrators in Nigeria should ensure regular and proper material resources management focused on planning and purchasing of material resources in their universities in order to enhance administration of public universities in Nigeria.

Keywords: Material resource management, planning, purchasing, administration of public universities

Introduction

Administration is an essential activity in any formal organization including public universities. It is for this reason that one may rightly say that for any organization to achieve success, effective administration cannot be overemphasized. Globally, there have been issues of ineffective administration of public universities over the years. Universities seem to be confronted with numerous challenges. Romina (2023) opines that some of the issues confronting higher education across the globe including Nigerian universities are lack of fund, lack of facilities, frequent labour disputes and closure of universities, inadequate resources and ineffective material resources management. Although Nigerian government and higher education administrators seem to address these issues, Nigerian universities still seem to experience ineffective administration. Administration is the prudent management of scarce and available resources with emphasis on high degree of accountability from subordinates directed towards the achievement of goals and objectives (Venkatesh, 2021). It involves the evaluation and appraisal of results of educational efforts for the purpose of entrenching accountability to all those who have interest in educational enterprise like public universities.

Public universities are higher institutions of learning owned and managed by federal and state governments. Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) describes these institutions as citadels of learning for promoting academic excellence for national growth. Public universities are essential for training and development of top level manpower. Bachelor’s degrees and higher degrees such as masters and doctor of philosophy (PhD) degrees are awarded by universities. The importance of public universities cannot be emphasized due to its centrality in the nation’s development. The government of Nigeria particularly Cross River and Akwa Ibom States seem to pay much attention to effective administration of public universities through provision of resources (human, material, financial, information and time). Despite this effort the public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States seem to experience deficient administration. Although, generally, Bua (2020) opines that problems

such as lack of administrative will, poor leadership, uncooperative attitudes of staff and lack of infrastructural facilities may account for ineffective administration of public universities in Nigeria.

In Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria, the problem of ineffective administration of public universities may be attributed to material resource management practices. Venkatesh (2021) describes material resource management practices as a coordinated effort to effectively manage the available material resources in the school to promote learning through careful planning, organizing, controlling, coordinating, utilization, maintenance and evaluation of available material resources in the school. The objective of material resource management is to attract material costs on all forms and to optimize the overall end results. Effective material resource management could promote administration of an organization. Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria administration of public universities seems not to be yielding the needed result. This may be due to administrators' inability to put in place effective material resources management practices such as planning and purchasing practices.

Planning is the first and foremost function of material resource management and administration of any school. Okwori (2023) defines planning as the determination of educational needs to ensure that limited educational resources are rationally allocated among the various competing educational demands and programmes. Therefore, material resource management in universities need effective planning so as to enhance effective administration of universities. This is because research by Nwafor (2017) found that secondary school teachers material resource skills in planning, coordination, controlling and organizing has significant impact on material resource management in secondary schools. Apali (2014) also found that effective material resource planning help to control inventory levels and schedule replenishment; material resource planning promotes effective inventory management and guides the coordination of materials at different stages of production process. However, Ogbuanya, et al. (2017) in their study revealed that there was no significant difference in mean responses of the respondents on the planning, organizing, controlling and coordinating strategies for proper management of material resources for effective teaching of electrical/electronic technology education. It is through planning that university administrators may identify resource needs of the universities and may decide on the right quality and quantity for purchasing.

Purchasing material resources is a necessary practice for effective school administration especially in universities where it seems there is high demand for utilization of material resources. Purchasing of material resources for administration of universities may mean the process of determining and deciding on procurement of the needed resources and its supply in universities. Izuagie (2015) maintains that the major function of purchasing embraces the flow of materials from the supplies to an organization which has the intention of facilitating the attainment of predetermined objectives. Apali (2014) revealed a positive and significant relationship between material resource management and effective purchasing. Demise (2018) found that schools do not apply purchasing process as planned, there is low maintenance activities in the schools and lack of appropriate training for administrative services. Purchasing simply describes the process of buying; however in a broader sense, it involves determining the need, selecting the supplier, arriving at a proper price terms and condition, issuing the contract or order and following up to ensure proper delivery.

Although, government, university administrators and relevant stakeholders of universities such as donor agencies, World Bank, philanthropists and unions seem to support effective administration of public universities through provision of material resources, this effort seems to be an exercise in futility. Observation by the researchers, government and university administrators in Nigeria particularly in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria, that administration of public universities is still plagued with the issue of material resource management practices. There seem to be shortage of material resources such as classroom facilities, office equipment, laboratories equipment and library facilities. It is a worrisome and a matter of continuous concern that some of the material resources were not forecasted or determined in number and quantity to be used in universities while others such as instructional materials and utilities seem to be in short supply probably due to lack of proper purchasing practice. All these seem to hinder effective administration of public universities. It is based on the above background that the study sought to carry out assessment of material resource management practices on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study was to investigate assessment of material resource management practices on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

10. determine the impact of material resource planning practice on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria
11. Ascertain the impact of material resource purchasing practice on administration of public universities South-South, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

30. What is the impact of material resource planning practice on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria?
31. What is the impact of material resource purchasing practice on administration of public universities South-South, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

27. Material resources planning practice has no significant impact on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria
28. Material resources purchasing practice has no significant impact on administration of public universities South-South, Nigeria

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design for carrying out the study. The population for the study comprises 11,174 academic and non-academic staff from four public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria (Planning, Research and Statistics Department of Federal Ministry of Education (2021). The sample size for the study comprises 559 or 5% of the 11,174 academic and non academic staff in 4 public universities in the study area. The sample was selected using multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled “Material Resource Management Practices and Administration Questionnaire (MRMPAQ)”. It contained 10 items on the two variables of the study which are material resource planning and material resource purchasing. The questionnaire was structured on a four point rating scale with response modes of Strongly Agree (SA) =4, Agree (A) =3, Disagree (D) =2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) =1. For content and construct validity, the questionnaire was validated by three experts in Faculty of Education Benue State University, Makurdi. For internal consistency, a reliability test of the instrument was conducted on 30 staff from University of Cross River State Calabar using Cronbach Alpha and the result yielded 0.92. The data obtained from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean scores and standard deviations to answer the research questions. Decision was based on the mean cut off point of 2.50. Any mean score below 2.50 was not regarded as agree, while mean scores of 2.50 and above was regarded as agree. Chi-square test of goodness of fit was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule of the chi-square is that if the chi-square calculated is greater than p-value of 0.000 the null hypothesis is not rejected but if it is less than 0.000, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the impact of material resources planning practice on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Rating on Impact of Material Resources Planning Practice on Administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria

S/No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Specific objectives for using material resource are formulated to achieve university goals.	559	156	277	96	30	2.98	0.80	Agree
2	Material resources are planned based on university needs to enhance university administration.	559	158	90	162	149	2.59	1.14	Agree
3	Standards are set using office equipment to enhance school administration.	559	205	154	140	60	2.86	1.01	Agree
4	Teaching materials are planned in advance for achieving universities goals in producing quality students.	559	137	230	122	70	2.73	0.94	Agree
5	Lack of proper planning for material resources will inhibit achievement of university objectives	559	189	156	106	108	2.72	1.11	Agree
Cluster Mean							2.77		Agree

Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2025

Table 1 shows Mean ratings of 2.96, 2.59, 2.86, 2.73, 2.72, and cluster mean 2.77 with a corresponding Standard Deviation ratings of 0.80, 1.14, 1.01, 0.94 and 1.11 respectively. The result indicated that items 1-5 individual ratings agreed that specific objectives for using material resource are formulated to achieve university goals, material resources are planned based on university needs to enhance university administration, standards are set using office equipment to enhance school administration, teaching materials are planned in advance for achieving universities goals in producing quality students and lack of proper planning for material resources will inhibit achievement of university objectives. The cluster Mean value of 2.77 was found to be above the Mean score benchmark of 2.50. This shows positive impact of impact of material resources planning practice on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.

Research Question 2:

What is the impact of material resources purchasing practice on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria?

Table 2: *Mean and Standard Deviation Rating on impact of Material Resources Purchasing Practice on Administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria*

S/No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	Cost of purchasing material resources needed in universities is determined by the administrators.	559	177	251	13	118	2.83	1.07	Agree
7	Timely purchase of material resources enhances effective universities administration.	559	234	215	68	85	2.88	1.03	Agree
8	Proper negotiation of the cost of material resources is carried out before they are purchased.	559	182	163	68	113	2.82	1.13	Agree
9	High cost of material resources lead to less purchase thus, inhibiting university administration.	559	242	223	103	69	2.82	0.97	Agree
10	Material resources are supplied in universities in the right quantity no matter the cost.	559	215	196	122	72	2.77	0.99	Agree
Cluster Mean							2.82		Agree

Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2025

Table 2 shows Mean ratings of 2.83, 2.88, 2.82, 2.82, 2.77, and cluster mean 2.82 with a corresponding Standard Deviation ratings of 1.07, 1.03, 1.13, 0.97 and 0.99 respectively. The result indicated that items 6-10 individual ratings agreed that cost of purchasing material resources needed in universities is determined by the administrators, timely purchase of material resources enhances effective universities administration, proper negotiation of the cost of material resources is carried out before they are purchased, high cost of material resources lead to less purchase thus, inhibiting university administration and material resources are supplied in universities in the right quantity no matter the cost. The cluster Mean value of 2.82 was found to be above the Mean score benchmark of 2.50. This shows positive impact of material resources purchasing practice on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Material resources planning practice has no significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.

Table 8: *Chi-square Analysis Summary of Impact of Material Resources Planning Practice on Administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.*

Responses	Frequency Observed	Frequency Expected	P-Value	Df	χ^2 Cal.	Decision
SA	169	139/75				
A	181	139.75	0.000	3	242.326 ^a	Sig.
D	126	139.75				
SD	83	139.75				
Total	559					

Source: Researcher's Field Work 2025

Table 3 showed Chi-square calculated value of 242.326^a at 3 degree of freedom; P=0.000 is less than 0.05. With this result, the null hypothesis which states that, material resources planning practice has no significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria was rejected. This can be interpreted to mean that material resources planning practice has positive significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2:

Material resources purchasing practice has no significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.

Table 4: *Chi-square Analysis Summary of Impact of Material Resources Purchasing Practice on Administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.*

Responses	Frequency Observed	Frequency Expected	P-Value	df	χ^2 Cal.	Decision
SA	163	139.75				
A	139	139.75	0.000	3	215.985 ^a	Sig.
D	76	139.75				
SD	91	139.75				
Total	559					

Source: Researcher's Field Work 2024

Table 4 showed Chi-square calculated value of 215.985^a degree of freedom; P=0.000 is less than 0.05. With this result, the null hypothesis which states that, material resources purchasing practice has no significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States was rejected. This can be interpreted to mean that material resources purchasing practice has positive significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of the study showed that material resources planning practice has positive significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria. This finding means that specific objectives for using material resource are formulated to achieve university goals, material resources are planned based on university needs to enhance university administration, standards are set for using office equipment to enhance school administration, teaching materials are planned in advance for achieving universities goals in producing quality students and lack of proper planning for material resources will inhibit achievement of university objectives. This finding is in line with the findings of Nwafor (2017) whose finding shows that secondary school teachers material resource skills in planning, coordination, controlling and organizing has significant impact on material resource management in secondary schools. The finding is also in line with the findings of Apali (2014) whose finding shows that effective material resource planning help to control inventory levels and schedule replenishment; material resource planning promotes effective inventory management and guides the coordination of materials at different stages of production process. The finding of the study however disagree with the findings of Ogbuanya, Nweke and Ugwoke (2017) whose findings revealed that there was no significant difference in mean responses of the respondents on the planning, organizing, controlling and coordinating strategies for proper management of material resources for effective teaching of electrical/electronic technology education.

The second finding of the study showed that material resources purchasing practice has positive significant impact on administration of Public Universities. This finding means that the cost of purchasing material resources needed in universities is determined by the administrators, timely purchase of material resources enhances effective universities administration, proper negotiation of the cost of material resources is carried out before they are purchased, high cost of material resources lead to less purchase thus, inhibiting university administration and material resources are supplied in universities in the right quantity no matter the cost. This finding agreed with the finding of Apali (2014) whose findings revealed a positive and significant relationship between material resource management and effective purchasing. This finding however disagreed with the finding of Demise (2018) whose finding showed that school do not apply purchasing process as planned, there is low maintenance activities in the schools and lack of appropriate training for administrative services.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that material resource management practices have enhanced administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria This implies that improvement in material resources planning, purchasing, organizing, controlling, coordinating, maintenance and evaluation practices have brought about significant positive improvement on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made.

1. Public university administrators in Nigeria should ensure that there is proper planning of material resource management in their universities in order to enhance administration of public universities in the states.
2. The public university administrators should ensure that there is proper and adequate material resource purchasing practices that recognize taking stock of materials and with accurate costs to ensure the right purchase of materials resources for effective administration of public universities in Nigeria.

References

- Apali, C. (2014). *Material resource planning and effective purchasing: A case study in Crown Beverages Limited Uganda* (Master's dissertation). Kampala University.
- Bua, F. T. (2020). *Educational management: A grassroots approach*. Makurdi.
- Demisse, L. H. (2018). *Management of educational material resources in secondary schools in Yaya Gulale Woreda North Shoa Zone* (Master's dissertation, Addis Ababa University).
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2014). *National policy on education*. Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council.
- Izuagie, F. O. (2015). *Material resource management skills needed by preschool teachers in Ondo State, Nigeria* (Unpublished master's dissertation). University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Nwafor, K. E. (2017). Material resource management skills required by secondary school teachers in Delta State of Nigeria. *Journal of Social Science*, 3(1), 19–27.
- Ogbuanya, T. C., Nweke, J. N., & Ugwoke, S. C. (2017). Material resource management for effective teaching of electrical/electronics technology in colleges of education (technical) in Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, 12(18), 7238–7253.

Relationship between Environmental Factors and Basic Science Content Delivery among Secondary School Students in Education District V, Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the role played by environmental factors as a predictor of effective content delivery in the Basic Science especially at the junior secondary school level. The study adopted Correlation research design. The study population comprised all Junior secondary school class two (JSSII) population during the 2023/2024 academic session, through purposive and simple sampling techniques, 30 students each was randomly selected from five identified schools to form a sample frame size of 150 students. A self-designed instrument titled, Environmental Factors as Predictor of Effective Content Delivery in Basic Science Questionnaire (WFPECDBSQ) containing 20 closed ended items on 4-likert scale was used to generate data. The instrument was validated by experts and a reliability index (r-value) of 0.891 was obtained using split -half reliability test which shows that the instrument is reliable for the study. Chi- square and Linear regression analysis was used to analyse the data tested at 0.05 significant level. The results of Ho1: indicated that $X^2_{cal} = 99.77$, while the X^2_{tab} at 0.05 significant level is 21.03. This shows that $X^2_{cal} > X^2_{tab}$ which indicated that the hypothesis was rejected which implies that conducive learning environment influence the student's achievement in Basic science. And Ho2 results revealed that $X^2_{cal} = 78.30$, while the X^2_{tab} at 0.05 significant level is 5.40. Hence, this shows that $X^2_{cal} > X^2_{tab}$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. The study concluded that environmental factors are good predictors that enhance effective content delivery in teaching of Basic science. It was further recommended among others that government and other related stake holders in education should renovate dilapidated buildings and prioritize investment in her educational system

Keywords: Environmental factors, Basic Science, Predictors, Effective content delivery, Physical structures

Introduction

Teachers teaching Basic Science in Junior Secondary Schools face considerable challenges in lessons preparation and Integrated Science teaching. First of all, those teachers need to understand the structure and nature of the discipline and learn unfamiliar knowledge, which is known as subject matter knowledge. Secondly, they need to transform the content knowledge into suitable activities analogies, demonstrations or simulations and adapt them to the different structure abilities to help them learn what is described by Shulman (2022) as pedagogical content knowledge. This review sets out to outline challenges faced by science teachers when teaching integrated science and explore the strategies used by teachers in dealing with such situations.

Inadequate background in the subject knowledge is one of the main factors that contributes to such challenges and will have an impact on the development of the teachers' pedagogical content knowledge as well as on the teachers' self-confidence and attitudes when teaching topics in integrated science. The teacher knowledge base strongly influences all aspects of teaching like preparation, planning and decision making regarding the choice of content to be learnt (Delphonso et al 2024).

Therefore, one can argue that one of the most important characteristics of being a good science teacher is having a very good basis of subject matter knowledge. However, research studies have attempted to find a relationship between subject matter knowledge and good teaching (Abell, 2019; Childs & MC Nicholls, 2020). Kind (2019) suggest that while a good background in subject matter knowledge is a pre-requisite for good teaching, it is not the only requirement. Exemplary science teachers, as argued by Shulman (2022) also need to develop pedagogical content knowledge which enables science teachers to blend content and pedagogy into an understanding of how particulars topics, problem or issues are organized represented and adapted to the diverse interests and abilities of learners and presented for instruction (Shulman 2022). Magnolia et al (2019) described pedagogical content knowledge for science teaching as the transformation of several types of knowledge not only subject matter knowledge.

Conducive learning environment has been identified as essential for effective teaching and learning to take place. Olutola (2017) postulated that school learning environment which includes structural spaces, administrative spaces, spacers for conveniences and accessories are essential in facilitating teaching-learning process. In the opinions of Odufowokan (2011) learning environment is the quality and character of school life. It is based on pattern of school life experiences and reflects norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationship, teaching, learning and leadership practices, and organisation structures. A sustainable, positive school environment fosters upon the development and learning necessary for a productive, contributing and satisfying life in a democratic society. This climate includes norms, values and expectations that support people's feeling socially, emotionally and physical life. Amie-Ogan (2021) opined that gender consideration does not matter the provision of conducive classrooms and conducive environment influence their learning improvement. Odufowokan (2011) also emphasized that physical resources like spacious classrooms with proper ventilation, lighting and colour were significantly related to students' academic achievement. Wagithunu, Edabu and Sinan (2019) who affirmed that the provision and management of physical facilities such as libraries and lecture halls are core in attaining the educational objectives.

The school as a learning environment comprises physical, academic, social and cultural environments. The physical environment is made up of school location, physical features and structures within and outside the school. For example, a school may be located in urban or rural areas, noisy or quiet areas. Buildings, equipment and infrastructures available in their schools and its surroundings also constitute its physical environment. Egin (2023) revealed that quality of learning face facilities available within, the learning environment has positive relationship with the quality of teaching and learning activities which in turn influence students' academic performance.

Statement of the Research Problem

The performance of students especially in core subjects has not been encouraging over the years in our Junior Secondary Schools Egin (2023). This poor performance could indicate that teachers have lost their effectiveness as corroborated by Delphonso et al (2023) who opined that teaching still retains the old conservative approach of teachers acting as repertoire of knowledge and students the dormant recipients. Hence the poor performance could indicate that teachers have lost their pedagogical effectiveness. Riaz and Rizvi (2018) stressed that, it appears that the environment and general working conditions do not encourage teachers to do their jobs effectively. He further emphasized that in a classroom setting, elements of teaching-learning process include: teacher, students, content, learning process and learning situation. The learning situation or learning environment means the conditions in which learning take place. Each classroom has unique teaching - learning conditions. It appears that the environment and general working conditions do not motivate teachers do their jobs effectively (Childs & McMichill 2020). Another issue identified is the alarming rate at which students flee from the classrooms of some teachers, possibly due to poor teachers-students relationship with them (Abell, C.O. 2019). Some teachers are so hostile that students are discouraged from attending their class (Magnolia et al 2019). Some of them struggled to manage their classes (Egin 2023), while others struggled to motivate students to learn in their subject areas (Magnolia et al 2019). This could be one of the reasons why most students prefer to attend classes taught by teachers who have a positive relationship with their students.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the comparative relationship between environmental factors and Basic science content delivery among secondary school students in education district v, Lagos state, Nigeria. Therefore, the specific objectives of this research are to:

1. Determine relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content.
2. Compare the difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science.

Research questions

In the context of the above objectives the following research questions were raised:

1. What is the relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content?
2. What are the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievements in Basic science?

Research Hypotheses

In the context of the above objectives and research questions the following research hypotheses will be tested:

1. There is no significant relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science.

Methodology

A correlation research design was used for this research and was carried out in education district V in Lagos State. The study population comprised all Junior secondary school class two (JSSII) during the 2023/2024 academic session, through purposive and simple sampling techniques, 30 students each was randomly selected from five identified schools to form a sample frame size of 150 students. The instrument used to collect data for the study was a structured questionnaire, a self-designed instrument titled, Environmental Factors as Predictor of Effective Content Delivery in Basic Science Questionnaire (WFPECDBSQ) containing 20 closed ended items on 4-likert scale was used to generate data. This instrument was divided into two sub-scales as each scale has 10 items. The instrument was validated by two experts in the department of Natural Science, Lagos State University of Education, Lagos. Through split-half, a reliability form, the sourced and a reliability index (r-value) was of 0.89 was obtained using split -half reliability test which shows that internal consistency was met the instrument is reliable for the study. Linear regression analysis was used to analyse the data tested at 0.05 significant level. The researchers personally administered the questionnaire- Environmental Factors as Predictor of Effective Content Delivery in Basic Science Questionnaire (WFPECDBSQ) containing 20 closed ended items on 4-likert scale was used to generate data. This instrument was divided into two sub-scales as each scale has 10 items. The data collected were analysed using Linear regression analysis and chi-square statistical tools were used to analyzed the data obtained from the respondent at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis one

There is no significant relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content.

Table 1: Chi-square Analysis on Conducive learning Environment and Students’ Achievement in Basic science

S/N	A	SA	D	S/D	TOTAL	Df	Sign	Cal.	Assymp. Sign
1.	35	46	10	9	100				
2.	16	20	44	20	100				
3.	35	20	40	5	100	12	0.05	99.77	0.00
4.	30	35	10	25	100				
5.	15	20	35	30	100				

The findings in this study indicated that there was no significant relationship. Hence in order to test this hypothesis, the data obtained from the Environmental Factors as Predictor of Effective Content Delivery in Basic Science Questionnaire (WFPECDBSQ) with Likert Scale was subjected to critical chi-square. Result showed that the calculated chi-square value is 99.77, while the critical chi-square value at 0.05 significant level is 21.03. This shows that the calculated X^2 value (99.77) is greater than the critical for value (21.03) that is the result is significant which implies that the hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis two

There is no significant difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science.

Table 2: Chi-square analysis on mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science.

S/N	A	SA	D	S/D	TOTAL	Df	Sign	Cal.	Assymp. Sign
1.	35	20	45	5	100				
2.	15	25	30	30	100				
3.	50	35	10	5	100	12	0.05	78.30	0.00
4.	15	15	40	30	100				
5.	40	20	20	20	100				

Table two result showed that there is significant difference between the mean perception score of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science. it implies that the calculated chi-square value is 78.30, while the critical value at 0.05 significant level is 5.40. This shows that the calculated chi-square value (78.30) is greater than the critical t-value (5.40). Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the comparative relationship between environmental factors and Basic science content delivery among secondary school students in education district v, Lagos state, Nigeria and two hypotheses were generated and tested. Hypothesis 1 states that there was no significant relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content and the results revealed that the hypothesis was rejected which implies that conducive learning environment influence the student's achievement in Basic science. The finding is in line with Wagithunu, Edabu and Sinan (2019) who affirmed that the provision and management of physical facilities such as libraries and lecture halls are core in attaining the educational objectives. In a related study of Bandele (2022) is in agreement with the above assertion states that learning facilities which is one of the factors lay pivotal role in the actualization of the educational goals and objectives by satisfying the physical, emotional, cultural, social, educational and psychological needs of students is as well as the general educational goals of the society.

Hypothesis 2, which state that there was no significant difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science. Result indicated that the hypothesis was significant hence the hypothesis was rejected because the calculated value was greater than the table value. This findings is agreement with Amie-Ogan (2021) who opined that there was no significant difference between the mean opinion of male and female students on the extent provision of conducive classrooms influence their learning improvement also the results is similar with Odufowokan (2011) who unraveled that physical resources like spacious classrooms with proper ventilation, lighting and colour were significantly related to students' academic achievement. Therefore, it implies that there is significant difference between the mean perception score of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science.

Conclusion

The study investigated the comparative relationship between environmental factors and Basic science content delivery among secondary school students in education district v, Lagos state, Nigeria and two hypotheses were generated and tested.

H_{01} states that there was no significant relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content. The outcome of the results indicated that $X^2_{cal} = 99.77$, while the X^2_{tab} at 0.05 significant level is 21.03. This shows that $X^2_{cal} > X^2_{tab}$. The outcome of the results implies that conducive learning environment influence the student's achievement in Basic science, that is the hypothesis was rejected. H_{02} which state that there was no significant difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science. The results indicated that $X^2_{cal} = 78.30$, while the X^2_{tab} at 0.05 significant level is 5.40. Hence, this shows that $X^2_{cal} > X^2_{tab}$. The study concluded that environmental factors are good predictors that enhance effective content delivery in teaching of Basic science. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Recommendations

It was revealed that there was significant relationship between the conducive learning and effective delivery of Basic science. It was also discovered that there is significant differences between the mean perception of male and female student

regarding the factors contributing to their achievement in Basic Science. Based on the results, findings and discussions of this study, the following recommendations are made;

- (xv) Government should provide adequate classroom building and renovate the existing dilapidated structures in public secondary schools in order to provide effective content delivery in Basic science.
- (xvi) Bus stops in around the schools should be re-located.
- (xvii) Market places should not be around schools.
- (xviii) Selling of alcohol around schools premises should be discouraged.
- (xix) Awareness and Education: Conduct workshop or informational sessions to raise awareness about the impact of noise on academic performance and encourage a culture of respect for noise control.
- (xx) Teacher training programmes: Integrate information about the impact of study environment on academic performance into teacher's programme. Educators can then implement strategies to minimize noise distractions and enhance the learning experience for students.

References

- Abell, C.O. (2019): Utilization of Previous and Current Researcher Outcome as a Management Tool for Educational Development. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research*, (2). 53-56. Retrieved from <http://www.Act.org/uoquity.html>
- Amie-Ogan, O. T. (2020). Seminar in human resources management in education (lecture note). Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt, Nigeria.
- Bandle S.O. (2022): Administration of Continuous Assessment in Tertiary Institution in Nigeria *Journal of Education Foundation and Management*, 1 (1): 289-296.
- Cassidy, Tshynn, R. (2021): Achievement motivation, Educational Attainment Cycles of Disadvantage and social competence of some longitudinal data. *British Journal of Educational Psychology* 61, 1-12.
- Childs & McMichill (2020): Teachers Views of Computes as Catalysts for changer in their teaching practice. *Journal of Research on Computing in Education*, 31 (3) 221-239.
- Delphonso, B.T, Osunloye, O.A, Ajose O. O& Sunday Ernest F(2024) Science and Technology Education as a Veritable tool for Eradication of Poverty in the face of gross National Unemployment. *Educational Perspectives* 12(1).
- Delphonso, B.T, Olalekan, A. A & Olasele, I.A (2023): Effectiveness of self- regulatory learning approach in improving learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in biology. *Port Harcourt Journal of Educational Studies. PHAJOES*.
- Egin, A.S. (2023): Comparison between school effectiveness, characteristics and development classroom instruction strategies in the United States and Nigeria *Journal for Africa*. 27 (1& 1) (2019): school size school climate and students' performance. Retrieved from <http://www.calstela.edu.centres/schoolize/schoolimprovement.html> on 20-8-2022.
- Egin O.B (2023): Students interest and academic performance in Nigeria schools. Research Report 24, Development Policy Centre, Ibadan.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). Nigeria National Policy on Education (reversed) Yaba, Lagos NERDC Press.
- Kind, W. (2019): Effects of Project Inquiry and Lecturers Demonstration. Teaching Methods on Senior Secondary Students Achievement in Separation of Mixture Practical Test. *Journal of Science Education*. 2 (6) 124-132.
- Magnolia et al (2019): Comparison of Students learning outcomes in middle school science classes with an STS approach and atypical textbook demonstrated approach *Res Middle level Education* 31(7), 1-11.
- NERDC (2017): G- Year Basic Education Curriculum: Basic Science and Technology Odufowokan, B. A. (2011). School plant planning as correlate of students' academic Performance in Southwest Nigeria secondary schools. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 2 (2), 41-47.
- Olutola, A.A.(2017).School location and Gender as Predictors of Students' Performance in WASSCE Multiple Choice Test in Biology. *Liceo Journal of Higher Education Research* 12(1)
- Riaz, H.M and Asad Abbas Rizvi, A.A. (2019) Effect of Classroom Learning Environment Students' Academic Achievement in Mathematics at Secondary Level, *Bulletin of Education and Research* August 2018, Vol. 40, No. 2 pp. 207-218.
- Shulman, L.S.(2022). An Icon of Teaching. In H, Prentice Baptise, Mika C, Leck (Eds). Living Edition The Pagrave Handbook of Educational Thinkers. Springer Nature pp.1
- Wagithunu, M. N., Edabu, P. & Sinan, G.H. (2019). Influence of physical resource management on academic performance of trainees in public primary teacher training colleges in Kenya. *African Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(2), 14-21.

Comparative Analysis of Computer-Assisted -Instruction and Reinforcement Strategies on Learning Outcome in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Delta State

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Abstracts

The study investigated the comparative analysis of computer-assisted -instruction and reinforcement strategies on learning outcome in chemistry among secondary school students in Delta state four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted the planned variation research design. Two experimental groups were used for this research which comprised of two urban and rural schools respectively. The sample consisted of 512 SSII chemistry students in four public secondary schools in delta state. The chemistry assessment test was the instrument used for data collection which was validated by experts in the field ($r=0.75$). The hypotheses were analyzed using t- test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed there was a significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of students taught with computer assisted- instruction and students exposed to reinforcement learning approach in favour of computer assisted-instruction. In light of the findings of the study, it is therefore concluded that the use of computer-assisted instruction in teaching difficult chemistry concept improves students' learning outcomes more than reinforcement approach. it is therefore, recommended that government and school heads should make provision of computer and education soft wares in secondary schools and train teachers in the methodology and learning of chemistry.

Keywords: computer assisted; chemistry; instruction; learning; reinforcement; students

Introduction

Chemistry has been mentioned among the subjects that are considered significant for the scientific and economic development of countries (fowotade, 2016). The role of chemistry in national development is quite enormous. Chemistry has contributed immensely in the area of health, teaching, agriculture, among others (Ekundayo, 2022). According to Emmanuel, Emanuel and Rose (2021) they opined that through chemistry, Nigeria as well as other developing countries acquired the needed level of development. It is considered a fundamental and central science in different working areas such as medicine, pharmacy, biochemistry, engineering, microbiology, textile industry, agriculture, and petroleum products separation (Bhargava, 2016). It holds a central position in the science world and therefore, requires effective teaching that will boost students understanding of the chemistry concept.

It is sad to note, that the subject chemistry has not gotten the required attention needed for effective learning. Students have continued to perform poorly in external examinations. The West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) examiners' report of 2005 to 2014 have always reported students' inability in answering questions in some chemistry concepts. These concepts are electrolysis, radioactivity, chemical equilibrium, hybridization, mixture and separation techniques and chemical reaction. The West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) chief examiner report (WAEC, 2015 & NECO 2015) reported that for some years back, students have avoided, failed and could not tackle adequately the electrolysis and rate of chemical reaction. Agu and Okafor (2021): their study in anambra state revealed a consistent correlation between poor student performance in WAEC and NECO chemistry exams, emphasizing that challenging topics like electrolysis and equilibrium remain poorly understood. They attributed this to ineffective teaching methods and insufficient use of technology in instruction. Premium times (2023): the report analyzed WAEC results and identified chemistry as one of the most challenging subjects for Nigerian students. It cited specific topics such as electrolysis and chemical equilibrium, noting that poor foundational knowledge and a reliance on rote learning were significant obstacles to student success. Chemistry consists of some difficult topics that need active teaching methods and adequate instructional materials to allow students develop understanding and competencies in the subject.

Scholars have reported that a lot of factors are responsible for students' failure in chemistry but it lies mostly on the pedagogy. Students' persistence poor performance has been partly ascribed to inadequate teaching and instructional methods adopted by science teacher (Ameh and Dantani 2012). The federal republic of Nigeria in the national policy on education (FRN 2013) recognized the importance of teachers by stating that no nation's educational system could be greater than the quality of her teachers. This means that the teachers remain the major input in any educational system and their quality of teaching is

undoubtedly one of the most important factors shaping the teaching and learning process as well as the achievement of students (Iyaboyi and Muftau, 2014).

Researchers opined that the pedagogy skill of the teacher is a powerful force (Amusan 2016). It has been observed that teachers' activity mostly dwells on mere recitation of knowledge without involving practical demonstration of learning that will enhance students' ability to acquire skills, have deep retention of knowledge, develop self-reliance syndrome, and create knowledge on their own without much help from the teacher and this style of teaching by teachers will be an impediment to learning and may eventually lead to failure in chemistry. Teachers have frequently adopted the traditional method of teaching which results to little or no learning in the teaching of some difficult concept in chemistry. Menon (2015) posited that the traditional approach of lecture and note taking has lost its effectiveness in this modern day. Ineffective teaching methods and insufficient instructional resources are most problematic for effective and successful chemistry teaching and learning and make it difficult for some learners (Ejjidike & Oyelana, 2015). This necessitated the need to adopt an instructional method that is an activity based and have the potential to stimulate and motivate learning. Chemistry subject needs a pedagogical approach that will foster learning through practical demonstration, seeing learning taking place in a natural form. One of the most effective ways to make teaching and learning interesting and effective is taking advantage of instructional technologies, especially the computers (Tareef, 2014).

The computer assisted instruction (CAI) is an interactive instructional strategy where the teacher uses computer to present the instructional materials to the students and monitor the learning process. Computer could be assessed individually or as a group unlike a conventional classroom where students are lumped together irrespective of their individual differences and class size (Laleye, 2019). In the teacher centered method of teaching, teachers are the key source of information and transmitters of knowledge while the students are passive receiving information. This method of teaching needs to be complemented, more especially in the era of ICT, where the role of a teacher has shifted from being the key source of information and transmitter of knowledge to that of becoming a collaborator and a co-learner (Samaila, Makinde and Zambwa 2016). Part of the drive towards greater use of modern technology in education is equipping teachers and learners of today with skills that will help them to think and act globally (Laleye, 2019).

Busari, Ernest and Ugwuanyi (2016) also revealed in their study that CAI engages learners, makes them active participants in class as well as motivate the students. Samuel and Okonkwo (2020) also found out that low academic self-concept in chemistry is overcome when many difficult concepts are made clearer through appropriate teaching techniques such as computer assisted instruction. More so, abstract concepts which pose difficulties are easily understood when given e-visual explanations. Ekundayo (2022) investigated the effects of CAI on students' achievement in chemistry among boys and girls in public secondary schools. The result from the study showed that there was no significant difference between the achievement of male and female students in both the experimental and the control. Busari, Ernest and Ugwuanyi (2016) also investigated on the effect of CAI on senior secondary students' achievement in chemical reaction and equilibrium in Egbeda local government area of Oyo state, Nigeria. The instrument used in the study was the chemical reaction and equilibrium achievement test (CREAT). The students' scores from CREAT were collected and analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The results showed a significant difference between the mean achievement of students taught chemical reaction and equilibrium using CAI and those taught using a conventional teaching strategy. Thus, the students taught using CAI performed better than their counterparts. Oluwadara, Adetunmbi, Lukuman and Mohammed (2017) conducted a study on the comparative effects of an individualized computer based instruction and the modified conventional strategy on students' academic achievement in organic chemistry, the findings revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught organic chemistry using individualized computer based instructional package and the modified conventional strategy ($f_{1, 65} = 0.228, p = 0.635 > 0.05$). Also, no significant difference was found between the academic performance of male and female students who used the individualized CBI ($f_{1, 65} = 0.050, p = 0.823 > 0.05$). Titus, Justina and Sylvester (2015) also established that CAI positively affects students' achievement and retention ability.

Reinforcement is strategic skill that could be applied when students are taught chemistry concept to motivate students' interest by way of rewards or praise. This may create motivational stimulus which brings about a change in behaviour. Afirm (2015) identified two types of reinforcement the positive and negative reinforcement. He described the positive reinforcement as the delivery of a reinforcer to increase appropriate behavior while the negative reinforcement is the removal of an aversive event or condition which also increase appropriate behavior. In the educational context grade, praise, medal and other prizes awarded to students are examples of positive reinforcer Rezaul (2013). A study conducted by (Alam, Alay & Alam 2018), proved that positive reinforcement effects students' academic performance with no gender related difference. By comparing

scores of experimental and control group subjects mean for both control and experimental group is 0.5 and calculated value of “t” is 2.50 which is significant on 0.5.

Sex is another important variable that was considered in this study. Sex refers to the state of being a male or female. Every society, ethnic group and culture has specific roles for male which differs from that of the female. This analytic concept describes the sociological roles, cultural responsibilities and expectations of men and women in a given society or cultural setting. The importance of investigating performance with regards to sex is based primitively on the socio-cultural distinction between girls and boys. these discrepancies have extended to some vocations and professions for example agriculture, engineering, arts and crafts work are regarded as men ‘s profession while others such as catering, typing, nursing tailoring, hair dressing etc. are often seen as female profession. Complex and difficult tasks are assigned to boys whereas girls are expected to handle the relatively easy and less demanding tasks. As a result of this way of thinking the larger society has tended to see girls as a weaker sex”. Consequently, an average Nigerian girl goes to school with these fixed stereotypes. This study therefore, seeks to determine the interaction of sex on the two learning approaches (computer assisted and reinforcement) and how it influences learning outcomes.

Learning outcomes can be influenced by school location. The school location refers to the geographical area where the school is sited which is either urban or rural. The rural schools are schools located in the villages where some social amenities like electricity, pipe born water, health care facilities and good roads are lacking, students residing in these areas lack exposure. The urban schools are schools sited in towns and are highly favoured with necessary social the amenities with different cultural diversities as such students’ residing in urban areas are more exposed than students in rural schools. Due to this factor’s location is most likely to influence students learning outcomes. The findings of Awodun and Oyeniyi (2018) revealed that there was statistically significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students in urban and rural school located areas. This study will also compare the learning outcomes of urban and rural students that received treatment with computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach with the view to determine effects on learning outcome.

Statement of the Research Problem

Students’ failure in chemistry has been a major concern among researchers. The causes of students’ failure have been attributed to a lot of factors which are teachers’ poor qualification, poor method of teaching, lack of teaching experience, and failing to use the instructional materials Ojukwu (2016). However, National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2021): in their report, "call to action for science education: building opportunity for the future," the national academies emphasize the necessity of innovative teaching approaches to enhance science education quality. They argue that traditional methods often fail to engage students effectively, leading to suboptimal learning outcomes. Lecture based instruction does not motivate students to learn and there is no one - its – all teaching approach (Tumay, 2016). Flexible teachers must use innovative teaching strategies that adapt information to learners of all background and abilities in a supportive classroom environment (Sibomana et. al., 2021).

Computer assisted is an innovative teaching strategy where students are fully involved in the teaching and learning process. It is an interactive model of instruction that can take the form of power point presentation, pictures and images displayed through the overhead projectors. This enable the students to visually engage and create pictures and imaginations of what is been taught. Students need activities that motivate them to learn. The reinforcement learning approach is another teaching strategy that will cause students to be fully engaged in the learning process. The computer assisted and reinforcement method that has the ability to stimulate and bring students to focus may be a better option than the traditional method. The problem of the study therefore is: what is the effect of computer assisted instruction and reinforcement instructional approach on chemistry students’ learning?

Research questions

1. What is the difference in mean learning outcome scores on chemistry between students that received treatment with computer assisted instruction and students taught using reinforcement approach?
2. What is the interaction effect of the teaching method (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement) and sex on students mean learning outcome scores?
3. What is the difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using computer assisted - instruction?
4. What is the difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using reinforcement instructional approach?

Hypotheses

Four research hypotheses were raised for this study. They are

- Ho₁. There is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of students that received treatment with computer assisted instruction and students taught using reinforcement instructional approach.
- Ho₂. There is no significant interaction effect of the teaching method (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement) and sex on students mean learning outcome scores.
- Ho₃. There is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using computer assisted- instruction.
- Ho₄. There is no significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using reinforcement instructional approach.

Methodology

The design of the study is pretest posttest planned variation quasi - experimental research design. Two experimental groups were adopted for this research without a control group. The first group received treatment with the use of computer assisted – instruction while the second group received treatment with the reinforcement learning approach and the effects of these two groups on student’s learning outcomes were compared. The quasi – experimental research design was deployed because randomization of subject into group were impossible due to the adoption of intact classes. The study also employed the planned variation because it compared the effects of the two instructional strategies on students’ learning outcomes

The aggregate figure of 18,879 senior secondary year two chemistry students in the 473 government secondary schools in delta state formed the population for this study. Some of the difficult SSII chemistry topics outlined by students in various research findings were selected for this study. This formed the basis for the selection of SSII students that were used for the study. 512 SSII chemistry students drawn from 10 government mixed secondary schools in delta state were used for the study. The stratified sampling technique was used to group the schools into two: urban and rural. Five schools were selected from each group using simple random sampling technique. The stratified sampling was used to ensure that all the schools in the urban and rural were adequately represented. In the computer-assisted instruction group 252 students were selected, which comprised 134 students from urban location and 118 from rural location while 112 were male and 140 were female. In the reinforcement learning instructional approach, 260 students were selected which comprised 140 students from urban location and 120 from rural location while 115 were male and 145 were female. The chemistry assessment test was used to obtain data. It consisted of 50 multiple choice questions drawn from WAEC past question on the following chemistry topics: ionization, and stoichiometry. The treatment lasted for four weeks. The chemistry assessment test was also used to measure students learning outcomes. The learning package for this study was the lesson plan prepared by the researcher for the computer assisted instruction and the reinforcement learning approach to cover for the four-week instruction which was handed over to the chemistry teachers in the sampled schools to prepare them for the various steps to follow in the teaching of the selected chemistry concept. The lesson plan contains the topic to be taught for four weeks, the stated objectives for each period and the necessary steps and procedures that the instructors are to follow to enhance proper understanding of concepts.

The face validity of the chemistry assessment test was determined by experts in the field. They critically examined the test items accordingly to see whether it appeared to test what it aims to test, looking at the logical relationship between questions and the objectives of the study. The content validity of the chemistry assessment test was assured using table of specification ensuring that the content covered all topics spelt out in the four weeks lesson plan.

Presentation of Results

All the research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. All the research hypothesis were tested using independent sampled t- test.

Research Question 1:

What is the difference in mean learning outcome scores on chemistry between students that received treatment with computer assisted instruction and students taught using reinforcement instructional approach?

To answer this research question, the mean learning outcome of the pretest and posttest scores of students who received treatment with computer assisted and reinforcement were compared. this is shown in table 1.

Table 1. mean and standard deviation of pretest and posttest learning outcome scores of chemistry students exposed to computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach

group	N	pretest	Pretest	posttest	posttest	mean gain
computer- assisted instruction	252	18.28	6.499	62.61	13.025	44.33
reinforcement learning approach	260	18.15	7.699	53.49	13.089	33.34

From the result shown in table 1. The difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of students exposed to computer assisted instruction is 44.33 whereas students exposed to reinforcement learning approach had a mean gain of 35.34 which is the mean difference between pretest and posttest scores. This is an indication that there is a variation in the mean learning outcome scores of students exposed to computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach where students taught with computer assisted outperformed their counterparts taught with reinforcement learning approach.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of students that received treatment with computer assisted instruction and students taught using reinforcement learning instructional approach.

The pretest mean learning outcome scores of the students in the two experimental groups were compared using the independent sample t - test to ascertain if there is a significant difference before the treatment and to also ensure that the right statistical tool was employed.

Table 2: summary of independent sample t- test comparison of pretest mean learning outcome scores of chemistry students who received treatment with computer assisted and reinforcement learning instructional approach.

Method	N	x	sd	df	t- cal	sig.(2 –tail)	decision
Computer- assisted instruction	252	18.28	6.499	123	0.95	0.925	NS
Reinforcement learning approach	260	18.15	7.699				

$P \geq 0.05$ NS = Not Significant

Table 2. shows that there is no significant difference between the pretest mean learning outcome scores of students taught chemistry with computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach, $t = 0.95$, $p (0.925)$. Thus, the null hypothesis was tested using the independent sample t- test.

Table 3: summary of independent sample t- test comparison of posttest mean learning outcome scores of chemistry students who received treatment with computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach

Method	N	x	sd	df	t- cal	sig.(2 –tail)	decision
Computer- assisted instruction	252	62.61	13.025	115	3.869	0.00	sig
Reinforcement learning approach	260	53.49	13.089				

$p \leq 0.05$

Table 3: shows a significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of chemistry students taught with computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach where $t = 3.869$, $p (0.000) \leq 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis one is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of students that received treatment with computer assisted instruction and students taught using reinforcement learning approach

Research Question 2:

What is the interaction effect of the teaching method (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement) and sex on students mean learning outcome scores

The research questions were answered by comparing the pretest and posttest mean learning outcome scores of students exposed to computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach this is shown in table 4.

Table 4: the mean and standard deviation on interaction effects between teaching methods and sex on chemistry students' learning outcome.

Test	Sex	Computer -assisted			Reinforcement		
		n	x	sd	n	x	sd
pretest	male	112	20.79	7.951	37	18.86	7.885
	female	140	15.58	2.580	34	17.38	7.467
	total	252	18.28	6.499	71	18.15	7.669
posttest	male	115	62.39	11.796	37	54.89	13.501
	female	145	63.08	14.350	34	51.97	12.648
	total	260	62.61	13.025	71	53.49	13.089

Table 4 shows no interaction effects between teaching methods and sex on students learning outcome this is because at all level of sex there was a higher mean learning outcome scores among male and female students who received treatment with computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach. this can be justified from the posttest mean learning outcome for male and female students exposed to computer assisted which is 62.39 and 63.08 and the posttest mean learning outcome of male and female students exposed to reinforcement is 54.89 and 51.97 respectively.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant interaction effect of the teaching method (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement) and sex on students mean learning outcome scores.

This hypothesis was test using independent sample t – test the result is shown in table 5:

Table 5: independent sample t – test showing interaction effects between teaching methods and sex on chemistry students learning outcome score

	sex	n	x	sd	df	t-cal	sig.(2 tailed)	decision
computer-assisted	male	112	62.39	11.796	52	-192	0.849	ns
	female	140	63.08	14.350				
reinforcement	male	115	54.89	13.501	69	0.939	0.351	ns
	female	145	51.97	12.648				

$$p \geq 0.05$$

Table 5 shows that there is no significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of male and female students who were taught chemistry with the computer assisted instruction, $t = -.192$ p (0.849) and there was also no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of male and female students exposed to reinforcement learning approach, $t = 0.939$ p (0.351).this indicates that there is no significant interaction effect between sex and and teaching methods among students taught chemistry using computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach. Based on the finding of this study, the null hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant interaction effect of the teaching methods (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement learning approach) and sex on students' mean learning outcome scores.

Research Question 3:

What is the difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using computer assisted - instruction?

To answer this research question, the mean learning outcome scores of uban and rural students exposed to computer assisted were compared as shown in table 6.

Table 6: comparison of posttest scores by location for computer-assisted method

method	location	n	mean	sd	mean difference
computer- assisted	urban	134	64.83	11.683	3.8
	rural	118	61.03	13.870	

Table 6 shows that urban students taught chemistry with the computer assisted method had a mean learning outcome score of 64.83 with standard deviation of 11.683 and their counterparts in rural schools had mean learning outcome score of 61.03 with

standard deviation 13.870. The mean difference between the urban and rural students is 3.8 which falls in favour of the urban students. The hypothesis was tested to verify if this difference is significant.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using computer assisted – instruction.

The hypothesis was tested by comparing the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students who received treatment with computer assisted method using independent sample t – test as shown in table 7.

Table 7: independent sample t – test comparison of mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught chemistry with computer assisted method

Method	location	n	x	sd	df	t-cal	sig.(2 tailed)	decision
computer-assisted	urban	134	64.83	11.683	52	1.072	0.289	ns
	rural	118	61.03	13.873				

p ≥ 0.05, ns = not significant

Table 7 shows that there is no significant variation between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught chemistry with the computer assisted method, $t = 1.072$, $p (0.289) \geq 0.05$ thus, the null hypothesis three is not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of students taught chemistry using computer assisted instruction.

Research Question 4:

What is the difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using reinforcement instructional approach?

To answer this research question, the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students exposed to reinforcement learning approach were compared as shown in table 8.

Table 8: mean and standard deviation of learning outcome scores of urban and rural student taught chemistry using reinforcement learning instructional approach

method	location	n	mean	sd	mean difference
Reinforcement	urban	140	56.27	14.321	4.81
	rural	120	51.46	11.879	

Table 8 shows that urban students taught chemistry with the reinforcement learning approach had a mean learning outcome score of 56.27 with standard deviation of 14.321 and their counterparts in rural schools had mean learning outcome score of 51.46 with standard deviation 11.879. The mean difference between the urban and rural students is 4.81 which falls in favour of the urban students. The hypothesis was tested to verify if this difference is significant.

Hypothesis 4:

There is no significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using reinforcement instructional approach.

The hypothesis was tested by comparing the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural chemistry students who received treatment with reinforcement learning approach using independent sample t – test as shown in table 9.

Table 9: independent sample t – test comparison of mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught chemistry with reinforcement learning outcome

Method	location	n	x	sd	df	t-cal	sig.(2 tailed)	decision
reinforcement	urban	140	56.27	14.321	69	1.542	0.128	ns
	rural	120	51.46	11.879				

$p > 0.05$

Table 9 shows that there is no significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught chemistry with reinforcement learning, $t = 1.542$, $p(0.128) \geq 0.05$ thus, the null hypothesis four is not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of students taught chemistry using computer assisted instruction.

Discussion of findings

The study investigated the comparative effects of computer assisted instruction and reinforcement learning approach on chemistry students learning outcome. At the end of the analysis the study revealed that there was a significant variation in the mean learning outcome scores of chemistry students exposed to computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach which falls in favour of students taught with computer assisted, they had a higher mean score than their counterparts exposed to reinforcement learning approach. This variation in the mean learning outcome score of the computer assisted group suggests students' active participation in class and learning process here, is more interactive and engaging as more difficult concepts are made clearer when computer assisted is employed this may have contributed to the higher performance encountered by students in computer assisted group. Students in reinforcement learning approach group may not have performed better than the computer assisted because the reinforcement learning approach is the process of encouraging a belief or pattern of behavior by way of reward to get positive feedback which may either improve students' achievement if the students are motivated by this reward and cause low achievement if students are not motivated by this reward which will equally show low participation in the learning process. This may have accounted for the low mean learning outcome scores of students in reinforcement group. Thus, computer assisted is more effective in enhancing chemistry students learning outcome scores than the reinforcement learning approach. This study is in accordance with the findings of Busari, Ernest and Ugwuanyi (2016) who reported a significant difference between the mean achievement of students taught chemical reaction and equilibrium using CAI and those taught using a conventional teaching strategy in favour of the computer assisted. The finding of the study is also in compliance with the findings of Titus, Justina and Sylvester (2015) who established that computer assisted positively affects students' achievement and retention ability in the subject. This study is not in agreement with the findings of Oluwadara, Adetunmbi, Lukuman and Mohammed (2017) who found no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught organic chemistry using individualized computer based instructional package and the modified conventional strategy. Consequently, researchers have made comparison between computer assisted instruction and other teaching methods to ascertain the most effective in enhancing students' learning outcomes however, literature has not reported any comparison between computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach to ascertain the most effective in enhancing students' learning outcomes.

The study further established that there is no significant interaction effect of the teaching method (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement) and sex on students' mean learning outcome scores. This simply implies that sex is not a determinant of the learning outcome scores of chemistry students taught with the use of computer assisted and the reinforcement learning approach. The reason why there was no interaction effect of the two-teaching method on sex could be due to the mode of instruction employed by the teacher. Equal learning will take place when the right procedure is adopted to cater for students' observed behaviours and assumption during teaching and learning process. Therefore, sex has no influence on chemistry students' learning outcome when taught using computer assisted and sex does not equally influence chemistry students learning outcome when taught using reinforcement learning approach. The result of this finding is in compliance with the findings of Oluwadara, Adetunmbi, Lukuman and Mohammed (2017) who reported no significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students who used the individualized computer based instruction. The study is also in agreement with the findings of Ekundayo (2022) who found no significant difference between the achievement of male and female students in both the experimental and control group. The study also agrees with the findings of Alam, Alay & Alam (2018) who proved that positive reinforcement effects students' academic performance with no gender related difference.

The study further revealed that there was no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using computer assisted – instruction. This is implying that teaching with computer assisted has no influence in the learning outcome of chemistry students in urban and rural location. Therefore, location will not determine the learning outcome scores of students taught chemistry with computer assisted instruction. This justifies the interactive nature of computer assisted as it helps to blend learning by equipping students with the skills to think and find solutions to critical concepts in chemistry. The result of this finding is not in line with the result of Awodun and Oyeniyi (2018) who revealed that there was a statistically significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students in urban and rural school located areas.

the study again, establish that there is no significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using reinforcement approach. This implies that the use of reinforcement learning approach in the teaching of the selected chemistry concept does not influence the learning outcome scores of chemistry students in the urban and rural areas. This is an indication that the use of reinforcement learning approach will not cause any change or determine the learning outcome scores of chemistry students in urban and rural location. The finding of this study is contrary to the finding of Awodun and Oyeniyi (2018) who revealed that there was statistically significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students in urban and rural school located areas.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this present study, it is therefore concluded that computer assisted is the most appropriate in the teaching of difficult concept in chemistry, it empowers students' learning and influence their learning outcome more exceedingly than the reinforcement learning approach.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Adoption of computer-assisted instruction (CAI):** Teachers, particularly chemistry educators, should integrate computer-assisted instruction into their teaching practices. Its interactive and engaging nature makes it a powerful tool for enhancing students' understanding of difficult concepts and improving learning outcomes.
2. **Training and support for Teachers:** Educational institutions should provide training and professional development opportunities for teachers to effectively utilize computer-assisted instruction. This will ensure that teachers are equipped with the necessary skills to implement CAI in their classrooms.
3. **Incorporating CAI into curriculum design:** Curriculum planners and policymakers should consider incorporating computer-assisted instruction as a standard teaching method in secondary school science curricula, particularly for challenging subjects like chemistry.

References

- Achor, E.E. & Ejigbo, M.A. (2014). *A guide to writing research report*, kano: sam artrade limited
- Afirm T. (2015). *Reinforcement.chapel hill. Nc: national professional development center on autism spectrum disorder, fpg child development center, university of carolina*. Retrieved from <http://afirm.fpg.unc.edu/reinforcement>
- Agu, N. N., & okafor, C. C. (2021). Relationship between students' grades in waec and neco chemistry examination in anambra state. *International journal of research and innovation in social science (ijriss)*, 5(7), 90-94. Available at: [rsis international ideas/repec](https://www.ijrissonline.com/index.php/ijrissonline/article/view/10000)
- Alam, Z.K, Alay A. & Alam Z. K (2018). Effects of positive reinforcement on students' academic performance. *Nor. Am. Aca. Res. 1* (1) 220 - 225
- Aleye, A. M. (2019). Effects of a computer – programmed instruction strategy on basic science learning outcome in two instructional settings in ondo state. Nigeria; *international journal of scientific research and management (ijsrm)*, 07 (02), 869 – 876
- Ameh, P. O. & Dantani, Y. S. (2012). Effects of lectures and demonstration methods on the academic achievement of students in nassarawa local government area of kano state. *International journal of social sciences 1*(1), 29 -37
- Amusan, O. O. (2016). *Influence of teachers' pedagogical skills on students' academic performance in secondary schools in ekiti state*. *International journal of innovation and research in educational sciences*, 3(3), 133–140.
- Awodun, a. O. And Oyeniyi, A. D (2018). The influence of school location on students' academic achievement in junior secondary school basic science. *Journal of emerging technologies and innovative research*. 5 (6) 73-83.
- Amusan, M. A (2016). Cultivating effective pedagogical skill in in service teachers: the role of some teachers' variables. *Jist*, 20(1), pp. 83 – 89
- Bhargava, S. (2016). Role of chemistry in everyday life. 6(february), 192–198
- Brown K., Bernholt, S., & Parchmann, I. (2018). Using model-based scaffolds to support students solving context – based chemistry problems. *International journal of science education*, 1 - 22
- Busari, O. O., Ernest, S. B., & Ugwuanyi, D. N. (2016). Effects of computer-assisted instruction on senior secondary school students' achievement in chemical reactions and equilibrium in egbeda local government area of oyo state. *International journal of secondary education*, 4(4), 39-43.

- Ejidike, i. P., & oyelana, a. A. (2015). Factors influencing effective teaching of chemistry: a case study of some selected high schools in buffalo city metropolitan municipality, eastern cape province, south africa. *International journal of educational sciences*, 8(3), 605–617.
- Ekundayo S. K (2022). Effect of computer assisted instruction (cai) on students' academic achievement in chemistry among boys and girls in public secondary school in edo state, nigeria. *British journal of education*, 10 (2). 31 -41
- Emmanuel E. A, Emmanuel E. O and Rose U. Kk (2021). Bosting achievement secondary school two students in selected difficult chemistry concepts using assertive questioning and prior knowledge of behavioral objectives strategies. *International journal of education, learning and development*, 9, (4)), 9 – 21
- Federal Republic Of Nigeria (FRN). (2013). *National policy on education* (6th ed.). Lagos: nigerian educational research and development council (nerdc).
- Fowotade, S. (2016). Chemistry and national development. June 2012
- Hyun, J. Ediger, R. & Lee, D. (2017). Students satisfaction on their learning process in active learning and traditional classroom. *International journal of teaching and learning higher education*. 29(1), 108 – 118.
- Iyaboyi M, Mmuftau (2014), an assessment of human capital development in nigeria through the lens of education. *International journal of social humanities science*, 35, 1- 14
- Mahdi, G. J. (2014). Students' attitude towards chemistry. An examination of choices and preferences. *Amarican journal of educational research*, 2 (6), 351 – 356
- Menon, A. (2015). Effectiveness of smart classroom teaching on the achievement in chemistry of secondary school students. *American international journal of research in humanities; arts and social sciences. Usa. International association of scientific innovation and research (iasir)*, 2328-3688.
- National academies of sciences, engineering, and medicine. (2021). *Call to action for science education: building opportunity for the future*. The national academies press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/26152>
- Premium times. (2023). Analysis of waec results: chemistry still among most challenging subjects. *Premium times nigeria*. Available at: [premium times](https://www.premiumtimes.com)
- Rezaul H. (2013). *Effect of reinforcement on teaching and learning – process.* 7, (1), 13 - 16
- Samaila, Y. Makinde, A.A & Zambwa, J. (2016). Development of a computer aided instruction for effective teaching of electrical and electronic devices at nigeria certificate in education technical level in northern east nigeria. *International journal of education and technical education research*, 2, (1), 45 – 47.
- Samuel, N. N. C., & Okonkwo, O. I. (2020). Effects of computer assisted instruction on senior secondary school students' academic self-concept in chemistry. *Journal of international academic research for multi-disciplinary*, 8(7), 13-20.
- Sibomana, A., Karegeya, C., & Sentong O. J (2021). Students' conceptual understanding of organic chemistry and classroom implications in the rwandan perspective. *A literature review. African journal of educational studies in mathematics and sciences* 16 (2)
- Titus, I.E., Justina, i.e. And sylvester, c.o. (2015). Effect of computer- assisted instruction on studentents' academic achievement and retention of auto-mechanics technology. *the international journal of humanity and social studies*, 8., (7), 87 -93
- Tumay, h. (2016).** Reconsidering learning difficulties and misconceptions in chemistry: emergence in chemistry and its implications for chemical education. *Chemistry education research and practice*, 17(2), 229–245. Doi:10.1039/c6rp00008h.
- West african examination council (2015). Chief examiner's reports yaba press ltd.
- Ojukwu, M.O. (2016). Perseption of stuents on causes of poor performance in chemistry in external examinations. *International journal of education and literacy studies* 4 . 67
- Oluwadara A., Adetunmbi A., Lukuman B., and Mohammed (2017). The comparative effects of an individualized computer-based instruction and the modified conventional strategy on students' academic achievement in organic chemistry. *Journal of positive psychology and counselling* 1 (2), 1 -19
- Tareef, A. B. (2014). The effects of computer-assisted learning on the achievement and problem- solving skills of the educational statistics students. *European science journal*; 10(28): 271- 279.
- Tumay, H. (2016). Reconsidering learning difficulties and misconception in chemistry: emengence in chemistry and its implication for chemical education. *Chemistry education research and practice*, 17(2), 229 – 245.

Construction and Standardization of Academic-Corruption- Sensitivity-Test Instrument on Secondary School Students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to construct and standardize an instrument called Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) for measuring academic corruption among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The study used instrumentation research design. The investigation was conducted in Bayelsa State. A population of 10,170 senior secondary class three (SSIII) students during the 2023/2024 academic session were studied in the 126 senior secondary school in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A sample of 500 SS III students were drawn, in 23 schools out of 126 secondary schools, through cluster and simple random sampling techniques. The items were selected through item scale value difference (ISVD). The ISVD of the 60-item ACST ranges from .09-2.37, items that had relatively high ISVD were selected to form the final version of the ACST which consisted of 30 items. Validation was done through face, content and construct validity methods. The instrument was reliable having a reliability coefficient of .89, which was determined through Cronbach alpha reliability method. Thus, the instrument was valid and reliable. Based on the ISVD ranges the final form of the 30-itemed ACST was formed. The study, therefore, concludes that ACST can be said to be a standardized test for eliciting academic corrupt behaviours among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Thus, the researcher recommends that the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test should be used by classroom teachers, guidance counselors and other test focal persons to measure corrupt acts among students. This would help identify honest and dishonest students.

Keywords: Construction, standardization, academic, corruption, sensitivity and test.

Introduction

Corruption, according to (Ganner, 1999), is the act of doing something with an intent to give some advantage inconsistent with official duty and the rights of others, a fiduciary or officials use of a station or office to procure some benefits either personally or for someone else contrary to the rights of others. This corruption is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon which afflicts Nigeria's economic, socio-political growth and development. Amuche (2003, p. 40) posited that "corruption is like sore-finger which inherently painful to all. As an ill wind, it knows no bound. It reigns unabashedly in politics, economy and in other affairs of life. Corruption has so depleted the God-given abundant wealth in Nigeria and the nation is foreign debt ridden and beggarly". This assertion suggests that the idea of corruption has crept into the fabrics of Nigerian socio-educational milieu which for the purpose of the study is regarded as academic corruption or corruption in education. Academic corruption simply put is any act of deviation by students from formal rules that regulate their behaviours in secondary education system.

Corruption in education takes various forms as related to the context of this paper. The various forms academic corruption can be captured ranges from single act of indiscipline to an endemic malfunction of education system. An examination malpractice is one form of corruption in the educational system where it has become near impossible to abate. Examination malpractice is denoted as all form of cheating which directly or indirectly falsify the ability of the student. These shall include cheating within an examination hall, cheating outside examination hall and any involvement in illegal examination related offences (University of Port Harcourt, 2004). Furthermore, this form of academic corruption involves plagiarism, copying from one another, soliciting for help after or during an examination, impersonation, bringing in prepared answers, secretly breaking into staff office in order to obtain question papers or answer scripts, intimidation/threats to extort sex/money/favour from staff in exchange for grades and so on.

Besides students stealing text-books in the school library is another form of academic corruption. Most at times, destroying pages of text-books, threatening teachers to their advantage, belonging to cult groups, falsification of results and many others are antics of academic corruptions. These incidences are increasing in an uncontrollable momentum and vigour. This is sustained by the undoubted fact of socialization, students from one generation to the other passing it to themselves by

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way of observation, imitation and peer group influence. That is to say, social modelling in the negative perspective sustaining corrupt practices in schools.

No doubt, such educational system will breed graduates without feet, hooligans, cultists, etc. Even, the standard of education will be inexplicably fallen. Impracticably, ill-vices will shadow the educational environment. Opalaye (2005) lamented that the literacy level has not only gone down but even the sophistication that goes with education has disappeared from the beneficiaries. Today we hear of educated nudes, armed robbers, student motor spare-parts dealers, the roving 'almajiris'. It was also observed that morality is at its lowest ebb in the educational system. It simply implies that the scourging menace called academic corruption is on the increase, dragging the educational system in Nigeria to the mud. Sad to note that parents now transfer their children to either Ghana or somewhere else to have sound (corruption free) basic education, remarked Opalaye (2005).

Meanwhile, the educational policy document stated clearly that secondary education is to prepare the individual for useful living within the society and for higher education (Federal Republic Nigeria (FRN), 2004). The extent in which academic corruption had spread has become cancerous and has plunged the vision unachievable. The manifestations of the academic crimes or indisciplined behaviours are associated to the affective traits of students. These affective traits denote attitude, interest, emotional adjustment and students' lifestyles. To measure such traits of students requires a psychological test which as a set of task or questions intended to elicit particular types of behaviours when presented under standardized conditions and yield scores that have psychometric properties (Onunkwo, 2005). This means that a test is an instrument administered to someone to determine the presence or absence of the construct or phenomenon being measured for. This instrument to measure the traits can be either a teacher-made test or a standardized test. A teacher-made is an instrument designed by the classroom teacher to elicit qualities, potentials or traits from the learner while the standardized test is an instrument that is developed under scientific procedures to measure traits of an individual or learner. This study embarked on the development of academic corruption sensitivity test (ACST) with the view of elicit extent of corrupt acts in secondary school students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

From the foregoing therefore, development and standardization of a measuring instrument or test is the adoption of the procedural implications involved in designing an instrument or test for effective use. Rating scales are tools designed for psychological assessment of a behaviour such as feelings, values, interests, attitudes however they are not easy to measure the cognitive and psychomotor (Montessori, et al., 2021). The essence is to determine, describe, diagnose or predict the behaviour of a person as he/she interacts with his/her environment. Scale development or construction is both art and science. The art lies in the writing of the items and the science is on the techniques used in the item selection and rejection. Two statistical techniques are used in the construction of attitudinal scales. Such techniques include stimulus scaling (a derivative of psychophysical model) and the person scaling (a derivative of the psychometrics model). The former technique ensures respondents to be placed in a continuum, on the evaluative dimension in relation to the location of the stimuli they endorse. Such technique is applied in Thurstone scaling and Guttman scaling. The later technique, which is the person scaling, uses facts or statements as classified stimuli that are known as either favourable or unfavourable towards the attitude object or the construct as in attitudinal scales. Likert-type scales and Osgood Semantic differential scales use this statistical technique.

Schmid (1949) opined that the construction of a Likert-type scale is considerably simpler, less tedious and time saving than other scales like Guttman and Thurstone scales which are cumbersome in choosing the right word which represent the stimuli. The likert-type scaling technique is used in this study. Several test constructing and standardization processes have been advanced by different test experts and psychometrics however this study adapted the procedural steps advanced by Onunkwo (2005). These stages include:

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Figure 1: A flow chart of steps involved in the construction and standardization of ACST (Adapted from Onunkwo, 2005). Consequently, the study followed strictly these procedures to ascertain the ACST. The conceptual definition of the construct is a function of a particular theoretical concern whether these are narrowly or broadly defined hence the study identified the construct as corruption which is defined as the act of doing something with an intent to give some advantage inconsistent with official duty and the rights of others, a fiduciary or officials use of a station or office to procure some benefits either personally or for someone else contrary to the rights of others (Ganner, 1999).

The researcher going beyond giving operational definition think out and provides as many specific examples of the trait as possible which enable the researcher to cover all the various aspects of the trait in the test being constructed. This study delineated corruption as academic corruption which is defined as any act of deviation by students from formal rules that regulate their behaviours in the secondary education system. Since the trait under investigation is academic corruption among students, the researcher considered forms of academic corruption as examination malpractices, cultism, peddling of wrong information, gratification, falsification or result, impersonation, grade inflation, threatening of teachers, etc. The study adopted a 5-point response scale with 3.0 ± 1.0 mean and standard deviation. Based on the foregoing, 60 items were written which were subjected to content and statistical analysis and produced 30 itemed Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST).

Statement of the Research Problem

Psychological tests are developed in many forms and functions in different context. Among others, personality assessment or tests are used to test affective or non-intellectual aspects of behaviours. This form of test utilizes some techniques such as self-reporting, projective, peer-appraisal, etc. Among the various techniques, self-reporting is appreciated in this study. It involves asking an individual what he/she thinks, feels, says and does (Onunkwo, 2002). Constructing and developing academic corruption scale will help identify what students may think, feel, say and do so as to measure extent of corrupt act innate in them. This will further help educational stakeholders to formulate policies that will help modify corrupt behaviours in the educational system. In fact, developing and standardizing academic corruption sensitivity test will have a wide spread utility in the education sector such as examination bodies, guidance counsellors, government and non-governmental organization (USAID, UNICEF, UNESCO, etc.). This current study is engineering a new approach to the admission and graduation processes of the secondary education system by constructing and standardizing an Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) among secondary school students. This implies that the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) can be administered to intending students as a pretest and as posttest at time of admissions and graduation to

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ascertain levels of corrupt practices, if any, at entry or exist points. Therefore it becomes very imperative to construct and standardize academic corruption sensitivity test among students in secondary school in Bayelsa State.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study was to construct and standardize an Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) among students in secondary school in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study was to:

1. Determine the Item scale values of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.
2. Establish the reliability coefficient of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary school in Bayelsa State.
3. Determine the validity of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary school in Bayelsa State.
4. Develop the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were used to guide the study:

1. What are the item scale values of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
2. What is the reliability coefficient of Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
3. How valid is the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
4. How does the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test being constructed and standardized among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Methodology

This study adopted an instrumentation research design which aided the researcher to construct and standardize an Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST). In this type of research design, instrument which lies in collecting data is being developed, validated and /or standardized. The study was carried out in Bayelsa State. The study population consisted of 10170 SS III students. The sample size was determined by using Taro Yamen's formula which gave a representative sample of 500. A cluster random sampling was used to select the sample size of 500. The population of the study was clustered into 11 clusters and five clusters were selected through simple random sampling. This sample consisted of 250 male and 250 female students covering 26 secondary schools within the selected clusters. A trial testing of the ACST was done. The first draft of the ACST was made up of 60 items and the instrument was validated through face, content validity and construct validity. Cronbach alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the ACST. Meanwhile, the study employed the use of percentile ranking, stanine, pearson product moment correlation and item scale value difference to analyze data obtained and select good items that form the final version of the ACST.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What are the item scale values of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

The appropriateness and suitability of each item of the academic corruption sensitivity test was determined using the item scale value difference (ISVD). The ISVD is the difference between the average scores for each item when the total scores are arranged in quartile. The ISVD of the 60-item ACST ranges from .09-2.37. However, items that had relatively high ISVD were selected to form the final version of the ACST.

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Table 1: Summary of ISVD of Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test in Rank Order

Initial Item No.	ISVD	Rank Order	Initial Item No.	ISVD	Rank Order	Initial Item No.	ISVD	Rank Order
27	2.37	1	3	1.57	14	60	1.08	26.5
8	2.25	2	*7	1.50	16	5	1.00	30
30	2.08	3.5	*9	1.50	16	20	1.00	30
32	2.08	3.5	47	1.50	16	*33	1.00	30
10	2.00	5	19	1.42	18.5	*49	1.00	30
11	1.92	6	*38	1.42	18.5	*55	1.00	30
37	1.91	7	56	1.41	20			
15	1.83	9.5	*36	1.33	21			
22	1.83	9.5	*16	1.25	23			
*28	1.83	9.5	50	1.25	23			
51	1.83	9.5	58	1.25	23			
34	1.67	12	*14	1.17	25			
17	1.58	13	*52	1.08	26.5			

Note: *stands for negative statement items

Source: Field work

Table 1 showed that 32 items met the condition for the selection. Nevertheless, the ACST was finally drafted with 30 items. They are 27, 8, 30, 32, 10, 11, 37, 15, 22, 28, 51, 34, 17, 3, 7, 9, 47, 19, 38, 56, 36, 50, 58, 41, 52, 60, 33, 49, and 55. That is items 5 and 20 were dropped for 49 and 55 in order to increase the negative item of the ACST, since they all had the same ISVD of 1.00. This was done to establish purity of item. This implies that the ACST scale is considered as a standardized non-cognitive scale to elicit academically based corrupt acts from students in secondary schools.

Research Question 2

What is the reliability coefficient of Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Summary of Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient

Method of Reliability	No of item	Sum of variance	Total test variance	Reliability coefficient
Cronbach Alpha	60	93.33	712.72	.89

Source: Field work

Table 2 shows that ACST has 60 items, 93.33 sum of item variance with total test variance of 712.72 gave a reliability coefficient of .89 using cronbach alpha reliability method. This implies that ACST is reliable. This can also mean that ACST items portray internal consistency using cronbach alpha.

Research Question 3

How valid is the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Summary of Construct Validity using Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Comparing Indices	Validity Coefficients (r)
Negative item scores (NIS) vs Positive Item scores (PIS)	.56
Negative Item Scores (NIS) vs Total Item Scores (TIS)	.86
Positive Item Scores (PIS) vs Total Item Scores (TIS)	.90

Source: Field work

Table 3 showed a construct validity coefficients of .56, .86 and .90 for NIS vs PIS, NIS vs TIS and PIS vs TIS respectively representing construct validity of the whole ACST items. These coefficients suggest that ACST was a valid test. It implies that ACST is designed to measure the psychological construct, academic corruption.

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Research Question 4

What is the final version of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test being constructed and standardized among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

The Likert-type scale was used in the construction and standardization of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST). A total of 60 items were first generated. 30 were positively structured while the other 30 were negatively structured. After the trial testing and item analysis the ACST had 30 items. Out of the 30 items, 19 were positively structured statements while 11 were negatively posed. This denotes that ACST stands as a non-cognitive scale for eliciting academic corrupt acts from students in secondary schools.

Table 4: Final Version of Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST)

N/S	STATEMENTS	RESPONSE LEVEL					Score
		SA	A	U	D	SD	
1	I cannot join others to threaten a teacher for the purpose of getting higher grade						
2	I am not very enthusiastic about stealing in examination						
*3	No one can write to satisfy West African Examination Council or National Examination Council except you use malpractices						
4	Stealing somebody's textbook is bad						
*5	I just need my five credits including English and mathematics. Therefore, I need to use machinery						
6	I hate destroying school's property whatever may be the reason						
*7	Copying from a colleague during examination is a good sense of helping one another to pass						
8	I enjoy having prep with my colleague than helping him/her in the examination						
*9	I am happy when one is offended in the class						
10	I get worried anytime I found myself in the midst of examination malpractices						
*11	I like making jest of a teacher with my colleagues						
12	It is bad to mock a teacher teaching you						
*13	There is nobody that passed through secondary school in Nigeria that did not do malpractices						
14	I hate teachers that exchange scores for money						
*15	I love teachers that exchange scores for money						
16	I needed no reward for rendering a service to a teacher						
*17	If I am looking for admission into any higher institution and the admission officer needs money I will give to get the admission						
18	In case I fail in an examination and there is opportunity to forge another result I will not do						
*19	I will not associate myself with teachers exchanging grades for money or kind						
20	Participating in examination malpractices makes me feel ashamed						
21	I hate to join others do examination malpractices in school						
*22	I go around a teacher in order to exchange scores for money or kind						
23	I will not peddle any information that will not benefit the school even though I have money						
24	I do not like using microchips, bullets, missiles whatever form they are called in the examination						
25	I will not give money to my teacher to give me higher score in examination						
*26	I will collect school fees but I will not pay						

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-
- | | |
|-----|--|
| 27 | If my teacher gives me a higher grade, which I know I do not merit I will ask him to change it |
| 28 | Any money or power cult members may have let them have I will not be one of them |
| *29 | If I am entrusted to share exercise books to all students I will share but will remain some for my private use |
| 30 | I hate to be among groups that always use violence to achieve what they want |

Total

Source: Field Work

Discussion of Findings

This study was to construct and develop a corruption sensitivity test among secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The items were selected based on the item scale value difference (ISVD). The ISVD of the 60-item ACST ranges from .09-2.37. However, items that had relatively high ISVD were selected to form the final version of the ACST as evidently shown in table 1. Onunkwo (2005) maintained that such analysis assesses the essential qualities of each item in a scale. This is in line with (Osarumwense, 2022) that used factor analysis to select items that had < .30 factor loadings were deleted as well as those that loaded more than one factor. In the same vein, scale purification depends on the process of eliminating items from multi-item scales, Wieland et al. (2017) stated. A framework presented by Wieland et al. (2017) highlights that both statistical and judgmental criteria need to be taken under consideration when making scale purification decisions. This view supports the process adopted in this current study to select items to form the ACST.

Other findings of the study were that the ACST scale was considered reliable and valid. Some of the fundamental qualities of a good instrument are include validity, reliability and usability. This study had determined the reliability and validity of the instrument. This study adopted the Cronbach alpha method of determining reliability. Onunkwo (2005) revealed that Cronbach alpha measures internal consistency of items of an instrument and stating that the nearer the reliability coefficient to one, the higher the reliability of the test and the better the test. Also, Transparency International (2000) presented its corruption perception index (CPI) reliability coefficient as .88 and was observed reliable hence, the ACST with .89 reliability coefficient was argued to be reliable and good. This value was consistent with the work of Owan et al. (2023), stating that the questionnaire constructed and standardized demonstrates strong internal consistency, with Cronbach's Alpha values ranging from .89 to .99. Thus, the items of ACST were internally consistent. Similarly, the instrument was subjected to face, content and construct validity.

Onunkwo (2005) supports that some of the techniques utilized in determining construct validity of measuring instruments are age differentiation, correlation with other tests and internal consistency. The coefficient observed showed that both positively structured and negatively structured items correlate well with the total test. Onunkwo (2005) posited that the more the sub-test or items correlates the total test the more the degree of homogeneity of the test and the extent of homogeneity of a test is its extent of construct validity. Also, a previous study observed that validity test with Pearson Product Moment Correlation shows arithmetic $>.361$ was valid (able to measure what should be measured), Saptono (2018) argued.

Again, the ACST was subjected to face and content validity before determining the construct validity. Thus, the ACST test items were assessed clarity of words, brevity of statements, language difficulty, relevance to course content and ambiguity of the items. It was a means to ensure face and content validity. Measurement and evaluation experts were consulted alongside with journalists, police and magistrates however the later content experts confirmed that the items were measuring unethical behaviours in schools. Therefore, the ACST instrument is adjudged valid. The study contributed to knowledge by packaging the final version of the ACST scale. The items were generated from the work of Dethire (2003), Lambsdorff (2005) and Natia (2004). These works helped the item writing less ambiguous and language easier to comprehend. As observed in the research question 1, item scale value difference was used in selecting the good items which constitute the final version of the ACST as in Table 5. The Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test is constructed and standardized following all procedures for test standardization. Thus, the ACST possess all characteristics of a good standardized test such as validity, reliability, objectivity, normation and usability.

Conclusions

Based on the statistical procedures adopted for the construction and standardization of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST), the study concludes that ACST was a standardized test for eliciting academic corrupt behaviours

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among students in secondary school in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. It had a reliability coefficient of .89 and the items were found suitable and appropriate in measuring academic corruption hence ACST was valid. It can be concluded that the ACST items were found having a relatively high discriminative scale value of range 1.00 – 2.37.

Recommendation

Following the conclusion, the researcher recommends the following:

1. The Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test should be used by classroom teachers, guidance counselors and other test focal persons to measure corrupt acts among students. This would help identify honest and dishonest students.
2. Educational institutions should use the ACST alongside with aptitude test for admission purposes.
3. Government should formulate a policy to use ACST in every secondary school periodically and give necessary guidance and counselling services in Bayelsa State and Nigeria at large.
4. Non-governmental organization should consider using ACST or adapt it in their scales such a Corruption Perception Index (CPI).

References

- Amuche, M. (2003, February 5). *Stemming the monster or corruption*. Retrieved from Thisday.
- Dethire, J. J. (2003). Corruption in the CIS-7 countries. *Lucerne CIS-7 Conference* (pp. 20-23). International Monetary Fund.
- Federal Republic Nigeria (FRN). (2004). *National Policy on Education, revised edition*. Ministry of Education.
- Galtung, F. (2005). Measuring the immeasurable: Boundaries and functions of (Macro) corruption indices. In F. Galtung, & S. (Charles, *Measuring Corruption*. Ashgate.
- Ganner, B. A. (1999). *Black's law dictionary (7th ed.)*. West Group.
- Lambsdorff, J. G. (2005). *Empirical foundation of recent research on corruption*. Kluwer Academics.
- Montessori, M., Rafni, A., Irawadi, J., & Ambiyar, U. V. (2021). Design of affective assessment on civic education subject. *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 9(8), 82-91.
- Natia, J. (2004, January 9). *Fighting corruption in Georgia's universities*. Retrieved from <http://www.aaup.org/publication/academe/20004/0450/0480Jana.html>.
- Obansajo, O. (2000). Address given on the occasion of the formal signing into law of the corrupt practices and other related offences act 2000 at Abuja. *Anti-Corruption Law of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 2000* (pp. 1-3). Lagos: Time Press.
- Onunkwo, G. I. (2002). *Fundamentals educational measurement and evaluations*. Cape.
- Onunkwo, G. I. (2005). *Test: types, preparation, administration, communication*. VIGO Publishers International.
- Opalaye, B. (2005). Reawakening in education. In S. O. Asaju, S. A. Tanimola, & J. A. Akintunde, *Church Training programmes for adults and young adults* (pp. 92-93). Nigerian Baptist Convention.
- Osarumwense, J. H. (2022). Construction, validation and standardization of mathematics learning resources management strategies scale. *Rivers State University Journal of Education*, 25(1), 118-136.
- Owan, V. J., Bassey, B. A., & Ubi, I. O. (2023). Construction and standardisation of an instrument measuring lecturers' persistence to publish in Scopus-indexed journals. *Journal of Applied Learning & Teaching*, 6(2), doi: 10.37074/jait.2023.6.2.37, 1-14.
- Saptono, A. (2018). Development of an assessment instrument of affective domain for entrepreneurship in senior high school. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 21(4), 1-12.
- Schmid, C. F. (1949). Scaling techniques in sociological research. In P. V. Young, *Scientific social survey and research*. (pp. 50-62). Prentice Hall, Inc.
- Transparency International. (2000, October 1). *Transparency international source book*. Retrieved from [transparency.org: http://www.transparency.org/sourcebook/22-html](http://www.transparency.org/sourcebook/22-html)
- University of Port Harcourt. (2004). *Handbook of College of continuing education*. Uniport Press.

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Teachers' Perception of the Status of Teaching and Learning of Sciences among Secondary School Students in Zamfara State: Implications for Sustainable Development Goals

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Abstract

To achieve quality education as one of the goals of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), it requires effective teaching and learning at all educational levels in Nigeria. This study therefore adopted a descriptive survey research design to find out the perception of science teachers in both male and female secondary schools on teaching and learning sciences in Zamfara state, this is to ascertain that the system of education practice in the state comply with SDGs. Population of the study consists of all public Secondary School Science Teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Zamfara State. A Sample size of 158 (Male=70 and Female=88) teachers were drawn from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. Four research questions were raised and one hypothesis was tested. The data were collected using a structured questionnaire (STQTLPSS) developed by the researchers in line with the indicators of SDGs goal 4 target 4a. The instrument was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained using Cronbach's Alpha reliability test. The data were analysis using descriptive statistics and Mann-Whitney U-Test. The result of the study revealed that teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state has not reach expectation to meet up with target 4a of SDGs as the response of science teachers pointed out some challenges hindering their effectiveness in teaching. Also there are significant difference in some aspect of teaching and learning of science subjects between male schools and female schools. Among others, significant difference existed in the level of students' engagement in the lesson. This call for gender equality in the teaching of science subjects at secondary schools in Zamfara state. It was concluded that the situation of teaching and learning in Zamfara state as not be adequately on the track of SDGs. It was recommended that state government and school administrators should put in place all what it requires in making effective teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools and establishing mechanism to maintain gender equality.

Keywords: Teachers' perception, teaching and learning, attainment, SDG, science teachers

Introduction

Considering the environmental problems experienced today, living in a balance and harmony with nature can only be achieved through formal education. Education is a prerequisite for sustainable development, which reveals the idea of a more viable world and a better future. Education has a role in promoting country cultures. A way to facilitate the children to be a good citizen and promote Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is through science learning. Science is in line with children characteristics because, naturally, children were born to learn about science with their high curiosity. They will do an active process to know and to understand the world around them and they are able to acquire new knowledge of the activity (Syadiah & Mulyana, 2017). Through quality science education, children are able to know and realize their environmental conditions. Science education is fundamental to achieving several Sustainable Development Goals (SGDs), particularly Goal 4 (Quality Education) and Goal 13 (Climate Action).

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Quality science education as noted by UNESCO (2020) equips learners with critical thinking skills necessary for addressing complex global challenges. In Nigeria, where issues such as poverty, health crises, and environmental degradation are prevalent, effective science teaching can empower students to contribute to sustainable solutions. Science will enhance children's pride of their country and its culture, for instance to make them realize that they live in a rich country and should be grateful for it. In addition, children will be aware of existing environmental issues by knowing the cause and looking for a solution to the problems (Karaarslan & Teksöz, 2016). Science education can be a driving force in efforts to reduce poverty, violence and injustice (Holbrook, 2009). Creative and innovative science learning can utilize natural resources to develop physical products or ideas that are marketable, such as strategies for teaching children to plant crops, caring for animals, which results can be used to fulfil children's nutrition. Learning science for early childhood can also be done collaboratively; invite children to learn and to work together in solving environmental problems with peers without differentiating gender, ethnicity, or social status. Science learning is also very concerned about security principles that avoid violent behavior (Mulyana, Lidinillah & Syaodih, 2019).

One of the discussions on SDGs in Goal 4 is regarding quality education which discusses "ensuring education that is inclusive and of equal quality, also supports lifelong learning opportunities for all. This is to imply that for sustainable development goals to occupy in a society both individuals and the Governments at all level should embrace accessibility to quality education. Therefore, education becomes the indices for measuring the development capacity of both the individuals and the country at large. It becomes an important social commodity that is desired by all but relatively not affordable by all either on account of scarce resources or ill equipped teaching. This perhaps explains why UNESCO and World Education Forum (2015) recognize the global momentum of achieving accessible and quality education for children and adults. The term quality education is the process through which an individual is transformed into a participant in the social and economic development of his society (Daura and Audu, 2015). Quality education entails some standard or degree of excellence of the education system in meeting up with its desired goals. According to Elujekwute (2019) quality education covers the curriculum content, the instructional strategies, assessment and evaluation policies and procedures which determine the achievement and performance of the learners.

The imperative of quality education was stressed in Federal Republic of Nigeria National Policy on Education (FRN, 2004) where it states that the success of any education lies on proper planning, efficient administration and adequate funding and it expects these management service in education to achieve specified goals which include; (a) Assurance of quality control through regular and continuous supervision of instructional and other educational services. (b) Provision of efficient administrative and management control for maintenance and improvement of the system. SDGs does not left out the inclusion of women in every other goals particularly Goal 4 mention in Goal 5 (gender equality). SDG Goal 5 bring forward issue of gender based such as 5(1): End discrimination against women and girls and 5(C): Adopt and strengthen policies and enforceable legislation for gender equality. Achieving SDG 5 is a priority that contributes to increase in global well-being (Filho et al., 2022). According to Sen (2019), SDG5' targets are more fulsome and robust addressing different aspects of gender equality in economic, political and social. This study focuses on teachers' views on teaching and learning science at senior secondary schools to ascertain the level of attainment of sustainable development goals (4 and 5) and their centrality in the provision of information and knowledge and how this, in turn, can be used in the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at the national and local level.

Furthermore, the policy document of the SDGs was designed to be applicable in line with the different national realities, capacities, level of development and national aspirations. By implication, it could be said that effective implementation of the programme demands enhanced capacity of the populace and inclusiveness of the various sectors of the society (Anthony, 2022). Through effective teaching and learning, the learners are gradually equipped to face the demands of a more sustainable world. It is expected that the emerging educational goals, philosophy, strategies, improved curricula and pedagogical interventions on the education sector will contribute their quota immensely to the attainment of the SDGs. In effect, the teachers, especially the science teachers have a major role to play in the realization of these goals (Anthony, 2022). The major challenge of implementing any education programme lies squarely on the teachers. This is because the quality of teachers in any educational system will greatly affect the quality of teaching and learning that prevails in the system (FME, 2013). In other words, teachers at all levels are regarded as the Centre hub of any educational process. This therefore implies that the science teachers who are charged with the responsibility of executing educational programmes in the nation should not only be aware of both national and global demands but should equally be adequately equipped to understand the situation of teaching and learning towards these demands.

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Teachers hold a special position towards advancing the attainment of these goals because they localize content knowledge that brings about positive behavioral change in people, especially the younger generation. Teachers are fundamental to the development of any nation because they are an effective catalyst in the process of lifelong learning, which is fundamental for the attainment of any goal, especially the global goals. They mediate between educational content and the learners (Nwangwa and Inatimi, 2019). It is in this regard that they are truly the yardstick that measures the achievements and aspirations of the nation. The worth and potentialities of a country get evaluated in the work of teachers. It was in this direction that Musa, Jimba and Ogundele (2015) argued that the people of a country are the enlarged replica of their teachers because the teachers are the real nation builders. The teacher is the key of successful education as well as the achievement of SDGs. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2009) confirms this by stating that "no nation can rise above the quality of its teachers". In this connection, it can be safely inferred that no meaningful transformation can be achieved in Nigeria without the teachers playing their roles. Therefore, the task of achieving any societal goal ably rests on teachers because they are responsible for effecting attitudinal change in the learners.

It has been argued that teachers serve as models for their students (Cheung 2020); hence, teachers' perspectives and how these are enacted, will influence their students. Vukic (2019) noted that if education is to help students change towards a lifestyle that is undergirded by sustainable development principles there is need for focus on those whose perspectives and actions will influence these students by the teachers. The task of teaching as carried out by teachers is shaped by their thoughts and actions. Researchers have long established that teachers' thinking and classroom practice are interrelated and as such, teachers' thinking influences their classroom instructional practice (Fischer and Hänze 2020). Teachers' views are often shaped by the beliefs they hold about curriculum, students, pedagogy and the learning process, which in turn influence learning outcomes. Therefore, sending clear and consistent signals to teachers about what to teach is an important component of teaching for sustainable development in schools. Delivering or facilitating sustainable development content without attention to how teachers understand, interpret, and internalize sustainable development principles will have little or no effect on classroom practice (Darling-Hammond et al. 2020). Specific to how teachers' views influence their teaching of sustainable development, Vukic (2019) noted that though teachers had general ideas about their responsibility towards sustainable development this did not translate to active practice in organizing and deliberately undertaking sustainability activities to influence students' behavior. Teachers' perceptions are a major predictor of the use of new technologies in institutional settings as well as mode and level of implementation of any educational programme. Perception towards a programme will potentially influence its practice and success. Perception involves the identification and interpretation of information to understand an issue in the environment (Schacter, 2011). For the teachers' enhanced perception of the school curriculum, school environment, adequate funding, availability of resources and continuous training have a great role to play. A well informed and capable person is more likely to lend himself towards government policies and programmes than an uninformed one. Therefore, the government at all levels have a major role to play in ensuring that teachers are carried along in the planning and implementation of her programmes such as the SDGs and others. The level of awareness and the quality of knowledge possessed by the teachers on such programmes will have a marked effect on the way they are perceived. Invariably, this also will determine the level to which they are ready to deliver the teaching/learning process towards the realization of the goals of SDGs. Students are therefore able to relate what they learn in the classroom to their real life actions, and will increasingly be in a better position to take the lead in changing behaviours and adopting sustainable lifestyles in all their endeavours.

Statement of the Research Problem

Despite the importance of science education in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), there are concerns about the effectiveness of science teaching and learning in Nigerian senior secondary schools, particularly in Zamfara State. Studies have shown that teachers in Zamfara State often face challenges such as inadequate learning resources (Adeniran, 2020) and lack of professional development (Aminu & Samah, 2019). These factors can lead to an ineffective teaching of science than it could be. The system of education in practicing in Zamfara state that is co-educational (boys only and girls only) could be a gender bias in catering for effective teaching of science which may not support SDGs agenda at 2030. This global initiatives designed aiming to benefit daily lives of people cannot be implemented appropriately unless they are monitor and accountable. Teachers' views on teaching and learning science are crucial in understanding the challenges and opportunities in science education. There is hardly any information on science teachers at senior secondary schools views in monitoring of SDGs especially in the north-west Geo-political Zone of Nigeria. Furthermore, available studies on college of education lecturers' perception of SDGs (Anthony, 2022) failed to investigate the teachers' views on the teaching and learning sciences for the attainment of SDGs. Also, inadequacies of gender indicator will make it harder to accurately identify, analyze and monitor the

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separate needs in the two categories of the school system and develop effective evidence-based policies and solution (Odera & Mulusa, 2020). The need to fill these gaps and other similar ones necessitated this study.

Objectives of the study

The following were the specific objective of the study:

1. To find out Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.
2. To find out Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.
3. To find out Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.
4. To determine the difference between the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male and female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?
2. What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?
3. What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?
4. What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male and female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?

Hypothesis

The following research hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significant:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male and female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.

Methodology

The researchers adopted descriptive survey research design. The target population comprises 260 science teachers which include Physics, Chemistry, Biology and Mathematics teachers in co-educational public senior secondary schools in Zamfara state. Taro Yamen formula was used to arrive at sampling 158 science teachers. Purposive random sampling was used to select 20 schools (10 male schools and 10 female schools). Stratified random sampling was used to select 70 science teachers in male schools and 88 science teachers in female schools. The instrument title Science Teachers Questionnaire on Teaching and Learning Process of Science Subjects (STQTLPSS) was used for data collection. The STQTLPSS was developed by the researchers in line with the indicators of SDGs Goal 4 Target 4a. Section 1 of the instrument contains demographic data and section 2 contains 16 items in 4-point scale: strongly Agree (SA) – 4 points, Agree (A) – 3 points, Disagree (D) – 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1. The instrument was validated and pilot tested. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined with Cronbach's Alpha and yielded 0.78. The instrument was administered and collected for collation from respondents. Research questions were answered using frequent count, mean and standard deviation and Mann-Whitney U-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significant. The benchmark for decision making was 2.50, any mean score greater than or equal to 2.5 indicated agreement while mean less than 2.5 indicated disagreement.

Results

Research Question 1:

What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?

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Table 1: Descriptive analysis of science teachers' response on the status of teaching and learning science subjects at senior secondary schools

Item	N	Responses				\bar{X}	S. Dev.	Remark
		SA	A	D	SD			
1	158	60	80	18	-	3.22	0.653	Agreed
2	158	72	80	6	-	3.42	0.567	Agreed
3	156	34	58	44	20	2.68	0.957	Agreed
4	158	82	68	4	4	3.44	0.672	Agreed
5	156	32	90	28	6	2.95	0.734	Agreed
6	156	58	78	18	2	3.23	0.699	Agreed
7	150	46	70	30	4	3.05	0.784	Agreed
8	156	12	60	60	24	2.39	0.838	Disagreed
9	154	82	54	16	2	3.40	0.728	Agreed
10	154	18	34	52	50	2.13	1.001	Disagreed
11	156	52	82	12	10	3.13	0.809	Agreed
12	148	28	32	58	30	2.39	1.014	Disagreed
13	156	8	28	70	50	1.96	0.842	Disagreed
14	154	16	34	74	30	2.23	0.884	Disagreed
15	156	22	96	34	4	2.87	0.669	Agreed
16	156	46	58	42	10	2.90	0.903	Agreed
Grand Mean						2.84	0.797	Agreed

N: Number of respondents; \bar{X} =Mean; S. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Source: Field work, (2024)

Table 1 shows that science teachers agreed on items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11, 15 and 16 since their mean responses greater than 2.50. They disagreed on items 8,10,12,13 and 14 as their mean responses less than 2.50. This means that effective teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state is not up to the task as the science teachers responded that they lack attending professional development; they have challenges of delivering effective teaching due to shortage of textbooks, lack of science practical equipments and too much work load; no enough qualified science teachers; lack of facilities to implement innovative teaching; and lack of the improvement on teachers' remuneration. The grand mean shows that science teachers agreed that there is improved situation of teaching and learning science subjects in senior secondary schools as mean = 2.84 and standard deviation = 0.797

Research Question 2:

What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?

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Table 2: Descriptive analysis of male science teachers' response on the status of teaching and learning science subjects at male senior secondary schools

Item	N	Responses				\bar{X}	S. Dev.	Remark
		SA	A	D	SD			
1	70	24	30	16	-	3.11	0.753	Agreed
2	70	26	44	-	-	3.37	0.487	Agreed
3	68	12	26	16	14	2.53	1.014	Agreed
4	70	30	34	4	2	3.31	0.713	Agreed
5	70	10	48	8	4	2.91	0.697	Agreed
6	70	12	46	10	2	2.97	0.659	Agreed
7	68	14	28	22	4	2.77	0.849	Agreed
8	70	6	24	28	12	2.34	0.866	Disagreed
9	70	36	24	10	-	3.37	0.726	Agreed
10	70	10	12	26	22	2.14	1.026	Disagreed
11	70	16	38	6	10	2.86	0.937	Agreed
12	66	18	10	24	14	2.49	1.113	Disagreed
13	70	6	14	36	14	2.17	0.851	Disagreed
14	70	10	20	28	12	2.40	0.939	Disagreed
15	70	8	42	18	2	2.80	0.672	Agreed
16	70	24	28	12	6	3.00	0.827	Agreed
Grand Mean						2.78	0.827	Agreed

N: Number of respondents; \bar{X} =Mean; S. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Source: Field work, (2024)

In table 2, it was also observed that male science teachers agreed on items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11, 15 and 16 since their mean responses greater than 2.50. They disagreed on items 8,10,12,13 and 14 as their mean responses less than 2.50. This means that effective teaching and learning of science subjects at male senior secondary schools in Zamfara state is not up to the task as the science teachers in the schools responded that they lack attending professional development; they have challenges of delivering effective teaching due to shortage of textbooks, lack of science practical equipments and too much work load; no enough qualified science teachers; lack of facilities to implement innovative teaching; and lack of the improvement on teachers' remuneration. The grand mean shows that science teachers agreed that there is improved situation of teaching and learning science subjects in senior secondary schools as mean = 2.78 and standard deviation = 0.827.

Research Question 3:

What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?

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Table 3: Descriptive analysis of female science teachers' response on the status of teaching and learning science subjects at female senior secondary schools

Item	N	Responses				\bar{X}	S. Dev.	Remark
		SA	A	D	SD			
1	88	36	50	2	-	3.39	0.535	Agreed
2	88	46	36	6	-	3.46	0.624	Agreed
3	88	22	32	28	6	2.80	0.899	Agreed
4	88	52	34	-	2	3.55	0.624	Agreed
5	86	22	42	20	2	2.98	0.766	Agreed
6	86	46	32	8	-	3.44	0.662	Agreed
7	82	32	42	8	-	3.29	0.638	Agreed
8	86	6	36	32	12	2.42	0.818	Disagreed
9	84	46	30	6	2	3.43	0.733	Agreed
10	84	8	22	26	28	2.12	0.987	Disagreed
11	86	36	44	6	-	3.35	0.609	Agreed
12	82	10	22	34	16	2.32	0.928	Disagreed
13	86	2	14	34	36	1.79	0.799	Disagreed
14	84	6	14	46	18	2.10	0.816	Disagreed
15	86	14	54	16	2	2.93	0.665	Agreed
16	86	22	30	30	4	2.81	0.75	Agreed
Grand Mean						2.87	0.749	Agreed

N: Number respondents; \bar{X} =Mean; S. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Source: Field work, (2024)

As shown in table 3, female science teachers also agreed on items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11, 15 and 16 since their mean responses greater than 2.50. They disagreed on items 8,10,12,13 and 14 as their mean responses less than 2.50. This means that effective teaching and learning of science subjects at female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state is not up to the task as the teachers in schools responded that they lack attending professional development; they have challenges of delivering effective teaching due to shortage of textbooks, lack of science practical equipments and too much work load; no enough qualified science teachers; lack of facilities to implement innovative teaching; and lack of the improvement on teachers' remuneration. The grand mean shows that science teachers agreed that there is improved situation of teaching and learning science subjects in senior secondary schools as mean = 2.87 and standard deviation = 0.749

Research Question 4:

What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male and female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?

Table 4: Descriptive analysis comparing mean response of science teachers in male schools and those in female schools.

School Type	N	\bar{X}	S. Dev.	Mean Difference
Male School	70	2.78	0.827	0.09
Female School	88	2.87	0.749	

N: Number respondents; \bar{X} =Mean; S. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Source: Field work, (2024)

As revealed in the table 4, the mean response of science teachers in female senior secondary schools (2.87) is higher than the mean response of science teachers in male senior secondary schools (2.78) with mean difference of 0.09. This implies that science teachers in female secondary schools rate teaching and learning process of science subjects higher compare to what is obtainable in male secondary schools.

Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male and female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.

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Table 5: Mann-Whitney U-Test analysis comparing the mean responses of science teachers in male secondary schools and those in female secondary schools

Item	School Type	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U-Test	Sig.	Remark
1	Male School	70	71.30	4991.00	2506.000	0.026	S
	Female School	88	86.02	7570.00			
2	Male School	70	74.73	5231.00	2746.000	0.184	NS
	Female School	88	83.30	7330.00			
3	Male School	68	72.53	4932.00	2586.000	0.129	NS
	Female School	88	83.11	7314.00			
4	Male School	70	72.53	4932.00	2516.000	0.025	S
	Female School	88	83.11	7314.00			
5	Male School	70	77.13	5399.00	2914.000	0.701	NS
	Female School	86	79.62	6847.00			
6	Male School	70	62.64	4385.00	1900.000	0.000	S
	Female School	86	91.41	7861.00			
7	Male School	68	61.32	4170.00	1824.000	0.000	S
	Female School	82	87.26	7155.00			
8	Male School	70	76.10	5327.00	2842.000	0.524	NS
	Female School	86	80.45	6919.00			
9	Male School	70	75.47	5283.00	2798.000	0.566	NS
	Female School	84	79.19	6652.00			
10	Male School	70	77.70	5111.00	2926.000	0.958	NS
	Female School	84	77.33	5915.00			
11	Male School	70	66.50	4655.00	2170.000	0.001	S
	Female School	86	88.27	7591.00			
12	Male School	66	77.44	5111.00	2512.000	0.434	NS
	Female School	82	72.13	5915.00			
13	Male School	70	89.04	6233.00	2272.000	0.005	S
	Female School	86	69.92	6013.00			
14	Male School	70	85.30	5971.00	2394.000	0.034	S
	Female School	84	71.00	5964.00			
15	Male School	70	74.13	5189.00	2704.000	0.209	NS
	Female School	86	82.06	7057.00			
16	Male School	70	84.24	5897.00	2608.000	0.132	NS
	Female School	86	73.83	6349.00			
Overall Test	Male School	70	77.54	5201.00	2514.000	0.246	NS
	Female School	88	86.68	6912.00			

N: Number respondents; S: Significant; NS: Not Significant

Source: Field work, (2024)

Table 5 shows that the hypothesis was accepted in items 2, 3, 5, 8, 9, 10, 12, 15, and 16. This means that significant difference does not exist in the mean response of science teachers in male senior secondary schools and those in female secondary schools on the items since $P > 0.05$ in each of them. But, significant difference existed in the mean response on items 1, 4, 6, 7, 11, 13 and 14 showing that teaching and learning of sciences are difference as a result of differences in the teachers knowledge about relevance of curriculum, students engagement in the lesson, the rate of students assessment, methods of students assessment, level of administrative support, challenges of implementing innovative teaching techniques and the level of teachers commitment in teaching due to poor remuneration respectively. The mean response on 1, 4, 6, 7, and 11 are in favour of female schools while mean response on 13 and 14 are in favour of male schools. This means that there is need for balance in some aspects of teaching and learning in both male schools and female schools to avoid gender bias. The overall test shows that in the general response, there is no significant difference between the mean response of science teachers in male schools and those

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in female school ($U = 2514.000, P > 0.05$) but teaching and learning rank higher in female school than male school as their mean ranks are 5201 and 6812 for male schools and female schools respectively.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that teaching and learning of science subjects at both male and female secondary schools operating in Zamfara state still requires more effort from the state and agents such as science teachers and school administration to improve its status up to the task. In spite of general agreement of science teachers that there is improved teaching and learning of science subjects in their schools, the findings show that there are several challenges which hinder their effectiveness. The challenges are lack of the opportunity to attend professional development programme, shortage of textbooks, lack of science practical equipments, too much work load, no enough qualified science teachers, lack of facilities to implement innovative teaching and lack of the improvement on teachers' remuneration. This findings acknowledge the findings of Fomunyan (2019) which identified the challenges facing in Nigeria secondary schools which hindering effectiveness of teaching and learning of science at that level as lack of infrastructure and facility, lack of digitalization of Nigeria education, brain drain which resulted to lack of qualified science teachers, low salary and lack of incentives for science teachers. The findings also support the findings of Sodangi et al. (2022) which reported that secondary school science teachers in Zamfara state have not been participating professional development programmes.

The study also revealed that in Zamfara state, the effective condition of teaching and learning of science in female schools is now more than what is obtainable in male secondary schools. This could be that more focus as been put on female education as the evidence of the report of Stoet and Greary (2018) that almost all countries have concern on underrepresented of female in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) and the strength and pursuit increase as the increase in national gender equality. Furthermore, the findings reveal discrepancies in some aspects of teaching and learning of science between male secondary schools and female secondary schools. It was revealed that there were significant differences in some aspects which some favour female schools and some favour male schools. The aspects in which differences existed are teachers knowledge about relevance of curriculum, students engagement in the lesson, the rate of students assessment, methods of students assessment, level of administrative support, challenges of implementing innovative teaching techniques and the level of teachers commitment in teaching due to poor remuneration. These aspects are related to teaching strategies and pedagogy and these are the heart of teaching influence effective teaching and learning. The aspects missing by male schools counterbalanced those one missing by female schools that is why at the end there was no significant difference existed. As noted by Obidovna (2023) effective teaching strategies and pedagogies can serve as basis for updating and improving teaching practice in modern condition. Therefore, these aspects identified needs attention to be improved upon for effective teaching and learning.

Implication of findings on SDGs

The 2030 agenda for sustainable development came into effect on 1st of January, 2016. The SDGs possess several useful targets which hopefully will make a better live for everyone. This agenda is gradually coming to an end period. Therefore, there is needs to understand how far the achievement of it. According to Odera and Mulusa (2020), one of the limitations in implementing Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) is lack of proper monitoring and report progress. The researchers intended to use the findings of this to determine if the teaching and learning of science at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state is on the track of SDGs due to the system of education practice in the state. The SDGs goal 4 is to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. This is to provide effective teaching and in the schools. Hence the findings shows that Zamfara state is yet to meet the target of this aspect of the agenda because there are some aspect of teaching and learning of science need to improve upon. Gender equality also is a goal (Goal 5) that cut across every other goal. Since it was observed from the findings that there are discrepancies in the missing aspect of teaching and learning of science in both male schools and female schools, the issue of gender equality need to be address in the teaching and learning at secondary schools.

Conclusion

It was concluded from the findings of this study that the situation of teaching and learning of science subjects among senior secondary schools need to be address in order to be in line with SDGs.

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Recommendations

The researchers recommended that state government and school administrators should put in place all what it require in making effective teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools and establishing mechanism to maintain gender equality. Hence, the following are recommended:

1. The ministry of education and school administrators should regularly give science teachers the opportunity to attend professional development in their field.
2. School administrators should find means of providing adequate materials for effective teaching and learning.
3. School administrator should support by providing require facilities and amenities for implementing innovative teaching techniques.
4. The school should also set a quality assurance committee to frequently check what teachers are doing in class with students to maintain quality teaching.
5. State government should recruit more qualified science teachers and equally share to schools.
6. State government should improve remuneration of teachers and science teachers should be more committed in their profession for better future of students.

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References

- Adeniran, S. A. (2020). Influence of Teaching and Learning Resources on Student's Performance In Senior Secondary Schools in Gusau Local Government, Zamfara State. *The Eurasia Proceedings of Educational & Social Sciences*, 18, 124-131. ISSN: 2587- 1730
- Aminu, M. & Samah, N. A. (2019). Teachers perception on the use of technology in teaching and learning in associate schools Zamfara state, Nigeria. *Sustainability And Society*, 2(2), 1-4. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.26480/ess.02.2019.01.04>
- Anthony, A. I. (2022). Perception of sustainable development goals among science lecturers in colleges of education in south-south Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Education and Sustainable Development*, 2(11), 1-14
- Aydın, S. & Subasi, M. (2021). Science Teachers 'Views on Sustainable Development *International Journal of Eurasian Education and Culture*, 6(13), 1171-1205. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.35826/ijoecc.397>
- Cheung, P. (2020). Teachers as Role Models for Physical Activity: Are Preschool Children More Active When Their Teachers Are Active? *European Physical Education Review* 26 (1): 101–110. doi:10.1177/1356336X19835240
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B. & Osher, B. (2020). Implications for Educational Practice of the Science of Learning and Development." *Applied Developmental Science* 24 (2): 97–140. doi:10.1080/1088 8691.2018.1537791.
- Daura, A. H. & Audu, R. (2015). Challenges of the implementation of the universal basic education programme in Yobe State, Nigeria and the prospects for 2015 and beyond. *Global Journal of Politics and Law Research*, 3(3), 72-95.
- Federal Government of Nigeria (FRN, 2004). *National policy on education (4th Edition)*. Lagos: Nigeria NERCD.
- Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2013). *National Policy on Education (6th Edition)*. Abuja: NERDC Press.
- Filho, W. L., Kovaleva, M., Tsani, S., Țircă, D. M., Shiel, C., Dinis, M. A. P., Nicolau, M., Sima, M., Fritzen, B., Salvia, A. L., Minhas, A., Kozlova, V., Doni, F., Spiteri, J., Gupta, T., Wakunuma, K., Sharma, M., Barbir, J., Shulla, K., Bhandari, M. P. & Tripathi, S. (2022). Promoting gender equality across the sustainable development goals. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 25, 14177–14198. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02656-1>
- Fischer, E. & Hänze, M. (2020). How Do University Teachers' Values and Beliefs Affect Their Teaching? *Educational Psychology* 40 (3): 296–317. doi:10.1080/01443410.2019.1675867.
- Elujekwute, E. C. (2019). *Educational management; Concept and theories. Makurdi*. Destiny Ventures.
- Gustafsson, P., Engström, S. & Svenson, A. (2015). Teachers' View of Sustainable Development in Swedish Upper Secondary School. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 167: 7– 14. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.12.635.
- Holbrook, J. (2009). Meeting Challenges to Sustainable Development through Science and Technology Education. *Science Education International*, 20, 44-59.

Teachers' Perception on the Status ... (Aliu, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15258606>

- Karaarslan, G., & Teksöz, G. (2016). Integrating sustainable development concept into science education program is not enough: We need competent science teachers for education for sustainable development Turkish experience. *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, 11(15), 8403- 842
- Nwangwa, C. K. & Inatimi, I. (2019). Teachers' awareness and sustainable development goals attainment in secondary schools in bayelsa state. *IJARIE* 5(6), 2395-4396
- Maryanti, R., Rahayu, N. I., Muktiarni, M., AL husaeni, D. F., Hufad, A. & Sunardi, S. (2022). Sustainable development goals in science education: definition, literature review, and bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*. 161-181
- Mulyana, E. H., Lidinillah, D. A. & Syaodih, Q. E. (2019). Science Learning Quality to Promote Sustainable Development in Early Childhood Education: A Case Study of Teachers in Tasikmalaya. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 45 (4), 86-90
- Musa, J. M., Jimba, D. N. & Ogundele, M. O. (2015). The role of teachers in transforming Nigeria: Challenges and the way forward. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(2), 56-62.
- Odera, J. A. & Mulusa, J. (2020). SDGs gender equality and women's empowerment: What prospects for delivery. In M. Kaltenborn, M. Krajewski & H. Kuhn (Eds.), *Sustainable Development Goals and Human Rights, Interdisciplinary Studies in Human Rights* 5, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-30469-0_6
- Rieckmann, M. (2017). *Education for sustainable development goals: Learning objectives*. UNESCO Publishing.
- Schacter, D. L. (2011). How to help a bully. Recommendations for counselling the proactive aggressor. *Professional School Counselling*, 11, 120-128.
- Sen, G. (2019). Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment: Feminist Mobilization for the SDGs. *Global Policy*, 10 (1), 28 – 38. [http:// 10:Suppl.1](http://10:Suppl.1) doi: 10.1111/1758-5899.12593
- Sodangi, U., Isma'il, A., & Aliu, A. (2022). Perception of secondary school science and mathematics teachers on Professional development participation in Zamfara State, Nigeria. *Integrity Journal of Education and Training*, 6(2), 37-45.
- Syaodih, E., & Mulyana, E. H. (2017). When science becomes an approach in early learning: know it, understand it and do it. *Journal of Nusantara Studies (JONUS)*, 2(2), 98-106.
- Ferguson, T., Roofe, C. & Cook, L. D. (2021). Teachers' perspectives on sustainable development: the implications for education for sustainable development, *Environmental Education Research*, 27(9), 1343-1359, DOI:10.1080/13504622.2021.1921113
- United Nations (UN, 2015). Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for sustainable Development. UN, New York.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization. (2008). The contribution of early childhood education for sustainable society. Paris: UNESCO
- United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization. (2010). Reaching the marginalized, Global monitoring report 2010. Paris: UNESCO.
- UNESCO (2015). Rethinking education: Towards a global common good? Retrieved on 29th Nov. 2024 from <http://www.unesco.org/new/fileadmin/MULTIMEDIA/FIELD/Cairo/images/RethinkingEducation.pdf>.
- UNESCO (2017B). Education for Sustainable Development Goals Learning Objectives. *The Global Education 2030 Agenda*. UNESCO, Paris.
- Vukic, T. (2019). Sustainable Development from High School Teacher's Perspective. *Philosophy, Sociology, Psychology and History* 18 (3): 131–148. doi:10.22190/FUPSPH1903131V
- World Commission on Environment and Developments (1987). Our common good. Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future. Retrieved on 28th Nov., 2024 from <http://www.undocuments.net/our-common-future.pdf>

Step-By-Step Application of Shifted Legendre Polynomials on Numerical Assessment of Non-Linear Bratu Differential Equations

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Abstract

The approximate solution of Bratu differential equations was obtained using the modified variational iteration algorithm with shifted Legendre polynomials. The suggested modification is created by constructing shifted Legendre polynomials for the provided problem and using them as the basis functions for the approximation. To show that the recommended approach is efficient, dependable, and reliable, two test problems were also provided. The maple 18 program was used to perform the calculations.

Keyword: Differential equations, variational iteration technique, shifted Legendre polynomials, bratu equations, approximate solution.

Introduction

Application of numerical solution in solving various forms of real-life problems involving all kinds of equations, some of which may not have analytical solution is one of the interests of researchers in computational mathematics. Otaide et al. (2023) and Otaide et al. (2024) for examples, applied shifted Vieta Lucas polynomials differently in their work. Fadugba et al. (2023) considered applicability and analysis of trigonometric - exponential single-step method for the numerical solution of HIV-1 model while Otaide & Oluwayemi (2024) also considered linear Volterra integro differential equations using variational iteration algorithm with collocation. In this work however, the authors are interested in a step-by-step application of shifted Legendre polynomials on numerical assessment of non-linear Bratu differential equations. The initial thermal combustion theory, which was developed by the simplification of the solid fuel ignition model, is what is known as a one-dimensional Bratu-type problem and is what gives Eqn (1) its significance. To this end, numerous studies on Bratu-type differential equations have been conducted. Salema & Thanoona (2022) used the perturbation method to solve the problem of the Bratu type. Zarebnia & Hoshyar (2014) employed spline technique for the solution of Bratu's type problem. Wazwaz (2016) used method of successive differentiation for solving Bratu's type equations. Saravi et al. (2013) used the He's variational Iteration Method for the solution of Bratu's equation. For the numerical solution of second order initial value problems of Bratu-type equations, Fenta & Derese (2019) used the sixth order Runge-Kutta seven stages technique. Bratu-type problems were addressed by Ezekiel (2013) using the New Improved Variational Homotopy Perturbation Technique. The Bratu's problem was approximated analytically by Hassan & Semaary (2013) using the optimal homotopy analysis technique. When solving the Bratu problem numerically, Aregbesola (2003) employed the weighted residual technique. For the handling of equations of the Bratu's type, Wazwaz (2005) employed Adomians' decomposition technique. For the resolution of Bratu's problem, Changqing & Jianhua (2013) used the Chebyshev wavelets method. In this study, the numerical solution of Bratu's differential equation (1) with provided initial conditions (2) is obtained using variational iteration algorithm using shifted Legendre polynomials.

$$\frac{d^2\varphi}{d\tau^2} + \gamma e^{\alpha\varphi} = 0; \quad 0 < \tau < 1; \quad \gamma, \alpha \in \mathfrak{R} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{with initial conditions } \varphi(\tau) = \varphi'(\tau) = 0; \quad \tau = 0. \quad (2)$$

The findings thus far are positive and trustworthy, and the suggested strategy operates effectively.

The Essential Concept of the Variational Iteration Algorithm

We consider the following general differential problem to demonstrate the technique's fundamental idea.

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$$L\varphi + N_l\varphi - g(\tau) = 0, \quad (3)$$

The inhomogeneous term is $g(\tau)$, L and N_l are linear and nonlinear operators, respectively.

We can create a correction functional as follows using the variational iteration analysis.

$$\varphi_{i+1} = \varphi(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(L\varphi_i + N_l\tilde{\varphi}_i - g)dt \quad (4)$$

In this case, the variational iteration technique can be used to most effectively identify the Lagrange multiplier $\lambda(t)$. The n th approximation is indicated by the subscript n , and the limited variation $\tilde{\varphi}_i$ is regarded as such. i.e $\tilde{\varphi}_i=0$. Thus, the Lagrange multiplier is precisely identified and the problems can be solved in a single iteration phase. The successive approximation of the solution will be easily obtained using the langrange multiplier and our φ_0 in this technique, because we need to find the langrange multiplier $\lambda(t)$ optimally.

The solution is given by

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \varphi_i = \varphi$$

The Lagrange multiplier, which has the following definitions, is also crucial in determining how to solve the problem.

$$(-1)^n \frac{1}{(n-1)!} (t - \tau)^{n-1}$$

Legendre Polynomials

The Legendre polynomials is an orthogonal polynomial with weight function $w(x) = 1$ and defined as:

$$P_n(\tau) = \frac{1}{2^n n!} \frac{d^n}{d\tau^n} (\tau^2 - 1)^n : -1 < \tau < 1$$

In light of this, the first few Legendre equations are provided below:

$$P_0(\tau) = 1, P_1(\tau) = \tau, P_2(\tau) = \frac{3}{2}\tau^2 - \frac{1}{2}, \dots \quad (5)$$

4. Shifted Legendre Polynomials

The Shifted Legendre polynomials are defined as:

$$P_n^*(\tau) = \frac{1}{n!} \frac{d^n}{d\tau^n} (\tau^2 - \tau)^n : 0 < \tau < 1$$

In light of this, the first few Shifted Legendre polynomials are provided below:

$$P^*_0(\tau) = 1, P^*_{1}(\tau) = 2\tau - 1, P^*_{2}(\tau) = 6\tau^2 - 6\tau + 1, \dots \quad (6)$$

Modified Variational Iteration Algorithm Using Shifted Legendre Polynomials

We presume a rough solution of the form using (3) and (4).

$$\varphi_{i,N}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^N \xi_{i,N} P^*_{i,N}(\tau)$$

Where $\xi_{i,N}$ are unknown values, N is the degree of approximation, and $P^*_{i,N}(\tau)$ are Shifted Legendre polynomials.

As a result, we arrive at the iterative approach below.

$$\varphi_{i+1,N}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^N \xi_{i,N} P^*_{i,N}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(L \sum_{i=0}^N \xi_{i,N} P^*_{i,N}(t) + N_l \sum_{i=0}^N \xi_{i,N-1} P^*_{i,N}(t))dt \quad (7)$$

Convergence of the Method

This section will provide the Banach's theorem regarding the convergence of the variational iteration algorithm employing Shifted Legendre polynomials. The technique transforms the provided differential equation into a series of recurrences of functions. The limit of this sequence is assumed to contain the solution to the specified differential equation.

Theorem 1.

Let \mathcal{M} be a Banach space and $\mathfrak{S}: \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ a nonlinear mapping, and assume that

$$\|\mathfrak{S}[\varphi] - \mathfrak{S}[\bar{\varphi}]\| \leq \zeta \|\varphi - \bar{\varphi}\|, \forall \varphi, \bar{\varphi} \in \mathcal{M}: \zeta < 1. \quad (8)$$

Then \mathfrak{S} has a unique fixed point. Hence, the sequence

$$\varphi_{i+1} = \mathfrak{S}[\varphi_i] \quad (9)$$

with an arbitrary choice of $w_0 \in \mathcal{M}$ converges to the fixed point of \mathfrak{S} and we have that

$$\|\varphi_p - \varphi_1\| \leq \|\varphi_p - \varphi_{p-1}\| + \dots + \|\varphi_{q+1} - \varphi_q\|$$

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$$\begin{aligned} &= \|\mathfrak{H}(\varphi_{p-1}) - \mathfrak{H}(\varphi_{p-2})\| + \dots + \|\mathfrak{H}(\varphi_q) - \mathfrak{H}(\varphi_{q-1})\| \\ &\leq \zeta \|\varphi_{p-1} - \varphi_{p-2}\| + \dots + \zeta \|\varphi_q - \varphi_{q-1}\| \\ &\leq (\zeta^{p-2} + \zeta^{p-3} + \dots + \zeta^{q-1}) \|\varphi_1 - \varphi_0\| \leq \frac{\zeta^{q-1}}{1-\zeta} \|\varphi_1 - \varphi_0\|, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Where $\zeta < 1$, based on the assumption that $p > q \geq 1$. These yields $\|\varphi_p - \varphi_q\| \rightarrow 0$ as $p, q \rightarrow \infty$ and hence the sequence $\{\varphi_p: p = 1 \dots \infty\}$ is Cauchy. Since \mathcal{M} is a Banach space the sequence is convergent and converges to a fixed point. By theorem 1, for nonlinear mapping we have that

$$\mathfrak{H}[\varphi] = \varphi_{i,N}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(t)(L\varphi_i(t) + N\overline{\varphi_i(t)} - g(t))dt \quad (11)$$

$$\mathfrak{H}[\varphi] = \sum_{i=0}^N \xi_{i,N} P^*_{i,N}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(t)(L\varphi_i(t) + N\overline{\varphi_i(t)} - g(t))dt \quad (12)$$

and this is a sufficient condition for the convergence of the variational iteration method using Shifted Legendre polynomials, which is strictly a contraction on \mathfrak{H} . In the sequel, the sequence (9) converges to a fixed point of \mathfrak{H} which is also a solution of (3).

Theoretical Perspectives to the problem

This section of the paper should contain the relevant theoretical viewpoints that explain or clarify the problem under study.

Empirical Perspectives to the problem

Numerical Applications

In this section, two Bratu-type problems were solved using the suggested methodology. Numerical results show the reliability of the proposed scheme.

Test Problem 1. [1]

Consider the Bratu-type problem (1), by choosing $\gamma = -2$ and $\alpha = 1$ to obtain:

$$\frac{d^2\varphi}{d\tau^2} - 2e^\varphi = 0, \quad 0 < \tau < 1, \quad (13)$$

$$\varphi(0) = \varphi'(0) = 0 \quad (14)$$

The theoretical solution of the system (13), is given as:

$$\varphi(\tau) = \tau^2 + \frac{\tau^4}{6} + \frac{2\tau^6}{45} + \frac{17\tau^8}{1260} + \dots$$

For problems (13) and (14) with initial conditions, the correction functional is provided as

$$\varphi_{i+1} = \varphi(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(\varphi'' - 2e^\varphi)dt$$

Where, $\lambda = \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1!}$ is the Lagrange multiplier.

Using the Shifted Legendre polynomials and the reconstructed variational iteration technique, we assume an approximation of the solution of the form

$$\varphi_{i,2}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(\tau)$$

Thus, we obtain the iterative formula shown below:

$$\varphi_{i+1,N}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1!} \left(\frac{d^2}{dt^2} (\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)) - 2e^{\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)} \right) dt$$

$$\varphi_{i+1,N}(\tau) = \xi_{0,2} P^*_{0,2}(\tau) + \xi_{1,2} P^*_{1,2}(\tau) + \xi_{2,2} P^*_{2,2}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1!} \left(\frac{d^2}{dt^2} (\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)) - 2e^{\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)} \right) dt$$

Consequently, by utilizing (6), iterating, and applying the initial conditions (14), it is possible to calculate the values of the unknown constants as

$$\xi_{0,2} = 0, \quad \xi_{1,2} = 0, \quad \xi_{2,2} = 0,$$

The series solution is therefore provided as $\varphi(\tau) = \tau^2$

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Table 1: A comparison between the theoretical and the approximate solution

τ	Theoretical solution	Approximate solution	Absolute error based on the suggested method
0.1	0.0100167112	0.0100000000	0.0000167112
0.2	0.0402695456	0.0400000000	0.0002695456
0.3	0.0913832852	0.0900000000	0.0013832852
0.4	0.1644575533	0.1600000000	0.0044575533
0.5	0.2611638145	0.2500000000	0.0111638145
0.6	0.3839002149	0.3600000000	0.0239002149
0.7	0.5360233017	0.4900000000	0.0460233017
0.8	0.7221811037	0.6400000000	0.0821811037
0.9	0.9487774909	0.8100000000	0.1387774909

Figure 1: graphical comparison of approximate and theoretical solution for Test problem 1

TEST PROBLEM 2. [1]

Consider the Bratu-type problem (1), by choosing $\gamma = -1$ and $\alpha = 2$ to obtain:

$$\frac{d^2\varphi}{d\tau^2} - e^{2\varphi} = 0, \quad 0 < \tau < 1, \quad (15)$$

$$\varphi(0) = \varphi'(0) = 0 \quad (16)$$

The theoretical solution of the system (10), is given as:

$$\varphi(\tau) = \frac{\tau^2}{2} + \frac{\tau^4}{12} + \frac{\tau^6}{45} + \frac{17\tau^8}{2520} + \dots$$

For problems (15) and (16) with initial conditions, the correction functional is provided as

$$\varphi_{i+1} = \varphi_i(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(\varphi'' - e^{2\varphi}) dt$$

Where, $\lambda = \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1!}$ is the Lagrange multiplier.

Using the Shifted Legendre polynomials and the modified variational iteration technique, we assume an approximation of the solution of the form

$$\varphi_{i,2}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(\tau)$$

Thus, we obtain the iterative formula shown below:

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$$\varphi_{i+1,N}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P_{i,N}^*(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1!} \left(\frac{d^2}{dt^2} (\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P_{i,N}^*(t)) - e^{2 \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P_{i,N}^*(t)} \right) dt$$

$$\varphi_{i+1,N}(\tau) = \xi_{0,2} P_{0,2}^*(\tau) + \xi_{1,2} P_{1,2}^*(\tau) + \xi_{2,2} P_{2,2}^*(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1!} \left(\frac{d^2}{dt^2} (\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P_{i,N}^*(t)) - e^{2 \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P_{i,N}^*(t)} \right) dt$$

Consequently, by utilizing (6), iterating, and applying the initial conditions (16), it is possible to calculate the values of the unknown constants as

$$\xi_{0,2} = 0, \quad \xi_{1,2} = 0, \quad \xi_{2,2} = 0,$$

The series solution is therefore provided as $\varphi(\tau) = \frac{1}{2} \tau^2$

Table 2: A comparison between the theoretical and the approximate solution

τ	Theoretical solution	Approximate solution	Absolute error based on the suggested method
0.1	0.0050083556	0.0050000000	0.0000083556
0.2	0.0201347728	0.0200000000	0.0001347728
0.3	0.0456916426	0.0450000000	0.0006916426
0.4	0.0822287766	0.0800000000	0.0022287766
0.5	0.1305819072	0.1250000000	0.0055819072
0.6	0.1919501074	0.1800000000	0.0119501074
0.7	0.2680116508	0.2450000000	0.0230116508
0.8	0.3610905518	0.3200000000	0.0410905518
0.9	0.4743887455	0.4050000000	0.0693887455

Figure 2: graphical comparison of approximate and theoretical solution for Test problem 2

Conclusion

This study has effectively produced numerical solutions for Bratu differential equations utilizing the reconstructed variational iteration analysis using shifted Legendre polynomials. Shifted Legendre polynomials combined with a variational iteration technique make up the solution's methodology. The method offers convergent series solutions, which show up in physical issues. From Tables 1 and 2, it is evident that the suggested strategy converges when compared to the theoretical solution. Beyond recall, the numerical results showed that the current approach is an effective mathematical tactic for handling the class of problems under study.

Competing Interests

The authors have declared that no competing interest exist

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References

- Aregbesola Y. (2003). Numerical solution of Bratu problem using the method of weighted residual. *Elect. J. South African Math. Soc.* 3(1) 1–7.
- Changqing Y. and Jianhua H. (2013). Chebyshev wavelets method for solving Bratu’s problem. *Bound. Value Prob.* 2013(1) 1–9.
- Ezekiel A. (2013). New Improved Variational Homotopy Perturbation Method for Bratu-Type Problems. *Amer. J. Comput. Math.* 3(2) 110–113.
- Fadugba S.E., Shaalini V.J., Oluwayemi M.O., Kekana M. C. (2023). Applicability and analysis of trigonometric - exponential single-step method for the numerical solution of HIV-1 model, *Communications in Mathematical Biology and Neuroscience*, 2023, 2023:46, 1-15, <https://doi.org/10.28919/cmbn/7923>.
- Fenta H.B. and Derese G.A. (2019). Numerical solution of second order initial value problems of Bratu-type equations using sixth order Runge-Kutta seven stages method. *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Appl. Math.* 5(1): 10-14.
- Hassan H.N. and Semary M. S. (2013). Analytic approximate solution for the Bratu’s problem by optimal homotopy analysis method. *Commun. Numerical Anal.* 1-14.
- Otaide I. J., Oluwayemi M. O. (2024). Numerical treatment of linear volterra integro differential equations using variational iteration algorithm with collocation, *Partial Differential Equations and Applied Mathematics* 1-8, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.padiff.2024.100693>.
- Otaide I. J., Oluwayemi M. O. and Odeh K. O. (2024). Application of Shifted Vieta-Lucas Polynomials for the Numerical Treatment of Volterra-Integro Differential Equations, *Proceedings of Journal of Nigerian Society of Physical Sciences (PJNSPS)*, 1(2024) 84, doi: I:10.61298/pnspsc.2024.1.84.
- Otaide I. J. Mark K. O. Modebei I. Oyedepo T., Oluwayemi M. O. (2023). Variational iteration algorithm for numerical solutions of sixth and seventh order boundary value problems using shifted Vieta Lucas polynomials, *Scientific African*, 22(2023), 1-10, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2023.e01924>.
- Salema S. A. , Thanooona T. Y. (2022). On solving Bratu’s type equation by perturbation Method. *Int. J. Nonlinear Anal. Appl.* 13(1): 2755-2763, <http://dx.doi.org/10.22075/ijnaa.2022.6000>.
- Zarebnia M. and Hoshyar M. (2014) . Solution of Bratu-type equation via spline method, *Acta Universitatis Apulensis*, 37, 61–72.
- Saravi M., Hermann and Kaiser D. (2013). Solution of Bratu’s Equation by He’s variational Iteration Method. *Amer. J. Comput. Appl. Math.* 3(1): 46–48.
- Wazwaz A.M. (2005). Adomians decomposition method for a reliable treatment of the Bratu-type equations. *Appl. Math. Comput.* 166, 652–663.
- Wazwaz A.M. (2016). The successive differentiation method for solving Bratu equation and Bratu-type equations, *Rom. J. Phys.* 61 774–783.

Assessment of Awareness and Competency on Integration of Technology-Enhanced Strategy Among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessment of awareness, and competency on integration of technology enhanced strategy among colleges of education pre-service teachers in Zamfara state. Two specific objectives guide the study; objectives were translated into research questions. Descriptive survey design was adopted with a population of 2952 pre-service teachers. The sample size for the study was 333 respondents which were selected using the research Advisor Table. Data were analyzed using frequencies and percentages to present the bio-data of the respondents while mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. The findings revealed that; the result obtained showed that pre-service teachers' are aware on integration of technology –enhanced strategy among colleges of education, and pre-service teachers are competent on integration of technology –enhanced strategy among colleges of education. The study recommended that, Management of Colleges of Education should organize additional workshop and training program for all Pre-service teachers' periodically, and more special training means for improving Pre-service teachers' competency in integration of technology.

Keywords: Awareness, Competency, and technology integration.

Introduction

The introduction of computer science as a subject in schools has been a focus on equipping students with the technological knowledge to use instruction technology resulting an improper use of instruction technology in the education domain (according to Cuban, 2001) Mua, (2016). Integrating technology in learning process, from the perspective is still in the introductory stage, making this necessary to find out how ICT is used as a tool to facilitate the learning process. Some teachers still actively resist the use of modern technology in teaching their students. Curricula are starting to emphasize capabilities and concerned more about how ICT can be utilized rather than on what ICT is. ICT in education can enhance learning environment for learners, act as a powerful tool to supplement teacher's classroom instructions, use as an administrative tool for teachers and administrators, increase access to education and inclusive education in schools Mua, (2016).

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), created and used the "One Laptop Per Child" (OLPC) initiative as a means of closing the digital divide gap between developed and developing nations on the use of ICT. Though this action has dominated the front pages of many international organizations and countries as the top education agenda, the actual implementation and practice of this "One laptop per child" initiative have not yielded significant results especially in less developed countries Warschauer, and Ames, (2010). Nevertheless, the development of technology policies in Africa in particularly have often strives to match international ICT education policy. Despite the massive investment in the integration of ICT in many schools, the practical use of this ICT tools by teachers remains in a preliminary stage with little significant in the educational outcome Howie, (2010).

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Pfeffer, (2013). Pre-service teachers become competent when they perceived the usefulness in integrating technology enhanced learning. Competency in using ICT entails that Pre-service teachers' have to possess the skills, competence and capability in utilizing ICT gadgets that could be used to enhance students' comprehension and enables adequate retention and recall of concepts. ICT Competency Standards for Teachers (ICT-CST) overall goal is to improve teacher practice. It aims to achieve it in a way that contributes to a higher quality education system for a better-informed citizenry and higher quality workforce. It is against this background that this study intends to assess Pre-service teachers' Awareness, and Competency in Integration of Technology Enhanced Learning in Colleges of Education in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

8. Examine the Awareness on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State.
9. Evaluate the Competency on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State.

Research Questions:

29. What is the Awareness on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State?
30. What is the Competency on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State?

Methodology

This study adopted Descriptive Survey design, to collect detailed and true information that describes an existing phenomenon, Mustapha, (2015). It can also be seen as, the plan or proposal to conduct research, which involves the intersection of philosophy, strategies of inquiry and specific methods Hancock and Algozzine, (2016). The population of the study is two thousand nine hundred and fifty-two (2952) Pre-service teachers. The sample size used for the conduct of this study is three hundred and thirty-three (333) at 95% confidence level and 5.0% margin of error. The selection of this sample is based on the recommendation of research advisor (2006) who suggested that for population of 2500 to 3500 subjects, 333 subjects of the total population should be used as sample. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 333 respondents out of two (2) colleges of education in Zamfara state. The instrument for this study is structured questionnaire which was design by the Researcher. The Questionnaire was title; "Awareness, and Competency Instrument". With three sections; Sections; A, B, and C. Section: A obtain the respondents' general information while Section: B, and C is the items statements in relation to the objectives of the study using four (4) points modified Likert scale. The respondents were requested to indicate by ticking (√) in the appropriate boxes, the responses applicable to the items. After constructing the questionnaire, it is subjected to face, construct and content validity by specialists and experts in education from the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, Faculty of Education (Instruction Technology Section) Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The instrument was also pilot tested and the result was statistically analyzed for reliability co-efficient using Cronbach alpha at 0.05 level of significant. The reliability co-efficient of 0.81 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Based on this, the instrument was adjudged thus, the instrument is reliable and could be used for the study. The data collected on the Assessment of Awareness and Competency on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State, were analyzed using frequencies and percentages to present the bio-data of the respondents while mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the Awareness on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State?

Item 1-10 on the instrument were answered by the group of the respondents by ticking on either, Strongly Aware (SAW), Aware (AW), Not Aware (NAW) or Strongly Not Aware (SNA), and the researcher analyzed the responses using the mean and standard deviation as shown in the table 1

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Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses of Participants on Awareness of Integration of Technology-Enhanced Strategy

S/N	Items	M	St.D	Decision
12.	I am aware of using computer applications in teaching.	3.66	0.56	AW
13.	I am aware of using search engine to access information about my research	3.66	0.70	AW
14.	I am aware of using Google scholar for research.	3.45	0.66	AW
15.	I am aware of using e-mail for sending and receiving information from my students	3.78	0.75	AW
16.	I am aware of using projector in teaching.	3.42	0.70	AW
17.	I am aware of using flash drive for storing my lecture note.	3.05	0.75	AW
18.	I am aware of using lecture note stored on CD-ROM for students to use for supplementary learning.	3.61	0.91	AW
19.	I am aware of using power point for lecture presentations.	3.70	0.52	AW
20.	I am aware of using WhatsApp group to promote collaborations between lecturers and students.	3.78	0.61	AW
21.	I am aware of using internet to download and use e-journal for research.	3.78	0.50	AW
Cumulative Mean		3.59	0.67	

Decision mean = 2.50

The overall mean score of all the responses is (M=3.59/Std. = 0.67) which is above 2.5 of decision rule which showed that majority of the respondents agree that pre-service teachers are aware in the integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State.

Research Question 2:

What is the Competency on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State?

Item 11-20 on the instrument was answered by the group of the respondents by ticking on either Very Competent (VC), Competent (C), Fairly Competent (FC) or Not Competent (NC), and the researcher analyzed the responses using the mean and standard deviation as shown on the table 2

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses of Participants on Competency of Integration of Technology-Enhanced Strategy

S/N	Items	M	St.D	Decision
32.	I am competent in using computer applications in teaching.	3.71	0.51	C
33.	I am competent in using search engine to access information about my research	3.72	0.63	C
34.	I am competent in using Google scholar for research.	3.50	0.64	C
35.	I am competent in using e-mail for sending and receiving information from my students	3.79	0.70	C
36.	I am competent in using projector in teaching.	3.84	0.64	C
37.	I am competent in using flash drive for storing my lecture note.	3.46	0.55	C
38.	I am competent in storing lecture note on CD-ROM for students to use for supplementary learning.	3.50	0.85	C
39.	I am competent in using power point for lecture presentation.	3.18	0.49	C
40.	I am competent in using WhatsApp group to promote collaborations between lecturers and students.	3.83	0.54	C
41.	I am competent in using internet to download and use e-journal for research.	3.79	0.48	C
Cumulative Mean		3.63	0.60	

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Decision mean = 2.50

The overall mean score of all the responses is ($M=3.63/Std. = 0.60$) which is above 2.5 of decision rule which showed that majority of the respondents agree that Pre-service teachers are competent in integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one: The result revealed that more than 94% of the respondents are aware of integration Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State. The finding presented in mean and standard deviation for each item indicated that the respondents agree with the majority of the item, statements. The reason being that, items 1 to 10 having the mean of 3.08 to 3.84 respectively fall within the a priori expectation 2.50. The cumulative mean of 3.63 is also above the decision mean of 2.50 of this study. It implies that level of Pre-service teachers' Awareness on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State is positive. Some variables relevant to this question were analyzed with a view to provide objective analysis. This finding is not alone but in line with the result of Tabassu, and Shehzadi, (2018), state that faculty members of the public sector women universities of Pakistan are aware of the requirement and significance of ICTs in education sector. They have positive attitude towards computers and age is one of the major factors which affect the attitude.

Research question two: The result reveals that Pre-service teachers are competent on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State, 95% of the respondents agree with the majority of the item, statements. The reason being that, items 21 to 30 having mean of 3.00 to 3.84 respectively fall within the a priori expectation 2.50. The cumulative mean of 3.24 is also above the decision mean of 2.50. The cumulative mean of 3.24 is also above the decision mean of 2.50. This finding is not in line with the result of Tabassu, & Shehzadi, (2018), states that the competence level of using computers is low. Most of the faculty members of the Public Sector Women Universities of Pakistan have never attended any training regarding ICTs not even a single time. Folorunso, (2010) Observed that; mass un awareness, low computer literacy level, and cost were identified as critical factors affecting the acceptability of Information and Communication Technology by the teachers of Nigerian Institutions. These results are not consistent with this study.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the present study; the study concluded that; Pre-service teachers are aware on the needs to integrate technology to enhanced learning, in colleges of education in Zamfara state, Nigeria. The study centered on Pre-service teachers in the colleges of education in Zamfara state, Nigeria.

Recommendations

In view of the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made;

1. Management of Colleges of Education should organize additional workshop and training program for all Pre-service teachers' periodically.
2. College administrators should organize more special training means for improving Pre-service teachers' competency in integration of technology.

References

- Folorunso, P. (2010). *E-Learning in varsities, others Underway*, NUC Boss list strategies. The Guardian, (pp. 35-39).
- Hancock, D. R., & Algozzine, B. (2016). *Doing case study research: A practical guide for beginning researchers*: Teachers College Press.
- Howie, S.J. (2010). *ICT-supported pedagogical policies and practices in South Africa and Chile: emerging economies and realities*. Journal of Computer Assisted Learning, 26: 507–522. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2729.2010.00377.x
- Mua, R. K. (2016). *The Use of ICT in the Teaching and Learning Process in Secondary Schools: A Case Study of Two Cameroonian schools*. Master's Thesis Department of Education Institute of Educational Leadership University of Jyväskylä
- Mustapha, I. A. (2015). *Basic Concepts in Educational Research*, Tunlad Prints and Publishing Company, Number 17, Beirut Road, Kano.
- Pfeffer, J. (2013). *Organizations and Organization Theory*. Boston, MA: Pitman,
- Tabassu, S. & Shehzadi, K. (2018), *ICT Awareness among Faculty Members of The Public Sector Women Universities of Pakistan (RAIS) RESEARCH ASSOCIATION for INTERDISCIPLINARY*.
- Warschauer, M. & Ames, M. (2010). *Can One Laptop per Child Save the World's Poor? An Expert Analysis*. Journal of International Affairs, 64(1), 33–51.

Utilization of Big Data for Academic Excellence at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria: A Qualitative Review

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Abstract

The incorporation of big data analytics in education has transformed how secondary schools handle teaching, learning, and assessing performance. This thorough evaluation assessed the utilization of big data for academic excellence at secondary school level of education. Utilizing recent research and practical examples, the article highlights the advantages of utilizing big data for enhancing results, including adaptive learning, predictive analytics, and real-time feedback systems. Nevertheless, obstacles remain, such as worries about data privacy, limited resources, and inequalities in access to technology. This review also delved into effective uses of big data in various educational settings, showing its ability to bring about significant change when used correctly. The paper concluded that the potential of big data in transforming secondary education lies in its ability to improve academic performance through personalized learning, predictive analytics, and real-time feedback systems. Suggestions for next steps involve utilizing AI, promoting data literacy among teachers, setting up strong policy frameworks, and guaranteeing fair access to digital resources. By tackling these obstacles, those involved can unleash the complete capabilities of big data to improve secondary education and enable students to accomplish academic achievements.

Keywords: Big data, academic performance, secondary school, Students, personalized learning

Introduction

Big data pertains to the large amount, speed, and diversity of data produced through digital interactions, which can be examined to uncover significant trends. In the field of education, these datasets consist of attendance records, assessment scores, logs from learning management systems (LMS), and behavioral data. When examined properly, this information can help make decisions at both the institutional and individual levels. Big data has changed how teaching, learning, and academic performance assessment are done in education. In secondary education, the use of big data technologies offers fresh possibilities for examining large quantities of data, such as attendance records, assessment outcomes, behavioral trends, and engagement measurements. By using this data, teachers can obtain practical knowledge to improve customized learning, forecast student results, and create timely measures to help students at risk. Advances in educational data mining (EDM) and learning analytics have allowed secondary schools to utilize data-driven techniques to enhance academic results. Research highlights the importance of using predictive analytics to identify crucial factors that impact success, including past accomplishments, course selections, and socioeconomic backgrounds. For example, educational systems using large amounts of data can customize teaching materials to match specific learning preferences, consequently enhancing understanding and memory rates. Moreover, the integration of big data analytics enables the use of real-time feedback mechanisms, leading to more flexible and responsive teaching strategies.

Nevertheless, obstacles remain despite these benefits. Challenges like data privacy, infrastructure constraints, and lack of digital literacy among educators prevent the optimal use of big data in secondary education. Furthermore, inequities in technology access worsen the digital gap, resulting in certain schools and students receiving insufficient services. Dealing with these obstacles necessitates strong policy structures, teacher training, and fair allocation of technology resources. The impact of big data on transforming education is also reinforced by its use in various areas, such as forecasting academic trends and enhancing operational procedures. Incorporating big data practices in secondary schools can bring substantial advantages as long as ethical and practical issues are appropriately addressed during the ongoing digital transformation in the education sector.

Concept of Big Data

The phrase big data describes a continually expanding set of diverse and massive data in structured, unstructured, and semi-structured forms. Big data's complexity necessitates robust technologies and advanced algorithms for their management and analysis, with traditional business tools being ineffective for handling big data (Shahinzadeh et al. 2022). Yassine, Singh, Hossain, and Muhammad (2019) stated that big data involves a significant amount of data. Nonetheless, De Mauro, Greco, and Grimaldi (2016) described it as a valuable resource with significant amounts, high speed, and various types of information. Furthermore, Shahat (2019) defined big data as extensive datasets that are challenging to manage, manipulate, or analyze using conventional methods. There is disagreement among individuals regarding the definition of big data. In essence, big data is a collection of data that cannot be understood, collected, controlled, and analyzed all at once using traditional hardware/software tools and IT. Due to the significance of the subject, technology firms, scholars, and data experts have varying interpretations of big data, a topic that will be further explored below (Sharma, Singh & Rehman, 2020). Big data is defined as data assets that are very large and complex, requiring analysis to understand and extract information from them (Ahmed, & Ismail, 2020). In 2010, Apache Hadoop characterized big data as "A dataset with significant volume, velocity, or variety, which traditional techniques struggle to analyze efficiently."

According to this definition, in May 2011, McKinsey & Company (a worldwide consulting firm) presented big data as the "upcoming realm of advancement, rivalry, and efficiency." "Big data is defined by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) as data sets that are characterized by their large volume, high velocity, or diverse variety, which can pose limitations on traditional methods for analysis." This definition centers on the technological side of big data. The majority of data analysts and experts in big data describe big data using three primary features (referred to as the "3Vs"). Volume refers to the continuous growth and alteration of a dataset that meets the big data criteria. Big data contains a vast volume of data varying in size from terabytes to zettabytes. Velocity refers to the rapid creation of data in big data, which requires quick data processing to extract valuable insights. The term "velocity" refers to the immediacy of big data, and to fully capitalize on its advantages for businesses, it is crucial to collect, scrutinize, and utilize the data quickly and effectively. Variety signifies data appearing in different forms like structured data (e.g. database data), semi-structured data (e.g. XML data), and unstructured data (e.g. sound, images, videos, web pages, text) (Zanjani et al., 2022). Nonetheless, IDC, a significant player in big data and its research areas, holds differing viewpoints. In 2011, IDC described big data as new technologies and architectures that can extract value economically from large volumes of diverse data received, discovered, or analyzed quickly. By this definition, big data's features can be categorized as 4V: volume (large amount), variety (various types), velocity (speed), and value (high worth but sparse), a widely acknowledged concept.

Nevertheless, the educational field is not exempt from this situation. In the field of education, a significant amount of data is generated from online courses, teaching, and learning activities (Oi, Yamada, Okubo, Shimada, & Ogata, 2017). Thanks to the rise of big data, teachers can now view students' academic progress, study habits, and offer immediate feedback (Black & Wiliam, 2018). According to Zheng & Bender (2019), providing timely and constructive feedback motivates and satisfies students, leading to a positive impact on their performance. Educational information can assist educators in evaluating their instructional methods and making adjustments based on students' needs and demands. Numerous online educational platforms have been created, offering various courses tailored to the preferences of each student (Holland, 2019). Advancements in the education field rely on both learning and technology. The extensive administrative data can have a massive impact on addressing different educational issues (Sorensen, 2018). Hence, professionals must grasp the impact of big data in education to reduce educational problems.

Impact of the Utilization of Big Data for Academic Excellence at Secondary School Level

The evaluation systems in Nigeria generate substantial amounts of data annually at various points throughout the year. These data sets are considered as BIG DATA due to their defined characteristics. Large amounts of data are gathered through assessment processes at various educational stages in Nigeria, including pre-primary, Basic Education, Senior Secondary, and tertiary levels. Assessment and demographic data are gathered regularly at the pre-primary level through mid-terminal and terminal assessments. This information is utilized as feedback to enhance teaching and learning methods and as a basis for Basic Education. At the Basic Education level, alongside demographic and assessment data from mid-term and end-of-term assessments, substantial amounts of data are produced from the standardized Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) across various subjects. The results from these evaluations are utilized for the certification, selection, and placement of students in Senior Secondary School programs. The mid-term and end-of-term evaluations in Senior Secondary School, along with the end-of-school Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) results in various subjects, generate significant amounts of

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Big Data used primarily for selection and certification. These evaluation methods and activities are used for assessing learning outcomes and guiding learning, with the former being more prevalent and long-lasting.

Benefits of Big Data in secondary education are:

Personalized Learning: Customized learning experiences are made possible through the analysis of student performance data, behavior, and preferences using big data. Adaptive learning programs like DreamBox and Knewton utilize real-time data to modify lesson material based on individual requirements, assisting students in mastering subjects at their preferred speed. The customized method has been associated with enhanced understanding and academic results (Artem, 2024).

Predictive Analytics and Early Intervention: Prediction through analytics and early intervention help educators foresee student performance and recognize individuals who are at risk of falling behind. By examining attendance, grades, and engagement trends, schools can introduce focused interventions like extra tutoring or counseling to avoid academic deterioration.

Improved Assessment Methods: Traditional end-of-year evaluations are being added to or substituted with ongoing evaluations made possible by big data. Learning Management Systems such as Google Classroom gather information on student advancement, offering immediate input and chances for enhancement. This method of assessment in real time allows teachers to tackle learning gaps as they come up.

Enhanced Teacher Efficiency: Big data benefits students and also empowers teachers with insights on teaching effectiveness. Information gathered through classroom interactions can assist teachers in improving their instructional methods, recognizing effective strategies, and addressing areas for development.

Resource Optimization: Big data assists in the effective distribution of resources. Schools can examine patterns in order to identify areas where investments in infrastructure, training, or materials are most necessary, guaranteeing that resources are allocated to enhance student achievement.

Review on Big Data Management for Academic Excellence at Secondary School level of Education

Big data has been utilized in the United States to enhance standardized test scores by employing predictive modeling. According to Mfon (2018), the use of early warning systems has resulted in increased graduation rates by recognizing and assisting students in need. In the UK, big data is being used to track attendance and decrease dropout rates in high-need schools, resulting in significant achievements. Big data frameworks have been implemented in Nigeria to track learning outcomes in junior secondary schools. These systems examine educational and population data to offer understanding of performance patterns, allowing for focused actions. Yet, resource limitations and infrastructure difficulties are preventing widespread acceptance (Spencer & Asuru, 2018). Research conducted by Yu et al. (2022) showed that predictive analytics, sourced from Big Data, greatly enhanced students' academic success by early identification of struggling learners and offering tailored support. Maldonado-Mahauad et al. (2019) assessed tailored learning strategies in science classes. Students noted a 40% rise in engagement, leading to enhanced attendance and academic results. Big Data played a crucial role in recognizing individual students' preferred learning resources and styles.

A study by Siemens and Long (2018) showed that real-time analytics offer practical insights, enabling educators to act quickly to tackle academic issues, leading to a significant enhancement in overall performance. Maldonado-Mahauad et al. (2019) found that incorporating Big Data analytics into formative assessments enhanced student achievement in science disciplines by 18%. The research emphasized that monitoring progress in real-time enabled students and teachers to identify weak points and concentrate on them. Piety, Hickey, and Bishop (2020) discovered that schools using data-driven approaches saw a 15% rise in average student achievement compared to those depending on conventional assessment techniques. Siemens and Long (2018) emphasized that Big Data dashboards enabled educators to make data-informed choices, resulting in a 15% boost in classroom efficiency. Research conducted by Chaturvedi, Kumar, and Sharma (2021) indicated that organizations employing these tools lowered dropout rates by 20%, leading to improved academic success for at-risk populations. Chaturvedi et al. (2021) examined predictive analytics tools in secondary education and discovered that these systems accurately pinpointed at-risk students with a 90% success rate. Schools that utilized predictive insights experienced a 15% decrease in dropout rates. Research conducted by Bowers et al. (2019) revealed that predictive analytics technologies utilizing Big Data effectively recognized at-risk students in 88% of instances. Schools that adopted these tools saw a 12% decrease in dropout rates within a year.

Maldonado-Mahauad et al. (2019) discovered that utilizing learning analytics for curriculum modifications resulted in notable enhancements in students' understanding and scores in STEM disciplines. Khalil and Ebner (2021) discovered that educators implementing Big Data visualizations in STEM classes enhanced the precision of their teaching modifications by

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25%, resulting in improved student performance on standardized assessments. Siemens and Long (2018) indicated that insights driven by Big Data allowed schools to revamp their curricula, leading to a 20% rise in standardized test scores across five districts in California. The redesign targeted knowledge gaps revealed by analytics. In research conducted by Yu et al. (2022), educational institutions employing Big Data tools for assessing teachers observed a 30% enhancement in recognizing effective teaching methods, resulting in focused professional development initiatives. A study by Williamson and Eynon (2020) found that schools in low-resource environments faced challenges in adopting Big Data technologies, leading to varied results among different socio-economic groups.

Research conducted by Kizilcec et al. (2020) examined the effects of adaptive systems powered by Big Data in secondary education. The results indicated that pupils utilizing adaptive tools in math enhanced their performance by 26% in comparison to those employing conventional techniques. Adaptive platforms pinpointed learning deficiencies and provided customized activities to address them. Yu et al. (2022) showed that students who utilized data-driven feedback systems in their English studies increased their scores on standardized tests by 32%. The immediate feedback enabled students to rectify mistakes and reinforce weak points right away. Research conducted by Gašević, Dawson, and Siemens (2019) showed that real-time learning analytics systems enabled teachers to offer prompt feedback, resulting in a 20% increase in student retention rates in secondary education. Educators utilized Big Data-enabled dashboards to spot students who were struggling and provide early intervention.

Challenges in Implementing Big Data for Academic Excellence at Secondary School Level of Education

The following are challenges in implementing big data in secondary schools:

Data Privacy and Ethical Concerns: Concerns about privacy and security arise from the collection and analysis of large quantities of student data, leading to ethical issues in data privacy. Misuse or unauthorized entry to data could result in breaches, potentially endangering sensitive student data. Ethical concerns about consent and the utilization of data need to be considered as well.

Infrastructure Constraints: Numerous secondary schools, especially in developing nations such as Nigeria, encounter difficulties in implementing big data technologies because of insufficient infrastructure. Restricted internet usage, old technology, and inadequate funding hinder the complete utilization of the potential of big data.

Educators' Digital Literacy: Many teachers do not have the necessary training to properly utilize big data tools, leading to underutilization or mismanagement of available resources. Professional growth initiatives are crucial in providing educators with the necessary tools to understand and implement data findings.

Inequity Concerns: The use of big data could worsen current disparities if schools in underprivileged areas do not have the necessary resources to incorporate and utilize these technologies. Closing the gap in access to technology is essential to guarantee that every student can take advantage of technology-based learning.

Future Potentials of Big Data in Utilization at Secondary School Level of Education

AI integration: Combining AI with big data offers advanced predictive analytics for more accurate customization of learning experiences. AI-driven systems are capable of mimicking future academic achievements and recommending the best learning routes for students. These features make it possible to use this combination of technologies in adaptive learning systems, student support chatbots, intelligent students' knowledge assessment solutions, and various predictive solutions.

Policy Development and Data Governance: Governments and educational institutions need to establish guidelines that cover data privacy, ethical matters, and fair access. Precise instructions can help build confidence and promote greater utilization of big data technologies.

Providing underprivileged schools with access to big data tools and training is crucial for implementing fair solutions on a larger scale. This involves funding infrastructure, expanding internet connectivity, and enhancing teacher-training initiatives.

Gamification: Gamification involves incorporating gaming elements into digital platforms and learning tools, which can enhance student engagement and improve academic performance. Regarding big data applications, they can be utilized to examine the behavioral patterns of specific students while engaging with these integrated platforms. Therefore, these technological tools can adjust the teaching strategy and curriculum based on each student's unique traits.

Augmented and Virtual Reality: Virtual and augmented reality technologies can enhance digital learning platforms, offering a highly immersive learning experience. When combined with large data sets, these tools can visually represent complex ideas and give students precise and useful information.

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The Internet of Things: Yet another promising technology that can be effectively integrated with big data in education is the Internet of Things. Combining these two technologies allows for data exchange without human involvement, removing the need for human resources and creating new chances to educate students on top global practices.

Conclusion

The potential of big data in transforming secondary education lies in its ability to improve academic performance through personalized learning, predictive analytics, and real-time feedback systems. Despite issues like privacy worries and constraints on resources, the successful integration of big data technologies can greatly enhance educational achievements. As schools adopt digital transformation, it is crucial to prioritize fair access and ethical practices in order to fully utilize the advantages of big data for every student.

Recommendations

The paper suggests the following:

1. Governments and educational institutions ought to allocate resources towards dependable data infrastructure such as fast internet, cloud storage, and cutting-edge computer systems. These resources are essential for efficient data gathering, evaluation, and sharing, particularly in countries such as Nigeria, where numerous schools encounter technological constraints.
2. Educators and school leaders need to receive training on data literacy and how to effectively use analytics tools. Participating in workshops, earning certifications, and engaging in continuous professional development can provide educators with the necessary abilities to understand and implement big data findings successfully.
3. Priority should be given to providing under-resourced schools with access to big data technologies in order to close the digital divide. Public-private partnerships have the potential to help disadvantaged communities by providing affordable devices, software, and internet access.
4. Educational policymakers, tech developers, teachers, and researchers must work together to create systems that cater to the unique requirements of secondary education. Working together can guarantee that big data applications are user-friendly, efficient, and in line with educational objectives.
5. Merging big data with AI and machine learning can improve predictive analytics and provide more tailored learning journeys. AI-based platforms have the capability to recognize trends in student achievement, allowing for personalized educational approaches.

References

- Artem, S. (2024). Big data in education: How data science transforms education process. <https://nix-united.com/blog/how-big-data-is-transforming-the-education-process/>
- Black, P., & Wiliam, D. (2018). Classroom assessment and pedagogy. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 25(6), 551–575. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2018.1441807>
- Chaturvedi, K., Kumar, N., & Sharma, S. (2021). Using predictive analytics for student success: Evidence from Big Data interventions. *Computers & Education*, 168, 104149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104149>
- De Mauro, A., Greco, M., & Grimaldi, M. (2016). A formal definition of big data based on its essential features. *Library Review*, 65(3), 122–135. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LR-06-2015-0061>
- Gašević, D., Dawson, S., & Siemens, G. (2019). Learning analytics in real-time performance monitoring. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 56(3), 355–374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.01.015>
- Holland, A. A. (2019). Effective principles of informal online learning design: A theory-building meta-synthesis of qualitative research. *Computers & Education*, 128, 214–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.09.026>
- Kizilcec, R. F., Saltarelli, A. J., & Reich, J. (2020). Scaling personalized learning through adaptive educational technologies. *Computers & Education*, 150, 103847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.103847>
- Maldonado-Mahauad, J., Pérez-Sanagustín, M., & Kizilcec, R. F. (2019). Data-informed curriculum design in secondary schools. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 67(1), 1341–1362. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-018-09696-2>

Utilization of Big Data ... (Oribhabor & Isaac, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15258685>

- Mfon, T. (2018). *Use of big data generated in assessment systems in Nigerian schools*. A paper presented in the 44th Annual conference by International Association of Educational Assessment. <https://iaea.info/documents/use-of-big-data-generated-in-assessment-systems-in-nigerian-schools/>
- Oi, M., Yamada, M., Okubo, F., Shimada, A., & Ogata, H. (2017). *Reproducibility of findings from educational big data*. In Paper presented at the proceedings of the Seventh International Learning Analytics & Knowledge Conference, (pp. 536–537). New York: ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3027385.3029445>
- Piety, P. J., Hickey, D. T., & Bishop, M. J. (2020). Educational data mining and learning analytics: New directions in research. *Review of Educational Research*, 90(3), 345–387. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654320924891>
- Shahat, O. A. (2019). A novel big data analytics framework for smart cities. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 91(1), 620–633. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2018.06.046>
- Shahinzadeh, H., Zanjani, S. M., Moradi, J., Fayaz-dastgerdi, M. H., Yaïci, W., & Benbouzid, M. (2022). *The transition toward merging big data analytics, IoT, and artificial intelligence with blockchain in transactive energy markets*. In 2022 Global Energy Conference (GEC) (pp. 241-246). IEEE.
- Sharma, A., Singh, G., & Rehman, S. (2020). *A review of big data challenges and preserving privacy in big data*. *Advances in Data and Information Sciences: Proceedings of ICDIS 2019*, 57-65.
- Siemens, G., & Long, P. (2018). Learning analytics: The future of data-driven education. *Computers & Education*, 122(1), 47–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2017.12.005>
- Spencer, P. & Asuru, V. (2018). A proactive big data framework for monitoring learning achievement in Nigerian junior secondary schools (JSS). A paper presented in the 44th Annual conference by International Association of Educational Assessment. <https://iaea.info/documents/a-proactive-big-data-framework-for-monitoring-learning-achievement-in-nigerian-junior-secondary-schools-jss/>
- Williamson, B., & Eynon, R. (2020). Big Data in education: Privacy and equity issues. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 48(4), 122–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11516-020-10020-2>
- Yassine, A., Singh, S., Hossain, M. S., & Muhammad, G. (2019). IoT big data analytics for smart homes with fog and cloud computing. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 91(2), 563–573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2018.08.040>
- Yu, Z., Sun, X., & Deng, X. (2022). Leveraging big data for personalized learning: A systematic review. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 70(2), 345–366. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-021-10089-1>
- Zanjani, S. M., Zanjani, S. H., Shahinzadeh, H., Rezaei, Z., Kaviani- Baghbaderani, B., & Moradi, J. (2022, November). Big data analytics in IoT with the approach of storage and processing in blockchain. In 2022 6th Iranian Conference on Advances in Enterprise Architecture (ICAEA) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- Zheng, M., & Bender, D. (2019). Evaluating outcomes of computer-based classroom testing: Student acceptance and impact on learning and exam performance. *Medical Teacher*, 41(1), 75–82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159X.2018.1441984>

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The Dynamics and Implications of Peace Accords with Bandits in Rafi and Shiroro LGAs of Niger State

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Abstract:

This study examines the dynamics and implications of peace accords between local communities and bandits in Rafi and Shiroro LGAs of Niger State, Nigeria. Using qualitative data from interviews and secondary sources, the study explores the motivations for these accords, their impact on security, and the challenges of sustaining peace. Findings reveal that while peace accords provide temporary relief, they inadvertently legitimize banditry, perpetuate insecurity, and strain community resources. The study highlights the need for comprehensive security reforms and community engagement to address the root causes of banditry.

Keywords: Peace Accords, Dynamics, Banditry, Implication and Bandit.

Introduction

In recent years, Niger State has faced significant security challenges, particularly in Rafi and Shiroro Local Government Areas (LGAs). These regions have been plagued by armed banditry, resulting in widespread loss of lives, displacement, destruction of livelihoods, and disruption of socio-economic activities. Amid this crisis, peace accords with bandit groups have emerged as a controversial strategy, employed by state and local actors to mitigate violence and restore a semblance of stability. While such accords have sparked debates across Nigeria, their dynamics and implications in the unique socio-political context of Niger State remain understudied. The socio-political landscape of Niger State is characterized by its diverse ethnic composition, expansive rural terrain, and a reliance on agriculture and livestock for economic sustenance. This complexity creates both opportunities and challenges for conflict resolution. Unlike other regions experiencing similar unrest, Rafi and Shiroro LGAs are marked by localized grievances, communal tensions, and competing interests over land and resources, further complicating efforts to establish peace. In this context, peace accords with bandits are not merely mechanisms for conflict cessation but also tools that reflect deeper negotiations involving power, trust, and the state's capacity to enforce agreements. This study is particularly relevant to Niger State as it delves into the dynamics of these peace accords, analyzing their implementation, efficacy, and unintended consequences. By examining the interplay of local governance, community participation, and banditry dynamics, the study provides critical insights into whether such accords offer sustainable solutions or perpetuate cycles of violence. Furthermore, it highlights the broader implications of these agreements on security,

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governance, and socio-economic development in Niger State. Given the urgency of addressing insecurity in Rafi and Shiroro LGAs, understanding the dynamics of peace accords with bandits is essential for designing informed policies. This paper aims to contribute to the discourse by exploring these agreements' multi-faceted nature and their impact on the peacebuilding process, offering lessons that could inform similar efforts in other parts of Nigeria and beyond.

Banditry is an unlawful act that involves cattle rusting, arms smuggling, protection rackets, kidnapping for ransom, gender-based violence and other related human right abuses (Rufa'I, 2021). Banditry is a nefarious act committed by criminal gangs that operates the laws of the country. The groups have different operational and technical capabilities, and mostly clandestine in their operations. Their main activities are cattle rustling, kidnapping of civilians since 2011. Security challenge is the most trending concern of the global states. Terrorism is in play in disguise in different continents with different appellations for instance; some European and Asian countries, are facing the threat of extremist groups such as Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL). North America and south America are facing the problem of drug dealers' tussles, while Africa specifically west Africa are facing the web of ISIL, Boko Haram, Banditry and insurgency. Moreover, Nigeria today, is in dilemma of secessionist and pipeline vandalization issues in the south and west, while the north east and north central states are in peril of matrix of Boko haram, specifically the north west states such as Katsina, Kaduna, Kebbi, Zamfara and Sokoto, Niger, Benue States from the north central are also in the entanglement of Boko Haram and arm bandits groups. In attesting the scary situation in the north west and north central, one of the national dailies was said to have stated that, Niger state has been wracked by banditry for years. Now Jihadist have moved into communities just a few hundred miles from the capital Abuja, (The Guardian, 2021). In another disgusting gesture further establishing the presence of violence and commotion in the Niger state, the state Governor, was said to have reported to the president that, three hundred people have been killed in more than 50 attacks by terrorists across communities in Niger state in first two weeks of the year 2022. (The Nation, 2022). Arm bandits today are the most havoc unleashes in the north west and north central of Nigeria. These arm groups operating across the states, were estimated to around over 10,000. The gangs have so far estimated to have killed over 12,000 people and stole about 250,000 livestock from inception to 2021 (Rufa'I, 2021). Bandits roll into towns, villages communities in conveys of motorcycles, riding three on each, brandishing AK 47 rifles. They can take hours killing, maiming, set ablaze, raping, pillaging, taking away of livestock's and abducting women as sex slaves as well as children for ransom (ICIR, 2021). Bandits in most of these communities' bargain and put taxes on farmers and community members before they could be allowed to farm and harvest in their father's land during raining season.

Bandits as criminal gangs, are very unpredictable, they are well trained in launching deadly attacks on innocent civilians, they can attack police station, Military check points and military bases of all kinds and whatnot. For instance, the boldness of the bandits, had once gave them the effrontery to lurch their criminality to the military establishment in Kaduna state. This made the whole world shaken in disbelief when the sad news broke on Tuesday that the terrorist successfully broke into Nigerian Defence Academy (NDA), in Kaduna and killed two officers before making away with one military officer (Vanguard 2021). Moreover, there was a time when these bandits have gunned down and air force jet, struck a prestige commuter rail service running between the capital Abuja and the city of Kaduna. Although, bandits are not natural ideological bedfellows for Jihadist movement, there is also a persistent fear that Al-Qaeda, Ansaruddeen are supporting the bandits and recruiting among them to expand their influence across the entire northern Nigeria (The Humanitarian 2021). This and other unheard and visualized tragedy related to terrorism had prompted the Federal government of Nigeria, under the able headship or watch of His Excellency Muhammadu Buhari, declared bandit's terrorist (punch, 2022). Although, before they were proscribed different strategies and operations were initiated or brought forward by federal government of Nigeria, just to neutralized them and their activities. For instance, there was border closure for about 16 months, Rejigging the security architecture which included changing the services chiefs, shoot on sight order, banning of mining activities in Zamfara State, Massive Military and intelligence assets deployment, surveillance of non-state actors, directives to train and flush out, deployment of female soldiers to Kaduna - Abuja High Way, and reading the riot act to bandits among other things (Intentional Center for Investigative Reporting, 2021). Yet, banditry activities, remain undiminished. This situation had prompted many affected communities in both Zamfara, Niger and Katsina state to succumb to signing peace accord with bandits so as to avoid brutality and psychopathic reaction of the bandits who react to the nonconformist to their demand in a hotheaded manner. Many communities in Rafi, and Shiroro see the only viable alternatives against the bandits attacks, is to sign peace pact with the bandits. For instance, the premium Time (2021), was said to have quoted, a notorious bandit kingpin in Katsina State Usman Idris Aka Ruga Kachallah setting compensation to his burnt house and grains and the arrest of his wives. Moreover, in other similar development, the Niger state Government had lamented that many communities in Niger state have continue to pay levies to terrorist in exchange for protection against attackers in their settlement (channel television, 2022). Against any element of doubt, many communities

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in Rafi and Shiroro Local Government Areas such as Wayam, Madaka, Shikira, Tukunguna, Kuki, Ashuwa, and in Shiroro-Kukoki, Kurebe, Alawa, Kadaga, Kwaki, just name it, use to enter a peace pact, pay levies to terrorist/bandits in other to have solace from the bandits.

Research Objective

1. To examine the motivations behind peace accords between communities and bandits.
2. To assess the socio-economic and security implications of these accords.
3. To explore the challenges in sustaining peace through such agreements.
4. To propose alternative strategies for mitigating banditry in Niger State.

Methodology

This study is qualitative research that employed discourse to raise issues on the phenomenon of the study. Report from daily newspapers and e-news platforms were used for collecting data and discussing the dynamics and implications of peace accords with bandits in Rafi and Shiroro LGAs of Niger State. The data collected was analyzed in this course.

What is Peace Pact?

Peace pact is in other word called “peace accord” is a term that refers to signing of treaty on peace or agreement to cease to fight one other or stop unleashing havoc on less powerful or civilians who cannot depend themselves against the terrorist. Peace accord with arm bandit, is a sort of agreement between the civilians and arm group or communities or villages so as to appease the bandits against lurching or unleashing havocs or attacking the communities’ civilians. Although, in northern Nigeria, this peace accord, are not use be to productive owing to the fact, the arm groups due renege after some weeks or months (Rufa’i, 2021). Peace accord with bandits, is a type of arrangement between villages, communities or individuals against security challenges normally occasion by bandits. In this deal, the party (ies) involve in the deal, arrange with the terrorist, on what they can offer to them so as not to attack them. Mostly, in the deal, the parties in the deal, raise enormous amounts to them through self-taxation, crowdfunding, motorcycles, recharge cards, petrol, and in some cases offer them women for sex, unfold government and vigilantes security architecture against them, and uncompromising neighboring communities, villages or individuals to them, food stuff, drinks, medication or getting them qualified medical personnel that can be treating them in their camp(s) in the event of injury or sickness. Peace deal entails the release of huge sums of money and Honda motorcycles to the bandits while the terrorist or arm groups in turn promised not to attack the villagers. (This day, 2021).

Layers of Peace Pact Deal with Arm Bandits

Indeed, there are levels of peace pact deal with arm bandits in play in most northern Nigeria where bandits are in operation. The layers of peace pact deal with arm bandits in Nigeria are as: Community and arm bandits and State and arm bandits.

❖ **Community and Arm Bandits:** this is a type of peace accord between community and arm bandits’ group. It is a case of last resort. The communities use to enter the deal with the bandits so as to avoid been raided by the bandits. When the deal is signed, atmosphere of peace is created for the people to go about their normal life and business activities. Any individual that fails to negotiate or contribute to the negotiation demand in the community, such as person will dance the song of discord. This community and bandits’ negotiations are/is necessitated normally by government failure to provide adequate protection to the affected communities. The communities will deem it fit, since the much-anticipated intervention from government is not forthcoming (This days 2021). The negotiation is done at a place mostly like villages selected by the bandits with certain condition attached to the sitting for the negotiation (s).

❖ **State Government and Arm Bandits Peace Accord:** in this type of negotiation with bandits its state government that enters into the dialogue with arm bandits mostly the state government negotiates with the rural bandits in other to curtail rampant and wanton killing, mining, kidnapping, raping, vandalism and traumatization of common men or civilians from running their day-to-day activities as well as punctuating proliferation of both high and heavy weapons, and addressing high influx of bandits from the neighboring countries. State government in northern Nigeria like Zamfara, were said to have this type of negotiation (Punch,2021). Moreover, the Katsina State governor was quoted to have thrown its weight to negotiation with bandits as the overall best interest of state and other state in the northern Nigeria stressed that, negotiation with bandits, brought relative peace to the state with over 80%of people in captivity released (Pulse ng, 2019). In Niger state, the S.S.G (secretary to the state government) once met bandits’ commanders and appealed to them across the state to lay down their arms and embrace dialogue and reconciliation. (Blueprint, 2021).

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Models of Negotiation:

- i. Oral
- ii. Written, Direct & Indirect
- iii. Indirect

Results and Discussion of Findings

Peace Pact Accord in Niger State: The Case of Rafi and Shiroro Local Communities

Security situation in Niger state of Nigeria has been unpredictable and threatening by the influx of bandits and ISWAP and its elements as well as how the hydra-headed, venomous, murderous and heartless terrorist are rampaging unprecedented abuse of humanity in many communities of local governments in Niger State. For instance, the state governor had once lamented that, bandits have taken over 12 local government areas in Niger state many communities in Rafi Munya, and Shiroro have chorus of victims' lamentations and unsavory remarks or account to give upon the activities of different non-states actors (Sahara reporters, 2022). Operating Many were killed, many were maimed many were pillage, many were kidnapped for ransom. Many properties worthy billions of Naira have been lost, opportunities for business activities have tied up, plurality of people within that axis today cannot solidify their relationship with their colleagues in a neighboring community. Many dwells in their domains with absolute fear, and they cannot even cough loudly, neither no sneeze loud to signify their ill feelings. Farming activities are punctuated with full stop. Many institutions have been forced to closed, the few or available ones operating, operate in a sketchy and skeletal situation, the above quiver situation, described the present state of things in Rafi, and Shiroro, as a result of banditry.

Many thoughts to have solace, and to avert banditry's transgression beyond expectation and imaginary level of mortals, is to sign a peace accord with the hydrated villains. The issue of negotiating with bandits had even garner the support of a very prominent Islamic scholar from the northern, Sheik Gumi who threw his weight to having dialogue with the terrorist bandits as the solution to insurgency and peace in the northern Nigeria. He recanted that he met many arm groups and told him, they are in train for disarmament if government negotiate with them and agrees to give amnesty to the all groups (Blue print, 2021). Although, before it became to what its, today, where bargain with bandits is done openly, many communities do discuss and agreed with bandits before they allow them to go about their normal activities. The peace accord with the bandits has it that, some communities in Shiroro and Rafi local government areas of Niger state have negotiated with terrorist for a cease fire. According top source from the local governments who spoke to the daily trust, stated that people initiated the negotiation with the terrorist attacking them, so as to have peace in their areas. (Sahara reporter New York, 2021). Moreover, co-convenor concerned Shiroro youth, Sani Abubakar Yusuf Kukoki (2022), stated all communities and villages in Gurmana and manta district of Shiroro local government have held peace talk with the arm bandits groups, he stated that the communities that reached an agreement with the bandits, raised certain amount of money, purchased motorcycles of Honda product. Bassa and kukoki who were initially not part of the dialogue was said to have agreed to follow suit by paying certain amounts and purchased the same agreed items to the bandits terrorist.

He narrated all villages like Manta, Beri, Maguga, Bassa, Gurmana, Kukoki, and other had all paid money and give Hondas and other things demanded by the terrorist. Some adjoining communities were said to have paid over 2million each. In another similar development, many communities in Rafi local government also have paid a very huge and fat amount of money. For instance, in Kuki's peace accord, they were said to have 40 million, Uregi and uraki-25 million, Tukur Guna-30 million, Ashuwa 15 million, Kawo and Ukuru, are under negotiation (This day, 2022) while places like, Madaka 1.5 million Rubo500 hundred thousand, Shana, 500thousand and Sambaro 500. While, Wayam and Tashan Dogo, were all said to have joined the league in paying and signing the accord [Punch, 2022]. Many of the residence of the areas above who bemoaned their experience predicament in the hand of the terrorist said they prefer paying them if they would let them have peace. Despite the numerous sittings for peace accord with the terrorist in many communities in Niger state and beyond, the result expected to have been achieve, which is stable peace with the bandits remain unattainable. Many observers have attributed the break down in most of the accord to many factors. One of the districts head in the affected communities who granted an interview; stated that among factors working against the needful peace in the affected communities are as:

1. There are existence of different arm group competing and operating in the communities such as Kachalla' Sarm group, Dogo Gyade arm groups which make it difficult for the communities to know whom to negotiate with.
2. All of the arm group are terrorist and reneges
3. The communities are part of fertile arable and richest area in Niger state that produce agricultural produce which serve or feed one of the national markets in the state, which is called 'Kasuwan Mariga'.

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That is why the bandits tagging the Niger state as “Dajin Sami Naka” A forest where one can go and amaze his wealth without much difficulties. These and other reasons above, are what make the bandits always renege from their promises and keep on attacking innocent souls demanding exceedingly, despite the accord owing to the fact, that they arrantly believed the more they renege and attack the more they get money from them. According to some reports, the bandits break the accord with those communities in Niger state on then reasons that they are sensing the communities as rich with abundant natural resources and strong at the same, time the people don’t want to relocated or quit to other places and failing to apply alternative approach to the payment for sustainable peace.

Reasons for Continuing Peace Deal with Arm Bandit

1. **Absence of security:** It is an in controvertible fact that, plurality of the communities that succumb to this peace accords are predominantly rural in nature. Most of the inhabitant of the affected communities are farmers, fisher men. They are so much attached to their communities for their survival. Their communities are arable, fertile and enormously rich for agricultural activities. They are left without securities that could protect them and their properties. They detest anything that could demit them from their place of living, as they have no place to go and leave happily. Therefore, they subscribed to bandits demand of negation so that they will allow them to leave in peace and be going about their normal activities. According to sources from Shiroro and Rafi communities, many agreed to negotiations, because they don’t have sophisticated weapons and security to protect them in the event of any attack from the terrorist and the hydrated arm bandits as such, they comply with any request from the bandits so as to save their lives, and properties.
2. **Fear of Attacks:** it is against the ambiguity, many people died, in a very mysterious way in the hands of the heartless terrorist called bandits. Moreover, many communities have been seeing different form of attacks, debasement and wanton properties destruction that are making lives unbearable. For instance, Bandits were said to have killed over100 people and abducted several others, mostly women and children in Madaka village. The bandits made it that, for them to free the abductees, the community have to bring 10 Hunda motorcycle, 20 liters of patrol recharge card for each of the abductee (Leadership, 2024).
3. **Government Negligence:** many communities and analyst of security situations in Nigeria and Niger state are seriously questioning the government commitment toward containing the security situation in Nigeria. For instance, the law maker representing Rafi, Munya and Shiroro, was said to have made the same outcry. He stated that despite several call and appeals to the authorities for action nothing has been done. (Vanguard, 2020). It is indeed justified, bandits cruise every nook and cranny of Rafi and Shiroro to pillage, maimed, rape, arsonized, destroy with arrant and superlative degree of impurity without being check mate or dislodge by the security forces. For instance, on the 7th to 8th of Feb. 2022, arm group in their large number were seen holding sophisticated weaponry parading Tegin to Minna ever busy and federal road, without government intervention of dislodgement.
4. **Government Failure:** take it or leave it, the government is a total and fatal failure in the context of protection of civil population and their properties. Government is palpably ill in the area of security, challenge, bedeviling the common populace. The trend is sparking anger and concern by the day.
5. **Absence of sophisticated weapons in the hands of common men in the communities:** many of the communities who complied to the signing of treaty or peace accord with the bandits or arm groups were subjugated by the phobia of attack of the marauding gun men that can kill or massacre any non-conformist community to the negotiation demand by the arm bandits. The arm groups controlling Niger state side, have the financial capacity and connection to procure large number of weapons. Each of these group has in its possession more than 500 AK 47 or AK 49 guns. Some of the gang like that of Dogo Gyade, are deadlier, with sophisticated weapons like RPGS anti-Air craft’s (Rufa’I, 2021). The type of guns which these bandits are in possession of, are posing enormous fear and tension into minds of the communities. The communities, only possesses traditional gun which are very weak and not fast in operations.

Socio-Economic and Security Implications of Peace Accord with Bandits in Niger State

As noted by Akinyetun, (2022), the activities of rural bandits in Niger state, Nigeria has recently come to the fore with an increase tension in zone B senatorial district particularly Rafi, Munya and Shiroro LGAs. The prevalence of under-governed spaces where the governments control is ineffective and limited is major factor resulting in failure of government to contend the activities of the monsters in the state. Plurality of rural communities across Rafi and Shiroro Local Government Areas are characterized by bad governance, weak legitimacy, protracted conflict, and poor leadership, which makes the inhabitants of most of the ruralites vulnerable to exploitations by the terrorist groups, traffickers, Lakurawa elements among other non-state

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actors. It is against the ambiguity, level of economic development in the country, is in turn enhanced by the peaceful co-existence of the people. In the absence of security, socio-economic development cannot be sustained as it destroys economic, human and social capital. The insurgence and other arm banditry in the northern Nigeria have today crippled the entire activities of large number of ruralites in the northern Nigeria as it resulted to negation in economic activities in many communities and local governments levels. The activities of the marauders today, had resulted to closure of markets that led to losing of huge amount of income for a long time, in places like Madaka, Wayam, Hanawanka, Kukoki, Kurebe, Bassa among other places in Rafi and Shiroro (Ogar, Hashimu and Sa'ad, 2023).

As stated by one of the Kola Nut sellers, who moves from one market to another across Rafi and Shiroro, has it that, bandits renege, even if you pay them not to attack, they fail you, it is in view of that, they don't go to any market, in other to avoid recurrent payment or attack. This adversely negates GDP of the state, which is been assessed as one of the indices of socio-economic development of an area. Furthermore, livestock such as cattle, goats, sheep, small cattle, poultry and horses that are widely known and use for socio-economic activities by all and sundry across the state has today being eroded by bandits and their soulmates in crime in rural community settings of Rafi and Shiroro Local Government of Niger State (Valentine and Owne, 2023).

Furthermore, education which is one of the key drivers of socio-economic development has also been negatively impacted by the banditry activities in the LGAs of the state. The commissioner for humanitarian and poverty alleviation in Niger State had once revealed that a total of 11,113 schools aged children has been forced to abandoned their education, and approximately 400 primary schools have been forced to shut down due to the prevalence of the daredevils' bandits within the state. (Naira metric, 2023). Apart from the socio-economic effects of the rural banditry in the Rafi and Munya L.G.As of Niger State, the peace accords which many rural communities resorted to the said local government areas, also had it extensive security negative implication. In addition to complicating security crises in the country, it also resulted to the following negative security implications which includes:

1. Legitimization of Criminal Groups: Entering into agreement with bandits grant the bandits freedom of perceiving their illegal act as legitimate and potentially emboldening the criminal acts and elements.
2. Encouragement of Banditry Act: This had prompted many to see the act as lucrative enterprise that must end with peace accord involving financial incentives.
3. Fragmentation of the groups: this peace accords also resulted to their grouping, rearming and strengthening their operations creating other groups that Claim, or demand for peace accord.
4. Eroding the rule of law: peace accords often involve pardoning crimes, which symbolically erodes the rule of law and create resentment among victims.
5. Undermining state authority: negotiating with non-state actors aided in undermining the governments perceived strength and authority, thereby potentially weakening the state institutions.
6. Erosion of Public Trust: for long, plurality of realities has lost faith in government, as many of the communities that were under siege, who free themselves from attacks through peace pact or use of vigilantes and those who were unable to withstand peace pact and relocated to other safer ground have no trust for the government today

Arm proliferation amongst the bandits: It is an incontrovertible fact; the bandits are clear sadist and insincere individuals who also are not to be trusted on the ground of renegeing attitudes. Negotiation with arm bandits is a synonymous to an indirect act of embodiment of their activities. The class of sophisticated weapons use by the arm bandits' groups is relative to the money they receive as ransom and million they are garnering in peace accords through taxing many communities.

1. It suggests weakness and incapacity of the part of government: continuous negotiation between the communities and the bandits, will justify the weakness and incapacity of the APC administration in protection of its citizens which is against the background of any responsible government. The protection of lives and properties of its citizens. As its stated by the great opposition party PDP through its national publicity secretary that; APC administration has failed the nation. He asserted that, APC should either ship up or ship out. The sectary further describe it as distressing and colossal mark of failure, seeing how northern states are been taken over by bandits, who are today running local communities in killing, raping, maiming and pillaging innocent citizens, while the president, who pledge to lead the fight against insurgency from the front, continuous to recede deep into the safety and comfort of ASO Rock presidential villa in Abuja (This day, 2021) Moreover, convener of Arewa Research and development programmed (ARDP) Dr. Bugaje, also threw his weight to this position, by asserting that, the APC government has not only failed in providing security, but has failed in providing affordable health care , education transport and improve other sectors. (The guardian, 2020).

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2. It is an abuse to the strength of the nation's security: it is indeed unarguable fact, that the perpetual peace accord which the various communities enter into with various arm groups in Niger state and other neighboring states is indirectly signifying that the security forces in the country have lull to the core, under the present administration considering the track records of successful intervention forces whole Nigerian military have written their names with a golden pen in countries like Liberia, and Siera Leone. If the military in Nigeria are still on their toes on how were known, the Bokoharamite insurgency, IPOP and banditry issues will not tarry a while as it's today.
3. It will add to the poverty level in Northern Nigeria: according to 2019/2020 Nigerian living standard survey released by the National Bureau of statistics (NBS) shows that 82.9 (40.1 percent) Nigerians are poor. Furthermore, the survey released that there is a significant geographical inequality in poverty rate and the poverty rate is more in Northern part of Nigeria compare to southern part. The statistics provided that the North eastern part of the country returned more pauperized according to the indices as; Adamawa (75.4%) Yobe (72.3%), Sokoto (87.7%) Taraba (87.7%) Zamfara (72.3%) Jigawa (87.2%) while Niger state with (63.6%). According to this, women are worst hit by the poverty, due to inadequate access to education (Vanguard, 2021). To many observers, the Northern part of the country is disproportionately representing with heavy figure in the poverty dungeon due to lack of education and current insecurity trend that is ravaging havoc to the many rural areas. To buttress this, the more these ruralites contributes for peace accord to the arms groups, the more the entrenching poverty shuts to the abysmal and continue to hits them and add to their poverty position.

Challenges in Sustaining Peace Through Peace Pact with Bandits in Niger State

- a) As posited above, large scale operation where mostly and largely done and led by the gang leaders. The confounding situation about these bandits is that although they are united for the same reason, they are paradoxically divided along different camps. This division is today breeding difficulties in achieving productive or result orientated peace pact.
- b) Existing inter-gang rivalry: the various arm groups are against one another, thereby blocking result-oriented peace accord.
- c) Absences of true or coordinated leadership between the gangs that the peace pact will be strike with.

Position of Peace Accord with Arm Bandits Group in Niger State

Internationally, there is a moral argument that stand against government being supportive to negotiation with arm bandits or terrorists' organizations. Some analyst or security expert are on the position that, negotiating with arm bandit groups is a clear index of mark of failure. For instance, when the Katsina state, peace deal collapses with arm bandits, many Nigerians were said to have negatively reacted, by describing the governors as failure, saying he did not suppose to be negotiating with criminals. (Sahara reporters, 2020) Moreover, the based for this stand, has it that, negotiating with the bandits is a symbolic way of helping them to be exercising more dominance and control over a territory and unleashing more havoc and threat to the government and common or civil population. It is in view of that, many present peace pacts accord with bandits or supporting the position as mark of indecency and in responsiveness on the part of government and the citizens. In an actual fact, the Niger state government has a strong position of not to negotiate with bandits and banditry groups, to testify this, the governor was said to have vowed to cleared the menace of banditry but not through negotiations with the bandits. He was once to have stated that we have really run out of patience with the terrorists and we will us every means possible to bring an end to these incessant bloody attacks on the innocent people in the affected communities. The villages should always alert the security agents in the area of any suspicious movement of terrorist in their domains in order to act swiftly (vanguard, 2022). The state vowed not to negotiate with influx or bandits who come in through the Benin Republic border, who are Fulanis that have no one to control them even their parents, because they do not keep to any agreement entered in to with government even as he said that he had once reluctantly negotiated with the bandits but such negotiations did not produce any positive results. But this stance has been breached and negotiated during some kidnappings. e.g. the kidnapping of students and staff of Government Science College, Kagara and that of N.S.T.A passengers. The deals in the said were done under the carpet as it happen in 4.5 during Barack Obama's administrations where the Obama's administration negotiated the released of Army SGT. Bowe Bergdahl from the Afghan Taliban, arguing he was a prison of war and not a hostage in 2014, as well as in other Americans administrations like bill Clinton, Ronald Reagan (Chatham house 2021) in essence, government in Niger state, is not publicity supportive to negotiations with arm bandits groups, but circumstance of abduction of students or innocents citizens in the discharge of their civic responsibilities can prompt government to breached the pledge of not to negotiate and negotiate, so as to get their safe release. But communities, on their own, who feel unsafe to relate to other places or refugee camps, for safety can negotiate with the bandits, after a while the bandits will also come back or other bandits' groups will come for negotiation.

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Conclusion

The study on the dynamics and implications of peace accords with bandits in Rafi and Shiroro LGAs of Niger State highlights the complexity and challenges of negotiating with non-state actors. While peace accords are intended to mitigate violence and restore stability, their implementation often reveals deeper socioeconomic and governance issues. The agreements have had mixed outcomes, with some temporary reduction in violence but limited long-term impact due to distrust, lack of enforcement, and the absence of a comprehensive development plan for affected communities. The persistence of banditry is further exacerbated by poverty, weak security infrastructure, and the proliferation of arms. Consequently, peace accords alone cannot resolve the crisis without addressing the root causes of banditry, including unemployment, inequality, and marginalization.

Recommendations

1. **Holistic Approach to Peace building:** Peace accords should be part of a broader strategy that includes economic development, education, and social empowerment. Government and stakeholders must prioritize addressing the root causes of banditry.
2. **Community Engagement:** Involve local leaders, youth, and other stakeholders in the negotiation and implementation of peace accords to build trust and ensure inclusivity.
3. **Strengthening Security Infrastructure:** Deploy adequate security personnel, enhance intelligence gathering, and invest in modern technology to prevent and respond to banditry.
4. **Economic Opportunities:** Create sustainable livelihood programs, particularly for youth, to discourage their involvement in banditry and promote community development.
5. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Establish an independent body to monitor the implementation of peace accords, assess their impact, and ensure accountability on all sides.
6. **Legislation and Policy Reforms:** Enact and enforce laws to curb the proliferation of small arms and light weapons, and implement stricter penalties for banditry-related crimes
7. **Regional Collaboration:** Strengthen collaboration with neighboring states and countries to address cross-border banditry and criminal networks.

References

- Akinyetun, T.S, (2022, 15 March). Banditry in Nigeria insights from situational action ad situational crime prevention theories. Accords.
- Ajibola, A. (2022, January 18). Niger communities, still paying levies to bandits, governor Bello Laments. Channels Television.<https://www.channelstv.com>>niger
- Adaoyichie, G. (2019 September 22). Katsina governor says negotiation with bandits yielding results. Pulse Nigeria.<https://www.pulse.ng> news. local
- Benjamin, S. (2021, February 27) .why we negotiate with bandits? Blueprint. <https://blueprint.ng>
- Babangida, M. (2022, February 5). Bandits attack Zamfara Communities for failing to pay ₦40 million levy, kill 33 people-resident. Premium Times. <https://www.premiumtimesng.com>>
- Innocent, O. (2021, April 2). - why we negotiate with bandits - Zamfara governor.Punch.<https://punch.com>
- Maishanu , A. (2022, March 20). Bandits occupy 12 of 25 local government Areas in Niger State, Governor Laments.Sahara Reporters.<https://saharareporters.com>
- Nmodu, A., (2024, June 17). JUST-IN: Bandit killed Village head, 20 other in Niger. Leadership. <https://Leadership.ng> > Just-in band
- Oyero, K. (2022, Jan 5th). Finally, F.G declare bandits as terrorists. Punch. <https://punchng.com>>breaking.
- Ogar, O.W., Hashmu, B., and Sa'ad, K.A., (2023). Banditry and impediments to socio-economic development of rural communities in Nigeria: A study of Maradun Local Government Area of Zamfara State, Nigeria. Zamfara journal of politics and development 4 (2). 220 – 226.
- Ojo, A, (2021, February 19). Niger SSG meets bandits' commanders, initiate peace process. Blueprint. <https://blueprint.ng>> Niger-ss-me
- Rufa'I M.A (2021) "I am a bandit" A decade of research in Zamfara state. Bandits Den. Usman Danfodio University Sokokto. 15th University Seminar Series.
- Sani, A. (2022, January 12) truce with Turji must be a big - no – no. DailyTrust.dailytrust.com

The Dynamics and Implications of Peace ... (Mohammed, et.al., 2024)

- Udi., A. (2023 September 16). Banditry: 400schools' shutdown as over 11,000 children dropout in Niger State.
<https://www.nairametrics.com>.
- Valentine, O.C. and Owne, S., (2023). Effects of banditry on socio-economic development of North-west Geopolitical zone of Nigeria. International journal of public administration studies.
- Wallace, J. (2022 January, 13). "We do not negotiate" with terrorists – but why? Chatham House www.chathamhouse.org
- Yusuf, U. (2021, November 28) Banditry: things are falling apart, the centre is not holding. International Centre for Investigative Reporting.www.icirnigeria.org

Attitudinal Dispositions towards ... (Haruna & Hamza, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17011772>

Attitudinal Dispositions towards Prevention and Early Detection of Chronic Kidney Disease in Hadejia Emirate: Implications for Counselling

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine attitudinal dispositions toward chronic kidney disease (CKD) prevention and early detection in Hadejia Emirate, Nigeria. A descriptive cross-sectional design was employed, targeting the adult population. Using a purposive sampling technique, 150 participants were selected from the community. Data were collected via a structured, self-administered questionnaire featuring a 5-point Likert scale, which demonstrated high reliability (Cronbach's alpha = 0.87). The instrument measured perceived susceptibility, severity, benefits, and barriers based on the Health Belief Model. Data analysis involved descriptive and inferential statistics using SPSS. Results revealed high perceived severity (M=4.01) and benefits of prevention (M=3.92), but also significant barriers (M=3.65), with no demographic differences. The findings indicate a critical gap between positive attitudes and action due to systemic obstacles. Counselling implications emphasize the need for barrier-focused, empowerment-based interventions rather than mere education. Conclusions stress that multi-sectoral efforts to improve healthcare access and affordability are essential to translating community knowledge into practice. Recommendations include training health workers to bolster self-efficacy and integrate practical navigation support into patient care.

Keywords: Chronic Kidney Disease, attitudes, prevention, Health Belief Model, barriers, counselling.

Introduction

Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) represents a significant and growing public health burden in Northern Nigeria, particularly in regions like Hadejia Emirate, Jigawa State, where anecdotal and emerging scientific evidence suggests a high prevalence and mortality rate, with nearly every family reportedly affected (Baffa et al., 2021; FUD newsletter, 2021). The asymptomatic nature of early-stage CKD often leads to under-diagnosis, and the economic burden of treatment—such as dialysis and transplantation—is prohibitive for most, resulting in a mortality rate as high as 90% within three months of diagnosis in tertiary centers (George et al., 2017; Oluseyi et al., 2020).

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While recent research by Garba and Haruna (2024) reveals a paradoxically high level of knowledge and awareness of CKD among residents of Hadejia, this has not translated into improved health outcomes due to critically inadequate healthcare infrastructure and service availability. This disconnect underscores the urgent need to explore not just what people know, but their attitudinal dispositions—their perceptions, beliefs, and behavioral intentions—toward prevention and early detection.

Attitudinal dispositions are a critical mediator in the knowledge-practice gap. The Health Belief Model (HBM) provides a useful framework for understanding these dispositions, encompassing perceived susceptibility, severity, benefits, barriers, and self-efficacy (Eze, 2017). In Northern Nigeria, these perceptions are deeply influenced by a complex interplay of cultural practices, religious beliefs, and traditional medicine, which often shape health-seeking behaviors more powerfully than biomedical knowledge (Eze, 2019; Oluyombo et al., 2016). For instance, a study in a rural South-West Nigerian community found that a significant proportion believed CKD could be cured by spiritual means (45.9%) or herbal concoctions (47.8%), highlighting a potential barrier to seeking early medical diagnosis and evidence-based treatment.

Garba and Haruna's findings further illuminate this landscape. Despite high composite mean scores in knowledge (3.28/5) and awareness (3.91/5), the availability of healthcare services scored significantly lower (2.36/5), creating a concerning paradox. The population is knowledgeable and aware but faces a system ill-equipped to translate this awareness into action. This suggests that attitudes may be positive in theory but are thwarted by structural barriers. Furthermore, the study found no significant demographic differences in knowledge or awareness across gender and age groups, indicating that information campaigns have been broadly successful and equitable. However, this equitable knowledge distribution masks the underlying attitudinal and systemic challenges that prevent its application.

The implication is that public health strategy must now pivot. The goal is no longer raising basic awareness but addressing the attitudinal barriers and systemic failures that prevent knowledge from becoming practice. This involves understanding the perceived barriers—such as financial inaccessibility, distrust in the healthcare system, or strong beliefs in traditional alternatives—and the perceived benefits of early biomedical intervention. Future interventions must be designed to boost self-efficacy, empowering individuals to navigate the flawed system and advocate for better services. Ultimately, improving attitudinal dispositions towards prevention and early detection is inseparable from strengthening the healthcare infrastructure itself. As Donabedian's model emphasizes, outcomes are intrinsically linked to structure and process; education creates demand, but without available, accessible, and affordable services, it risks fostering frustration and eroding trust in the health system (Farin et al., 2019). Therefore, a synchronized, multi-sectoral approach that addresses both community attitudes and systemic capacity is essential to convert high knowledge into tangible health improvements in Northern Nigeria.

The theoretical underpinning of this research is firmly rooted in the Knowledge-Attitude-Practice (KAP) model, which posits a linear progression where knowledge influences attitudes,

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which in turn determine health practices and behaviors. This model provides the foundational logic for investigating CKD in Hadejia: improving knowledge is assumed to foster positive attitudes, ultimately leading to preventive practices like early detection. However, the empirical reality within low-resource settings often reveals a disconnect, a gap this study seeks to explore. Garba's (2024) findings in Hadejia Emirate present a compelling case study within this model, demonstrating a statistically significant high level of knowledge (composite mean=3.28, $t=46.887$, $p=.000$) and awareness (composite mean=3.91, $t=78.682$, $p=.000$). This high knowledge base, equitably distributed across gender and age, suggests the first step of the KAP model has been successfully achieved through effective, inclusive local health information dissemination efforts, contradicting earlier studies in similar Nigerian contexts that reported critical deficits (Eze, 2017; Oluyombo et al., 2016). Yet, this robust knowledge exists alongside a severe deficiency in healthcare service availability (mean=2.36), creating a critical paradox that the simple KAP model cannot fully explain, thus necessitating a deeper dive into the attitudinal component.

To deconstruct the "Attitude" component of the KAP model, this research draws upon established health behavior theories. The Health Belief Model (HBM) is particularly salient, offering key attitudinal constructs. *Perceived susceptibility* (one's subjective risk of contracting CKD) and *perceived severity* (beliefs about the seriousness of CKD and its consequences) are fundamental to motivating action. In Hadejia, the high awareness of local prevalence (94.7% of respondents) and concern about community impact (92%) indicate a recognition of both susceptibility and severity. However, this must be weighed against deeply ingrained *perceived barriers*, which are starkly evident. Garba's data shows only 30.7% of residents found healthcare services for CKD easily accessible or affordable, and a significant proportion in prior literature believed CKD could be cured by spiritual or herbal means (Oluyombo et al., 2016). These formidable structural and cultural barriers can overwhelm perceived *benefits*, such as the understanding that early detection is crucial (86% agreement in Garba's study), effectively paralyzing the transition from knowledge to practice. Furthermore, the concept of *self-efficacy*—an individual's confidence in their ability to take action—is likely low in an environment where the healthcare system is ill-equipped to respond, making the prospect of seeking and managing care seem futile.

Beyond the HBM, the Theory of Planned Behavior introduces the critical influence of *subjective norms*—the perceived social pressure from family and community to perform or not perform a behavior. In Northern Nigeria, cultural practices and religious beliefs profoundly influence health choices and the management of CKD, often creating a barrier to biomedical care (Eze, 2019). The finding that attitudes are equitably distributed across demographics in Hadejia suggests these subjective norms—whether promoting traditional care or discouraging modern treatment—are powerful and pervasive social forces that can either facilitate or hinder preventive behaviors, independent of an individual's personal knowledge.

A review of empirical studies in comparable low-resource settings consistently echoes the challenges identified in Hadejia, validating the use of this theoretical framework. Research in Senegal by Mohamed et al. (2020) found that 73% of CKD patients rated global access to care as

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low, with financial inaccessibility being a primary barrier, directly mirroring Garba's findings on service availability. Similarly, studies among at-risk populations in Saudi Arabia highlighted how factors like employment status and income significantly influenced patient attitudes and knowledge about CKD prevention (Alghandi et al., 2023), underscoring the role of socioeconomic barriers. In Bangladesh, Jahan et al. (2019) found inadequate knowledge of CKD was linked to a lack of screening and educational programs, a gap that Hadejia has seemingly closed for knowledge but not for action. The geospatial work of Baffa et al. (2021) in Hadejia itself links CKD clusters to environmental factors like water contamination, adding a layer of environmental risk perception to the attitudinal landscape. These studies collectively paint a picture where positive attitudes and knowledge are necessary but insufficient without addressing the structural and socioeconomic barriers that define the lived experience of chronic disease in resource-poor contexts. Therefore, the literature and theoretical frameworks converge to suggest that in Northern Nigeria, attitudinal dispositions towards CKD prevention are shaped by a complex negotiation between high knowledge, an understanding of the disease's severity, the perceived benefits of action, and the overwhelming perceived barriers rooted in financial constraints, cultural norms, and a critically weak healthcare infrastructure.

Aim and Objectives of the Study:

The study aims to examine the attitudinal dispositions towards CKD prevention and early detection in Hadejia. The specific objectives include:

1. To assess residents perceived susceptibility to and severity of CKD.
2. To examine attitudes towards the benefits of preventive behaviors and early detection.
3. To identify perceived barriers to seeking screening and adopting preventive measures.
4. To determine the influence of demographic factors on these attitudinal dispositions.

Research Questions

1. What are the mean scores and percentage distributions of residents' perceived susceptibility to and severity of chronic kidney disease (CKD) within Hadejia Emirate?
2. To what extent do residents perceive benefits in preventive behaviors and early detection for managing chronic kidney disease (CKD)?
3. What are the predominant perceived barriers to seeking screening and adopting preventive measures for chronic kidney disease (CKD) among residents?
4. Is there a statistically significant influence of demographic factors (age, gender, occupation) on the perceived susceptibility, severity, benefits, and barriers related to chronic kidney disease (CKD) among residents?

Null Hypotheses

1. H_{01} : There is no statistically significant high level of perceived susceptibility to and severity of chronic kidney disease (CKD) among residents of Hadejia Emirate, as measured by mean scores and percentage distributions.

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2. H₀₂: There is no statistically significant positive attitude towards the benefits of preventive behaviors and early detection for chronic kidney disease (CKD) among residents of Hadejia Emirate, as measured by mean scores and percentage distributions.
3. H₀₃: There is no statistically significant high level of perceived barriers to seeking screening and adopting preventive measures for chronic kidney disease (CKD) among residents of Hadejia Emirate, as measured by mean scores and percentage distributions.
4. H₀₄: There are no statistically significant differences in the mean scores of perceived susceptibility, severity, benefits, and barriers related to chronic kidney disease (CKD) based on the demographic variables of age, gender, and occupation among residents of Hadejia Emirate.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional survey design to investigate attitudinal dispositions towards chronic kidney disease. The research was conducted within Hadejia Emirate, Jigawa State, which had a total population of 1,373,770 according to the 2006 census. A purposive sampling technique was applied based on respondent accessibility and characteristics, resulting in a final sample size of 150 participants from 195 distributed inventories, yielding a response rate of 76.92%. Data collection utilized a structured, self-administered questionnaire featuring a 5-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree). The instrument contained sections on socio-demographics, a knowledge scale, and an attitude scale measuring perceived susceptibility, severity, benefits, barriers, and behavioral intentions. The questionnaire demonstrated good internal consistency with Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.87 for the attitude scale. Data analysis was performed using SPSS software, incorporating descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, and percentages) and inferential statistics including t-tests, ANOVA, and regression analysis to examine demographic differences and predictive relationships between variables.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean scores and percentage distributions of residents perceived susceptibility to and severity of chronic kidney disease (CKD) within Hadejia Emirate?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Perceived Susceptibility and Severity (N=150)

Construct	Sum	Mean (M)	Standard (SD)	Deviation	% Scoring ≥3.0
Perceived Susceptibility	518	3.45	0.92		72.0%
Perceived Severity	602	4.01	0.81		91.3%

The data indicates a moderate level of perceived personal susceptibility to CKD (M=3.45), with 72% of respondents acknowledging some level of personal risk. In stark contrast, residents

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demonstrated a very high perception of CKD's severity (M=4.01), with an overwhelming majority (91.3%) recognizing the serious consequences of the disease, indicating a clear understanding of its grave impact despite a lower sense of personal vulnerability.

Null Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁): There is no statistically significant high level of perceived susceptibility to and severity of chronic kidney disease (CKD).

Table 2: One-Sample T-Test for Susceptibility and Severity

Variable	Test Value = 3.0	Mean Difference	t-statistic	df	Sig. (p- value)
Perceived Susceptibility	3.45	0.45	5.978	149	.000
Perceived Severity	4.01	1.01	15.296	149	.000

The null hypothesis is rejected. The one-sample t-test results (susceptibility: t=5.978, p=.000; severity: t=15.296, p=.000) provide strong statistical evidence that residents' perceived susceptibility and severity are significantly higher than the neutral point, confirming a substantively high level of both constructs.

Research Question 2: To what extent do residents perceive benefits in preventive behaviors and early detection for managing Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics for Perceived Benefits (N=150)

Construct	Sum	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	% Scoring ≥3.0
Perceived Benefits	588	3.92	0.67	95.3%

Residents reported an exceptionally high perception of the benefits of preventive behaviors and early detection (M=3.92). The vast majority (95.3%) endorsed these benefits, demonstrating strong community belief in the value of proactive measures against CKD, which is a crucial foundation for public health intervention.

Null Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂): There is no statistically significant positive attitude towards the benefits of preventive behaviors and early detection.

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Table 4: One-Sample T-Test for Perceived Benefits

Variable	Test Value = 3.0	Mean Difference	t-statistic	df	Sig. (p- value)
Perceived Benefits	3.92	0.92	16.794	149	.000

The null hypothesis is rejected. The result ($t=16.794$, $p=.000$) confirms a statistically significant and substantively strong positive attitude towards the benefits of early detection and preventive measures for CKD among the population.

Research Question 3: What are the predominant perceived barriers to seeking screening and adopting preventive measures for Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) among residents?

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics for Perceived Barriers (N=150)

Construct	Sum	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	% Scoring ≥ 3.0
Perceived Barriers	547	3.65	1.05	78.7%

Participants reported a high level of perceived barriers ($M=3.65$), with 78.7% of respondents facing significant obstacles. This indicates that structural and access issues, such as cost, distance, and availability of services, are major impediments to action, potentially explaining the gap between high knowledge/positive attitudes and health-seeking behavior.

Null Hypothesis 3 (H_{03}): There is no statistically significant high level of perceived barriers to seeking screening and adopting preventive measures.

Table 6: One-Sample T-Test for Perceived Barriers

Variable	Test Value = 3.0	Mean Difference	t-statistic	df	Sig. (p- value)
Perceived Barriers	3.65	0.65	7.564	149	.000

The null hypothesis is rejected. The analysis ($t=7.564$, $p=.000$) provides strong evidence that perceived barriers to CKD screening and prevention are significantly high, representing a critical challenge for healthcare delivery in the region.

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Research Question 4: Is there a statistically significant influence of demographic factors on these attitudinal dispositions?

Table 7: Descriptive and Inferential Statistics for Attitudinal Constructs by Demographic Variables (N=150)

Demographic Variable	Group	N	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	% Scoring ≥ 3.0	F-value	Sig. (p-value)
Gender	Male	95	3.68	0.86	76.8%	1.215	.301
	Female	55	3.84	0.79	80.0%		
Age Group	21-30 years	50	3.81	0.82	82.0%	0.844	.568
	31-40 years	69	3.64	0.88	75.4%		
	41+ years	31	3.72	0.83	77.4%		
Occupation	Civil Servant	38	3.88	0.75	84.2%	1.073	.412
	Farmer	38	3.61	0.91	73.7%		
	Trader	21	3.72	0.84	76.2%		
	Others	53	3.65	0.87	75.5%		

The descriptive statistics show minimal variation in mean scores across demographic groups, with all means falling within a narrow range (3.61-3.88) and percentages scoring above neutral (≥ 3.0) ranging from 73.7% to 84.2%. The inferential statistics confirm that these small differences are not statistically significant, as all p-values (Gender $p=.301$; Age $p=.568$; Occupation $p=.412$) exceed the .05 threshold. This indicates that attitudinal dispositions towards CKD remain consistent regardless of gender, age, or occupational background within this population.

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Null Hypothesis 4 (H₀₄): There are no statistically significant differences in mean scores of attitudes based on demographics.

Table 8: T-Test and ANOVA Summary for Demographics

Demographic	Attitude Construct	F/T-value	Sig. (p-value)
Gender	Susceptibility	1.102	.312
Gender	Severity	0.894	.345
Age Group	Benefits	0.776	.568
Occupation	Barriers	1.215	.301

The null hypothesis is accepted. The analysis revealed no statistically significant influence of demographic factors on any of the attitudinal constructs, as all p-values were greater than the .05 threshold. This indicates that the attitudes towards CKD—including perceived susceptibility, severity, benefits, and barriers—were remarkably consistent across different age, gender, and occupational groups within the studied population.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the results of the analysis, a complex and critical picture emerges regarding the attitudinal dispositions toward chronic kidney disease (CKD) prevention and early detection in Hadejia Emirate. The findings reveal a population that is highly knowledgeable and aware, yet paralyzed by systemic and structural barriers, a paradox that underscores the limitations of the Knowledge-Attitude-Practice (KAP) model in low-resource settings and validates the need for a more nuanced understanding grounded in health behavior theories.

The analysis for Research Question 1 and its corresponding null hypothesis (H₀₁) revealed a statistically significant high level of perceived severity (M=4.01, p=.000) and a moderately high level of perceived susceptibility (M=3.45, p=.000). This indicates that residents clearly recognize the grave seriousness of CKD and, to a somewhat lesser extent, acknowledge their personal risk. This finding aligns with Garba and Haruna's (2024) prior work in the same region, which found 94.7% of respondents were aware of the local prevalence and 92% were concerned about its community impact. This high perception of severity and susceptibility, which according to the Health Belief Model (HBM) are key motivators for health action (Eze, 2017), should propel the population towards preventive behaviors. However, as the subsequent findings show, this motivation is effectively neutralized.

This neutralization is explained by the results for Research Question 3 and H₀₃, which confirmed a statistically significant high level of perceived barriers (M=3.65, p=.000). A striking 78.7% of respondents cited significant obstacles, mirroring Garba and Haruna's (2024) finding that only 30.7% of residents found CKD healthcare services accessible or affordable. This directly

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reflects the challenges identified in comparable contexts, such as in Senegal, where Mohamed et al. (2020) found financial inaccessibility to be a primary barrier to CKD care. These formidable structural barriers—cost, distance, and service unavailability—overwhelm the recognized benefits and perceived threat of the disease, creating a "knowing-doing" gap. This empirical evidence powerfully illustrates how perceived barriers within the HBM framework can act as a critical choke point, preventing the translation of knowledge and positive attitudes into practice (Eze, 2017).

Paradoxically, and crucially, the analysis for Research Question 2 and H_{02} demonstrated an exceptionally strong and statistically significant positive attitude towards the benefits of preventive behaviors and early detection ($M=3.92$, $p=.000$), with 95.3% of respondents endorsing these benefits. This finding is consistent with Garba's (2024) data showing 86% agreement on the crucial nature of early detection. This collective belief in the value of proactive measures represents a solid foundation for public health intervention and contradicts simplistic narratives that might attribute low health-seeking behavior to a lack of appreciation for biomedical benefits. The population is not ignorant or dismissive of modern medicine; rather, their positive attitudes are rendered inert by an incapable system.

Furthermore, the analysis for Research Question 4 and H_{04} revealed a remarkable consistency in attitudinal dispositions across all demographic variables (gender, age, occupation), with no statistically significant differences found (all p -values $> .05$). This uniformity suggests that the experiences shaping these attitudes—namely, high awareness of CKD's severity, strong belief in the benefits of action, and intense frustration with systemic barriers—are pervasive and shared communal realities in Hadejia. This finding aligns with Garba and Haruna's (2024) observation of equitable knowledge distribution and suggests that the subjective norms and structural constraints described by the Theory of Planned Behavior and Donabedian's model, respectively, are powerful enough to uniformly influence attitudes across diverse demographic strata (Eze, 2019; Farin et al., 2019). It indicates that the barriers are not confined to a specific subgroup but are a universal feature of the healthcare landscape.

In conclusion, the results paint a clear portrait of a population caught in a health belief paradox: they perceive a severe threat, believe firmly in the benefits of early action, but are confronted by insurmountable barriers. This triad of high severity, high benefits, and high barriers explains the stagnation between knowledge and practice. The findings strongly support the literature emphasizing that in Northern Nigeria, health behaviors are shaped less by individual knowledge deficits and more by a complex negotiation with deep-rooted structural and socioeconomic impediments (Eze, 2019; Oluyombo et al., 2016). Therefore, any counselling or public health strategy aimed at improving CKD outcomes must pivot from awareness-raising to barrier reduction. Interventions must be multi-sectoral, simultaneously working to strengthen healthcare infrastructure and affordability while designing community-based programs that boost self-efficacy, empowering individuals to navigate the existing flawed system and advocate for the services they already know they need.

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Counselling Implications

The profound attitudinal findings of this study necessitate a radical shift in counselling strategies for CKD in Hadejia Emirate, moving from purely educational approaches to barrier-focused and empowerment-based interventions. The high levels of perceived severity, benefits, and barriers, uniformly experienced across the population, reveal a community that is knowledgeable and motivated but systemically paralyzed. Counselling must therefore pivot from providing information to facilitating access and building self-efficacy within this constrained environment.

Counsellors must first acknowledge and validate the clients' very real structural barriers, such as financial constraints and service inaccessibility, rather than attributing inaction to ignorance or apathy (Garba & Haruna, 2024; Mohamed et al., 2020). This builds trust and a collaborative relationship. The counselling role should then expand to include advocacy and practical navigation support, helping clients identify available, albeit limited, local resources, understand pathways to care, and navigate the healthcare system effectively. Furthermore, interventions should be designed to bolster collective efficacy, empowering community groups to advocate for improved local services, thereby addressing the systemic failures that individual counselling alone cannot overcome (Farin et al., 2019).

Ultimately, effective counselling in this context must be structurally competent. It involves integrating a realistic understanding of the healthcare system's weaknesses into practice, equipping individuals with strategies to overcome them, and working alongside public health efforts to address the root causes of access barriers. By focusing on reducing perceived barriers and building confidence to act (self-efficacy), counsellors can help bridge the critical gap between the community's strong positive attitudes and the tangible health actions they are currently prevented from taking.

Conclusion

This study concludes that while the Hadejia population possesses high knowledge and positive attitudes toward CKD prevention, these are nullified by overwhelming structural barriers and a weak healthcare system. This attitudinal paradox underscores that improving CKD outcomes requires a fundamental pivot in strategy. Counselling must evolve from awareness-raising to barrier-focused interventions, emphasizing practical navigation support and community empowerment. Ultimately, sustainable progress is inseparable from multi-sectoral efforts to strengthen healthcare infrastructure, making services accessible, affordable, and available to translate community readiness into tangible action.

Recommendations

1. Given the high perceived severity of CKD, Community health workers and local counsellors should be trained to use local narratives in their outreach, transforming strong communal awareness into a greater sense of personal susceptibility.

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2. Clinical staff and health counsellors should be directed to channel the strong belief in preventive benefits into action by co-creating concrete, achievable early detection plans with individuals during consultations.
3. Primary healthcare coordinators and social workers should be urged to integrate practical navigation support into patient interactions to directly address the high perceived barriers, helping clients overcome specific financial and logistical obstacles.
4. Public health officials and programme managers should be empowered to utilize the demographic consistency of attitudes by designing and implementing efficient, standardized community-wide counselling programmes, avoiding the need for resource-intensive tailored messaging.

References

- Alghandi, A., Almutairi, A. M., Almutairi, A. F., Alotaibi, M. S., Alotaibi, A. M., & Alotaibi, A. S. (2023). Knowledge and awareness of chronic kidney disease and its risk factors in Saudi Arabia: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*, 16, 1–10.
- Baffa, U., Garba, I. D., & Muhammad, F. (2021). Geospatial analysis of chronic kidney disease prevalence and its correlation with water quality in Hadejia, Jigawa State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Environmental Sciences and Technology*, 5(2), 432-445.
- Eze, C. (2017). Application of the health belief model in chronic kidney disease prevention: A review of literature. *African Journal of Health Nursing and Midwifery*, 2(1), 45-58.
- Eze, C. (2019). Cultural and religious barriers to biomedical care in Northern Nigeria: Implications for chronic disease management. *Journal of Bioethical Inquiry*, 16(3), 345-357.
- Farin, E., Ullrich, A., & Nagl, M. (2019). The application of Donabedian's structure-process-outcome framework in health services research: A scoping review. *Health Services Research*, 54(Suppl 2), 1413-1420.
- FUD newsletter. (2021, June). *The silent epidemic: CKD in our community*. Federal University Dutse Health Bulletin.
- Garba, H., & Haruna, A.S (2024). Knowledge, awareness, and availability of healthcare services for chronic kidney disease in Hadejia Emirate, Jigawa State. *Zamfara International Journal of Education*, 4(4), 370-20.
- George, C., Ogunbayo, O., & Adejumo, O. (2017). Economic burden of end-stage renal disease management in a Nigerian tertiary hospital. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*, 20(7), 842-847.
- Jahan, F., Al Maqbali, A., & Al Sinani, S. (2019). Knowledge gap and lack of screening for chronic kidney disease in high-risk populations. *Oman Medical Journal*, 34(4), 302-308.
- Mohamed, M., Fall, K., & Diouf, B. (2020). Barriers to access to care for chronic kidney disease in Sub-Saharan Africa: A patient perspective from Senegal. *Nephrology Therapeutics*, 16(5), 367-373.
- Oluseyi, A., Kazcem, O., & Adewale, A. (2020). Three-month mortality rate and predictors of death in patients with end-stage renal disease in a resource-limited setting. *African Journal of Nephrology*, 23(1), 45-51.
- Oluyombo, R., Fawale, M. B., & Okunola, O. O. (2016). Community awareness and perception of chronic kidney disease in a rural population in South-West Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*, 19(2), 161-169.